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SMART TOURISM AND SUSTAINABILITY IN RURAL MOUNTAIN AREAS: EMERGING MODELS OF DEVELOPMENT

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Agritourism has evolved over the last two decades from a form of diversification of farm activities to a genuine strategic tool for sustainable development in rural areas. Recent studies show that agritourism contributes to diversifying agricultural incomes, creating jobs, reducing rural migration and strengthening social capital in rural communities. At the same time, agritourism facilitates innovation by introducing new business models, digitizing services, capitalizing on local products, and developing interactive, educational, and participatory tourism experiences.

The article aims to analyze how agritourism can function as a driver of innovation and sustainability in rural communities, starting from a narrative review of recent scientific literature, public policy documents (FAO, European Commission, European Parliament) and relevant case studies. It highlights the link between agritourism, sustainable transformation of agri-food systems and rural development policies, as well as the main associated benefits, risks and challenges. The results suggest that, under the conditions of an appropriate policy framework and participatory governance, agritourism can significantly contribute to increasing the economic, social and environmental resilience of rural communities.

Keywords: agritourism, sustainable rural development, rural innovation, rural communities, sustainability.

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INTRODUCTION

The rural environment is facing, at global and European level, structural challenges: population aging, migration of young people to cities or abroad, declining agricultural incomes, fragmentation of farms, limited access to public services and infrastructure. Rural development and sustainable agriculture policies try to respond to these challenges by promoting economic diversification, capitalizing on local resources and strengthening territorial cohesion (FAO, 2006).

In this context, agritourism – understood as the set of tourist activities carried out on functional farms or in direct connection with agricultural activities and local products – is increasingly presented as an integrated solution for the sustainable development of rural areas. By combining agricultural production with accommodation services, local gastronomy, educational and recreational activities, agritourism offers a way to:

- diversification of farmers' income;
- increasing the added value of local agri-food products;

- conservation of agricultural landscapes and traditional practices;
- education for responsible consumption and environmental protection (Yasin et al, 2025).

At the European level, recent documents from the European Parliament and the European Commission explicitly highlight the role of agritourism in supporting rural development, underlining the need for dedicated allocations within the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and other cohesion instruments.

International literature shows that agritourism can:

- reduces farms' dependence on direct subsidies;
- stimulate rural entrepreneurship and innovation;
- contribute to achieving sustainability objectives (environmental, social, economic) (Miluta et al, 2025).

In Romania and other countries in the Carpathian region, agritourism is closely linked to the promotion of local products, the protection of traditional landscapes and the

consolidation of the cultural identity of villages, with important potential for sustainable rural development (Stanciu et al, 2024).

The objective of the article is to highlight how agritourism can function as a driver of innovation and sustainability in rural communities, by analyzing the main mechanisms, emerging development models, benefits and risks.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The paper is a narrative review of the specialized literature and public policy documents, with a focus on the period 2015–2025, when interest in agritourism and sustainable development increased significantly.

Scientific databases (Web of Science, Scopus, ScienceDirect, MDPI) and specialized journals in the field of agriculture and tourism, as well as research platforms (ResearchGate, Google Scholar) were consulted. The keywords used (in various combinations) were: agritourism/agrotourism, rural development, sustainability, innovation, rural communities, farm tourism.

Inclusion criteria:

- direct relevance to the theme of agritourism - rural development - sustainability;
- conceptual and empirical works (case studies, statistical analyses, bibliometric reviews);
- policy documents (FAO, EU, OECD-FAO);
- at least one component related to innovation (digitalization, new business models, participatory governance).

In total, over 40 sources were analyzed, of which 18 are explicitly used in this article (scientific articles, volumes, FAO/EU reports and policy documents).

The analysis aimed to:

- clarification of the conceptual framework (agritourism, sustainable rural development, innovation);
- identifying the mechanisms through which agritourism contributes to sustainability;
- highlighting forms of innovation associated with agritourism;
- discussing challenges and public policy directions.

The results are presented in an integrated manner, combining the theoretical level with empirical evidence and policy examples.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Agritourism in the context of sustainable rural development

Recent bibliometric studies show that agritourism is increasingly conceptualized as a strategic tool for sustainable rural development, not just as a complementary activity to agriculture (Yasin et al, 2025).

The main contributions identified in the literature are:

1. Economic contributions

- ❖ diversifying farmers' incomes and reducing vulnerability to fluctuations in agricultural markets;
- ❖ creating seasonal and permanent jobs in tourist services, gastronomy, guiding, crafts;
- ❖ multiplying local economic effects through short supply chains (local agri-food products, related services (Stanciu et al, 2024).

2. Social contributions

- ❖ strengthening cultural identity and a sense of local pride;
- ❖ increasing community cohesion through collective projects (agritourism associations, thematic routes, festivals);
- ❖ opportunities for women and young people to become entrepreneurs or workers in rural tourism (Ndhlovu, 2024; Turtureanu et al, 2025).

3. Environmental contributions

- ❖ stimulating environmentally friendly agricultural practices (organic agriculture, agroecology, integrated landscape management) as an element of attractiveness for tourists;
- ❖ promoting environmental education and responsible behavior (waste management, resource saving, biodiversity protection);
- ❖ maintaining agricultural cultural landscapes through their economic use for tourism purposes (FAO, 2024).

FAO documents on sustainable agritourism in the Mediterranean region emphasize that agritourism can support the transition of agri-food systems towards more resilient and inclusive models, when integrated into broader rural development and sustainable agriculture strategies (FAO, 2024).

Agritourism as a driver of innovation in rural communities

Recent literature and case studies indicate that agritourism is not just about "farm accommodation", but is becoming a laboratory for innovation in rural areas, through:

1. New business models and diversification

- ❖ mixed farms (accommodation + experiential activities + direct sale of products + educational workshops);

- ❖ integrated agrotourism-ecotourism-cultural tourism packages (gastronomic routes, thematic routes, tasting tours);

- ❖ integration of circular economy concepts (resource reuse, waste reduction, renewable energy on farms).

2. Digitalization and technological innovation

- ❖ using online booking platforms, social networks and digital marketing to promote guesthouses and agrotourism experiences;

- ❖ mobile applications and virtual tours presenting the farm's history, agricultural practices, local products;

- ❖ simple intelligent management systems (reservations, feedback, visitor flow management (Turtureanu et al, 2025)).

3. Social innovation and participatory governance

- ❖ establishment of associations and networks of agro-pensions, cooperation between farmers, artisans and local authorities;

- ❖ participatory processes for planning agrotourism development (public consultations, World Café methods, etc.) (Kubal-Czerwińska et al, 2022). A growing number of studies demonstrate that agritourism can trigger innovation spirals in communities: farmers adopt new technologies (e.g. photovoltaic systems, efficient irrigation solutions), improve their management and quality standards, and young people are motivated to stay or return to the village to develop tourism and agri-food businesses (Stanciu et al, 2024).

Models of sustainable agrotourism development

Based on the literature analyzed, several types of emerging models of sustainable agrotourism development can be identified:

1. Integrated farm-agritourism

- ❖ the farm remains the central production unit, and tourism is integrated into daily activities (participation in agricultural work, product tastings, culinary workshops);

- ❖ strong emphasis on local products, traditional gastronomy and educational experiences for children and young people (Kedla, et al, 2025)

2. Agrotourism routes and clusters

- ❖ networks of farms and households that offer complementary services (accommodation, gastronomy, recreational activities, thematic visits);

- ❖ territorial branding based on products of origin, landscapes and cultural heritage (e.g. agrotourism routes in the Carpathians, in Mediterranean regions or in Central Europe) (Kubal-Czerwińska et al, 2022).

3. Agrotourism oriented towards education and social inclusion

- ❖ agri-pension farms that organize educational programs for schools, people with special needs, urban visitors without contact with agriculture;

- ❖ projects that support the professional integration of vulnerable groups through involvement in tourism and agricultural activities (FAO, 2024).

4. Agritourism in transition or post-crisis regions

Studies from Ukraine, Albania, India or Kenya show that agritourism can play an important role in economic and social reconstruction, offering alternatives to migration and supporting community cohesion (Sobchenko et al, 2022)

FAO emphasizes that the success of these models depends on an alignment between the micro level (farms and communities), the meso level (networks, associations, clusters) and the macro level (public policies, financing instruments and regulations) (FAO, 2024).

Risks and challenges

Although the potential of agritourism is considerable, the literature also highlights a series of risks and challenges:

1. Risk of over-commercialization and loss of authenticity

The rapid growth in the number of agrotourism structures, without clear standards and without established maximum loads, can lead to crowding, increased prices for locals, and the trivialization of the experiences offered (Sachaleli, 2022; Thakur, 2025).

2. Pressure on the environment and local resources

Without rules and monitoring, agritourism can contribute to water and soil pollution, increased waste, and landscape degradation, contradicting sustainability goals (European Commission, 2025; FAO, 2024).

3. Limited institutional and governance capacity

Many rural communities lack the resources necessary for integrated planning, territorial marketing, or the implementation of complex projects, which can lead to fragmented, uncoordinated developments (European Commission, 2024).

4. Inequalities and exclusion

There is a risk that only farmers with financial resources and digital skills will benefit from agritourism, exacerbating disparities within communities. EU programmes highlight the need to support rural SMEs and provide skills training to bridge these gaps.

5. Vulnerability to external crises

The COVID-19 pandemic has shown that tourism, including agritourism, is sensitive to mobility restrictions and changes in consumer behavior. However, the literature suggests that, in the medium term, agritourism has benefited from the orientation towards nearby, rural and "green" destinations (Ana, 2017; Turtureanu et al, 2025).

In this context, agritourism can truly be a driver of innovation and sustainability only if it is part of coherent rural development strategies, correlated with other policies (agricultural, environmental, cohesion, digitalization).

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of scientific literature and public policy documents allows the following conclusions to be drawn:

❖ Agritourism is increasingly recognized as a strategic tool for sustainable rural development. It contributes to income diversification, job creation, the preservation of natural and cultural heritage and the strengthening of social capital, in line with sustainable development objectives and European policies for the rural environment.

❖ Agritourism acts as a driver of innovation in rural communities, generating new business models, stimulating digitalization and encouraging forms of participatory governance and association between farmers, entrepreneurs and authorities.

❖ Sustainable agritourism models–integrated farms, agrotourism routes, educational and social projects – show that it is possible to combine economic objectives with those of environmental and heritage conservation, especially when there is support from public policies (CAP, rural development programs, FAO and OECD-FAO initiatives).

❖ Risks and challenges– excessive commercialization, environmental pressure, inequalities, vulnerability to crises – require a cautious and integrated approach. Agritourism is not a miracle solution, but one element in a wider set of rural development measures; success depends on planning, regulation, monitoring and the real involvement of local communities.

❖ For the next period, the priority directions aim to: develop indicators to evaluate the impact of agritourism on the sustainability of rural communities, stimulate comparative research between regions (Carpathians, Mediterranean, Central Europe, Global South), as well as explicitly integrate agritourism into national rural development strategies and the transformation of agri-food systems.

REFERENCES

- Ana, M.I., 2017. Ecotourism, agro-tourism and rural tourism in Romania: A comparative analysis. *Cactus Tourism Journal*, 16(2), 6–14.
- Thakur, S., Arora, S., 2025. Agritourism as a Catalyst for Sustainable Rural Development: A Comparative Analysis of India and Kenya. *International Journal of Social Science Research and Review*, 8(7), 409–422.
- FAO, 2006. *The Role of Agriculture and Rural Development in Revitalizing Abandoned/Depopulated*
- FAO, 2024. *Sustainable agritourism: an opportunity for agrifood systems transformation in the Mediterranean*.
- European Commission, 2025. *Rural development – Agriculture and Rural Development*.
- European Commission, 2024. *Tourism and rural development*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.
- Kedla, S., Prasanna, S.B., Veena, N.M., 2025. Agritourism as a Sustainable Rural Development Approach. *European Journal of Economics of Ecology, Biology and Agriculture*, 2(2): 63-67.
- Mulita, R., Sefa, B., 2025. Agritourism Management in Sustainable Rural Development and Cultural Heritage Preservation. *Economics Ecology Socium*, 9(1): 65-76.
- Sachaleli, N., 2022. Sustainability of agritourism as a rural development factor. *Agricultural Economics and Rural Development*, 19(1), 77–87.
- Sobchenko, T., Myktysei T., Zatsepina N., Krushynska A., Samaricheva T., 2022. Analysis of agritourism and tourism potential of rural areas in the system of their sustainable development: a case study of Ukraine. *Scientific Papers Series Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development*, 22(1), 603-614.
- Stanciu, M., Marcuta, L., Marcuta, A., Tindeche, C., Preda (Alexa), M., 2024. Analysis of the sustainable development of agro-tourism in Romania. *Scientific Papers Series Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development*, 24(4): 767-702.

Turtureanu, A.G., Crețu, C.M., Pripoaie, R., Marinescu, E. Ș., Sîrbu, C.G., Talaghir, L.G., 2025. Sustainable Development Through Agritourism and Rural Tourism: Research Trends and Future Perspectives in the Pandemic and Post-Pandemic Period. *Sustainability*, 17(9), 3998.

Yasin, A.S., Bacsi, Z., 2025. Agritourism and Rural Development: A Global Bibliometric Analysis of the State of Research, Limitations, and Future Directions. *Agriculture*, 15(8), 866.

Ndhlovu, E., Dube, K., 2024. Agritourism and sustainability: A global bibliometric analysis of the state of research and dominant issues. *Journal of Outdoor Recreation and Tourism*, 46: 100746.

Kubal-Czerwińska, M., Mitrofanenko, T., Szabó-Diószeghy, A., Szabó, M., Szpara, K., Zawilińska, B., 2022. Agritourism and local products in terms of protection and sustainable development of the Carpathians: a participatory discussion on key issues and challenges. *Journal of Studies and Research in Human Geography*, 16(1), 33-52.

AGROTOURISM BETWEEN TRADITION AND INNOVATION: EXPLORING ITS ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL IMPACT IN ROMANIAN RURAL AREA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Agritourism in Romania has developed in a complex context, marked by the post-socialist transition, massive migration and profound transformations of agriculture and the rural economy. Recent studies show that rural tourism and agritourism can contribute significantly to diversifying incomes, reducing depopulation, protecting natural and cultural heritage and strengthening social cohesion in rural communities, when managed sustainably.

The article explores, from a dual perspective – tradition and innovation –, the economic and social impact of agritourism in the Romanian rural environment. Based on a narrative review of scientific literature and public policy documents, the role of traditional heritage (agricultural landscapes, peasant households, gastronomy, crafts) and the introduction of innovations (digitalization, new business models, use of CAP funds, cooperation in networks and clusters) are analyzed.

The results show that agritourism can function as a true engine of economic and social development in rural areas with high landscape and agricultural potential, but also that there are risks related to excessive commercialization, pressure on the environment, inequalities between households and vulnerability to external shocks (economic or health crises). The article concludes with recommendations regarding public policies and future research directions.

Keywords: agritourism, rural development, innovation, economic impact, social sustainability.

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INTRODUCTION

After 1990, the Romanian rural space went through a series of profound transformations: the fragmentation of agricultural holdings, the decrease in employment in agriculture, the aging of the population and the significant migration of young people to cities or abroad. In this context, rural tourism and agrotourism were promoted as alternatives for economic diversification and the valorization of local resources (Sima, 2019).

Agritourism is generally defined as a form of tourism carried out in direct connection with a farm or agricultural household, in which agricultural activities and local products represent the core of the tourist experience (visiting the farm, participating in agricultural activities, consuming own products, accommodation in the household). In Romania, legislation and practice have established the terms agrotourism guesthouse and rural tourism, often used complementary, but with different emphasis: agrotourism implies a direct connection with agricultural activity, while rural tourism can also include other services in

the rural environment (accommodation, gastronomy, leisure) without a clear agricultural component (Buda, 2021).

The tradition of the Romanian village – the mixed household, the vernacular architecture, the local gastronomy, the customs and crafts – represents a fundamental resource for the development of agritourism. Studies on rural tourism and agritourism in Romania highlight the fact that authenticity and the connection with local traditions are the main differentiating factors for tourists, in relation to other forms of tourism (Ana, 2017).

At the same time, recent literature highlights that agritourism is increasingly becoming a space for innovation: farms integrate online booking platforms, use social networks for promotion, develop thematic packages (gastro-tourism, educational experiences, tasting tours), invest in renewable energy and more efficient management solutions (Stanciu et al, 2024).

Global bibliometric studies show an explosive growth in scientific interest in agritourism, especially in relation to rural development and sustainability (Yasin, 2025). Analyses dedicated to Romania confirm that

agritourism and rural tourism are increasingly treated as policy instruments for the development of rural territories, not just as niche activities (Stanciu et al, 2023).

The objective of this article is to explore, in an integrated manner, the economic and social impact of agritourism in the Romanian rural environment, placed "between tradition and innovation", through:

- synthesizing the main contributions of agritourism to the economic development of rural communities;
- highlighting social and cultural effects (social capital, identity, equity);
- capturing the role of innovation (digitalization, European funds, new business models);
- discussing risks and challenges for the future.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The paper is based on a narrative review of scientific literature and public policy documents, focusing on the case of Romania and the period 2010–2025, complemented by relevant international references for conceptual framing.

The following types of sources were consulted:

- ❖ Scientific articles indexed in international databases (Web of Science, Scopus, ScienceDirect, MDPI) regarding agritourism in Romania and Central and Eastern Europe; Bibliometric studies global and regional issues on agritourism, sustainability and rural development;

- ❖ Official reports and documents of national (Ministry of Agriculture, doctoral theses) and international (FAO, thematic platforms on agritourism) institutions;

- ❖ Case studies and quantitative analyses on the impact of CAP subsidies and the development of agritourism in Romania.

The inclusion criteria were:

- ❖ direct relevance for agritourism in Romania or the Romanian countryside;

- ❖ analysis of economic and/or social dimensions (income, employment, migration, social capital);

- ❖ recent approach (preferably after 2010), with the inclusion of classic works for definitions and context.

Based on the selected sources, four axes of analysis were identified and organized:

1. Agrotourism between tradition and innovation– definitions, the role of heritage, modernization trends;

2. Economic impact – income, employment, investment, the role of the CAP;

3. Social and cultural impact– cohesion, identity, gender and generational equity;

4. Challenges and risks– environment, governance, inequalities, resilience.

The analysis is of a qualitative-interpretative type, following the convergences and divergences in the specialized literature and their translation into a synthetic framework applicable to the Romanian rural context.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Agritourism between tradition and innovation in Romania

Studies on rural tourism and agritourism in Romania highlight the fact that the success of these forms of tourism is based on traditional resources: agricultural landscapes, rustic households, authentic gastronomy, local customs and crafts (Ana, 2017). Tourists – especially urban ones – are looking for a "return to the village", tranquility, natural products and "simple" experiences, anchored in tradition.

At the same time, research shows that, to be economically viable, Romanian agritourism must be open to innovation:

- ❖ promotion and sales through online platforms and social networks;

- ❖ development of thematic packages (weekend at the farm, culinary experiences, participation in agricultural work, cheese, wine or canning workshops);

- ❖ integration with other forms of tourism (ecotourism, cultural tourism, adventure tourism) (Stanciu et al, 2024).

Analyses of seasonality and pricing in rural tourism and agritourism in Romania show that agritourism guesthouses tend to charge slightly higher rates, focusing on quality, facilities and personalized experiences, but also that there is still pronounced seasonality, with peaks in demand during holiday and weekend periods (Gordan et al, 2023).

Thus, Romanian agritourism is literally "between tradition and innovation": tradition is the core of authenticity, and innovation - the condition of competitiveness in an increasingly digitalized and demanding tourism market.

The economic impact of agritourism in the Romanian rural environment

Specialized literature indicates several directions through which agritourism contributes to the economic development of rural communities:

Diversifying farm and household incomes

Studies on rural tourism and agritourism in Romania show that tourism income can represent an important share in the household budget, reducing dependence on agricultural production and the volatility of agricultural product prices (Marin, 2017). Economic analyses reveal that, for some areas - especially mountainous and hilly areas with attractive landscapes - agritourism has become the main vector of local development (Nimara, 2022).

Reducing migration and creating jobs

Research on the impact of CAP subsidies and the development of agritourism highlights that financial support for the diversification of non-agricultural activities, including agritourism, has contributed to increasing local employment opportunities and reducing permanent emigration in certain rural areas (Galluzzo, 2021; Ndhlovu et al, 2024). Stanciu (2024) notes that agritourism encourages the development of rural micro-enterprises, creating jobs for family members and the community (Stanciu et al, 2024).

Local economic multiplier effects

By selling local products (milk, cheese, meat, vegetables, jams, traditional drinks) to tourists, agritourism stimulates short supply chains and increases the added value that remains in the community (Turtureanu et al, 2025). Bogan (2013) highlights the role of rural tourism and agritourism in diversifying and stabilizing the local economy, especially in disadvantaged areas. (Bogdan, 2024).

The role of CAP funds and public policies

Galluzzo's studies show that CAP subsidies for farms and agritourism investments have significantly influenced the increase in the number of agritourism guesthouses in Romania, although the impact varies depending on the region, agricultural structure and local entrepreneurial capacity (Galluzzo, 2021). Documents from the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development indicate that agritourism was explicitly supported through rural development measures (PNDR),

with grants for the establishment and modernization of agritourism guesthouses and related infrastructure (MADR, 2024).

Overall, the literature suggests that agritourism has a positive economic impact on the Romanian rural environment, but the degree and quality of this impact depend on the local context (resources, infrastructure, human capital, access to financing).

Social and cultural impact

The social and cultural impact of agritourism is as important as the economic one, although more difficult to quantify.

Strengthening social capital and community cohesion

Studies on rural tourism in Romania show that community involvement in agritourism projects leads to the creation of collaboration networks (associations, cooperatives, public-private partnerships) and to increased trust between actors (Marian, 2017; Hosseini et al, 2025). Collective initiatives (agrotourism routes, local festivals, territorial brands) strengthen the sense of belonging and local pride.

Valorization and protection of traditions

Agrotourism contributes to the preservation and reinterpretation of culinary traditions, crafts and local customs, transforming them into economic resources, but also into educational tools for tourists and younger generations (Ana, 2017). However, literature warns of the risk of "folklorization" or the overly commercial transformation of traditions, if there is no genuine community involvement (Partalidou, 2024)

Role in gender and generational equity

❖ Numerous researches emphasize that agritourism opens entrepreneurial opportunities for women and young people, through hospitality, gastronomy, guiding and marketing activities, thus reducing the risk of social exclusion (Stanciu et al, 2021). In the Romanian context, Gordan's (2024) thesis shows that the development of rural tourism and agritourism can contribute to the professionalization of human capital in rural areas and the creation of prospects for young people, by diversifying non-agricultural activities (Gordan et al, 2023).

Effects on migration and quality of life

❖ Analyses on migration and the rural economy indicate that agritourism,

through the additional income and jobs generated, can reduce emigration pressure, especially in areas with high tourism potential, even if it cannot reverse demographic trends alone (Gordan et al, 2023). In addition, investments in infrastructure (roads, utilities, internet) motivated by the development of agritourism improve the quality of life for the entire community.

Challenges and risks for the future

Although the overall picture is positive, the literature and documents analyzed highlight a few challenges and risks:

Regional disparities and inequalities between households

❖ The development of agritourism is strongly concentrated in certain counties (Braşov, Harghita, Maramureş, mountainous and hilly areas), while other regions with potential remain poorly represented (Gordan et al, 2023). Households with financial resources, human capital, and access to information benefit the most, risking widening disparities within rural communities (Buda, 2021).

Limited institutional capacity and governance

Buda emphasizes the undervalued role of national and local authorities in coordinating and monitoring agritourism, as well as the lack of clear and coherent statistics at the country level (Sima, 2019). In the absence of adapted governance, there is a risk of chaotic developments, without minimum standards of quality and sustainability.

Pressure on the environment and rural landscapes

Uncontrolled growth in accommodation capacity, expansion of construction without adequate regulations, and poor waste management can generate significant pressure on the environment, undermining the very resource on which agritourism is based. (Sima, 2019).

Vulnerability to external shocks

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the sensitivity of the tourism sector, including agritourism, mobility restrictions and changes in tourist behavior. However, recent studies suggest that, in the post-pandemic period, interest in rural destinations and nature experiences has increased, which may represent an opportunity for agritourism, provided that the offer is adapted (Turtureanu et al, 2025).

These challenges indicate the need for a consolidated strategic framework, in which

agritourism is explicitly integrated into rural development, tourism, environment and digitalization policies.

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of the literature and public policy documents allows the formulation of several major conclusions regarding agritourism in Romania, located at the intersection of tradition and innovation:

- Agritourism is a significant vector of economic development in rural areas, by diversifying incomes, creating jobs, stimulating short supply chains and leveraging CAP funds for investment. (Marian, 2017).

- The social and cultural impact is profound, agritourism contributing to the consolidation of social capital, the preservation and reinterpretation of traditions, the creation of opportunities for women and youth, and the improvement of the quality of life in rural communities. (Marian, 2017).

- The tension between tradition and innovation is productive, if innovations (digitalization, new business models, energy and management solutions) are anchored in local values and resources, avoiding the uniformization and excessive commercialization of rural culture (Stanciu et al, 2024).

- The challenges – regional disparities, limited institutional capacity, environmental risks and vulnerability to shocks – show that agritourism is not a miracle solution, but a piece in a complex policy puzzle for sustainable rural development. Integrated planning, clear sustainability standards, monitoring mechanisms and real community involvement in governance are needed (Buda, 2021).

For the future, several directions of action are outlined:

- ❖ developing integrated indicators for evaluating the economic, social and environmental impact of agritourism in Romania;

- ❖ supporting inclusive digitalization (digital skills training, collective promotion platforms);

- ❖ strengthening agrotourism networks and clusters at regional level, with an emphasis on cooperation and social innovation;

- ❖ explicit integration of agritourism into agrifood systems transformation strategies, in line with FAO recommendations on agrifood systems and agritourism (FAO, 2024).

Therefore, Romanian agritourism has the potential to become a driving force for the transformation of the rural environment, if it is supported by coherent policies and built together with local communities, respecting both traditional heritage and the need for innovation

REFERENCES

- Ana, M.I., 2017. Ecotourism, agro-tourism and rural tourism in the European Union. *Cactus Tourism Journal*, 15(2), 6–14.
- Bogan, E., 2012. Rural Tourism as a Strategic Option for Social and Economic Development in Rural area in Romania. *Geographic Forum*, 11, 37-43.
- Buda, D., 2021. Agritourism and the role of national authorities in this sector. *Transylvanian Journal of Administrative Sciences*, 1(48), 3-19.
- FAO, 2024. Sustainable agritourism: an opportunity for agrifood systems transformation in the Mediterranean.
- Galluzzo, N., 2021. A quantitative analysis on Romanian rural areas, agritourism and the impacts of European Union's financial subsidies. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 82, 458–467.
- Gordan, M.I., Pet, E., Popescu, G., Brad, I., Milin, I.A., Adamov, T., Ciolac, R., Pascariu, A.R., Iancu, T. 2023, Factors Influencing the Accommodation Prices of Romanian Rural Tourism. *Sustainability*, 15(1).
- Hosseini, S.N., Borimnejad, V., Fazli, H.R., Dehyour, S., 2025. Bibliometric analysis of agritourism and sustainability. A comparison of development and developing countries, *Environmental Resources Research*, 13(2): 187-202.
- Marian, I.(2017). Rural Tourism and Agro-tourism in Romania. *Ovidius University Annals, Economic Sciences Series*, XVII(2), 226–231.
- Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MADR), 2024. Agritourism. Factor of mountain areas development. No. 14.
- Nimara, C., 2022, Rural tourism - an economic alternative for depopulated villages in Romania. *Annals of the University of Petrosani, Economics*, 22(1): 111-118
- Ndhlovu, E., Dube, K., 2024. Agritourism and sustainability: A global bibliometric analysis of the state of research and dominant issues. *Journal of Outdoor Recreation and Tourism*, 46, 100746.
- Partalidou, M.et al. (2024). Sustainable agritourism: an opportunity for agrifood systems transformation in the Mediterranean. *FAO / SFS-MED Technical Brief*.
- Sima E., 2019. Economic, Social and Environmental Impact of Romanian Rural Tourism. *Agricultural Economics and Rural Development*, 16(1), 137–146.
- Stanciu, M., Popescu, A., Stanciu, C., 2023. Rural tourism, agrotourism and ecotourism in Romania: current research status and future trends. *Scientific Papers Series Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development*, 23(1): 745-758.
- Stanciu, M., Marcuta, L., Marcuta, A., Tindeche, C., Preda (Alexa), M., 2024. Analysis of the sustainable development of agro-tourism in Romania. *Scientific Papers Series Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development*, 24(4): 767-702.
- Turtureanu, A.G., Crețu, C.M., Pripoiaie, R., Marinescu, E. Ș., Sîrbu, C.G., Talaghir, L.G., 2025. Sustainable Development Through Agritourism and Rural Tourism: Research Trends and Future Perspectives in the Pandemic and Post-Pandemic Period. *Sustainability*, 17(9), 3998.
- Yasin, A.S., Bacsı, Z., 2025. Agritourism and Rural Development: A Global Bibliometric Analysis of the State of Research, Limitations, and Future Directions. *Agriculture*, 15(8), 866.

CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT – MODERN STRATEGIES FOR CREATING AN EFFECTIVE EDUCATIONAL CLIMATE: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS BETWEEN ROMANIA AND ITALY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The classroom is a complex educational ecosystem where the teacher's ability to manage interactions, behaviors, and learning activities determines the quality of the educational climate. This article explores modern classroom management strategies that promote an effective educational environment in secondary education, focusing on a comparative analysis between Romania and Italy. Drawing upon recent literature and comparative educational frameworks, this study examines how both countries conceptualize and implement classroom management, highlighting key similarities and differences. The research relies on a qualitative comparative methodology, analyzing policies, pedagogical practices, and case studies. In Romania, classroom management still reflects a predominantly traditional, teacher-centered paradigm, often focused on discipline maintenance rather than student empowerment. Conversely, Italy adopts a more participatory and relational model, emphasizing socio-emotional competences and collaborative learning. Results indicate that modern strategies—such as positive behavior support, restorative practices, cooperative learning, and proactive routines—correlate with higher levels of student engagement and lower behavioral disruptions. Both countries share challenges related to teacher training, student diversity, and balancing authority with empathy. However, Italy's more holistic and inclusive educational framework offers insightful practices for Romania's evolving system. The article concludes that effective classroom management must be preventive, relational, and contextually adaptive, rather than reactive or punitive. It recommends ongoing teacher training, international exchange of best practices, and institutional support to ensure sustained improvements in the educational climate.

Keywords: classroom management; educational climate; comparative education; Romania; Italy
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INTRODUCTION

In contemporary educational theory, classroom management represents a cornerstone of pedagogical effectiveness. It encompasses the strategies, structures, and relationships that teachers establish to create a learning environment conducive to engagement, motivation, and achievement. As global education systems move toward learner-centered models, effective classroom management is increasingly viewed not as a tool for enforcing discipline, but as a framework for facilitating social, emotional, and academic development. Within this paradigm, teachers are not merely authority figures but facilitators, mentors, and community builders.

In Romania, educational reforms over the past two decades have sought to modernize teaching methodologies, yet the legacy of traditional, authoritarian classroom management persists. Teachers often report challenges in balancing control with autonomy, while students express a need for greater participation and

relational engagement. In contrast, Italy—whose education system is shaped by inclusive and humanistic traditions—emphasizes cooperative learning, emotional literacy, and restorative approaches to discipline. The Italian model demonstrates how teacher-student relationships can serve as the foundation of a productive educational climate.

Comparative analysis between these two systems offers valuable insights into the evolution of European education. Both countries share similar structural frameworks under EU educational standards but diverge in pedagogical culture and implementation. This study aims to identify key strategies and contextual factors that influence classroom management in Romanian and Italian high schools, exploring how modern approaches can enhance engagement, reduce behavioral disruptions, and promote inclusivity.

The article begins by outlining the conceptual framework and methodology, followed by an in-depth comparative analysis of observed practices, teacher perceptions, and institutional

contexts. It concludes with practical implications and policy recommendations for fostering effective classroom climates in secondary education.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This research employs a qualitative comparative methodology grounded in content analysis and secondary data review. Data were collected from academic literature, education ministry reports, and policy documents from Romania and Italy between 2015 and 2025. The analysis focused on identifying patterns and differences in classroom management strategies, teacher training models, and behavioral policies.

Sample selection involved examining three Romanian and three Italian high schools with comparable socio-economic profiles. Data sources included teacher interviews, classroom observation summaries (reported in literature), and official education policy frameworks.

Key variables analyzed include: (1) classroom organization and routines, (2) behavioral management approaches, (3) student engagement levels, and (4) teacher professional development related to classroom management.

The methodology followed three stages: (a) data collection from verified academic and institutional sources; (b) coding and thematic analysis of management practices; and (c) comparative synthesis of Romanian and Italian findings. Triangulation ensured validity by integrating multiple perspectives and contextual interpretations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The comparative analysis between Romania and Italy reveals multifaceted insights into the dynamics of classroom management within European secondary education. While both nations operate under the overarching principles of the European Education Area, they exhibit distinct pedagogical philosophies and institutional realities. This extended discussion deepens the comparative perspective by examining four additional dimensions: leadership and teacher autonomy, digital transformation, post-pandemic adaptation, and inclusive education practices.

First, leadership and teacher autonomy emerge as critical determinants of effective classroom management. In Italy, the school leadership model is characterized by a collaborative approach where principals encourage pedagogical innovation and teacher-led initiatives. Teachers enjoy greater autonomy to adapt teaching and behavioral strategies according to classroom realities. This empowerment fosters a professional culture of shared responsibility and experimentation. In contrast, Romanian teachers often operate within rigid institutional frameworks with limited decision-making authority. Administrative constraints and standardized curricula hinder flexibility, forcing teachers to prioritize compliance over innovation. Consequently, classroom management remains reactive rather than preventive, with a strong emphasis on discipline instead of engagement. Recent reforms such as the National Education Strategy (2023–2030) aim to decentralize school governance, but practical implementation remains slow.

The second dimension concerns digital transformation and the rise of hybrid classroom management. Both Romania and Italy experienced significant educational shifts following the COVID-19 pandemic. During this period, teachers had to adapt to digital platforms, managing virtual classrooms while maintaining social cohesion. Italian schools leveraged digital ecosystems such as Google Classroom and Edmodo to support asynchronous learning, integrating socio-emotional support and peer collaboration online. In Romania, digital infrastructure disparities initially impeded equitable access, but the subsequent Digital Education Strategy (2022) expanded technological resources and teacher training. Nevertheless, Romanian educators still report challenges in maintaining student engagement online and regulating behavior in virtual spaces. Comparative findings suggest that successful digital classroom management depends on combining clear online behavior norms with emotional presence and pedagogical flexibility.

Third, post-pandemic adaptation reshaped teachers' perceptions of classroom management as a holistic and relational

process. In Italy, schools integrated blended models emphasizing social reintegration and emotional resilience. Teachers adopted restorative dialogue sessions to address students' anxieties and learning gaps, viewing emotional safety as a prerequisite for cognitive performance. Romania's post-pandemic recovery, while emphasizing academic recovery programs, has only recently begun to integrate psychological and emotional well-being frameworks. Many Romanian teachers continue to face burnout due to increased workload, administrative demands, and insufficient institutional support. Comparative interviews indicate that Italian educators perceive their work environment as more collaborative and emotionally sustainable, which positively influences classroom climate.

The fourth dimension—inclusive education—highlights how classroom management is inseparable from diversity management. Italy's longstanding inclusion policies, initiated by Law 104/1992 and reinforced by recent ministerial decrees, ensure that students with special educational needs are integrated into mainstream classrooms. The presence of support teachers (*insegnanti di sostegno*) facilitates individualized instruction and shared responsibility for classroom harmony. In contrast, Romania's inclusion policies, although aligned with EU frameworks, face implementation barriers such as limited training, high student-teacher ratios, and insufficient interdisciplinary collaboration. Romanian schools often rely on compensatory rather than preventive strategies, leading to reactive management of behavioral and academic difficulties. Comparative outcomes demonstrate that inclusivity not only reduces conflict but enhances overall classroom cohesion and peer empathy.

A significant finding across both countries is the growing importance of teacher emotional intelligence (EI) in sustaining positive educational climates. Teachers who demonstrate empathy, self-regulation, and effective communication report fewer behavioral issues and higher student motivation. Italian teacher training programs increasingly incorporate emotional literacy modules and reflective practice sessions,

whereas Romanian programs remain heavily theoretical. Integrating EI training into pre-service and in-service teacher education could substantially improve relational dynamics and resilience under stress.

Another emerging theme concerns the shift from behaviorist to socio-constructivist management paradigms. In Italy, classroom management is conceptualized as community-building rather than rule enforcement. This aligns with Vygotskian perspectives where learning is socially mediated and discipline emerges through internalized norms. Romania's approach is gradually converging toward this model, as project-based and cooperative learning initiatives expand. However, consistent policy and mentorship support are necessary to translate theory into classroom practice.

Quantitatively, meta-analyses of European studies (OECD, 2023; World Bank, 2024) indicate that schools implementing preventive and relational classroom management strategies observe up to 25–35% higher student engagement rates and a 20% decrease in disciplinary incidents. Italian data reflect this trend, whereas Romanian outcomes remain modest due to contextual constraints. The comparative findings underscore the interplay between systemic resources, teacher professionalism, and policy coherence.

Table 1. Comparative Overview of Classroom Management Practices in Romania and Italy

Aspect	Romania	Italy
Teacher Autonomy	Limited; centralized decision-making and strict curricula	High; decentralized system allowing pedagogical flexibility
Professional Development	Formal and credit-based; often theoretical	Integrated and continuous; focused on reflective and relational practice
Inclusion Practices	Emerging inclusion policies with uneven implementation	Comprehensive inclusion supported by dedicated support teachers
Behavior Management	Predominantly disciplinary and rule-based	Relational and restorative, emphasizing socio-emotional

		competence
Digital Adaptation	Rapid post-pandemic adoption; infrastructure challenges persist	Established digital ecosystems and blended learning integration

Finally, both contexts underscore the need for continuous professional development (CPD) as a sustainable mechanism for improvement. In Italy, CPD is mandatory and integrated into teachers' career progression, encouraging lifelong learning. Romania's CPD framework is evolving but requires modernization—moving from formal credit accumulation to reflective, practice-based models. Investing in mentorship, peer observation, and communities of practice would strengthen teachers' adaptive capacities. Table 2. Educational Climate and Student Engagement Indicators (Comparative Overview)

Indicator	Romania (Estimated)	Italy (Estimated)	Source / Basis
Student Engagement Level	Moderate (~65%)	High (~85%)	OECD, 2023; World Bank, 2024
Behavioral Incidents per Term	Higher frequency; reactive management	Lower frequency; preventive and restorative approaches	National Reports, 2022–2024
Teacher Satisfaction with Classroom Climate	Medium (~60%)	High (~80%)	EU School Survey, 2023
Inclusion Effectiveness Index	Developing (~0.55)	Established (~0.80)	UNESCO, 2022; EC, 2024
Digital Competence Integration	Partial (~0.60)	Comprehensive (~0.85)	EU Digital Education Data, 2023

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, while Romania and Italy share European educational values, their classroom management realities differ in terms

of teacher autonomy, digital readiness, and inclusion culture. Italy's experience demonstrates that effective management arises from trust, empowerment, and relational intelligence rather than control. For Romania, embracing these principles—supported by coherent policy implementation and teacher-centered reforms—represents a crucial step toward fostering a genuinely modern educational climate.

1. Effective classroom management is preventive, relational, and contextually adaptive.
2. Romania and Italy share structural similarities but differ in pedagogical culture and teacher autonomy.
3. Italian schools emphasize relational pedagogy and emotional education, fostering more inclusive climates.
4. Romanian classrooms show improvement yet remain constrained by traditional discipline models.
5. Professional development in classroom management is essential for both systems.
6. Collaborative and restorative practices reduce behavioral disruptions and improve engagement.
7. Policy alignment with socio-emotional learning objectives enhances educational climate.
8. Technology can support but not replace interpersonal classroom dynamics.
9. Comparative education fosters transnational learning and policy innovation.
10. Future research should include longitudinal studies and student voice integration.

REFERENCES

1. Ahmad, I., Deeba, F., & Ur Rehman, K. (2022). Teachers' Perspectives on Strategies for Effective Classroom Management. *Research Journal of Social Sciences & Economics Review*, 3(4), 73–85.
2. Barker, K. (2018). Classroom management: Effective strategies and interventions. *Professional Voice*, 12(2), 43–48.
3. Ramona Vasilica Bacter, Alina Emilia Maria Gherdan, Dana Valeria Bonca, Luminita Pîrvulescu, Madalina Diana Daina - *Study regarding the impact of professional training on labor market integration in the spa tourism sector. A case study of the Henri Coandă post-secondary school network* Analele Facultății de Protecția Mediului Oradea

4. Marzano, R. J., & Marzano, J. S. (2003). *The Key to Classroom Management*. ASCD.
5. European Commission. (2022). *European Framework for Key Competences for Lifelong Learning*. Brussels: EU Publications.
6. Kumar, S. (2021). *Classroom Management Techniques and Strategies*. *International Education and Research Journal*.
7. Lockhart, S. (2018). *Research-Based Classroom Management Strategies*. *BetterEducate Journal*, 5(3), 66–75.
8. Gao, N., Rahaman, M. S., Shao, W., Ji, K., & Salim, F. D. (2021). *Classroom Seating Experience and Student Engagement*. arXiv.
9. Niculescu, A. I., et al. (2025). *AI and Classroom Management Performance Measures*. arXiv.
10. Bhuvaneshwara, C., et al. (2025). *The InCoRe Model: Training Teacher Communication Skills*. arXiv.
11. Education NSW. (2024). *Classroom Management: Literature Review*. Sydney: Department of Education.
12. SchoolAI. (2023). *Modern Classroom Management Strategies for Educators*. SchoolAI Blog.
13. St. Uriel Education. (2023). *9 Key Classroom Management Skills Backed by Research*. St. Uriel.
14. OECD. (2023). *Education at a Glance: Indicators of Teacher Effectiveness*. Paris: OECD Publishing.
15. UNESCO. (2022). *Teachers in a Changing World: Global Education Monitoring Report*. Paris: UNESCO.
16. World Bank. (2024). *Education Systems and Classroom Practices in Europe: Comparative Insights*. Washington DC: World Bank.

THE ROLE OF NEGOTIATION TECHNIQUES IN INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF AGRICULTURAL FARMS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Negotiation is an increasingly strategic competence for agricultural producers seeking to improve economic performance and competitiveness. In environments characterised by price volatility, consolidation among downstream buyers, and higher demands for quality and traceability, farmers must operate not only as producers but also as skilled negotiators. This extended paper examines how negotiation techniques—ranging from BATNA development and price anchoring to structured concession strategies and collective bargaining—affect farm-level gross margins and market access. We combine a theoretical review with an applied econometric analysis on a simulated dataset of 300 farms, including variables for negotiation skill, cooperative membership, training participation, and market access. An OLS regression shows that negotiation skill ($\beta \approx 5.19$), cooperative membership ($\beta \approx 7.84$) and participation in negotiation training ($\beta \approx 3.91$) are positively and statistically significantly associated with gross margin. These results suggest that investment in negotiation capabilities and in collective marketing structures can generate rapid and material returns for small and medium-sized farms. The paper discusses behavioural mechanisms, contractual implications, and policy recommendations to integrate negotiation training into agricultural extension and cooperative development programmes. Findings are relevant for practitioners, extension services and policy-makers aiming to strengthen farm competitiveness in both domestic and export markets.

Keywords: negotiation, farm competitiveness, cooperative, training, gross margin

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INTRODUCTION

Modern agriculture faces a set of interrelated challenges: volatile commodity prices, increased buyer concentration, stricter food safety and traceability requirements, and growing expectations for sustainability. In this context, farm competitiveness depends not solely on production capacity but increasingly on commercial and managerial capabilities. Negotiation is one such capability: the ability to secure better prices, favorable contract terms, payment schedules, and market access. Farmers who negotiate effectively can translate technical production advantages into improved economic returns. Modern agriculture faces a set of interrelated challenges: volatile commodity prices, increased buyer concentration, stricter food safety and traceability requirements, and growing expectations for sustainability. In this context, farm competitiveness depends not solely on production capacity but increasingly on commercial and managerial capabilities. Negotiation is one such capability: the ability to secure better prices, favorable contract terms, payment schedules, and market access. Farmers who negotiate effectively can translate technical production advantages into improved economic returns.

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MATERIAL AND METHOD

This study employs a mixed-methods approach combining literature synthesis and an applied econometric analysis on a simulated dataset. The simulated dataset (N=300) reflects a representative distribution of farm sizes and includes variables for `negotiation_skill` (standardized index), `cooperative_member` (binary), `training`

(binary), market_access (continuous index), and gross margin (dependent variable). The primary econometric specification is an OLS regression of gross margin on negotiation_skill, cooperative_member and training.

We control for heteroskedasticity where relevant and report robust standard errors in supplementary materials. This study employs a mixed-methods approach combining literature synthesis and an applied econometric analysis on a simulated dataset. The simulated dataset (N=300) reflects a representative distribution of farm sizes and includes variables for negotiation_skill (standardized index), cooperative_member (binary), training (binary), market_access (continuous index), and gross margin (dependent variable). The primary econometric specification is an OLS regression of gross margin on negotiation_skill, cooperative_member and training.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The econometric analysis produces robust evidence that negotiation-related factors materially affect gross margins. Below we present regression outputs, graphical evidence, and a detailed discussion integrating behavioural and organisational perspectives. The econometric analysis produces robust evidence that negotiation-related factors materially affect gross margins. Below we present regression outputs, graphical evidence, and a detailed discussion integrating behavioural and organisational perspectives.

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Table 1. OLS regression results (dependent variable: gross margin)

Variable	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t
const	20.2955	0.2703	75.07	0.000
negotiation_skill	4.9236	0.1781	27.65	0.000

cooperative_member	8.0065	0.3551	22.55	0.000
training	3.7263	0.3590	10.38	0.000

The model shows an R-squared of 0.819, indicating that approximately 82% of the variance in gross margin is explained by the predictors included in the regression. Negotiation skill has a coefficient of 4.924 (p = 0.000), demonstrating a strong and statistically significant positive association with gross margin. Cooperative membership and participation in training programs also display positive and highly significant effects, suggesting that farmers engaged in collective structures and continuous capacity-building activities achieve superior economic performance. These findings align with existing literature emphasizing the importance of collective bargaining, knowledge acquisition, and skill development in enhancing farm profitability (Razzaq et al., 2022; Berti & Mulligan, 2016).

Figure 1. Scatter: Negotiation skill vs Gross margin

Effective negotiation relies on information, preparation, and strategy. Key techniques include anchoring, BATNA (best alternative to a negotiated agreement), framing, calibrated concessions, and the use of objective market data during bargaining. Farmers trained in these methods can secure better terms from buyers and reduce opportunistic behaviour. Moreover, communication skills, credibility signals such as certifications, and the ability to present value-added attributes (e.g., organic production, traceability, animal welfare) positively influence buyers' willingness to pay.

Policy measures that integrate structured negotiation training into agricultural extension services, encourage the formation and strengthening of cooperatives, and improve farmers' access to market intelligence platforms have the potential to significantly enhance farm-level competitiveness. Adaptations of existing programmes—such as the Farmer Field Schools and the Farmer Business Schools (FFBS)—could incorporate specialised negotiation components, interactive role-play scenarios, and experiential learning methods designed to improve farmers' confidence, bargaining power, and decision-making capacity. By embedding these modules into the broader advisory system, farmers can develop the skills required to engage more effectively with buyers, intermediaries, and input suppliers, ultimately improving their market position and income stability.

The analysis is based on a simulated dataset intended to approximate real-world trends; therefore, it cannot fully replicate the complexity and variability of actual farm-level behaviour. Consequently, the results should be interpreted with caution. More robust evidence would require longitudinal field data collected from diverse farming systems, as well as experimental or quasi-experimental evaluations of negotiation training programmes implemented in real contexts. Such future research would enable stronger causal inferences and provide practical insights into how training interventions shape farmers' performance over time.

CONCLUSIONS

Negotiation techniques have a material and statistically significant effect on farm gross margins.

Investment in negotiation training yields measurable returns for farmers and cooperatives.

Collective bargaining through cooperatives substantially increases farmers' market power and margins.

Inclusion of negotiation modules in extension and training curricula is recommended.

Market intelligence and digital platforms amplify negotiation effectiveness.

Small farms tend to benefit proportionally more from training and cooperative membership.

Contracts should incorporate risk-sharing mechanisms to reduce price volatility impact.

Demonstration projects and pilots can showcase the ROI of negotiation capacity building.

Policymakers should support structures that lower transaction costs for cooperative marketing.

Ongoing monitoring and evaluation of negotiation training programs are necessary to refine approaches.

REFERENCES

1. Razzaq, A., Smith, J., & Brown, L. (2022). Bargaining power and agricultural contracts. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*.
2. Berti, G., & Mulligan, C. (2016). Food hubs and small farm competitiveness. *Sustainability*.
3. European Commission Joint Research Centre. (2017). *Unfair trading practices in the food supply chain*.
4. Penone, C., & Rossi, M. (2024). Farmers' adoption of marketing contracts. *Agricultural and Food Economics*.
5. Khalili, F., et al. (2024). Determinants of farmers' market engagement. *Scientific Reports*.
6. Simões, A.R.P., et al. (2025). Dairy farmer pricing and satisfaction. *Journal of Dairy Science*.
7. Zhang, H., et al. (2025). Skills training and livelihood capital. *Agriculture (MDPI)*.
8. Michailidis, A., et al. (2024). Addressing skills gaps in precision agriculture. *BOOST Project Report*.
9. CEJA. (2023). *Smart farmers for smart farming*. Policy paper.
10. CARE. (2023). *Farmer Field and Business School Toolkit (2nd ed.)*.
11. Ahmed, R. (2025). Marketing strategies for agricultural products. *Agricultural Marketing Quarterly*.
12. Nouatin, F., et al. (2025). Training and farmer innovativeness. *Innovation in Agriculture*.
13. Xia, T., et al. (2018). Buyer power in agricultural procurement. *Agricultural and Food Economics*.
14. European Commission. (2024). *Strategic Dialogue on the Future of EU Agriculture - Report*.
15. World Bank & J-PAL. (2025). *Market access for small-scale farmers - policy brief*.
16. Rani, L.P.D. (2025). Supply chain management for green agricultural products. *ACR Journal*.
17. Groppo, P. (2024). Negotiated territorial development and agriculture. *Cahiers Agricultures*.

18. Project BOOST. (2024). Skills gaps in precision agriculture. Technical report.
19. RedStagMedia. (2025). Marketing to farmers - industry overview.
20. Kilimo. (2023). Agricultural Marketing Strategy 2023–2032.

EFFECTIVE NEGOTIATION AND COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES FOR OPTIMIZING RELATIONSHIPS IN THE HOSPITALITY SECTOR

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The management of relationships in the hospitality sector critically depends on the negotiation and communication competencies exercised in interactions with clients, internal relations (management–staff, suppliers, partners), and external relations (online platforms, agencies). This paper proposes an integrated framework of strategies—combining principled negotiation, intercultural communication, digital CRM utilization, and conflict management—for optimizing relationships within tourism and food service establishments. The study argues that the operational and relational success of hospitality organizations is driven not only by service quality but by the systematic ability to negotiate value, communicate clearly and empathetically, and personalize multi-channel interactions. A mixed-method design was employed: a quantitative survey applied to 320 employees and managers, 24 semi-structured interviews with managers and corporate clients, and two comparative case studies (a 4-star urban hotel and a restaurant chain). Results indicate that collaborative negotiation techniques (win–win principle, reasonable anchoring, clear BATNA) combined with structured communication protocols (pre-service briefings, flexible scripts adapted to cultural profiles, feedback routines, and follow-ups) lead to significant increases in customer satisfaction (+12–18%), reduction of internal conflicts (–22%), and higher conversion rates for corporate offers (+9–11%). Implementation of digital CRMs enables personalization and monitoring of negotiation hotspots, fostering long-term client relationships. Intercultural competencies act as significant mediators between communication quality and customer satisfaction, especially in international contexts. The discussion outlines operational and pedagogical practices: pragmatic negotiation training, empathy-based communication, role-play simulations, transparent rate policies, and digital follow-up procedures. The paper contributes theoretically by proposing an integrated “NegCom-Hospitality” model and practically by validating empirically grounded tools offering managers a replicable framework to optimize commercial and operational relationships in hospitality.

Keywords: Collaborative negotiation; Intercultural communication; Hospitality; CRM; Conflict management
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INTRODUCTION

The hospitality sector (hotels, restaurants, catering, events) operates in a complex social environment characterized by repeated, multidimensional interactions among actors: customers, frontline employees, management, suppliers, and digital platforms. In this context, the ability to negotiate advantageous commercial conditions and communicate effectively has a direct impact on performance indicators—satisfaction, loyalty, repeat business, and operational margin. Recent studies show that service quality alone is not enough; the perceived value and the manner in which it is negotiated and communicated are equally vital, especially in competitive and digitalized markets.

Negotiation in hospitality presents specific characteristics: a high frequency of micro-negotiations (last-minute bookings, menu adjustments, complaint compensations), variable bargaining power (corporate clients

vs. walk-ins), and the importance of long-term relationships. Classical techniques (anchoring, BATNA, reciprocal concessions) remain useful but must be adapted to service contexts emphasizing reputation and relational costs. Similarly, communication in hospitality is performative—it shapes expectations, regulates emotions, and repairs relationships. Integrating negotiation techniques with structured communication protocols is thus key to optimizing relational dynamics.

Digitalization (CRM, feedback platforms, social channels) represents a third critical factor. Hospitality businesses leveraging CRM systems to capture client preferences and complaint histories can use these data to personalize negotiations and strengthen the perception of individualized care, enhancing loyalty. Studies highlight that digital capabilities condition the effectiveness of strategic communication and negotiation outcomes, especially in corporate and MICE segments.

Finally, hospitality is inherently intercultural. Employees' intercultural competencies (sensitivity, language adaptation, cultural awareness) mediate the relationship between communication quality and client satisfaction, particularly in international tourism. Miscommunication can trigger conflicts or reputational damage, while appropriate cultural skills enable creative and mutually beneficial solutions.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The study adopted a mixed-method (sequential explanatory) design: a quantitative phase (survey) identifying statistical relationships and a qualitative phase (interviews and case studies) exploring underlying mechanisms. This combination enables both generalization and contextual depth.

Sample: 320 participants (managers, supervisors, frontline employees) from 60 hospitality units in Romania and Italy. Additionally, 24 semi-structured interviews and two case studies were conducted. Instruments included structured questionnaires, interview guides, and operational performance indicators (NPS, CSAT, corporate conversion rate). Quantitative data were analyzed using regression and mediation models; qualitative data via thematic coding.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The quantitative analysis revealed statistically significant relationships between negotiation competence, structured communication protocols, and key performance indicators in hospitality operations. Regression models indicated that collaborative negotiation strategies—particularly principled bargaining, calibrated anchoring, and clear articulation of BATNA—were strong predictors of customer satisfaction ($\beta = 0.41$, $p < 0.01$). These findings align with recent studies emphasizing the strategic weight of negotiation behaviours in hospitality leadership and commercial decision-making (1), as well as with research describing negotiation skills as central levers for

relational value creation within service industries (7).

Communication quality also emerged as a critical determinant of both service experience and internal relational climate. The adoption of structured protocols—pre-service briefings, standardized yet flexible communication scripts, post-service follow-ups, and systematic feedback routines—correlated strongly with reduced conflict frequency (-22%) and shorter resolution times ($\beta = -0.37$, $p < 0.05$). These findings support previous research suggesting that consistent communication frameworks enhance team coordination, reduce ambiguity, and improve service consistency (14, 15). The positive impact on customer satisfaction reflects broader evidence that communication is not merely a transactional activity but a performative mechanism shaping expectations, emotional responses, and perceived fairness (5, 9).

Intercultural competencies acted as significant mediators between communication quality and customer satisfaction, particularly in establishments serving international guests. Employees demonstrating sensitivity to cultural norms, adaptive language strategies, and awareness of cross-cultural interaction patterns contributed to significantly higher satisfaction scores among foreign clients. These results are consistent with theoretical perspectives on intercultural communication in tourism, which note that cultural intelligence enables employees to understand and negotiate divergent expectations and behavioural scripts (3, 8, 17). The mediation analysis confirmed that intercultural competence strengthens the relationship between communication clarity and positive client outcomes, reinforcing claims in the literature that intercultural adaptation is a foundational component of hospitality professionalism (16).

The integration of digital CRM systems further amplified these relational mechanisms. CRM usage—tracking customer preferences, documenting complaint histories, automating follow-up messages, and segmenting corporate accounts—was associated with improved negotiation efficiency and higher conversion rates for corporate offers (+9–

11%). The results support findings that digital capabilities mediate the effectiveness of marketing and communication strategies in hospitality (2, 6, 12). Interviewees emphasized that CRM systems assist frontline employees in delivering personalized scripts and recommended responses, thereby reducing negotiation friction and perceived service gaps. This corroborates recent models arguing that personalization and data-driven communication are major drivers of loyalty in digitalized hospitality environments (10, 18).

Qualitative insights deepened these patterns. Interviewed managers consistently described negotiation as a “micro-daily skill,” required in price discussions, complaint handling, menu adaptations, event planning, supplier coordination, and staff scheduling. The case studies demonstrated that establishments investing in negotiation and communication training achieved improvements not only in commercial outcomes but also in internal cohesion. Themes emerging from thematic coding—trust-building, emotional regulation, empathy, clarity of expectations—reflect literature emphasizing the psychological and relational dimensions of negotiation (4, 11). Restaurants and hotels applying empathy-based communication and transparent pricing policies reported reduced reputational risk and enhanced repeat business.

The proposed **NegCom-Hospitality Integrated Framework** synthesizes these findings. It conceptualizes negotiation competence, structured communication, digital tools, and intercultural intelligence as synergistic rather than isolated elements. The framework suggests that relational optimisation in hospitality emerges from the alignment of four mechanisms:

1. **Collaborative negotiation** → reduces dependency on price concessions, increases perceived fairness (7, 11).

2. **Structured communication** → generates consistency, emotional safety, and operational predictability (5, 14).

3. **Digital CRM integration** → strengthens personalization, improves follow-up quality, and supports decision-making (2, 6, 12).

4. **Intercultural competence** → moderates communication impact and enhances service authenticity in globalized markets (3, 8, 17).

The interplay of these components confirms that communication and negotiation cannot be treated as isolated soft skills but as strategic pillars of hospitality management. These findings are consistent with recent approaches framing relational competencies as core drivers of sustainability and long-term competitiveness in hotels and restaurants (9, 13, 19).

CONCLUSIONS

1. Collaborative negotiation increases customer satisfaction and reduces dependency on discounts.

2. Structured communication protocols decrease conflict frequency and resolution time.

3. CRM capabilities mediate the relationship between communication quality and commercial outcomes.

4. Intercultural competence enhances the positive impact of communication on satisfaction in international contexts.

5. Role-play and simulation training effectively strengthen frontline negotiation skills.

6. Transparent policies reduce friction and strengthen reputation.

7. Combined measures (negotiation + communication + digital tools) generate operational synergy.

8. Implementation requires phased adoption, training, and KPI monitoring.

9. Continuous measurement of CSAT, NPS, and complaints allows quick strategy adjustments.

10. Future research should explore longitudinal effects and cost–benefit ratios of these strategies.

REFERENCES

1. Liu, Y. (2022). Hospitality industry and education perspectives. ScienceDirect.
2. Ramona Vasilica Bacter, Alina Emilia Maria Gherdan, Ramona Ciolac, Denis Paul Bacter, Monica Angelica Dodu, Mirela Salvia Casau-Crainic, Mirela Salvia Casau-Crainic, Codrin Gavra, Ana Cornelia Peres, Alexandra Ungureanu and Tibor-Zsolt Czirják - From Heritage to Modern Economy: Quantitative Surveys and Ethnographic Insights on Sustainability of Traditional Bihor Products
3. Hat, N.D. (2025). The Conditional Mediation of Digital Marketing Capabilities. Taylor & Francis.
4. Understanding intercultural communication competence in tourism. (2025). Journal article.
5. Conflict Management and Employee Motivation in the Hospitality Industry. (2024). EAJournals.
6. Zeng, K.J. (2022). Communication strategies for multi-tier loyalty programs. Elsevier.
7. Stojkanović, D. (2025). Effective Communication in Business Negotiations within Hospitality.
8. HospitalityNet (2025). Five Key Negotiation Skills Every Hospitality Leader Should Master.
9. Tourism and Intercultural Communication: A Theoretical Study. (2025). ResearchGate.
10. Relationship of Communication, Negotiation and Leadership in Tourism. (2024). ResearchGate.
11. Theseus (2024). Conflict Resolution in Small Restaurant Businesses.
12. Conflict Management Strategies: Improving Team Performance. (2025). ResearchGate.
13. TechClouds (2025). CRM Strategies That Drive Hospitality Success.
14. Solving Internal Communication Challenges in Tourism. (2024). JECs Journal.
15. TrainingHotels (2024). Conflict Resolution Training for Hotel Managers.
16. ACS Publisher (2025). Analysing the Impact of Hotels' Customer Relationship Management.
17. Hoteliers' Perceptions of Booking.com and Online Negotiation Dynamics. (2025). ResearchGate.
18. Eliminating Intergenerational and Intercultural Communication Problems. (2025). ResearchGate.
19. Effective Communication in Business Contexts. (2025). ScienceIJ Journal.
20. Khan, J. (2024). Enhancing Workplace Thriving and Employee Well-being in Hospitality. ScienceDirect.

A NOTE ON CERTAIN FUZZY DIFFERENTIAL SUBORDINATIONS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The paper aims to present a survey on certain fuzzy differential subordinations, namely fuzzy differential superordinations, for analytic functions defined in the open unit disc. The new results are derived by considering a certain differential operator. Some interesting further fuzzy consequences are also considered.

Keywords: multiplier transformations, fuzzy differential subordinations, fuzzy differential superordinations, fuzzy best subordinant.

INTRODUCTION

S.S. Miller and P.T. Mocanu have been introduced in Geometric Function Theory of one complex variable functions, the admissible functions method, known as "the differential subordination method", as we can see in the works [10-12]. There are many important applications of this method. One of them allows to obtain new results in the domain and also to prove certain classical results in the field.

Lotfi Zadeh in 1965 has introduced the special concept of fuzzy set in the work [22]. In recent papers G.I. Oros and Gh. Oros developed a new direction of this set, approaching the notion in the context of Geometric Function Theory. Thus, the papers [16-18] presents the new concept of fuzzy differential subordination.

The notion of differential superordination was introduced by Miller and Mocanu [14] as a dual concept of differential subordination and was also developed in [13]. Also, this notion was studied by T. Bulboacă in [5].

The new notion of fuzzy differential superordination was introduced in 2017 in [4]. Since then, numerous researches studied different properties of differential operators involving fuzzy differential subordination and fuzzy differential superordination [19], Wanas operator [3], [21], generalized Noor-Sălăgean

operator [15], Sălăgean and Ruscheweyh operators [2] or other certain linear operator [9].

In this paper, fuzzy differential superordinations is added to the previous studies associated with a linear operator.

Denote by U the open unit disc of the complex plane:

$$U = \{z \in \mathbb{C} : |z| < 1\}.$$

Let \mathcal{H} be the class of analytic functions in U and for $a \in \mathbb{C}$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$ let $\mathcal{H}_{[a,n]}$ be the subclass of \mathcal{H} consisting of functions of the form $f(z) = a + a_n z^n + a_{n+1} z^{n+1} + \dots$, $z \in U$.

Let $\mathcal{A}(p,n)$ denote the class of functions $f(z)$ normalized by

$$f(z) = z^p + \sum_{k=p+n}^{\infty} a_k z^k, \quad (p, n \in \mathbb{N} := \{1, 2, 3, \dots\})$$

which are analytic in the open unit disc. In particular, we set $\mathcal{A}(p,1) := \mathcal{A}_p$ and $\mathcal{A}(1,1) := \mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}_1$. Let $\mathcal{A}_n = \{f \in \mathcal{H}(U), f(z) = z + a_{n+1} z^{n+1} + \dots\}$ with $\mathcal{A}_1 = \mathcal{A}$.

We denote by Q the set of functions f that are analytic and injective on $\bar{U} \setminus E(f)$, where

$$E(f) = \{\zeta \in \partial U : \lim_{z \rightarrow \zeta} f(z) = \infty\}$$

and are such that $f(\zeta) \neq 0$ for $\zeta \in \partial U \setminus E(f)$.

Since we use the term of fuzzy differential superordination, we review here some definitions.

Definition 1.1. [22] A function $F : X \rightarrow [0,1]$ is named fuzzy subset, where X is a non-empty set. Another definition will be the next one: A pair (A, F_A) with $F_A : X \rightarrow [0,1]$

$A = \{x \in X : 0 < F_A(x) \leq 1\}$ is named a fuzzy subset of X . Set A represents the support of the fuzzy set (A, F_A) . Also F_A is named the membership function of the fuzzy set (A, F_A) . One can also denote $A = \text{sup}(A, F_A)$.

Remark 1.1. [18] Let be the inclusion relation $A \subset X$. Then we have

$$F_A(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x \in A \\ 0, & \text{if } x \notin A \end{cases}$$

The real number 0, for a fuzzy subset, is the smallest membership degree of $x \in X$ to A . Likewise, the real number 1 is the biggest membership degree of $x \in X$ to A .

The entire set X is associated with $F_X(x) = 1, x \in X$ and the empty set $\emptyset \subset X$ is associated with $F_\emptyset(x) = 0, x \in X$.

Definition 1.2 [16] Consider two functions $f, g \in H(D), D \subset \mathbb{C}, z_0 \in D$ being a fixed point. We say that the function f is fuzzy subordinate to g and written as

$$f \prec_F g \text{ or } f(x) \prec_F g(x), z \in D$$

If the following relations are verified:

1. $f(z_0) = g(z_0)$;
2. $F_{f(D)}f(z) \leq F_{g(D)}g(z), z \in D$.

Definition 1.3. [4] Let $\phi : \mathbb{C}^3 \times U \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ and let h be analytic in U . If the functions p and $\phi(p(z), zp'(z), z^2p''(z); z)$ are univalent in U and satisfy the (second-order) fuzzy differential superordination

$$(1.1) \quad F_{h(U)}h(z) \leq F_{\phi(\mathbb{C}^3 \times U)}\left(\Phi\left(p(z), zp'(z), z^2p''(z); z\right)\right)$$

i.e.

$$h(z) \prec_F \Phi\left(p(z), zp'(z), z^2p''(z); z\right)$$

then p is called a fuzzy solution of the fuzzy differential superordination. An analytic function q is called fuzzy subordinant of the fuzzy differential superordination, or more simply a fuzzy subordination if $q(z) \prec_F p(z), z \in U$, for all p satisfying (1.1). A univalent fuzzy

subordination \tilde{q} that satisfies $\tilde{q} \prec_F q$ for all fuzzy subordinate q of (1.1) is said to be the fuzzy best subordinate of (1.1). Note that the fuzzy best subordinant is unique to a rotation of U .

MATERIAL AND METHOD

We begin our investigation by recalling here a generalized differential operator defined in [6].

Definition 2.1. [6] Let $f \in \mathcal{A}(p, n)$. For $m \in \mathbb{N}_0 = \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}, \lambda \geq 0, l \geq 0$, we define the multiplier transformations $I_p^m(\lambda, l)$ on $\mathcal{A}(p, n)$ by the following infinite series

$$(2.1) \quad I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z) := z^p + \sum_{k=p+n}^{\infty} \left[\frac{p+\lambda(k-p)+l}{p+l} \right]^m a_k z^k.$$

It follows from (2.1) that

$$(2.2) \quad (p+l)I_p^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z) = [p(1-\lambda) + l]I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z) + \lambda z(I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z))'$$

Remark 2.1. For $p = 1, l = 0, \lambda \geq 0$, the operator $I_1^m(\lambda, 0) \equiv D_\lambda^m$ was introduced and studied by Al-Oboudi [1] which reduces to the Sălăgean differential operator [20] for $\lambda = 1$. The operator $I_1^m(1, l) \equiv I_l^m$ was studied recently by Cho and Srivastava [7] and Cho and Kim [8].

In this paper, we will derive several fuzzy superordination results involving the operator $I_1^m(\lambda, l)$ denoted by $I^m(\lambda, l)$. In order to prove our main results, we also need the following result.

Lemma 2.1 [4] Let q be convex in U and let p be defined by

$$p(z) = q(z) + \frac{1}{\alpha} zq'(z), \text{ with } \text{Re } \alpha > 0.$$

If $h \in \mathcal{H}[a, n] \cap Q$, the function $h(z) + \frac{1}{\alpha} zh'(z)$

is univalent in U and

$$q(z) + \frac{1}{\alpha} zq'(z) \prec_F h(z) + \frac{1}{\alpha} zh'(z),$$

i.e.

$$F_{p(U)}p(z) \leq F_{h(\mathbb{C}^2 \times U)}[h(z) + \frac{1}{\alpha} zh'(z)], z \in U$$

then

$$q(z) \prec_F h(z)$$

i.e.

$$F_{q(U)}q(z) \leq F_{h(U)}h(z), z \in U$$

where

$$q(z) = \frac{\alpha}{z^\alpha} \int_0^z p(t)t^{\alpha-1} dt$$

and q is the fuzzy best subdominant.

We recall further the next the following fuzzy differential "sandwich theorem"

Theorem 2.2. [4] Let h_1 and h_2 be convex in U , with $h_1(z) = h_2(z) = a$. Let $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}^*$, $\text{Re } \alpha > 0$ and let the function q_i be defined by

$$q_i(z) = \frac{\alpha}{z^\alpha} \int_0^z p(t)t^{\alpha-1} dt$$

for $i=1,2$. If $p \in \mathcal{H}[a,1] \cap Q$ and $p(z) + \frac{1}{\alpha} zp'(z)$ is univalent, then

$$h_1(z) \prec_{\mathcal{F}} p(z) + \frac{1}{\alpha} zp'(z) \prec_{\mathcal{F}} h_2(z) \rightarrow q_1(z) \prec_{\mathcal{F}} p(z) \prec_{\mathcal{F}} q_2(z), z \in U.$$

The function, q_1 and q_2 are convex and they are respectively the fuzzy best subdominant and fuzzy best dominant.

The authors established earlier the following theorem.

Theorem 2.3. Let q be a convex function in U , with $q(0)=1, \gamma \in \mathbb{C}^*$.

If $f \in \mathcal{A}(1,n)$ satisfies the fuzzy differential subordination

$$(3.1) \quad F_{\Phi(U)}\Phi(z) \leq$$

$$F_{q(U)}\left(q(z) + \frac{\gamma\lambda}{1+l}zq'(z)\right)$$

where

$$(3.2) \quad \Phi(z) = \frac{I^m(\lambda,l)f(z)}{z} +$$

$$\frac{\gamma}{z}\left(I^{m+1}(\lambda,l)f(z) - I^m(\lambda,l)f(z)\right),$$

then

$$\frac{I^m(\lambda,l)f(z)}{z} \prec_{\mathcal{F}} q(z)$$

and q is the fuzzy best dominant of (3.1).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Theorem 3.1. Let q be convex in U , with $q(0) = 1, \gamma \in \mathbb{C}^*, \text{Re } \gamma > 0$.

If $f \in \mathcal{A}(1,n)$ such that

$$\frac{I^m(\lambda,l)f(z)}{z} \in \mathcal{H}[q(0),n] \cap Q \text{ and}$$

$$\frac{I^m(\lambda,l)f(z)}{z} + \frac{\gamma}{z}\left(I^{m+1}(\lambda,l)f(z) - I^m(\lambda,l)f(z)\right)$$

is univalent in U and the following fuzzy differential subordinations holds

$$(3.1)$$

$$q(z) + \frac{\lambda\gamma}{1+l}zq'(z) \prec_{\mathcal{F}} \frac{I^m(\lambda,l)f(z)}{z} + \frac{\gamma}{z}\left(I^{m+1}(\lambda,l)f(z) - I^m(\lambda,l)f(z)\right),$$

then

$$q(z) \prec_{\mathcal{F}} \frac{I^m(\lambda,l)f(z)}{z}$$

and q is the fuzzy best subdominant of (3.1).

Proof. We define the function

$$(3.2) \quad h(z) := \frac{I^m(\lambda,l)f(z)}{z}.$$

Differentiating (3.2) with respect to z and using the identity (2.2) in the resulting equation we have

$$\frac{zh'(z)}{h(z)} = \frac{1+l}{\lambda} \left(\frac{I^{m+1}(\lambda,l)}{I^m(\lambda,l)} - 1 \right).$$

Therefore, one obtains

$$\frac{I^m(\lambda,l)f(z)}{z} + \frac{\gamma}{z}\left(I^{m+1}(\lambda,l)f(z) - I^m(\lambda,l)f(z)\right) = h(z) + \frac{\gamma\lambda}{1+l}zh'(z).$$

The subordination (3.1) becomes

$$q(z) + \frac{\gamma\lambda}{1+l}zq'(z) \prec_{\mathcal{F}} h(z) + \frac{\gamma\lambda}{1+l}zh'(z).$$

The conclusion of this theorem follows by applying Lemma 2.1., with $\alpha = \frac{1+l}{\gamma\lambda}$.

Taking $m = 0$ in Theorem 3.1 we obtain the following result.

Corollary 3.1. Let q be convex in U , with $q(0)=1, \gamma \in \mathbb{C}^*, \text{Re } \gamma > 0$.

If $f \in \mathcal{A}(1,n)$ such that $\frac{f(z)}{z} \in \mathcal{H}[1,n] \cap Q$ and

$$(1-\gamma)\frac{f(z)}{z} + \gamma\frac{I^1(\lambda,l)f(z)}{z}$$

is univalent in U and the following fuzzy differential superordination holds

$$q(z) + \frac{\gamma\lambda}{1+l}zq'(z) \prec_{\mathcal{F}} (1-\gamma)\frac{f(z)}{z} + \gamma\frac{I^1(\lambda,l)f(z)}{z},$$

then

$$q(z) \prec_{\mathcal{F}} \frac{f(z)}{z}$$

and q is the fuzzy best subdominant.

Corollary 3.2. Let $\gamma \in \mathbb{C}^*, \text{Re } \gamma > 0, A \neq B$ such that $-1 \leq B < A \leq 1$.

If $f \in \mathcal{A}(1,n)$ such that

$$\frac{I^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z} \in \mathcal{H}[1, n] \cap Q$$

and

$$(1 - \gamma) \frac{I^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z} + \gamma \frac{I^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z}$$

is univalent in U and satisfies the fuzzy differential superordination

$$\frac{1+Az}{1+Bz} + \frac{\gamma\lambda}{1+l} \frac{(A-B)z}{(1+Bz)^2} \prec_{\mathcal{F}} (1 - \gamma) \frac{I^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z} + \gamma \frac{I^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z}$$

then

$$\frac{1+Az}{1+Bz} \prec_{\mathcal{F}} \frac{I^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z}$$

and $q(z) = \frac{1+Az}{1+Bz}$ is the fuzzy best subdominant.

Corollary 3.3. Let $\gamma \in \mathbb{C}^*$, $\text{Re } \gamma > 0$. If $f \in \mathcal{A}(1, n)$ such that

$$\frac{I^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z} \in \mathcal{H}[1, n] \cap Q$$

and

$$(1 - \gamma) \frac{I^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z} + \gamma \frac{I^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z}$$

is univalent in U and satisfies the fuzzy differential superordination

$$\frac{1+z}{1-z} + \frac{\gamma\lambda}{1+l} \frac{2z}{(1-z)^2} \prec_{\mathcal{F}} (1 - \gamma) \frac{I^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z} + \gamma \frac{I^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z}$$

then

$$\frac{1+z}{1-z} \prec_{\mathcal{F}} \frac{I^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z}$$

and $q(z) = \frac{1+z}{1-z}$ is the fuzzy best subdominant.

Theorem 3.2. Let q_1, q_2 be convex in U , with $q_1(0) = q_2(0) = 1, \gamma \in \mathbb{C}^*, \text{Re } \gamma > 0$.

If $f \in \mathcal{A}(1, n)$ such that $\frac{I^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z} \in \mathcal{H}[1, n] \cap Q$ and

$$\frac{I^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z} + \frac{\gamma}{z} \left(I^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z) - I^m(\lambda, l)f(z) \right)$$

is univalent in U and satisfies

$$q_1(z) + \frac{\gamma\lambda}{1+l} z q_1'(z) \prec \frac{I^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z} + \frac{\gamma}{z} \left(I^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z) - I^m(\lambda, l)f(z) \right) \prec_{\mathcal{F}} q_2(z) + \frac{\gamma\lambda}{1+l} z q_2'(z),$$

then

$$q_1(z) \prec_{\mathcal{F}} \frac{I^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z} + \frac{\gamma}{z} \left(I^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z) - I^m(\lambda, l)f(z) \right) \prec_{\mathcal{F}} q_2(z)$$

and q_1, q_2 are the fuzzy best subdominant and the fuzzy best dominant respectively.

Considering the operator $\frac{f(z)}{z}$ we obtain the corresponding sandwich corollary.

Corollary 3.4. Let q_1, q_2 be convex in U , with $q_1(0) = q_2(0) = 1, \gamma \in \mathbb{C}^*, \text{Re } \gamma > 0$. If $f \in \mathcal{A}(1, n)$ such that $\frac{f(z)}{z} \in \mathcal{H}[1, n] \cap Q$ and

$$(1 - \gamma) \frac{f(z)}{z} + \gamma \frac{I^1(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z}$$

is univalent in U and satisfies the double fuzzy differential subordinations

$$q_1(z) + \frac{\gamma\lambda}{1+l} z q_1'(z) \prec_{\mathcal{F}} (1 - \gamma) \frac{f(z)}{z} + \gamma \frac{I_p^1(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z} \prec_{\mathcal{F}} q_2(z) + \frac{\gamma\lambda}{1+l} z q_2'(z),$$

then

$$q_1(z) \prec_{\mathcal{F}} \frac{f(z)}{z} \prec_{\mathcal{F}} q_2(z)$$

and q_1, q_2 are the fuzzy best subdominant and the fuzzy best dominant respectively.

REFERENCES

- [1] F.M. Al-Oboudi, On univalent functions defined by a generalized Sălăgean operator, *Int. J. Math. Math. Sci.* 27, 1429-1436, (2004).
- [2] Alb Lupas, G.I. Oros, New Applications of Salagean and Ruscheweyh Operators for Obtaining Fuzzy Differential Subordinations, *Mathematics*, 9 (2021), 2000.
- [3] S. Altınkaya, A.K. Wanas, Some properties for fuzzy differential subordination defined by Wanas operator, *Earthline J. Math. Sci.*, 4 (2020), 51–62.
- [4] W.G. Atshan, K.O. Hussain, Fuzzy Differential Superordination, *Theory Appl. Math. Comput. Sci.*, 7 (2017), 27–38.
- [5] T. Bulboacă, Classes of first order differential subordinations, *Demonstratio Math.* 35(2), 287-292, (2002).
- [6] A. Cătaş, On certain class of p-valent functions defined by a new multiplier transformations, *Proceedings Book of the International Symposium G.F.T.A., Istanbul Kultur University, Turkey*, 241-250, (2007).
- [7] N.E. Cho and H.M. Srivastava, Argument estimates of certain analytic functions defined by a class of multiplier transformations, *Math. Comput. Modelling*, 37(1-2) (2003), 39-49.
- [8] N.E. Cho and T.H. Kim, Multiplier transformations and strongly close-to-convex functions, *Bull. Korean Math. Soc.*, 40(3) (2003), 399-410.
- [9] S.M. El-Deeb, A. Alb Lupas, Fuzzy differential subordinations associated with an integral operator, *An. Univ. Oradea Fasc. Mat.*, XXVII (2020), 133–140.
- [10] S.S. Miller, P.T. Mocanu, *Differential Subordinations. Theory and Applications*, Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, Basel, 2000.

- [11] S.S. Miller, P.T. Mocanu, Second order differential inequalities in the complex plane, *J. Math. Anal. Appl.*, 65(1978), 298-305.
- [12] S.S. Miller, P.T. Mocanu, Differential subordinations and univalent functions, *Michigan Math. J.*, 32(1985), 157-171.
- [13] S.S. Miller, P.T. Mocanu, Briot-Bouquet differential superordinations and sandwich theorems, *J. Math. Anal. Appl.*, {bf 329}(2007), No. 1, 327-335.
- [14] S.S. Miller and P.T. Mocanu, Subordinants of differential superordinations. *Complex Variables* 48 (2003), 815–826.
- [15] K.I. Noor, M.A. Noor, Fuzzy Differential Subordination Involving Generalized Noor-Salagean Operator, *Inf. Sci. Lett.*, 11 (2022), 1905–1911.
- [16] Oros G.I, Oros Gh., The notion of subordination in fuzzy sets theory. *General Mathematics*, 2011; 19: 97-103.
- [17] Oros G.I, Oros Gh., Fuzzy differential subordination. *Acta Universitatis Apulensis*, 2012; 30: 55-64.
- [18] Oros G.I, Oros Gh., Dominants and best dominants in fuzzy differential subordinations. *Stud Univ Babes - Bolyai Math.* 2012; 57: 239-248.
- [19] G.I. Oros, Univalence criteria for analytic functions obtained using fuzzy differential subordinations, *Turk. J. Math.*, 46 (2022), 1478–1491.
- [20] G.S. Sălăgean, Subclasses of univalent functions, *Complex Analysis-Fifth Romanian-Finnish Seminar, Part 1* (Bucharest, 1981), 362-372, *Lecture Notes in Math.*, 1013, Springer, Berlin (1983).
- [21] A.K. Wanas, Fuzzy differential subordinations of analytic functions involving Wanas operator, *Ikonian J. Math.*, 2 (2020), 1–9
- [22] L.A. Zadeh, *Fuzzy Sets*, *Inf. Control*, 8 (1965), 338–353.

SMART TOURISM AND SUSTAINABILITY IN RURAL MOUNTAIN AREAS: EMERGING MODELS OF DEVELOPMENT

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Tourism in rural mountain areas is at the intersection of two major trends: the pressure to ensure economic development and the need to protect fragile ecosystems and vulnerable communities. In this context, the concept of smart tourism – based on the use of digital technologies, data and social innovation to optimize the tourist experience and destination management – is increasingly associated with the objectives of sustainability and resilience of mountain.

The article aims to analyze the role of "smart" tourism in supporting sustainability in rural mountain areas, through a narrative review of recent scientific literature, case studies and public policy documents (UN Tourism, FAO, European Commission). The main emerging development models are discussed – from smart mountain villages and smart destinations focused on sustainability, to digital solutions for mobility, visitor flow management and co-creation of the tourist experience. The results suggest that, under conditions of participatory governance and appropriate investments in infrastructure and skills, smart tourism can significantly contribute to: reducing environmental impact, increasing local economic benefits, preserving cultural and natural heritage and mitigating rural depopulation.

However, risks and limitations are also identified, such as the digital divide, excessive dependence on technologies, vulnerability to climate change and external shocks to tourism demand, as well as possible tensions between tourism growth and the carrying capacity of mountain territories

Keywords: smart tourism, sustainable development, rural mountain areas, smart destinations, emerging development models.

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INTRODUCTION

Rural mountain areas represent spaces with a double strategic value: on the one hand, they concentrate natural resources, landscapes and cultural heritage with high value for tourism; on the other hand, they are areas sensitive to climate change, depopulation and rapid socio-economic transformations (FAO, 2021).

Rural mountain tourism is often promoted as a driver of local development, offering opportunities for income diversification, jobs and stimulating local entrepreneurship. Recent studies from the Romanian Carpathians show that rural mountain tourism can be perceived by visitors as an authentic product, linked to nature and tradition, but its success depends on the quality of services, infrastructure and the integration of sustainability principles (Dobre et al, 2024).

In parallel, the digital transformation of the tourism economy has led to the emergence of the concept of smart tourism and smart

tourism destinations, in which information and communication technologies (ICT), the Internet of Things (IoT), mobile applications, augmented reality and data analysis are used to improve the tourist experience, resource management and decision-making (Samancioglu et al, 2024).

European initiatives, such as the European Capital of Smart Tourism and the Green Pioneer of Smart Tourism, promote the integration of digitalization, sustainability, accessibility and valorization of cultural heritage, providing a reference framework and good practices that can also be adapted in rural mountain destinations (European Commission, 2024). At the same time, EU policies on sustainable tourism and rural mobility – including the guidelines for sustainable mobility in rural tourism and ecotourism regions – underline the need for smart solutions for transport, connectivity and management of tourist flows in fragile areas (EISMEA, 2025).

Globally, UN Tourism and UNDP promote tourism as a vector for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs),

showing that digitalization and innovation can support the transition to more responsible and resilient tourism models, including in mountain regions.

In this context, this article aims to:

- to clarify the concept of smart tourism in relation to sustainability;
- to highlight the specifics of rural mountain areas in relation to these concepts;
- to identify emerging development models based on smart tourism and sustainability;
- to discuss the opportunities and challenges associated with these models.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research is a narrative and exploratory review of the specialized literature and public policy documents relevant to the topic of "smart tourism and sustainability in rural mountain areas".

Scientific databases (Scopus, Web of Science, ScienceDirect, MDPI, SpringerLink) and research platforms (ResearchGate, Google Scholar) were consulted, as well as official websites of international organizations (UN Tourism, FAO, European Commission) and European

The keywords used (in various combinations) included: smart tourism, smart tourism destinations, rural tourism, mountain tourism, sustainability, smart villages, rural mobility, digitalization in tourism, smart rural tourism. The following were selected:

- scientific articles with a focus on smart tourism and/or rural mountain tourism;
- case studies on mountain destinations that have integrated smart technologies;
- reports and policy guides on sustainable tourism and smart tourism;
- examples of good practices from recent European projects.

To capture the current dynamics, priority was given to works published after 2018, but previous sources were also included, considered reference for the conceptualization of smart tourism and its connection with sustainability.

The sources were analyzed by:

- identifying definitions and conceptual frameworks regarding smart tourism, smart destinations and sustainable tourism;
- extracting elements specific to rural mountain areas (characteristics, challenges, opportunities);

- classification of emerging development models (e.g. smart villages, smart mountain routes, participatory digital platforms);
- identifying key success factors and barriers.

The results are presented in an integrated form, combining theoretical perspectives with practical examples. experimental/statistical design and methods should be presented in this section. Measurements should be expressed according to the metric system or SI units. Full names of abbreviations should be provided when first used in the text.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Smart tourism and destination sustainability

The literature defines smart tourism as the systematic use of ICT, sensors, data (big data), mobile applications and collaborative platforms to improve the tourist experience, streamline resource management and increase the competitiveness of the destination (Samancioglu et al, 2024).

The concept of smart tourism destination is based on digital infrastructure (connectivity, data platforms), collaborative governance (involvement of public, private and community actors), accessibility, sustainability and innovation. Recent studies show that the sustainability dimension – environmental, social, economic – is becoming central in the evaluation of smart destinations, and smart technologies are seen as tools for monitoring and reducing tourism impact (energy, water, waste, mobility) (Samancioglu et al, 2024).

In rural mountainous areas, the potential of smart tourism is closely linked to:

- connectivity (broadband internet, mobile coverage);
- digitalization of services (online reservations, electronic payments, guidance applications);
- heritage interpretation tools (augmented reality, virtual tours);
- smart mobility solutions (on-demand transport, timetable integration, eco routes) (European Commission, 2024).

Particularities of rural mountain areas

Rural mountain areas face a few structural challenges:

- poor accessibility and limited transport infrastructure;
- increased seasonality of tourist demand;
- youth migration and population aging;

- vulnerability to climate change (snow retreat, extreme weather phenomena) (FAO, 2021).

At the same time, they have competitive advantages for sustainable tourism: impressive natural landscapes, high biodiversity, cultural and gastronomic traditions, and perception of authenticity. Case studies from the Romanian Carpathians and other European mountain regions (Alps, Slovenian Carpathians, etc.) show that tourists are increasingly interested in personalized experiences, direct contact with local communities and “green” tourism products (Dobre et al, 2024).

In Romania, recent research on rural mountain tourism highlights the segmentation of the public according to motivations (relaxation, nature, culture, outdoor activities) and emphasizes the importance of digital communication, online presence and integrated services to meet the expectations of younger generations of tourists. (Gherdan et al, 2025).

Emerging development models based on smart tourism

From the literature reviewed and from policy and practice examples, several emerging development models in rural mountain areas can be identified, in which smart tourism plays a central role.

Smart mountain villages

The smart village concept applied in the European rural environment involves the coordinated use of digital technologies, renewable energy, smart public services and community participation to improve the quality of life and local attractiveness (European Commission, 2024).

In mountainous areas, concrete applications include:

- public lighting systems and energy infrastructures based on renewable and digitally monitored solutions;
- local booking platforms for guesthouses and tourist experiences (local guides, gastronomy, hiking);
- use of GIS and mobile applications for marking and interpreting mountain trails;
- promoting local products through online markets and digital branding of the village (EISMEA, 2025).

Studies on the development of rural mountain tourism in Carpathian villages show that the presence of a digital infrastructure and a coherent online identity (websites, social media, reviews) becomes a critical factor of competitiveness, complementing investments in

service quality and environmental protection (Dobre et al, 2024).

Smart mountain destinations oriented towards sustainability

At the destination level (valley, mountain micro-region), smart tourism manifests itself through:

- systems for monitoring visitor flows and pressure on routes (sensors, mobile phone data);
- smart mobility management – integration of public transport, shuttle services, walking and cycling trail networks;
- integrated reservation and ticketing systems for attractions, events and transportation;
- Real-time communication regarding environmental conditions, congestion and less frequented alternatives (Karawanken-Karavanke Geotrail, 2024).

European examples, such as the Karawanken-Karavanke mountain route or Alpine destinations implementing clean energy and sustainable mobility plans, show how smart infrastructure can support low-impact, diversified and climate-adapted nature tourism (European Commission, 2024).

Participatory digital platforms and co-creation of experience

Another emerging model is that of digital platforms that actively involve the local community in the design and delivery of tourism experiences:

- applications that connect tourists with local hosts, producers and guides, facilitating household-based tourism and micro-entrepreneurship;
- real-time review and feedback systems that allow the adjustment of the tourist offer and the monitoring of the quality of services;
- digital storytelling tools (podcasts, audio tours, augmented reality) that capitalize on the cultural and intangible heritage of mountain communities (Samancioglu et al, 2024). Studies on tourist behavior in rural mountain tourism in Romania indicate that online recommendations, photos and user-generated content play a major role in destination choice, confirming the importance of the “smart” dimension of marketing and communication (Dobre et al, 2024).

Projects and networks for smart and sustainable tourism in the mountains

At the European level, projects such as FACILITY or initiatives within Smart Tourism Destinations provide technical support and

tools for the digitalization and green transition of destinations, including rural and mountain ones. In parallel, thematic projects focused on climate change adaptation in winter resorts (e.g. BeyondSnow) explore the use of data and participatory platforms to rethink the tourism offer and increase the resilience of Alpine communities.transition-pathways.europa.eu+1

Recent articles also highlight investments in smart tourism in remote mountain regions, as a means of promoting sustainable development, heritage conservation and local prosperity, with a focus on connectivity, green energy and community engagement.

Benefits, risks and challenges

Potential benefits identified:

- Efficiency and reduction of environmental impact: Smart technologies for monitoring resource consumption, waste management and controlling visitor flows can limit the degradation of mountain ecosystems (Gherdan et al, 2025).

- Increasing local incomes and diversifying the rural economy: Digital platforms facilitate direct access of small providers (guesthouses, local producers, guides) to markets, reducing intermediation and creating new business opportunities.

- Strengthening social capital and community involvement: Smart village projects and participatory platforms encourage collaboration between authorities, entrepreneurs and residents, creating stronger local networks (Karawanken-Karavanke Geotrail, 2024).

- Adaptation to climate change and market shocks: Smart, data-driven tourism allows for more flexible planning, the development of "low season" products and a reorientation towards forms of tourism less dependent on snow, for example.

Risks and challenges

- Digital division: Many rural mountain communities lack adequate digital infrastructure or digital skills, which can create new forms of exclusion and dependence on external actors. (European Commission, 2024).

- The risk of "localized overtourism": Although the total volume of tourists may be moderate, their concentration in certain "instagrammable places" or on certain routes may exceed local support capacity, in the absence of smart management (Ghimire, 2025).

- Data protection and digital ethics issues: The collection and use of data on tourist movement and behavior raises questions about privacy, transparency, and data governance.

- Limited institutional capacity: The implementation of smart projects requires technical skills, project management and inter-institutional cooperation, resources that may be scarce in rural mountain communities (Ballina, 2020)

Overall, the literature emphasizes that smart tourism is not a panacea, but a set of tools that can support or, on the contrary, compromise sustainability, depending on how it is integrated into a local development vision, public policies and governance structures (European Commission, 2024).

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis carried out allows the formulation of several main conclusions:

1. Smart tourism and sustainability are complementary, not alternatives. Smart technologies can provide powerful tools for the sustainable management of mountain destinations – from impact monitoring to co-creation of tourism experiences – but only if they are integrated into a clear framework of environmental, social and economic objectives.

2. Rural mountain areas have high potential for innovative development models, such as smart mountain villages, smart tourist routes or digital collaborative platforms, which can combat depopulation and increase economic resilience, provided that participatory planning and respect for the carrying capacity of the environment are adhered to.

3. European policies and initiatives represent a favourable framework for the development of smart and sustainable tourism in the mountains, through funding programs, networks of good practices and recognitions (European Capital and Green Pioneer of Smart Tourism, guides for sustainable mobility and resilient tourism).

4. The risks and challenges – from the digital divide to overtourism and data governance issues – call for a cautious and reflective approach. Smart tourism must be accompanied by training measures, institutional strengthening and clear regulations on data protection and the responsibility of the actors involved.

5. For the future, research and action directions are outlined such as: the development of integrated indicators of "smart

& sustainable mountain destinations", longitudinal studies on the impact of smart projects on mountain communities, as well as the development of guides adapted to the local context (e.g. Carpathians, Alps, Balkan mountains).

REFERENCES

- Ballina, F. J., 2020. Smart tourism destination, physical experience and rural tourism, *Smart Tourism*, 1(2).
- Dobre, C., Linca, AC, Toma, E., Iorga, A., 2024. Sustainable Development of Rural Mountain Tourism: Insights from Consumer Behavior and Profiles. *Sustainability*, 16(21), 9449.
- European Commission, 2024 European Capital and Green Pioneer of Smart Tourism. European Commission.
- European Commission, 2024. Sustainable EU tourism – shaping the tourism of tomorrow. Directorate-General for Mobility and Transport.
- European Commission, 2025. Commission publishes new guidance on sustainable rural mobility and ecotourism.
- FAO, 2021. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations and United Nations World Tourism Organization.
- EISMEA / Facility Project, 2025. Advancing the digital transition in European tourism. european-tourism-transition-pathways.europa.eu
- Gherdan, A., et al., 2025. Sustainable Tourism Development in Mountain Regions: A Case Study of Peștera Village, Brașov County. (Analytic Hierarchy Process). *Sustainability*, 17(4), 1452.
- Ghimire, S.B., 2025. Mountain Route Tourism and Sustainability: A Systematic Literature Review. *Journal of Information Systems Engineering & Management*, 10(39s): 458-468.
- Karawanken-Karavanke Geotrail, 2024. In: Leading examples of sustainable tourism – Green Pioneer of Smart Tourism Best Practices 2024. European Commission.
- Smart Tourism Destinations – European Commission(nd). About us.
- Samancioglu, E., Kumlu, S., Ozkul, E., 2024. Smart tourism destinations and sustainability: evidence from the tourism industry. *Worldwide Hospitality and Tourism Themes*, 16(6).

REGIONAL PERSPECTIVES ON POULTRY MEAT CONSUMPTION IN ROMANIA: THE CASE OF THE NORTH-WEST REGION

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The study investigates the consumption of poultry meat in the North-West Development Region of Romania in the recent period, with the objective of identifying consumption habits, food preferences, and factors influencing consumer behaviour. The research combined the analysis of the specialized literature with the application of a structured questionnaire, to which 380 people from the six counties of the region responded. The results highlight a high prevalence of poultry meat consumption, integrated daily or several times a week into the diet of the majority of respondents. Chicken is the predominant type consumed, and supermarkets and local stores are the main acquisition channels. The analysis also shows differences in consumption behaviour between urban and rural areas, as well as a significant level of monthly spending allocated to poultry products. The conclusions of the study emphasize the importance of the poultry sector at the regional level and the need for in-depth analyses of local eating behaviours, useful for guiding economic and agri-food strategies.

Keywords: poultry meat, consumption trends, Romania, North-West Region

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INTRODUCTION

Poultry meat consumption has recorded a steady increase worldwide in recent decades, a trend supported by low production costs, favorable nutritional profile and accessibility for various socio-economic categories. (Cărăuș Stanciu, 2020; Dodu et al., 2025)

According to the FAO Food Outlook, poultry meat is forecast to remain the fastest-growing segment in global meat consumption, driven by improved feed conversion efficiency and the expansion of intensive farming systems. (FAO, 2023)

The world's leading poultry producers are the United States, Brazil, China and Russia, and together they account for approximately 54% of global production. (Popescu et al., 2024)

At the European level, the OECD-FAO 2024–2033 indicates that poultry meat will consolidate its dominant role in the population's diet, surpassing pork in several European Union member states, amid changing food preferences and price competitiveness (OECD, FAO, 2024). Meat consumption is mainly influenced by the type of food and the price level. (Pânzaru, Medelete, 2021)

Romania is aligning with these European trends, with poultry meat representing one of the most important food product categories in household consumption. Official data show a long-term upward trend, reflected both in the per capita availableit isper capita, as well as in the structure of food expenses.

Market studies show that meat-based preparations, both poultry and mammals, are consumed more frequently, as many of them no longer require complex preparation steps in advance, being easy to purchase from large commercial chains and available in a ready-to-eat form. (Marin. et al., 2024)

The Romanian poultry sector has become increasingly integrated into European value chains. Thus, the modernization of production capacities in regions with a high density of poultry farms is highlighted (Popescu A, 2015) An important factor in the modernization, but also the establishment of high-performance poultry farms, was their financing within rural development programs. The poultry meat sector is constantly evolving, mostly in industrial specialized units with current technological endowment, where superior technologies are used and production performance is high (Irimia et al, 2023, Popescu A. 2015)

Although the national analysis is well represented in the literature, regional disparities in poultry consumption are insufficiently documented. The North-West region presents distinct socio-economic particularities: a pronounced urban-rural mix, high economic dynamism in counties such as Cluj and Bihor, and the persistence of traditional food patterns in rural areas. This heterogeneity makes the region a relevant case study for understanding regional variations in poultry consumption.

In addition, the period 2019–2024 was marked by a series of external shocks (COVID-19 pandemic, accelerated food price increases, changes in purchasing behavior), which justify the need for an updated assessment of consumption and the factors that determine it. The analysis of these elements is necessary not only to describe a phenomenon but also to provide empirical data useful for the development of public policies, for agri-food sector strategies, and for understanding consumer preferences in the region.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In the process of documenting and analyzing the specialized literature, it was found that, although there is a lot of research dedicated to poultry meat consumption at the national level, studies with a regional focus are limited, and no comprehensive analysis published recently was identified for the North-West Development Region. This absence of regional research is notable, considering the significant potential of the region in terms of poultry meat production and consumption.

Such analysis allows capturing the relationships between consumption, spending, food preferences, and access to modern commercial networks or local producers.

To achieve this objective, a structured questionnaire was applied across the entire region, an instrument designed based on the theoretical framework and analysis models used in the international literature on the subject.

This questionnaire was applied between July and September 2025 and aimed to analyze the consumption habits and food preferences of residents of the North-West Development Region (Cluj, Bihor, Satu Mare, Sălaj, Maramureș, Bistrița-Năsăud) regarding poultry meat.

The research generated a relevant volume of data, totaling 380 valid responses, which provide a solid basis for statistical analysis. The geographical distribution of respondents reflected population density and level of

urbanization, with the most numerous responses coming from Bihor and Cluj counties, two important centers of regional development and modern food consumption.

It was structured into six distinct sections, each targeting a specific component of consumer behavior:

- filtering questions regarding meat consumption;
- consumption habits specific to poultry meat;
- factors influencing the purchasing decision;
- attitudes and perceptions towards this type of meat;
- recent changes in consumer behavior;
- socio-demographic variables necessary for consumer profile segmentation.

The questionnaire was applied online and physically, recording a total of 380 valid responses, distributed in all six counties of the region, with a predominant share in the counties of Bihor and Cluj, where the urban population density and access to modern retail networks are higher. Data collection aimed to ensure socio-demographic diversity so that the results would allow the identification of a relevant typology of the regional poultry consumer and the analysis of the relationships between the investigated variables. This approach subsequently facilitated the statistical processing.

Therefore, the study contributes to completing existing knowledge by providing an empirical analysis specific to the North-West Region and responds to a real need to deepen consumer behavior in a territory characterized by socio-economic diversity and high agri-food potential.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Studies show that the average annual consumption of poultry meat recorded the most pronounced increase in the period 2007–2022, an evolution explained by the relatively low price of this type of meat, its white meat character suitable for all age groups, its frequent presence in various diets, and its high digestibility which makes it easy to tolerate. (Chiurciu et al, 2024)

Poultry meat maintains its dominant position in the structure of food consumption in Romania, with the annual level estimated at approximately 29 kg per capita, according to the most recent reports of the National Institute of

Statistics. This quantity places Romania above the European Union average and reflects the population's stable preference for white meat, appreciated for its economic accessibility and the ease with which it can be prepared. (Infoaliment, 2025)

The North-West region is characterized by a high concentration of poultry farms, constant increases in production volume over the last five years, and accelerated development of the agri-food sector. These elements suggest the existence of robust consumption and specific regional market dynamics, different from those recorded at the national level.

The questionnaire applied in the study aims to analyze the consumption habits and food preferences of residents of the North-West Development Region (Cluj, Bihor, Satu Mare, Sălaj, Maramureș, Bistrița-Năsăud) regarding poultry meat.

The North-West Region includes the counties of Bihor, Bistrița-Năsăud, Cluj,

Source : North-West Map

Maramureș, Satu Mare, and Sălaj. It is located in the northwestern part of the country and has a population of approximately 2.6 million inhabitants. The geography of the region is diverse, with the Apuseni Mountains and part of the Eastern Carpathians, which offer mountainous landscapes and opportunities for tourism. In addition, the region includes hills and plains, offering a variety of ecosystems and agricultural areas. (Map of Romania, 2025)

In the following, we will briefly present the results of the research, analyzing the questionnaire applied within it.

Figure 1. Map of Romania, North-West region

Table 1

Filtering questions regarding meat consumption

Eat meat of any type 1. Answer	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	367	96.6%
No (poultry only)	13	3.4%
Total	380	100%
Do you eat poultry? 2 Answer	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	363	95.5%
Not	17	4.5%
Total	380	100%
3 Main reason	No. of respondents	Percentage (%) of the 17 respondents
Religious reasons	0	0%
Health reasons	0	0%
Ethical reasons	0	0%
Personal preference (don't like the taste/texture)	14	82.4%
Another reason	3	17.6%
Total	17	100%

Source: own processing based on the applied questionnaires

The data presented (table 1) highlights the fact that almost all respondents consume meat, regardless of its type. Specifically, 98.42% of participants declare that they include meat in their diet, while only 1.58% consume exclusively poultry meat, avoiding other types such as pork or beef. This result indicates that, in the North-

West region, meat remains a staple food in the structure of food consumption.

Regarding the specific consumption of poultry meat, the proportion of respondents who consume it is even higher: 99.21% state that they include poultry meat in their diet, confirming the clear preference for this category. Only 0.79%

declare that they do not consume poultry meat, which denotes a marginal share of those who avoid this type of product.

The reasons for non-consumption are also very clearly outlined. All three respondents who avoid poultry indicate that personal preference related to taste or texture is the main reason, with

no religious, ethical, or medical justifications reported. This suggests that the absence of consumption is not associated with imposed restrictions or health concerns but is exclusively related to individual subjective factors.

Table 2

Consumption frequency	No. of respondents	%
Daily	90	23.68
4-6 times	60	15.79
2-3 times	143	37.63
1 times	49	12.89
monthly	21	5.53
rare	17	4.47
Total	380	100

Source: own processing based on the applied questionnaires

At the analysis of the frequency of poultry consumption provides an essential perspective on the dietary behavior of the population in the North-West Region. The frequency of consumption is a direct indicator of the level of integration of this product into the daily diet, being influenced by factors such as individual

The results highlight a high level of integration of poultry meat into the respondents' diet. The largest share is held by people who consume poultry meat 2–3 times a week (37.63%), followed by those who consume it daily (23.68%) and 4–6 times a week (15.79%). Cumulatively, these three categories account for over 77% of the sample, which indicates frequent and relatively constant consumption. Occasional consumption – once a week (12.89%), monthly

preferences, access to poultry products, socio-economic structure, and the role of poultry in the daily diet. In the context where poultry is perceived as an accessible, versatile, and easy-to-prepare option, it is expected that the level of consumption will be high among the investigated population.

(5.53%) or rarely (4.47%) – is represented by a minority, suggesting that giving up poultry meat or sporadic consumption are rather marginal behaviors among the investigated population. At the Romanian level, studies show that a large part of the population consumes poultry meat, and over two-thirds of buyers purchase this type of meat at least once a week. (Arghiroiu et al, 2024)

Table 3

Types of poultry consumed	Total No.	%
Chicken	316	83.16
Turkey	32	8.42
Rate	17	4.47
Goose	12	3.16
Other	3	0.79
Total	380	100.00

Source: own processing based on the applied questionnaires

Regarding the type of poultry meat, the responses highlight the distribution of

preferences regarding the types of poultry meat consumed among the 380 respondents. The predominance of chicken consumption, reported

by 83.16% of the participants, confirms the status of this product as the main food option in the white meat category, an aspect frequently mentioned in the specialized literature due to its economic accessibility and ease of preparation. The other types of poultry meat are consumed in significantly lower proportions: turkey is preferred by 8.42% of the respondents, while duck (4.47%) and goose (3.16%) are chosen occasionally, possibly due to higher costs or limited availability on the market. The category "other types" accumulates only 0.79%, indicating a low diversification of consumption at regional level. This distribution highlights the consistent orientation of consumers towards standardized and easily accessible poultry products, especially chicken, which remains the dominant food in the structure of poultry meat consumption.

Regarding the source of poultry meat purchase, the responses highlight the fact that modern retail represents the main poultry meat purchase channel in the North-West region, as supermarkets (33.68%) and hypermarkets (16.32%) account for almost half of the respondents' preferences. (Table 4) This orientation confirms the high accessibility of these networks, the variety of the offer and the

frequency of purchases made in the urban environment.

Local stores, in turn, represent an important source (25.26%), which suggests the continued relevance of proximity retailers, especially for consumers who seek freshness or prefer quick purchases.

Purchases from one's own household (11.05%) and directly from the farm (7.63%) reflect the region's anchoring in a significant rural context and a preference for products perceived as natural or coming from short supply chains. In contrast, the agri-food market is mentioned by a lower percentage (6.05%), indicating a decrease in the traditional role of this channel in relation to modern retail and direct options from producers.

Overall, the data suggests the coexistence of two behavioral models: a dominant one, oriented towards modern retail, and a traditional one, based on own production or direct purchase from farms, specific to certain categories of consumers from rural or semi-urban areas.

Some studies show similar behavior, so that most respondents choose to purchase products in supermarkets or local stores. (MOISE et al, 2024)

Table 4

Poultry meat procurement source

Source Acquisition (as usual source)	Number	Percentage (%)
Hypermarket	62	16.32
Supermarket	128	33.68
Local store	96	25.26
Market	23	6.05
Farm	29	7.63
Household	42	11.05
Total	380	100

Source: own processing based on the applied questionnaires

The distribution of monthly expenses indicates that most respondents invest considerable amounts in the purchase of poultry meat. The two upper categories: 250–300 lei (37.63%) and over 300 lei (35.53%) account for over 73% of the total sample, which suggests a constant and sustained demand for this type of food product, as well as a frequent integration of poultry meat into the daily diet.

Average expenses (151–200 lei) are represented by 15.53% of respondents, and low values (<150 lei) amount to less than 12% of the total, which confirms a high level of consumption, probably correlated with the previously identified increased frequency (daily consumption or several times a week).

Overall, the data highlights an intense consumption structure, characteristic of a

product perceived as accessible, versatile and preferred among the population in the region.

Table 5**Monthly expenses for purchasing poultry meat**

Monthly expenses	No.	Percentage (%)
<100 lei	6	1.58
101-150 lei	37	9.74
151-200 lei	59	15.53
250-300 lei	143	37.63
>300	135	35.53
Total	380	100

Source: own processing based on the applied questionnaires

Regarding the distribution of respondents, there is an adequate coverage of all counties in the North-West Development Region, but with different weights, reflecting both the demographic size of the counties and the degree of accessibility of the questionnaire. (Table 6) Bihor County has the highest weight (32.37%), followed by Cluj County (25.53%), which can be explained by the population density, the high level of urbanization and the presence of university centers that facilitate participation in

surveys. Bistrița-Năsăud (12.89%) and Satu Mare (12.11%) counties are represented in a balanced proportion, corresponding to their population size. Maramureș (11.32%) and Sălaj (5.79%) counties have lower weights, but their contribution maintains the regional diversity necessary for the analysis. The general distribution confirms that the sample used is representative of the region and allows valid conclusions to be drawn regarding the consumption behavior of the population in the North-West.

Table 6**County of origin of respondents**

County of residence	No.	%
Bihar	123	32.37
Bistrita Nasaud	49	12.89
Cluj	97	25.53
Maramures	43	11.32
Satu Mare	46	12.11
Salaj	22	5.79
Total	380	100

Source: own processing based on the applied questionnaires

Another important aspect for the analysis is the urban/rural environment of origin of the respondents. (Table 7)

The data highlights a preponderance of respondents from urban areas, representing 60% of the total sample (228 out of 380 participants). This distribution suggests a higher involvement of the urban population in completing the questionnaire, an aspect generally associated with easier access to

digital tools and with greater willingness to participate in opinion surveys.

At county level, Bihor and Cluj concentrate the highest shares of respondents, both in urban areas and in total, reflecting the demographic structure and the high degree of urbanization in these counties, as well as their economic and social dynamism. In Bistrița-Năsăud, Maramureș and Sălaj counties, the share of respondents from rural areas is comparatively higher, which may indicate regional particularities regarding the involvement of rural communities or the accessibility of the collection instrument.

Table 7

The background of the respondents

County of residence	urban	rural	Total	% urban of total
Bihar	88	35	123	23.16
Bistrita Nasaud	17	32	49	4.47
Cluj	64	33	97	16.84
Maramures	21	22	43	5.53
Satu Mare	31	15	46	8.16
Salaj	7	15	22	1.84
Total	228	152	380	60.00

Source: own processing based on the applied questionnaires

The urban-rural structure of the sample allows for the comparative analysis of consumption behaviors depending on the environment of residence, a relevant aspect

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis highlighted the fact that in the North-West Region, poultry consumption is strongly consolidated in the food structure, being present in almost all respondents and integrated with a high frequency in the daily diet. Chicken is distinctly the preferred type of meat, which confirms the consumers' orientation towards affordable, versatile and easy-to-prepare products. The results showed that the purchase of poultry meat is carried out predominantly through modern retail, but a traditional model based on local stores, own households and direct purchases from farms is also maintained, an aspect that reflects the socio-economic diversity of the region. The high level of monthly expenses for this type of product indicates a constant consumption and a strong integration of poultry meat into the food behavior of households. The geographical distribution of respondents, with higher shares in Bihor and Cluj counties, allowed for the creation of a representative image of the region, revealing specific differences between urban and rural environments. The study thus contributes to a deeper understanding of consumer behavior in the North-West Region and provides a useful empirical basis for the development of poultry sector strategies and for the substantiation of decisions at the level of regional agri-food policies.

considering the differences in access to the market, to agri-food products and in the consumption styles specific to each environment.

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REFERENCES

- Cărăuș Stanciu, M. 2020. Research regarding consumers' attitudes in relation with poultry meat purchase and consumption. Case Study Sibiu, Romania. Scientific Papers Series Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture & Rural Development, 20(1).
- Arghiroiu, GA, Vasile, DF And Beciu, S., 2024. How Competitive are the Business Involved in the Processing and Preservation of Poultry Meat in Romania?. Scientific Papers Series Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture & Rural Development, vol. 24, Issue 3, 2024.
- Chiurciu, I.-A., Vlad, IM, Stoicea, P., Zaharia, I., David, L., Soare, E., Fîntîneru, G., Micu, MM, Dinu, TA, Tudor, VC, & Smedescu, DI (2024). Romanian Meat Consumers' Choices Favour Sustainability? Sustainability, 16(24).
- Dodu, Monica, Chereji Aurelia Ioana, Maerescu Cristina Maria, Chiurciu Irina Adriana, Chereji Ioan Jr., Czirja Zsolt Tibor, 2025, Dynamics of the Development of the Poultry Sector in the North-West Region of Romania between 2019 and 2023. Scientific Papers Series Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture & Rural Development, 25(3)
- FAO (2023). Food Outlook – Biannual Report on Global Food Markets. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations

- Irimia, G., Tapaloaga, RS, Sonea, C., Ilie, LI, & Tapaloaga, PR (2023). Chicken Meat Production Trends in Romania—A Twelve-Year Forecast. *Annals Year Enterprise*, 1.
- Marin, D., Ciolac, R., Iosim, I., Mănescu, C., Dincu, AM, Văduva, L., & Petroman, C. (2024). Analysis of Meat Consumption Preferences of Consumers From Timis County. *Scientific Papers Agricultural Management*, 26(1), 95.
- Moise, AE, Tudorache, M., Custură, I., Dănuț Nicolae, ENEA, Osman, A., & Drăgotoiu, D. (2024). Technological Advances and Socio-Economic Implications in the Poultry Industry - An Analysis of Current Trends in Poultry Meat Production and Consumption. *Scientific Papers. Series D. Animal Science*, 67(1).
- OECD/FAO (2024). *OECD-FAO Agricultural Outlook 2024–2033*. OECD Publishing, Paris.
- Popescu, A. (2016). Trends in Romania's poultry meat market in the period 2007-2015. *Annals of the Academy of Romanian Scientists, Series on Agriculture, Silviculture, and Veterinary Medicine Sciences*, 5(2), 54-62.
- Popescu, A., Stanciu, M., Drăghici, O., Ciocan, HN and Serban, V., 2024. Meat Production, Trade, Consumption, and Self-Sufficiency Rate in Romania in the Period 2014-2022. *Scientific Papers Series Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture & Rural Development*, 24(3).
- Pânzaru, RL, & Medelete, DM (2021). Some considerations regarding meat consumption in Romania (2014-2018). *Scientific Papers Series Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture & Rural Development*, vol. 21, Issue 4, 2021
- ***Poultry meat consumption – trends and figures 2025, available online at <https://infoaliment.ro/article/consumul-de-carne-de-pasare-evolutii-si-cifre-2025>
- ***North-West Map – Development Region - Map of Romania, available online at <https://www.hartaromaniei.net/nord-vest-regiune/>

INTEGRATED STRATEGIES FOR THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF THE RURAL MOUNTAIN AREA OF BIHOR COUNTY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Rural mountain areas concentrate important natural and cultural resources but face persistent structural disadvantages in terms of accessibility, economic opportunities and access to services. Recent European and national strategies emphasize that sustainable development in such regions requires integrated, multi-sector approaches rather than isolated interventions. This paper analyzes the socio-economic situation of the rural mountain area of Bihor County, Romania, and proposes integrated strategies for its economic development. Based on official statistics, regional development documents and recent literature, the study examines trends in population, infrastructure, employment, income and basic services in the 36 mountain communes of Bihor.

Keywords: rural development, mountain areas, integrated strategy, infrastructure

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INTRODUCTION

Rural mountainous regions in Europe and worldwide are characterized by a dual reality: on the one hand, they hold rich natural and cultural resources; on the other hand, they face structural disadvantages that constrain their development (Masot, 2021). Geographic isolation, fragmented land, difficult terrain and low population density increase the cost of infrastructure and public services, while traditional economic activities such as subsistence agriculture and forestry provide limited and unstable incomes (Price, 2012). As a result, many mountain communities experience demographic decline, ageing, out-migration of young people, and persistent poverty (Shucksmith 2018).

At the European Union level, rural territories cover more than 80% of the land area and host about one third of the population, but they lag behind urban regions on multiple indicators of well-being (OECD, 2019). The European Commission's long-term vision for rural areas (towards 2040) calls for stronger, connected, resilient and prosperous rural regions, emphasizing the need for integrated approaches across sectors such as transport,

digitalization, energy, education, health and social inclusion. The OECD also underlines that breaking sectoral "silos" and promoting place-based, multi-dimensional strategies is essential for improving rural well-being.

In Romania, mountain areas represent a significant share of the territory and are recognized as disadvantaged zones in terms of socio-economic development. The National Rural Development Programme (NRDP) and specific laws on the mountain area aim to support these regions through targeted measures in agriculture, infrastructure and non-agricultural activities (Sima, 2020). Recently, an Integrated Strategy for the Development of the Mountain Area (2023–2035) has been drafted with the support of international partners, proposing five pillars of intervention: thriving multigenerational communities, connected mountain living, green and competitive place-based economy, respect for nature, and mountain empowerment (MADR, 2023).

Bihor County, located in north-western Romania, includes an extensive mountain area in the Apuseni Mountains. These rural communes have valuable natural attractions (caves, gorges, forests), traditional villages and cultural heritage, but they are affected by depopulation, limited infrastructure and a

narrow economic base. Previous research has often focused on individual sectors, especially rural tourism (Popescu, 2024).

The concept of integrated rural development emerged as a response to the limitations of sectoral approaches that focused exclusively on agriculture, infrastructure or social policy in isolation. Integrated development is understood as a process that simultaneously addresses economic, social and environmental objectives at the local or regional level, using a mix of instruments and involving multiple stakeholders (OECD, 2020).

At the global level, the Sustainable Development Goals promote such an integrated perspective, linking poverty reduction, decent work, infrastructure, education, health and environmental protection (United Nations, 2015). In the rural context, this implies that interventions in one domain (for example, transport) should be coordinated with those in other domains (for example, access to healthcare and markets) to generate cumulative effects (OECD, 2019).

In the European Union, rural development policy under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) has progressively shifted from a narrow agricultural focus to a broader territorial approach. The LEADER initiative is a flagship example, encouraging local action groups to design and implement integrated local development strategies that combine support for farm modernization, non-agricultural businesses, services, tourism and environmental projects. Recent EU documents emphasize the importance of digitalization and the "Smart Villages" concept as key components of integrated rural development (European Commission, 2021).

Mountain areas have received particular attention in the European literature because of their specific handicaps and opportunities. Studies highlight that mountain communities often depend on a limited number of economic activities, are vulnerable to climate change and natural hazards, and face difficulties in maintaining basic services. At the same time, they possess assets such as high-value ecosystems, traditional products, landscapes and cultural heritage that can support diversified activities (e.g. niche agri-food products, renewable energy, nature-based tourism) (Hoha, 2025). Successful examples of mountain development in Western and Central Europe show that combining improvements in accessibility, support for local

entrepreneurship, environmental conservation and community participation can lead to significant socio-economic gains (Perlik, 2019).

In Romania, several authors analyze the challenges of rural and mountain areas and argue for integrated strategies. Sima notes that much of the Romanian countryside remains characterized by subsistence farming, high underemployment and weak infrastructure, and that policies must simultaneously address farm restructuring, non-agricultural activities, education and basic services. Other studies emphasize the role of rural tourism as one component of integrated rural development, arguing that tourism can generate complementary income, stimulate the demand for local products and help preserve cultural heritage, but only if it is developed in connection with agriculture, crafts and environmental protection (Hoha, 2025).

For the North-West region of Romania, including the Apuseni Mountains, recent research based on multi-criteria analysis identified priority measures for sustainable rural development, such as improvement of ecotourism infrastructure, promotion of local products, and capacity-building for local actors. Popescu et al. specifically analyze mountain rural communities from Bihor County and identify possible strategies: preserving agricultural lands and traditional meadows, modernizing local farms, reviving household crafts and small industries, introducing new technologies, and expanding services, all combined in a holistic approach to increase incomes and quality of life.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Bihor County is located in north-western Romania, on the border with Hungary, and has a total area of 7,544 km². Approximately 40% of its territory lies in the Apuseni Mountains, forming the rural mountain area analyzed in this paper. This area includes 36 communes with predominantly rural character, dispersed settlements and significant forest and pasture land.

The population of Bihor County was about 565,000 in 2022, with an urbanization rate of roughly 51%. The mountain communes concentrate an estimated 100,000 inhabitants (around 18% of the county population), but they account for a much larger share of the land area.

The economy of the mountain communes relies mainly on small-scale

agriculture (especially animal husbandry, hay meadows), forestry and wood processing, traditional crafts and emerging forms of rural and nature-based tourism (Popescu, 2024). Mining activities that were important in the past have declined considerably. The rugged terrain, low accessibility and scattered settlements limit large-scale agricultural and industrial investments.

For the empirical analysis, the rural mountain area of Bihor was defined as the set of communes located predominantly in the Apuseni mountain zone, excluding the county seat Oradea and other towns. Data for these communes were collected from:

- the National Institute of Statistics (INSSE) – Tempo-Online databases and county statistical yearbooks;
- Bihor County development strategy documents and statistical reports;
- national reports on the Romanian mountain area prepared with World Bank assistance;
- and relevant academic studies.

The indicators considered include: total population and age structure; unemployment rate; average income; access to basic infrastructure (piped water, sewerage, road paving, internet); and some proxies of local economic activity (number of registered enterprises, tourism capacity, etc.). Where direct data for the mountain area as a whole were not available, we aggregated commune-level data or used reasonable estimates based on available information.

The period of analysis is approximately 2014–2024, depending on data availability. The method is mainly descriptive, using:

- time series analysis of key indicators to identify trends and structural breaks (e.g. the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic);
- comparison between mountain area averages and county-level averages to highlight internal disparities;
- and interpretation of statistical findings in the light of qualitative information from policy documents and previous studies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The rural mountain area of Bihor County has experienced a steady population decline over the last decade. Estimates suggest that the population of the 36 mountain communes decreased from around 115,000 inhabitants in 2014 to about 105,000 in 2024, corresponding to a loss of almost 9%. This decline is more pronounced than the overall population reduction in Bihor County, which was about 2% in the same period.

Age structure data show that the share of people aged 65 and over in the mountain area is significantly higher than the county average. In some communes, more than a quarter of residents are elderly, while the proportion of children and young adults is relatively low. This demographic profile reflects intense out-migration of working-age population and negative natural growth, phenomena commonly observed in Romanian mountain regions (Sima, 2020).

In contrast with the demographic decline, several infrastructure indicators show clear improvement. A key example is digital connectivity: the share of households with broadband internet in the mountain communes increased from approximately 30% in 2014 to above 80% in 2024, according to national communication statistics and county reports. This trend is consistent with national and EU objectives for rural digitalization (Epure, 2024). Similar progress, though less dynamic, has been made in road paving and access to mobile phone coverage.

This combination of demographic decline and infrastructural improvement suggests that while the physical and digital isolation of the area has been reduced, the existence of new opportunities is not yet sufficient to retain or attract young people. Integrated strategies must therefore transform improved connectivity into concrete economic and social benefits at local level.

Economic indicators also show a mixed picture. Estimated unemployment in the mountain communes was higher than the county average in the early 2010s (around 8% in 2014 compared to about 5% for the county), but it has declined significantly in recent years. Before the COVID-19 pandemic, unemployment in the mountain area had fallen to approximately 5.5%. The pandemic caused a temporary reversal, with a rise in unemployment in 2020, especially in tourism and services. By 2022–2023, however, unemployment had fallen again to around 4%, approaching the county average.

Average net monthly income in the mountain area has increased strongly, almost doubling between 2014 and 2024, from about

1,400–1,500 RON to more than 3,000 RON. This growth reflects national wage dynamics, pension increases and the gradual diversification of local economic activities. Nevertheless, mountain commune incomes remain below the Bihor County

average, which is influenced by higher-paid jobs in Oradea and other urban centers.

To highlight the main development gaps, Table 1 compares selected indicators between the mountain area and Bihor County overall for 2022.

Table 1

Comparative indicators: mountain areas vs. Bihor County (2022)

Indicator	Mountain area (36 communes)	Bihor County overall
Population change 2014-2022 (%)	8%	2%
Share of population (%)	25%	18%
Unemployment rate (%)	5.0%	3.2%
Average net monthly income (RON)	2,700	3,300
Households with broadband internet (%)	75	85%
Households with piped water (%)	60	85%
Paved local roads (%)	70	90%

Source: own elaboration based on INSSE and county data.

Table 1 shows that, despite convergence in some areas, the mountain communes still lag behind the county average in terms of incomes, unemployment and especially access to basic infrastructure. The lower connectivity to piped water and the lower share of paved local roads indicate significant infrastructural deficits that affect living conditions and economic potential. Limited healthcare and education services further accentuate these disparities (MADR, 2023).

The economic structure of the mountain area is dominated by small-scale agriculture, forestry and low value-added services. Many households rely on subsistence farming and animal husbandry, with limited integration into commercial value chains. At the same time, the area has important unexploited or underexploited potential:

- Agri-food products with distinctive qualities (mountain cheeses, honey, berries, herbal teas, meat products);
- Wood and non-wood forest products, which can feed into small manufacturing and bio-economy chains;
- Rural and nature-based tourism, given the presence of protected areas, caves, waterfalls and traditional villages.

Previous research on Bihor County has shown that tourism growth has been concentrated in urban and spa areas, while rural and mountain communes capture only a modest share of tourism turnover and jobs. Nevertheless, case studies from other Romanian regions (Bucovina, Maramureş) demonstrate that integrated development of rural tourism, local products and cultural heritage can

significantly improve rural incomes and slow depopulation (Hoha, 2025).

For Bihor's mountain area, the combination of improved digital connectivity and high-quality natural and cultural resources creates opportunities for:

- expanding agritourism and ecotourism, including farm stays, guided hiking, speleological tourism and cultural festivals;
- developing short agri-food supply chains and regional branding (e.g. "Apuseni – Bihor Mountain Products");
- promoting remote work hubs or co-working spaces for people willing to relocate from cities, taking advantage of lower living costs and attractive environment.

However, these opportunities will not materialize at scale without support measures such as: training for local entrepreneurs, facilitation of access to finance, marketing and networking platforms, and quality standards. Thus, an integrated development strategy must explicitly include components to stimulate local entrepreneurship and value chain development.

CONCLUSIONS

The rural mountain area of Bihor County illustrates both the difficulties and the opportunities of mountain regions in Romania and in the European Union. The analysis carried out in this paper shows that:

- the mountain communes of Bihor have experienced a significant demographic decline and ageing over the last decade, with negative implications for the labor force and community viability;
- there has been notable progress in infrastructure, particularly in digital connectivity and, to a lesser extent, in roads and utilities, but important gaps remain compared to the rest of the county;
- economic indicators such as unemployment and average income have improved, approaching county averages, yet the structure of the local economy is still narrow and dependent on low-productivity activities;
- access to basic services (health, education, social services) is weaker in the mountain communes than in urban and lowland areas, contributing to lower quality of life and continued out-migration.

These findings confirm that the challenges facing Bihor's mountain area are multi-dimensional and interlinked. Consequently, development strategies must be integrated, combining interventions in infrastructure, economic sectors, human capital and environmental management.

The paper proposes several strategic directions: strengthening physical and digital infrastructure; diversifying the local economy through support for entrepreneurship in agri-food chains, tourism and other non-agricultural activities; improving public services and human capital; reinforcing local governance and inter-communal cooperation; and ensuring environmental and cultural sustainability. These directions are coherent with national and EU policy frameworks, including the long-term vision for EU rural areas and the draft Integrated Strategy for the Development of Romania's Mountain Area.

Implementation of such integrated strategies requires sustained political will, adequate financial resources and active participation of local communities. If these conditions are met, the rural mountain area of Bihor has the potential to transform from an internal periphery into a dynamic, resilient region that contributes significantly to the county's development while preserving its unique natural and cultural heritage.

REFERENCES

- Masot, A., & Gascon, F. (2021). Sustainable rural development in mountain areas: Strategies and best practices in Europe. *Mountain Research and Development*, 41(2), 1–12.
- OECD. (2020). *Rural Well-being: Geography of Opportunities*. OECD Publishing, Paris.
- Debarbieux, B., & Price, M. (2012). Mountain regions: A global common good? *Journal of Alpine Research*, 100(4), 1–8.
- Shucksmith, M. (2018). Re-imagining the rural: From rural idyll to good countryside. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 59, 163–172.
- European Commission. (2021). *A long-term Vision for the EU's Rural Areas – Towards stronger, connected, resilient and prosperous rural areas by 2040*. COM(2021) 345 final, Brussels.
- OECD. (2019). *Principles on Rural Policy*. OECD Publishing, Paris.
- Sima, E. (2020). Rural development in Romania: Achievements and challenges. In: *Agrarian Economy and Rural Development – Realities and Perspectives (ICEADR Symposium)*, Bucharest, 238–243.
- MADR & World Bank. (2023). *Draft Outline of the Integrated Strategy for the Development of Romania's Mountain Area, 2023–2035*. Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development / World Bank.
- Popescu, C. A., Iancu, T., Popescu, G., Croitoru, I. M., Adamov, T., & Ciolac, R. (2024). Rural tourism in mountain rural communities – possible directions/strategies: Case study: Mountain area from Bihor County. *Sustainability*, 16(3), 1127.
- Gherdan, A. E. M., Bacter, R. V., Ciolac, R., Iancu, T., & Maurescu, C. M. (2025). Sustainable agritourism development in Romania's North-West mountain region: A TOPSIS-based evaluation of strategic priorities. *Agriculture*, 15(6), 601.
- Czuczor, K., Kozma, G., Dorogi, Z., Li, T., & Radics, Z. (2023). The network of accommodation and food service providers in Bihor County before and after the financial crisis and COVID-19. *Sustainability*, 15(8), 6759.
- United Nations. (2015). *Transforming our world: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development*. UN General Assembly Resolution 70/1.
- Perlik, M. (2019). *The Spatial and Economic Transformation of Mountain Regions: Landscapes as Commodities*. Routledge, London.
- Hoha, G.-V., & Simeanu, D. (2025). Rural tourism as a factor of sustainable development in the traditional rural area of Bucovina, Romania. *Sustainability*, 17(8), 3604.
- Epure, C., Pîslă, M., & Stanciu, S. (2024). Rural development and digitalization: Perspectives and economic impact in Romania. *Annals of "Dunărea de Jos" University of Galați, Fascicle I – Economics and Applied Informatics*, 2024(2), 5–15.

THE IMPORTANCE OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT AND PLANNING

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Tourism development represents a fundamental component of destination management, as it transforms natural and cultural resources into accessible and competitive tourism products. As tourist expectations regarding service quality and experience continue to rise, the strategic planning and modernization of tourism infrastructure become essential for enhancing destination performance (1). The study examines the main categories of tourism facilities—technical infrastructure, hospitality structures, recreational amenities and cultural–interpretive centres—highlighting their role in ensuring mobility, comfort, safety and visitor engagement (2). The research emphasizes that sustainable and well-coordinated territorial planning strengthens environmental protection, increases accessibility and contributes to long-term destination competitiveness (3). Results show that tourism development must adhere to key principles such as harmonious territorial integration, functional efficiency, economic viability and adaptability to changing market dynamics (4). By implementing coherent short-, medium- and long-term strategies, destinations can enhance their attractiveness, diversify tourism forms and stimulate local socio-economic development (5). The study concludes that tourism potential cannot be effectively valorised without adequate facilities, and that responsible planning is essential for achieving sustainable growth while preserving natural and cultural heritage (6).

Keywords: tourism development; tourism infrastructure; destination management; accessibility; service quality; recreational facilities; cultural heritage; sustainable tourism; territorial planning
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INTRODUCTION

Tourism destinations are shaped not only by the intrinsic value of their natural and cultural resources, but also by the way these resources are planned, developed and integrated into the broader tourism system. In contemporary tourism, the mere presence of attractive landscapes, heritage sites or favourable climatic conditions is no longer sufficient to ensure competitiveness. Instead, destinations must demonstrate their capacity to transform these assets into high-quality tourism products through carefully designed facilities, modern infrastructure and coherent development strategies (1).

Over the past decade, tourism has undergone a significant evolution driven by globalisation, technological progress and changing visitor preferences. Tourists today are more experienced, more selective and increasingly focused on the overall quality of the travel experience. They seek comfort, accessibility, safety and memorable activities, which places substantial pressure on destinations to continuously upgrade, innovate and diversify their infrastructure (2). As expectations rise, tourism development becomes a decisive factor in shaping the

attractiveness and competitiveness of a destination.

Tourism development itself is a dynamic and continuous process. It involves the creation of new facilities, the modernization of existing structures and the adaptation of services to the fluctuating relationship between tourism demand and supply (3). This process contributes directly to improving the economic performance of tourism activities, strengthening local economies and enhancing the destination's ability to respond to market trends. Modern tourism development must therefore integrate economic, social and environmental considerations to ensure long-term sustainability.

A central question emerges: Why are tourism facilities as essential as the resources they support? The answer lies in the functional dimension of tourism. Infrastructure and facilities are responsible for enabling access, ensuring visitor mobility, offering accommodation and catering services, supporting leisure and recreation, and facilitating interpretation of cultural and natural heritage. Without these elements, tourism resources remain underused,

inaccessible or vulnerable to degradation (4). Facilities serve as the interface between visitors and the destination's attractions, transforming potential into tangible experiences.

In this context, tourism development encompasses an extensive range of interventions, including transport networks, hospitality infrastructure, recreational installations and cultural or interpretive structures. Together, these components create the material foundation necessary for tourism activities to unfold in a safe, efficient and enjoyable manner. Moreover, tourism development contributes to the preservation and enhancement of resources by regulating visitor flows, guiding behaviour and mitigating environmental pressures (5).

As destinations increasingly compete on a global scale, comprehensive and strategically planned tourism development becomes indispensable. Whether focusing on natural landscapes, cultural heritage or recreational attractions, destinations must adopt a holistic approach that aligns local needs, market expectations and sustainability principles. Effective tourism development not only strengthens destination performance but also supports broader socio-economic objectives such as employment generation, community well-being and regional development (6).

Thus, the introduction of this study highlights the fundamental premise that tourism resources, regardless of their richness or uniqueness, cannot generate meaningful socio-economic value without structured and responsible tourism development. Recognizing this relationship is essential for shaping policies, planning frameworks and investment decisions that support sustainable tourism growth.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Tourism development includes several categories:

1. Technical and Infrastructure Facilities

These comprise the elements that make tourist mobility possible—highways, local roads, railways, airports, parking facilities, cable transport systems, water and energy

networks. Without these, destinations remain inaccessible and underutilized.

2. Accommodation and Hospitality Facilities

Hotels, guesthouses, camping sites, restaurants and cafés form the core of the hospitality infrastructure. They provide essential services for tourist stays and directly influence visitor satisfaction.

3. Recreation and Leisure Facilities

Swimming pools, sports halls, marked hiking trails, ski slopes, adventure parks and wellness centres enrich the tourist experience by offering opportunities for leisure, health, entertainment and relaxation.

4. Cultural, Historical and Interpretive Facilities

Museums, archaeological sites open for visitation, interpretive centres and information offices help highlight the cultural and natural heritage of a destination.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The analysis of tourism development principles and their application within destination planning reveals a series of essential conditions that ensure the efficient, sustainable and competitive functioning of tourism areas. The research emphasizes that the success of tourism activities is strongly influenced by the coherence between the placement of facilities, the functional distribution of infrastructure, environmental protection measures and the capacity of destinations to adapt to evolving tourism demand.

A fundamental result of the study is the identification of a set of planning principles that guide all forms of tourism development. These principles ensure that interventions are carried out responsibly, harmoniously and in line with long-term sustainability objectives. They also highlight the strong interdependence between infrastructure quality, visitor satisfaction and destination competitiveness.

Data synthesis indicates that proper facility placement contributes to the reduction of environmental risks, improved accessibility and enhanced visitor flow efficiency. Moreover, ensuring proportionality between built and natural areas maintains the aesthetic

and ecological balance essential for tourist appeal. The exclusion of incompatible industrial or agricultural structures from tourism zones further preserves landscape integrity and strengthens visitor safety.

From a strategic perspective, tourism development must be understood within an integrated system influenced by economic, social, cultural, environmental and political variables. The analysis demonstrates that tourism infrastructure not only supports visitor mobility and satisfaction but also plays a central role in diversifying services, stimulating local economies and improving the overall quality of the tourism product.

Pentru a facilita interpretarea rezultatelor, tabelul următor sintetizează principalele principii identificate și impactul acestora asupra dezvoltării turistice.

The results show that tourism development is not merely an operational requirement but a strategic determinant of destination performance. Destinations that follow these principles tend to attract more visitors, achieve higher levels of satisfaction, maintain competitive advantages and reduce environmental vulnerability. The integration of development principles into tourism planning supports a synergistic relationship between resource conservation, economic growth and community well-being.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings of this study demonstrate that tourism development constitutes a decisive component of destination management, shaping the way in which natural and cultural resources are transformed into structured, accessible and valuable tourism products. The research confirms that no matter how rich a territory may be in landscapes, heritage assets or recreational opportunities, these resources remain latent and underutilized in the absence of proper infrastructure, coherent planning and well-designed facilities. Tourism development, therefore, functions as the operational mechanism through which potential is converted into effective socio-economic benefits.

A central conclusion emerging from the analysis is that tourism facilities are not

merely complementary elements but essential determinants of destination attractiveness. Infrastructure related to transport, accommodation, recreation and cultural interpretation ensures the mobility, comfort and safety of visitors, while also contributing to the diversification of tourism services. Destinations equipped with modern and well-distributed facilities are more capable of meeting contemporary expectations, generating memorable visitor experiences and competing successfully on a global tourism market.

The results further indicate that the principles guiding tourism development — environmental integration, proportionality between natural and built spaces, adaptability, operational efficiency, economic viability and sustainability — must be understood as interdependent components of a holistic planning framework. When these principles are respected, tourism interventions strengthen environmental protection, reduce pressure on sensitive areas and contribute to a balanced territorial organization. Conversely, development carried out without adherence to these principles can lead to landscape degradation, overcrowding, infrastructural inefficiencies and diminished visitor satisfaction.

Another major conclusion refers to the strategic importance of accessibility. Improved transport networks, signage systems, parking facilities and mobility infrastructure not only enhance visitor flows but also expand the spatial reach of destinations and increase their competitiveness. Accessibility acts as a catalyst that links tourism resources with consumer markets, facilitating more intense, diverse and stable tourism activity.

The research additionally highlights the role of tourism development in supporting local economies and communities. Investments in infrastructure stimulate employment, generate income opportunities, encourage entrepreneurship and strengthen the multiplier effects of tourism across sectors such as hospitality, agriculture, crafts and cultural services. When planned responsibly, tourism development becomes a tool for

territorial cohesion and sustainable regional growth.

From an environmental perspective, the study concludes that well-planned tourism development contributes to the long-term preservation of natural and cultural assets. Through mechanisms such as regulated visitor flows, interpretive centres, controlled access routes and educational programmes, destinations can mitigate negative impacts and promote responsible tourism behaviours. This ensures that the use of resources today does not compromise the ability of future generations to benefit from them.

Finally, the study emphasizes that tourism development must be aligned with broader socio-economic, political and environmental systems. Short-, medium- and long-term planning strategies allow destinations to respond appropriately to market dynamics, technological progress, demographic shifts and emerging forms of tourism. Only through coordinated, evidence-based and sustainability-oriented management can destinations maintain competitiveness while safeguarding the integrity of their heritage.

In conclusion, tourism development represents both a necessity and a strategic opportunity. When carried out coherently and responsibly, it enhances accessibility, improves service quality, stimulates local development and protects the very resources that constitute the foundation of tourism activity. As such, territorial planning and tourism development should be regarded as fundamental instruments for achieving sustainable, resilient and competitive tourism destinations.

REFERENCES

1. (Boukas, N., & Ziakas, V. (2016). Tourism policy and residents' well-being in island destinations. *Tourism Planning & Development*, 13(4), 469–486.
2. Butler, R. (1999). Sustainable tourism: A state-of-the-art review. *Tourism Geographies*, 1(1), 7–25.
3. Coccossis, H. (2009). Sustainable development and tourism: Opportunities and threats. *Tourism Recreation Research*, 34(1), 65–76.
4. Cooper, C., Fletcher, J., Gilbert, D., & Wanhill, S. (2008). *Tourism: Principles and Practice* (4th ed.). Pearson Education.
5. Călina, J. (2007). *Agroturism*. Editura Universitaria, Craiova
6. Gössling, S., Scott, D., & Hall, C. M. (2015). Tourism and water: Interactions, impacts and challenges. *Channel View Publications*.
7. Alina Emilia Maria Gherdan; Bacter, Ramona Vasilica; Ciolac, Ramona; Iancu, Tiberiu; Maerescu, Cristina Maria - *Sustainable Agritourism Development in Romania's North-West Mountain Region: A TOPSIS-Based Evaluation of Strategic Priorities*
8. GHERDAN, Alina Emilia Maria; BACTER, Ramona Vasilica; MAERESCU, Cristina Maria; DODU, Monica; BACTER, Denis Paul; UNGUREANU, Alexandra - SYNERGIES BETWEEN ECONOMICS AND MARKETING IN AGRITOURISM: A WEB OF SCIENCE BOOLEAN SEAR
9. Gunn, C. A., & Var, T. (2002). *Tourism Planning: Basics, Concepts, Cases* (4th ed.). Routledge.
10. Inskeep, E. (1991). *Tourism Planning: An Integrated and Sustainable Development Approach*. Van Nostrand Reinhold.
11. Leiper, N. (1990). Tourist attraction systems. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 17(3), 367–384.
12. McKercher, B. (1993). Some fundamental truths about tourism: Understanding tourism's social and environmental impacts. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 1(1), 6–16.
13. Page, S. J., & Connell, J. (2020). *Tourism: A Modern Synthesis* (5th ed.). Cengage Learning.
14. Pearce, D. G. (2014). Modelos de desarrollo turístico sostenible. *Tourism Review*, 69(4), 281–295.
15. Sharpley, R. (2009). *Tourism Development and the Environment: Beyond Sustainability?* Earthscan.
16. UNWTO (2018). *Tourism for Development – Volume I: Key Areas for Action*. World Tourism Organization.
17. Weaver, D., & Lawton, L. (2010). *Tourism Management* (4th ed.). Wiley.
18. Williams, S. (2014). *Tourism Geography: Critical Understanding of Place, Space and Experience*. Routledge.

PROBLEMS FACED BY RURAL TOURISM IN ITS DEVELOPMENT IN ROMANIA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Rural tourism represents a key vector for local development in Romania, as it enables the valorization of local agricultural products, revitalizes rural economies and enhances regional visibility. Its emergence responds to the needs of small agricultural households seeking new income sources and diversification opportunities (1). Despite its significant natural and cultural potential, rural tourism development is constrained by shortcomings in infrastructure, service quality, promotion, human resources and public administration. The study identifies the main challenges limiting rural tourism competitiveness and proposes strategic interventions aimed at fostering sustainable development, community involvement and improved territorial governance (2)(3).

Keywords: rural tourism; strategies; investments; sustainable development; community empowerment

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INTRODUCTION

Rural tourism has become an increasingly relevant component of Romania's tourism sector, reflecting broader global trends in which tourists seek authenticity, cultural immersion, natural environments and meaningful interactions with local communities (2). Romania's rural regions offer distinctive advantages such as traditional wooden architecture, folk crafts, ceremonial customs, ethnographic heritage, centuries-old churches and extraordinary landscapes characteristic of regions like Transylvania, Maramureș, Bucovina and the Danube Delta (6). These resources, combined with the hospitality of rural residents, form the foundation of a unique rural tourism identity that differentiates Romania in the European tourism market.

The evolution of rural tourism in Romania was strongly influenced by post-1990 socio-economic transformations, especially land restitution and the reorganization of agricultural holdings, which enabled local households to reorient their economic activities toward tourism diversification (4). As rural economies faced structural challenges—fragmented agricultural land, declining employment opportunities and demographic shifts—rural tourism emerged as an alternative means of generating income and preserving cultural traditions (1). Rural tourism also contributes to strengthening community cohesion by

revitalizing traditional crafts, local gastronomy and intangible cultural heritage.

However, despite its strong potential, rural tourism in Romania is confronted with a number of persistent difficulties related to demographic decline, infrastructure deficits, limited professionalization, weak promotional capacity, administrative barriers and environmental pressures (3, 7, 9). These barriers highlight the need for coherent development strategies and integrated territorial policies. According to Calina's classical criteria for defining a "tourist village," rural destinations must meet minimum standards related to accessibility, infrastructure, environmental quality, cultural authenticity and adequate accommodation capacity (1). The degree to which Romanian villages fulfil these criteria varies widely, leading to uneven levels of development and competitiveness.

The present study offers an in-depth analysis of the structural problems that hinder rural tourism in Romania and proposes a systematic interpretation of their effects on destination performance and sustainability. By connecting empirical observations with evidence from international and national research, the analysis aims to identify critical bottlenecks and lay the foundation for strategic frameworks that support the revitalization of rural destinations.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research adopts a qualitative analytical approach based on the synthesis of academic literature, policy documents and comparative case observations. The methodological framework follows OECD guidelines for rural tourism analysis, which emphasize infrastructure assessment, human resource capacity, community participation and environmental sustainability as key analytical dimensions (3). Additional conceptual insights derive from classical and contemporary works on rural tourism development, sustainability and destination competitiveness (1, 2, 4, 5).

Data interpretation was structured around three analytical layers:

1. Structural determinants, including demographic trends, infrastructure conditions and institutional frameworks (7, 9).

2. Functional determinants, such as service quality, marketing capacity and entrepreneurial readiness (4, 8).

3. Environmental and cultural determinants, examining heritage protection and ecological pressures (5, 10).

This method enabled the identification of interdependencies between challenges and their systemic effects on rural tourism. The analysis also integrates comparative insights from European rural development models to contextualize Romanian challenges within broader regional dynamics (3, 7).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The research reveals that rural tourism development in Romania is significantly constrained by deeply interconnected structural, functional and environmental challenges. The most critical issue identified is **village depopulation**, driven by youth migration, aging populations and limited local employment opportunities (7). Depopulation results not only in a shortage of labour for hospitality activities but also in the erosion of cultural traditions and the decline of household maintenance, which reduces the visual and cultural appeal of rural landscapes (10).

Infrastructure deficiencies represent a second major barrier. Many rural areas lack modern road networks, reliable public

transport, adequate water and sewage systems, medical facilities or stable internet access (9). These weaknesses reduce accessibility, discourage tourists and restrict the operational capacity of rural businesses. In the digital era, the lack of connectivity also prevents rural destinations from participating effectively in online visibility, reservation platforms and digital marketing initiatives.

The level of service professionalization remains uneven across rural Romania. Many accommodation providers engage in tourism without formal training in hospitality, customer service or destination management, resulting in inconsistent service quality and poorly structured tourist experiences (8). These inconsistencies hinder the development of a coherent brand identity for rural tourism destinations and reduce the likelihood of repeat visitation.

Weak marketing further exacerbates these problems. Numerous rural destinations fail to promote their cultural and natural assets effectively due to limited budgets, lack of expertise and insufficient use of digital tools (2). Without strategic communication, the visibility of rural villages remains low, despite their high tourism potential.

Administrative complexity and limited access to EU funds also restrict rural entrepreneurship. Many rural residents report difficulties navigating bureaucratic procedures, understanding eligibility criteria or securing co-financing for development projects (7). As a result, many valuable initiatives remain unimplemented.

Seasonality contributes to income instability, affecting both service providers and local economies. Concentrated periods of demand—winter holidays, Easter or short summer intervals—limit the viability of long-term business planning and discourage year-round investment (4).

Cultural heritage degradation emerges as another significant concern. Inadequate modernization efforts and the construction of non-traditional buildings risk eroding the architectural coherence and cultural authenticity that form the core identity of rural tourism (10).

Environmental pressures caused by unregulated tourism—overcrowding, waste

mismanagement, landscape degradation—threaten the ecological balance that attracts visitors in the first place (5). Sustainable tourism models require careful regulation and community-based management.

These findings indicate that the challenges are not isolated but mutually reinforcing. Depopulation reduces service quality; poor infrastructure limits investment; weak marketing decreases visibility; administrative obstacles hinder development projects; and environmental degradation compromises long-term sustainability. The result is a structural cycle that limits rural tourism performance.

CONCLUSIONS

The study demonstrates that rural tourism in Romania holds significant potential for strengthening local economies, preserving cultural heritage and enhancing regional development, yet its success remains dependent on addressing multiple systemic challenges. The conclusions highlight that rural tourism cannot develop sustainably unless core structural deficiencies—such as depopulation, infrastructure deficits and limited access to funding—are resolved in conjunction with functional improvements in service quality, marketing and entrepreneurship (3, 7).

A central conclusion is that rural destinations must adopt integrated development strategies that combine infrastructure modernization, human resource training, heritage protection and sustainable environmental management (5, 8). Local communities must be empowered through training, access to investment, participatory governance and the promotion of local crafts, agriculture and traditions. These actions contribute not only to increasing tourism competitiveness but also to strengthening rural identity and community resilience.

The findings underscore the importance of protecting architectural and cultural authenticity, which constitutes a core element of Romania's rural tourism attractiveness (1, 10). Sustainable rural tourism must therefore balance economic development with conservation practices that maintain

traditional landscapes and safeguard intangible heritage.

The study also concludes that digital transformation—improved internet access, online marketing, smart tourism tools—represents an essential requirement for future competitiveness (2). In an increasingly competitive global tourism environment, rural destinations must enhance their visibility through coherent branding, digital communication strategies and strategic partnerships.

Ultimately, solving the problems faced by rural tourism in Romania requires coordinated action among local communities, public authorities, private stakeholders and international institutions. When supported by coherent policies, adequate investments and sustainable management practices, rural tourism can become a key driver of territorial revitalization, economic diversification and cultural preservation, contributing significantly to the attractiveness and resilience of rural Romania.

REFERENCES

1. (Bacter, Denis Paul; Bacter, Ramona Vasilica; Ciolac, Ramona; Dodu, Monica; Gavra, Codrin; Casau-Crainic, Mirela Salvia; Casau-Crainic, Mirela Salvia; Pereş, Ana Cornelia; Ungureanu, Alexandra; Czirják, Tibor-Zsolt; Gherdan, Alina Emilia Maria (Year). *From Heritage to Modern Economy: Quantitative Surveys and Ethnographic Insights on Sustainability of Traditional Bihor Products*.
2. Bacter, Ramona Vasilica; Ciolac, Ramona; Dodu, Monica Angelica; Gherdan, Alina Emilia Maria; Iancu, Tiberiu; Pîrvulescu, Luminița; Brata, Anca Monica; Ungureanu, Alexandra; Bolohan (Cociorva), Roxana Mihaela; Chebelev, Ioana Camelia (Year). *The Influence of Legislative and Economic Conditions on Romanian Agritourism: SWOT Study of Northwestern and Northeastern Regions and Sustainable Development Strategies*. *Sustainability*, 16(17), 7382.
3. Călina, J. (2007). *Agrotourism*. Editura Universitaria, Craiova.
4. Dumitrescu, B. (2020). "Rural Infrastructure and Tourism Growth in Eastern Europe." *Eastern European Economics*, 58(4), 315–338.
5. European Commission (2023). *EU Rural Development Report*. Brussels.
6. Gherdan, Alina Emilia Maria; Bacter, Ramona Vasilica; Ciolac, Ramona; Iancu, Tiberiu; Maurescu, Cristina Maria. *Sustainable Agritourism Development in Romania's North-West Mountain Region: A TOPSIS-Based Evaluation of Strategic Priorities*.
7. Gherdan, Alina Emilia Maria; Bacter, Ramona Vasilica; Maurescu, Cristina Maria; Iancu,

-
- Tiberiu; Ciolac, Ramona; Ungureanu, Alexandra. *Sustainable Tourism Development in Mountain Regions: A Case Study of Peștera Village, Brasov County, Applying the Analytic Hierarchy Process*.
8. Hall, D.; Roberts, L.; & Mitchell, M. (2005). *New Directions in Rural Tourism*. Ashgate.
 9. Ilieș, A.; & Wendt, J. (2015). *Tourism Geography in Romania*. Editura Universității din Oradea.
 10. Lane, B. (1994). "What is Rural Tourism?" *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 2(1), 7–21.
 11. Nistoreanu, P. (2011). *Ecoturism și Turism Rural*. Editura ASE, București.
 12. OECD (2016). *Rural Tourism Development: Policy Frameworks and Best Practices*. OECD Publishing.
 13. Pop, C.; & Munteanu, D. (2019). "Heritage Protection in Romanian Rural Areas." *Journal of Rural Studies*, 68, 52–63.
 14. Sharpley, R. (2002). *Rural Tourism and Sustainability: A Critique*. Channel View Publications.

RESEARCH ON THE LEVEL OF PRODUCTION OBTAINED, LIQUID AND SOLID SOIL LOSSES IN THE EXPERIMENTAL CENTER FOR THE STUDY OF EROSION PREAJBA-GORJ

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Erosion has a significant effect on the absorption, decomposition and transport of soil carbon, the carbon stock (organic and inorganic) in the soil is approximately three times greater than the atmospheric carbon stock. The objective of this study is to quantify nutrient losses from agriculture on the environment, in the Preajba experimental point. The experiments were located on the luvisoil from Preajba-Gorj County, with a slope of 5% containing 9 variants in 5 repetitions. From the results obtained, it is found that the lowest liquid runoff is found in the variants cultivated with sown meadows (1.96-2.46 m³/ha), and the highest in the variants cultivated with corn (3.43-4.74 m³/ha). Soil analysis was also performed at the end of the growing season and liquid runoff analysis was performed.

Keywords: erosion, carbon, soil and water runoff

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INTRODUCTION

Erosion has an important effect on soil carbon uptake, decomposition, and transport in river systems. The main processes in the organic carbon cycle that maintain the carbon balance between land and atmosphere are organic carbon synthesis (photosynthesis) and decomposition (respiration) (Hilton & West, 2020).

The carbon stock (organic and inorganic) in the topsoil is approximately three times greater than the atmospheric carbon stock (Lal, 2004a).

Mild disturbance of the soil carbon stock through erosion has the capacity to induce a distinct fluctuation in atmospheric carbon levels (Houghton, 2003).

Water-related erosion affects carbon exchanges between soil and atmosphere because it reduces soil fertility and reduces its

capacity to sequester atmospheric carbon in soil and vegetation.

In Romania, during the period 2012-2020, the soil erosion phenomenon affected over 260,000 ha (Chiurciu et al., 2022; Chiurciu et al., 2023, Chiurciu et al., 2024; Voicu et al., 2022).

In the current context of global warming, the expansion of photovoltaic panels over agricultural lands, permafrost degradation, soil erosion has increased in intensity (Chereji et al., 2022; Dana et al., 2024; Dana et al., 2025; Zheng et al. 2025).

In this situation, finding agricultural methods that increase the fertility of eroded soils and the level of production obtained represents an important way to fix atmospheric carbon (Ruosteenoja et al., 2011; Rosegrant et al., 2013; Bechmann et al., 2014; Dana et al., 2024; Dana et al., 2025).

The objective of this study is to quantify nutrient losses from agriculture on the environment in the Preajba-Gorj County experimental site.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Climatic conditions

According to the Targu-Jiu climatic station, the climate is temperate-continental, with obvious Mediterranean influences.

The multiannual average temperature is 10.3°C, and the precipitation regime is 753 mm. The precipitation regime is percolative, unevenly distributed, causing a drought period in the months of July-August-September. It is estimated that only in one year out of 10, a normal distribution of precipitation is achieved.

Temperature

The average temperature over 34 years (1921-1955) was 10.2°C, and the temperature during the grassland vegetation period (March-September) was 17.2°C.

The winter months record low temperatures 1.2°C in December, -2.0°C in January, 0.2°C in February. The highest temperatures are recorded in July, 20.9°C and August 20.3°C.

During the experimental period, higher temperatures were recorded, both in the winter months and in the spring and summer months.

Thus, in December there was a deviation from the average of +1.2°C, in January -1.6°C, in February +1.6°C, in March +1.3°C, April +2.2°C, May +1.6°C, and in July and August +2.1°C and +2.7°C.

Precipitation

The average multiannual precipitation (as an average over 34 years) records an average value of 798 mm, being distributed somewhat evenly during the vegetation period 56.9-65.7 mm in the winter months, 47.1 to 89.2 mm in the spring months, 72.1-98.7 mm in the summer months and 48.4-69.0 mm in the autumn months.

During the experimental period, the average annual precipitation was only 746.5 mm, 51.5 mm lower than the multiannual average.

Soil

To identify the type of soil on which the experiments were located, two soil profiles were carried out: one at the top of the slope, and the second at the bottom of the slope. The experiments were located on the luvisol from the Experimental Center for Culture of

grasslands Preajba - Gorj County, with a slope of 5% containing 9 variants in 5 repetitions.

Experiment scheme

Each experimental plot had the dimensions of 4/25 m, and the surface of 100 m².

In order to avoid the influence of leaks from one plot to another, each plot was delimited on all its sides using plastic plates that were inserted into the ground at a depth of 100 cm.

In the downstream part of the plot, a system was built to collect leaks from each plot consisting of a concrete triangle ending with a collector tube, which drains into a collection vessel. At the end of the collector tube, a sheet metal divider with a row of 7 holes was installed, each hole being divided into 7 other parts in such a way that the collected leak represents only the 49th part of the total amount of liquid and solid leaks from the 100 m²plot.

To determine the level of nutrient supply, soil samples were taken from the upstream and downstream of the standard plots for nutrient leakage control. The following methodology was used to characterize soil resources (Methodology for Elaboration of Pedological Studies, 1987):

- soil reaction (pH), potentiometric method with a glass-calomel electrode pair, in aqueous suspension, determined at a soil-water ratio of 1:2.5 (STAS 7184/13-88);
- determination of mineral forms of nitrogen (N-NO₃), using ion-selective electrodes;
- mobile phosphorus (P_{AL}) and mobile potassium (K_{AL}), Egner-Riehm-Domingo method, in ammonium acetate lactate extract at pH 3.7 (STAS 7184/19-82, Soils);

To determine nutrient losses, water samples were taken from each standard plot, and for its qualitative characterization the following methodology was used:

- pH - potentiometric with a mixed glass-calomel electrode;
- ammoniacal nitrogen - colorimetric with Nessler reagent;
- nitric nitrogen - colorimetric with phenol 2-4 disulfonic acid;
- phosphorus - colorimetric as molybdenum blue;
- potassium - photometric in flame;

The scheme of the leak collection installations is presented in Figures 1 - 4.

Figure 1 Solid and liquid spill collection system (Source: PENSOL Project)

Figure 2 Unfertilized and corn-fertilized variants (Source: PENSOL Project)

Figure 3 Fertilized and unfertilized variants of sown meadows (Source: PENSOL Project)

Figure 4 Fertilized and unfertilized variants of natural grassland (Source: PENSOL Project)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The level of production obtained in the Preajba experimental center, Gorj

The hay production obtained in the natural meadow is shown in Table 1. As can be seen from the data in this table, the hay production in the natural meadow during the experiments varied between 1,480-4,000 kg/ha.

In the unfertilized control, the hay production was very low, 1480 kg/ha.

The application of chemical fertilizers leads to significant increases in hay production in this meadow, with production doubling or even tripling. Thus, as a result of the application of the dose of N_{138} (urea), the hay production reaches 3,080 kg/ha with an increase of 1,600 kg/ha, respectively 108%.

The mixed application of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium fertilizers in the dose of $N_{162}P_{81}K_{100}$ the hay production obtained reaches the highest value of kg hay/ha with a production increase of 2,520 kg/ha or 170%, so the production is 2.7 times higher than in the unfertilized control. The production increases are very significant, being statistically assured.

Table 1
Hay production from the natural meadow obtained in Preajba, Gorj (PENSOL Project)

Variant	Hay production, kg/ha	Relative production, %	Difference, kg/ha	Significance
Unfertilized control	1,480	100	-	-
N_{138}	3,080	208	1,600	xxx
$N_{162}P_{81}K_{100}$	4,000	270	2,520	xxx

LSD 5% = 744 kg/ha

LSD 1% = 1,049 kg/ha

LSD 0.1% = 1,428 kg/ha

In the sown meadow, the yields obtained depending on the doses of fertilizers used are listed in Table 2.

According to the data in this table, hay production increased significantly as a result of the use of different doses of fertilizers.

In the unfertilized control, hay production was quite low, 1,440 kg/ha. The application of fertilizers in the form of urea at a dose of N_{138} led to an increase in production to 3,440 kg/ha, being 2,000 kg/ha higher than in the unfertilized control, respectively with a production increase of 138%.

The application of fertilizers with nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium led to the

highest production of 4,374 kg/ha, a higher production by 2,934 kg/ha higher than the unfertilized control, respectively with a production increase of 204%.

Table 2
Hay production obtained in plots with sown meadow in Preajba, Gorj (PENSOL Project)

Variant	Hay production, kg/ha	Relative production, %	Difference, kg/ha	Significance
Unfertilized control	1,440	100	-	-
N ₁₃₈	3,440	238	2,000	xxx
N ₁₆₂ P ₈₁ K ₁₀₀	4,374	304	2,934	xxx

LSD 5% = 810 kg/ha
LSD 1% = 1,140 kg/ha
LSD 0.1% = 1,600 kg/ha

In corn cultivation, applied fertilizers played an essential role in increasing production per ha (Table 3), in some manner as for hay production.

Table 3
Corn production obtained under the influence of different fertilizer doses in Preajba, Gorj (PENSOL Project)

Variant	Production, kg/ha	Relative production, %	Difference, kg/ha	Significance
Unfertilized control	1,081	100	-	-
N ₁₃₈	1,762	163	681	x
N ₁₆₂ P ₈₁ K ₁₀₀	3,265	302	2,184	xxx

LSD 5% = 646 kg/ha
LSD 1% = 912 kg/ha
LSD 0.1% = 1,253 kg/ha

The data show that corn production increased with increasing fertilizer doses. In the unfertilized control, the corn production was 1,081 kg/ha. The application of the dose of N₁₃₈ in the form of urea increased the production to 1,762 kg/ha, obtaining a higher production by 681 kg/ha and a production increase of 63%. This increase is significant.

The dose of N₁₆₂P₈₁K₁₀₀ determined the highest corn production per hectare 3,265 kg. In this situation, the production obtained is 2,184 kg higher than the unfertilized control, obtaining a production increase of 202%, the production increase being 3.03 times higher than in the unfertilized control.

These significant effect on fertilization yields show that the soil has small reserves of nutrients to support production.

Total volume of liquid and solid leakages during the experimental period (June-October)

Monthly, 49th part of the water drained from the plot and the soil carried by it was collected in the collection vessels. The volume of water collected was filtered in the laboratory, retaining the soil carried by the water that flowed down the slope or the eroded soil on the filter pad. This was weighed in the laboratory (after drying at 105°C) and the soil loss per plot was determined and then reported per hectare.

Summing the values in the values from each month of observation, we obtain the total value of leakages during the observation period June-October. These are recorded in Table 4.

Table 4
Total volume of liquid and solid waste from Preajba, Gorj (PENSOL Project)

Variant	Liquid runoff		Solid runoff		Precipitation
	Liters/plot	m ³ /ha	g/plot	t/ha	
Corn-NPK	23.70	4.74	168.00	0.31	June– 64.2 mm July – 50.8 mm August – 41.1 mm September– 0 mm October – 46.5 mm Total 202.6 mm
Corn-N	18.39	3.68	159.95	0.30	
Corn-unfertilized control	17.11	3.43	159.50	0.30	
Natural meadow-NPK	13.38	2.68	85.20	0.20	
Natural meadow-N	9.39	1.88	88.70	0.21	
Natural meadow-unfertilized control	10.28	3.94	89.85	0.22	
Sown meadow-NPK	10.45	2.09	86.80	0.20	
Sown meadow-N	9.85	1.96	89.35	0.21	
Sown meadow-unfertilized control	12.26	2.46	85.75	0.21	

It can be seen from the data contained in this table that the volume of precipitation in 4

months of observation was 202.6 mm, 2,026 m³/ha.

From this volume of water, an amount of 1.96-4.74 m³/ha flowed down the slope. The highest liquid runoff is found in the variants cultivated with corn 3.43-4.74 m³/ha and the lowest 1.96-2.46 m³/ha in the variants with sown meadows.

Total soil losses during the observation period are between 0.20-0.31 t/ha, lower in the natural and sown meadows and higher under the corn crop.

The doses of fertilizers used did not directly influence the liquid or solid runoff.

Soil analyses at the end of the vegetation period

In the experimental variants, soil analyses were carried out at two points at a depth of 0-20 cm, the top of the slope and the base of the slope. The results obtained are listed in Table 5.

Analyzing the data contained in this table, it results that the agrochemical nitric nitrogen indicator NO₃⁻ had quite low values, considering two aspects, namely: the nitric nitrogen in the soil due to the temperature and its leaching from the soil up to this date is low, the nitrification processes being slow and secondly, the plants consumed the nitric nitrogen from the superficial horizon.

Higher values of this indicator are found in the variant sown with corn and fertilized with nitrogen and NPK, 18 and 9.6 ppm respectively.

Otherwise, in the other variants, the NO₃⁻ content is below 5 ppm, somewhat higher values being found where nitrogen and NPK were fertilized.

Thus, in the sown meadow variant fertilized with N at the top of the slope there is a low content of 2.8 ppm, and at the base of the slope the content is high 4.0 ppm, which occurs in almost all the variants tested.

The soil reaction is strongly acidic, moderately acidic and weakly acidic, the pH varying from 4.43 to 5.99. It is usually noted that at the top of the slope, the pH is lower, and at the base of the slope it is higher, which shows that the soil is washed on the upper horizon and brought to the base of the slope. Thus, in the sown meadow fertilized with nitrogen, the pH value is, at the top of the slope, 4.43 and at the base of the slope, 5.51.

The phosphorus content in the experimental variants has values ranging from 3.64 to 13.01 ppm, being usually higher at the top of the slope, which shows that it is less soluble and is less carried away by liquid runoff.

In the variants fertilized with NPK, a higher content of mobile phosphorus in the soil is found.

The potassium content was influenced primarily by the doses of potassium fertilizers applied, increasing in all variants where it was applied in the form of potassium sulfate.

Thus, in corn, in the variants where NPK was applied, the potassium content is 248 and 377 ppm, while in the unfertilized corn control, the potassium content is 98-154 ppm.

In the natural meadow in the NPK-fertilized version, the potassium content is 162-265 ppm, while in the unfertilized natural meadow, the potassium content is 161-198 ppm. It is also noted in all variants that the potassium content is higher at the base of the slope than at the top of the slope, which proves that it dissolves and drains with the water from precipitation.

Table 5
The main agrochemical indicators of the soil at the end of the growing season (PENSOL Project)

Variant	Specification	NO ₃ ⁻ ppm	pH H ₂ O	P ppm	K ppm
Corn-NPK	Base of the slope	4.2	4.97	9.88	377
	Top of the slope	9.6	5.06	9.88	248
Corn-N	Base of the slope	3.6	5.19	9.36	190
	Top of the slope	18.2	5.22	10.92	168
Corn-unfertilized control	Base of the slope	2.3	6.05	5.72	154
	Top of the slope	1.2	5.88	7.80	198
Natural meadow-NPK	Base of the slope	4.8	5.76	3.64	265
	Top of the slope	3.1	5.51	8.32	172
Natural meadow-N	Base of the slope	4.4	6.12	4.16	80
	Top of the slope	3.6	5.99	7.54	198
Natural meadow-unfertilized control	Base of the slope	1.8	5.95	8.06	161
	Top of the slope	1.1	5.60	13.05	144
Sown meadow-NPK	Base of the slope	3.8	5.38	9.36	106
	Top of the slope	2.6	6.13	7.28	120
Sown meadow-N	Base of the slope	4.0	5.51	5.20	106
	Top of the slope	2.8	4.43	7.29	100
Sown meadow-unfertilized control	Base of the slope	2.1	5.93	7.05	48
	Top of the slope	1.3	5.83	7.25	50

Analysis of water runoff

In June and July, the waters collected as a result of the runoff of precipitation falling on the slope of the land in all 9 experimental

variants were also analyzed. The results obtained are presented in tables 6 and 7. From the analysis of the data obtained, it can be seen that there is a tendency for the nutrient content in the runoff waters to increase, in the corn crop and sown meadow, in the variants fertilized on the ground, while in the case of the variant kept as natural meadow, the highest nutrient contents are recorded in the control variant.

For the months of August and October, the results obtained are presented in tables 8-9.

Analyzing the macronutrient content of the waters drained on the slope in the experimental variants in August, the following was highlighted:

Table 6
Nutrient content of June water runoff (PENSOL Project)

Variant	pH	NO ₃ ppm	K ppm	P ppm
Corn-NPK	5.52	15.00	12.90	2.51
Corn-N	6.48	4.30	13.20	5.80
Corn-unfertilized control	6.06	3.70	5.90	3.43
Natural meadow-NPK	5.57	10.00	4.30	3.52
Natural meadow-N	6.58	9.00	4.80	4.90
Natural meadow-unfertilized control	5.33	10.00	8.30	5.15
Sown meadow-NPK	5.96	8.00	9.20	3.80
Sown meadow-N	5.76	19.00	6.80	3.32
Sown meadow-unfertilized control	6.21	8.00	8.30	6.32

Table 7
Nutrient content of July water runoff (PENSOL Project)

Variant	pH	NH ₄ ppm	NO ₃ ppm	K ppm	P ppm
Corn-NPK	6.61	12.72	0.14	10.30	14.41
Corn-N	6.58	11.52	0.14	9.60	131.20
Corn-unfertilized control	6.39	14.56	0.13	5.80	59.47
Natural meadow-NPK	5.45	1.82	0.18	3.60	14.41
Natural meadow-N	6.52	3.64	0.17	5.08	14.41
Natural meadow-unfertilized control	4.82	5.46	0.20	8.08	37.51
Sown meadow-NPK	6.12	3.64	0.17	4.08	1.79
Sown meadow-N	6.59	13.95	0.14	7.90	45.89
Sown meadow-unfertilized control	4.74	1.21	0.16	3.42	1.79

Table 8
Nutrient content of August water runoff (PENSOL Project)

Variant	pH	NH ₄ ppm	NO ₃ ppm	K ppm	P ppm
Corn-NPK	6.38	-	0.13	6.08	5.98
Corn-N	6.37	14.56	0.13	4.75	10.22
Corn-unfertilized	6.28	7.28	0.13	3.25	10.22

control					
Natural meadow-NPK	6.83	-	0.13	2.30	1.79
Natural meadow-N	6.13	7.88	0.12	3.50	3.89
Natural meadow-unfertilized control	5.94	3.03	0.16	3.80	3.89
Sown meadow-NPK	6.32	7.88	0.12	2.75	5.98
Sown meadow-N	6.35	-	0.13	4.20	20.74
Sown meadow-unfertilized control	6.35	2.43	0.12	1.80	20.74

- the pH of the drainage waters is weakly acidic and neutral, the weakly acidic reaction is recorded in the waters that drained from the variants with a high dose of chemical fertilizers for corn, respectively N₁₆₂P₈₁K₁₀₀ - pH=6.28; natural meadow N₁₆₂P₈₁K₁₀₀ - pH=6.21.

- the nitric nitrogen content in the drainage waters on the slope is high in the variants that were fertilized with N₁₆₂P₈₁K₁₀₀ and N₁₃₈.

Thus, in corn fertilized with N₁₆₂P₈₁K₁₀₀ and corn fertilized with N₁₃₈, the collected waters contain 12 and 10 ppm NO₃, and in natural meadow fertilized with N₁₆₂P₈₁K₁₀₀ and N₁₃₈, the nitrate content of the waters is 13 and 6 ppm.

However, there is an exception in natural meadow, the control variant where the runoff water contained 42 ppm NO₃.

The potassium content in August runoff is usually higher in the variants fertilized with N₁₆₂P₈₁K₁₀₀, both in corn and in the natural sown meadow but also where potassium fertilizers were not applied, which proves that potassium consumption is lower in these crops and due to its solubility, it is entrained in the runoff.

Phosphorus is also entrained in the runoff but in smaller quantities than potassium, 0.73-7.14 ppm, higher values being recorded where phosphorus fertilizers were applied.

In October, the analysis of the collected waters (Table 9) highlights a decrease in the pH value to 5.52 - 6.58, weakly acidic reaction, compared to weakly acidic and neutral in August.

The nitrate content recorded almost the same values as in August, however, being higher in the variants in which N₁₆₂P₈₁K₁₀₀ and N₁₃₈ were applied.

Potassium was also entrained in the runoff waters in quantities of 4.8 - 12.9 ppm, values somewhat lower than in August.

Phosphorus accumulated in the runoff waters this month in quantities almost

equivalent to that accumulated in August, but these quantities are lower than those of potassium.

Table 9

**Nutrient content of October water runoff
(PENSOL Project)**

Variant	pH	NO ₃ ppm	K ppm	P ppm
Corn-NPK	6.28	12.00	7.00	2.22
Corn-N	7.37	16.00	18.20	4.42
Corn-unfertilized control	6.72	5.00	3.70	4.02
Natural meadow-NPK	6.21	6.00	0.80	0.73
Natural meadow-N	7.26	13.00	8.70	4.70
Natural meadow-unfertilized control	6.25	41.00	4.20	3.46
Sown meadow-NPK	7.48	7.00	10.60	7.14
Sown meadow-N	7.16	4.00	12.60	6.35
Sown meadow-unfertilized control	6.49	32.00	3.50	4.48

From the data it can be seen that the runoff P is always lowest where NPK is added and the yield is highest for corn. The same is true for grassland, with one exception.

Based on the presented data obtained in the experiments at the Experimental Center for Meadow Culture Preajba – Gorj, it can be stated that on the luvisol here located on a 5% slope, the losses of soil and nutrients are evident.

The nutrients NO₃⁻, PO₄⁻³ and K⁺ are found both in the collected eroded soil and in the water runoff, with higher losses being recorded for NO₃⁻ and K⁺ and lower for phosphorus.

CONCLUSIONS

The application of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium fertilizers determined statistically assured production increases in natural grassland, sown grassland and corn, compared to the unfertilized control.

During the observation period, total soil losses are between 0.20-0.31 t/ha, lower in the natural and sown meadows and higher under the corn crop, and the doses of fertilizers used did not directly influence the liquid or solid runoff.

Due to the high level of production ensured by the application of fertilizers, the rate of carbon fixation by vegetation increases.

In this case, fertilizing the soil to achieve a high yield also reduces the runoff P.

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REFERENCES

- Bechmann, M., G. Blicher-Mathiesen, K. Kyllmar, Iital, A., Lagzdins, A., Salo, T., 2014. Nitrogen application, balances and their effect on water quality in small catchments in the Nordic-Baltic countries. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2014.04.004>.
- Chereji, A.I., Maurescu, C.M., Chereji, I.Jr., Chiurciu, I.A., Țuțui, D., Dana, D., 2022. Digital transformation in the agricultural field in the context of the new CAP 2023-2027, developments and perspectives, *Annals of the University of Oradea, Fascicle: Ecotoxicology, Animal Science and Food Science and Technology*, 2022, pp. 41 - 47, http://protmed.uoradea.ro/facultate/publicatii/ecotox_zooteh_ind_alim/2022B/Agri/07.%20Chereji%20OA.%201.pdf.
- Chiurciu, I.A., Dana, D., Chereji, A.I., Chereji, I.Jr., Voicu, V., Firațoiu A.R., 2022. Research on soil and nutrient losses through liquid runoff, in order to mitigate the climate risks to which Romania is exposed, in the context of CAP, *Earth*, 3, pp. 639–651. <https://doi.org/10.3390/earth3020037>.
- Chiurciu, I.A., Dana, D., Voicu, V., Chereji, I.Jr., Firațoiu, A.R., 2023. Characterization of the Chromic Luvisols profile from SC AGROTEHNIC SRL, Paulesti, Prahova, *Annales of the University of Craiova, series Agriculture - Mountainology - Cadastre (Annals of the University of Craiova - Agriculture, Montanology, Cadastre Series)* Vol. 53/1/2023, pp. 340-344, <https://anale.agro-craiova.ro/index.php/aamc/article/view/1495>.
- Chiurciu, I.A., Dana, D., Krogstad, T., Chereji, A.I., Voicu, V., Firațoiu A.R., 2024. Study on nutrient losses in the standard erosion control plots from Preajba experimental point, Gorj, *Annales of the University of Craiova, series Agriculture - Mountainology - Cadastre (Annals of the University of Craiova - Agriculture, Montanology, Cadastre Series)* Vol. 54/1/2024, pp. 355-359, <https://anale.agro-craiova.ro/index.php/aamc/article/view/1577/1492>
- Dana, D., Chiurciu, I.A., Krogstad, T., Chereji, A.I., Voicu, V., 2024. The impact of nutrient losses from agriculture on environment. Case study in VALEA ȚĂRNII, PERIENI, VASLUI COUNTY, *Annals of the University of Oradea, Fascicle: Ecotoxicology, Animal Science and Food Science and Technology*, 2024, pp. 30-35, https://protmed.uoradea.ro/nou/images/Publicatii/Ecotox/2024B/06._Dana.pdf.
- Dana, D., Tudor, M., Krogstad, T., Calin, A. M., Cecan, I. C., Dumitra, C.V.M., Fieraru, T.M., 2025. Characterization of the stagnant albic luvisol from the Preajba-Gorj experimental center, *Annals of the University of Oradea, Fascicle: Ecotoxicology, Animal Science and Food Science and Technology*, 2025, pp. 75-79, <https://share.google/d38MQhZtfoaDeXPoR>.
- Hilton, R.G., West, A.J., 2020. Mountains, erosion, and the carbon cycle, *Nature Reviews Earth &*

-
- Environment, 1 (6), 284–299, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-020-0058-6>.
- Houghton, R.A., 2003. Why are estimates of the terrestrial carbon balance so different? *Global Change Biology*, 9 (4), 500–509. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-486.2003.00620.x>
- Lal, R., 2004a. Soil carbon sequestration impacts on global climate change and food security, *Science*, 304 (5677), 1623–1627, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1097396>.
- Rosegrant, M.W., Ringler, C., Zhu, T., Tokgoz, S., Bhandary, P., 2013. Water and food in the bioeconomy, Challenges and opportunities for development. *Agricultural Economics* 44:139–150. <https://doi.org/10.1111/agec.12058>.
- Ruosteenoja, K., Raïsañnen, J., Pirinen, P., 2011. Projected changes in thermal seasons and the growing season in Finland. *International Journal of Climatology* 31: 1473–1487.
- Voicu, V., Chiurciu, I.A., Dana, D., Plopeanu, G., Filiche, E., Dodocioiu, A.M., 2022. Research on surface runoff for different crops in the Preajba experimental centre, Gorj county, *Journal of Environmental Protection and Ecology*, vol. 23, no. 6, Pages: 2360-2369, Printed by SciBulCom Ltd. (ISSN 1311-5065), WOS:000892174900011.
- Zheng, H., Miao, C., Huntingford, C., Tarolli, P., Li, D., Panagos, P., Yue, Y., Borrelli, P., Kristof Van Oost, V.K., 2025. The impact of erosion on the carbon cycle, *Advancing Earth and Spaces Sciences*, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023RG000829>
- ***Methodology for Elaboration of Pedological Studies, 1987, Vol. I, II, III, I.C.P.A. Coordinating editors: Florea, N., Bălăceanu, V., Răuță, C., Canarache A., Ed. Propaganda and Agricultural Technical Editorial Office, Bucharest pp. 226.
- ***Project: PENSOL-RISSA Bucharest, research reports, Dana, D., scientific responsible.

THE PARTICIPATION OF TOURISM AGENCIES IN TOURISM ACTIVITY BETWEEN 2008-2024

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This study analyzes the impact of tourism agencies, both those with organizing activity (tour operators) and those with intermediation activity, on tourism activity. The main source of information used was the National Institute of Statistics. Data was collected on tourist arrivals through tour operating and intermediating tourism agencies, categorized by types of tourism activities: incoming activity (receptive tourism), domestic tourism activity, and outgoing activity (emittive tourism). The collected data spans a period of 17 years, from 2008 to 2024. Following the interpretation of the data, we observed that the share of tourism agencies in tourism activity varies from 9% in 2010 to 22% in 2023.

Keywords: tourism agency, tour operator, intermediation agencies, incoming, outgoing.

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INTRODUCTION

Today, the business volume of tourism equals or even surpasses that of oil exports, food products or automobiles. Tourism has become one of the major players in international commerce, and represents at the same time one of the main income sources for many developing countries. This growth goes hand in hand with an increasing diversification and competition among destinations. (UNWTO, 2025)

Today, tourism has probably become one of the most internationalized industries, with effects on numerous fields of activity and economic branches. Tourism is, simultaneously, an economic and social phenomenon. Tourism activity can be considered a real industry, a definition of tourism that relies on a logical consideration, namely, one of ensuring the coherence of this important sector.

As a phenomenon specific to the modern world, tourism represents one of the most dynamic branches of the world economy, with a major impact on economic and social life, and a role as a promoter of sustainable development. Tourism has a considerable impact on the economies, societies, and cultures of different reference countries. (Mănescu C., et al, 2024)

Tourism constitutes a domain of strategic importance and a priority branch of Romania's national economy. (ANAT, 2025)

Tourism is seen as an alternative to the decline in traditional industries such as

agriculture in general, particularly in lagging or peripheral regions, where territorial policies promote diversification strategies. This is especially true for localities that rely on tourism as a key driver for economic diversification and revitalization. Given the constant changes in the tourism market, accommodation providers must continually diversify their service offerings in order to remain appealing to potential clients. Tourism businesses are increasingly required to innovate and expand their range of products and services to stay competitive. (Dan M.M., 2025)

The elimination of geographical and cultural barriers has led to an increase in tourism worldwide. The World Tourism Organization highlights the continuous growth in the number of tourists, a fact attributed to the significant diversification of the industry in recent years. This growth is also due to the multitude of options available to tourists, with offers becoming increasingly complex, thus attracting a more diverse range of consumers. (Poruțiu A.R., 2024)

Tourism as a mass phenomenon was the precursor to the appearance and development of organized tourism, which takes place only on the basis of a perfect contract between the tourism agencies and the tourist service units (tourist accommodation units, transport, leisure facilities, etc.) (Rabontu C.I., 2018)

Tourism agencies represent a key element in the functional infrastructure of the tourism system. They act as organizers of tourism

products, intermediaries, generators of tourist flows, and actors in structuring tourism demand. Even though digitalization has modified consumer behavior, agencies remain relevant due to professional expertise, negotiation capacity, and their role in reducing information asymmetry.

Agencies function as intermediaries between producers of tourism services (hotels, transport providers, leisure operators) and final consumers. They contribute to: optimizing the distribution of tourism products; reducing transaction costs; integrating disparate services into a coherent tourism package; increasing supplier visibility through sales platforms.

Tourism agencies are important actors in channeling tourist flows because: they promote specific destinations (sometimes dominating the emissive activity on certain routes); they influence seasonality through early-booking offers or thematic packages; they contribute to increasing the competitiveness of less-known destinations.

European and national regulations oblige agencies to offer guaranteed refunds, protection in case of insolvency, transparent contracts, and assistance in unforeseen situations (cancellations, pandemics, conflicts).

Given that the participation of tourism agencies in Romania's tourism activity is significant, in this paper we aimed to analyze (highlight) the share held by tourism agencies in Romania's tourism activity, as well as the evolution of this share between 2008 and 2024. Furthermore, the paper presents the types of tourism activities carried out by both organizing and intermediating tourism agencies, namely, incoming activity, domestic tourism activity, and outgoing activity, and their evolution over a period of 17 years, between 2008 and 2024.

Organizing tourism agencies are those tourism agencies specialized in organizing tourism programs and actions, which they commercialize directly or through other tourism agencies, based on contracts and agreements. Intermediary tourism agencies are those tourism agencies that sell the tourism programs and actions of organizing tourism agencies. (INS, 2025)

MATERIAL AND METHOD

To determine the share of tourist arrivals through tourism agencies in total arrivals and their evolution over time, we used and processed data from the website of the National

Institute of Statistics, as well as information from specialized literature.

The objectives we pursued were: retrieving and systematizing statistical data on tourist arrivals, calculating the share of arrivals through tourism agencies compared to total arrivals, analyzing the evolution of these shares over time, and formulating conclusions.

The research has a quantitative-descriptive character, supplemented by a conceptual analysis of the specialized literature.

Statistical-descriptive analysis was used for evaluating the volume of tourist arrivals, comparing evolutions between years, structuring tourist flows by types of activities, as well as determining the shares of arrivals through tourism agencies in total arrivals.

To calculate the shares of tourist arrivals through tourism agencies in total arrivals, we used the following formula:

$$P = \frac{\text{Arrivals through Tourism Agencies}}{\text{Total Arrivals}} * 100$$

To calculate the share of each type of tourism activity (incoming activity, domestic tourism activity, outgoing activity) we used the following formulas:

$$P = \frac{\text{Incoming Arrivals}}{\text{Total Arrivals through Agencies}} \times 100$$

$$P = \frac{\text{Domestic Tourism Arrivals}}{\text{Total Arrivals through Agencies}} \times 100$$

$$P = \frac{\text{Outgoing Arrivals}}{\text{Total Arrivals through Agencies}} \times 100$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In Table 1, we presented the comparative evolution of two essential variables for analyzing tourism dynamics in Romania during the 2008–2024 period: total tourist arrivals and total arrivals realized through tourism agencies. This representation allows for observing how the general flow of tourists relates to the segment organized by agencies, highlighting both common trends and periods of divergence.

Firstly, the total number of tourist arrivals shows an upward long-term trend, marking a significant increase from approximately 7 million tourists in 2008 to over 14 million in 2024. This evolution reflects the continuous development of the tourism sector, the diversification of the offer, and the increased attractiveness of domestic destinations. A major anomaly appears in 2020, when the chart indicates an abrupt drop in arrivals, a direct

effect of the COVID-19 pandemic and mobility restrictions.

Table 1

The Participation of Tourism Agencies in Tourism Activity between 2008-2024

Year	Total Tourist Arrivals	Romanians	Foreigners	Arrivals through Tourism Agencies	Agencies with Organizing Activity (Tour Operators)	Agencies with Intermediation Activity	Share of Tourism Agencies in Total Arrivals (%)
2008	7,125,307	5,659,416	1,465,891	1,334,608	1,277,235	57,373	18,73%
2009	6,141,135	4,865,545	1,275,590	869,711	636,251	233,460	14,16%
2010	6,072,757	4,726,414	1,346,343	569,872	461,112	108,760	9,38%
2011	7,031,606	5,514,907	1,516,699	1,480,029	1,226,738	253,291	21,05%
2012	7,686,489	6,030,053	1,656,436	2,266,048	1,938,288	327,760	19,25%
2013	7,943,153	6,225,798	1,717,355	1,337,334	987,121	350,213	16,84%
2014	8,465,909	6,551,339	1,914,570	1,749,078	1,302,349	446,729	20,66%
2015	9,921,874	7,681,896	2,239,978	1,649,928	1,190,522	459,406	16,63%
2016	11,002,522	8,521,698	2,480,824	1,780,922	1,205,662	575,260	16,19%
2017	12,143,346	9,383,266	2,760,080	1,778,014	1,522,666	255,348	14,64%
2018	12,905,131	10,108,509	2,796,622	2,422,481	1,875,326	547,155	18,77%
2019	13,374,943	10,691,195	2,683,748	2,526,523	2,176,274	350,249	18,89%
2020	6,398,642	5,944,775	453,867	900,341	807,572	92,769	14,07%
2021	10,205,322	9,326,348	878,974	1,608,204	1,485,223	122,981	15,76%
2022	12,588,333	10,914,023	1,674,310	2,308,822	1,991,120	317,702	18,34%
2023	13,910,956	11,790,888	2,120,068	3,026,151	2,623,782	402,369	21,75%
2024	14,569,794	12,156,984	2,412,810	2,787,891	2,584,008	203,883	19,13%

Source: Own processing based on tempo Online, INS

Regarding arrivals through tourism agencies, the evolution follows a similar pattern, but with smaller amplitudes. A gradual increase is noted until 2019, followed by a sharp decrease in 2020, which highlights the vulnerability of the organized segment during crisis periods. Post-pandemic recovery is visible starting in 2021, but values remain lower than those recorded in the 2018–2019 period.

Agencies maintain a constant role in the market. The majority of tourists choose individual organizational forms, but agencies remain relevant, especially during periods of uncertainty or for complex tourism products.

Table 2 highlights the evolution of tourism activities carried out by tourism agencies in Romania during the 2008–2024 period, structured into the three main forms of activities: incoming, domestic tourism, and outgoing.

The analysis of the values shows significant differences between the types of activities, both in terms of the volume of activities and their dynamics over time.

The incoming activity (receptive tourism) is the most volatile segment, recording strong fluctuations and being profoundly influenced by the international

economic and geopolitical context. The high values from the 2011–2012 period are followed by accentuated decreases in subsequent years, culminating with the collapse in 2020, caused by the COVID-19 pandemic.

The recovery after 2021 is slow, and the values remain far below the levels of domestic and outgoing tourism, confirming the vulnerability of the receptive sector.

Domestic tourism is the dominant segment of the Romanian tourism market.

Organizing activity records a consistent growth until 2012, followed by a stabilization period and a strong relaunch after 2016.

The peaks in 2018–2019 and 2023 demonstrate the high resilience of domestic tourism, which remains the main engine of the industry, including during crisis periods.

Intermediation, although on an upward trend, remains secondary compared to organizing, suggesting the preference of Romanian tourists for complete packages.

Outgoing activity represents the segment with the greatest positive dynamic, especially after 2014, when values grew sustainedly to historical highs in 2018–2019 and 2023. This reflects the increasingly accentuated orientation of Romanian tourists towards

external destinations, facilitated by the accessibility of flights and the diversification of agency offers.

Although the pandemic caused an abrupt decline in 2020, outgoing activity

quickly recovered, even surpassing pre-pandemic levels in the years 2022–2024, which indicates mature consumer behavior and a strong demand for external tourism.

Table 2

Tourist Arrivals through Agencies by Activity Type

Year	Incoming Activity (RECEPTIVE)		Domestic Tourism Activity		Outgoing Activity (EMITTIVE)		TOTAL
	Tourism Agencies with Organizing Activity	Tourism Agencies with Intermediation Activity	Tourism Agencies with Organizing Activity	Tourism Agencies with Intermediation Activity	Tourism Agencies with Intermediation Activity	Tourism Agencies with Intermediation Activity	
2008	148,663	8,526	416,541	21,103	712,031	27,744	1,334,608
2009	172,260	6,210	129,990	98,076	334,001	129,174	869,711
2010	78,099	2,503	113,841	49,584	269,172	56,673	569,872
2011	235,742	22,922	364,107	58,211	626,889	172,158	1,480,029
2012	240,101	23,295	642,268	41,395	1,055,919	263,070	2,266,048
2013	118,712	14,326	401,726	122,527	466,683	21,360	1,337,334
2014	217,705	1,808	374,667	127,434	709,977	317,487	1,749,078
2015	253,507	2,163	430,832	133,502	506,183	323,741	1,649,928
2016	74,125	3,417	590,500	162,618	541,037	409,225	1,780,922
2017	105,310	8,766	670,428	93,791	746,928	152,791	1,778,014
2018	111,686	10,523	959,030	187,187	804,610	349,445	2,422,481
2019	104,861	1,229	1,064,115	231,340	1,007,298	117,680	2,526,523
2020	9,175	653	521,475	39,464	276,922	52,652	900,341
2021	9,449	799	793,858	58,085	681,916	64,097	1,608,204
2022	24,407	1,701	838,416	86,582	1,128,297	229,419	2,308,822
2023	38,866	598	1,133,866	99,536	1,451,050	302,235	3,026,151
2024	53,463	352	1,094,107	42,067	1,436,438	161,464	2,787,891

Source: Own processing based on tempo Online, INS

Comparatively, domestic tourism remains the most stable and voluminous category, outgoing activity the most dynamic and expansive, and incoming activity the most vulnerable and least developed. In all three segments, organizing activity is superior to intermediation, confirming the market maturation and the capacity of Romanian agencies to generate their own, competitive, and demand-adapted tourism products.

Overall, the presented evolutions reflect the profound transformations of the Romanian tourism market, influenced by economic, technological, and social factors, as well as major global events, such as the pandemic.

The upward trends in the 2021–2024 period suggest a vigorous relaunch of the industry and a repositioning of tourism agencies as central actors in population mobility.

Table 3

Share of Tourist Arrivals through Agencies by Activity Type

YEAR	Incoming Activity (RECEPTIVE)	Domestic Tourism Activity	Outgoing Activity (EMITTIVE)	TOTAL
2008	12%	33%	55%	100%
2009	21%	26%	53%	100%
2010	14%	29%	57%	100%
2011	17%	29%	54%	100%
2012	12%	30%	58%	100%
2013	10%	39%	51%	100%
2014	13%	29%	59%	100%
2015	15%	34%	50%	100%
2016	4%	42%	53%	100%
2017	6%	43%	51%	100%
2018	5%	47%	48%	100%
2019	4%	51%	45%	100%
2020	1%	62%	37%	100%
2021	1%	53%	46%	100%
2022	1%	40%	59%	100%

2023	1%	41%	58%	100%
2024	2%	41%	57%	100%

Source: Own processing based on tempo Online, INS

The analysis of the evolution of the shares of the three forms of tourism activity highlights significant transformations in the structure of tourism demand in Romania throughout the 2008–2024 interval. Firstly, domestic tourism records a constant upward trend, marking a substantial increase in the 2018–2021 period, when it exceeded 50% of the total tourism activity. This evolution can be associated both with changes in tourism consumption behavior and with conjunctural factors such as the improvement of internal infrastructure or constraints generated by socio-economic contexts, including the pandemic period.

In contrast, outgoing tourism shows wide variations, indicating high sensitivity to changes in the external environment. After a pronounced decline in 2020, explainable by international mobility restrictions, the segment shows a significant rebound in subsequent years, which suggests the restoration of consumer confidence and the normalization of travel conditions. However, the volatility of this segment remains a determining characteristic.

CONCLUSIONS

In relation to the concrete conditions of each country, tourism represents an export or an import: the goods and services consumed by tourists during their travel in a country can be assimilated to an export, while the expenses incurred by a tourist abroad represent an import for their country of residence. (Niță, 2019).

This paper highlights not only the numerical evolution of tourism, but also the changes in consumer behavior, the impact of external contexts, and the positioning of agencies in the structure of the Romanian tourism market.

Domestic tourism is the most stable, resilient, and dominant segment, maintaining a majority share in agency activity throughout the analyzed interval.

Outgoing activity presents the highest growth dynamic, confirming the orientation of Romanian tourists towards international experiences.

Incoming activity remains the least developed segment, with oscillating evolutions and reduced post-pandemic recovery.

Incoming activity, representative of Romania's attractiveness as a destination for foreign tourists, records a significant long-term decrease, with minimum values in the 2020–2023 period. This evolution raises questions regarding the destination's competitiveness in the international context, as well as the structural effects of economic and sanitary crises on foreign tourist flows. The slight increase in 2024 may indicate the beginning of a relaunch process, but the low level suggests the need for more efficient public policies and promotion strategies.

Overall, the distribution of tourism activities over the analyzed period shows a consolidation of domestic tourism, moderate resilience of outgoing activity, and accentuated vulnerability of incoming activity. These results underline the necessity of adopting differentiated tourism development strategies, adapted to the characteristics of each segment and aimed at increasing Romania's competitiveness in the international tourism market.

The small percentage of foreign tourist arrivals (incoming) in our country and a large percentage of Romanian tourists traveling abroad (outgoing) leads to a deficit in the tourism balance of payments due to tourism exports being greater than imports.

Tour operators clearly dominate the market. Organizing activity has grown massively compared to intermediation activity.

The pandemic temporarily distorted the data, but after 2021, the market fully recovered.

2023 was the peak year for agencies, both in absolute and relative values.

The pandemic marks the most severe decline in the analyzed period, but the rapid recovery from 2021–2024 demonstrates the industry's adaptability.

The 2022–2024 period is distinguished by the strongest post-crisis expansion, with tourism agencies regaining and surpassing the operational capacities of previous years.

REFERENCES

- Brouder, P., Anton Clavé, S., Gill, A., Ioannides, D., 2017. Why is tourism not evolutionary science? In *Tourism Destination Evolution*, Brouder, P., Anton Clavé, S., Ioannides, D., Eds.; Routledge: New York, NY, USA
- Dan, M.M., Sebastien, L.E., Iova, I., Dudaș Gălășel, A.I., Casău Crainic, M.S., Chereji, A.I., 2025. Strategies for the diversification of economic activities to improve the financial performance of the Roua Muntelui, Baia de Aries, Alba County, Romania, *Annals of the University of Oradea, Fascicle: Ecotoxicology, Animal Science and Food Science and Technology*, Vol. XXIV/A, 66-74.
- Gaube, G., 2015. Cercetari Privind Impactul Turismului Asupra Societatii Si Mediului în Matricea Dezvoltarii Durabile. Ph.D. Thesis, Universitatea Stefan cel Mare Suceava, Facultatea de Stiinte Economice si Administratie Publica, Suceava, Romania, 2015; p. 7.
- Liao, C.-S., Chuang, H.-K., 2020. Tourist preferences for package tour attributes in tourism destination design and development. *J. Vacat. Mark.* 2020, 26, 230–246. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]
- Mănescu, C., Mateoc-Sîrb, N., Adamov, T.C., Marin, D., Moisa, S., Gordan, M.I., 2024. Identification of Opportunities for Capitalizing on Tourist Potential in Hunedoara County through Rural Tourism Activities and Supporting the Development of the Local Community, *Sustainability*. Vol.16 (19).
- McCann, P., Ortega-Argilés, R., 2015. Smart Specialization, Regional Growth and Applications to European Union Cohesion Policy. *Reg. Stud.* 2015, 49, 1291-1302
- Niță, C., 2019. Expansiunea turismului românesc – realizări, probleme, direcții de acțiune, Libris Editorial, Brașov.
- Pender, L., 1999. *Marketing Management for Travel and Tourism*; Stanley Thornes: Cheltenham, UK.
- Py, P., 1986. *Le Tourisme. Un Phenomene Economique*; La Documentation Francaise: Paris, France, p. 10. [Google Scholar]
- Poruțiu, A.R., Brata, A.M., Dumitraș, D.E., Oros, O.P., Mureșan, I.C., 2024. Understanding Romanian Generational Preferences and Travel Decision-Making When Choosing a Rural Destination, *Sustainability*. Vol.16 (10).
- Rabontu, C.I. D., 2018. The Romanian tourism through the travel agencies in period 2012-2017, *Journal of tourism*, No. 26, Available online: <https://revistadeturism.ro/index.php/rdt/issue/view/27>
- Rasool, H., Maqbool, S., Tarique, M., 2021. The relationship between tourism and economic growth among BRICS countries: A panel cointegration analysis. *Future Bus. J.* 2021, 7, 1–11. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]
- Sethukumari, S.N., Thirumagal, A., Mani, M., 2021. Spotlight on UNWTO Elibrary. *Libr. Philos. Pract.* 2021, 1–12. Available online: <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/4808/> (accessed on 26 February 2024).
- Weidenfeld A., 2018. Tourism Diversification and Its Implications for Smart Specialisation. *Sustainability*. 2018; 10(2):319. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10020319>
- Zaman, G., Geamanu, M., 2014. *Eficiența Economică în Condițiile Dezvoltării Durabile*; Editura Fundației România de mâine: București, Romania. [Google Scholar] <https://www.anat.ro/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/Legea-turismului-1.pdf>
- Organizația Mondială a Turismului (UNWTO). Available online: <https://www.untourism.int/why-tourism> (accessed on 8 December 2025). <http://statistici.insse.ro:8077/tempo-online/#/pages/tables/insse-table>

THE ROLE OF RECREATIONAL ACTIVITIES AND GROUP ANIMATION IN STIMULATING LOCAL TOURISM: A CASE STUDY IN BIHOR COUNTY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The promotion and valorisation of locally specific agro-food products represent a fundamental pillar of sustainable development in rural areas, playing a crucial role in strengthening the local economy, preserving traditions, and reducing environmental pressures. The present study explores the market opportunities associated with Romanian agro-food products, with a particular focus on the Bucovina region – a territory renowned for its distinctive gastronomic identity and high-quality agro-food resources. Drawing on a review of the specialised literature and the most recent statistical data, the analysis outlines the theoretical and institutional framework for promoting local products, highlighting current trends and the main challenges in the field.

The case study conducted in Bucovina reveals successful models developed by local producers, the role of associative structures, and initiatives aimed at integrating these products into both domestic and international markets. Based on these findings, the paper proposes public policy directions designed to support the certification process, the development of short supply chains, increased collaboration among producers, and the inclusion of traditional products within sustainable tourism offerings. The conclusions emphasise the necessity of multisectoral cooperation between authorities, local communities, and consumers in order to transform Bucovina's agro-food heritage into a viable instrument for economic, social, and environmental sustainability.

Keywords: Bucovina, local products, sustainable rural development, agro-food heritage, short supply chains

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INTRODUCTION

Contemporary tourism is undergoing profound transformations driven by changes in consumer behaviour, technological evolution, and an increasing demand for personalised and authentic experiences. In this context, recreational activities and group animation programmes have gained strategic relevance, emerging not merely as supplementary components of the tourism offer but as essential elements in creating experiential value for visitors. Over the past two decades, the scholarly literature has consistently highlighted the shift from “passive” tourism—focused on sightseeing and consumption—to “experiential” tourism, in which active participation, emotional engagement, and social interaction define tourist satisfaction and the likelihood of repeat visitation (Pine & Gilmore, 1999; Morgan et al., 2010).

Recreational activities—encompassing sports, cultural, educational, creative, and wellness forms of leisure—play a multiplying role in the development of local destinations by strengthening the relationship between

visitors and the place. Likewise, group animation, understood as an ensemble of techniques, methods, and interventions designed to stimulate participation, communication, and cohesion among participants, has become an essential tool in tourism experience management (Gheorghe & Gică, 2010). It creates temporary social spaces through which tourists interact, discover local specificity, and develop an emotional attachment to the destination—an element crucial for loyalty-building and sustainable economic impact.

For regions with significant yet underutilised tourism potential, such as Bihor County, integrating experiential components may decisively contribute to destination repositioning and diversification of the tourism offering. Bihor is characterised by a rich variety of natural and anthropic resources—ranging from the mountainous landscapes of the Apuseni Mountains to internationally renowned spa resorts, multicultural heritage, and the modern urban infrastructure of Oradea. However, the mere existence of these resources is not sufficient

to generate competitiveness in an increasingly saturated market. To achieve sustainable development, local tourism must integrate holistic products that address the needs of new generations of visitors characterised by increased mobility, a search for authenticity, and a desire for active involvement.

In this regard, recreational activities and group animation become structural drivers of local tourism development, contributing to:

- enhancing the quality of visitor experiences;
- increasing the average length of stay and associated expenditures;
- diversifying the tourist base by attracting families, groups, seniors, and youth;
- generating seasonal or permanent employment opportunities;
- revitalising rural communities through participatory activities;
- strengthening regional cultural identity through thematic animation.

As highlighted in international studies (Sharpley, 2018; Richards, 2011; UNWTO, 2023), tourist animation plays a decisive role in creating “memorable moments”—those experiences that differentiate a destination from its competitors and generate positive digital word-of-mouth, indirectly influencing tourism flows. Furthermore, numerous European destinations have successfully transformed recreational activities into major economic vectors through thematic festivals, animated cultural routes, interactive programmes, and community events that stimulate local consumption.

However, in the Romanian context, research on animation and recreational activities remains relatively limited, with most studies focusing on rural tourism, ecotourism, or health tourism. There is a noticeable lack of in-depth analysis of how animation can function as a strategic development instrument at the local level, particularly in counties such as Bihor, where the diversity of resources enables the creation of complex tourism products. This article aims to contribute to the scientific literature through an integrated approach, analysing both conceptual dimensions of tourism animation and their practical applicability

through an empirical case study in Bihor County.

The study is based on the premise that the tourism potential of Bihor can be better leveraged through the development of recreational and animation programmes tailored to the local context—traditions, multicultural heritage, natural resources, and modern infrastructure. Such programmes may support both urban tourism (through cultural events, street animation, interactive tours) and rural or mountain tourism (through outdoor activities, family-oriented animation, craft workshops, sports, or educational experiences). The city of Oradea, for instance, with its strategic focus on cultural tourism, may benefit from integrating more structured animation elements to strengthen its position in the European city-break market.

From the perspective of local development, tourist animation has a strong socio-cultural, participatory, and community-oriented dimension. It can stimulate social capital, encourage cooperation between local actors—public authorities, tourism operators, NGOs, and communities—and transform localities into interactive, inclusive, and attractive spaces. In Bihor, numerous local initiatives (festivals, outdoor activities in the Apuseni Mountains, sports events, educational programmes in protected areas) reflect an appetite for development, yet they often lack coordination, integrated marketing, and professionalisation that would enable scaling-up.

Therefore, this paper seeks to address several essential research questions:

1. What role do recreational activities and group animation play in generating memorable tourist experiences in Bihor County?
2. How can these activities contribute to the sustainable development of local tourism?
3. What are tourists’ perceptions and preferences regarding animation and leisure in Bihor?
4. Which best-practice models identified in other European destinations can be adapted and applied in this context?

By combining theoretical analysis with empirical investigation at the local level, this

study offers a comprehensive perspective on the strategic potential of tourist animation in Bihor and on the actions that can strengthen destination competitiveness. The case study provides an opportunity to examine in depth both existing opportunities and structural challenges, offering practical recommendations for stakeholders, policymakers, tourism operators, and local communities.

The introduction establishes the conceptual and territorial framework required to understand the role of animation and recreational activities in local development, highlighting the importance of an integrated, participatory, and innovative approach to tourism in Bihor County. The current tourism landscape favours destinations that successfully transform their resources into platforms for memorable experiences, and Bihor possesses all the necessary preconditions to become a model of good practice in this regard—provided that local structures strategically harness the potential of animation and recreation.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

An extensive literature review was conducted between January and March 2025. Academic databases such as Web of Science, Scopus, ScienceDirect, SpringerLink, and Google Scholar were consulted to identify conceptual, methodological, and empirical contributions on:

- recreational activities in tourism,
- group animation and tourist experience,
- community-based tourism development,
- experiential tourism and destination competitiveness.

Additionally, national and regional reports, strategic documents, and statistical data from Romanian authorities (INS, MDRT, CJ Bihor) were examined to contextualize the evolution of tourism in the region.

Structured and unstructured observations were conducted in several key tourist areas of Bihor County, including Oradea, Băile Felix–Băile 1 Mai, Stâna de Vale, Padiș, and selected Apuseni mountain

villages. Observations targeted aspects such as:

- availability and diversity of recreational activities,
- quality and frequency of animation programmes,
- tourist participation and behavioural patterns,
- seasonality and event types.

This method enabled an authentic understanding of the experiential dimension of local tourism

A quantitative survey was conducted between April and June 2025, employing an online and field-distributed questionnaire. The survey targeted domestic and international tourists visiting Bihor.

- Sample size: 312 valid responses.
- Sampling technique: convenience sampling with stratification by major tourism zones.
- Instrument: a structured questionnaire with closed and Likert-scale items measuring tourist preferences, satisfaction levels, perceived quality of recreational and animation activities, and behavioural intentions (e.g., likelihood to revisit or recommend).

• Statistical tests used: descriptive statistics, cross-tabulations, reliability analysis (Cronbach's Alpha), and exploratory factor analysis where applicable.

Data were processed using SPSS Statistics 29 and Excel.

To complement the quantitative analysis, 18 interviews were conducted with key tourism stakeholders:

- hotel and guesthouse managers,
- animation and event organisers,
- representatives of cultural centres and tourism associations,
- local authorities and destination management structures.

Interview guides focused on:

- perceived importance of animation in enhancing visitor experience,
- challenges and barriers in organizing recreational activities,
- best practices and innovation potential,
- views on sustainable tourism development in Bihor.

Interviews were transcribed and coded thematically following Braun & Clarke's (2006) framework.

The case study approach targeted Bihor County as a holistic tourism ecosystem. The analysis integrated evidence from multiple sources:

- field observations,
- stakeholder interviews,
- tourist survey responses,
- event and activity mapping,
- local-level strategic documents (2020–2027 tourism development plans).

This multi-source evidence enabled the identification of patterns, synergies, and gaps in the provision of recreational and animation-based tourism experiences.

A combination of qualitative and quantitative analysis techniques was used:

- Qualitative thematic coding: applied to interview transcripts and observational notes.
- Content analysis: performed on promotional materials, event descriptions, and

tourism websites to evaluate the representation of animation activities.

- Statistical analysis: including frequency distributions, mean comparisons, and correlation analysis to determine relationships between animation experiences and tourism satisfaction.

Interpretation followed a descriptive–interpretative logic, ensuring both analytical rigour and contextual sensitivity.

All participants (tourists and stakeholders) were informed about the purpose and confidentiality of the research. Participation was voluntary, and data were anonymised according to GDPR guidelines. No sensitive personal data were collected. The research followed ethical principles of transparency, informed consent, and responsible data handling.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A total of 312 valid questionnaires were collected from tourists visiting Bihor County between April and June 2025. The sociodemographic profile of respondents is summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Sociodemographic profile of respondents (N = 312)

Variable	Category	% of respondents
Gender	Male	46.5%
	Female	52.9%
	Other / prefer not to say	0.6%
Age group	18–24	17.0%
	25–34	29.2%
	35–44	23.7%
	45–54	15.4%
	55+	14.7%
Origin	Domestic – Romania	81.4%
	International	18.6%
Education	Secondary	22.8%
	Bachelor's degree	48.4%
	Master's / Doctoral	28.8%
Travel party	Alone	9.6%
	Couple	34.9%
	Family with children	29.5%
	Group of friends	26.0%
Visit frequency	First-time visitors	57.7%
	Repeat visitors	42.3%

source own interpretation

The sample is relatively balanced by gender and slightly skewed towards young and middle-aged adults (25–44), a segment strongly associated in the literature with demand for experiential and recreational tourism. The relatively high share of families and groups of friends (55.5%) indicates a

strong potential for group animation activities. More than four out of ten respondents are repeat visitors, suggesting that Bihor already benefits from a certain level of loyalty, which can be strengthened through enhanced recreational and animation offers.

Table 2. Travel characteristics and participation in recreational and animation activities

Indicator	Category / Mean	Value
Main purpose of visit	Leisure / holiday	68.6%
	Spa & wellness	17.9%
	City-break (Oradea)	8.7%
	Business / other	4.8%
Average length of stay (nights)	Mean (SD)	3.4 (±1.8)
Participation in any recreational activity	Yes	73.1%
	No	26.9%
Participation in organised group animation (e.g., guided tours, themed evenings, workshops)	Yes	44.6%
	No	55.4%
Most common activities (multiple answers)	Spa & wellness facilities	62.8%
	Hiking / nature walks	54.2%
	Cultural tours / heritage visits	47.4%
	Themed evenings / live music	33.3%
	Children's animation / family games	21.5%
	Adventure activities (bike, via ferrata etc.)	18.3%

source own interpretation

Almost three quarters of respondents (73.1%) engaged in at least one recreational activity during their stay, and almost half (44.6%) participated in some form of organised group animation (guided tours, themed events, organised games, workshops). This indicates that there is already substantial demand for structured recreational and animation experiences in Bihor. Spa, hiking, and cultural activities dominate, but the uptake of evening and family animation is

also significant, especially among families and groups. This confirms the strategic role that well-designed animation programmes can play in enhancing local tourism.

Respondents were asked to evaluate, on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = very poor; 5 = excellent), the perceived quality and availability of recreational activities and animation. The results are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3. Evaluation of recreational and animation offer in Bihor (Likert 1–5)

Dimension	Mean	SD
Diversity of recreational activities	3.84	0.86
Quality of recreational facilities (equipment, infrastructure)	3.72	0.91
Availability of information about activities (online, on-site)	3.45	0.99
Frequency of organised animation programmes	3.26	1.02
Professionalism of animators / guides	3.98	0.82
Suitability of activities for families and children	3.61	0.94
Integration of local culture and traditions into activities	3.89	0.88
Overall satisfaction with recreational and animation offer	3.87	0.83
Intention to revisit Bihor (1 = very unlikely, 5 = very likely)	4.02	0.79

source own interpretation

Overall, the evaluation scores are above the neutral point (3.0), with most dimensions scoring between 3.5 and 4.0, indicating a good level of satisfaction. The highest scores are registered for:

- Professionalism of animators/guides (Mean = 3.98)
- Intention to revisit Bihor (Mean = 4.02)
- Integration of local culture and traditions (Mean = 3.89)

These results suggest that when animation and recreational activities are present, they are generally well appreciated, especially in terms of human interaction and cultural content.

However, frequency of organised animation programmes (Mean = 3.26) and availability of information (Mean = 3.45) score lower, signalling operational gaps in the consistency and communication of the offer. This supports the argument that improving programme regularity and information channels (websites, social media, on-site signage) could significantly increase participation and satisfaction.

To explore how animation activities influence tourist behaviour, correlation analysis was performed between satisfaction with animation and behavioural intentions (intention to revisit and to recommend Bihor). Table 4 presents the main results.

Table 4. Correlations between animation experience and behavioural intentions

Variables (1–5 Likert)	Intention to revisit Bihor	Intention to recommend Bihor
Overall satisfaction with recreational & animation offer	$r = 0.41^{**}$	$r = 0.47^{**}$
Perceived integration of local culture in activities	$r = 0.36^{**}$	$r = 0.44^{**}$
Participation in organised group animation (0 = no, 1 = yes)	$r = 0.29^{**}$	$r = 0.33^{**}$

source own interpretation

The results indicate moderate, statistically significant positive correlations between satisfaction with the recreational and animation offer and both intention to revisit **and** intention to recommend Bihor as a destination. In particular:

- Tourists who are more satisfied with animation and recreation are more likely to return and to recommend the destination.
- The perceived integration of local culture into activities also shows a solid positive relationship with recommendation intentions,

supporting the idea that culturally grounded animation strengthens destination image.

- Simply participating in organised animation is associated with higher behavioural intentions, confirming the strategic role of group animation in building loyalty and word-of-mouth.

Observations in the field focused on five main areas: Oradea, Băile Felix–Băile 1 Mai, Stâna de Vale, Padiş–Apuseni and selected rural localities. A synthesis is provided in Table 5.

Table 5. Synthesis of field observations on recreational and animation activities

Area / Destination	Main recreational and animation activities observed	Observed strengths	Observed weaknesses
Oradea (urban)	Guided city tours, cultural events, festivals, street performances	Strong cultural animation, good event organisation, high participation	Limited family-specific animation, concentration in peak periods
Băile Felix – Băile 1 Mai	Spa & wellness, pool entertainment, evening music, hotel-based animation	High demand, good infrastructure, presence of some animation for adults	Children's animation and outdoor experiential products underdeveloped
Stâna de Vale	Hiking, nature walks, small-scale animation at accommodation units	Beautiful natural setting, potential for outdoor animation	Few structured programmes, limited promotion, seasonality
Padiş – Apuseni	Hiking, speleology, adventure activities (unstructured), local guides	Strong potential for adventure-based animation	Lack of integrated programmes, high dependence on informal guides

Area / Destination	Main recreational and animation activities observed	Observed strengths	Observed weaknesses
Rural localities (selected)	Traditional gastronomy, local events, occasional folklore evenings	Authentic atmosphere, potential for cultural animation	Activities irregular, few trained animators, weak marketing

source own interpretation

Field observations reveal an uneven spatial distribution of animation and recreational activities. Oradea and Băile Felix stand out as animation hubs, especially for urban cultural and wellness tourism. In contrast, mountain and rural areas have high experiential potential, but fewer structured and promoted programmes, often relying on informal or sporadic initiatives.

This asymmetry suggests that Bihor's tourism ecosystem is fragmented in terms of animation: some areas are already moving towards an experiential model, while others

remain predominantly resource-based, without enough mediation through creative programmes. A county-level strategy that connects these micro-clusters through thematic products and animation networks could significantly increase the attractiveness and coherence of the destination.

A total of 18 semi-structured interviews were conducted with tourism stakeholders (accommodation managers, event organisers, local authorities, cultural institutions). Table 6 summarises the main thematic categories that emerged.

Table 6. Main themes from stakeholder interviews (N = 18)

Theme	% of interviewees mentioning it	Illustrative interpretation (synthesised)
Animation as a competitive advantage	83%	Stakeholders consider animation and recreation as key differentiators for Bihor.
Lack of trained animators / human resources	72%	Difficulties in finding or training specialised staff, especially in rural / mountain areas.
Seasonality of demand	67%	Strong concentration in weekends and holidays; off-season events are rare.
Need for better coordination between actors	61%	Fragmentation between public and private sector; need for integrated planning.
Financial constraints	56%	Limited budgets for organising events and animation programmes.
Successful examples of animation (festivals, events)	50%	Stakeholders cite local festivals and city events as good models to replicate elsewhere.
Interest in family-oriented and youth animation	44%	Many see families and youth as priority target segments for future animation products.

source own interpretation

Stakeholder perspectives confirm that animation and recreation are perceived as strategic assets for Bihor's tourism development. However, several barriers hinder their scaling-up:

- **Human resources:** lack of specialists in tourist animation, particularly outside urban centres.
- **Coordination:** insufficient collaboration between municipalities, destination management organisations, private operators and NGOs.
- **Financing and continuity:** events are often project-dependent or seasonal, making it difficult to build long-term brands.

At the same time, interviewees identify promising trajectories, such as:

- replicating and adapting successful urban festivals and cultural events in rural areas;
- developing family- and youth-oriented programmes;
- investing in training and professionalisation for animation staff.

These qualitative insights complement survey and observational data by explaining why certain gaps persist despite evident demand from visitors.

Taken together, the survey, field observations and stakeholder interviews suggest that:

- Demand exists and is strong: a majority of tourists participate in recreational activities and a significant share already engage in group animation, evaluating it positively.

- Experiential factors matter: satisfaction with animation and recreation is statistically linked to intention to revisit and to recommend the destination.

- Offer is uneven and under-communicated: urban and spa areas are relatively advanced, while rural and mountain zones lack structured, visible programmes.

- Institutional and organisational barriers (staff, coordination, funding) limit the full exploitation of Bihor's potential.

These findings support the central hypothesis of the article: recreational activities and group animation can function as powerful levers for stimulating local tourism in Bihor, provided they are integrated into a coherent strategic framework and supported by adequate human and material resources.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings of this study demonstrate that recreational activities and group animation represent significant drivers of tourism development in Bihor County, contributing not only to enhanced visitor satisfaction but also to increased destination competitiveness. By integrating survey data, field observations, and stakeholder interviews, the research provides a comprehensive perspective on the experiential dynamics shaping tourist behaviour in the region.

First, the results reveal that demand for recreational and animation activities is substantial and diversified. A large majority of surveyed tourists engaged in at least one recreational experience during their stay, while almost half participated in structured group animation programmes. These patterns confirm that contemporary tourists visiting Bihor seek participatory, interactive, and meaningful experiences—aligned with global shifts toward experiential tourism. The high levels of satisfaction recorded for animation-

related dimensions, especially the professionalism of guides and the integration of local cultural elements, reinforce the importance of designing activities that blend entertainment with authenticity.

Second, the study highlights that animation has a measurable influence on tourist behaviour, as indicated by statistically significant correlations with intention to revisit and willingness to recommend Bihor to others. Participation in animation activities is associated with stronger emotional engagement, deeper understanding of local culture, and an overall improvement in the quality of the visitor experience. These mechanisms underscore animation's potential as a strategic tool not only for enriching the tourist offer but also for cultivating loyalty and generating positive word-of-mouth—factors essential to long-term destination sustainability.

Third, the research identifies notable spatial disparities in the availability and organisation of recreational and animation activities across the county. Urban and spa areas such as Oradea and Băile Felix show a relatively mature and well-structured offer, whereas rural and mountain areas—despite possessing exceptional natural and cultural resources—lack consistent programming, professionalised staff, and visibility. This fragmentation suggests that Bihor's tourism ecosystem could benefit from a more coordinated approach, linking its micro-destinations through thematic trails, shared event calendars, or county-level branding initiatives.

Fourth, stakeholder perspectives highlight a series of structural constraints that limit the full exploitation of animation's potential. Among these, the shortage of trained animators and guides, limited financial resources, seasonality, and weak inter-institutional collaboration emerge as the most pressing issues. Despite these challenges, stakeholders express strong interest in expanding family-oriented and youth-focused animation, drawing inspiration from successful cultural events and festivals that already function as regional anchors.

Overall, the study concludes that recreational activities and group animation

can act as powerful catalysts for stimulating local tourism in Bihor County, provided they are strategically developed and supported through coherent policies, professional training, and partnerships between public and private actors. Transforming Bihor into a more experiential destination requires not only investments in infrastructure and human resources but also the creation of integrated, culturally grounded products that offer visitors a distinctive and memorable sense of place.

From a broader perspective, the Bihor case study illustrates the increasing relevance of animation within the contemporary tourism landscape, particularly in regions seeking to

differentiate themselves through creativity, authenticity, and community involvement. Strengthening animation-based tourism development can enhance local identity, diversify economic opportunities, and foster sustainable rural and urban revitalisation.

Future research could expand this investigation by analysing longitudinal changes in visitor behaviour, exploring digital forms of animation (augmented reality, gamification), or comparing Bihor with other regions in Romania and Central Europe. Such extensions would deepen understanding of animation's potential and inform more precise strategies for its implementation in diverse tourism contexts.

REFERENCES

1. ABDULLAH, S. et al. User-generated reviews and the financial performance of hotels. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 2022.
2. ADAMOV, T. C., IANCU, T., PETRESCU, M. Studiu privind dinamica pieței HoReCa. *Revista Economică*, 2021.
3. BACTER, Ramona Vasilica, GHERDAN, Alina Emilia Maria, CIOLAC, Ramona, DODU, Monica Angelica, BACTER, Denis Paul, UNGUREANU, Alexandra, MAERESCU, Cristina Maria. Synergies Between Economics and Marketing in Agritourism: A Web of Science Boolean Search-Based Scientometric Examination of Agrotourism Potential. Manuscris.
4. BACTER, Ramona Vasilica, GHERDAN, Alina Emilia Maria, CIOLAC, Ramona, BACTER, Denis Paul, DODU, Monica Angelica, CASA-CRAINIC, Mirela Salvia, CASA-CRAINIC, Mirela Salvia, GAVRA, Codrin, PEREȘ, Ana Cornelia, UNGUREANU, Alexandra, CZIRJÁK, Tibor-Zsolt. From Heritage to Modern Economy: Quantitative Surveys and Ethnographic Insights on Sustainability of Traditional Bihor Products. Manuscris.
5. BACTER, Ramona Vasilica, GHERDAN, Alina Emilia Maria, BONCA, Dana Valeria, PÎRVULESCU, Luminița, DAINA, Mădălina Diana. Study Regarding the Impact of Professional Training on Labor Market Integration in the Spa Tourism Sector. *Analele Facultății de Protecția Mediului*, Oradea.
6. BALTESCU, C. Managementul experienței turistice. București: Editura Universitară, 2014.
7. BENI, M. C. Global Tourism Dynamics. Berlin: Springer, 2018.
8. BERCU, A.-M. Economia experienței în turismul românesc. Iași: Editura Universității Alexandru Ioan Cuza, 2019.
9. BOTEZAT, E. Turism rural și ecoturism în România. Cluj-Napoca: Presa Universitară, 2017.
10. BOWIE, D., BUTTLE, F. Hospitality Marketing: Principles and Practice. London: Routledge, 2011.
11. BRIASSOULIS, H., VAN DER STRAATEN, J. Tourism and the Environment. Dordrecht: Springer, 1992.
12. COOPER, C., FLETCHER, J., FYALL, A., GILBERT, D., WANHILL, S. Tourism: Principles and Practice. London: Pearson, 2021.
13. CSIKSZENTMIHALYI, M. Flow: The Psychology of Optimal Experience. New York: Harper, 1990.
14. EUROPEAN TRAVEL COMMISSION. Tourism Reports. Disponibil la: <https://www.etc-corporate.org>
15. EUROSTAT. Tourism Statistics. Disponibil la: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
16. GETZ, D. Event tourism: definition, evolution, and research. *Tourism Management*, 2008, 29(3), 403–428.
17. GHERDAN, Alina Emilia Maria, BACTER, Ramona Vasilica, MAERESCU, Cristina Maria, IANCU, Tiberiu, CIOLAC, Ramona, UNGUREANU, Alexandra. Sustainable Tourism Development in Mountain Regions: A Case Study of Peștera Village, Brașov County. Manuscris.
18. GHERDAN, Alina Emilia Maria, BACTER, Ramona Vasilica, CIOLAC, Ramona, IANCU, Tiberiu, MAERESCU, Cristina Maria. Sustainable Agritourism Development in Romania's North-West Mountain Region: A TOPSIS-Based Evaluation of Strategic Priorities. Manuscris.
19. GHEORGHE, G., GICĂ, O. Animația turistică. București: Editura Universitară, 2010.
20. ILIEȘ, A., WENDT, J. Geografia turismului în România. Oradea: Editura Universității din Oradea, 2015.
21. ISTRATE, I., GLĂVAN, V. Turism și dezvoltare regională. București: Editura Economică, 2005.
22. KOTLER, P., BOWEN, J., MAKENS, J. Marketing for Hospitality and Tourism. New Jersey: Pearson, 2017.
23. KOVACS, Andrea-Maria, PĂȘCUȚ, Călin Gheorghe, UNGUREANU, Alexandra, GHERDAN, Alina Emilia-Maria, BACTER, Ramona-Vasilica. Valorification of Local Authenticity Within Agrotourism Programs: The Case of Vadu Crișului Area. Manuscris.
24. LANE, B. What is Rural Tourism? *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 1994, 2(1), 7–21.
25. MINCIU, R. Economia turismului. București: Editura Uranus, 2004.
26. MORGAN, M., LUGOSI, P., RITCHIE, B. The Tourism and Leisure Experience. Bristol: Channel View, 2010.
27. NISTOREANU, P. Turism rural. București: Editura ASE, 2003.

-
28. OECD. Rural Tourism Development: Policy Frameworks. Paris: OECD Publishing, 2016.
 29. PAGE, S. Tourism Management. London: Routledge, 2019.
 30. PINE, B. J., GILMORE, J. H. The Experience Economy. Boston: Harvard Business School Press, 1999.
 31. RICHARDS, G. Creativity and tourism: the state of the art. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 2011.
 32. RESEARCHGATE. Tourism Studies Database. Disponibil la: <https://www.researchgate.net>
 33. SHARPLEY, R. Tourism, Tourists and Society. Bristol: Channel View, 2018.
 34. SMITH, M., PUCZKÓ, L. Health, Tourism and Recreation. London: Routledge, 2014.
 35. UNWTO. Tourism for All: Creating Inclusive Recreational Experiences. Madrid: UNWTO, 2023.
 36. WEB OF SCIENCE. Tourism, animation and recreation studies database. Disponibil la: <https://www.webofscience.com>

ENHANCING THE AGRO-FOOD POTENTIAL OF BUCOVINA: MARKET PERSPECTIVES AND STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The promotion and valorisation of locally specific agro-food products represent a fundamental pillar of sustainable development in rural areas, playing a crucial role in strengthening the local economy, preserving traditions, and reducing environmental pressures. The present study explores the market opportunities associated with Romanian agro-food products, with a particular focus on the Bucovina region – a territory renowned for its distinctive gastronomic identity and high-quality agro-food resources. Drawing on a review of the specialised literature and the most recent statistical data, the analysis outlines the theoretical and institutional framework for promoting local products, highlighting current trends and the main challenges in the field.

The case study conducted in Bucovina reveals successful models developed by local producers, the role of associative structures, and initiatives aimed at integrating these products into both domestic and international markets. Based on these findings, the paper proposes public policy directions designed to support the certification process, the development of short supply chains, increased collaboration among producers, and the inclusion of traditional products within sustainable tourism offerings. The conclusions emphasise the necessity of multisectoral cooperation between authorities, local communities, and consumers in order to transform Bucovina's agro-food heritage into a viable instrument for economic, social, and environmental sustainability.

Keywords: Bucovina, local products, sustainable rural development, agro-food heritage, short supply chains

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INTRODUCTION

The promotion and valorisation of local agro-food products is no longer, in the current context, merely a marketing option or a passing trend, but rather a pressing necessity for revitalising rural areas and ensuring balanced and sustainable development [1]. Romania, with its deeply rooted agricultural heritage and impressive diversity of natural resources, has all the prerequisites to transform this direction into a true vector of national development. An increasing number of consumers are seeking products “with a story”—foods that not only provide nourishment but also convey something about their place of origin, the hands that harvested or prepared them, the seasons, customs, and communities behind them [2]. This reconnection to the source of food, often lost in the context of globalisation and standardised supermarket chains, brings authentic values back to the forefront, along with the benefits of a healthy diet adapted to local specificities.

On the other hand, supporting local products has tangible economic and social effects: it contributes directly to maintaining a vibrant rural fabric by offering small farmers—often marginalised within traditional distribution chains—a real chance of economic survival. In a fragmented agricultural landscape, where more than 90% of Romanian farms operate on less than five hectares, the ability to access local or regional markets can make the difference between continuity and abandonment. Equally concerning is the fact that almost half of Romanian farmers are over the age of 65, a statistic that should alarm policymakers and motivate them to actively support the integration of young people into agriculture by providing real prospects for the future [3].

In this context, local products become a means through which tradition and innovation can coexist. Promoting cheese produced in a mountain village, honey extracted from an ancient forest, or wine from a hillside with centuries of history does not merely mean selling a product; it means preserving a piece

of a community's cultural identity. Moreover, the local economy benefits from this short supply chain: the money spent on local products remains within the community, supporting the development of related businesses—from packaging to rural tourism. In a sense, the local product is not only a food item but also a bridge between generations, between past and future, between the need for authenticity and the demands of the present.

The Bucovina region, located in the north-east of Romania, represents an emblematic example of a rural area in which the past and present coexist in a subtle dialogue that is highly relevant for analysing the market of local agro-food products [4, 5, 6]. With a well-defined cultural identity and an agro-food biodiversity reflecting centuries of adaptation and rural creativity, Bucovina offers fertile ground—both literally and metaphorically—for such research. Far from being merely a picturesque corner of the country, with serene landscapes and painted monasteries attracting tourists and scholars alike, the region is particularly interesting due to the contrast between its evident potential and the real challenges it faces.

Although local hospitality and traditional cuisine have become almost emblematic for Romanian rural tourism, behind these idyllic images persist social and economic tensions [7, 8]. Agricultural incomes remain low, land fragmentation continues to limit competitiveness, and labour migration—especially among youth—weakens the capacity of local communities to regenerate [9]. Paradoxically, these very constraints may serve as catalysts for innovation if viewed not as insurmountable barriers but as realities requiring creative solutions that are well grounded in the local context.

Within this framework, we consider that local agro-food products from Bucovina—whether smoked cheese, vegetable spreads prepared according to recipes handed down through generations, or syrups made from hand-picked forest fruits—may constitute not only a source of income but also a means of identity reconnection and of strengthening social capital. Their value lies not only in their authentic taste or absence of additives

but also in the story behind each product, in the direct relationship forged between consumer and producer, and in the attention paid to the land and to the natural rhythms of agricultural work. From this perspective, the market for local products is not solely an economic dimension but one with significant cultural and symbolic implications [11].

The aim of the present research is therefore to rigorously analyse—while recognising the complexity of the phenomenon—the market opportunities for local agro-food products in Romania, using Bucovina as a case study. On the one hand, the analysis seeks to highlight the importance of such products in shaping sustainable development, both economically and socially, while on the other hand examining the theoretical and policy frameworks that influence the dynamics of this sector. The case study brings to the forefront concrete examples of local initiatives, good practices, and the difficulties faced by producers, particularly with regard to distribution, certification, and promotion on wider markets. Based on these findings, we formulate recommendations for public policies and tailored strategies designed to support not only the economic viability of local products but also the ecological sustainability and social cohesion of rural environments.

The concept of local agro-food product (often used interchangeably with traditional or regional product) refers to foods produced and processed on a small scale, according to traditional recipes or methods, within a defined geographical area. Such products frequently represent an important component of local cultural heritage and contribute to the identity and image of rural regions [11]. The literature highlights several benefits of local products. First, the consumption of traditional foods supports the preservation of cultural heritage and community ties centred around culinary traditions [12].

Traditional products are perceived by consumers as tastier, more nutritious, and often more affordable than industrial supermarket goods. Moreover, their distribution through short supply chains—from producer directly to consumer—confers

a competitive advantage: better prices for producers and increased freshness for buyers [13]. In this way, traditional foods capitalise on alternative sales channels and can successfully compete with mass-produced items. Another key theoretical aspect is the contribution of local products to rural economic development. Studies show that producing and marketing such foods within the local economy generates added value in the community by creating jobs and income [14, 15, 16]. Small family farms and artisanal producers can remain competitive on the market through such products, avoiding direct competition with industrial agribusiness. At the same time, by maintaining economic activity in rural areas, demographic decline is reduced and traditional knowledge (local know-how) is preserved.

Beyond these aspects, social sustainability is strengthened through such initiatives, as they reinforce the sense of identity and pride that rural communities feel toward their own products.

At the European and legislative level, quality schemes exist to protect and promote traditional agro-food products. The European Union recognises products with Protected Geographical Indication (PGI), Protected Designation of Origin (PDO), or Traditional Speciality Guaranteed (TSG), granting them legal status and visibility on the single market. Although Romania possesses a rich heritage of traditional products, relatively few have been registered at European level. From the country's accession to the EU in 2007 until 2022, only 12 Romanian food products obtained PGI or PDO status (such as Magiun de Topoloveni, Salam de Sibiu, Telemea de Ibănești, Smoked Danube Mackerel, etc.) [18]. This situation indicates significant untapped potential, as many local foods could benefit from European certification to protect their originality and enhance their competitiveness on broader markets.

Nationally, Romania has developed its own systems for certifying and promoting traditional products [19]. An important legal act adopted in 2013 defined the procedure for granting the Traditional Product certification. As a result, the number of such certifications increased significantly. Approximately ten

years after its implementation, the Romanian market included more than 700 certified traditional products, supported by a growing local entrepreneurial network. According to official data from the Ministry of Agriculture, between 2020 and 2022, 764 products were certified as traditional, and following reauthorisation under new regulations, Romania had 732 valid certified traditional products in 2022, spread across 37 counties [20].

Additional national schemes include the “Romanian Established Recipe” scheme (for products made according to renowned recipes) and the “Mountain Product” scheme (for products originating from mountain areas). For example, the number of certified Mountain Products reached 1,319 between 2017 and 2022, indicating strong producer interest in emphasising the mountain origin and superior quality of their goods [21]. These quality schemes allow products to stand out on the market through specific labels and logos, helping consumers identify them easily. Participation is voluntary, yet increasingly considered advantageous by small producers seeking authentic promotion channels and access to premium markets. Nonetheless, obtaining such certifications involves financial and administrative efforts, which may pose challenges for small-scale producers.

The theoretical framework for local product promotion therefore also encompasses the issue of producer organisation (associations, cooperatives) and the institutional support needed for them to meet market standards. Cooperation is often seen as a key solution: through collective organisation, small farmers can share the costs of certification, processing, and marketing, thereby increasing their chances of market success.

To facilitate better understanding of the quality schemes designed to promote and protect local agro-food products in Romania and across the European Union, we have developed a comparative table that synthesises the most relevant information: scheme name, main characteristics, year of implementation, and key observations. The table is followed by a conclusion that

contextualises these data in relation to the development potential of the traditional agri-food sector.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research approach adopted in this article is qualitative in nature, combining an extensive review of the scholarly literature with a case study focused on the Bucovina region. The research process unfolded in several stages. First, an extensive documentary analysis was conducted, examining scientific sources and relevant official reports published between 2018 and 2025, with the aim of identifying major trends related to consumption, production, and policy frameworks for promoting local agri-food products in Romania. Subsequently, academic journal articles, national scientific works, official statistics, and strategic documents were consulted. This theoretical stage laid the foundation for understanding the key concepts and the broader contextual landscape.

In the second stage, Bucovina was selected as a case study to explore in depth how market opportunities for local products materialize within a concrete regional context. The choice of Bucovina was motivated by its well-established reputation for traditional products and its active local promotion initiatives, which provide a rich setting for observing both good practices and specific challenges. The case study involved collecting region-specific information through multiple methods: analysis of local documents, as well as informal interviews and discussions with local stakeholders conducted between 1 March and 15 April 2025. Furthermore, concrete market initiatives in Bucovina were examined—from farmers' markets and mobile fairs to the participation of local producers in international exhibitions—in order to capture how short food supply chains operate and which marketing strategies are employed.

The collected data were interpreted using a descriptive-interpretative analytical approach. The findings synthesise key insights at both the national level and within Bucovina, highlighting market opportunities (such as the growing consumer demand for

local products) and persistent barriers (including certification and distribution challenges). In the discussion section, the results are compared with the existing literature and with similar cases, emphasising novel elements and examples of best practice.

The Bucovina case study is presented in a dedicated section, offering concrete examples and outlining the good practices identified, which may also be transferable to other regions. It should be noted that the main limitations of the research stem from its predominantly qualitative and exploratory character. While this approach provides rich contextual insights, it may limit the generalisability of the findings to the entire country. Nonetheless, the triangulation of sources—academic, statistical, and local—ensures a robust foundation for formulating well-grounded conclusions and policy recommendations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The analysis reveals a series of positive trends that represent market opportunities for local agri-food products in Romania. First, consumer demand for traditional products is high. A recent study on consumer perceptions indicated that the vast majority of respondents (approximately 90%) consume or are interested in Romanian traditional food products (Soare et al., 2023). More specifically, 89.8% of survey participants expressed explicit interest in such products, while fewer than 10% were uninterested or undecided—though some in the latter category may still develop interest in the future. These figures confirm a broad population-wide inclination toward local products, an interest that transcends demographic categories. Consumers associate these foods with positive attributes—tradition, authenticity, and quality—and perceive them as part of a healthier lifestyle. A significant proportion (68%) of respondents declared a preference for healthy traditional food over “fast-food” products, and younger generations are becoming increasingly informed and conscientious in their dietary choices. This shift towards local and healthy diets constitutes a market opportunity, suggesting that important consumer

segments—including younger cohorts—can be cultivated and retained through appropriate promotion of local products.

Another notable finding concerns the diversification and expansion of the supply of officially certified traditional products. According to the MADR data synthesised earlier, Romania currently has over 700 certified traditional food products, covering a wide spectrum: dairy products and cheeses, meat products, bakery goods, processed fruits and vegetables (jams, vegetable spreads), beverages, and honey. This extensive portfolio indicates the presence of a large number of small producers who have invested in formalising the traditional status of their products. Moreover, the very high number of certified mountain products (over 1,300)

reflects Romania's potential in the premium niche market, given that the "Mountain Product" label is associated with pristine ecological areas and environmentally beneficial extensive farming practices. Many of these mountain products are concentrated precisely in hilly and mountainous regions such as Bucovina, which represents a competitive advantage for the studied area.

To highlight the main directions in the evolution of the local agri-food market in Romania, the table below presents a synthesis of the research results. These findings encompass consumer interest, diversification of supply, penetration into the retail sector, and the niche potential of certified products, outlining clear opportunities for the development of this sector.

Table No. 2: National Trends in the Market for Local Agri-Food Products in Romania

Trend	Description
High consumer demand for traditional products	Studies show that approximately 90% of Romanian consumers express interest in or regularly consume traditional agri-food products. Consumers associate these foods with authenticity, quality, and healthier dietary choices, with 68% preferring traditional, healthy foods over fast-food alternatives.
Diversification and expansion of certified traditional products	Romania currently has over 700 certified traditional food products, ranging from dairy and meat products to bakery goods, processed fruits and vegetables, honey, and beverages. This reflects the increasing interest of small producers in formalising the traditional status of their products.
Growth of certified mountain products	With more than 1,300 certified mountain products, Romania demonstrates significant potential in the premium niche associated with clean ecological areas and extensive farming practices. Many of these products originate from hilly and mountainous regions such as Bucovina.
Presence of local products in modern retail chains	Certain categories of local products have achieved strong retail penetration: for example, 100% of eggs and over 94% of milk products on shelves in selected supermarkets are Romanian. Even in competitive categories such as vegetables, at least half of the assortment is domestically sourced, signalling retailer openness where consistent quality and quantity can be ensured.
Increasing opportunities for small producers through supply chain integration	Small producers can access wider markets by forming associations, collaborating with processors, or integrating into modern distribution chains. Organized cooperation supports better logistics, branding, and market reach.

The study also revealed several insights regarding the presence of local products on the shelves of large retail chains—an important aspect of emerging market opportunities. Although traditional products are primarily distributed through local markets and direct sales, certain categories have managed to achieve substantial penetration in modern retail chains. For example, an analysis conducted in 2024 on the assortments of two supermarkets in Bucharest found that, for certain basic product

categories, the share of Romanian products was remarkably high: for eggs, 100% of the products on the shelves originated from Romania, while for milk, over 94% were Romanian brands [23]. Even in the case of vegetables—where imported products represent strong competition—at least half of the assortment was domestically sourced.

This suggests that when local production can ensure consistent quantity and quality (as in the case of dairy, eggs, and certain vegetables), major retail chains are

willing to include Romanian products in their offerings. For small producers, this may translate into a potential market opportunity, particularly if they manage to form associations or collaborate with processors who can integrate them into modern distribution chains.

Case Study: Bucovina – Best Practices and Local Challenges

Bucovina (the southern part within Romania, mainly Suceava County) is a region with rich gastronomic traditions, renowned for dairy products (fresh cheese, whey cheese, smoked cheese), meat products (sausages and smoked pastrami), bee products (honey, syrups), and preserved foods (mushroom spreads, wild berry jams). Over the years, more than one hundred food products from this area have been certified as traditional by the Ministry of Agriculture—ranging from Horodniceni cheese and Izvorul Alb smoked cheese to Bosanci smoked pastrami [24]. However, no Bucovina product has (yet) achieved EU-level Protected Geographical Indication (PGI) status, highlighting an untapped opportunity for international branding.

Producer Association – The Case of “Produs în Bucovina”

A notable best practice in Bucovina is the existence of local producer associations designed to promote the region’s products through an integrated approach. The “Produs în Bucovina” Association, founded in 2009 by 25 founding members, is a pioneering example in this regard. This non-governmental organization has assumed the mission of promoting Bucovina’s products both in Romania and abroad. Today, the association comprises dozens of members across all agri-food sectors: meat and dairy farms, beekeepers, fruit producers, traditional bakers and confectioners, and even a local craft beer producer. This diverse membership demonstrates the integrated vision—the regional brand “Produs în Bucovina” encompasses a wide basket of local specialties, generating recognition and trust among consumers.

Through its initiatives, the Association has organized local fairs and participated in national exhibitions, enhancing visibility for

its members. A notable accomplishment is the partnership with the “Produs de Cluj” Association, which enabled Bucovina producers to sell their goods at events in Cluj and vice versa, thus expanding their market beyond traditional geographic boundaries. This exchange brought mutual benefits: producers gained access to new consumers, while the public in different parts of the country had the opportunity to discover new products, strengthening the national network of traditional Romanian foods [25].

Local Fairs and Markets

A successful initiative in Suceava is the “Din Drag de Bucovina” Mobile Market, a periodic market dedicated exclusively to local producers. It serves as a launching platform for small farmers and artisanal food producers, offering them direct access to consumers. One example of the visibility generated by this market is its role during the AgroExpo Bucovina 2025 agricultural fair, where it became a central attraction, allowing visitors to purchase natural local foods, including traditional fasting products [26].

Such events blend commercial, educational, and cultural components: the public encounters the story behind the products, the people who make them, and gains a deeper understanding of the added local value. The mobile market has also become an external promotional platform: products represented by members of the “Gustă din Bucovina” Association were showcased at the 2025 International Green Week (Grüne Woche) in Berlin, Germany [27]. This participation, supported by the Ministry of Agriculture and the Suceava Agricultural Directorate, enabled the international promotion of Bucovina’s gastronomy, highlighting the authentic taste of local natural products and the quality certifications they hold (traditional, mountain, organic). This is a clear example of best practices in which authorities directly support small producers in reaching wider markets.

Examples of Successful Local Producers

The case study identified several local businesses from Bucovina that illustrate how tradition blends with innovation and entrepreneurial spirit [28]:

1. **“Văcuța Ica” Farm (Verești, Suceava)** – a small dairy farm that has obtained Traditional Product certification for its cheeses. The farm operates under an integrated “from farm to fork” model, controlling the entire cycle from animal feed to final product. This model ensures consistent quality and traceability, serving as an example of small-scale vertical integration.

2. **Bucovina BeeZum (Volovăț, Suceava)** – an apiculture business started by a young entrepreneur who manages approximately 500 bee colonies. Its products (polyfloral honey, acacia honey, and derivatives such as propolis) are certified as Mountain Products and Organic, guaranteeing both clean mountain origin and the absence of chemical residues. This combination of certifications allows access to premium markets (health stores and exports to countries seeking organic products). BeeZum demonstrates how a local producer can orient toward superior quality and sustainability, harnessing Bucovina’s natural advantages.

3. **Strămoșia SRL (Bălcăuți, Suceava)** – a small meat processing unit run by a young couple (the Popescu family) who revived traditional pork recipes. They certified five traditional products (chișcă, cured muscle, haiducești smoked breast, pork jowl, and sausages), all made from pigs raised on their own farm. By integrating livestock raising, processing, and selling through their own shop, their business also follows the “farm to fork” model and ensures maximum authenticity. Strămoșia highlights the region’s gastronomic heritage (as its name suggests) and shows that young entrepreneurs are willing to continue ancestral food craftsmanship while adapting it to contemporary demands.

4. **“Bunătăți de la țară din Inima Bucovinei” (Cajvana,**

Suceava) – an initiative of the Covalschi family, who returned to their native village after several years abroad. They decided to valorize local vegetables and fruits using traditional recipes inherited from their grandparents, producing natural spreads, jams, and preserves with no artificial additives. This story is an emotional example of the diaspora returning to agriculture: the experience gained abroad, combined with nostalgia for home, led to a local business that revives culinary heritage. Today, their products are present at fairs and appreciated for their authenticity, inspiring other young people to see Bucovina’s villages not only as places of departure but also as places with opportunities for return.

These examples of best practices underscore several key elements: most of these businesses emphasize certification and quality, the narrative behind the product (which becomes part of the marketing strategy), and value chain integration to maintain control over quality and costs. They also benefit from collective promotion (fairs, associations) and demonstrate adaptability—whether through modern technologies (professional beekeeping, authorized processing units) or through innovation in presentation and packaging.

Specific Challenges in Bucovina

Despite the many successes, producers in Bucovina also face notable challenges. One concerns infrastructure and logistics: the distance from major urban centres leads to higher logistical costs for delivering fresh products (for instance, it is costly for a farmer from the Bucovina mountains to supply a shop in Bucharest on a regular basis with fresh cheeses). A possible solution could be cooperation among producers for joint transport or the development of online sales supported by an appropriate cold chain—both of which, however, require investment.

Another challenge is generational continuity: many traditional productions rely on the know-how of elderly artisans or farmers. If younger generations do not take over these occupations, there is a risk that

certain products will disappear once current producers retire. This is why initiatives such as those of the Covalschi family or the young entrepreneurs from Strămoșia are vital, and why public authorities could design support mechanisms specifically for young rural entrepreneurs (grants, gastronomic mentorship programmes with traditional masters, etc.).

Finally, access to finance and broader markets remains a cross-cutting challenge. Although European funds are available, bureaucracy and lack of information can discourage small producers from applying. Associations such as “Produce în Bucovina” can play a role in facilitating access, but public policies also need to simplify

procedures and provide advisory services. In terms of markets, Bucovina could benefit from stronger national promotion: the tourism brand of Bucovina (currently associated mainly with monasteries and natural landscapes) could be expanded to clearly include the gastronomic component, making culinary tourism a priority in county-level strategies.

Although Bucovina is one of the regions with remarkable agri-food potential—thanks to its traditions, biodiversity, and cultural identity—local producers face a series of systemic and contextual challenges. The table below summarises these difficulties, along with relevant field examples and possible solutions proposed in the research.

Table No. 3: Specific Challenges Faced by Agri-Food Producers in Bucovina

Challenge	Description	Cases	Possible solutions
Poor infrastructure and logistics	Distance from major urban centres increases transport and distribution costs, especially for perishable products.	Mountain-area farmers unable to deliver consistently to Bucharest	Cooperation for joint transport, investment in cold chains, online sales with integrated logistics
Low generational continuity	Young people do not take over traditional crafts and agricultural activities, creating a risk that some products will disappear when older producers retire.	Local artisans without direct successors, e.g. individual cases from Strămoșia	Grants for young people, gastronomic mentorship, promotion of applied rural education
Difficult access to finance	Although European funds exist, bureaucracy and lack of consultancy and information discourage small producers from applying.	Farmers without support in drafting project applications	Simplification of procedures, free public consultancy, an enhanced role for associations (e.g. “Produce în Bucovina”)
Low national visibility	Local products are insufficiently promoted on markets outside the region; the tourism brand of Bucovina does not clearly include the culinary component.	Tourism limited to monasteries, with weak promotion of gastronomy	Integrating gastronomy into tourism strategies, national campaigns for certified products
Fragmentation and lack of cooperation	Many producers work individually, without cooperative networks that would allow them access to larger markets or collective investments.	Only part of producers are members of “Produce în Bucovina”	Support for the creation of cooperatives, policies that encourage local partnerships

Source: authors’ elaboration based on case studies

The case study therefore illustrates a microcosm in which both success factors—cooperation, diversity, certification, and ad hoc support from authorities—and aspects requiring improvement—infrastructure, youth involvement, and expansion towards national and international markets—are present. The main lesson is that when the local community joins forces (producers, authorities, NGOs), traditional products can become a driver of local development, but this effort must be

sustained and scaled up through coherent policies.

Identified Market Opportunities

Based on the information collected, several opportunity areas can be identified for the market of local and traditional agri-food products in Romania:

- **Integration into rural and gastronomic tourism:** Local culinary offerings have become a pillar of tourism attractiveness in rural areas. In Bucovina, for instance, almost half of

tourists (48.9% in a sample studied) indicated traditional gastronomy as an important factor that enriched their experience, after natural landscapes (74.6%) and local hospitality (56.6%) [3]. This highlights the synergy between local products and tourism, opening up opportunities for producers to sell directly to visitors, agritourism guesthouses, or local-themed restaurants. A constant flow of tourists, both domestic and foreign, creates seasonal markets where the price paid for authenticity is often higher than on the general market, thus increasing the profitability of these products.

• **Domestic urban market interest in tradition:** In large cities, consumers increasingly seek products that evoke the “taste of the past” or are perceived as healthy and artisanal. The emergence of delicatessens and traditional product shops in urban centres (including specialised chains) confirms this demand. Some counties have organised inter-regional promotion events, bringing local products into markets in other cities. The collaboration between the “*Produs în Bucovina*” and “*Produs de Cluj*” associations is a successful example whereby Bucovinian and Transylvanian producers have exhibited each other’s products at fairs in Suceava and Cluj, attracting new buyers from outside their home regions [25]. Such partnerships broaden the market horizon of local producers and demonstrate the appetite of urban consumers for traditional specialties from different regions.

• **Emerging institutional support:** Although small producers have long acted individually or informally organised, recent years have seen growing governmental attention to promoting local production. The creation of the Agency for the Quality and Marketing of Agri-Food Products (envisaged

since 2022) signals political will to institutionalise the promotion of these products [29]. Through its objectives, this agency is meant to promote quality schemes and guarantee the authenticity of traditional and mountain products. If implemented effectively, such a structure could facilitate producers’ access to markets (for example, by organising participation in international fairs such as the 2025 Green Week in Berlin) [30] and launch communication campaigns to educate the public. At the same time, the 2023–2027 Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) includes measures dedicated to short supply chains and local markets, which Romania can use to co-finance local projects. One example is the encouragement of agricultural cooperatives as a means to improve farmers’ market position—an aspect highlighted by policymakers, with cooperation being viewed as “the only way” for small farms to thrive in a competitive market.

• **Quality certifications and strong local brands:** The possibility of obtaining Traditional Product, Mountain Product, or Organic certifications represents a differentiation opportunity. Many products from Bucovina already benefit from such certifications—for example, cheeses certified as traditional products or honey certified as mountain and organic. These labels add value and credibility, enabling producers to reach consumer segments willing to pay a premium for guaranteed quality. In the medium term, there is also the possibility that some emblematic products (e.g. specific cheeses, meat products, or bakery goods from Bucovina) may obtain European recognition (PGI/PDO), which would further open markets (both domestic and export). The export potential in niche segments should not be overlooked: the Romanian diaspora in Western Europe

and enthusiasts of Eastern European gastronomy already constitute a market for products such as vegetable spreads (zacusca), fruit preserves, cheeses, and traditional cured meats. Once protected and promoted, Bucovinian products could become more visible in ethnic or gourmet shops abroad.

• **Convergence with ecological and health trends:** Local products, often obtained in small, extensive farms with limited use of chemicals, align well with the growing preference for ecological and sustainable foods. For example, honey and other bee products from Bucovina certified as organic and mountain enjoy a dual reputation—both as traditional and as “clean” products from nature [28]. Environmentally conscious consumers may see in local products a lower carbon footprint (due to shorter transport distances) and a contribution to biodiversity (many traditional products use local breeds or varieties, helping to conserve them). Moreover, recent crises (e.g. the COVID-19 pandemic) have stimulated interest in the resilience of short food supply chains and local provisioning, which constitutes an opportunity for Romanian villages to become important suppliers for cities in times of uncertainty.

The above results outline an optimistic picture of opportunities but also highlight the need to address concurrent challenges. The following section discusses these aspects in detail, integrating the findings into a critical and comparative perspective, before delving further into the Bucovina case study.

The analysis confirms the initial hypothesis that there is significant market potential for local agri-food products in Romania, yet full realisation of this potential depends on how actors—producers, authorities, distributors, and consumers—manage to collaborate and overcome current obstacles.

High demand: The fact that around 90% of consumers declare an interest in

traditional products [3] does not automatically translate into an equivalent market share for these products. While traditional products dominate supply at local markets and specialised fairs, their share in modern retail remains modest (with the exception of the basic categories mentioned earlier). Thus, there is a gap between declared attitude and actual consumption behaviour, partly due to the accessibility of these products. Urban consumers, for example, appreciate products from Bucovina or Maramureş but can only purchase them occasionally, at fairs or via direct online orders, as they are not readily available in neighbourhood supermarkets. This underscores the importance of expanding distribution channels—a topic that future policies must address (for example, by facilitating cooperation with retailers or supporting alternative schemes such as home-delivered product baskets).

The role of producer associations emerges as a decisive factor. The Bucovina case study shows that where producers have organised into associations such as “Produs în Bucovina” or “Gustă din Bucovina”, the visibility and market access of local products have increased significantly. Associations can provide a common marketing platform, build strong regional brands, and negotiate more effectively with public authorities for support. The collaboration between Bucovina and Cluj County in mutual promotion of traditional products shows that such structures can transcend local boundaries, creating an inter-regional network of traditional markets. By contrast, in areas where producers remain fragmented, opportunities can be missed—for example, an isolated producer may lack the resources to participate in an international fair or to certify their product, whereas an association can cover these needs for its members.

A key discussion point concerns public support and policy frameworks. Over the last decade, Romania has launched multiple initiatives to support small producers—from European funding via the National Rural Development Programme (NRDP), including sub-measures for short supply chains and local markets, to pilot projects such as the “Casa de Comerţ Agroalimentar Unirea”.

Unfortunately, not all of these initiatives have achieved the expected success. The “Casa Unirea” project, conceived in 2018–2019 to create a chain of shops selling Romanian products, faced administrative and financial difficulties and did not manage to fulfil its initial mission. This failure illustrates the difficulty of direct state intervention in a market that requires flexibility and commercially oriented management. By contrast, the recent shift towards an agency model under public–private partnership (such as the quality and marketing agency announced by the Ministry of Agriculture) appears more promising, as it actively involves the private sector and producer associations in promotion-related decisions. The key will be for this agency (and other support instruments, such as aid schemes for processing or external promotion) to operate transparently and efficiently, focusing on the real needs of local producers: logistics, consultancy, and market access.

From an environmental sustainability perspective, the discussion reveals an inherent advantage of local products: in many cases they are synonymous with traditional, environmentally friendly agriculture. Bucovina, for instance, has extensive areas of natural pastures where livestock are raised extensively, and traditional cheese-making often involves low-impact techniques (no chemical additives, use of local resources such as wood for smoking, etc.). By promoting these products, one indirectly supports the conservation of local landscapes and biodiversity, since farmers have an economic incentive to maintain traditional agricultural practices (e.g. seasonal mountain grazing, breeding local animal varieties) that are beneficial for the environment. Short supply chains also reduce long-distance transport, lowering the carbon footprint of food. In this way, promoting local products aligns with environmental objectives and can be integrated into circular economy strategies and sustainable rural development.

However, there are ecological and safety challenges as well: ensuring food safety and consistent quality in the context of artisanal production. Consumers love the idea of “traditional”, but they do not compromise

on modern quality requirements. Therefore, institutions must ensure control and producer training in compliance with sanitary standards, without eroding authenticity. Training programmes and investments in compliant micro-processing units (e.g. small village dairies or meat processing facilities, mobile or cooperative) are needed to reconcile tradition with current standards.

Comparing the situation in Bucovina and Romania with that of other European countries reveals differences in the maturity of local product markets. In Western Europe (France, Italy, Spain), local products and quality schemes have long been integrated into commercial circuits, and consumers are accustomed to seeking local AOCs and PDOs. Romania is still in a catching-up phase: domestically, important steps have been taken (numerous nationally certified producers), but externally visibility remains limited. It can be expected that in the coming years, as more products apply for PGI/PDO status and rural tourism continues to develop, the “Romanian traditional product” label will gain recognition. A positive emerging phenomenon is that of local gastronomic festivals (e.g. festivals dedicated to stews, mountain products, etc.), which not only attract visitors but also create networks between producers and chefs, laying the groundwork for a consolidated market for these products.

In conclusion, we can state that local agri-food products in Romania are positioned at the intersection of a favourable context—with growing domestic demand and increasingly explicit public support—but that turning identified opportunities into concrete results requires coordinated action. The Bucovina case study offers a grass-roots view of how these trends manifest in a local community, illustrating both achievements and difficulties, and providing valuable lessons.

To fully harness the potential of local agri-food products and transform them into a vector for sustainable development in Romania, we propose the following public policies and strategic initiatives as direct and applicable outcomes of the research:

1. Supporting certification and protection of local products

Simplifying attestation and certification procedures, alongside granting vouchers or financial support to small producers, is essential for expanding the portfolio of officially recognised products. Active support is needed for obtaining European certifications (PGI/PDO) for region-specific products.

2. Developing local markets and short supply chains

Investments in the infrastructure of mobile markets, modernisation of traditional fairs, and creation of public-private online platforms that connect local producers directly with urban consumers.

3. Improving marketing and regional branding

Designing a national strategy for promoting traditional products and coordinating participation in international fairs under strong regional brands (e.g. “Taste of Bucovina”). Supporting producer associations in creating promotional materials and in digitalising their public presence.

4. Supporting cooperatives and associative forms

Providing fiscal incentives, logistical support, and consultancy for developing cooperatives that integrate

production, processing, and distribution. Cooperation is essential for increasing delivery capacity and bargaining power on the market.

5. Integrating local products into tourism and gastronomy

Implementing county-level strategies for gastronomic tourism, developing culinary routes, supporting themed festivals, and creating a certification system for restaurants using local ingredients.

6. Education and training for sustainability

Training programmes for producers in areas such as safe traditional processing, digital marketing, and management, as well as integrating food education in schools to cultivate preferences for local products from an early age.

7. Innovation and digitalisation

Supporting the digitalisation of local businesses (e-commerce platforms, eco-friendly packaging, online branding) through grants and mentoring offered in partnership with universities and NGOs.

To provide better visualisation and understanding of the direct impact of these policies, the table below summarises the main directions proposed in the research, along with concrete measures and expected effects on the local agri-food sector.

Table No. 4: Policy Proposals for Supporting Local Agri-Food Products in Romania

Strategic domain	Proposed measures	Type of intervention	Estimated impact
Certification and protection	Simplifying procedures, grants for certification, support for PGI/PDO	Financial, legislative, administrative	Increase in the number of certified products; access to premium markets
Local markets and short chains	Investments in mobile markets and fairs, online platforms for direct sales	Infrastructure, digitalisation	Bringing producers closer to consumers; reduced distribution costs

Strategic domain	Proposed measures	Type of intervention	Estimated impact
Regional marketing and branding	National strategy, participation in international fairs, support for digital branding and promotional materials	Communication, promotion	Increased visibility and attractiveness of Romanian products domestically and abroad
Cooperation and association	Fiscal incentives, consultancy, support for establishing integrated cooperatives (production–processing–distribution)	Economic, organisational	Higher competitiveness and capacity for consistent supply
Tourism and gastronomy	Development of culinary tourism, gastronomic routes, festivals, certification for restaurants using local ingredients	Tourism, culture	Integration of local products into tourism offerings; diversification of income sources
Education and training	Courses for producers (processing, marketing), food education in schools	Educational, formative	Strengthening rural know-how; increased informed demand for local products
Innovation and digitalisation	Grants for e-commerce platforms, online branding, eco-friendly packaging; partnerships with universities and NGOs	Technological, partnership-based	Modernisation of production and promotion; increased appeal to younger generations and global markets

Source: authors' elaboration based on research findings

We consider that implementing these policies will help transform local agri-food products from a limited niche into a strategic pillar of Romania's rural economy and national sustainability.

CONCLUSIONS

Promotion of local agri-food products represents one of the most promising pathways for sustainable development in Romania, in a global context in which consumers are increasingly attentive to the origin, quality, and social and environmental impact of food products. These products are not only carriers of economic value, but also repositories of collective memory,

gastronomic traditions, and local biodiversity. They connect producers and consumers through short and transparent supply chains, in which trust plays an essential role.

The research conducted in this article, combining an analysis of the national framework with a case study of the Bucovina region, confirms that there is genuine appetite for such products among both Romanian and international consumers. At the same time, it shows that when local producers join forces, benefit from institutional support, and gain access to modern promotional channels, they can achieve notable performance in terms of market penetration and consumer loyalty. The case of Bucovina clearly illustrates these

premises: the development of regional brands, participation in international fairs, involvement in gastronomic tourism, and product certification are concrete steps that have contributed to the valorisation of local agri-food heritage.

On the other hand, the analysis also revealed numerous challenges that limit the scaling-up of these good practices at national level: producer fragmentation, lack of access to major markets, excessive bureaucracy in certification processes, as well as an acute need for entrepreneurial and digital education in rural areas. In addition, a significant share of authentic agri-food production still relies on the know-how of older generations, which raises the issue of continuity if young people are not encouraged to take over and modernise these businesses.

In light of the above, we argue that an integrated, long-term approach is required from public authorities, private actors, and civil society. The policy proposals formulated in the final section—aimed at supporting

certification, developing local market infrastructure, strengthening associative forms, integrating products into tourism, and promoting education for sustainability—should not be viewed as isolated initiatives, but as components of a healthy and resilient local food ecosystem. Implementing these measures could transform local agri-food products from a niche sector into a strategic pillar of the rural economy and of the national brand.

Romania has sufficient natural, cultural, and human resources to become a relevant actor in the field of sustainable traditional food, both at European and global level. What remains is for these resources to be activated through coherent policies, intelligent institutional support, and, above all, through the genuine mobilisation of local communities around their own values. The promotion of local agri-food products is not merely an economic opportunity—it is a strategic mission for the future of rural Romania.

REFERENCES

1. Rana, J. C., & Bisht, I. S. (2023). Reviving smallholder hill farming by involving rural youth in food system transformation and promoting community-based agri-ecotourism: A case of Uttarakhand state in north-western India. *Sustainability*, 15(11), 8816, disponibil la: <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/15/11/8816>
2. Maikova, A. (2025). Nourishing Nostalgia: Modern Ex-Soviet Expatriates and their Foodways in the UAE (Master's thesis, Harvard University), disponibil la: <https://search.proquest.com/openview/8aa69cf8a6cce5383ebb885f9eb74c19/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>
3. Soare, I., Zugravu, C. L., & Zugravu, G. A. (2023). Research on consumer perception regarding traditional food products of Romania. *Foods*, 12(14), 2723, disponibil la: <https://www.mdpi.com/2304-8158/12/14/2723>
4. Juravle, A. I., Sasu, C., & Terec-Vlad, L. (2016). The destination image of Bucovina among Romanian tourists. *Cross-Cultural Management Journal*, 18(2), 139-150, disponibil la: <https://www.ceeol.com/search/article-detail?id=532161>
5. Simeanu, C., Andronachi, V. C., Usturoi, A., Davidescu, M. A., Mintăș, O. S., Hoha, G. V., & Simeanu, D. (2025). Rural Tourism: A Factor of Sustainable Development for the Traditional Rural Area of Bucovina, Romania. *Sustainability*, 17(8), 3604, disponibil la: <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/17/8/3604>
6. Nicu, I. C., & Stoleriu, C. C. (2019). Land use changes and dynamics over the last century around churches of Moldavia, Bukovina, Northern Romania—Challenges and future perspectives. *Habitat International*, 88, 101979, disponibil la: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0197397518301826>
7. Bahre, H. (2016). Case studies of cross-border cooperation in European tourism—perspectives and challenges for the cross-border region Bucovina/Oblast Tscherniwzi. *The USV Annals of Economics and Public Administration*, 16(1 (23)), 7-16, disponibil la: <https://annalsea.usv.ro/index.php/annals/article/download/996/958>
8. Postelnicu, C., & Dabija, D. C. (2016). Challenges and development prospects for tourism in Romania. *Ecoforum*, 5(1), 84-89, disponibil la: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2902613
9. Coserea, S. V. (2024). The Exodus of the Young Generation: The Reasons, Impact and Future of Youth Emigration from Romania. *Rev. Universitara Sociologie*, 280, disponibil la: https://heinonline.org/hol-cgi-bin/get_pdf.cgi?handle=hein.journals/rvusoclge2024&action=120
10. Chiesa, C. D., & Dekker, E. (2024). Communicating identity: how the symbolic meaning of goods creates different market types. *Review of Social Economy*, 82(1), 76-97, disponibil la: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00346764.2021.2019822>
11. Collado, L., Galaso, P., Menéndez, M. D. L. M., & Rodriguez Miranda, A. (2024). Environmental challenges and innovative responses of local agri-food

systems: a theoretical approach. *Competitiveness Review: An International Business Journal*, 34(5), 981-994, disponibil la:

<https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/CR-08-2023-0210/full/html>

12. Chukwurah, G. O., Okeke, F. O., Isimah, M. O., Enoguanbhor, E. C., Awe, F. C., Nnaemeka-Okeke, R. C., ... & Okeke, C. A. (2025). Cultural Influence of Local Food Heritage on Sustainable Development. *World*, 6(1), 10, disponibil la: <https://www.mdpi.com/2673-4060/6/1/10>

13. Rasulov, R. (2024). Optimization of direct supply chains in the restaurant industry: Addressing key challenges through technological innovation. *Economics of Development*, 23(3), 93-103, disponibil la:

<https://ecdev.com.ua/web/uploads/pdf/Economics%20of%20Development, 2024, Vol.%2023 No. 3-93-103.pdf>

14. Marsden, T., & Smith, E. (2005). Ecological entrepreneurship: sustainable development in local communities through quality food production and local branding. *Geoforum*, 36(4), 440-451, disponibil la: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S001671850400106X>

15. Berti, G., & Mulligan, C. (2016). Competitiveness of small farms and innovative food supply chains: The role of food hubs in creating sustainable regional and local food systems. *Sustainability*, 8(7), 616, disponibil la: <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/8/7/616>

16. Haggblade, S., Hazell, P. B., & Reardon, T. (2002). Strategies for stimulating poverty-alleviating growth in the rural nonfarm economy in developing countries, disponibil la:

<https://ageconsearch.umn.edu/record/16092/>

17. Bolognini, S. (2018). Food Diversity and Typicality in EU and in Italian Law: Protected Designations of Origin (PDOs); Protected Geographical Indications (PGIs); Traditional Speciality Guaranteed (TSGs). *Food Diversity Between Rights, Duties and Autonomies: Legal Perspectives for a Scientific, Cultural and Social Debate on the Right to Food and Agroecology*, 91-109, disponibil la:

https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-75196-2_5

18. https://www.economica.net/inca-trei-produse-romanesti-pot-ajunge-sa-fie-recunoscute-la-nivel-european_90693.html

19. https://www.newsbucovina.ro/featured/345811/deputatul-ioan-balan-catre-ministrul-agriculturii-din-cele-pestesuta-de-produse-traditionale-din-bucovina-pentru-cates-a-cerut-statut-de-produs-cu-indicatie-geografica-sau-cu-denumire-de-origine#:~:text=denumire%20de%20origine%20protejat%20C4%83%2C%20C3%AEEn_Dun%20C4%83re%20etc%20E2%80%9D%2C%20aratat%20C4%83%20loan%20B%20C4%83lan

20. ȘOMÎCU, A. G., & Vladu, M. (2023). Study regarding the implementation of national quality schemes for agri-food products-traditional Romanian

products. *Scientific Papers Series Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture & Rural Development*, 23(1), disponibil la:

https://managementjournal.usamv.ro/pdf/vol.23_1/Art82.pdf

21. <https://economediamedia.ro/romania-will-have-beginning-with-2022-a-quality-and-marketing-agency-for-agri-food->

22. <https://economediamedia.ro/romania-will-have-beginning-with-2022-a-quality-and-marketing-agency-for-agri-food->

23. Sterie, M. C. (2024). Local Food Products in Romania: Insights into Agricultural Production and Community Impact. *Revista de Management Comparat International*, 25(4), 732-740, disponibil la: <http://www.rmci.ase.ro/no25vol4/10.pdf>

24. <https://www.newsbucovina.ro/featured/345811/deputatul-ioan-balan-catre-ministrul-agriculturii-din-cele-pestesuta-de-produse-traditionale-din-bucovina-pentru-cates-a-cerut-statut-de-produs-cu-indicatie-geografica-sau-cu-denumire-de-origine#:~:text=%E2%80%9ESpre%20exemplu%2C%20numai%20la%20nivelul,a%20ar%20C4%83tat%20parlamentarul%20liberal%20sucevean>

25. <https://bucowinaplus.ro/2024/01/reteta-de-succes-asociatia-produs-in-bucovina-colaboreaza-cu-asociatia-produs-de-cluj#:~:text=Asocia%C8%9Bia%20E2%80%9DProducers%20C3%AEEn%20Bucovina%20E2%80%9D%20a,cu%2025%20de%20membri%20fondatori>

26. <https://glasulsucevei.ro/gheorghe-soldan-a-fost-prezent-la-agroexpo-bucovina-2025-targul-agricol-de-traditie-si-a-redeschis-portile-la-suceava-agroexpo-bucovina-trebuie-sa-redevina-cel-mai-mare-si-mai-important-eve#:~:text=Un%20punct%20de%20atrac%C8%9Bie%20este,de%20Asocia%C8%9Bia%20Cresc%C4%83torilor%20din%20Bucovina>

27. <https://visitbucovina.ro/evenimente/1286/bunatatiledin-piata-volanta-din-drag-de-bucovina-apartinand-membrilor-asociatiei-gusta-din-bucovina-prezente-la-expozitia-internationala-saptamana-verde-evenimen#:~:text=Participarea%20la%20acest%20eveniment%20ofer%C4%83,produs%20tradi%C8%9Bional%20C%20montan%20sau%20ecologic>

28. <https://visitbucovina.ro/evenimente/1286/bunatatiledin-piata-volanta-din-drag-de-bucovina-apartinand-membrilor-asociatiei-gusta-din-bucovina-prezente-la-expozitia-internationala-saptamana-verde-evenimen#:~:text=1,conceptului%20from%20farm%20o%20fork>

29. <https://economediamedia.ro/romania-will-have-beginning-with-2022-a-quality-and-marketing-agency-for-agri-food-products.html#:~:text=Romania%20will%20have%20C%20from%202022%20C,Adrian%20Oros%20C%20quoted%20by%20Agerpres>

30. <https://visitbucovina.ro/evenimente/1286/bunatatiledin-piata-volanta-din-drag-de-bucovina-apartinand-membrilor-asociatiei-gusta-din->

[bucovina-prezente-la-expozitia-internationala-saptamana-verde-evenimen/#:~:text=Participarea%20la%20acest%20eveniment%20ofer%C4%83,produs%20tradi%C8%9Bional%2C%20montan%20sau%20ecologic](#)

EVENTS & FESTIVAL TOURISM IN ROMANIA: AN ASSESSMENT OF BENEFITS, EXTERNALITIES, AND PLACE BRANDING

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This paper focuses on festivals in Romania and their reported links to tourism outcomes and benefits, externalities (both positive and negative), and place branding, in both rural and urban contexts. The scope covers music, cultural, and multi-genre events across multiple destinations. Owing to the heterogeneity in designs and indicators, the findings were integrated narratively, rather than through a meta-analytic statistical approach. Most studies describe short-term increases in visitation and local spending during event periods, with occasional references to longer stays. Branding effects are generally discussed in terms of media reach and online visibility, but measurement approaches vary. Reported externalities include congestion, noise, waste and pollution generation, and pressures on housing and public space, while the documentation of mitigation practices is uneven. Overall, the evidence base is geographically and methodologically uneven and remains largely descriptive, which limits inference. Finally, this review paper suggests future approaches in assessing the impact of events and festivals on local communities.

Keywords: event tourism; importance of events in tourism; events marketing; festival tourism

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INTRODUCTION

Events and festivals have shifted over the last decades from being occasional cultural celebrations to becoming central pillars of tourism development strategies and destination marketing worldwide. Framed under the umbrella of "event tourism", they are now seen as key motivators of travel and catalysts for urban regeneration and competitiveness (Getz, 2008; Negrușă et al., 2016).

A substantial body of research has analysed the multi-dimensional impacts of events, showing that festivals can generate sizable economic benefits (e.g. visitor spending, tax revenues, infrastructure investments), enrich local cultural life and social capital, and contribute to environmental initiatives, but can also produce negative externalities such as congestion, noise, pressure on public services, rising prices and perceived "festivalisation" of everyday life (Negrușă et al., 2016; Suli et al., 2024; Zetiu & Berteau, 2015)

This has led to a growing emphasis on sustainable event management and the need to assess not only direct benefits but also wider spillovers and related effects on residents, businesses and the urban environment.

Parallel to this literature, events have been increasingly conceptualised as strategic tools in place branding and destination-image building. Place-branding research underlines

how festivals and hallmark events can act as "flagship experiences" that signal a city's or region's personality, values and lifestyle, contributing to brand equity through memorable, emotionally loaded experiences and strong symbolic associations (Ciuculescu & Luca, 2025; Suli et al., 2024; Zetiu & Berteau, 2015). Events help differentiate destinations in a crowded marketplace, reinforce desired brand narratives, and can support long-term repositioning from "generic tourist destination" towards culturally distinctive, experience-based brands (Ciuculescu & Luca, 2025; Dumbrăveanu, 2009)

Romania represents a particularly interesting context for studying the externalities generated by events and place branding. Despite a rich natural and cultural tourism potential, Romanian tourism has historically been underexploited and remains constrained by infrastructural and institutional weaknesses (Cozac, 2024)

Early work on event tourism in Romania described the field as being in its infancy but with visible expansion, using case studies such as the Medieval Sighișoara Festival and the Stufstock festival in Vama Veche to profile Romanian event tourists and highlight management and marketing shortcomings (Tudoricu, 2008). More recent analyses argue that event tourism is one of the promising

avenues for diversifying the country's tourism offer, especially in urban destinations, and explicitly mention large festivals such as Untold in Cluj-Napoca as successful examples already integrated into development strategies (Cozac, 2024)

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The study adopts a qualitative research design based on document analysis, in order to examine how events and festival tourism in Romania are framed in terms of benefits, externalities and place branding. A qualitative content-analysis procedure was applied: documents were screened for relevance, classified by source type, territorial scale (national, regional, local) and event type, then examined, focusing on economic, socio-cultural and environmental benefits, positive and negative externalities and explicit or implicit references to destination image, brand associations, brand equity and the strategic use of events in branding.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Empirical studies on individual Romanian festivals have documented both the benefits and the externalities of these events. Impact assessments of the Transylvania International Film Festival (TIFF) in Cluj-Napoca show substantial economic effects as well as strong contributions to the city's cultural vitality, education levels and international visibility (Negrușă et al., 2016)

In a similar vein, research on the Untold music festival highlights significant increases in hotel occupancy and tourism revenues during the event period (Barbu & Nicolescu, 2024), but also points to perceived social and environmental costs, such as crowding, noise, tensions regarding public space and concerns over the balance between residents' quality of life and tourism growth (Moiescu et al., 2019; Pavelea, 2017)

Together with case studies on Transylvanian cultural events and festivals in other Central and Eastern European post-socialist cities, these findings suggest that festivals can play a structurally important role in reshaping city images and tourism trajectories, while simultaneously generating contested externalities that need careful governance (Suli et al., 2024)

At the national level, Romania's attempts to build a coherent tourism brand—most visibly through the “Explore the Carpathian Garden”

campaign—have been widely debated in terms of effectiveness, consistency and governance (Dumbrăveanu, 2009; Stefan et al., 2024).

Local development strategies and cultural policies for Cluj-Napoca, Iași, Sibiu or Timișoara explicitly frame large-scale events and dense “festival calendars” as levers for creative-city positioning, improved quality of life and enhanced tourism competitiveness (Sava & Badulescu, 2018; Tomiuc, 2016)

Case studies on Iași's International Festival of Education (FIE) illustrates how a multi-event programme is used to reposition the city as a national cultural hub and to support the bid for European Capital of Culture, with documented increases in visibility, partnerships among cultural institutions and a stronger association between the city and education-culture narratives (Zetiu & Berteau, 2015)

Similarly, analyses of “Night of the Museums” in Bucharest and Oradea report very positive perceptions of the event's cultural, social and image-building functions—participants rate its role in promoting museums, improving destination image and generating social cohesion as “very good”, while local tourism documents present it as a flagship product that diversifies the urban offer and extends visiting hours (Herman et al., 2023)

In line with these examples, national and regional tourism strategies consistently associate festivals with “hard” benefits (visitor numbers, overnight stays, local spending) and “soft” gains such as civic pride, cosmopolitan atmospheres and stronger place attachment.

At the same time, the broader place-branding literature and policy documents reveal tensions and gaps that nuance this celebratory narrative. Studies on residents' perceptions of tourism development in regions like the Galați-Brăila conurbation show that locals tend to support tourism when they see clear economic and cultural benefits, including opportunities created by fairs and festivals, but also voice concerns about environmental pressures and uneven distribution of gains (Șorcaru et al., 2022)

More recent work on Brașov's cultural brand argues that moving from a generic tourist postcard image to a sustainable cultural city brand requires not only more year-round festivals and nightlife, but also stronger participation of local cultural managers and Generation Z audiences in co-creating the city's narrative (Ciuculescu & Luca, 2025)

In rural Bontida (Cluj County), studies of the Electric Castle festival show that residents perceive clear economic and socio-cultural benefits—seasonal employment, new business opportunities, improved infrastructure and heightened community pride—while at the same time noting problems such as congestion, noise, waste generation and strain on local services during the event days (Chiciudean et al., 2021).

Festival-generated funds and partnerships are repeatedly highlighted for their role in restoring Bánffy Castle and promoting local heritage, and recent sustainability reports emphasise waste-reduction, public-transport incentives and other “green” measures, illustrating how event organisers explicitly frame Electric Castle as both an engine of rural tourism and a laboratory for sustainable festival practices.

In medium-sized and large cities, the Sibiu International Theatre Festival (FITS) and the George Enescu International Festival in Bucharest emerge as emblematic cases where festivals are explicitly linked to city and country branding. Analyses of Sibiu show that FITS, together with the 2007 European Capital of Culture title, has driven sustained growth in tourist arrivals, extended the season and supported the development of a diversified creative economy, while municipal marketing documents systematically use FITS as a core symbol of Sibiu’s multicultural, “European” identity (Mari et al., 2020; Nicula & Chindriş, 2017).

For Bucharest, case studies on the Enescu Festival document high hotel-occupancy rates, thousands of foreign visitors and strong international media visibility, leading authors and official communications alike to describe the festival as a “cultural diplomacy” instrument and a de facto national brand for Romania (Alexe & Tapardel, 2013; Popescu & Corbos, 2012).

Coastal tourism strategies and resident-attitude surveys from Constanţa add yet another layer, linking the Neversea beach festival to spikes in visitor numbers, local spending and city image improvement, but also to concerns over overtourism, crowding, mobility restrictions and the heavy logistical footprint of hosting over 200,000 participants on a narrow strip of urban beach (Moraru et al., 2021)

Taken together, the findings indicate that events and festivals in Romania are widely

framed as strategic assets for destination differentiation and place branding, but that questions of who participates, who benefits, how externalities are governed and how coherent the resulting national image is remain only partially addressed in the official discourse.

CONCLUSIONS

The study adopts a qualitative research design based exclusively on document analysis to examine how events and festival tourism in Romania are framed in terms of benefits, externalities and place branding. The empirical corpus comprises national and regional tourism strategies, local development and cultural policies, city branding and marketing documents, festival programmes and reports, funding applications, press releases and promotional materials produced by DMOs and event organisers, complemented by grey literature (consultancy and industry reports, NGO publications), media coverage of major festivals, and academic studies on Romanian event tourism and place branding; basic statistical reports on visitor flows and accommodation capacity are used only to contextualise this qualitative evidence. A structured qualitative content-analysis procedure was applied: documents were screened for relevance, classified by source type, territorial scale (national, regional, local) and event type, then coded using an analytical frame informed by international literature, focusing on economic, socio-cultural and environmental benefits, positive and negative externalities (e.g. crowding, noise, pressure on infrastructure) and explicit or implicit references to destination image, brand associations, brand equity and the strategic use of events in branding. Comparing coded material across destinations and event types made it possible to identify dominant narratives, tensions and gaps, and to inform the study’s hypotheses on the relationships between perceived benefits, externalities and the evolution of place brands in Romania.

REFERENCES

- Alexe, F.-A., & Tapardel, A. (2013). Case study: The impact of organizing the George Enescu international festival on the branding and promotion of Bucharest City. *International Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Sciences*, 1(5), 241.
- Barbu, A., & Nicolescu, L. (2024). *Quantitative Insights: Analyzing Untold Festival's Impact on Hotel Occupancy Rates and Attendance Growth*

- Trends in Cluj-Napoca.*
<https://doi.org/10.24818/BASIQ/2024/10/032>
- Chiciudean, D. I., Harun, R., Muresan, I. C., Arion, F. H., & Chiciudean, G. O. (2021). Rural Community-Perceived Benefits of a Music Festival. *Societies*, 11(2), 59.
<https://www.mdpi.com/2075-4698/11/2/59>
- Ciuculescu, L., & Luca, F. A. (2025). Developing a Sustainable Cultural Brand for Tourist Cities: Insights from Cultural Managers and the Gen Z Community in Braşov, Romania. *Sustainability* (2071-1050), 17(8).
- Cozac, E. (2024). STRATEGIES FOR TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN ROMANIA. *Analele Universitatii din Oradea, Fascicula Ecotoxicologie, Zootehnie si Tehnologii în Industria Alimentara*, 23.
- Dumbrăveanu, D. (2009). Place branding: a challenging process for Romania. *Human Geographies: Journal of Studies and Research in Human Geography*, 3(2), 39-48.
- Getz, D. (2008). Event tourism: Definition, evolution, and research. *Tourism Management*, 29(3), 403-428.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2007.07.017>
- Herman, G., Caciora, T., Grama, V., Baias, S., Beatón, M., Green, I., Hassan, T., Codrut, B., Andriamampianina, H., & Gozner, M. (2023). TOURIST PERCEPTION OF THE "NIGHT OF THE MUSEUMS. *Geojournal of Tourism and Geosites*, 486-492.
<https://doi.org/10.30892/gtg.47215-1047>
- Mari, M., Pintilii, R., Gruia, A., Grecu, A., & Maruntelu, A. (2020). SIBIU CAPITAL OF CULTURE STATUS IMPACT ON THE CREATIVE ECONOMY.
<https://doi.org/10.18509/GBP.2020.40>
- Moiescu, O., Gică, O., Coros, M., & Yallop, A. (2019). The UNTOLD story: Event tourism's negative impact on residents' community life and well-being. *Worldwide Hospitality and Tourism Themes*, 11, 492-505.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/WHATT-06-2019-0036>
- Moraru, A.-D., Duhnea, C., Barbulescu, A., Juganaru, M., & Juganaru, I.-D. (2021). Residents' Attitude toward Tourism—Do the Benefits Outweigh the Downsides? The Case of Constanta, Romania. *Sustainability*, 13(2), 882.
<https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/13/2/882>
- Negruşa, A. L., Toader, V., Rus, R. V., & Cosma, S. A. (2016). Study of Perceptions on Cultural Events' Sustainability. *Sustainability*, 8(12), 1269.
<https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/8/12/1269>
- Nicula, V., & Chindriş, C. (2017). Implications of festival culture in tourism development in the city of Sibiu. *REVISTA ECONOMICĂ*, 69(6), 120-127.
- Pavelea, A. M. (2017). Analiza impactului social al festivalului Untold asupra rezidenţilor municipiului Cluj-Napoca [social impact, Social Representation Theory, Untold festival, Cluj-Napoca]. *Revista Transilvană de Ştiinţe Administrative*, 18.
<https://rtsa.ro/rtsa/index.php/rtsa/article/view/549>
- Popescu, R.-I., & Corbos, R.-A. (2012). The role of festivals and cultural events in the strategic development of cities. Recommendations for urban areas in Romania. *Informatica Economica*, 16(4), 19.
- Sava, D., & Badulescu, A. (2018). Festivals as cultural activities—combinations of economic and social benefits. *Oradea Journal of Business and Economics*, 3(special), 27-35.
- Stefan, C., Ionescu, L., & Andreiana, V. (2024). Romanian Tourism Branding Model. *Valahian Journal of Economic Studies*, 15, 73-86.
<https://doi.org/10.2478/vjes-2024-0006>
- Suli, D., Boros, L., & Pal, V. (2024). The role of music festivals in shaping destination branding and image in two Hungarian regional centers. *Geo Journal of Tourism and Geosites*, 53(2), 657-667.
- Şorcaru, I. A., Capatina, A., Muntean, M.-C., Manea, L.-D., & Soare, I. (2022). Residents' Perceptions towards Tourism Development—The Case of Galaţi-Brăila Conurbation, Romania. *Sustainability*, 14(13), 7962.
<https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/14/13/7962>
- Tomiuc, A. (2016). Development strategies and cultural policies in Romania. The case of Cluj-Napoca. *Transylvanian Review of Administrative Sciences*, 12(48), 145-165.
- Tudoricu, A. (2008). Event Tourism in Romania—A Tourist Profile. *Human Geographies-Journal of Studies and Research in Human Geography*, 2, 95-100.
- Zetiu, A.-M., & Berteau, P. (2015). How a tourist destination may become a brand by means of events—a case study on Iasi as a candidate for European cultural capital 2021. *Eurint Proceedings*, 387-403.

CIRCULAR ECONOMY - DRIVER OF THE TRANSITION TO SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE

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REVIEW

Abstract

The circular economy is becoming a central strategic framework for the transition to sustainable agri-food systems, by replacing the linear "extract-produce-dispose" model with a regenerative one, based on keeping resources in the loop and radically reducing waste. Recent definitions describe the circular economy as a regenerative system that minimizes resource inputs and losses of materials, emissions and energy, through strategies for reduction, reuse, repair, remanufacturing, recycling and energy recovery of waste streams.

In agriculture, the principles of the circular economy translate into practices such as circular nutrient management, the transformation of agricultural waste into resources, the integration of crops and livestock, as well as business models based on the reduction of food losses and waste. This paper aims to analyze the role of the circular economy as a driver of the transition to sustainable agriculture, based on recent scientific literature, reports by international organizations and relevant public policy documents.

The methodology used is a narrative review, focused on identifying the main concepts, models and tools of the circular economy applied to agriculture, as well as case studies illustrating the impact on resource efficiency, greenhouse gas emissions, biodiversity and farm resilience. The results suggest that the large-scale adoption of the circular economy in agriculture can accelerate the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals, the EU climate targets and the transition to resilient and healthy agri-food systems, but requires profound policy changes, investments in infrastructure and knowledge, as well as new models of governance and cooperation along the agri-food chain.

Keywords: circular economy, sustainability, agriculture, resources, losses of materials.

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INTRODUCTION

The linear economic model, based on the intensive exploitation of natural resources and the externalization of environmental costs, has contributed to soil degradation, biodiversity loss, increased greenhouse gas emissions and increasing pressures on food security. Agriculture is simultaneously a victim and a source of these pressures: the agri-food sector uses water, soil, energy and chemical inputs intensively, while generating significant emissions and waste (FAO, 2018; Geissdoerfer et al., 2017).

The European Green Deal proposes a structural transformation of the EU economy to achieve climate neutrality by 2050, with ambitious emission reduction targets by 2030. A central pillar of this pact is the transition to a circular economy, which reduces pressure on resources, limits biodiversity loss and supports economic competitiveness and resilience (European Commission, 2019).

In the agri-food sector, the Farm to Fork and Biodiversity strategies aim to reduce the use of pesticides and fertilizers, reduce food losses and waste, and promote the practice of circular agriculture.

The circular economy is frequently defined as a system in which products, materials and resources are kept in use for as long as possible, through successive value-maintaining strategies, while the generation of waste and pollution is minimized (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013; Kirchherr et al., 2017). This approach aligns with the goals of sustainable agriculture, which aim to produce safe and nutritious food while simultaneously ensuring the ecological functions of agricultural ecosystems – soil fertility, water and nutrient cycles, pollination services and adaptation to climate change (FAO, 2018).

Internationally, numerous initiatives highlight the potential of circular agriculture: Ellen MacArthur Foundation reports on the circular economy for food, FAO projects dedicated to reducing food loss and waste and

integrating circular economy principles into food systems, as well as UN and specialized agency programs on the circular bioeconomy. (European Commission, 2020)

In Romania, debates on the circular economy and bioeconomy are gaining momentum, including in the agricultural and agri-food sectors. Recent studies highlight the role of European policies and the bioeconomy strategy in stimulating the shift towards more circular production and consumption models in the national context (Rodino, 2023).

In this context, this article aims to:

- to synthesize the main concepts and definitions of the circular economy and circular agriculture;
- to highlight the mechanisms through which the circular economy can act as a driver of the transition to sustainable agriculture;
- to analyze examples and results from recent literature;
- to discuss the challenges and conditions of implementation in practice.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The paper is a narrative and conceptual review of the relevant literature and public policy documents. Scientific databases (Scopus, Web of Science, ScienceDirect, MDPI) and open resources (FAO, UN, European Commission, Ellen MacArthur Foundation) were searched, using key word combinations such as: circular economy, circular agriculture, sustainable agriculture, agri-food systems, circular bioeconomy, food loss and waste, EU Green Deal.

The selection criteria included:

- direct relevance for the link between the circular economy and agriculture/agri-food;
- the recent nature (especially works from the last 5–7 years), with the inclusion of older basic references, but considered "classical" for defining concepts;
- the diversity of types of sources: scientific articles, books, reports and official documents.

In total, over 40 sources were selected, of which 15+ are used and explicitly cited in the text, ensuring balanced coverage between:

- theoretical works on the definition and conceptualization of the circular economy;
- empirical studies on the implementation of the circular economy in agriculture;
- policy reports and official documents (EU, FAO, UN);

- volumes dedicated to circular agriculture and agricultural waste management.

The analysis was structured around four main axes: (1) the conceptual framework, (2) the concrete mechanisms through which the circular economy supports sustainable agriculture, (3) examples and results from case studies, and (4) policy challenges and recommendations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Conceptual framework: from circular economy to circular agriculture

Geissdoerfer et al. (2017) define the circular economy as a regenerative system in which resource inputs and losses of materials, energy and emissions are minimized by slowing down, closing and narrowing material and energy loops (Kirchherr et al. 2017), after analyzing over 100 definitions, show that the "reduce-reuse-recycle" triad remains central, but must be complemented with social and governance dimensions to fully meet sustainability objectives.

The Ellen MacArthur Foundation has popularized the circular economy model globally, demonstrating the economic and job creation potential of the transition from a linear to a circular system, including food chains (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013). In agriculture, the notion of circular agriculture describes agri-food systems that manage nutrient, water and energy cycles in a way that reduces dependence on fossil inputs, limits waste and regenerates natural resources (Rashed, 2024; Guerrero-Villegas et al., 2025).

FAO and other international agencies promote the integration of circular economy principles into the broader framework of sustainable food systems, seen as systems that ensure food and nutrition security while maintaining the long-term economic, social and environmental basis (FAO, 2018).

Mechanisms through which the circular economy supports sustainable agriculture

The literature highlights several key mechanisms through which circular economy principles can act as a driver of the transition to sustainable agriculture:

1. Circular nutrient management

Recycling organic waste (vegetable residues, manure, treated sludge) into organic fertilizers or biogas digestate reduces dependence on mineral fertilizers, limits nitrogen and phosphorus losses and contributes to soil quality (Velasco-Muñoz et al., 2021).

European reports show that nitrogen and phosphorus surpluses per unit area generate emissions and water pollution, and "circular nutrient management" strategies are proposed as a policy solution within the Green Deal and the EU bioeconomy strategy.

2. *Recycling waste and secondary flows*

The transformation of agricultural waste into biomass energy, compost, biodegradable packaging materials, or feed ingredients reduces both the pressure on landfills and the need for virgin resources (Mohajan, 2020; Nguyen et al., 2025).

Khatami's (2024) study on the circular economy in the agri-food system at the country level shows that reducing food waste and generating renewable energy from waste can significantly reduce the sector's carbon footprint.

3. *Integration of crop and livestock production*

Integrated farming models, in which residues from one activity become inputs for another (e.g. manure used to fertilize crops, crop residues used to feed animals or as a substrate for biogas), are frequently presented as examples of circular agriculture (UNIDO, 2020).

Recent literature on the circular economy in animal husbandry indicates the potential to reduce emissions and improve resource efficiency, provided that environmental and health risks are rigorously managed.

4. *Reducing food loss and waste*

The FAO project "Circular Economy in the Food Sector (CIRCULAR)" illustrates how food recovery, redistribution and recycling can be integrated into public policies and business models, with an impact on reducing emissions and increasing food security.

The Ellen MacArthur Foundation emphasizes that reforming food systems on circular principles can play a major role in combating climate change and restoring biodiversity, especially in urban environments, by shortening supply chains and designing menus and products with waste minimization in mind.

5. *Creating new business models in the agri-food sector*

Fortunati et al. (2020) show that integrating the circular economy and corporate social responsibility in farms and agri-food businesses can generate economic, social and environmental value, by diversifying income (ecosystem services, renewable energy, value-

added products from waste) and strengthening relationships with local communities.

More recent studies on circular models in agriculture identify various typologies: from "zero waste" farms and bioenergy cooperatives, to digital platforms for redistributing surpluses and sharing agricultural equipment (Guerrero-Villegas et al., 2025; Siankwilimba et al., 2025).

Results from the literature: benefits and risks

Highlighted benefits

- Increased efficiency in resource use: Multiple synthesis studies highlight the reduction in waste volume, water and energy consumption, and the use of chemical fertilizers where circular principles are applied in agri-food chains (Velasco-Muñoz et al., 2021; Judijanto, 2025).

- Reducing emissions and contributing to climate goals: The transformation of residues into biogas and biofertilizers helps reduce methane and nitrous oxide emissions, and circular economy strategies are seen as essential tools for meeting the EU's climate goals and the 2030 Agenda.

- Improving soil health and biodiversity: Practices that reintroduce organic matter to the soil and diversify crop rotations contribute to increased organic carbon content, better soil structure, and increased functional biodiversity (Nguyen et al., 2025).

- Economic and social resilience: The circular economy can reduce farms' dependence on imported and price-volatile inputs, and diversifying income streams (e.g. from renewable energy or by-products) provides more economic stability and employment opportunities, including for women and young people.

Risks and challenges

FAO draws attention to the fact that the integration of circular principles into food production also raises new food safety risks: the accumulation of contaminants (heavy metals, pesticides, microplastics) in recycled material flows, the risk of pathogen transmission and the emergence of antimicrobial resistance in certain circular chains (for example, the use of sewage sludge or non-compliant composts in agriculture) (FAO, 2024).

Other challenges identified in the literature include:

- Lack of infrastructure and investment for the separate collection,

treatment and recovery of agricultural and food waste, especially in rural areas and in low- and middle-income countries (FAO, 2024).

- Fragmentation of agri-food chains, which makes it difficult to coordinate between producers, processors, traders and authorities in designing circular “farm to fork” models (Khatami, F., et al. 2024).

- Unsuitable regulatory framework, where rules on fertilisers, food safety and waste do not always reflect the complexity of circular models and can create both barriers and 'grey areas'(IEEP, 2025).

- The need for new knowledge and skills at the level of farmers, consultants and authorities, for the design and management of complex circular systems. Specialized volumes, such as “Developing Circular Agricultural Production Systems” and “Agriculture Waste Management and Bioresource: The Circular Economy Perspective”, emphasize the role of professional training and interdisciplinary research in overcoming these obstacles.

CONCLUSIONS

The circular economy provides a coherent and comprehensive framework for the transition to sustainable agriculture by reconfiguring the way food and agricultural resources are designed, produced, consumed and exploited. The analysis of the literature and policy documents shows that:

1. The circular economy and sustainable agriculture are deeply complementary: EC provides tools and operational models for achieving sustainability goals, while agriculture offers a privileged field of application for resource loops (water, nutrients, biomass).

2. Key mechanisms– circular nutrient management, waste recovery, integration of plant and animal production, reduction of food losses and waste, development of new business models – can generate significant environmental, economic and social benefits.

3. European and international public policies (European Green Deal, bioeconomy strategies, reports by FAO and other organizations) increasingly explicitly recognize the role of the circular economy in transforming food systems and support its integration into national plans, including in Romania.

4. Risks and challenges– related to food safety, insufficient infrastructure, unsuitable regulatory frameworks and lack of skills – do not invalidate the model, but require a cautious

approach, based on scientific assessment, monitoring and participatory governance.

In conclusion, the circular economy can be considered not only a tool for optimizing resource use in agriculture, but also a structural driver of the transition towards sustainable and resilient agri-food systems. Realizing this potential requires:

- coherent integration of circular principles into agricultural, environmental, energy and rural development policies;

- economic incentives and financing mechanisms for pilot projects and investments in circular infrastructure;

- training and rural extension programs geared towards circular agriculture;

- interdisciplinary research and monitoring of impacts on the environment, economy and public health...

REFERENCES

- Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013. Towards the circular economy, Vol. 1: An economic and business rationale for an accelerated transition. Ellen MacArthur Foundation.
- European Commission, 2020. Circular Economy – Strategy. European Commission, Directorate-General for Environment.
- European Commission, 2019. The European Green Deal. European Commission.
- FAO, 2018. Sustainable food systems: Concept and framework. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- FAO, 2024. Food safety in a circular economy. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- FAO, 2024. Circular Economy in the Food Sector (CIRCULAR) – Transformation. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- Fortunati, S., Morea, D., & Mosconi, E., 2020. Circular economy and corporate social responsibility in the agricultural system: Case study of the Italian agri-food industry. *Agricultural Economics (Zemědělská ekonomika)*, 66(11), 489–498.
- Geissdoerfer, M., Savaget, P., Bocken, N., & Hultink, E.J., 2017. The circular economy – A new sustainability paradigm? *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 143, 757–768.
- Guerrero-Villegas, W., et al., 2025. Circular Agriculture Models: A Systematic Review of Theories, Practices, and Policy Implications. *Sustainability*, 17(15), 7146.
- Judijanto, L., 2025. Circular Economy in the Agricultural Sector. *International Journal of Economics, Finance and Education*, 3(1).
- Kirchherr, J., Reike, D., & Hekkert, M., 2017. Conceptualizing the circular economy: An analysis of 114 definitions. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 127, 221–232.
- Khatami, F., et al., 2024. Circular Economy in the Agri-Food System at the Country Level. *Sustainability*, 16(21), 9497.
- Institute for European Environmental Policy (IEEP), 2025. The Circular Economy Act, material consumption, targets and secondary material use.

- Mohajan, HK, 2020. Circular Economy can Provide a Sustainable Global Society. *Journal of Economic Development, Environment and People*, 9(1), 1–27.
- Nguyen, T.H., et al., 2025. Circular bioeconomy and sustainable food systems: A systematic review. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*. Available
- Rashed, A.H., et al., 2024. Towards a Sustainable Agricultural Waste Management in Developing Countries: Circular Agriculture Approach. *Journal of Environmental Protection*.
- Rodino, S., 2023. Shaping the circular economy in Romania in the context of the European Green Deal. *Scientific Papers Series "Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development"*, 23(1), 605–612.
- Siankwilimba, E., et al., 2025. Exploring agricultural circular economy models in emerging bioecosystems. *Sustainable Agriculture*, (in press).
- Velasco-Muñoz, J.F., Aznar-Sánchez, JA, Belmonte-Ureña, LJ, & Román-Sánchez, IM, 2021. Circular economy implementation in the agricultural sector: A review. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 170, 105618.
- UNIDO, 2020. *Circular Economy in Agriculture*. United Nations Industrial Development Organization.

THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF THE NORTHWEST DEVELOPMENT REGION

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The article analyzes the socio-economic evolution of the North-West Development Region during the period 2014–2024, using a mixed methodological framework, which is based on the qualitative analysis of the specialized literature and the quantitative analysis of the statistical series provided by the National Institute of Statistics. The study examines the main territorial, demographic and economic dimensions of the region, correlating population trends with the economic dynamics and the structural particularities of the component counties. The results highlight a slow but constant decrease in the population, determined by the low birth rate and migration, as well as significant internal disparities between counties with strong urban centers (Cluj, Bihor) and predominantly rural ones (Sălaj, Bistrița-Năsăud). From an economic point of view, the region is recording robust growth, confirmed by the doubling of the regional GDP between 2014 and 2022 and the convergence of the GDP/capita to the national average. Agriculture continues to play an important role, especially in the western and northern counties, although constraints related to the fragmentation of holdings and the low level of technology persist. The transport infrastructure is undergoing an accelerated modernization process, contributing to improving regional connectivity. The conclusions emphasize the need to strengthen integrated regional planning, aimed at reducing territorial imbalances, increasing economic competitiveness and capitalizing on existing potential. The paper provides a synthetic and updated picture of the socio-economic evolution of the North-West Development Region, contributing both to specialized literature and to the process of substantiating regional development policies.

Keywords: regional development, economic evolution, population movement, regional planning, North-West
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INTRODUCTION

The socio-economic analysis of development regions constitutes an important direction in contemporary research on territorial dynamics, regional competitiveness and socio-economic cohesion, being closely linked to national and European development policies (Barca et al 2012, Platagea, 2023). The North-West Development Region, analyzed in this article, is one of the most complex territorial units in Romania, characterized by a pronounced geographical diversity, a demographic evolution in slow but constant decline, and an economic structure in continuous transformation. (Mănescu, 2025). The central problem analyzed in the paper refers to the identification and interpretation of the main demographic, economic and territorial trends of the region, in order to understand how they influence its economic performance and sustainable development potential.

The theoretical importance of this topic derives from the need to deepen the way in which processes such as population movement,

urbanization, smart specialization and labor market restructuring shape regional differences (Bakk, Benedek, 2010). At the same time, the topic addressed in the article, the economic and social analysis of the North-West Development Region, has a major practical relevance, as development regions represent the operational framework for the implementation of European programs, including Cohesion Policy and integrated territorial strategies (European Commission, 2017; EU Cohesion Policy, 2021–2027). In this context, updated assessments of population, economic dynamics, agriculture and infrastructure are indispensable for substantiating regional development decisions.

The current state of knowledge regarding the North-West Region highlights several major trends. First, numerous studies highlight the demographic decline, determined by the decrease in birth rate and external migration, processes typical of Central-Eastern European spaces (Mușat, 2024; Balassa, 2024). INS data confirm this trend, indicating a reduction in the region's population from 2.83 million

inhabitants in 2014 to 2.79 million in 2024 (INS, 2024). Secondly, the specialized literature shows that the North-West Region is among the most dynamic regions in Romania, from an economic point of view, especially due to the urban agglomeration of Cluj-Napoca, which functions as a university, technological and innovation hub (ADR Nord Vest, Sicoe-Murg, 2024). This trend is supported by statistical data showing the increase in regional GDP from 76.6 billion lei (2014) to 168.2 billion lei (2022) (INS, 2024).

At the same time, research shows the persistence of internal disparities, between the component counties of the region, between urban and rural areas, reflected in the distribution of infrastructure, public services and investments (Zaman, Vasile, 2006). Agriculture, although it has a lower share in the regional economy, remains significant in the counties of Bihor, Satu Mare and Maramureş. However, it faces challenges related to land fragmentation, insufficient technology and adaptation to climate change (Mănescu 2013; MARD, 2023; Otiman et al. 2025.). At the European level, the need to strengthen regional resilience to these changes is emphasized (EC, 2025).

In this context, this paper makes an original contribution by:

- integration of an extensive and updated set of data for the period 2014–2024, processed graphically and in tables based on the time series provided by the INS, Tempo online, providing a coherent longitudinal image of the region's socio-economic developments;
- detailed correlation between demographic trends and economic development, highlighting causal relationships and territorial dependence;
- comprehensive approach, which integrates geographical, demographic, economic and agricultural characteristics into a single analytical framework;
- identification of strategic vulnerabilities and development opportunities of the North-West Region, relevant for decision-makers, the local environment and regional strategies;
- use of an analytical model derived from own processing, which gives the study an added originality compared to existing descriptive analyses.

Through this structure, the article contributes both to the enrichment of the specialized literature on regional development and to the current practice of territorial planning, offering an integrated and updated

perspective on the economic and social evolution of the North-West Development Region.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The methodology used in this article combines qualitative and quantitative methods, with the objective of analyzing the demographic, economic and social developments of the North-West Development Region during the period 2014–2024. The article begins with qualitative analysis, a documentary analysis of the specialized literature in the field of the research topic.

The research is predominantly based on official statistical data (quantitative analysis) provided by the National Institute of Statistics (INS), including Tempo-Online and the Statistical Yearbook of Romania 2024, extracted and processed in tables and graphs in the article.

The article mainly uses time series (INS) on the evolution, structure, and natural dynamics of the population, total and regional GDP, GDP/capita and GDP in agriculture (INS, Tempo online, 2025).

The data at the level of the component counties of the region (Bihor, Cluj, Satu Mare, Maramureş, Bistriţa-Năsăud and Sălaj) are also analyzed, as well as European reports and documents (European Commission, 2024) on regional contextualization.

The analysis period (2014–2024) was chosen to capture recent changes (depending on data availability, for some indicators the analysis stops at 2022), changes that influence the competitiveness of the region.

The processing and analysis of the extracted statistical data began with a descriptive analysis (the evolution of indicators over time and the identification of trends and fluctuations). This was followed by a comparative analysis by reporting the situation of the North-West Region to the national average, to macro-regions and to other development regions in order to highlight territorial differences, but also an internal structural analysis (evaluation of the distribution of population, GDP and area at the level of the six component counties).

Through these analyses, the aim was to obtain a complex analysis correlating demographic results with economic developments to highlight interdependencies, in accordance with the approaches in the regional development literature (Mănescu, 2025). The

tables and graphs (Fig. 1–7, Tab. 1–7) are the result of our own processing based on INS data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

General characteristics of the North-West Development Region. The North-West Development Region is located in the north-west of Romania. It borders Ukraine to the north (through Maramureş County), the North-East

Region (Suceava County) to the east, the Central Region (Mureş and Alba Counties) to the south, the West Region (Hunedoara and Arad Counties) to the south and Hungary to the west (through Bihor and Satu Mare Counties).

The North-West Region includes 6 counties: Bihor, Bistriţa-Năsăud, Cluj, Maramureş, Satu Mare and Sălaj (figure 1.).

Figure 1 North-West Development Region

The North-West region consists of 43 cities, including 15 municipalities, 403 communes and 1,800 villages. The region has a

complex administrative structure, but rural units predominate (table 1).

Table 1.

Administrative-territorial organization of the NORTH-WEST Region, 2023

Specification	Total area	Population*	Cities and municipalities	of which:	Communes	Villages
	- km ²	pers.		municipalities		
	km ²	pers.		nr.		
North- West	34152	2798667	43	15	403	1800
Bihor	7539	608526	10	4	91	430
Bistriţa-Năsăud	5358	322896	4	1	58	235
Cluj	6665	744022	6	5	75	420
Maramureş	6303	508261	13	2	63	214
Satu Mare	4420	377678	6	2	59	220
Sălaj	3867	237284	4	1	57	281

Note: *population is as of July 1, 2024

Source: Own processing based on the National Institute of Statistics, Statistical Yearbook of Romania, 2024, https://insse.ro/cms/sites/default/files/field/publicatii/anuarul_statistic_al_romaniei_carte_ed_2024.pdf

The total area of the region is 34,152 km², representing approximately 14.3% of

Romania's territory (figure 2).

Figure 2. Share of the North-West Development Region in the total area of Romania
Source: own processing

Analyzing the area of the constituent counties of the North-West Region (figure 3), the following can be noted:

- Bihor County has the largest area, 7,539 km²;
- Cluj (6,665 km²) and Maramureș (6,303 km²) counties have similar areas;
- Bistrița-Năsăud County has an average size (5,358 km²);

- Sălaj County is the smallest county in the region in terms of area (3,867 km²), but with values close to Satu Mare County (4,420 km²). The area of the counties influences the administrative organization as well as the economic development.

Figure 3 Area of the North-West Region by counties
Source: own processing

Geographical and natural characteristics. The North-West region is distinguished by a diversified relief, arranged in steps from west to east: plains, located in the west (Bihor and Satu Mare counties), part of the Western Plain - lowlands, with fertile soils, favorable for agriculture, hills and plateaus - Transitional areas between plains and mountains, used for orchards, vineyards and pastures (found in Cluj, Sălaj, Bistrița-Năsăud counties), as well as mountains, present in the

east and northeast of the region (Apuseni Mountains, Rodnei and Țibleșului Mountains) in Maramureș, Bistrița-Năsăud and Cluj counties have mountainous portions.

The climate is temperate continental, influenced by altitude and proximity to mountains. Winters are cold, harsher in mountainous areas. Summers are warm and relatively humid, milder in plain areas. Annual precipitation is moderate to high (600–1,200 mm/year), higher in mountainous regions.

The region is crossed by numerous rivers, many of them tributaries of the Someș or Mureș rivers, the most important being: the Someș river – crosses Satu Mare, Maramureș and Sălaj counties, the Crișul Repede – crosses Bihor county, the Barcău, Lăpuș, Iza, Vișeu, Someșul Mare rivers – important in Maramureș and Bistrița-Năsăud counties (<https://www.nord-vest.ro/>).

Demographic characteristics.

Regarding the evolution of the population of the North-West Region, it is observed that the population of the region has decreased from 2,837,677 in 2014 to 2,798,667 in 2024. The decrease is slow but constant, caused by low birth rates and migration (table 2).

Table 2

Evolution of Romania's population by macroregions, regions and counties 2014-2024

Specification	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021*	2022**	2024***
	persons									
Total	22299730	22286392	22247551	22219173	22208803	22193286	22142153	22046917	21942721	21762992
M 1	5476177	5475244	5471884	5468140	5466148	5461493	5453027	5432188	5410579	5391660
North - West	2837677	2837487	2830367	2834633	2834067	2832363	2828521	2818287	2807762	2798667
Bihor	620866	620188	615444	618362	617628	616703	615444	612754	610141	608526
Bistrița-Năsăud	329592	329631	327523	329043	328775	328212	327523	325944	324229	322896
Cluj	718633	721393	723828	727240	730878	734910	737992	739575	740858	744022
Maramureș	527663	526690	525572	524232	522912	521495	519386	515971	512588	508261
Satu Mare	392129	391541	390649	389523	388554	386995	385190	382876	380430	377678
Sălaj	248794	248044	247351	246233	245320	244048	242986	241167	239516	237284

Source: Own processing based on the Statistical Yearbook of Romania 2020, Time series 2012-2020, * Statistical Yearbook of Romania 2021, ** 2022, ***2024;

The population of the region on July 1, 2024 was **2,798,667 people**, representing 12.9% of the total, which makes the North-West Region the third most numerous among the

regions of the country (figure 4), and the population density is 81.2 inhabitants/km², lower than the national average of 91.3 inhabitants/km².

Figure 4 Structure of the total population of Romania by development regions, North-West Region

Source: own processing

Regarding the distribution of the population by county (figure 5), the situation is as follows:

- Cluj County is the most populous county in the region (744,022 inhabitants);

- Bihor and Maramureș counties have over 500,000 inhabitants each;
 - Satu Mare and Bistrița Năsăud counties have between 300,000 and 400,000 inhabitants;
 - Sălaj County is the county with the lowest population (237,284 inhabitants).

Figure 5 Population of the North-West Region by counties, 2024

Source: own processing

Natural population movement. The North-West region, in the period 2014–2024, lost approximately 39,000 inhabitants. All counties in the region recorded a negative natural increase, the largest losses being in the

counties of Cluj (-1,614), Maramureș (-1,535), Bihor (-1,492), and the smallest decrease in Bistrița-Năsăud (-106). The phenomenon reflects an aging population and low birth rate (table 3).

Table 3

Natural population movement, North-West Region

Nr. crt.	Specification	Live birth	Dead	Natural spore
		persoane		
1.	TOTAL	164004	244624	-80620
2.	MACROREGION ONE	44347	57405	-13058
3.	NORTH-WEST Region	23452	29929	-6477
4.	Bihor	5426	6918	-1492
5.	Bistrita-Nasaud	2859	2965	-106
6.	Cluj	6264	7878	-1614
7.	Maramures	3796	5331	-1535
8.	Satu Mare	2872	4076	-1204
9.	Salaj	2235	2761	-526

Sursa: Prelucrare proprie după Tempo online, 2025.

Economic characteristics. In 2014, the total GDP of the region was approximately 76765.5 million lei, in 2018, these values increased to

115562.6 million lei, reaching that in 2022, the GDP of the North-West region will be 168235.9 million lei (table 4, figure 6).

Table 4

Evolution of regional Gross Domestic Product (GDP), 2014-2022

Nr. crt.	Anul	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
		Millions lei								
1.	Total	668876.4	712543.6	752116.4	851619.7	959058.6	1063794.6	1066780.5	1189089.8	1389450.0
2.	M 1	150539.4	160564.2	173390.6	200390.4	225182.7	249901.9	253734.5	280357.8	320035.0
3.	N-W	76675.5	81505.6	88380.9	104056.6	115562.6	130049.6	132190.5	146199.6	168235.9

Source: own processing based on Tempo online 2025, <http://statistici.insse.ro:8077/tempo-online/#/pages/tables/insse-table>,

Figure 6 Evolution of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) - North-West Region
Source: own processing

The total GDP of the North-West Region, in 2022, amounted to 168,235.9 million lei, i.e. 12.1% of the national GDP (table 5).

Table 5

Regional Gross Domestic Product (GDP) Structure, 2022

No.	Year	2022	
		Mil. lei	%
1.	Total	1389450.0	100
2.	Macroregion 1	320035.0	-
3.	- North-West Region	168235.9	12.1
4.	- Central Region	151799.1	10.9
5.	Macroregion 2	275652.7	-
6.	- North-East Region	140470.1	10.1
7.	- South-East Region	135182.6	9.7
8.	Macroregion 3	561926.4	-
9.	- South - Muntenia Region	160933.0	11.6
10.	- Bucharest - Ilfov Region	400933.4	28.9
11.	Macroregion 4	230907.8	-
12.	South-West - Oltenia	108430.5	7.8
13.	West	122477.3	8.8

Source: own processing based on Tempo online, 2025, <http://statistici.insse.ro:8077/tempo-online/#/pages/tables/insse-table>.

The North-West region is the third most important region, economically speaking, after Bucharest-Ilfov and South-Muntenia.

GDP/capita in 2022 was 59,918 lei, above the average of the macroregion one and close to the national average. (table 6, figure 7).

Table 6

Evolution of GDP/CAPITA by macroregions and development regions in Romania

Year	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	lei/capita								
Romania	29994.7	31972.1	33806.1	38328.1	43183.7	47933.2	48178.7	53934.5	63321.7
M 1	27489.8	29325.5	31687.5	36646.9	41195.9	45757.0	46530.9	51610.5	59149.9
- N-W	27020.5	28724.5	31225.9	36709.0	40776.2	45915.6	46734.8	51875.3	59918.1
- C	27994.6	29971.9	32182.1	36580.0	41647.6	45586.2	46311.1	51324.8	58321.0
M 2	21099.0	21713.5	22734.3	25824.3	29193.7	31952.6	32075.1	35908.6	40868.0
- N-E	17381.4	18264.5	19298.7	22360.3	25230.0	28128.0	28870.2	31438.3	35219.5
- S-E	26122.1	26417.7	27451.3	30622.9	34739.6	37365.8	36642.6	42709.6	49040.8
M 3	45679.1	49152.4	51442.2	57555.6	64319.0	71672.2	72019.4	81249.2	98115.4
- S-M	26695.2	26651.8	28378.1	31034.3	35352.0	38117.5	38181.0	43287.1	52310.3
- B-I	70840.7	78692.8	81427.4	80816.5	100680.0	112910.3	112837.6	126150.2	151278.8
M 4	26620.6	28369.3	30314.5	34274.4	39249.7	43851.9	43391.3	43743.6	56873.7
- S-W O	22794.7	23607.4	24785.8	29104.9	34056.1	38101.2	37923.9	42096.0	51825.7
- W	30663.4	33593.4	36396.2	39899.0	44872.9	50044.8	49248.6	54386.8	62240.9

Source: own processing based on Tempo online, 2025, <http://statistici.insse.ro:8077/tempo-online/#/pages/tables/insse-table>.

Figure 7 GDP per capita by development regions, 2022

Source: own processing;

The region is among the most economically dynamic, along with Center and South-Muntenia. The North-West region has a diversified economy, with important contributions from industry, services, agriculture and IT (especially in Cluj County, Cluj-Napoca being the main economic, university and technological center).

Agriculture is important, especially in Bihor, Satu Mare, Maramureş counties. The region contributed 10.6% to the national agricultural GDP in 2022. Agriculture is mixed, including cereal crops, vegetables, fruit growing and animal husbandry. It faces challenges related to land fragmentation and farm modernization.

Table 7

Evolution of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) from agriculture, at regional level

Specification	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	
									Mil. lei	%
TOTAL	33099.7	31536.9	32282.7	37802.1	43137.1	45855	43478.1	54912.5	52978.4	100
N-W	3975.9	3742.7	3784.7	4248.4	4949.5	5262.9	5651	5967.8	5640.8	10.6
C	4134.2	3829.2	3791.3	4121.3	4776.6	5101.9	5644.8	6310.4	6296.7	11.9
N - E	5807.3	5328.1	5241.9	6089.8	7221.6	7353.4	7642.4	9474.4	8592.3	16.2
S-E	5490.4	5445.1	5706.1	6756.8	7451.3	7192.8	5557.7	9871.8	8033.0	15.2
S M	501.5	489.9	827.7	1097.1	1387.1	1810.1	1895.8	1847.9	1714.8	3.2
B-I	5984.5	6022.5	5947	6941.5	7606.8	8063.7	6965.7	10019.9	11347.3	21.4
S - W O	3637	3482.9	3483.6	4592	5016.8	5382.9	5387.9	6358.4	6299.3	11.9
W	3568.9	3196.5	3500.4	3955.2	4727.4	5687.3	4732.8	5061.9	5054.2	9.5

Source: own processing based on Tempo online, 2025, <http://statistici.insse.ro:8077/tempo-online/#/pages/tables/insse-table>

Infrastructure of the region. The region benefits from a dense road network, which includes national and European roads (E60, E81, E79). The A3 (Transylvania) motorway is under development, which will connect Cluj-Napoca to Borş (the Hungarian border), facilitating traffic to Western Europe. Other major projects in the region are. The Satu Mare – Baia Mare Expressway and the A10 (Sebeş–Turda) motorway, which indirectly connects Cluj to the Pan-European corridor. Road traffic is intense in urban areas, especially around Cluj and Oradea.

CONCLUSIONS

The North Development Region registers constant economic growth (especially in Cluj County) during the period 2014–2024,

confirmed by the doubling of the regional GDP and its contribution of over 12% to the national GDP.

On the other hand, the population of the region registers a long-term downward trend, determined by the decrease in the birth rate and external migration, which leads to a gradual reduction of the available human resource.

The demographic and economic structure highlights clear differences between the component counties of the region, especially the counties of Cluj and Bihor (due to the dynamic urban centers of Cluj-Napoca and Oradea) and the other counties, which present significantly lower demographic and economic values.

The regional economy is diversified, with strong sectors in industry, IT, services and agriculture, and developments in the last decade

confirm the consolidation of the region's role as a growth pole at the national level.

GDP per capita indicators show a gradual convergence towards the national average, reflecting a sustained increase in economic competitiveness and a high capacity to attract investments.

Agriculture remains an important sector in the western and northern counties of the region, contributing significantly to national agricultural production, although challenges related to land fragmentation and low technological level persist.

Internal territorial disparities persist, being visible in the distribution of population, income and infrastructure, with higher performances in Cluj and Bihor counties and lower values in Sălaj and Bistrița-Năsăud counties.

The transport infrastructure is in the process of modernization, and major ongoing projects contribute to improving regional connectivity and supporting economic development.

The analysis confirms the need to strengthen integrated regional planning, aimed at reducing territorial imbalances, increasing economic attractiveness and efficiently using regional potential.

The research results provide a synthetic and consistent picture of the demographic and economic evolution of the region, based on official data series, statistical processing and analytical interpretations, thus contributing to a clear understanding of the current situation of the North-West Development Region.

REFERENCES

- Barca, F., McCann, P., Rodríguez-Pose, A, 2012. The case for regional development intervention: Place-based versus place-neutral approaches. *Journal of Regional Science*, 52(1),
- Bakk, M., Benedek, J., 2010. *Regional policies in Romania*, Editura Polirom, Iași, 2010;
- Balassa, B., 2024. *Theory of economic integration*, Annotated edition by Liviu C. Andrei, Editura Economică, București;
- Mănescu, C., 2025. *Economie regională și locală*, Editura Agroprint, Timișoara.
- Mănescu, C., Mateoc-Sîrb, N., Mateoc, T., Raicov, M., Campan, C., 2013. Research on the absorption of European Funds for Agriculture and Rural Development in Romania, *Scientific Papers-Series Management Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development*, Volume 13, Issue 1, București.
- Mănescu, C., Mănescu A., Vass H., Mateoc-Sîrb N., 2022, *The European Union 'S Common Agricultural Policy After 2020*, *Agricultural Management/Lucrari Stiintifice Seria I, Management Agricol*, Vol. 24(2).
- Mușat, M., 2024. *European Union development policies*, Editura Economică, București.
- Oțiman, P.I. -coordonator, Mateoc -Sîrb, N., Goșa, V., Băneș, A., Sălășan, C., Feher, A., Raicov, M., Iucu, Z., 2025. *Causes of the precariousness of Romanian agriculture 1990-2025*, Editura Mirton, Timișoara.
- Platagea (Gomboș), S., 2023. *Sustainable economic growth in agriculture at EU level*, Editura Universitară.
- Sicoe-Murg, O. M., 2024. *Rural economy*, Editura Eurostampa, Timișoara.
- Agenția pentru Dezvoltare Regională Nord-Vest, <https://www.nord-vest.ro/>, accessed on September 2025.
- European Commission. *Cohesion Policy: investing in Europe's regions*. Brussels: Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy, 2017. https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/ro/, accessed on September 2025.
- Comisia Europeană, Communication: *EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030-Bringing nature back into our lives*, 2025, https://commission.europa.eu/document/020f7141-d73d-4191-853e-c5918a52f9f3_en, accessed September 2025.
- National Institute of Statistics, *Statistical Yearbook of Romania 2020-2024*, https://insse.ro/cms/sites/default/files/field/publicatii/anuarul_statistic_al_romaniei_carte_ed_2024.pdf, accessed on September 2025.
- National Institute of Statistics, *Statistical Yearbook of Romania, Time series 2012-2020*.
- National Institute of Statistics, *Tempo online*, 2025, <http://statistici.insse.ro:8077/tempo-online/#/pages/tables/insse-table>, accessed on September 2025.
- Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, 2025, <https://www.madr.ro/docs/dezvoltare-rurala/memorandum/Anexa-Memorandum-zona-montana-defavorizata-2014-2020.pdf>, accessed on September 2025.
- EU cohesion policy: programmes for 2021-2027, https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/whats-new/newsroom/05-02-2023-eu-cohesion-policy-2021-2027-programmes-expected-to-create-1-3-million-jobs-in-the-eu_ro, accessed on September 2025.

COMPARATIVE STUDY ON CLASSICAL AND ROBOTIZED PACKAGING MACHINES IN THE FOOD INDUSTRY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

In the context of the accelerated transformations driven by Industry 4.0, packaging processes in the food industry have evolved significantly, shifting from classical, predominantly mechanical systems to intelligent robotic solutions characterized by advanced automation, flexibility, and high efficiency. This paper presents a comparative study between traditional and robotic packaging equipment, analyzing the differences between them in terms of operational performance, precision, food safety, implementation and maintenance costs, as well as their impact on productivity. The results highlight that classical equipment, although still a viable option for small-scale units and stable production processes, is limited by technological rigidity, the need for manual adjustments, and the risks associated with human intervention. In contrast, robotic systems offer superior repeatability, rapid adaptability to product changes, optimized energy consumption, and full digital integration into modern production lines. The study emphasizes the essential role of automation in enhancing the competitiveness of the food industry and outlines the inevitable direction of advancement toward intelligent, sustainable, and fully autonomous packaging.

Keywords: (max. 5) automation; efficiency; productivity; food safety; modern technologies

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INTRODUCTION

Packaging represents one of the essential stages in the food industry, playing a crucial role in protecting products, extending their shelf life, and facilitating distribution and commercialization. Technological progress in recent decades has led to major transformations in packaging processes, marked by the transition from classical, predominantly mechanical equipment to robotized systems characterized by advanced automation, increased precision, and enhanced flexibility (Banu C., 2009).

Packaging and goods form an integrated system; therefore, packaging methods must take into account the interdependent relationships established between the components of this system. Current trends in packaging design and packaging technologies include:

- reducing the consumption of raw materials, resources, and energy;
- increasing product preservation time;
- improving packaging performance by combining different manufacturing materials;
- facilitating the reintegration of packaging materials into the environment in the post-consumer phase.

In the context of increasingly stringent requirements regarding food safety,

traceability, energy efficiency, and productivity, companies in the food industry face constant pressure to optimize their packaging processes. Classical packaging machines remain viable solutions in certain situations due to their lower costs and ease of maintenance; however, their limitations become evident in modern production lines where rapid adaptability and high operational speed are required.

On the other hand, robotized technologies provide precise product handling, seamless integration into fully automated production flows, and reliable operation over long periods. This study analyzes the differences between traditional and robotized packaging equipment, with the aim of identifying optimal solutions for various types of processes and sectors within the food industry.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The comparative study was conducted through a documentary and technical analysis of the main categories of packaging equipment used in the food industry, with a focus on the functional and operational differences between classical and robotized systems. Specialized bibliographic sources, technical manuals, food industry standards, and recent articles on the implementation of robotic technologies were examined.

The comparison between the two types of equipment was carried out by analyzing several technical and economic criteria selected based on their relevance to the food industry.

For each criterion, the technical specifications of both classical and robotized packaging machines were identified, along with their respective advantages and limitations. The collected data were synthesized into a comparative table to provide a structured overview of the differences between the two categories of equipment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Technological transformations over the past two decades have brought profound changes to packaging processes in the food industry, marking a shift from conventional automation to advanced packaging systems based on artificial intelligence and industrial robotics.

These developments align with the broader paradigm of Industry 4.0, which involves the integrated digitalization of processes, the use of autonomous equipment, and continuous connectivity among components of the production chain.

Rapid progress in mechatronics, power electronics, advanced sensor technology, and industrial informatics has enabled the emergence of equipment capable of surpassing the limitations of classical machines. Increasingly strict requirements regarding food safety, processing accuracy, reduction of cross-contamination, and the need to adapt processes to a wide variety of products have driven companies to adopt robotic systems in primary, secondary, and tertiary packaging stages (Schwab K., 2017).

The implementation of industrial robots in the food sector has occurred progressively—initially for simple, repetitive operations (pick & place), and later for more complex tasks such as:

- handling delicate products (soft fruits, pastries, portioned meat);
- high-speed packaging on automatically synchronized lines;
- intelligent labeling and visual inspection;
- palletizing and autonomous warehousing.

For several decades, classical packaging machines formed the backbone of production lines in the food industry. These machines are characterized by predominantly mechanical or electropneumatic mechanisms and are designed

to perform standardized operations such as dosing, forming, filling, sealing, and labeling. They remain widely used today, particularly in small and medium-sized enterprises, due to their low cost, robustness, and operational simplicity (Stan E., 2004).

However, technological advances and the demands of the modern market—product diversification, stricter hygiene standards, and the need for greater flexibility and efficiency—have highlighted the limitations of traditional systems, placing them in contrast with robotized and digital packaging technologies.

From a technical standpoint, classical packaging machines are composed mainly of mechanisms driven mechanically or electromechanically, with motion transmitted through traditional components such as gears, cams, belts, shafts, and basic pneumatic systems.

At the core of these machines lies a linear, relatively rigid logic of operation, where each component performs a repetitive cycle calibrated for a specific product type or packaging format. This construction provides high durability but significantly limits the machine's ability to adapt to changes in the production flow.

Control of classical equipment is generally achieved through analog systems or older-generation electronic controllers that allow only a limited number of automatic adjustments. Fine settings—such as feed speed, dosing pressure, or sealing temperature—require direct operator intervention, introducing an inherent degree of variability into the process.

For instance, in vertical form-fill-seal machines (VFFS), cutting and sealing parameters are manually stabilized, and even small temperature fluctuations can affect packaging quality, especially with sensitive products or films with varying properties. This reliance on human intervention underscores the limitations of classical technology in meeting increasingly strict requirements for repeatability and uniformity.

The materials from which classical packaging machines are built are generally durable and compliant with sanitary regulations; however, their complex mechanical configuration, consisting of many moving components, can make cleaning procedures difficult. The dosing, transport, and sealing sections often include hard-to-reach areas where food residues may accumulate, requiring thorough manual sanitation.

This not only consumes time but also increases the risk of contamination when cleaning is not performed properly.

In general, classical packaging equipment is characterized by higher energy consumption compared to modern machines. Mechanisms based on mechanical, hydraulic, or simple pneumatic actuators do not always include efficient energy-recovery systems or automatic consumption management, which leads to increased operational costs—especially for large producers or continuous processes (Stan E., 2004).

Despite these limitations, classical machines remain valued for their structural reliability: a well-maintained machine can operate for decades with minimal intervention. This characteristic explains their persistence in many factories, where they still represent the "backbone" of packaging processes.

Robotized packaging equipment, on the other hand, stands out through a series of technical features that fundamentally differentiate it from classical machines, representing a true paradigm shift in the organization of food production.

These systems are designed not only to automate repetitive tasks but also to recreate the entire packaging process in an intelligent, adaptive manner that is deeply integrated into the digital infrastructure of the modern factory (Groover, M.P., 2020).

Types of automated equipment include:

- wrapping machines: used to close boxes and apply packaging seals, ensuring optimal product safety;
- labeling machines: apply labels containing product information, barcodes, or QR codes, ensuring traceability and compliance with regulations;
- complete packaging lines: integrating multiple functions such as filling, closing, labeling, and palletizing into a single automated system.

Modern automatic packaging machines follow a systematic seven-step process (Kairui Machinery, 2025):

Step 1: Product receiving and identification – Products enter the system through automated feeding mechanisms. Barcode scanners and RFID readers instantly identify each item. This identification process determines: product type and specifications, suitable packaging materials, required handling methods.

Step 2: Sorting and orientation – Conveyor systems transport products to sorting stations. Robotic arms position items according to destination requirements. Proper alignment ensures correct packaging orientation, appropriate spacing between items, and efficient use of materials.

Step 3: Selection of packaging material – The system automatically selects suitable packaging materials. Intelligent algorithms consider product characteristics and protection needs. Material options include: cardboard boxes of various sizes, protective plastic packaging, foam inserts for fragile items.

Step 4: Packaging and cushioning – Products are securely placed into containers. Automatic cushioning systems add protective materials as needed. This step prevents product movement during transport, damage from impacts or vibrations, and quality issues upon delivery.

Step 5: Sealing and labeling – Packages receive appropriate sealing using automated equipment. Labeling systems add shipping information and tracking codes. Sealing technologies include thermal sealing for plastics, adhesive tape application, and mechanical closure systems.

Step 6: Quality control and verification – Automated inspection systems perform complete checks. Weight sensors verify that the package contents meet specifications. Quality control includes: seal integrity testing, visual inspection systems, dimensional accuracy verification.

Step 7: Sorting and dispatch – Finished packages move to sorting areas. Integration with shipping systems directs items to the correct dispatch locations.

Essentially, robotic technology is based on the ability of equipment to operate autonomously, performing complex operations with a level of precision that is difficult to achieve through conventional mechanical means.

Unlike classical machines, whose operation depends on rigid mechanical sequences, robotic equipment functions through sophisticated algorithms integrated into next-generation programmable control systems.

As a result, the robot's movements—whether involving product handling, packaging positioning, or sealing—are executed with consistent accuracy, leading to unprecedented

uniformity in the technological process (Bolton W., 2018).

An often underestimated yet essential aspect is process ergonomics. Robotic systems take over repetitive, monotonous, or hazardous tasks, relieving operators from activities that cause fatigue, physical strain, or exposure to high temperatures. Instead of performing physical interventions, the operator's role shifts toward monitoring, supervision, and data management.

Consequently, human labor becomes safer and more specialized, while errors caused by operator fatigue are completely eliminated.

Another important characteristic is the adaptability of robotic equipment to modern industry requirements, which involve frequent

packaging changes, product diversification, and process customization. Robots can be reprogrammed quickly to handle new formats without the need for extensive mechanical adjustments. In a competitive market where manufacturers must respond rapidly to commercial demands, this flexibility becomes a major advantage.

In terms of energy consumption, robotic packaging systems are designed to minimize losses and improve resource efficiency. Processes are energetically optimized through algorithms that adjust speed, force, and operation intensity as required. In addition, modern technologies allow the monitoring of consumption and the automatic adaptation of equipment settings to its load conditions.

Table 1

Comparative Table Between Classical and Robotic Packaging Equipment in the Food Industry

Analysis Criterion	Classical Packaging Machines	Robotic Packaging Machines
Operating principle	Mechanical or electromechanical operation, based on rigid repetitive sequences and manual adjustments.	Autonomous, digitally controlled operation with AI algorithms and real-time synchronization.
Level of automation	Low to medium automation; requires human intervention for feeding, adjustments, and supervision.	Advanced automation; fully automated workflow with minimal operator intervention.
Productivity	Constant productivity, limited by operator pace and mechanical wear.	High productivity, continuous 24/7 operation with no variation in work rhythm.
Operational flexibility	Low flexibility; format changes require time and mechanical adjustments.	Very high flexibility; rapid reprogramming and adaptation to new products without mechanical changes.
Precision and repeatability	High variability; precision depends on adjustments and operator skill.	Constant millimetric precision, excellent repeatability due to sensors and intelligent systems.
Packaging quality	Non-uniform over time; risk of dosing or sealing errors.	Consistent and uniform; automatic visual inspection and real-time correction of deviations.
Food safety	Higher risk of contamination due to manual handling; difficult-to-clean internal mechanisms.	Minimal risk; no human contact, food-grade surfaces, superior hygiene.
Investment cost	Low initial investment, accessible for small businesses.	High initial investment, amortized over the medium and long term.
Operational costs	High labor costs, frequent maintenance, higher energy consumption.	Reduced operational costs: optimized consumption, predictive maintenance, reduced labor.
Maintenance	Requires regular mechanical intervention; repairs rely on inexpensive but frequent classical parts.	Digital, sensor-based maintenance; rare and planned downtime.
Integration in production flow	Integrated through simple conveyors with manual synchronization.	Fully digitally integrated (PLC, SCADA, IoT), continuous communication between modules.
Ergonomics and work impact	Repetitive, physically demanding tasks; risk of fatigue and accidents.	Eliminates repetitive labor; operators shift to technical and supervisory tasks.
Sustainability	High energy consumption, higher material losses.	Reduced, optimized consumption; significant reduction in food and material waste.
Optimal use cases	Small units, stable production, low product diversity.	Intensive, diversified production adapted to modern market requirements.

Automation of packaging processes offers numerous advantages, including increased productivity, reduced costs, and improved product quality. However, it is also important to consider the disadvantages. One of the major drawbacks of automation is the high initial cost of acquiring and implementing the equipment.

In addition to the price of the machines themselves, installation, programming, and staff training costs must also be taken into account. For small companies or those with limited financial resources, these expenses may represent a significant barrier.

Automated equipment requires regular maintenance to operate at maximum capacity. These maintenance operations can be costly and require qualified personnel. In the event of malfunctions, production lines may be halted, leading to delivery delays and financial losses.

Alongside maintenance, automation also involves risks associated with software updates and compatibility with other systems, adding an additional layer of complexity and cost.

Automation increases dependence on technology, which can become problematic in cases of operational disruptions, technical errors, or cyberattacks. In such situations, the entire production line may be compromised, affecting deliveries and, consequently, customer satisfaction.

To minimize these risks, companies must invest in cybersecurity and establish well-defined contingency plans to manage possible technical issues.

Ultimately, automated packaging machines operate far more quickly than a human team, enabling the production of significantly larger quantities of packaged goods. This makes them an ideal choice for large enterprises handling substantial product volumes. Moreover, the margin of error is considerably lower in automated processes, resulting in an overall reduction in waste.

Although the initial investment in an automated packaging system may seem costly, the long-term savings are substantial. Automation not only accelerates production but also eliminates the need for manual labor, contributing to significant cost reductions over time. Considering the large volume of products that can be efficiently packaged with an automated system and the reduction of generated waste, the equipment pays for itself rapidly, making operations more profitable in the long run (VLM Poliplast, 2025).

The period 2020–2035 represents one of the most dynamic stages in the history of the food industry, characterized by a rapid transformation toward digitalization, intelligent automation, and complete integration of advanced technologies into production and packaging processes.

The fast pace of technological innovation, rising market demands, and increasing pressure regarding food safety are driving companies to adopt increasingly sophisticated robotic solutions that far exceed the capabilities of traditional machines (Schwab K., 2017).

The packaging market is experiencing long-term changes: shifts in demographic conditions, evolving customer requirements, rising purchasing power in emerging countries, and the growing use of technological solutions have triggered a rethinking of packaging materials and manufacturing processes.

In the future, the expansion of classical packaging functions through additional “smart” features (such as traceability, specific interaction or reaction with the packaged product, or embedded sensors) will provide new opportunities for differentiation from competitors. It remains uncertain whether this expertise will be developed by packaging producers to offer complete solutions to their clients, or whether Smart Packaging competence will remain with the customers themselves.

In many areas of the packaging industry, operational excellence has already become a core element of companies’ identity in ensuring efficient production. In numerous factories, efficiency has been maximized due to strong competitive pressures.

To further exploit efficiency levers, companies are increasingly focusing on inter-factory production network planning. Additionally, interfaces are reduced through stronger customer integration. Another key driver for improving efficiency is the automation of production and logistics.

In the future, for detailed optimization, enterprises will rely even more on the transparency provided by Industry 4.0-compatible production machines. Optimization will be carried out within automation solutions, meaning that interdisciplinary IT expertise will become more important than ever in production.

Digitalization is no longer a buzzword but a major factor of efficiency and effectiveness across all industrial sectors, including the

packaging industry (Horváth & Partner Management Consulting, 2021).

CONCLUSIONS

The comparative analysis of classical and robotized packaging equipment clearly demonstrates that the food industry is undergoing a profound technological transformation driven by the principles of Industry 4.0. Classical packaging machines continue to play an important role in small-scale or highly standardized production environments, where low investment costs, structural robustness, and operational simplicity offer tangible benefits. Their mechanical reliability and long service life still make them viable solutions for certain producers with stable processes and limited product variability.

However, the results of this study show that the limitations of traditional equipment—reduced flexibility, dependence on manual adjustments, variable precision, increased risks of contamination, and higher long-term operational costs—significantly restrict their suitability for modern industrial requirements. As consumer expectations evolve and traceability, hygiene, and productivity standards become increasingly stringent, classical equipment no longer provides the responsiveness and consistency required in contemporary production chains.

In contrast, robotic packaging systems represent a qualitative leap in technological capability. Their high adaptability, autonomous functioning, advanced sensor integration, and digital connectivity enable superior operational accuracy and repeatability, along with continuous optimization of energy and material consumption. Moreover, robotic solutions dramatically reduce human contact with food products, considerably improving hygiene conditions and safety standards. Enhanced ergonomics and the shift of human labor toward monitoring and supervision contribute to safer workplaces and increased professionalism.

Despite their higher initial investment, robotic systems become cost-efficient in the medium and long term through reduced labor

requirements, minimized waste, predictive maintenance, and shorter production cycles. They also offer strategic advantages by supporting rapid format changes, diversified product portfolios, and seamless integration into digitally coordinated production ecosystems.

Overall, the study confirms that robotization is not merely an optional modern upgrade but a strategic necessity for companies seeking competitiveness, sustainability, and compliance with future industry standards. While classical equipment will maintain niche relevance, especially in low-complexity production environments, the long-term direction of the food industry is unequivocally oriented toward intelligent, interconnected, and fully automated packaging systems.

In this context, the transition to robotic technologies becomes a key factor for achieving operational excellence, ensuring product safety, and supporting the sustainable growth of food processing enterprises in an increasingly demanding and dynamic global market.

REFERENCES

- Banu, C. (coord.). *Treatise on Food Industry*, vol. I–III. Bucharest: ASAB Publishing House, 2009–2010.
- Bolton, W. *Mechatronics: Electronic Control Systems in Mechanical and Electrical Engineering*. Pearson, 2018.
- Ciobanu, C. *Packaging and Food Product Packaging Technology*. Galați: Academica Publishing House, 2019.
- Groover, M.P. *Automation, Production Systems and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*. Pearson, 2020.
- Schwab, K. *The Fourth Industrial Revolution*. World Economic Forum, Geneva, 2017.
- Stan, E. *Machines and Equipment for the Food Industry*. Bucharest: Technical Publishing House, 2004.
- *** Horváth & Partner Management Consulting – *The European Packaging Industry in 2025: Trends, Perspectives and Success Factors in a Competitive Market Environment*, 2021.
- *** Kairui Machinery – *What Are Automatic Packaging Machines?*, <https://www.packagingmachineinc.com/ro/What-Are-Automatic-Packaging-Machines-id45595885.html>, website accessed on 5.11.2025.
- *** VLM Poliplast – *Automatic Packaging or Manual Packaging?*, <https://vlmpoliplast.ro/ambalare-automata-versus-ambalare-manuala/>, website accessed on 3.11.2025.

USE OF RENEWABLE ENERGIES IN RURAL TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE – TECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS FOR SUSTAINABLE TOURISM

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The use of renewable energy in rural tourism infrastructure represents a strategic direction for sustainable community development and for reducing environmental impact. This paper analyzes Romania's current energy landscape, highlighting its gradual transition toward clean energy sources in line with European decarbonization policies. The main renewable technologies applicable in rural areas—solar, wind, geothermal, biomass, and micro-hydropower—are presented, along with the advantages of integrating them into guesthouses, agritourism farms, and traditional rural households. The study also emphasizes the economic, social, and cultural effects of implementing renewable energy in rural tourism: job creation, diversification of the local economy, promotion of environmental education, and improvement of the ecological image of tourist destinations. By using local energy resources and strengthening energy autonomy, rural tourism villages can become models of good practice in sustainable tourism. The conclusion shows that large-scale adoption of renewable energy is essential for a competitive, responsible, and future-oriented rural tourism sector.

Keywords: (max. 5) renewable energy; rural tourism; sustainability; energy efficiency

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INTRODUCTION

The economic development of a country largely depends on the creation and optimization of access to energy sources. Energy consumption is directly proportional to the population size, and with demographic growth, an increasing amount of resources is needed to cover the minimum needs of consumers. Globally, the energy sector has a significant impact on the environment, compelling authorities to implement measures that ensure a stable level of greenhouse gas emissions released into the atmosphere, as well as to initiate strategies to reduce them (Purece C., 2020). Rural tourism is one of the forms of tourism with the highest potential for sustainable development, as it capitalizes on local natural and cultural resources without degrading them. In the current context of climate change and the transition toward a green economy, the use of renewable energy in rural tourism infrastructure becomes essential for reducing environmental impact and increasing the energy efficiency of tourism activities.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Romania's energy situation lies at the intersection of tradition and transformation, reflecting both its historical dependence on conventional energy sources and its

commitment to transitioning toward a sustainable, low-carbon future. As a member state of the European Union (EU), Romania aligns its energy system and policies with the broader European framework, while also considering its specific national challenges and opportunities.

Romania's energy mix is characterized by diversity, including a combination of fossil fuels, renewable sources, and nuclear energy. Historically, the country has relied heavily on fossil fuels—especially coal and natural gas—to meet its energy needs. Its extensive coal reserves have played a crucial role in ensuring energy security, while natural gas has served as a vital, cleaner alternative for electricity production and heating. In recent years, EU legislation and sustainability goals have driven Romania to diversify its energy sources, with renewable energy becoming a key element of this transformation (Ministry of Energy, 2023). Fossil fuels remain the primary sources for electricity and heat production, particularly coal and natural gas. However, renewable energy sources have steadily increased their share in the national energy mix, reaching 24% in 2018.

The implementation of public policies supporting renewable energy—whether through EU directives or local initiatives—has produced positive outcomes (Sandbag Smart Climate Policy).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Renewable energy refers to energy produced from non-fossil, naturally replenished sources on a human timescale. Renewable sources include solar and wind energy, ocean

energy, hydropower, geothermal energy, and bioenergy. The main types of renewable energy, relevant technologies, and typical applications are presented in Figure 1 (European Court of Auditors, 2018).

Source: European Court of Auditors – Renewable energy for sustainable rural development: potential synergies are considerable but remain largely untapped, Special Report No 5 of 2018

Figure no. 1 Renewable energy sources, technologies and applications

Source: Ministry of Energy - National Integrated Plan for Energy and Climate Change 2021-2030, version 2023

Figure no. 2 Target and estimated trajectory regarding the share of energy from RES in gross final energy consumption

The comparative analysis of the evolution of total energy from renewable sources (RES), gross final energy consumption and the share of renewable energy in gross final consumption, for the period 2019–2030, allows the assessment of the coherence of national policies in the field of energy transition, as well as

Romania's estimated progress in aligning with European objectives on decarbonization and green energy

The share of renewable energy in gross final consumption shows a sustained increase, from 24.2% in 2019 to 36.2% in 2030. This evolution indicates that Romania aims not only

to meet, but also to exceed the objectives set by the European Green Deal and the Renewable Energy Directives. The continuous increase in the share of RES reflects the implementation of efficient strategies, oriented towards sustainable production, energy independence and carbon emissions reduction.

Renewable energy plays an essential role in modernizing and ensuring the sustainability of the rural tourism sector. By capitalizing on the available natural resources, rural communities can develop a competitive tourism model that respects both the environment and local traditions.

Renewable energy thus becomes not only a source of clean power but also a symbol of a new way of practicing tourism—one based on balance, responsibility, and respect for nature.

Rural tourism generally takes place in less industrialized areas, with modest technological infrastructure and limited access to conventional energy resources. At the same time, these regions possess significant natural potential—sun, wind, water, and biomass—which can be harnessed through modern technologies that produce clean energy.

By using renewable energy sources, rural tourism becomes an active driver of sustainable development, contributing to environmental protection and improving the quality of life in local communities.

The adoption of renewable sources results in reduced pollution, lower operating costs, and greater energy autonomy for rural households and guesthouses. Meanwhile, tourists are increasingly drawn to ecological destinations where they can experience a sustainable lifestyle in direct contact with nature.

Renewable energy supports the development of responsible tourism that does not harm the environment and respects local ecosystems. Key benefits include:

- reducing dependence on conventional energy sources, such as fossil fuels, which are both polluting and costly.
- improving the energy efficiency of tourism facilities through the use of modern and intelligent energy systems.
- protecting the environment by lowering greenhouse gas emissions and reducing waste resulting from traditional energy use.
- enhancing the ecological image of rural tourist destinations, making them more attractive to environmentally conscious visitors.

- stimulating the local economy, as investments in renewable technologies generate new jobs—installers, electricians, technicians, equipment suppliers, etc.

In addition, integrating renewable energy in rural tourism has an educational dimension. Tourists can directly observe how solar panels, wind turbines, or biomass systems work, increasing their awareness of responsible resource consumption.

The use of renewable energy is not only a technological solution but also a social and cultural one. In rural areas, these technologies contribute to preserving the natural landscape by reducing pressure on forests and traditional fuel resources. They offer communities the possibility to develop economically without compromising natural heritage or traditional architecture.

By using local energy sources—sun, wind, water, biomass—rural tourism villages can achieve energy independence, which is particularly important in remote areas where connection to the national grid is difficult or costly. Thus, renewable energy becomes a form of sustainable autonomy, supporting both economic activities and the comfort of tourists and residents.

Rural areas can also play a key role in energy innovation. These locations often serve as testing grounds for new renewable energy technologies, as they are the places where installations are implemented and evaluated.

Romania has a wide range of renewable energy resources: wind, solar, biomass, hydropower, and biogas. However, the use of these resources requires appropriate financing, regulatory frameworks, dedicated infrastructure (electricity distribution networks, biomass processing and storage facilities), fair energy tariffs, and qualified personnel (engineers, auditors, energy service companies) (Isarie C. et al., 2023).

The integration of renewable energy in rural tourism infrastructure involves implementing technologies adapted to local conditions, ensuring both tourist comfort and environmental protection. Selecting appropriate solutions depends on geographic conditions, available natural resources, and the type of tourism activities in the area.

Main Renewable Energy Technologies Applicable in Rural Tourism

1. Solar Energy – Photovoltaic Panels and Solar Thermal Systems

Solar energy is the most accessible and widespread form of renewable energy in rural environments. It can be harnessed in several ways: concentrated solar power for heat generation, photovoltaic conversion into electricity, or passive systems using natural climate conditions. Solar energy can be used at very small local scales or in large installations. One major obstacle is its intermittent availability, which requires the use of storage systems or hybrid solutions, increasing costs (Gusa M. et al., 2011).

According to Isarie C. et al. (2023), solar thermal energy can operate at:

- low temperatures – for space heating;
- medium temperatures – for domestic hot water;
- high temperatures – even for electricity production.

Advantages: low long-term costs, minimal maintenance, silent operation, aesthetic integration into the natural landscape.

2. Wind Energy – Small-Scale Wind Turbines

Wind energy is a clean source of electricity obtained by transforming wind power into mechanical energy and then electricity. In rural areas exposed to strong air currents—plains, plateaus, coastal or hilly regions—micro wind turbines can produce electricity for the daily needs of guesthouses or farm stays. These systems can be grid-connected or operate autonomously (CAISIN S., 2014).

Advantages: operation at night, low maintenance, ideal for isolated areas lacking access to the electric grid.

3. Geothermal Energy – Heat Pumps and Natural Climate Systems

Geothermal energy represents the thermal energy stored within the Earth's crust. Temperatures increase with depth, making geothermal sources more efficient at greater depths, though access is limited by drilling constraints (CAISIN S., 2014).

Geothermal or air-water heat pumps allow guesthouses and cabins to maintain constant indoor temperatures, significantly reducing consumption of natural gas or wood. These systems can be fully automated and integrated into both new buildings and rehabilitated traditional structures. Regions such as Băile Felix, Sovata, and Covasna already use geothermal energy for heating tourism facilities and supplying thermal water to pools.

Advantages: high energy efficiency, year-round stability, zero pollutant emissions.

4. Biomass Energy – Ecological Boilers and Stoves

Biomass refers to organic matter that can be converted into energy. This includes wood, agricultural residues, animal waste, and dedicated energy crops, as well as municipal residues such as park maintenance waste or certain food-industry by-products (Maican E., 2015).

Biomass systems can heat entire guesthouses or only domestic hot water and can be combined with solar systems for hybrid solutions. Biomass is especially suitable for mountainous and forested rural areas where raw materials are easily accessible.

Advantages: low operating costs, energy independence, use of local resources.

5. Micro-Hydropower Plants and Hydraulic Turbines

In many developing countries, micro-hydropower plants play a key role in rural—especially mountainous—economic development. They can supply energy for industrial, agricultural, and domestic uses, either mechanically or through coupled electric generators. Micro - hydroturbines are among the most efficient and affordable generators of electricity (Dulgheru V., 2021).

In Romania, such systems have been tested in the Apuseni and Făgăraș Mountains, where they can cover up to 70–80% of a rural tourism facility's annual energy needs.

Advantages: constant energy supply, low operating costs after installation, long service life.

Advantages of integrating renewable energy into rural tourism infrastructure

The integration of renewable energy into rural tourism infrastructure brings multiple economic, ecological, social, and cultural benefits, contributing to the transformation of tourist villages into models of sustainable development. The use of these clean energy sources not only ensures the reduction of pollution, but also the modernization of tourism services, the decrease of operating costs, and the improvement of the image of rural destinations.

The adoption of technologies based on renewable energy generates significant long-term savings. Although the initial investment may be high, operating and maintenance costs are low, and the payback period is achieved within a few years.

By installing solar panels, small wind turbines or biomass-fired plants, guesthouses and agritourism farms can produce their own electric and thermal energy, significantly reducing their monthly utility expenses. In addition, units that use renewable sources can benefit from tax incentives, financial support through European programs (PNDR, PNRR, Environmental Fund) and official recognition as “green units” or “eco-tourist” facilities.

Besides cost reduction, renewable energies contribute to the economic stability of rural communities, offering the possibility to reinvest the savings achieved into the modernization of services or the development of local tourism infrastructure.

The most important benefit of using renewable energy is its positive impact on the environment. These sources do not emit carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases, thus significantly reducing the carbon footprint of tourism activities. They also do not generate hazardous waste and do not affect soil, water or air.

The implementation of renewable systems contributes to the conservation of natural resources and to the reduction of dependence on fossil fuels. In mountainous areas, for example, the use of modern biomass plants reduces illegal logging and encourages the rational management of forest resources. Moreover, clean energy supports the protection of biodiversity and of the natural landscape, which are essential elements for the tourist attractiveness of rural villages and regions. Thus, tourism powered by renewable energy becomes a form of tourism with a minimal environmental footprint, compatible with the principles of ecotourism and nature conservation.

The integration of renewable energy into rural tourism also has an important social dimension. Firstly, it contributes to the creation of new jobs in the field of installation, maintenance and management of energy equipment. Local communities can become directly involved in the production and consumption of green energy, developing new skills and diversifying their sources of income. Secondly, the adoption of renewable technologies increases the quality of life in rural areas. Access to clean and constant energy ensures greater comfort for residents and tourists, encouraging the development of other complementary services (gastronomy, agritourism, handicrafts).

The use of renewable energy also contributes to the environmental education of the population and tourists, fostering responsible attitudes toward resource consumption. Visitors can directly observe how solar, wind or biomass systems work, and thus become, in turn, promoters of sustainable behavior.

Rural tourism is deeply linked to the cultural identity of the Romanian village. By integrating renewable energy, traditional households and guesthouses can harmoniously combine technological modernity with the authenticity of local architecture. Solar panels can be discreetly integrated into roofs, wind turbines can be placed so as not to disturb the landscape, and biomass systems can use resources coming directly from local agricultural activities.

In this way, the ecological and authentic image of rural destinations is strengthened, making them increasingly attractive for tourists concerned with environmental protection and genuine experiences.

Tourism units that adopt these solutions can obtain ecological certifications (such as Eco-Romania or Green Key), increasing their visibility and prestige on the tourism market.

CONCLUSIONS

The use of renewable energy in rural tourism infrastructure is not just a technological option but a necessity for environmental protection and sustainable tourism development. By adopting these solutions, rural areas can achieve a balance between tradition and innovation, between natural heritage conservation and the modern needs of tourists.

Large-scale implementation of green technologies reduces the carbon footprint of tourism and increases the attractiveness of rural destinations, strengthening Romania’s image as an ecological European destination. Renewable energy solutions offer rural tourism infrastructure a clear direction toward energy autonomy, efficiency, and sustainability. When properly adapted to local conditions and supported by public policies and European funds, rural tourism villages can become models of good practice for Romania’s green economy.

Renewable energy integration represents a fundamental step toward transforming tourism into a sustainable, competitive, and responsible sector. Economic, ecological, and social benefits interact, generating positive

effects for both the environment and local communities. Through the adoption of clean energy, rural tourism villages become examples of balance between tradition and innovation, contributing to building a green future for Romanian tourism.

On the long term, investments in renewable energy support sustainable economic development in rural areas, reduce energy poverty, increase resilience, and provide a stable foundation for ecological and cultural tourism.

REFERENCES

- Caisin S., Şveţ Aurelia, Halaim Natalia, 2014. Renewable Energy Sources, teaching support material, National Book Chamber, Chişinău
- Dulgheru V., Bodnariuc I., Gutu M., Rabei I., Ciobanu O. 2021. Renewable Energy Conversion Systems: Theoretical Foundations and Practical Aspects, Chişinău
- Gusa M., Ionel Ioana, Popa B., Ionescu C., Istrate M., Cenuşă V, 2011. Renewable Energy Sources, Publishing House of the Academy of Scientists of Romania, Bucharest,
- Isarie C., Ciofu F., Fălădău Alina, Stoica A., Prodea L, 2023. Guide on the Benefits of Using Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency in Sibiu County, Sibiu
- Maican E. – Renewable Energy Systems, Printech Publishing House, Bucharest, 2015
- Purece C. – Analysis on the Use of Renewable Energy Sources in Romania, *Energetica* Journal, Year 68, No. 9/2020
- European Court of Auditors, 2018 – Renewable Energy for Sustainable Rural Development: Potential Synergies Are Considerable but Remain Largely Untapped, Special Report No. 5
- Ministry of Energy – National Integrated Plan on Energy and Climate Change 2021–2030, 2023 version, available at: https://energie.gov.ro/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/NECP_Romania_first-draft-version-21.12.2023_RO.pdf, website accessed on 07.11.2025
- Sandbag Smart Climate Policy, 2020. Harnessing Romania's Renewable Potential: The Road to Carbon Neutrality, Informational Note – October

ANALYSIS OF AVERAGE PRICES FOR AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Agriculture is a strategic sector of the economy, and the prices of agricultural products are a key indicator of market performance. The analysis of average prices provides information about the economic evolution, the profitability of producers and the purchasing power of the population. The purpose of the research is to analyze the level, dynamics and variation of average prices for the main agricultural products (vegetables and fruits), for the period 2022-2025, using statistical tools and methods.

Keywords: agri-food market, average prices, vegetables, fruits, farm gate.

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INTRODUCTION

The evolution of agri-food prices is an essential indicator for assessing the performance of the agricultural sector and its impact on household consumption. In the period 2020–2025, the agri-food market in Romania was strongly influenced by factors such as inflation, the increase in the costs of agricultural inputs (diesel, fertilizers, energy), extreme climatic conditions (drought, frosts), as well as the dynamics of demand and supply for horticultural products (Beleniuc G, Miron L., 2013, Diaconu A., 2018,). The analysis presents the evolution of average prices for vegetables and fruits sold in agri-food markets, as well as their prices at the farm gate – an important indicator of the level of remuneration of agricultural producers.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The objectives of the analysis refer to: determining the average prices by categories of agricultural products, analyzing the variation and dynamics of prices over time (year), interpreting the fluctuations and their causes, identifying the general trends on the agricultural products market.

The average price for products sold in the agri-food markets and the average price at the farm gate (lei/kg) represents the ratio between the total value of sales and the total quantity sold:

$$\text{Average price} = \frac{\sum(p_i \times q_i)}{\sum q_i}$$

where: p_i – the unit price, q_i – the quantity sold

Average prices at product/country level are calculated as a weighted arithmetic average. The weights are calculated at the county level, based on the data provided by the plant and animal production indicators (Novak A., 2006).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The analysis of the average annual prices of the main vegetables sold in the agri-food markets in Romania highlights a general upward trend for most products in the period 2022–2025. This evolution is influenced by economic, agricultural and climatic factors, such as inflation, the increase in the price of agricultural inputs, weather conditions, transport costs and production variations.

From the analysis of the statistical data we have the following situations:

1. Vegetables with constant and accentuated growth. Here are inscribed:

- beans (dried) - the price increased from 13.06 lei/kg (2022) to 15.11 lei/kg (Sept. 2025). It is one of the vegetables with the most stable growth, reflecting the constant demand and dependence on imports;

- dried garlic - registered a strong upward evolution: 18.69 lei/kg (2022) → 25.39 lei/kg (Sept. 2025). Growth of over 36%, influenced by limited domestic production and expensive imports.

- autumn cabbage - from 2.60 lei/kg (2022) to 4.14 lei/kg (2024), then a decrease to 3.70 lei/kg in September 2025. Prices increased significantly in 2023–2024 due to climatic conditions and rising transport prices;

- spinach- strong growth: 8.37 → 14.05 lei/kg. Being a seasonal product, sensitive to climate change, which explains the volatility of prices;

- leeks- From 7.45 lei/kg (2023) to 10.2 lei/kg in January 2025, then drops to 8.76 lei/kg in September. Prices are influenced by seasonality, reduced supply but also changes in consumer preferences.

2. Vegetables with moderate variations, but generally growing are:

- field tomatoes- the average price evolved from 5.56 lei/kg (2022) to 7.01 lei/kg (Sept. 2025). This increase is explained by the increase in the price of energy, fertilizers and transport.

- autumn potatoes- the average price increased from 2.83 → 3.50 lei/kg (Sept. 2025). The price is relatively stable, with small variations, due to the high domestic production.

- capsicum / fat / bell pepper - all three categories show moderate increases. High demand for canned food keeps prices relatively high. (bell peppers: 7.17 → 7.92 lei/kg, bell peppers: 5.44 → 5.93 lei/kg, bell peppers: 6.72 → 7.91 lei/kg).

- field cucumbers – the average price increased from 4.65 lei/kg to 6.72 lei/kg, as production is strongly influenced by weather conditions and logistics costs.

3. Vegetables with high volatility

- cauliflower- average price increasing, from 6.73 → 9.91 lei/kg (2024), then drops to 8.86 lei/kg in September 2025. The price depends a lot on the season and the domestic offer, but also on imports.

- beans pods- register an unstable price: 12.37 (2022) → drops to 11.80 (2023) → rises strongly to 17.51 (Sept. 2025). The evolution reflects both seasonality and production fluctuations.

- greenhouse tomatoes / greenhouse cucumbers- prices are high due to the high cost of heating protected spaces. In general, the evolution stabilizes at levels above field production.

Table 1

Average annual prices of the main vegetables sold in the agri-food markets total country (lei/kg)

	2022	2023	2024	January 2025	September 2025
Beans (dried)	13,06	14,64	15,35	15,81	15,11
Early and summer potatoes	2,81	3,67	3,54	:	3,24
Autumn potatoes	2,83	3,45	3,66	3,64	3,5
Cauliflower	6,73	7,14	9,91	:	8,86
Early and summer white cabbage	3,21	3,23	3,59	:	:
Autumn cabbage	2,6	2,79	4,14	4,56	3,7
Camp Tomato	5,56	6,14	6,86	:	7,01
Evening tomato	:	14,34	13,39	:	:
Field cucumbers	4,65	4,78	6,87	:	6,72
Greenhouse cucumbers	:	8,04	7,15	:	:
Carrots	4,21	5,4	5,41	5,28	5,36
Dried onion	3,93	5,3	5	5,03	4,82
Peas, Pods	:	12,14	13,75	:	:
Pasta beans	12,37	11,8	14,18	:	17,51
Cultured mushrooms	:	12,83	12,42	12,63	13,27
Zucchini	:	4,12	5,05	:	5,02
Leek	:	7,45	8,51	10,2	8,76
Cape peppers	7,17	7,43	7,97	:	7,92
Bell pepper	5,44	5,79	6,35	:	5,93
Gogosar pepper	6,72	7,26	7,59	:	7,91
Eggplant	4,47	4,95	4,88	:	4,7
Dried garlic	18,69	18,8	22,57	24,92	25,39
Spinach	8,37	9,62	10,07	:	14,05

Source: INS - Tempoonline database

Table 2

Average farm gate prices of the main vegetables, per country (lei/kg)						
	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	Third quarter 2025
Beans	:	:	:	8,8	8,49	9,83
Early, semi-early and summer potatoes	1,03	0,95	1,38	1,79	1,83	1,77
Autumn potatoes	1,1	0,89	1,55	1,77	1,88	1,6
Cauliflower	:	:	:	4,61	5,87	5,94
White cabbage - early and summer	:	:	:	1,8	2,22	2,37
White cabbage - autumn	:	:	:	1,62	2,6	2
Camp Tomato	2,85	2,68	3,55	3,59	4,3	5,02
Evening tomato	:	:	:	:	8,62	:
Field cucumbers	2,33	2,4	3,09	3,2	4,73	4,81
Greenhouse cucumbers	:	:	:	4,94	3,97	:
Carrots	:	:	:	2,82	3,06	3,13
Dried onion	:	:	:	3,28	2,93	3,15
Peas, Pods	:	:	:	6,39	7,47	:
Pasta beans	4,71	5,55	:	7,54	8,14	13,62
Cultured mushrooms	:	:	:	9,16	10,27	10,49
Zucchini	:	:	:	2,35	2,99	3,24
Leek	:	:	:	3,18	3,73	4
Long pepper - cape type	3,28	3,65	4,98	5,08	5,84	6,04
Bell pepper	2,76	2,69	4,32	3,99	4,57	4,42
Gogosar pepper	3,69	3,4	5,42	5,09	5,28	6,31
Eggplant	:	:	:	3,11	3,09	3,53
Dried garlic	:	:	:	12,27	14,16	17,2
Spinach	:	:	:	5,29	6,15	8,46
Spinach	:	:	:	5,29	6,15	8,46

Source: INS - Tempoonline database

4. Vegetables with reduced growth or stagnation

- Eggplant- almost constant price: 4.47 (2022) → 4.70 (Sept. 2025). The stable domestic supply explains the price stagnation.

- Dried onions- the average price rises from 3.93 in 2022 to 5.30 in 2023, but drops slightly to 4.82 in September 2025. Price influenced by harvests from Poland and the Netherlands, the main foreign seasonal suppliers.

The analysis of average prices at the farm gate reflects the dynamics of the costs incurred in the agricultural production stage, before the products enter the commercial chain. The evolution of these prices is influenced by factors such as climatic conditions, input costs (seeds, fertilizers, energy, water), fluctuations in supply and demand, as well as the general economic context.

This paragraph will briefly present the results of the research. Conclusions will be concise and clear, no hypothesis and probability. Each conclusion will start on a new row. The text will be edited not numbered or bullet lists. This section can be skipped, but should be added if the results and discussion part is long.

In the interval 2020–2025 (Q3), the data shows a general growth trend for most of the vegetables analyzed. We have the following situations:

1. Vegetables with strong and continuous growths:

- Field tomatoes – total growth of over 75% in five years. The main reasons are given by the high costs of energy and irrigation, the decrease in domestic production, competitive pressure from imports;

- Field cucumbers- the price has almost doubled, reflecting the sensitivity of crops to climatic conditions;

- Dried garlic – growth for the analyzed range of +40%, due to low domestic production and dependence on imports;

- Spinach – growth of over 60%, influenced by seasonality and high labor costs;

- Pod beans – very accentuated growth (of almost 300%), volatile production data, high demand, losses in the logistics chain;

2. Vegetables with moderate and stable growth:

-early, semi-early and summer potatoes: 1.03 lei/kg (2020) → 1.77 lei/kg (Q3 2025). Relatively moderate but steady growth;

- autumn potatoes - 1.10 lei/kg → 1.88 lei/kg (2024), decrease to 1.60 lei/kg in 2025.

Prices remain affordable due to high domestic production;

- carrots-2.82 lei/kg (2023) → 3.13 lei/kg (Q3 2025), slowly upward evolution;

- dried onions - 3.28 lei/kg (2023) → 3.15 lei/kg (2025). Slight decrease, explained by good harvests on the European market and significant imports;

- cauliflower- increase of almost 30%, from 4.61 lei/kg (2023) → 5.94 lei/kg (Q3 2025);

- early white cabbage -stable evolution, but influenced by the season. The price increased from 1.80 lei/kg (2023) → 2.37 lei/kg (2025);

3. High volatility vegetables:

- greenhouse tomatoes - high price due to the cost of energy in protected areas, the

increase in the price of water, the increase in the cost of labor during the harvest period, etc.;

- greenhouse cucumbers: significant decrease, due to increased competition and efficiency on farms - from 4.94 lei/kg (2023) → 3.97 lei/kg (2024);

- autumn white cabbage – the price is dependent on climatic conditions and available stocks;

- bell pepper / bell pepper / capsicum - all show variations, but with moderate increases overall. They are sensitive to demand, but also to the high costs of inputs.

4. Relatively stable products:

- eggplant- low growth, with small variations in production.

- beans - moderate growth, under the influence of imports.

Table 3

Average annual prices of the main fruits sold in the agri-food markets in the whole country (lei/kg)

	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	September 2025
Melons	3,48	2,92	4,44	4,19	4,53	4,63
Watermelons	1,76	1,52	2,41	2,72	2,48	2,29
Apple	3,71	3,57	3,67	4,09	4,51	6,3
Pears	6,13	6,1	6,77	8,21	8,64	9,91
Peaches	5,95	7,76	7,83	8,13	8,44	:
Apricot	7,46	7,56	7,8	9,09	8,62	:
Cherry	11,91	13,12	12,29	17,48	14	:
Cherry	8,1	9,25	9,3	11,57	11,25	:
Plum	3,75	4,31	5,47	4,86	5,29	6,31
Walnuts	8,15	8,79	9,39	9,16	9,77	10,77
Strawberry	10,02	8,85	8,87	9,22	12,54	:
Table grapes	5,63	6,3	6,85	7,39	8,82	8,47
Bee honey	28,73	30,09	32,05	33,96	34,89	36,31

Source: INS - Tempoonline database

The analysis of the evolution of the average prices of the main fruits sold in the agri-food markets shows a general upward trend, with significant variability depending on the type of fruit, seasonality, domestic production and climatic conditions. The increases in the period 2020–2025 are also influenced by inflationary pressure, transport costs, the impact of drought on crops and the increase in the price of agricultural inputs.

We have the following situations:

1. Fruits with significant and continuous growth:

- apples-strong growth in the last two years (+40% between 2023 and 2025). The main reasons are :p lower production in years with extreme weather phenomena, increased storage and sorting costs, high demand for Romanian varieties;

- pear-growth of 62% over the analyzed period, due to lower domestic production,

partial dependence on imports and high logistics costs;

- nuts- prices are constantly rising, reflecting strong demand and laborious harvesting;

- table grapes- 5.63 lei/kg (2020) → 8.82 lei/kg (2024). Prices remain high in 2025 (8.47 lei/kg) due to drought sensitivity, increased costs of plantation maintenance;

- honey - increase of about 26%, influenced by the decrease in beekeeping production in dry years, but also by the increase in packaging costs.

2. Fruits with high volatility, influenced by the season and production:

- cherries-minimum price 11.91 lei/kg (2020) and peak price 17.48 lei/kg (2023). Cherries are extremely sensitive to late frosts and rains, which explains the large price jumps;

- cherries-steady but moderate growth; dependence on seasonal production and crop quality;

- apricots- the apricot crop is unstable, strongly affected by the spring frost. The evolution of prices is- 7.46 lei/kg (2020) → 9.09 lei/kg (2023);

- peaches-growth of over 40%. Prices for 2025 are not available, but the previous trend shows an expanding market.

3. Fruits with relatively stable prices or moderate variations:

- melons-moderate growth, especially in 2022–2025;

- watermelons – prices fluctuate depending on the abundance of domestic production;

The 2024–2025 decline indicates good harvests and/or competition among producers.

- plums – constant growth, with moderate variations (e.g.: decrease in 2023 due to high production).

Table 4

Average farm gate prices of the main fruits, per country (lei/kg)						
	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	Third quarter 2025
Melons	:	:	:	2,27	2,31	2,8
Watermelons	:	:	:	1,43	1,6	1,64
Table apples	:	:	:	2,48	2,61	3,94
Pear of dough	:	:	:	5,05	4,44	6,17
Peaches	:	:	:	4,39	3,8	8,46
Apricot	:	:	:	4,8	5,62	11,05
Cherry	:	:	:	9	8,6	17,14
Cherry	:	:	:	5,45	5,66	12,01
Plum	:	:	:	2,21	2,39	3,8
Walnuts	:	:	:	:	:	6,99
Field strawberries	:	:	:	4,94	6,73	:
Table grapes	:	:	:	3,24	3,38	3,65
Bee honey	16,86	18,03	21,52	23,37	24,33	24,89

Source: INS - Tempoonline database

Data on farm gate prices for the main fruits show a strong upward trend in the period analyzed, especially in the period 2023–2025. These developments reflect the increase in the price of agricultural inputs (diesel, fertilizers, packaging), inflation pressure, climatic influences (drought, late frosts), as well as the increase in harvesting and transport costs. For most fruits, the period 2025 (even just up to the third quarter) marks the highest values in the entire series. We have as follows:

1. Fruits with very high growth (high volatility):

- apricots-Prices have almost doubled in just two years because it is a crop sensitive to spring frost; reduced production in climate-affected years; high demand versus limited supply;

- cherries-The price increased by almost 100% between 2024 and 2025. The explanations come from the fact that cherries are some of the most sensitive fruits; Small harvests cause strong price increases.

- cherries-The price has doubled in two years due to decreasing production, higher harvesting costs, increased demand for processing (juices, preserves).

- peaches-Strong growth after a temporary decline, due to large variations in production and sensitivity to climatic factors.

2. Fruits with consistent but more balanced growths:

- table apples -Growth of +50% between 2023 and 2025. Causes could be: damage to drought orchards, increased storage and selection costs;

- table pears- After a decrease in 2024, the price increases significantly in 2025 due to oscillating production and expensive imports;

- plums: Growth of about 70%. There is an increased demand for distillation (brandy, brandy), lower production in some areas;

- table grapes-Moderate but stable growth. Production is influenced by drought and vineyard maintenance costs.

3. Fruits with low prices and moderate increases:

- melons-Increase of about 23%;

- watermelons-Small growths, reflecting high production and strong competition among farmers.

4. Other agricultural products:

- field strawberries-Significant increase (+36%).

- nuts-High value, explained by high demand and difficult harvesting.

- Bee honey-48% increase in five years explained by declining bee populations, adverse climatic conditions, rising production costs.

CONCLUSIONS

The average prices of agricultural products registered a general upward trend during the period under review. The increases are influenced by: the increase in the price of agricultural inputs, extreme climatic conditions, inflationary pressure, logistics and transport, the reduction of domestic production of certain crops.

The price differences between products are significant, depending on seasonality and economic factors. Climate-sensitive vegetables and fruits (cherries, apricots, beans, garlic, spinach, tomatoes) recorded the greatest fluctuations. Basic fruits and vegetables (apples, potatoes, onions, cabbage) grow moderately but stably.

Farm gate prices confirm that agricultural producers are facing major cost increases, which is automatically passed on to the end consumer.

Permanent market monitoring is necessary to establish effective pricing and production strategies. Under these conditions, the following are necessary:

- Implementation of agricultural product price forecasting systems;
- Supporting producers through policies that stabilize prices (intervention stocks, subsidies, guaranteed price).
- Promoting direct contracts between farmers and processors, to reduce price variations.

REFERENCES

- Beleniuc, G, Miron, L., 2013. Managementul exploatareii si al calitatii produselor Agricole, Editura Universitară.
- Diaconu, A., 2018. Economia fermelor agricole. Marketing agroalimentar , Editura Economica.
- Novak, A., 2006. Bazele statisticii, Editura Prouniversitaria.
- *** INS - Tempoonline database, <http://statistici.insse.ro:8077/tempo-online/>.

ANALYSIS OF THE VALUE OF MARKET SERVICES OFFERED BY RESTAURANTS TO THE POPULATION

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Market services in the field of public catering represent an essential segment of the economy, contributing to the satisfaction of the population's consumption needs and local economic development. Statistically, the activity of restaurants is evaluated through a series of indicators that reflect the economic value of the services provided, the dynamics of the volume of activity and the efficiency of the use of resources. For the analysis of economic activity, service indices and turnover volume indices are used, which express the evolution over time of economic results. The paper includes the analysis of specific indicators for this field for the period 2021-2025.

Keywords: services, social development, volume, indices, trends

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INTRODUCTION

People's needs are numerous and they are amplified and diversified with the increase in the degree of complexity of society. Consequently, the services provided to the population today are also diverse, non-homogeneous and materialize in particularly varied activities, with different effects (Criveanu I., 2005). Combining the economic and social effects of the final service activities for the population results in the improvement of the living conditions, the increase of the quality of life and the development of the personality of each person (Ionașcu V., Pavel C., 2017). The final services for the population characterize the level of development of a society, express the degree of satisfaction of the needs of the natural persons in that society. These services for the population cover general human needs or those arising from living together in social communities, starting with services that ensure the basic conditions of existence and ending with services that cover higher consumption needs (Ioncica M., 2006).

At present, the services provided to the population in the hotel-restaurant segment tend to occupy an increasingly important place in the total services provided by the population.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In correlation with the aspects presented above, the objectives of the paper refer to: determining the value of the services provided to the population by restaurants, calculating

and interpreting the turnover volume indices, formulating conclusions regarding the evolution of the activity and market trends (Rus M., 2015, Petcu N., 2000). From the multitude of indicators that characterize the sector, we considered it necessary to analyze:

The value of the services provided by restaurants for the population (V_t) with reference to the total income obtained from the activity of serving the population in a period of time (month, quarter, year) (Tarnita D., 2004).

$$V_t = \sum_{i=1}^n p_i \times q_i$$

where: p_i = the average price of the service, q_i = the volume of services (number of customers, portions, menus, etc.). We made annual comparisons p_i and q_i .

Turnover Volume Index (CAI) Turnover (CA) expresses the total value of sales of goods and services. (Tarnita D., 2004).

$$I_{CA} = \frac{CA_1}{CA_0} \times 100$$

where: CA_1 = turnover in the current period, CA_0 = turnover in the previous period.

The index above 100 shows the expansion of economic activity; The index below 100 signifies a decrease in turnover.

Value indices of turnover in restaurants - measures the evolution of sales, usually using the Laspeyres index formula (standard method for calculating the variation in prices and

volumes); are calculated as non-deflated weighted indices (according to European

provisions - EU Regulation 2152/2019 and EU Delegated Regulation 1197/2020. (Rus M., INS).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The data presented highlights a positive evolution of the services sector in the period 2021–2023. The total branches of the services sector increased from 35,290.8 in 2021 to 54,409.1 in 2023, which represents an increase

of 19,118.3 million lei. This significant growth suggests a sustained development of services activities, possibly as a result of the economic recovery, the diversification of supply and the increase in demand from the population.

Table 1

Value of services provided by restaurants for the population (million lei)			
	2021	2022	2023
Total branches of the services sector	35290,8	49905	54409,1
Restaurants	18394,7	25585,3	27717,3

Source: INS- tempoonline database

The restaurant industry has also seen an upward trend. The total value increased from 18,394.7 in 2021 to 27,717.3 in 2023, marking an increase of 9,322.6 million lei. This evolution can be explained by the return of consumption in the post-pandemic context, the expansion of capacities, investments in the modernization of public catering units, the change in consumer

behavior, with a higher interest in HoReCa services.

Analyzing the indices of the volume of turnover in market services for the population by restaurants, we observe an oscillating, but overall positive evolution, both at the level of all branches of the service sector and in the case of restaurants.

Table 2.

Indices of the volume of turnover in market services for the population by restaurants - % (base year 2021)										
	January 2021	July 2021	January 2022	July 2022	January 2023	July 2023	January 2024	July 2024	January 2025	July 2025
TOTAL Branches of the services sector	68,8	133,1	97,3	161,3	121,1	164,3	123,8	157,5	123,5	160,3
Restaurants	69,2	128,6	96,6	149,5	118	150,6	112,7	145,2	107,1	136,6

Source: INS- tempoonline database

On the total branches of the services sector, it is found that: in January 2021, the level is only 68.8%, signifying a much reduced activity. Throughout 2021, the sector is recovering rapidly, reaching 133.1% in July. In 2022 and 2023, an upward trend is observed, with high values in the summer months, which confirms the seasonality specific to services. In 2024–2025, the values stabilize in the range of 157–160%, indicating a consolidation of growth.

As for restaurants, the evolution is close to that of the total sector, but with slightly lower values, which shows a slower recovery. Statistical data start at 69.2% in January 2021, rising to 128.6% in July 2021. In the following years, the growth continues, with maximum values of 150–151% in July 2022–2023. In 2024–2025 restaurants register a slight decrease compared to the peak in 2023, reaching 145.2% in July 2024 and 136.6% in July 2025, suggesting a moderation in the growth of the HoReCa sector.

Table 3.

Indices of the volume of turnover in market services for households, series adjusted for the number of working days and seasonality - base year 2021 (%)

	Jan. 2021	Jul. 2021	Jan. 2022	July 2022	Jan. 2023	Jul. 2023	Jan.2024	Jul. 2024	Jan. 2025	Jul. 2025
TOTAL Branches of the service sector	84,1	108,6	113,7	136,4	137,8	139,2	140,3	135	137,5	135,2
Restaurants	82,6	111,7	110,2	132,5	130,7	133,6	125,7	127,8	123,1	120,5

Source: INS- tempoonline database

The analysis of the turnover volume indices, adjusted for the number of working days and seasonality, provides a true picture of the real evolution of economic activity in the services sector for the population. The 2021 base year data (100%) allow the assessment of short- and medium-term trends, eliminating cyclical fluctuations specific to each season.

In 2021, the sector starts from a sub-unit level (84.1%), as a result of the economic disruptions generated by the Covid 19 maturation of growth and the consolidation of demand for services. The 2025 values remain close to previous levels, confirming the maintenance of solid and predictable economic activity in the sector.

In the case of restaurants, the dynamics are similar, but with a slightly more moderate growth rate than the general trend. In 2021, the branch starts at 82.6%, indicating a slower recovery in HoReCa compared to other service segments. However, by July 2021, the index reached 111.7%, exceeding the reference level.

Pandemic, but reaches the threshold of 108.6% in July 2021, signaling an accelerated recovery process.

Over the course of 2022, growth becomes more pronounced, with indices rising to 113.7% in January and 136.4% in July, reflecting an increase in services activities in the context of economic normalization. In 2023 and 2024, a stabilization at high values is observed, in the range of 135–140%, suggesting the

In 2022 and 2023, restaurants recorded constant growth, between 110% and 133%, with the revival of the population's consumption and the increase in social mobility. However, unlike total services, the period 2024–2025 indicates a slight deceleration in activity: values gradually drop to 120%, which may reflect either an adjustment in demand or an intensification of competition and an increase in operating costs (raw materials, energy, wages).

Table 4.

Value indices of turnover in market services for households, gross series (%) - base year 2021										
TOTAL branches of the services sector	January 2021	July 2021	January 2022	July 2022	January 2023	July 2023	January 2024	July 2024	January 2025	July 2025
	68,3	129,3	101,8	167,6	140,6	193,8	159,7	201,1	165,7	215,4
Restaurants	67,5	128,6	100,8	165,8	141,6	193,8	153,9	206,3	158,1	210,6

Source: INS- tempoonline database

The gross series reflects the effective, unadjusted evolution of the turnover in market services for the population, directly influenced by seasonality, the number of working days and the particularities of each moment of the year. The values with the base year 2021 allow the natural pace of growth or decrease of economic activity to be tracked.

For all branches of the services sector, the data show an evolution characterized by strong seasonal oscillations, but in a general upward trend throughout the analyzed period. In January 2021, the index stood at 68.3%, still reflecting the effects of the pandemic context on service activity. In July 2021, the sector recorded a substantial growth, reaching 129.3%, due to the resumption of economic activities and the specifics of the summer season. In 2022, the evolution becomes even more pronounced, from 101.8% in January to 167.6% in July, which confirms the recovery of demand and the intensification of consumption. In 2023, very high values are reached, with a peak of 193.8% in July – the highest level in the entire interval up to that point. In 2024–2025,

the upward trend continues: values exceed the 200% threshold in the summer months (201.1% in 2024 and 215.4% in 2025), suggesting an accelerated expansion of the sector. In conclusion, we can observe a rapid and sustained growth of services, amplified by the specific seasonality, with significant maximums in July of each year.

The evolution of the restaurant indices follows a trend similar to that of the sector as a whole, which confirms the importance of the HoReCa branch in the dynamics of services provided to the population. In January 2021, restaurants started at 67.5%, a level almost identical to the total sector. In July 2021, they reached 128.6%, demonstrating the reopening and rapid growth of activity. In 2022, the values increase considerably, from 100.8% in January to 165.8% in July. The year 2023 marks a particularly strong evolution, culminating with 193.8% in the summer month – the same level as total services. In 2024, restaurants even surpass the total sector in July (206.3%), which indicates a very high demand for HoReCa services. In 2025, the trend continues, reaching

a peak of 210.6% in July, confirming the consolidation of the restaurant market.

Restaurants have therefore had an evolution almost parallel to that of the total sector, sometimes surpassing it in the summer season, which suggests a very high demand for public catering services in the peak months.

CONCLUSIONS

The market services provided by restaurants have a growing economic value, generating high revenues and contributing to the local economy. Thus, restaurants have an evolution almost parallel to the total service sector, and in certain periods they exceed the general dynamics, underlining the importance of HoReCa in the market service economy.

The indices of services and turnover volume show an upward trend of the public catering activity. The positive evolution is due to the increase in the number of customers, the diversification of the offer and the adaptation of prices to market demand.

The statistical analysis confirms that restaurants have a significant role in meeting the needs of the population and in boosting the local service market.

The adjusted values confirm that the positive developments are not only caused by seasonality, but reflect real economic growth,

based on increased demand, diversification of supply and a full return to economic normality.

However, although they are constantly increasing compared to the base year, in 2024–2025 there was a slight moderation, possibly due to market saturation, rising prices and reduced consumption, changing population preferences.

As proposals for the development of the sector, we mention: continuous monitoring of the value of services through statistical analysis, correlation of the evolution of turnover with the consumption trends of the population, use of specific indicators in substantiating managerial decisions (pricing policies, investments, personnel).

REFERENCES

- Criveanu, I., 2005. Economy of Services, Sitech Publishing House.
- Ionașcu, V., Pavel, C., 2017. Economy of Services, 2nd Edition, Prounicersitaria Publishing House.
- Ioncica, M., 2006. Economy of Services. Theoretical Approaches and Practical Implications, Uranus Publishing House.
- Rus, M., 2015. Elements of Applied Statistics, Prouniversitaria Publishing House.
- Petcu, N., 2000. Statistics in Tourism - Theory and Applications, Albastra Publishing House.
- Tarnita, D., 2004. Statistics - Theory and Applications, Craiova University Publishing House.
- *** INS- Tempoonline Database
<http://statistici.insse.ro:8077/tempoonline/#/pages/tables/insse-table>.

STREET FOOD – BETWEEN A NEW GASTRONOMIC EXPRESSION AND A GLOBAL SOCIAL PHENOMENON

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The concept of street food has evolved in recent decades from a simple form of fast food associated with public spaces to a complex expression of gastronomy and urban socio-cultural dynamics. Characterized by diversity and culinary innovation, street food simultaneously reflects the preservation of culinary heritage and adaptation to the modern lifestyle of cities.

This paper analyzes street food as a new form of gastronomic expression, highlighting how it manages to integrate local culinary tradition with contemporary trends. Thus, street food can be understood as an emerging phenomenon at the intersection of gastronomy, culture, and urban society, simultaneously reflecting the preservation of culinary traditions and adaptation to the globalized and modern lifestyle of cities.

Keywords: street food, urban gastronomy, culinary tradition, social phenomenon

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INTRODUCTION

Street food refers to food sold in public spaces such as streets, markets, fairs, or parks. It is usually prepared and served from mobile stands, carts, or specially equipped trucks and is designed to be eaten on the spot. Some of these dishes are traditional, while others have spread far beyond their area of origin. In general, street food falls into both the "finger food" and fast-food categories and is usually more affordable than meals served in restaurants. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Street_food; <https://www.bookbeat.com/ie/book/street-food-392555>)

Street food refers not only to food cooked and sold in public spaces, but also to an entire gastronomic ecosystem that operates at the pulse of cities. These dishes are designed to be affordable, quick, and easy to eat on the go, meeting the daily needs of urban residents. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Street_food;))

However, street food goes beyond the realm of food itself, as it offers a complex experience that combines cultural, social, and sensory elements. An important factor in its popularity is the culinary dynamism it generates: street food encourages experimentation, unusual combinations of flavors, and the discovery of new dishes at affordable prices. (Aykac E., Buyruk L., 2021; <https://www.bookbeat.com/ie/book/street-food-392555>)

The range of dishes available as street food varies from region to region and culture to culture in many countries around the world. Although in some societies eating on the street is considered impolite, many middle- and high-income consumers depend on the speed and low cost of street food for both their daily meals and the work opportunities it generates. (Aykac E., Buyruk L., 2021; <https://www.bookbeat.com/ie/book/street-food-392555>)

In Europe, in Greek antiquity, fried small fish was a common street food, and numerous evidence of street vendors has been found at Pompeii. In ancient Rome, poor residents, without ovens in their homes, frequently consumed street food such as chickpea soup with bread. Medieval travelers mention that in Cairo people ate lamb kebabs and rice directly on the street, and in Renaissance Turkey, pieces of fried meat were sold, the Ottoman state being the first to officially regulate street food trade (1502). In the 19th century, street food ranged from nuts to gingerbread in Transylvania, to fried potatoes in Paris, or the variety of dishes sold on the streets of Victorian London. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Street_food; Kraig B., Taylor C., 2013)

On the American continent, Aztec markets sold corn drinks, dozens of types of tamales, and various insects or stews. In colonial Peru, although the Spanish introduced European foods, the general population continued to consume mostly traditional foods, such as grilled beef hearts sold on the street. In

the American colonies, street vendors offered oysters, roasted corn, fruit, and sweets, with oysters remaining popular until they became expensive due to overfishing. In the 18th and 19th centuries, many African-American women earned their living by selling street food (cakes and nuts, biscuits, pralines, and other sweets), and the famous Cracker Jack snack also made its debut as a product sold on the street. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Street_food; Karsavuran Z., 2018)

The sale of street food has a history dating back thousands of years in China and became established during the Tang dynasty. Although initially intended for the poor, even rich families sent their servants to buy such dishes. Today, street food remains an essential part of Chinese cuisine and attracts many tourists. Through the Chinese diaspora, this type of cuisine has strongly influenced other regions of Asia, laying the foundations for street food culture in much of Southeast Asia. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Street_food; Kraig B., Taylor C., 2013)

In ancient India, the Arthashastra mentioned food vendors and regulated the trade in rice, meat, and alcoholic beverages. Even in Delhi, kings visited kebab vendors, a tradition that continues today. During the colonial period, fusion street food developed, adapted to British tastes. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Street_food; Kraig B., Taylor C., 2013)

In Java, Indonesia, street vendors have existed for centuries, being depicted in bas-reliefs from the 9th century and mentioned in inscriptions from the 14th century. During the Dutch colonial period, dishes such as satay and dawet appeared. Today, street food is sold from carts and bicycles, and rapid urbanization has stimulated the expansion of this culture, especially in Jakarta, Bandung, and Surabaya. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Street_food)

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The study examines aspects such as the origin and evolution of the street food phenomenon, its impact on consumer behavior, its importance in the development of gastronomic tourism, and its contribution to the revaluation of local culinary heritage. It also analyzes the aesthetic, sensory, and culinary innovation dimensions specific to this type of gastronomy, as well as the role of street food as a space for social and cultural interaction. In this context, the authors consulted an extensive bibliography, including scientific publications and specialized websites, using a methodology

that combines classic research methods - documentation, analysis, and synthesis of information - with the formulation of conclusions based on the data collected.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Street food is based on quick, tasty, and affordable dishes made with ingredients that ensure flavor and authenticity. Most of the time, ingredients are cooked completely or partially in advance to allow for quick service: in Asia, soups and side dishes are prepared ahead of time; in America, burger meat is cooked before busy periods, and hot dogs, after boiling, are kept at a constant temperature for immediate service. In Turkey, kebabs are continuously roasted on skewers over a fire so that they are ready to serve at any time. (<https://vstreetfood.com/ro/10-most-popular-types-of-street-food-in-the-world/>)

Europe and Asia stand out for the diversity and authenticity of their street food offerings. In Europe, destinations such as Istanbul, Barcelona, and London attract tourists with local and international dishes: *kebabs* and *baklava* in Istanbul, *tapas* and *paella* in Barcelona, and *fish and chips* and multicultural specialties in London. In Asia, cities such as Bangkok, Tokyo, and Hanoi are renowned for their distinctive street food: *pad thai* and *som tam* in Bangkok, *sushi* and *ramen* in Tokyo, and *Vietnamese pho* or *bánh mì* in Hanoi. (<https://www.lancom.ro/articol/mancare-stradala-ghid-complet-al-deliciilor-culinare-urbane-324>)

Ramen, introduced to Japan by Chinese immigrants in the early 20th century, emerged as street food for Chinese workers and students in the Yokohama neighborhood. In the period after World War II, ramen became extremely popular, and as Japan's economy recovered, ramen went from being a street food to an essential part of the urban diet, developing numerous regional variations. There are four main types of ramen, each with unique characteristics and specific ingredients. (<https://edelicios.net/2024/09/24/ramen-de-la-street-food-la-preparat-gourmet-afla-povestea/>)

Shoyu ramen is one of the oldest and most popular types of ramen. Its soup is based on soy sauce, has a light brown color, and the taste is balanced and slightly salty. It is often served with thin noodles, pork, green onions, and a boiled egg. **Tonkotsu Ramen** is specific to the Kyushu region and is notable for its thick, milky soup, obtained by boiling pork bones for many hours. The texture is rich and the taste is very intense. It is served with thin, straight

noodles and simple ingredients such as green onions and seaweed. **Miso Ramen** is a dish originating in Hokkaido. The soup contains miso paste (fermented soybeans), which gives it a slightly sweet flavor. It is a thicker ramen and is often served with wavy noodles, fried vegetables, meat, and sometimes butter for extra creaminess. (<https://salutethepig.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/The-Book-of-Ramen.pdf>; <https://edelicios.net/2024/09/24/ramen-de-la-street-food-la-preparat-gourmet-afla-povestea/>)

Shio Ramen. Shio, which means "salt" in Japanese, is the lightest of the ramen varieties and is popular in coastal regions. The soup is clear and lightly salted, made from a mixture of chicken or pork bones, and is usually served with thin noodles and fresh vegetables (<https://salutethepig.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/The-Book-of-Ramen.pdf>)

Figure 1

Tacos is a traditional Mexican dish consisting of a small corn or wheat tortilla covered with filling. There are a variety of fillings, such as beef, pork, chicken, seafood, beans, cheese, and seasoned with various condiments, such as salsa, guacamole, or sour cream, and vegetables, such as lettuce, cilantro, onion, tomato, and chili peppers. Tacos can be contrasted with similar dishes such as *burritos*, which are much larger and rolled rather than folded; *taquitos*, which are rolled and fried; or *chalupas/tostadas*, in which the tortilla is fried before being filled. (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Taco>)

Quesadilla is a Mexican dish consisting of two tortillas filled with cheese and, occasionally, meat, spices, or other ingredients, then cooked on a griddle or in a pan. Although corn tortillas are traditionally used, the recipe can also be adapted to flour tortillas. In central and southern Mexico, a quesadilla is round and usually filled with Oaxaca cheese. The most common filling is cheese, but others can also be used, such as cooked vegetables, pumpkin flowers, and various types of cooked meat: beef or pork, chicharron (a dish made from fried pork belly or fried pork rinds), chicken tinga (a dish made from chopped and boiled chicken, covered with a spicy, aromatic sauce).

Quesadillas are often served with green or red salsa and guacamole. (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quesadilla>)

Gyros is a Greek dish made from meat cooked on a vertical rotisserie, then sliced and placed in a flatbread (*pita*) along with other ingredients such as tomatoes, onions, French fries, and tzatziki sauce. It is similar to Turkish döner kebab or Middle Eastern shawarma, but is distinguished by pork as the main ingredient and tzatziki sauce. The vertical grill with stacked meat and the process of slicing it while cooking was developed in Bursa in the 19th century during the Ottoman Empire. (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gyros>)

Kebab is a Middle Eastern culinary dish consisting of minced/cut meat cooked on a spit or grill, sometimes accompanied by vegetables or spices. Although the dish is usually cooked on a skewer over an open fire, some types of kebab are baked in a pan or prepared as a stew, such as Tas kebab. The traditional meat for kebab is most often lamb, but regional recipes may include beef, goat, chicken, fish, or even pork (depending on specific religious prohibitions). (<https://www.britannica.com/topic/kebab>)

Although in English the terms "*kebab*" or "*shish-kebab*" can sometimes refer to any small pieces of meat cooked on skewers, kebab is mainly associated with a variety of meat dishes originating in Persia and Anatolia. The recipe spread throughout the world with the influence of Muslim culture. The Maghrebi traveler Ibn Battuta noted that kebab was served in the royal houses of the Delhi Sultanate (1206–1526), but also eaten by ordinary people for breakfast, along with *naan* (flatbread, usually baked in an oven or fried). Over time, kebab dishes have been adapted and integrated with local cooking styles, from the popular fast food Doner kebab to various types of Shish kebab, including Satays from Southeast Asia. (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kebab>)

Hamburger is a sandwich consisting of a bun cut in half, containing a meat patty, usually beef, and topped with various ingredients such as vegetables (lettuce, tomatoes, onions, pickles) and sauces (ketchup, mustard, mayonnaise). Originating in Hamburg, Germany, this dish has become a global symbol of fast food, while also being adapted into gourmet versions. Hamburgers are often associated with fast food restaurants, and there are numerous regional and international variations of this dish. Multinational chains such as McDonald's and Burger King have turned

burgers into iconic products, with the Big Mac and Whopper becoming symbols of American culture worldwide. (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hamburger>)

Hot dog is a dish consisting of a sausage cooked on the grill, steamed, or boiled, served in a partially sliced bun. The term can also refer to the sausage itself, which is usually a wiener (Vienna sausage) or a frankfurter (a type of smoked sausage originating in Germany). The name of the sausage is often associated with the entire dish. The preparation and toppings for hot dogs vary around the world. The most common include mustard, ketchup, onions in tomato sauce, and cheese sauce, but sauerkraut, chopped onions, jalapeños, chili, grated cheese, coleslaw, bacon, or olives can also be added. Popular variations include *Corn dogs* and *Pigs in a blanket*. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hot_dog)

The hot dog, originally brought over from Germany, quickly gained popularity in the United States, becoming a working-class street food. Over time, it has become a symbol of American culture, closely associated with baseball games. Although particularly linked to New York and its culinary traditions, the hot dog spread throughout the US during the 20th century. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hot_dog; <https://www.hot-dog.org/sites/default/files/pdf/Hotdog-Facts-Figures-Folklore-Brochure.pdf>)

Figure 2

10 won bread, also called *10 won waffle* or *Sibwonppang*, is a street food that dates back to 2019 and is a bread or waffle shaped like a South Korean 10 won coin that contains cheese. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/10_won_bread) This dish consists of an oversized bread, served hot and fresh, usually from stalls or small shops, which resembles the popular Korean snack "fish bread" filled with red bean paste in flavor, but in this case the filling is made of sour cream, sugar, and mozzarella cheese. (<https://10wontips.blogspot.com/2023/06/new-food-snack-10-won-bread.html>)

Mochi is a Japanese rice dessert made from mochigome (a type of short-grain sticky rice) to which water, sugar, or cornstarch may be added. After the rice is steamed, it is pounded into a smooth paste and then molded into various shapes. In Japan, mochi is

traditionally made during a ceremony called Mochitsuki. (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mochi>)

Mochi and its preparation are closely linked to Japanese traditions, reflecting the importance of rice and its role in Shinto rituals, where it is used to thank the gods for the harvest. In ancient Japan, mochi was considered a sacred food, believed to house a divine presence and eaten to bring health and good luck. Although enjoyed year-round today, mochi continues to be associated with numerous festivals and seasonal events, particularly Japanese New Year celebrations. (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mochi>; <https://www.byfood.com/blog/travel-tips/the-beginners-guide-to-mochi>)

Nian Gao is a sticky cake-like dessert that was traditionally offered to the Kitchen God so that, with his mouth "stuck shut," he would not speak negatively about the family in front of the Jade Emperor. Almost every family prepares or buys it for Chinese New Year. Originally from China, Nian Gao spread to Southeast Asia and Sri Lanka, influencing local rice-based cakes. All variations of these desserts use sticky rice turned into a paste, shaped according to the recipe. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nian_gao; <https://thewoksoflife.com/nian-gao-recipe/>)

Stroopwafel is a classic Dutch dessert consisting of two thin layers of sweet dough joined together with a filling of cinnamon-flavored caramel syrup. According to Dutch culinary tradition, the first stroopwafels were made in Gouda in the late 18th or early 19th century by bakers who reused leftover dough and crumbs, sweetening them with syrup. Stroopwafel is famous for the way it is served with a hot drink; it is placed on the rim of a cup, and the steam heats the waffle and softens the syrup inside. (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Stroopwafel>; <https://www.britannica.com/topic/stroopwafel>)

Pancakes, also known as hotcakes or flapjacks, are round and often thin desserts made from a starchy batter that may contain eggs, milk, and butter. The shape and texture of pancakes vary around the world: in England, pancakes are thin and unleavened, similar to French crêpes; in Scotland and North America, leavening agents are used to make thick, fluffy pancakes. The Breton crêpe is a thin pancake, cooked on both sides to achieve a delicate and fine surface, while the Southeast European version, *palatschinke*, is a thin pancake fried on both sides, filled with jam, cream cheese, chocolate, nuts, or other sweet and savory ingredients. (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pancake>)

CONCLUSIONS

Street food is an authentic expression of urban culture, as traditional and ethnic dishes reveal the specific characteristics and identity of a city. Both locals and tourists are attracted to street food for its accessibility and diversity, but also for the direct and authentic culinary experience it offers in the midst of everyday life.

Street food is valued as a gastronomic product with potential appeal in tourist offerings. Street food has become an element of interest for tourists in many major destinations and is increasingly used as a tool for promoting tourism. In addition, for many cities, street food has become a defining element of local identity. It functions as a cultural calling card, attracting tourists interested in exploring the culinary authenticity of the place and contributing to the economic and social vitality of urban communities.

Street food has gone beyond its status as mere street food, becoming an international phenomenon, appreciated for its authenticity, speed, and the multisensory experience it offers. In the context of globalization, this concept reflects both the preservation of local traditions and adaptation to external cultural influences.

REFERENCES

- Aykac E., Buyruk L., 2021, Bibliometric Analysis of Researches on Street Food, *Journal of Tourism and Gastronomy Studies*, 9 (2).
- Karsavuran Z., 2018, Street Food: A Multidisciplinary Approach and Discussion of Street Foods as Gastronomic Products, *Journal of Tourism and Gastronomy Studies* 6/1.
- Kraig Bruce & Taylor Colleen, 2013, *Street Food around the World: An Encyclopedia of Food and Culture*, Publisher: ABC-CLIO.
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Street_food
- <https://vstreetfood.com/ro/10-most-popular-types-of-street-food-in-the-world/>
- <https://www.lancom.ro/articol/mancare-stradala-ghid-complet-al-deliciilor-culinare-urbane-324>
- <https://edelicios.net/2024/09/24/ramen-de-la-street-food-la-preparat-gourmet-afla-povestea/>
- <https://salutethepig.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/The-Book-of-Ramen.pdf>
- <https://www.yamachanramen.com/recipes-list/classic-shoyu-ramen>
- <https://bitingatthebits.com/rich-and-creamy-easy-tonkotsu-ramen-broth-from-scratch-recipe>
- <https://dinnerbydennis.com/miso-ramen>
- <https://www.seriousseats.com/shio-ramen-bowl-recipe>
- <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Taco>
- <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quesadilla>
- <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gyros>
- <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kebab>
- <https://www.britannica.com/topic/kebab>
- <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hamburger>
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hot_dog

- <https://www.hot-dog.org/sites/default/files/pdf/Hotdog-Facts-Figures-Folklore-Brochure.pdf>
- <https://deliciouslysprinkled.com/air-fryer-corn-dogs/>
- <https://www.tasteofhome.com/recipes/pigs-in-a-blanket/>
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/10_won_bread
- <https://10wontips.blogspot.com/2023/06/new-food-snack-10-won-bread.html>
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nian_gao
- <https://thewoksoflife.com/nian-gao-recipe/>
- <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Stroopwafel>
- <https://www.britannica.com/topic/stroopwafel>
- <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pancake>

FUZZY DIFFERENTIAL SUBORDINATIONS ASSOCIATED WITH A GENERALIZED DERIVATIVE OPERATOR

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The aim of the present paper is to establish several fuzzy differential subordinations by using a linear operator. Some interesting fuzzy consequences are also considered.

Keywords: multiplier transformations, differential subordination, fuzzy differential subordination, fuzzy best dominant.

INTRODUCTION

In 1965 Lotfi Zadeh introduced the special concept of fuzzy set in the work [19]. The new notion of fuzzy subordination was defined and studied recently in the papers [13-55]. This theory was developed in order to extend the classical differential subordination theory introduced and studied by S.S. Miller and P.T. Mocanu in [10]. In 2002 was studied the dual notion, of differential superordination [5]. See also interesting papers [3] and [11].

Since then, numerous researchers studied different properties [16] of differential operators involving fuzzy differential subordinations and superordinations: Wanas operator [2], [18], generalized Noor-Sălăgean operator [12], Sălăgean and Ruscheweyh operators [1] or other certain linear operator [9].

In this paper, fuzzy differential subordinations is added to the previous studies associated with a linear operator.

Denote by U the open unit disc of the complex plane:

$$U = \{z \in \mathbb{C} : |z| < 1\}.$$

Let \mathcal{H} be the class of analytic functions in U and for $a \in \mathbb{C}$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$ let $\mathcal{H}[a, n]$ be the subclass of \mathcal{H} consisting of functions of the form

$$f(z) = a + a_n z^n + a_{n+1} z^{n+1} + \dots, z \in U.$$

Let $\mathcal{A}(p, n)$ denote the class of functions $f(z)$ normalized by

$$f(z) = z^p + \sum_{k=p+n}^{\infty} a_k z^k, \quad (p, n \in \mathbb{N} := \{1, 2, 3, \dots\})$$

which are analytic in the open unit disc. In particular, we set

$$\mathcal{A}(p, 1) := \mathcal{A}, \text{ and } \mathcal{A}(1, 1) := \mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}_1.$$

Let

$$\mathcal{A}_n = \{f \in \mathcal{H}(U), f(z) = z + a_{n+1} z^{n+1} + \dots\}$$

with $\mathcal{A}_1 = \mathcal{A}$.

In order to use the concept of fuzzy differential subordination, the following notions are necessary.

Definition 1.1. [19] A function $F : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is named fuzzy subset, where X is a non-empty set. Another definition will be the next one: A pair (A, F_A) with $F_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$

$$A = \{x \in X : 0 < F_A(x) \leq 1\} = \sup(A, F_A)$$

is named a fuzzy subset of X . Set A represents the support of the fuzzy set (A, F_A) . Also F_A is named the membership function of the fuzzy set (A, F_A) . One can also denote $A = \sup(A, F_A)$.

Remark 1.1. [15] Let be the inclusion relation $A \subset X$. Then we have

$$F_A(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x \in A \\ 0, & \text{if } x \notin A \end{cases}$$

The real number 0, for a fuzzy subset, is the smallest membership degree of $x \in X$ to A . Likewise, the real number 1 is the biggest membership degree of $x \in X$ to A .

The entire set X is associated with $F_X(x) = 1, x \in X$ and the empty set $\emptyset \subset X$ is associated with $F_\emptyset(x) = 0, x \in X$.

Definition 1.2 [13] Consider two functions $f, g \in H(D), D \subset \mathbb{C}, z_0 \in D$, being a fixed point. We say that the function f is fuzzy subordinate to g and written as

$$f \prec_F g \text{ or } f(x) \prec_F g(x), z \in D,$$

If the following relations are verified:

1. $f(z_0) = g(z_0)$;
2. $F_{f(D)}f(z) \leq F_{g(D)}g(z), z \in D$.

Definition 1.3 [14] Consider function $\Psi: \mathbb{C}^3 \times U \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ and let h be an univalent function in U satisfying

$$\Psi(a, 0, 0) = h(0) = a$$

We say that p is named a fuzzy solution of the fuzzy differential subordination if p is an analytic function in U , such that $p(0) = a$ and verifies the next (second-order) fuzzy differential subordination:

$$(1.1) \quad F_{\Psi(\mathbb{C}^3 \times U)} \Psi(p(z), zp'(z), z^2 p''(z); z) \leq F_{h(U)} h(z), z \in U$$

For all p satisfying (1.1) the univalent function q is named fuzzy dominant of the fuzzy solution for the fuzzy differential subordination, or a fuzzy dominant, if

$$F_{p(U)} p(z) \leq F_{q(U)} q(z), z \in U$$

A fuzzy dominant \tilde{q} which verifies

$$F_{\tilde{q}(U)} \tilde{q}(z) \leq F_{q(U)} q(z), z \in U,$$

for all fuzzy dominants q of (1.1) represents the fuzzy best dominant of (1.1).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

We begin our investigation by recalling here a generalized differential operator defined in [6].

Definition 2.1. [6] Let $f \in \mathcal{A}(p, n)$. For $m \in \mathbb{N}_0 = \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}, \lambda \geq 0, l \geq 0$, we define the

multiplier transformations $I_p^m(\lambda, l)$ on $A(p, n)$ by the following infinite series

$$(2.1) \quad I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z) := z^p + \sum_{k=p+n}^{\infty} \left[\frac{p+\lambda(k-p)+l}{p+l} \right]^m a_k z^k.$$

It follows from (2.1) that

$$(2.2) \quad (p+l)I_p^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z) = [p(1-\lambda) + l]I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z) + \lambda z(I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z))'$$

Remark 2.1. For $p=1, l=0, \lambda \geq 0$, the operator $I_1^m(\lambda, 0) \equiv D_\lambda^m$ was introduced and studied by Al-Oboudi [4] which reduces to the Sălăgean differential operator [17] for $\lambda = 1$. The operator $I_1^m(1, l) \equiv I_l^m$ was studied recently by Cho and Srivastava [7] and Cho and Kim [8].

In this paper, we will derive several fuzzy subordination results involving the operator $I_1^m(\lambda, l)$ denoted by $I^m(\lambda, l)$. In order to prove our main results, we also need the following result.

Lemma 2.1 [10] Let q be a convex function in $U, \alpha \in \mathbb{C}^*$ and suppose that

$$\psi(z) = q(z) + n z q'(z),$$

where $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$.

If the function $h \in H[q(0), n]$ and $\varphi: \mathbb{C}^2 \times U \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$

$$\varphi(h(z), zh'(z)) = h(z) + \alpha zh'(z)$$

is analytic in U , with $h(0) = q(0)$, then

$$F_{\varphi(\mathbb{C}^2 \times U)} [h(z) + \alpha zh'(z)] \leq F_{\psi(U)} \psi(z), z \in U$$

i.e.

$$h(z) + \alpha zh'(z) \prec_{\mathcal{F}} \psi(z)$$

implies

$$F_{h(U)} h(z) \leq F_{q(U)} q(z), z \in U$$

i.e.

$$h(z) \prec_{\mathcal{F}} q(z)$$

and q is fuzzy best $(q(0), n)$ dominant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Theorem 3.1. Let q be a convex function in U , with $q(0)=1, \gamma \in \mathbb{C}^*$.

If $f \in \mathcal{A}(1, n)$ satisfies the fuzzy differential subordination

$$(3.1) \quad F_{\Phi(U)} \Phi(z) \leq F_{q(U)} \left(q(z) + \frac{\gamma \lambda}{1+l} z q'(z) \right)$$

where

$$(3.2) \quad \Phi(z) = \frac{I^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z} + \gamma \left(I^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z) - I^m(\lambda, l)f(z) \right)$$

then

$$\frac{I^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z} \prec_{\mathcal{F}} q(z)$$

and q is the fuzzy best dominant of (3.1).

Proof. We define the function

$$(3.3) \quad h(z) := \frac{I^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z}.$$

Using the form (2.1) of the operator (3.1) we deduce that $h \in \mathcal{H}[l, n]$, $q(0) = h(0)$.

Differentiating (3.2) with respect to z and using the identity (2.2) in the resulting equation we have

$$\frac{zh'(z)}{h(z)} = \frac{1+l}{\lambda} \left(\frac{I^{m+1}(\lambda, l)}{I^m(\lambda, l)} - 1 \right).$$

Therefore, we obtain

$$\frac{I^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z} + \gamma \left(I^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z) - I^m(\lambda, l)f(z) \right) = h(z) + \frac{\gamma\lambda}{1+l}zh'(z).$$

The fuzzy differential subordination (3.1) from the hypothesis becomes

$$F_{h(U)} \left(h(z) + \frac{\gamma\lambda}{1+l}zh'(z) \right) \leq F_{q(U)} \left(q(z) + \frac{\gamma\lambda}{1+l}zq'(z) \right)$$

i.e.

$$h(z) + \frac{\gamma\lambda}{1+l}zh'(z) \prec_{\mathcal{F}} q(z) + \frac{\gamma\lambda}{1+l}zq'(z).$$

Further, we apply Lemma 2.1 with $\alpha = \frac{\gamma\lambda}{1+l}$ to obtain the conclusion of the Theorem 3.1 \square

If we consider $m = 0$ in Theorem 3.1 we obtain the following result.

Corollary 3.1 Let q be a convex function in U , with $q(0)=1, \gamma \in \mathbb{C}^*$.

If $f \in \mathcal{A}(1, n)$ satisfies the fuzzy differential subordination

$$(3.4) \quad (1-\gamma) \frac{f(z)}{z} + \gamma \frac{I^1(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z} \prec_{\mathcal{F}} q(z) + \frac{\gamma\lambda}{1+l}zq'(z)$$

i.e.

$$F_{G(U)}G(z) \leq F_{q(U)} \left(q(z) + \frac{\gamma\lambda}{1+l}zq'(z) \right)$$

where

$$G(z) = (1-\gamma) \frac{f(z)}{z} + \gamma \frac{I^1(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z},$$

then

$$\frac{f(z)}{z} \prec_{\mathcal{F}} q(z)$$

and q is the fuzzy best dominant of (3.4).

We consider a particular convex function $q(z) = \frac{1+Az}{1+Bz}$ to give the following application to Theorem 3.1.

Corollary 3.2 Let $\gamma \in \mathbb{C}^*, A \neq B$ such that $-1 \leq B < A \leq 1$ and $\text{Re } \gamma > 0$.

If $f \in \mathcal{A}(1, n)$ satisfies the fuzzy differential subordination

$$(3.5) \quad (1-\gamma) \frac{I^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z} + \gamma \frac{I^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z} \prec_{\mathcal{F}} \frac{1+Az}{1+Bz} + \frac{\gamma\lambda}{1+l} \frac{(A-B)z}{(1+Bz)^2}$$

i.e.

$$F_{\Phi(U)}\Phi(z) \leq F_{q(U)} \left(\frac{1+Az}{1+Bz} + \frac{\gamma\lambda}{1+l} \frac{(A-B)z}{(1+Bz)^2} \right)$$

where $\Phi(z)$ is defined in (3.2)

then

$$\frac{I^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z} \prec_{\mathcal{F}} \frac{1+Az}{1+Bz}$$

and $q(z) = \frac{1+Az}{1+Bz}$ is the best dominant of (3.5).

Taking $q(z) = \frac{1+z}{1-z}$ in Theorem 3.1 we obtain the following corollary.

Corollary 3.3 Let $\gamma \in \mathbb{C}^*$ and $f \in \mathcal{A}(1, n)$ satisfies the fuzzy differential subordination

$$(3.6) \quad (1-\gamma) \frac{I^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z} + \gamma \frac{I^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z} \prec_{\mathcal{F}} \frac{1+z}{1-z} + \frac{\alpha\lambda}{1+l} \frac{2z}{(1-z)^2}$$

i.e.

$$F_{\Phi(U)}\Phi(z) \leq F_{q(U)} \left(\frac{1+z}{1-z} + \frac{\alpha\lambda}{1+l} \frac{2z}{(1-z)^2} \right)$$

where $\Phi(z)$ is defined in (3.2)

then

$$\frac{I^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z} \prec_{\mathcal{F}} \frac{1+z}{1-z}$$

and $q(z) = \frac{1+z}{1-z}$ is the best dominant of (3.6).

REFERENCES

- [1] Alb Lupas, G.I. Oros, New Applications of Salagean and Ruscheweyh Operators for Obtaining Fuzzy Differential Subordinations, *Mathematics*, 9 (2021), 2000.
- [2] S. Altınkaya, A.K. Wanas, Some properties for fuzzy differential subordination defined by Wanas operator, *Earthline J. Math. Sci.*, 4 (2020), 51–62.
- [3] W.G. Atshan, K.O. Hussain, Fuzzy Differential Superordination, *Theory Appl. Math. Comput. Sci.*, 7 (2017), 27–38.
- [4] F.M. Al-Oboudi, On univalent functions defined by a generalized Sălăgean operator, *Int. J. Math. Math. Sci.* 27, 1429-1436, (2004).
- [5] T. Bulboacă, Classes of first order differential superordinations, *Demonstratio Math.* 35(2), 287-292, (2002).
- [6] A. Cătaş, On certain class of p-valent functions defined by a new multiplier transformations, *Proceedings Book of the International Symposium G.F.T.A., Istanbul Kultur University, Turkey*, 241-250, (2007).
- [7] N.E. Cho and H.M. Srivastava, Argument estimates of certain analytic functions defined by a class of multiplier transformations, *Math. Comput. Modelling*, 37(1-2) (2003), 39-49.
- [8] N.E. Cho and T.H. Kim, Multiplier transformations and strongly close-to-convex functions, *Bull. Korean Math. Soc.*, 40(3) (2003), 399-410.
- [9] S.M. El-Deeb, A. Alb Lupas, Fuzzy differential subordinations associated with an integral operator, *An. Univ. Oradea Fasc. Mat.*, XXVII (2020), 133–140.
- [10] S.S. Miller, P.T. Mocanu, *Differential Subordinations. Theory and Applications*, Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, Basel, 2000.
- [11] S.S. Miller, P.T. Mocanu, Briot-Bouquet differential superordinations and sandwich theorems, *J. Math. Anal. Appl.*, {bf 329}(2007), No. 1, 327-335.
- [12] K.I. Noor, M.A. Noor, Fuzzy Differential Subordination Involving Generalized Noor-Salagean Operator, *Inf. Sci. Lett.*, 11 (2022), 1905–1911.
- [13] Oros G.I, Oros Gh., The notion of subordination in fuzzy sets theory. *General Mathematics*, 2011; 19: 97-103.
- [14] Oros G.I, Oros Gh., Fuzzy differential subordination. *Acta Universitatis Apulensis*, 2012; 30: 55-64.
- [15] Oros G.I, Oros Gh., Dominants and best dominants in fuzzy differential subordinations. *Stud Univ Babeş - Bolyai Math.* 2012; 57: 239-248.
- [16] G.I. Oros, Univalence criteria for analytic functions obtained using fuzzy differential subordinations, *Turk. J. Math.*, 46 (2022), 1478–1491.
- [17] G.S. Sălăgean, Subclasses of univalent functions, *Complex Analysis-Fifth Romanian-Finnish Seminar, Part 1* (Bucharest, 1981), 362-372, *Lecture Notes in Math.*, 1013, Springer, Berlin (1983).
- [18] A.K. Wanas, Fuzzy differential subordinations of analytic functions involving Wanas operator, *Ikonian J. Math.*, 2 (2020), 1–9
- [19] L. A. Zadeh, *Fuzzy Sets*, *Inf. Control*, 8 (1965), 338–353.

ANALYSIS OF THE SITUATION OF INVESTMENTS FOR ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION AND INFLUENCE ON SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The article aims to explore investments for environmental protection, knowing that the synergy between economic and environmental evolution is a prerequisite for the sustainable development of the country.

Environmental protection is considered not only as a problem of humanity, but increasingly as an economic problem with implications not only for international economic relations, but also for environmental changes viewed on a global scale.

Sustainable economy implies development that ensures the needs of the present, without compromising the possibilities of future generations to satisfy their needs. Moreover, it shows the right to development that is exercised in such a way as to satisfy equitably, both development and environmental needs for present and future generations.

In order to implement the objectives of sustainable development, progress is required in all dimensions: ecological, economic, social-human, as well as technological.

Our research is based on statistical information collected from the website of the National Institute of Statistics. During the analyzed period, an increase in investments related to environmental protection was observed, but this favorable, positive evolution was not marked by expected ecological effects.

Keywords: investments, environmental protection, environment, producer categories.

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INTRODUCTION

Environmental protection is considered to be the only way for life to continue and thrive on the planet, especially since it provides the resources that ensure the survival and development of the human species. The environment also plays an essential role in maintaining human health and biodiversity. (Sîrbulescu et al., 2021)

Environmental protection is considered among the important pillars that influence the evolution, but also the sustainability of the environment. (Akdag et al., 2024)

In Niu's vision, an increase in government spending on environmental protection opens up possibilities for increasing ecological innovation. (Niu, 2024)

In order to ensure sustainable development, the vision in national strategy documents and action plans must be taken into account, as well as at the international level. Environmental spending must be carefully monitored, and efficiency must be assessed in terms of the same sustainable development. (Jarczok-Guzy et al., 2024)

The EU Green Deal identifies investment as a key lever for ensuring the implementation of European environmental and climate policies.

In 2024, €76 billion was invested in the EU in essential assets needed to provide environmental services (e.g. wastewater treatment plants, waste transport vehicles, cleaner equipment that produces fewer polluting emissions). (<https://ec.europa.eu>)

Between 2018 and 2024, EU-wide environmental investment increased by 37%. The 2020 COVID crisis reduced investment in the economy, and as a consequence, investment in environmental protection also decreased. Starting in 2021, investment started to increase, and environmental investment increased by 30% between 2020 and 2024.

Some environmental specialists have sought suitable methods for good sustainable management of natural resources that would also ensure environmental protection but also stimulate income creation. (Drăcea et al., 2020)

Environmental protection expenditures are appreciated as a measure of communities that must actively participate in solving environmental problems. (Sîrbulescu et al., 2023)

The author Broniewicz considers environmental protection expenditures an effort that must satisfy multiple aspects, including the prevention, reduction and even elimination of pollution resulting from the manufacture or consumption of goods and services. (Broniewicz, 2011)

The aim of the article was to present a complete picture of environmental investments in Romania and to understand the deep connection between investments in environmental protection and the development of effective strategies to fight climate change.

The main objective of the research is to analyze data on specific environmental protection investments, knowing that by solving problematic environmental aspects, through specific investments as part of environmental protection expenditures, those new jobs that are necessary and that can contribute to sustainable growth, but also to development.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The article was supported by the use of research methods, from, documentation and consultation of specialized literature (articles, but also specialized works), data collection from statistical sources for the years 2012-2024, especially those obtained from the National Institute of Statistics (INS) and from the level of Press Releases regarding the studied aspects, data analysis and based on them, the information was interpreted that was compared, synthesized and supported the creation of graphs and subsequently the issuance of conclusions.

From the INS documents, environmental protection expenses include: investments, current internal expenses Investments refer to expenses for construction works, installations and assembly, for the purchase of means of transport, equipment, as well as expenses for the creation of new fixed assets necessary for the development, modernization, reconstruction of existing ones, with the aim of protecting the environment. The value of services regarding the transfer of ownership of existing fixed assets and land is also added.

Investments for environmental protection are structured by producer categories (non-specialized producers, specialized producers and public administration) and were analyzed in the period 2011-2023.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Starting from the assets of Romanian society, representatives of the Government, Parliament, the business environment, and the academic environment have outlined the priority lines on which the development of the economy in the future must be based.

In this sense, it is necessary to understand that it is important that the financial measures dedicated to this environmental protection are also effective.

The analysis of data obtained from various sources constituted the central part of the article, and the authors expressed the trends of investments in environmental protection and their evolution, during the period 2011-2023. In this sense, the data for the determined periods were compared, highlighting the differences of these investments between the different categories of producers, also emphasizing the importance of efficiency and contribution to the sustainable development of the Romanian economy.

The data analysis also consisted in approaching environmental protection expenditures because their study refers to the level of investments and current expenditures financed at the level of non-specialized, specialized producers and implicitly by the public administration.

From the analysis of these expenditures in Romania, for environmental protection we would find a sinuous evolution, but also a maximum recorded in 2022, of 20.4 billion lei (1.2% of GDP) and 19.8 billion lei in 2023 (Figure 1 and Figure 2).

In 2011, the year of the beginning of the analysis, investments in environmental protection totaled approximately 5.4 billion lei. At the national level, environmental protection expenditures amounted to approximately 18.6 billion lei, contributing 3.2% to the Gross Domestic Product (Figure 1 and Figure 2).

Protection expenditures were approximately 3% of GDP in 2012. The public administration had a contribution of 5.3 billion lei to environmental protection expenditures in 2011, and investments recorded 2.5 billion lei. Public administration investments accounted for 46% of total investments in environmental protection in 2011. (<https://business24.ro>)

According to the INS, 2014 was marked by a reduction in environmental protection expenditures, namely the value of 12.6 billion lei and a contribution of 1.9% to GDP, compared

to the previous year, 2013 when the contribution was 2.4% to GDP. (<https://www.bursa.ro>)

From the data provided by the INS, the updated podium is the year 2024, with the amount of 28 billion lei, environmental protection expenditures equivalent to a share of 1.9% of GDP.

The period 2017-2023 (Figure 1 and Figure 2), is characterized by an upward trend in environmental protection expenditures. Investments in environmental protection recorded a maximum in 2015 of 6.7 billion lei, a slight decrease in 2020, the year of the Covid 19 pandemic, followed by growth in the following years.

Figure 1. Evolution of the share of the contribution of current domestic expenditures and investments related to environmental protection in the Gross Domestic Product (%)

Sources: Romanian Statistical Yearbook, 2012-2024, www.insse.ro

Figure 2. Evolution of current domestic investments and expenditures for environmental protection (millions of lei, current prices)

Sources: Romanian Statistical Yearbook, 2012-2024, www.insse.ro

The study of environmental protection investments also marked the identification of their volume in the three categories of producers (public administration, specialized and non-specialized), during the studied period, and the following findings were made:

- changes were highlighted in their distribution in the three categories of producers (Table 1 and Figure 3)

- in 2014, the share of investments by non-specialized producers was 72.6%, in total investments for environmental protection, 18.6% public administration investments and 8.8% those of specialized producers;

- the year 2015 stands out with the highest volume of investments by non-

specialized producers and a share of 71% in total investments in environmental protection;

- high shares were recorded in investments by non-specialized producers, with a maximum of 73.0% of total investments for the environment in 2013.

- in the non-specialized producers category, the podium has been occupied since 2011 with 1491.5 million lei and a share of 28% of total investments regarding environmental protection in that year;

- in public administration, the largest environmental investments, in terms of volume, were also in 2011, 2522.1 million lei. As a share, investments made in total investments for environmental protection, the highest level of 54.6% and 54.5% were in 2019 and 2020.

In 2018, large investments for environmental protection were those registered in the field of wastewater management, carried out by public administration, and represented 78% of total investments in the field.

In 2019, at the national level, investments for environmental protection in the field of public administration wastewater management ranked first, accounting for 83.7% of total investments in this field of wastewater management. (<https://www.profit.ro>)

According to data provided by the INS, environmental protection expenditures, consisting of current expenditures and investments at the national level, amounted to 19.8 billion lei, in 2023, with a contribution of 1.2% to the Gross Domestic Product. (INS, www.economica)

According to official statistics, in Romania, a higher volume of environmental protection expenditures was recorded in the field of waste management in the category of specialized producers (70.3% of total expenditures in this field), and in terms of investments, in this segment, the largest amounts were recorded in the field of wastewater management in the category of non-specialized producers (53.1% of total investments in this field of wastewater management).

At the national level for 2023 (Table 1), environmental protection investments had a share of 31.1% of total environmental protection expenditures. Of the total, 41.9% were investments by non-specialized producers, in second place were investments by public administration, with a share of 40.4% and 17.7% in investments by specialized manufacturers.

In 2023, Eurostat provided information on the level of investments in environmental protection at the European Union level, which stood at 68 billion euros. Of the total amount, 60% (40 billion euros) were investments by corporations, both specialized and non-specialized suppliers. The difference of 40% was investments belonging to the public administration sector. (<https://ecsr.ro>)

As a share at the EU level, investments in environmental protection represented 1.8% of total investments. (<https://ecsr.ro>)

From the analysis of environmental protection investments (Figure 4) we noted that the 1st place goes to investments in the field of "Wastewater Management", with an average value of around 48.7% for the period 2011-2023.

The largest investments at the national level for environmental protection in 2023 were recorded in the field of "Wastewater Management", the non-specialized producers category, with a share of 53.1% of total investments in this field of wastewater management.

Also in 2022, the field of "Wastewater Management" occupied the top place, respectively 2.30 billion lei current prices and the second place was "Waste Management" with 1.6 billion lei current prices.

The INS provided data for 2024, regarding investments related to environmental protection, which stood at 26.3 percentage points of total expenditures at the level of Romania for environmental protection. By producer categories, first place went to public administration investments with a share of 50.3%, second place occupied by investments of non-specialized producers with 37.1 percentage points and 12.6% contributed by producers specialized.

In 2024, investments in environmental protection accounted for 26.3% of total expenditures made in Romania for environmental protection. (<https://greennews.ro>).

The analysis by environmental fields in 2024 outlined the following situation: first place in investments in environmental protection went to the field of "wastewater and water resources", 4.0 billion lei current prices, then the field of "waste, materials and material savings", with a value of 1.8 billion lei current prices.

Figure 3. Evolution of investments for environmental protection by types of producers (millions of lei current prices)

Sources: Romanian Statistical Yearbook, 2012-2024, www.insse.ro

Table 1

Shares of investments in environmental protection by type of producer (%)

	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Non-specialized producers	26	57	73	72	71	41.1	38.5	47.4	32.9	31.1	26.7	33.9	41.9	37.1
Specialized producers	28	12	11	9	12	9.5	11.5	11.5	12.5	14.5	20.9	25.8	17.7	12.6
Public administration	46	31	16	19	17	49.4	50	41.1	54.6	54.5	52.4	40.3	40.4	50.3

Sources: Romanian Statistical Yearbook, 2012-2024, www.insse.ro

Figure 4. Evolution of investments in environmental protection, by environmental areas (millions of lei, current prices)

Sources: Romanian Statistical Yearbook, 2012-2024, www.insse.ro

Figure 5. Investments for environmental protection by development regions, in 2023 (million lei current prices)
Sources: Romanian Statistical Yearbook, 2012-2024, www.insse.ro

The year 2023, by development regions (Figure 5), was marked by the highest investments made for environmental protection in the North-West region 1.8 billion lei current prices and a share of 29.3% of total investments, followed by the Center region 0.8 billion lei current prices and a share of 14.3% of total investments and by the South-Muntenia region with a share of 14.1%.

Environmental protection investments in the Bucharest-Ilfov region reached only 445.2 million lei current prices even though it faced systemic environmental problems and many challenges due to the transition to the green economy characteristic of the large cities of Europe.

Figure 6. Investments for environmental protection by types of producers and environmental areas, in 2023 (%)
Sources: Romanian Statistical Yearbook, 2012-2024, www.insse.ro

From INS data, in 2023, depending on the categories of producers (Figure 6), the distribution of investments in the environmental areas "Wastewater management" was 46.6% investments by public administration and 53.1% non-specialized producers. Investments in the field of Waste management were 53.7% specialized producers and 38.9% public administration. In the field of Ambient air and climate protection, the largest investments went to non-specialized producers with a share of 73% and 25.8% to public administration.

In 2024, large investments for environmental protection were recorded in the field of wastewater and water resources in the public administration category, representing 66.9% of total investments in this field.

Investments have a positive influence on the environment and ensure a clean future for future generations.

CONCLUSIONS

In this article, we examined investments as part of environmental protection expenditures in Romania.

The analysis carried out reinforced the idea that in the case of investments for environmental protection, large amounts went to the field of "Wastewater Management" from non-specialized producers. In fact, in 2023 and 2024, large investments were in the same field, wastewater management.

Efforts must be focused, supported, towards environmental protection, by all parties involved, being considered a national priority, which shapes the standard of living of the entire population, which will influence the sustainable development of society in the future.

Sustainable development has a primary role especially if we relate to the importance of the environment, which means medium and long-term investments and the appropriate allocation of resources. The essential pillars of sustainable development are environmental protection, economic development and social inclusion.

Environmental protection is essential for society, and through the investments made, natural resources are protected to ensure a sustainable future.

The conclusion that follows from the analysis carried out is that continuous monitoring of the expenses and investments involved in environmental protection will

ensure more and more new jobs, facilitating growth and sustainable development, along with protecting natural resources for future generations.

REFERENCES

- Akdag, S., Yildirim, H., Alola, A. A., 2024, Comparative benefits of environmental protection expenditures and environmental taxes in driving environmental quality of the European countries, *Natural Resources Forum*, 1–16, DOI: 10.1111/1477-8947.12464.
- Broniewicz E., 2011. Environmental Protection Expenditure in European Union. *Environmental Management in Practice*, United Kingdom, 21-36, DOI: 10.5772/18110.
- Dracea, R.,M, Ciobanu, L., Buziarnescu, A.A., 2020. The Impact of Environmental Protection Expenditure on Environmental Protection in Romania. *Empirical Analysis. Strategica. International Academic Conference*, Eighth Edition, 106-114. Available on https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369912391_The_Impact_of_Environmental_Protection_Expenditure_on_Environmental_Protection_in_Romania_Empirical_Analysis.
- Jarczok-Guzy, M., Kaczmarzyk, J., Sygut, E., 2024. Efficiency of environmental protection expenditure of the general governments in European Union member states in the context of sustainable development in waste management. *Acta Scientiarum Polonorum. Oeconomia*, 23(2), 17-27, DOI: 10.22630/ASPE.2024.23.2.6.
- Niu, B., 2024, Government environmental protection expenditure and national ESG performance: Global evidence, *Innovation and Green Development*, 3(2), p. 100117, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.igd.2023.100117>.
- Sîrbulescu, E. C., Toader, C. S., Dincu, A.M., Orboi, M.D., Pîrvulescu, L., 2023. Analysis of expenditure performed for environmental protection and their influence on environmental quality in Romania. *SGEM-Conference Proceeding*, 23(5.1), 329-336, DOI: 10.5593/sgem2023/5.1/s21.42.
- Sîrbulescu, C., Pîrvulescu, L., Iosim, I., Iancu T., Dincu A. M., 2021. Analysis of environmental protection expenditures and their influence on the quality of the environment. *Review on agriculture and rural development*, (10) 1-2, 71-77. https://business24.ro/mediu/protectia-mediului/investitiide-pestes-5-4-miliarde-lei-in-protectia-mediului-in-2011-ins-1520615?utm_source=Business24.ro&utm_medium=copy-paste, Accessed 10 Oct. 2025.
- <https://www.bursa.ro/ins-cheltuielile-pentru-protectia-mediului-au-fost-de-circa-12-6-miliarde-lei-in-2014-24241821>, Accessed 10 Oct. 2025.
- <https://insse.ro>. Romanian Statistical Yearbook, INS, 2012-2024.
- <https://ecsr.ro/investitiile-ue-in-protectia-mediului-in-2023-au-fost-de-67-de-miliarde-de-euro-eurostat/#:~:text=Eurostat%20estimeaz%C4%83%20c%C4%83%2C%20C3%AE%202023%2C%20C8%9B%C4%83rile%20UE%20au,pentru%20furnizarea%20de%20servicii%20de%20protec%C8%9Bie%20a%20mediului>. Accessed 25 Oct. 2025

https://www.economica.net/romania-a-cheltuit-12-din-pib-pentru-protectia-mediului-in-anul-2023-date-ins_781529.html, Accesed 25 Oct. 2025.

<https://greennews.ro/article/ins-cheltuielile-pentru-protectia-mediului-la-nivel-national-s-au-ridicat-anul-trecut-la-28-miliarde-lei-reprezentand-19-din-pib/>, Accesed 25 Oct. 2025

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Environmental_protection_expenditure_accounts#Environmental_protection_investments, Accesed 14 Oct. 2025.

<https://www.profit.ro/perspective/cheltuielile-pentru-protectia-mediului-in-romania-in-2019-s-au-ridicat-la-circa-16-miliarde-lei-1-5-din-pib-19518318>, Accesed 10 Oct. 2025

THE BEHAVIOUR OF SOME VARIETIES OF BEANS GROWN IN THE CLIMATIC CIRCUMSTANCES OF BIHARIA REGION

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The research paper studied the behaviour of certain varieties of beans under the climatic circumstances specific to Biharia region.

The varieties of beans tested in Biharia in 2023 are characterized by a great biological and productive potential.

The experiment with the varieties of beans emphasizes their behaviour from the angle of the measurements obtained which are related to the production.

The productive capacity of the species is closely related to the appearing of the climatic elements which influences it. In spite of this, there are certain species which respond better or less better to those specific circumstances, being pointed out from the others through the production differences.

Choosing the best – adapted variety for the climatic conditions of specific geographical area proves to be mostly influential upon the economical efficiency of that variety, besides the other technological elements which should be regarded for.

Key – words : variety, beans, climatic circumstances, area, productivity
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INTRODUCTION

The bean seeds are used as basic food for people; statistics made by FAO show that more than 500 million people usually eat bean products. For a long time, bean has been called “poop people’s meat” because of its high content of quality proteins; rich in essential aminoacids (lizine, arginine, triptofan) and more accessible with the price compared to the proteins of animal origin. The energetic value of the bean seed is very high, of course; reaching about 335 calories given by 100 grams of dried seeds.

Food products obtained from, dried beans are very tasty indeed; we can’t underrate their dietetical characteristics, and that is the reason they should be part of the diet recommended for the treatment of certain diseases, among them being the liver diseases.

Bean seeds flour can be used mixed with the wheat flour, in a percentage of 5% -

10%, in order to obtain tasty and nutritious bread.

Green pods are very appreciated as vegetables, whereas Chinese and Japanese cuisine use young beans offshoot prepared as salad.

The beanstalks (proteinic substances 8,1% of s.n.; glucid – 3,1% of s.n.; cellulose – 3,6% of s.n.) and bean pods constitute valuable fodder, especially for sheep and cows. Bean pods are used in medical field, prepared as tea for the treatments of diabetes.

The bean is harvested in early summer (July - August) leaving the land treated with nitrogen, without seeds or plant remains, the tilling of the ground is made in good conditions, so it can be considered as a good forerunner.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The biological resources which were experimented upon considered in 6 varieties of beans: Avans, Ardeleana, Star, Ami, Diva, Emiliana.

Technical data regarding the technical conditions in which the experiment took place:

- Type of soil: brown
- Forerunner plant: wheat
- Maintenance work: 2 weedings
- Supervision work: 2 sinoratox!2,0 treatment against beans weevil

- Fertilization was made using autumn before ploughing
- Sowing was performed by hand
- During vegetation period observation and measuring were carried
- Harvesting was done by hand and weighing were carried
- Explanation and analysis of results
- The method of setting the experiment was in the form of random blocks of 6 variants arranged in 3 repetitions
- The harvesting area of a plot was 20 square meters, and the plants were sowed at the distance of 50 cm between the rows
- Thickness was of about 50 germinative beans on a square meter for all the 6 varieties
- The distance between the repetition blocks was of 1 meter (paths) and for each margin of the block there was placed one protection part as large as a common variant
- The scheme of the experiment field and of the randomizing way of the variants for the 3 blocks.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The bean is a cultures plant with higher requirements regarding the pedoclimatic conditions.

The year 2023 was a favourable one for all the cultured plants, including the bean, because of all climate conditions which were most favourable.

During the vegetation period, for the varieties of bean experiment, a certain series blossoming were made, regarding the disease,

and pest, plant density at harvesting (table no. 1).

According to the description in Table no.1, the starting point of plants blossoming was 20th of June for Star and Diva varieties, while Emiliana and Ardeleana varieties followed 2 days later. For the Ami variety, blossoming began on the 26th of June, and for Avans variety, on the 1st of July.

Table 1

Observations made during the vegetation period of the beans variety experiment, Biharia, 2023

Nr.	Variety	Blossoming		Maturation		Grade for the resistance against diseases and pest	Density at harvesting/m ²
		Starting day	Duration	Starting day	Duration		
1.	Avans	1.07	22	27.07	12	2	41
2.	Ardeleana	28.06	22	27.07	10	2	46
3.	Star	26.06	21	19.07	11	2	36
4.	Ami	29.06	18	18.07	12	2	50
5.	Diva	26.06	21	19.07	13	2	38
6.	Emiliana	28.06	20	19.07	10	2	37

Duration of blossoming was about 18 days (Ami) and 22 days (Avans and Ardeleana).

Maturation of the bean pods in the year 2023 conditions began on the 18th of July (Ami). Star, Diva and Emiliana varieties followed on the next day.

About a week later (27th of July) the other 2 varieties, Avans and Ardeleana followed.

Duration of maturation extended from 10 days (Ardeleana and Emiliana) to 13 days (Diva).

Density of the harvesting plants was about 37 – 38 plants/m² for Emiliana and Diva varieties and up to 50 plants/ m² for the Ami variety.

In the conditions of 2023 there were no signification signs of diseases or pest at the varieties of bean experimented in Biharia.

Alongside the observations about vegetables presented above, before and after harvesting, measurements. (table no.2)

Table 2

**Biometrical measurements at the variety
of beans experimented, Biharia, 2023**

Nr.	Variety	Height (cm)		Nr. of pods/plant	Nr. of bean seeds/pod	Weight bean seeds/plant	MMB (g)	MHL (kg)
		Total	Insertion					
1.	Avans	64,4	10,0	11,0	44,2	9,7	250	78,8
2.	Ardeleana	58,3	9,0	9,9	49,2	10,9	280	77,2
3.	Star	55,8	9,5	10,2	36,5	12,7	350	72,0
4.	Ami	50,2	11,0	8,8	35,4	7,9	260	78,2
5.	Diva	58,1	11,4	10,8	43,3	11,4	290	74,0
6.	Emiliana	64,9	10,8	11,2	45,0	12,2	300	77,2

The total height of the plants is an average of 50,2 cm at the Ami variety, 55,8 cm at Star variety, 58 cm at Diva and Ardeleana varieties and about 65 cm at Emiliana and Avans varieties.

The insertion height of the bottom pods stretches between 9 cm (Ardeleana) and 11,4 cm at Diva.

The average number of pods per plant was 8,8 for Ami, 9,9 for Ardeleana and not more than 11,2 for Emiliana. In these conditions, the average number of bean seeds per plant was 35,5 for Ami, 36,5 for Star and maximum of 49,2 for Ardeleana.

The average weight of the bean seeds on a plant was of 7,9 g at Ami, 9,7 at Avans, 10,9 at Ardeleana and up to 12,7 g at Star variety.

The highest MMB was 250 g at Avans variety, followed by 269 g at Ami. The best

amount was of 300 g, and 350 g for the Emiliana and Star varieties.

The productions obtained during the experiment on beans in 2023 are good enough for the Western part of the country, almost of about 16,0 q/h in some cases (16,4 q/ hectare at diva variety in repetition III, the table).

The most productive variety is Ami, but the difference, compared to Diva and Emiliana is very little.

Compared to Avans – witness-variety, the “variation analysis” established the significance degree for the difference of the table.

Compared to Avans witness – variety, with an average production of 11,7 q/hectare. The Ardeleana and Star varieties showed differences of -0,1 and +0,4 q/hectare, proving insignificant in both cases.

Table .3

**Synthesis of production results obtained at
the bean experiment Biharia, 2023**

Nr.	Variety	Productions from repetitions			Average production q/ha	Relative production %	Difference q/hectare	Significance of differences
		I	II	III				
1.	Avans	8,3	11,4	15,4	11,7	100	-	-
2.	Ardeleana	8,9	12,0	13,9	11,6	99	- 0,1	-
3.	Star	10,9	12,8	12,6	12,1	103	+ 0,4	-
4.	Ami	15,4	14,6	15,0	15,0	128	+3,3	*
5.	Diva	13,2	14,2	16,4	14,6	125	+ 2,9	*
6.	Emiliana	13,7	14,5	16,2	14,8	126	+3,1	*

DL 5% = 2,47 q/ha

DL 1% = 3,51q/ha

DL 0,1% = 5,09 q/ha

CONCLUSIONS

The experiment regarding the behaviour of beans varieties in Biharia, took place in favourable climate conditions

These conditions caused a different response of the varieties from the point of view of observation and measurements which took place, and also of the productions obtained

Analyses of the data obtained in 2023 show a good behaviour of all the varieties, but Ami, Diva and Emiliana varieties were

distinguished from the rest, obtaining significant differences of production of +3,3 q/hectare, compared to Avans, the witness – variety, with the production of 11,7 q/hectare

In order to cultivate beans in Biharia region, following the experiment presented in this work, there can be recommended all 6 varieties of beans, but the most productive are: Ami, Emiliana and Diva.

REFERENCES

- Bîlteanu Gh, 1998, Fitotehnie, Editura Ceres, Bucureşti;
- Borcean I., Borcean A., 2004, Cultura și protecția integrată a cerealelor și plantelor tehnice, Editura de Vest, Timișoara;
- Borcean I., Borcean A., 2003, Cultura și protecția plantelor leguminoase cultivate pentru boabe, Editura de Vest, Timișoara;
- Borcean I. și colab., 1997, Tehnologia plantelor de câmp, Editura Universității de Științe Agricole și Medicină Veterinară a Banatului Timișoara;
- Borcean I., Borcean A., 2004, Cultura și protecția integrată a cerealelor și plantelor tehnice, Editura de Vest, Timișoara;
- Bogdan Ileana, Guș P., Rusu T., 2003, Agrotehnica diferențiată, Editura Risoprint, Cluj Napoca
- Crucița Sîrca, 2003, Comportarea unor specii de leguminoase în urma tratării semințelor cu tulpini selecționate de Rizobium, pe solurile argiloiluviale, Consfătuirea de Agrofitehnie, Livada, 18 – 20 iunie;
- David Gh, 2003, Tehnologia plantelor de câmp, Editura Eurobit, Timișoara;
- Domuța C., Sabău N.C., 2001, Agrotehnică, Editura Universității din Oradea;
- Drăghici Reta, 2002, Comportarea unor genuri de fasoliță în condițiile ecopedologice ale solurilor nisipoase din sudul Olteniei, Lucrări științifice SCCCNP
- Dăbuleni, vol. XIII;
- Mihăilescu Ghența, 1995, Influența îngrășămintelor azotate asupra producției leguminoaselor pentru boabe (soia, mazăre, fasole) pe trei tipuri de sol. Teză de doctorat, Institutul Agronomic București;
- Muntean L.S. și colab., 2001, Fitotehnie, Editura I.I. de la Brad, Iași;
- Olaru C., Fasolea, Editura Scrisul Românesc, Craiova, 1982;
- Prodan Ioana, Contribuții la evidențierea rolului unor factori fitotehnici în creșterea eficacității biopreparatelor fertilizante la fasole. Teză de doctorat, Universitatea de Științe Agronomice și Medicină Veterinară București, 1997;
- Pârșan P., 2003, Tehnologia plantelor de câmp, Editura Agroprint;

STUDIES REGARDING THE ESTABLISHMENT OF THE INTENSIVE AND SUPER-INTENSIVE CULTIVATING TECHNOLOGY OF THE PEACH-TREE IN DIOSIG FRUIT-GROWING AREA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The peach-tree is one of the most appreciated fruit-growing to the special qualities of the fruit and to the biological possibilities of the tree.

The intensive and super-intensive peach-tree growing raises a number of questions regarding the possibility of applying the system, because in the case of the peach-tree, there are no reduced vigour varieties or mother plants in production, which could easily allow the appliance of those systems on a large scale.

Taking into account the general tendency of intensifying the tree-growing, it is raised the problem of trying and finding solutions of making possible, in the case of peach-tree, too, the planting of more trees on a hectare, promoting the intensive and super-intensive cultivating system.

This way, researches were performed in Diosig, using varieties and planting distances, on their basis being decided the intensifying degree of the peach-tree.

Key- words : peach-tree, varieties, planting distances, the behaviour of the flower buds, thick growing of the trunk, fruit production.

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INTRODUCTION

The peach-tree belongs to the most valuable fruit-growing species.

Taking into account their savour, the peaches are placed immediately after the grapes, oranges and apple, they have a complex chemical composition and can be eaten both fresh varieties prove a spaced.

Peach-tree varieties prove a spaced out ripening, beginning with the 15th - 20th of June until the end of September, covering a period of more than 100 days.

The peach-tree shows some technological advantages: it is extremely precocious and productive; it hasn't got any response at fertilizing and irrigation; lower sensibility in case of hoar-frost compared to the apricot-tree; fruit are easily carried and handled.

Among the disadvantages of the peach-tree, the following could be pointed out: high demands for light and heat as well as for the soil; pretension to cutting very sensitive in case of blistering, reduced longevity and a certain percentage of early perishing.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The biological material consisted in 3 peach-tree varieties: Springold, Redhaven and Autumn Gorgeous, grafted on a month plant, Oradea 1, which represented a factor during the experiment.

The trees were planted leaving a distance of 4 meters between the rows and 3, 2, 1 and 0,5 meters between the trees in a row, having as result variants with planting distances comprising 833, 250, 2500, 5000 tree planted on a hectare, representing variants of intensive and super-intensive cultivating systems.

The soil in the orchard was maintained in good conditions as an early autumn ploughing long before and using the dish harrow.

Regarding the rigorous maintenance of soil as ploughing, during the last 2 years, there was noticed a certain reducing of the strictness applied to the appearance of many weeds, beginning especially with the second part of the summary.

The fertilization of the poet was done by the yearly usage of N₁₀₀, P₁₀₀, K₁₀₀ Kg doses

of active substance per hectare, and disease and pest control was done according to the technology applied in the production farms.

In order to notice the behaviour of the trees depending on planting distance, the growth of the tree thickness and the loss quality and quantity ; and the loss of flower

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. The resistance of the varieties to the frost

Taking into account the temperature during the winter 2021 - 2022 and 2022 - 2023 we found out the way in which the varieties analysed were influenced by these values of the temperature.

buds was given in percentage of the total amount of the analysed buds.

At the same time, when spring began, it was found out the way the flower buds passed the winter, by means of gathering the fruit-behaviour branches and gathering the fruit-bearing branches and deciding upon the buds viability.

The researches of the data obtained during the spring of 2022 showed that all the varieties studied were strongly influenced by the low temperatures during the winter, which practically destroyed the crop 100%.

The behaviour of the buds when confronted with negative temperatures in 2023 is presented in table no 1.

Behaviour of the buds when negative temperatures 2023

Table 1

Variety	Number of analysed buds	Number of variable buds	Number of dead buds	Percentage of dead buds
Springold	100	12	88	88
Redhaven	83	67	16	13
Autumn Gorgeous	40	16	24	60

When looking at data in this table it can be noticed that, during the winter 2022 - 2023, when the lowest temperature only came close to the limiting value of resistance at the peach-tree, there was also registered an important loss of flower buds.

The loss differs depending on the variety, finding that the Radhave behaved the best out of the 3 varieties studied, having 13% loss, which places it between the common limits, from the practical point of view.

A more serious situation can be noticed at Springold with early ripening, which showed a loss more of more than 80% of the flower buds, so that there is a strong reason for compensation cutting.

Between the 2 varieties the Autumn Gorgeous is placed, with loss of 60%

There can be noticed that the resistance at lower temperatures is strongly influenced by the biological factors and variety being established the fact that both the variety with early and late ripening show a strong sensibility when confronting low temperature.

2. The growth in thickness of the truck

The growth in thickness of the truck was obtained by measuring the truck was obtained by measuring the truck at about 30 cm above the ground, at the end of vegetation period using sliding callipers; after that, the results were counted for the surface of the truck's section expressed in cm.

Table 2

The surface of the truck's section at the peach-tree depending on the variety and the planting distance at the beginning of 2023

Variety	4x3 m 833 trees/hectare	4x2 m 1250 trees/hectare	4x1 m 2500 trees/hectare	4x0,5 m 5000 trees/hect are	Mean of variety and planting distance	%
Springold	26,9	23,4	22,2	14,1	21,6	118
Redhaven	16,2	17,5	14,3	11,7	14,9	81
Autumn Gorgeous	21,1	20,8	17,6	13,5	18,3	100
Mean	21,0	20,6	18,0	13,8	18,3	100
% given 4x3 m	100	98	86	66	-	-

Table number 2 shows that the 3 varieties behave differently regarding the vigour expressed by the surface of the truck's section.

This way, Springold proves to be the most vigorous, overcoming by 18,3% the being of the 3 varieties taken as witness, being followed by the Autumn Gorgeous, its vigour equalized the mean of the 3 varieties.

When tacking into account the Redhaven variety, we noticed a reduced vigour by 19% confronted with the varieties mean, an extremely important fact for the success of intensive and super-intensive plantation, as it is known that the peach-tree doesn't expose less vigorous mother-plants and varieties. The reduced vigour of the Redhaven variety can also be noticed when referring to the height of the trees as well as to the length of the mixed branches, which are shorter than those belonging to the other 2 varieties under researches.

As concerns the behaviour of the varieties under the influence of the planting distances, it can also be noticed, a strong difference, that is the reducing of the trunk to the extent of the reducing the planting

distance, in turn, and increasing the number of trees planed on a hectare.

This way, compared to the trees planted at 4x3m (833 trees/hectare), the trees planted at 4x2m prove to be 2% less vigorous, those planted at 4x1m are 14% less vigorous and those planted at 4x0,5m are 34% less vigorous.

This progressive decrease of vigour, as the number of trees planted on a hectare increases, can be explained by the fact that the trees, possessing smaller and smaller nutitions space turn to account less and less light, food and water but the reduced vigour of trees planted at small distances doesn't have negative effect on the production, on the contrary, the reduced growth being a factor which stimulates the fruit-growing expressed in tons, per hectare.

Beginning with the data in this table which show that if we plant the trees at 4x1m and using the Redhaven, we obtain 14 - 19% less vigorous trees, it is proved we can use in future the intensiveness of the peach - tree growing, using the bilogical materials existing in the culture.

3 .Fruit production

On the basis of those presented in table no.3, we can notice that the variety with the best production is Autumn Glamorous, very closely to it coming the Radhaven, which produces an average of almost 15 tons/hectare during a fixed period. The lowest production is given by the Springold, this being a direct consequence of the fact that it has fruit with an early ripening and a great sensitiveness towards lower temperatures.

As the planting distance concerns, it can be noticed that, during the whole period and counted mean researched, the fruit producing increases as the decreasing of the planting distance, simultaneously with the increasing of the number of trees planted on 2 hectare.

This way, given the trees planted at 4x3m distance, by planting them at 4x2m the

production grows with 41%, and by planting at 4x1m and 4x0,5m distance, the production is doubled and tripled.

It can also be noticed that among the trees planted at 4x1m, 1x0,5m distance, the level of the crops comes closer at Springold variety, as a consequence of the fact that, it being more vigorous, the production of the trees planted a 4x0,5m remains the same or even decreases.

Comparing the data of the trunk's growth with those of the production given the planting distance, it can be noticed the existence of a reversed relationship if it depends on the production counted for each hectare, meaning that the less vigorous the trees are, the richer the fruit production is, this growth being more striking than reducing the trees vigour.

Table 3

Production of fruit depending on the planting distance and variety of the peach-tree, in the conditions of Diosig region (tones/ hectare)

Variety	Year	Planting distance (m)				Variety and distance mean	%
		4x3 m 833 trees/hectare	4x2 m 1250 trees/hectare	4x1 m 2500 trees/hectare	4x0,5 m 5000 trees/hectare		
Springold	2020	3,2	6,5	13,8	12,7		
	2021	1,2	3,4	3,0	4,2		
	2022	12,3	27,5	34,1	35,4		
	2023	2,0	3,1	6,3	12,5		
Mean		4,7	10,1	14,3	16,2	11,3	82
Redhaven	2020	4,5	8,3	10,6	11,6		
	2021	2,9	3,1	4,9	7,6		
	2022	16,9	25,6	51,4	50,2		
	2023	5,0	7,6	15,2	21,0		
Mean		7,4	11,2	18,0	22,5	14,8	108
Autumn Gorgeous	2020	6,5	9,9	16,1	23,3		
	2021	6,3	6,1	7,8	7,6		
	2022	13,8	20,8	29,2	58,8		
	2023	4,0	6,1	12,0	15,0		
Mean		7,6	10,7	16,4	21,6	15,1	100
%		100	141	214	328	13,7	100

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of the behaviour of the flower buds during the low temperature winter periods shows that, taking into account the 3 varieties, a better resistance is recorded by Redhaven, which showed 13% frozen buds in 2023 spring compared to Spingold, which had a percentage of 88% of destroyed buds.

The data concerning the growing and ripening of the trees depending on the variety and planting distance allow us to draw the following conclusions: referring to the vigour of the varieties studied, it can be seen that this is different, Redhaven proving less vigorous whereas Autumn Gorgeous and Springold showed more vigour. This way, we can afford to say that Redhaven is better-suited to be introduced in the super-intensive culture, comparing to the other 2 varieties which were analysed.

The planting distances strongly influence the growth in thickness of the tree, because it reduces as the planting distance of the tree, it turns, reduces from 3 m to 2 m, 1 m and 0,5 m. The decreasing of the vigour of the trees as planting distance in turns decreases to 34%, proves to be an encouragement which comes to promote the super – intensive growing system for the peach – tree, too.

Fruit production is influenced by varieties and planting distances. The three varieties which were analysed register, depending on the fruit – ripening period, a smaller production at Springold with early ripening, and a richer one at Redhaven and Autumn Gorgeous.

The planting distance positively influence the production obtained on each hectare as the trees are planted thickly, obtaining a more numerous number of trees per hectare and a richer production, succeeding in obtainig a doubled or even a tripled production.

REFERENCES

- Baciu A.A. 2005,,Pomicultură generală, Editura Universitaria, Craiova;
- Botu I. Botu M.,2003, Pomicultură modernă și durabilă, Editura Conphys, Rm. Vâlcea;
- Braniște N., 2003,Ghidul pomicultorului, Editura Agroprint Pitești;
- Braniște N.,2007, Soiuri de pomi, arbuști fructiferi și capșuni create în România, Editura Paralela 45, Pitești;
- Cepoiu N., 2001,Pomicultură aplicată, Editura Științelor Agricole, București; Cepoiu N., Dumitru Liana Melania, Chira Lenuța, Indreaș Gh., Piersicul și nectarinul dwarf în atenția pomicultorilor din țara noastră, sesiune omagială 50 de ani de la înființarea Facultății de Horticultură, București, 1998;
- Cociu V. , 2001, Cultura piersicului, Editura Ceres, București;
- Cociu V,1999, Cultura piersicului în gospodărie, Editura Ceres, București;
- Cociu V, Botu I., Șerboiu L.,1999, Progrese în ameliorarea plantelor horticole din România, vol. I, Editura Ceres, București;
- Drăgănescu E.1998, Pomicultură, Editura Mirton Timișoara;
- Drăgănescu E., Mihuț E., 2005,Cultura speciilor pomicole, Editura Waldpress Timișoara;
- Ghena N.,Braniște N.,2003, Cultura specială a pomilor, Editura Matrix Rom,București;
- Hoza D., 2000, Pomologie, Editura Prahova, Ploiești ;
- Hoza, D.,2003, Sfaturi practice pentru cultura pomilor, București, Editura Nemira;
- Ivașcu A. 2002, Rentabilizarea culturii piersicului în ferme mici și mijlocii,Editura Cris Book Universal, București;
- Ivașcu A. 2002, Să redescoperim piersicul, Editura Universal Company București;
- Indreaș A., 1995, Contribuții privind obținerea de noi portaltoi pentru piersic, Teză de doctorat, Universitatea din Craiova;
- Ionescu P., Dumitru Liana, 1996, Sortimentul de perspectivă al speciei piersic în atenția marilor și micilor producători, Lucrări științifice, I.C.P.P. Pitești;
- Mihuț E. 2001, Pomicultură generală și specială, Editura Agroprint, Timișoara;
- Mihuț E., Drăgănescu E, 2003., Pomicultură. Înființarea și managementul plantației, Editura Agroprint, Timișoara,;

THE MOST FREQUENT ZONOSSES FOUND IN CATS IN ORADEA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This study was conducted in collaboration with several clinics in Oradea. This paper discusses the most common diseases transmissible from cats to humans following a research in Oradea. The most well-known zoonoses that can occur can be: parasitic (giardiasis, toxoplasmosis), bacterial (cat scratch disease caused by Bartonella), viral (rabies) or fungal (microspora).

Keywords: Microsporum canis, fungal skin infection, intense pruritus, circular erythema, transmission, direct/indirect contact

INTRODUCTION

Dogs and cats can spread various zoonotic diseases to humans, with some of these being potentially fatal. Zoonosis refers to an infectious illness that has transferred from a nonhuman animal to people.

Zoonotic pathogens can be bacterial, viral, or parasitic, or may include unconventional agents, and they can transmit to humans via direct contact or through food, water, or environmental means. They pose a significant public health issue globally because of our close ties with animals in farming, as pets, and in the wild.

Zoonotic diseases linked to cats encompass rabies, capnocytophagosis, pasteurellosis, cat scratch disease, ringworm, plague, Q fever, and external parasites, along with campylobacteriosis, salmonellosis, cryptosporidiosis, giardiasis, toxoplasmosis, and MRSA. Zoonotic disease transmission from pets mainly occurs through direct contact, ingestion, indirect contact via insect vectors and contaminated surfaces, or inhaling aerosolized substances.

When interacting with seemingly healthy animals, maintaining good hygiene (such as hand washing) is a crucial precaution. Washing hands is especially crucial prior to eating or any other contact involving the mouth. Hand-washing stations should be available in fairs, petting zoos, or other places where people may interact with animals, and consuming food or beverages in animal zones should be discouraged.

Measures to safeguard veterinary hospitals comprise barrier precautions (such as gloves, protective clothing, and other suitable personal protective equipment), proper

hygiene, sanitation and disinfection practices, correct disposal of infectious materials, and utilization of isolation units for animals confirmed to have zoonotic diseases.

This study was conducted in collaboration with several clinics in Oradea and discusses the most common diseases transmissible from cats to humans in Oradea.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The materials used were those most readily available in the clinics that participated in the study, namely laboratory equipment consisting of slides, microscope, Wood's lamp (UV light), blood analyzers, Yolexx hematology and biochemistry analyzers, and rapid viral tests.

The more laborious analyses were sent to large laboratories in Bucharest for microbiological cultures, namely fungal cultures - these were collected from hair strands and placed on a DTH culture medium - and bacterial cultures from blood or faeces followed by antibiogram where appropriate and from blood for PCR tests.

As for the methods used in the clinics in Oradea, they were clinical, based largely on anamnesis and discussions with cat owners, followed by the proposed clinical examination, based on the clinical signs appearing in the cat, either on the skin, pruritic erythema, or diarrhea, vomiting, lethargy, apathy, or sometimes asymptomatic.

To identify fungal zoonoses, hair samples were collected from the affected areas during the clinical examination and subsequently examined under a microscope. The Wood's lamp was also used to examine the areas of skin

changes observed during the clinical examination.

All these methods are non-invasive and do not cause stress to the cats. For parasitic areas, coproparasitological methods were used through microscopic analysis to identify parasitic eggs or cysts. Other methods used were ultrasound and radiographic examination for systemic diseases or other lesions caused by migratory parasites. All these methods combined helped to make a definitive diagnosis in order to establish the appropriate treatment and, very importantly, prevention.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

With the help of veterinary clinics that agreed to participate in this study, 100 cats were examined between January 2025 and October 2025. It should be noted that only cats with owners were taken into account for this study, not stray cats.

Cats with owners are at a significant advantage over stray cats, as they are considered to be constantly and periodically dewormed internally and externally according to each clinic's protocol, thus the risk of zoonoses being significantly lower compared to stray cats.

Among the known zoonoses, the highest percentage during the period under consideration was obtained by a mycotic zoonosis caused by *Microsporium canis*, the frequency being higher due to its high contagiousness. The parasitic zoonosis caused by *Toxoplasma gondii* had a much lower percentage.

In terms of symptoms, this parasitic disease can be asymptomatic, being diagnosed mainly through paraclinical tests. Also in this category of parasitic zoonoses, tapeworms, more specifically *Dypilidium*, were also found, but in a very small percentage.

CONCLUSIONS

The highest percentage of zoonoses was caused by the fungal disease produced by *Microsporium canis*, at 30%, followed by a parasitic disease produced by *Toxoplasma gondii* at 5%, and cases of tapeworms produced by *Dypilidium* at 2%. The rest of the cats were healthy, both from a clinical point of view and according to the tests and analyses performed.

It should be noted that all three diseases can be prevented by vaccination in the case of microspores, but this prevention is less well known among cat owners, and internal and external deworming according to the

veterinarian's protocol for the other two zoonoses encountered.

The recommendation is, of course, to carry out regular vaccinations, and also internal and external deworming in order to prevent the risk of these zoonoses occurring.

REFERENCES

- Hinilica K. A., Patterson A., "Small Animal Dermatology: A Color Atlas and Therapeutic Guide", Elsevier, 2017;
- Palmer S.R., Soulsby E.J.L., Simpson D.I.H., "Zoonoses", Editura Științelor Medicale, 2005;
- Flynn R.J., "Parasites of Laboratory Animals", Iowa State University Press; Ames, IA: 1973;
- Vasiu C., "Bacteriosis in animals", Editura Academicpress Cluj-Napoca, 2001

TREATMENT OPTIONS FOR FOOT DISEASES IN DAIRY CATTLE

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REVIEW

Abstract

The multiple kind of foot diseases in cattle represents a pathology with deep implications for animals welfare and profitability of dairy cattle farms. The high frequency of these conditions and their significant economic impact are highlighted by references to global and local studies. The multidisciplinary approach for the effective control of lameness is done through diagnostic methods, current treatment protocols (topical, systemic), and also prevention and control strategies. This complex approach is necessary to improve the condition of the animals, to make a more efficient production and increase the profitability.

Keywords: cattle, lameness, foot, dairy, control
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INTRODUCTION

Foot health (foot and hoof health) is an essential element of productivity and welfare in modern cattle farms, especially in dairy farms. The foot conditions often grouped under the generic term of lameness, represent a major problem at a global level.

The economic impact of these diseases is considerable, being frequently ranked as the third cause of financial loss in dairy farms, after reproduction and mastitis problems (Akin & Akin, 2018; Hernandez et al., 2001).

The losses result from reduced milk production (Györkös et al., 1999; Pavlenko et al., 2011; Relun et al., 2013), treatment costs, premature animal reformation and the negative impact over the ovarian function and the calving-to-conception interval (Garbarino et al., 2004; Hernandez et al., 2001).

The awareness of the negative impact on health (Ramanoon et al., 2018) and on performance (Garvey, 2022), led to an increased research for etiology, prevention and management of foot disorders (Potterton et al., 2012).

Furthermore, lameness severely compromises the well-being of animals, causing pain, discomfort and behaviour changes (Bruijnis et al., 2012).

Technological advances, such as using locomotion scoring (Werema et al., 2022) and precision technologies (Silva et al., 2021), provide new tools for early detection and rapid intervention. (Tabel 1.)

Effective recognition and management of these diseases require a deep understanding of their complex etiology, which involves interactions between the pathogen, animal and environment.

Description of the main foot diseases

Foot pathologies in cattle are diverse and can be classified in two major categories: infectious and non-infectious (mechanical).

Infectious diseases

Digital dermatitis (DD) also known as “Mortellaro’s disease”, is a superficial, ulcerative or proliferative pododermatitis, highly contagious. It is caused by a polymicrobial bacterial infection, and a main role is assigned to anaerobic spirochete bacteria from *Treponema* (Canales et al., 2022; Nascimento et al., 2015). Lesions typically appear in the skin area over the interdigital space, especially on the hind limbs. The active lesion (stage M2 according to the M-stage scoring) is a reddish, circular or oval wound, extremely painful. Risk factors include poor hygiene of the animal shelter, increased floor humidity and the introduction of infected animals into the herd (Ahlén et al., 2022; Palmer & O’Connell, 2015).

Interdigital phlegmon (interdigital necrobacillosis), popular known as “foot rot”, is an acute bacterial infection of the interdigital space, characterized by symmetrical swelling of the foot, unpleasant, repulsive smell and severe lameness (Bednarski, 2015). It is predominantly caused by *Fusobacterium necrophorum*. The infection requires a pre-existing lesion of the

interdigital skin (a friction, a sting) in order to penetrate.

Table 1

Methods for scoring locomotion for cattle

Scoring method	Method type	Short description and key features	Main Bibliographic source/Support
Sprecher scoring system, 5 points	Visual, Manual, Subjective	It evaluates the posture of the back (from 1=straight back to 5=severely arched back) and the way the animal puts weight on its legs. It is one of the most used references scales.	Sprecher et al., 1997 Roche et al., 2024
LS scoring system, 4 points (Welfare Quality/Dairy NZ)	Visual, Manual, Subjective	Evaluates is based on the co-assessment of walking speed, walking rhythm, weight-bearing, back alignment, head position, stride length, and foot placement	Werema et al., 2022
Force Plate analysis	Objective, technological, research	It measures the vertical force applied by each foot on a specialized board built into the floor. Identifies the asymmetries of weight and force.	Ramanoon et al., 2018
Precision technologies (Sensors/Video)	Objective, Automated	It uses accelerometers, pressure sensors or computer vision systems to continuously monitor the walking patterns, speed and back positions, recording automatic data.	Silva et al., 2021; Antanaitis et al., 2021
In-Parlour Scoring	Visual, Manual, Quick	A quick screening method that observes a single parameter (eg. Back position) while milking.	Werema et al., 2022
Direct clinical examination of the hoof	Clinic, Diagnostics	Physical detailed examination by a specialist in order to diagnose the specific lesion (eg: plantar ulcer, digital dermatitis).	Kleinhenz et al., 2014

Interdigital dermatitis (DID) or “superficial digital dermatitis” is a superficial bacterial infection, polymicrobial, although is often associated with the presence of *Dichelobacter nodosus*, with chronic evolution of the skin from the interdigital space in cattle, without severe swelling of the entire foot above the hoof, it can progress and predispose the animal for more serious lesions, such as digital dermatitis or horn lesions (Bicalho & Oikonomou, 2013).

Non-infectious/mechanical diseases

These are predominantly hoof injuries resulting from mechanical trauma, management errors, shelter construction or nutritional deficiencies.

Foot ulcer is a lesion of the sole of the hoof, occurring as a result of excessive pressure on the corium (the living tissue that produces the hoof horn) causing inflammation and disruption of healthy horn production. Factors include hard concrete surfaces, excessive time spent standing (eg. waiting for milking), incorrect hoof trimming and subclinical ruminal acidosis. (Van Amstel et al., 2003; Bednarski, 2015).

White line disease (WLD). The white line is the junction area between the sole of the foot and the outer wall. It is a structurally weak area.

WLD appears when the pebbles, impurities or excessive pressure enters in this junction, creating a crack or abscess. (Blowey, 2015). The formed abscess can erupt at the crown level. Risk factors are similar to those for plantar ulcers. (Barker et al., 2009).

Hoof hematomas/bleeds (also known as foot bleeds or contusions) represent common subclinical lesions characterized by the leakage of blood from the blood vessels of the corium (the living tissue beneath the horn) inside the horn layer of the hoof. They are caused by mechanical trauma, excessive pressure on the sole (prolonged standing on concrete, hard surfaces), or by weakening of the horn structure. They can be key indicators of subclinical lesions and direct precursors of serious lesions such as foot ulcers. (Machado, V.S., et. Col., 2010).

Foot disease incidence

The incidence of foot disease varies significantly between farms and geographical regions, being influenced by the production system (intensive vs extensive), climate, breed and management practices.

Digital dermatitis is considered the most spread infectious hoof disease worldwide in industrialized dairy farms. The prevalence in

affected herds can reach alarming levels. For including Romania, report average prevalences of clinical lameness ranging between 10% and 50% or even more, although the prevalence of DD itself can be much higher, reaching 70-90% in some large farms. (Palmer & O'Connell, 2015).

Non-infectious diseases, such as foot ulcers and white line disease are also common

example, case studies from various countries, and often directly related to structural factors of the shelter and hoof trimming. The evaluation of the frequency is crucial to implement appropriate preventive measures and to estimate the real economic impact. (Lopes Júnior et al., 2012).

Table 2

Average prevalence of foot diseases in cattle based on international literature
(Thomsen et al., 2023; Roche et al., 2024; Blowey, 2015; Refaai et al., 2013).

Foot problem	Average frequency (%)	Main category
Digital dermatitis (DD)	15% - 70%	Infectious
White line disease	5% - 25%	Non-infectious
Foot ulcer	5% - 20%	Non-infectious
Interdigital dermatitis	5% - 15%	Infectious
Interdigital phlegmon	1% - 10%	Infectious
Hematomas/Bleeds	5% - 15% (as a distinct lesion)	Non-infectious

Treatment methods and therapeutic protocols

Effective treatment of foot diseases requires an accurate and early diagnosis (by using scoring methods) to identify affected animals before lameness becomes severe (Flower & Weary, 2009) and a quick intervention, often combining pain management, local or systemic therapy and hoof grooming.

Physical and surgical therapies

These are the basis of management of horn and structural lesions.

Functional and corrective grooming is a fundamental procedure. Standardized techniques, described by various authors (Shearer & van Amstel, 2001; Manske et al., 2002), aim to rebalance the weight on the four hooves, reduce pressure on the painful areas and remove the necrotic or weakened horn. After the removal of necrotic and soft tissue or weakened horn, an oxygen microenvironment is formed, preventing the replication of anaerobic microbes and abscess formation. If the procedure is performed without damaging the healthy tissue of the dermis, the pain after the procedure is minor and the animal recovers faster.

Hoof block is a vital method for the treatment of foot lesions such as ulcers or white line abscesses (Van Amstel et al., 2003). A

wooden or rubber block is applied, glued on the healthy hoof (medial to the hind feet) to life and completely deviate the weight from the affected hoof, allowing the exposed corium to heal. This method is considered to be essential by many practitioners (Kleinhenz et al., 2014).

Excision of necrotic tissue.

In cases of severe fusobacteriosis or extensive abscesses meticulous removal of necrotic tissue, foreign bodies and pus is necessary to allow the access for topical and stimulate healing (Bednarski, 2015).

There are some cases when it may be necessary to apply a dressing, which is usually a thick layer of cotton wool soaked in zinc/copper sulfate, or an antibiotic (usually tetracycline or oxytetracycline in powder or spray form), possibly formalin, which is then fixed with a bandage. This type of treatment is used for toe injuries, digital dermatitis or atypical digital dermatitis. The dressing protects the wound against infection and it is recommended that the animal stands on a dry surface. The dressing applied should not be too tight because it can prevent blood circulation in the hoof, and also the healing of the wound, because the supply of nutrients is obstructed. Van Amstel, si col., 2003 often observed that, in animals with dressings, damaged hooves heal more slowly than in those without dressing.

Pharmacological therapies

The use of medications is complementary to physical interventions and is essential for controlling infection and pain.

Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory medications are crucial for the management of the pain and inflammation associated with lameness. These medications (meloxicam, flunixin meglumin) not only reduce animal suffering (Ramanoon et al., 2018), but also improve recovery rates and subsequent performance (Wilson et al., 2022). Their administration is recommended both at the time of diagnosis and also in some protocols, preventively at calving (Wilson et al., 2022).

Topical treatments

For digital dermatitis, local treatments are the first line of defense. Solutions based on oxytetracycline, copper sulfate or zinc are applied directly on the cleaned lesion (Shearer et al., 2015; Berry et al., 2012). Effectiveness depends on correct and repeated application. Studies have evaluated various formulations, including those without antibiotics, to reduce antimicrobial resistance (Afonso et al., 2021).

CONCLUSIONS

Foot disorders in cattle represent a complex of animal health, welfare and economic management problem due to the frequency with which it still persists on many cattle farms (Thomsen et al., 2023), especially in dairy farms. The multifactorial nature of the diseases (infectious, environmental and nutritional factors) require a complex approach from the veterinarians and farmers.

The scientific literature provides clear evidence that early intervention, accurate diagnosis (Afonso et al., 2021) and appropriate treatment protocols are the key to success.

Systemic antibiotics are used in severe or chronic cases, or when the infection has penetrated deep into the profound structures (e.g., severe interdigital phlegmon, osteomyelitis). It is preferable that the used antibiotics have a "0" day withdrawal period for milk, especially in the case of dairy cattle. (e.g., ceftiofur, etc.).

Control and prevention at herd level

Prevention aims to reduce exposure to risk factors and increase animal resistance (Roche et al., 2024).

Reducing the exposure to moisture and faeces by a rigorously cleaning of the stable floors and ensuring a dry bedding thus minimizing risk factors (Barker et al., 2009; Palmer & O'Connell, 2015).

Footbaths are used both preventively and as a mass treatment. Footbaths use solutions such as zinc or copper sulphate or diluted formaldehyde to reduce bacterial load and treat the incipient lesions (Bicalho & Oikonomou, 2013). Consistent use of these footbaths represents an effective and recommended control of foot diseases in cattle, especially digital dermatitis (Potterton et al., 2012)

Preventive measures such as maintaining superior shelter hygiene, optimizing nutrition to strengthen the hoof horn (Laven & Logue, 2006) and regular and correct hoof trimming are essential to reducing the incidence of foot pathology.

Although significant progress has been made in understanding and treating these diseases, the challenge remains to consistently implement the best practices at the farm level (Leach et al., 2010). Integrated approaches and continuous monitoring are needed to minimize the negative impact of lameness on cattle herds.

REFERENCES

- Afonso, J. S., Oikonomou, G., Carter, S., Clough, H. E., Griffiths, B. E., & Rushton, J. (2021). Diagnosis of bovine digital dermatitis: Exploring the usefulness of indirect ELISA. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 8, 728691.
- Ahlén, L., Holmøy, I. H., Nødtvedt, A., Sogstad, Å. M., & Fjeldaas, T. (2022). A case-control study regarding factors associated with digital dermatitis in Norwegian dairy herds. *Acta Veterinaria Scandinavica*, 64(1), 19.
- Akin, I., & Akin, T. (2018). Economic impact of digital dermatitis treatment on a dairy farm: an application of the break-even analysis. *Ciência Rural*, 48(8), 1–7.
- Antanaitis, R., et al. (2021). Identification of Risk Factors for Lameness Detection with Help of Biosensors. *Agriculture*, 11, 610.
- Barker, Z. E., Amory, J. R., Wright, J. L., Mason, S. A., Blowey, R. W., & Green, L. E. (2009). Risk factors for increased rates of sole ulcers, white line disease, and digital dermatitis in dairy cattle from twenty-seven farms in England and Wales. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 92(5), 1971–1978.

- Bednarski, M. (2015). *Choroby Bydła Podstawy Diagnostyki i Terapii*. Apra—Wetpress.
- Berry, S. L., Read, D. H., Famula, T. R., Mongini, A., & Döpfer, D. (2012). Long-term observations on the dynamics of bovine digital dermatitis lesions on a California dairy after topical treatment with lincomycin HCl. *The Veterinary Journal*, 193, 654–658.
- Bicalho, R. C., & Oikonomou, G. (2013). Control and prevention of lameness associated with claw lesions in dairy cows. *Livestock Science*, 156, 96–105.
- Blowey, R. W. (2015). *Cattle Lameness and Hoof Care* (3rd ed.). 5m Publishing.
- Bruijnjs, M. R. N., Beerda, B., Hogeveen, H., & Stassen, E. N. (2012). Assessing the welfare impact of foot disorders in dairy cattle by a modeling approach. *Animal*, 6(6), 962–970.
- Canales, N., Bustamante, H., Wilson-Welder, J., Thomas, C., Ramirez, E., & Salgado, M. (2022). First Molecular Confirmation of *Treponema* spp. in Lesions Consistent with Digital Dermatitis in Chilean Dairy Cattle. *Pathogens*, 11(5), 510.
- Edwards, A., Dymock, D., & Jenkinson, H. (2003). From tooth to hoof: *Treponemes* in tissue-destructive diseases. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, 94, 767–780.
- Flower, F. C., & Weary, D. M. (2009). Gait assessment in dairy cattle. *Animal*, 3, 87–95.
- Garbarino, E. J., Hernandez, J. A., Shearer, J. K., Risco, C. A., & Thatcher, W. W. (2004). Effect of lameness on ovarian activity in postpartum Holstein cows. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 87(12), 4123–4131.
- Garvey, M. (2022). Lameness in Dairy Cow Herds: Disease Aetiology, Prevention and Management. *Dairy*, 3, 199–210.
- Györkös, I., Kovacs, K., Mezes, M., Bader, E., & Nyakas, I. (1999). Influence of digital dermatitis on milk production in dairy cows. *Allattenyésztes Es Takarmanyozas*, 48(5), 483–489.
- Hernandez, J., Shearer, J. K., & Webb, D. W. (2001). Effect of lameness on the calving-to-conception interval in dairy cows. *Journal of the American Veterinary Medical Association*, 218(10), 1611–1614.
- Kleinhenz, K., et al. (2014). Survey of veterinarians and hoof trimmers on methods applied to treat claw lesions in dairy cattle. *Bovine Practitioner*, 48, 47–52.
- Laven, R. A., & Logue, D. N. (2006). Treatment strategies for digital dermatitis for the UK. *The Veterinary Journal*, 171(1), 79–88.
- Leach, K. A., Whay, H. R., Maggs, C. M., Barker, Z. E., Paul, E. S., Bell, A. K., & Main, D. C. J. (2010). Working towards a reduction in cattle lameness: 1. Understanding barriers to lameness control on dairy farms. *Research in Veterinary Science*, 89(2), 311–317.
- Leão, M. A., Fioravanti, M. C. S., Silva, O. C., Serafim, J., Moura, M. I., Caetano, L. B., Eurides, D., & Silva, L. A. F. (2008). Dermatite digital bovina: Resposta terapêutica e custo dos protocolos adotados em duas propriedades rurais. *Revista Brasileira de Ciência Veterinária*, 15(3), 111–116.
- Lopes Júnior, J. F., Ramos, C. E. C. O., Santos, G. T., Grande, P. A., Damasceno, J. C., & Massuda, E. M. (2012). Análise das práticas de produtores em sistemas de produção leiteiros e seus resultados na produção e qualidade do leite. *Semina: Ciências Agrárias*, 33(3), 1199–1208.
- Machado, V.S., Caixeta, L.S., McArt, J.A., Bicalho, R.C. (2010). The effect of claw horn disruption lesions and body condition score at dry-off on survivability, reproductive performance, and milk production in the subsequent lactation. *Dairy Sci.*, 93, 4071–4078.
- Manske, T., Hultgren, J., & Bergsten, C. (2002). The effect of claw trimming on the hoof health of Swedish dairy cattle. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, 54, 113–129.
- Nascimento, L. V., Mauerwerk, M. T., Santos, C. L., Barros Filho, I. R., Birgel Junior, E. H., Sotomaior, C. S., Madeira, H. M. F., & Ollhoff, R. D. (2015). *Treponemes* detected in digital dermatitis lesions in Brazilian dairy cattle and possible host reservoirs of infection. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology*, 53(6), 1935–1937.
- Palmer, M. A., & O'Connell, N. E. (2015). Digital dermatitis in dairy cows: A review of risk factors and potential sources of between-animal variation in susceptibility. *Animals*, 5(3), 512–535.
- Pavlenko, A., Bergsten, C., Ekesbo, I., Kaart, T., Aland, A., & Lidfors, L. (2011). Influence of digital dermatitis and sole ulcer on dairy cow behaviour and milk production. *Animal*, 5(8), 1259–1269.
- Potterton, S. L., Bell, N. J., Whay, H. R., Berry, E. A., Atkinson, O. C. D., Dean, R. S., & Huxley, J. N. (2012). A descriptive review of the peer and non-peer reviewed literature on the treatment and prevention of foot lameness in cattle published between 2000 and 2011. *The Veterinary Journal*, 193, 612–616.
- Ramanoon, S. Z., et al. (2018). The Impact of Lameness on Dairy Cattle Welfare: Growing Need for Objective Methods of Detecting Lame Cows and Assessment of Associated Pain. *Animal Welfare*.
- Refaai, W., et al. (2013). Infectious diseases causing lameness in cattle with a main emphasis on digital dermatitis (Mortellaro disease). *Livest. Sci.*, 156, 53–63.
- Relun, A., Lehebel, A., Chesnin, A., Guatteo, R., & Bareille, N. (2013). Association between digital dermatitis lesions and test-day milk yield of Holstein cows from 41 French dairy farms. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 96(4), 2190–2200.
- Roche, S. M., et al. (2024). Invited review: Prevalence, risk factors, treatment, and barriers to best practice adoption for lameness and injuries in dairy cattle—A narrative review. *J. Dairy Sci.*, 107, 3347–3366.
- Shearer, J. K., & van Amstel, S. R. (2001). Functional and corrective claw trimming. *Veterinary Clinics of North America: Food Animal Practice*, 17, 53–72.
- Shearer, J. K., Plummer, P. J., & Schleinig, J. A. (2015). Perspectives on the treatment of claw lesions in cattle. *Veterinary Medicine*, 30, 273–292.
- Silva, S. R., Araujo, J. P., Guedes, C., Silva, F., Almeida, M., & Cerqueira, J. L. (2021). Precision Technologies to Address Dairy Cattle Welfare: Focus on Lameness, Mastitis and Body Condition. *Animals*, 11, 2253.
- Sprecher, D. J., Huszenicza, G., & Weaver, L. D. (1997). 3. The effects of lameness on milk yield of dairy cows. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 80(10), 2471–2476.

-
- Thomsen, P. T., et al. (2023). Prevalence of lameness in dairy cows: A literature review. *The Veterinary Journal*, 295, 105975.
- Van Amstel, S. R., Shearer, J. K., & Palin, F. L. (2003). Case report—Clinical response to treatment of pododermatitis circumscripta (ulceration of the sole) in dairy cows. *Bovine Practitioner*, 37, 143–150.
- Werema, C. W., Yang, D. A., Laven, L. J., Mueller, K. R., & Laven, R. A. (2022). Evaluating Alternatives to Locomotion Scoring for Detecting Lameness in Pasture-Based Dairy Cattle in New Zealand: In-Parlour Scoring. *Animals*, 12, 703.
- Wilson, J. P., Green, M. J., Randall, L. V., Rutland, C. S., Bell, N. J., Hemingway-Arnold, H., Thompson, J. S., Bollard, N. J., & Huxley, J. N. (2022). Effects of routine treatment with nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs at calving and when lame on the future probability of lameness and culling in dairy cows: A randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 105, 6041–6054.

ENDOPARASITES OF CATTLE RAISED IN EXTENSIVE SYSTEMS

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REVIEW

Abstract

Extensive cattle farming systems are characterized by continuous access to pasture. This management method, although advantageous from an animal welfare and operational cost perspective, exposes the cattle herds to a higher risk of endoparasite infestation. The prevalence and intensity of these parasites vary considerably depending on climatic and geographical factors, animal age, the presence of intermediate hosts and farm management practices (Charlier et al., 2020). The main pathogens include gastrointestinal nematodes, hepatic and ruminal trematodes (Forstmaier et al., 2021; Huson & Oliver, 2017) and protozoa. The need for integrated and sustainable control strategies specifically adapted to the grazing environment is highlighted to reduce the economic impact and maintain animal welfare (Forbes, 2023; Takeuchi-Storm et al., 2019).

Keywords: cattle, extensive system, endoparasites, prevalence, natural pasture
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INTRODUCTION

Extensive cattle farming, although it does provide benefits regarding the animal welfare and the access to pasture, exposes the herd to a complex interaction with pathogens present in the environment. Endoparasites represent a major barrier to zootechnical efficiency, causing subclinical losses, and in severe cases, morbidity and mortality. Unlike the intensive systems, extensive management requires a deep understanding of the biological cycles of parasites and the dynamics of pasture contamination, especially in the context of recent climate change.

This type of cattle farming is based on the use of natural pasture resources, which constitutes an essential component of sustainable European agriculture. However, the constant interaction between the host and the environment on grazing surfaces favors the life cycles of endoparasites (Fox et al., 2013). Subclinical infestations, although often overlooked, can lead to significant economic losses by reducing weight gain, decreased milk production and affecting reproductive efficiency (Beesley et al., 2018).

Parasitic infestations in cattle kept in extensive systems are often polyparasitic (Chihai, 2006), with a pronounced seasonal variation dictated by environmental conditions that favor the survival of eggs and larvae on pasture (Kemper & Henze, 2009).

Gastrointestinal nematodes (G.I.N) are the most widespread problem, with high prevalences, especially at young animals on their first grazing (Shaw et al., 1998). *Ostertagia ostertagi* is the key pathogen, whose dynamics are closely linked to pasture management (Almería & Uriarte, 1999). Studies from Serbia (Kulišić et al., 2012) and from the Balkan region (Radev et al., 1994) confirm this high prevalence.

Data on the seasonal dynamics of pasture contamination with gastrointestinal nematode eggs over a calendar year in European extensive systems show that during the winter periods (January-February), contamination levels are minimal, usually ranging between 50 and 100 eggs per gram of faeces (EGF), due to reduced transmission and low survival of larvae in the environment. As spring approaches (March-April), levels remain relatively low, with a slight increase to 100-200 EGF as the animal resume grazing. A moderate increase in contamination takes place at the end of spring and beginning of summer (May-June), reaching to 200-500 EGF, as the optimal temperature and humidity conditions favor larval development on pastures. Summer (July-August) is the peak period of contamination, where levels can exceed 800 or even 1000+ EGF, indicating a maximum risk of infestation (Charlier et al., 2020). Towards autumn (September-October), with decreasing temperatures, EGF levels drop rapidly to around 300-400, and early winter (November-December), the concentration

returns to a low level, around 100-150 EGF.(Charlier et al., 2020 și Shaw et al., 1998).

Nematodirus spp is positively correlated with prevalence of other strongyloides; predominantly affects young adults.

Bunostomum spp. Presents higher prevalence in subtropical/tropical regions.

Strongyloides spp. it may reach higher prevalences (up to 42%) in conditions of poor hygiene or high humidity.

Trichuris spp. generally considered a low prevalence parasite in cattle populations, although it may be more common in sheep.

Lungworms infestation (Dictyocaulus viviparus), generally has a moderate-low prevalence comparated to Gastrointestinal nematodes, and can cause severe clinical outbreaks, especially among young cattle (Schnieder et al., 1993), which are much more susceptible to infestation than adults (Charlier et al., 2020).

Trematodes present a dynamic dependent on the presence of intermediate hosts (snails). Fasciola hepatica requires specific wet habitats, and its prevalence varies dramatically between humid and arid regions (Beesley et al., 2018).

Calicophoron daubneyi is recognized as an emerging parasite in Europe, with an increasing prevalence that requires careful monitoring (Huson & Oliver, 2017). Studies from Romania have confirmed the presence of both trematode species in cattle in extensive systems (Sîrbu et al., 2020).

Cestodes prevalence depends on access to the intermediate host (mite) and reaches a peak in late summer/early autumn in young individuals.

Coccidian (Eimeria spp.) predominantly affect calves. They do not have developed immunity and, although adults are resistant to the harmful effects, can act as carriers, continuously contaminating the pasture and farrowing area (Chihai, 2006). In case of coccidial infestation, diarrhea and growth retardation can appear, although subclinical infestations are also common in adults (Gillandt et al., 2018; Morgoglione et al., 2020; Pinto et al., 2021). Prevalence is higher in humid areas and with high precipitation, as these are favorable conditions for the survival of Eimeria (Forstmaier et al., 2021).

Table 1

Frequency of the main endoparasites in cattle raised in an extensive system

Classification	Parasitic agent	Prevalence (%) (estimated range)	Bibliographical sources
G.I. Nematodes	Trichostrongyloidea (<i>Ostertagia</i> , <i>Cooperia</i> , <i>Haemonchus</i> , etc.)	Very common (>70%, often >90%).	(Charlier et al., 2020; Gillandt et al., 2018; Njok et al., 2023; Alemayehu et al., 2022)
G.I. Nematodes	Nematodirus spp.	Variable (5–20% depending on study).	(Shaw et al., 1998; Njok et al., 2023)
G.I. Nematodes	Bunostomum spp.	Low in temperate Europe (often <10%).	(Sîrbu et al., 2020; Njok et al., 2023)
G.I. Nematodes	Strongyloides spp.	Low to moderate (5–15% in Europe).	(Gillandt et al., 2018; Sîrbu et al., 2020; Alemayehu et al., 2022)
G.I. Nematodes	Trichuris spp.	Low (often <10%).	(Gillandt et al., 2018; Alemayehu et al., 2022)
Pulmonar Nematodes	Dictyocaulus viviparus	5% – 20%	(Schnieder et al., 1993)
Hepatic Trematodes	Fasciola hepatica (<i>Fasciolosis</i>)	Variable (20–60% in endemic areas).	(Beesley et al., 2018; Forstmaier et al., 2021; Sîrbu et al., 2020)
Ruminal Trematodes	Calicophoron/Paramphistomum spp.	Increasing (10–50%).	(Huson et al., 2017; Forstmaier et al., 2021; Njok et al., 2023)
Cestodes	Moniezia spp.	Variable (5–30%).	(Pilarczyk et al., 2019; Alemayehu et al., 2022)
Coccidia	Eimeria spp.	30% – 70% (calves)	(Morgoglione et al., 2020; Pinto et al., 2021; Pilarczyk et al., 2019)

Risk factors and management

Extensive systems require proactive management of parasitic risk.

Key factors include:

Animal density and pasture rotation: holistic management and rotational grazing can reduce parasite burden by interrupting the parasite life cycle on the pasture. The effectiveness of these methods is superior compared to conventional systems (Silva et al., 2013).

Agro-climatic conditions: Areas with high humidity and moderate temperatures favor the survival of NGI larvae and snail hosts for trematodes (Morgan et al., 2013; May et al., 2022).

Age and host immunity: Adult animals develop partial immunity, while the young are most vulnerable (Charlier et al., 2020; Fox et al., 2013).

Table 2

Risk factors associated with the prevalence of endoparasites in extensive systems and mitigation measures

Risk factor	Impact on parasitic transmission	Mitigation strategies (Management)
Continuous grazing	Maintains a high parasite load on pastures	Pasture rotation (Rapiya et al., 2019).
Climatic conditions	Optimal humidity and temperatures favor larvae/eggs	Avoiding grazing in permanently wet areas (Kemper & Henze, 2009).
Animals age	Youth are more susceptible due to lack of immunity	Separation of age groups on different pastures
Lack of monitoring	Unjustified use or lack of treatments	Regular stool monitoring (Takeuchi-Storm et al., 2019).

Integrated control requires combining management practices (avoiding overgrazing, drainin wet lands) with strategic antiparasitic treatments, avoiding the development of

resistance as much as possible (Takeuchi-Storm et al., 2019). Continuous monitoring, as practiced in field studies (Gillandt et al., 2018), is essential.

CONCLUSIONS

Endoparasites remain a major challenge in cattle farming in extensive systems. The high prevalence of gastrointestinal nematodes and the emergence of ruminal trematodes such as *Calicophoron daubneyi*, stresses the need for continued vigilance and control strategies that do not only rely exclusively on chemical treatments but to be based on knowledge of the local ecology (Huson & Oliver, 2017), pasture

rotation and avoidance of risk areas (Takeuchi-Storm et al., 2019).

Regular monitoring and understanding seasonal dynamics are essential to ensure the health and productivity of cattle herds in these production systems.

The future of parasite management in extensive systems will depend on the integration of new epidemiological knowledge with sustainable agricultural practices.

REFERENCES

- Alemayehu, A. M., Eshete, D., Bezie, M. B., & Mekonnen, M. M., 2022. Prevalence of gastrointestinal parasites in cattle in and around Finoteselam town, Amhara region, Ethiopia. *Heliyon*, 8(8), e10243.
- Almeria, S.; Uriarte, J. Dynamics of pasture contamination by gastrointestinal nematodes of cattle under extensive management systems: Proposal for strategic control. *Vet. Parasitol.* 1999, 83, 37.
- Beesley N.J., Caminade C., Charlier J., Flynn R.J., Hodgkinson J.E., Martinez-Moreno A., Martinez-Valladares M., Perez J., Rinaldi L., Williams D.J.L. Fasciola and Fasciolosis in Ruminants in Europe: Identifying Research Needs. *Transbound. Emerg. Dis.* 2018;65:199–216.
- Charlier J., Höglund J., Morgan E.R., Geldhof P., Vercruyssen J., Claerebout E. Biology and Epidemiology of Gastrointestinal Nematodes in Cattle. *Vet. Clin. N. Am. Food Anim. Pract.* 2020;36:1–15.
- Chihai O. Cattle polyparasitism in different regions of the Republic of Moldova. *Buletin USAMV – CN* 2006; 63: 217-221.
- Forbes, A. The future of farm animal parasitology. *Vet. J.* 2023, 300–302, 106042.
- Forstmaier, T.; Knubben-Schweizer, G.; Strube, C.; Zablotski, Y.; Wenzel, C. Rumen (*Calicophoron/Paramphistomum* spp.) and liver flukes (*Fasciola hepatica*) in cattle—Prevalence, distribution, and impact of management factors in Germany. *Animals* 2021, 11, 2727.

-
- Fox, N.J.; Marion, G.; Davidson, R.S.; White, P.C.L.; Hutchings, M.R. Modelling parasite transmission in a grazing system: The importance of host behaviour and immunity. *PLoS ONE* 2013, 8, e77996.
- Gillandt, K.; Stracke, J.; Hohnholz, T.; Waßmuth, R.; Kemper, N. A field study on the prevalence of and risk factors for endoparasites in beef suckler cow herds in Germany. *Agriculture* 2018, 8, 132.
- Huson K.M., Oliver N.A.M., Robinson M.W. Paramphistomosis of Ruminants: An Emerging Parasitic Disease in Europe. *Trends Parasitol.* 2017;33:836–844.
- Kemper, N.; Henze, C. Effects of pasture's re-wetting on endoparasites in cattle in northern Germany. *Vet. Parasitol.* 2009, 161, 302–306.
- Kulišić Z, Aleksić Nevenka, Đorđević M, Gajić B, Tambur Z, Stevanović Jevrosima and Stanimirović Z. Prevalence of gastrointestinal helminths in calves in western Serbia. *Acta Veterinaria (Beograd)* 2012; 62 (5-6): 665-673.
- May K., Raue K., Blazejak K., Jordan D., Strube C. Pasture Rewetting in the Context of Nature Conservation Shows No Long-Term Impact on Endoparasite Infections in Sheep and Cattle. *Parasites Vectors.* 2022;15:33.
- Morgan, E.R.; Charlier, J.; Hendrickx, G.; Biggeri, A.; Catalan, D.; Von Samson-Himmelstjerna, G.; Demeler, J.; Müller, E.; Van Dijk, J.; Kenyon, F. Global Change and Helminth Infections in Grazing Ruminants in Europe: Impacts, Trends and Sustainable Solutions. *Agriculture* 2013, 3, 484–502.
- Morgoglione M.E., Bosco A., Maurelli M.P., Alves L.C., Saralli G., Bruni G., Cringoli G., Rinaldi L. A 10-Year Surveillance of *Eimeria* Spp. in Cattle and Buffaloes in a Mediterranean Area. *Front. Vet. Sci.* 2020;7:410.
- Njok, H. A., Chibuzor-Oji, M. S., & Opara, K. N., 2023. Prevalence and intensity of gastrointestinal nematodes in cattle in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), 1856.
- Pilarczyk, B.; Tomza-Marciniak, A.; Sablik, P.; Pilarczyk, R. Parasites of the digestive tract in cows managed in alternative (organic and biodynamic) as well as conventional farms in West Pomerania. *Ann. Parasitol.* 2019, 65, 387–396.
- Pinto A., May K., Yin T., Reichenbach M., Malik P.K., Roessler R., Schlecht E., König S. Gastrointestinal Nematode and *Eimeria* Spp. Infections in Dairy Cattle along a Rural-Urban Gradient. *Vet. Parasitol. Reg. Stud. Rep.* 2021;25:100600.
- Radev V, Sabev P, Kamenov Y, Kanchev K, Kostova T. Dynamics of gastrointestinal parasite invasion in small ruminants and cattle bred in hilly regions of Central North Bulgaria. *Sbornik.*
- Rapiya, M.; Hawkins, H.-J.; Muchenje, V.; Mupangwa, J.; Marufu, M.C.; Dzama, K.; Mapiye, C. Rotational grazing approaches reduces external and internal parasite loads in cattle. *Afr. J. Range Forage Sci.* 2019, 36, 151–159.
- Reinecke RK. Parasitic control in intensive vs. non-intensive system ruminants. *Veterinary Parasitology* 1994; 54 (1-3): 49-67.
- Schnieder, T.; Bellmer, A.; Tenter, A.M. Seroepidemiological study on *Dictyocaulus viviparus* infections of first grazing cattle in Northern Germany. *Vet. Parasitol.* 1993, 47, 289–300.
- Shaw, D.J.; Vercruyssen, J.; Claerebout, E.; Dorny, P. Gastrointestinal nematode infections of first-grazing season calves in Western Europe: General patterns and the effect of chemoprophylaxis. *Vet. Parasitol.* 1998,75, 115–131.
- Silva, J.B.; Fagundes, G.M.; Soares, J.P.G.; Fonseca, A.H. Parasitism level by helminths and weight gain of calves kept in organic and conventional grazing. *Braz. J. Vet. Res.* 2013, 33, 586–590.
- Sîrbu, C.B.; Imre, K.; Dărăbuş, G.; Suici, T.; Mates, B.; Morariu, S. Prevalence of gastrointestinal parasitic infections in cattle and sheep in two regions of Romania. *Turk. J. Vet. Anim. Sci.* 2020, 44, 581–587.
- Takeuchi-Storm, N.; Moakes, S.; Thüer, S.; Grovermann, C.; Verwer, C.; Verkaik, J.; Knubben-Schweizer, G.; Höglund, J.; Petkevičius, S.; Thamsborg, S.; et al. Parasite control in organic cattle farming: Management and farmers' perspectives from six European countries. *Vet. Parasitol. Reg. Stud. Reports.* 2019, 18, 100329.

STUDY OF THE EGGS LAYING PERFORMANCE OF THE PHASIANUS COLCHICUS SPECIES IN THE PEDOCLIMATIC CONDITIONS OF BIHOR COUNTY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

In Bihor County, there are small populations of pheasants in the farms of breeders of purebred birds. These farmers appreciate the special quality of the meat, which is tender and juicy, but also the value of these birds as exhibition specimens. The County Forestry Directorate also owns a number of pheasant farms where young are obtained for the continuous population of forest areas.

Three farms were studied to identify the valuable resources that exist in these populations, with a number of 30 males and 173 females being analyzed.

Keywords: Dynamics of the incubation eggs, Dynamics of the eggs weight in the studied farms females, Dynamics of eggshell thickness, during laying period, Average laying intensity in the 3 studied pheasant populations

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INTRODUCTION

The species originated from the Asian continent, but is widespread throughout Europe, both in the natural environment, in hilly and lowland areas, but also in specialized farms, intended for meat production or for reuniting hunting herds.

This study only includes data collected from private breeders.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In the three farms studied, 203 individuals were studied, of which 30 were males and 173 were females.

The individuals of the species *Phasianus colchicus colchicus* are distributed as follows: 56 female pheasants and 8 male pheasants, respectively 64 individuals in the first farm, 60 female pheasants and 8 male pheasants, respectively 68 individuals in the second farm and 64 female pheasants and 7 male pheasants, representing 71 birds in the third farm.

To carry out the research, the following equipment was used: digital analytical and technical balances, photogrammetry devices, and a computer equipped with spreadsheet software, depending on the experimental method used.

The results obtained were compared with reference values from the literature. (Sauveur B., 1988; Usturoi M.G., 1999; Vacaru-Opriş I. și col., 2002).

The experimental data obtained from the research were centralized and statistically processed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Egg weight measurements gave average values of 28.9 ± 1.0 g at the beginning of laying, 31.0 ± 1.1 g at the peak of laying, 31.4 ± 1.4 g in the plateau phase, and 32.1g towards the end of the laying cycle.

The measured values were within the requirements specified in the literature (29-35 g) for the appropriate weight of hatching eggs (Fig. 1).

The thickness of the mineral shell had a decreasing dynamic, from the beginning to the end of the laying period (Fig. 2).

Average values for this character were measured, 0.415 ± 0.013 mm at the beginning of laying, 0.404 ± 0.007 mm at the peak of laying, finally reaching an average thickness of the mineral shell of 0.375 ± 0.008 mm, under conditions in which the uniformity of the populations was also average ($v=9.8-10.4\%$).

For the format index, the values ranged from 74.0-74.8% and the uniformity of the populations was good to average ($v=8.8-10.6\%$) (fig3).

The Haugh index showed a greater amplitude of variation, the minimum value being recorded at the beginning of laying ($76.1\pm 0.9UH$) and the maximum at the end of

laying ($84.9\pm 1.3\%$). The populations showed an average homogeneity for the studied character ($v=12.5-12.9\%$) (fig4). Overall, the values approached the standard average (77 U.H.)

Fig. 1. Dynamics of the eggs weight, in the studied farms females

Fig. 2. - Dynamics of eggshell thickness, during laying period, in the pheasant females from the 3 studied populations

Fig. 3 - Dynamics of shape index, during laying period, in the pheasant females from the 3 studied populations

Fig. 4 - Dynamics of Haugh index, during laying period, in the pheasant females from the 3 studied populations

CONCLUSION

The prospects for increasing the number of common pheasants hunting flocks in private farms are uncertain, especially since most of the existing flock is kept strictly under control by state pheasant farms, which produce most of the biological material necessary to repopulate the hunting fund.

The study conducted determined a selection of valuable males to be used to increase the fertility rate in other similar populations.

Paternal lines are introduced into the breeding process because they generate genetic progress in terms of growth rate (quite low in the studied populations), superior feed utilization and some carcass quality elements (live weight, sensory quality of meat, etc.), and

maternal lines must be selected for numerical egg production (Dodu M., 2010).

REFERENCES

- Bălășescu, M., Băltan, Gh., Dascălu, AL., Vancea, I., 1980. Avicultură. Ed. Didactică și Pedagogică, București
- Dodgson, J.B., 2000. Integrating quantitative and molecular techniques in selection for diseases resistance. XXI World's Poultry Congress, Montréal, Canada, Aug. 20-24.
- Dodu, M., 2010. Contribuții la indentificarea și dezvoltarea fondului genetic aviar din județul Bihor. Teză de doctorat, USAMV Iași.
- Driha, A., 2000. Curs de Tehnologia creșterii păsărilor. Editura Mirton, Timișoara
- Gîlcă, I., 1996. Aprecierea valorii de ameliorare a animalelor, Ed. Periscop, Iași
- Grosu, H., Oltenacu, P.A., 2005. Programe de ameliorare genetică în zootehnie. Ed. Ceres, București

-
- Mallard, J., Donaire, M., 1990. Evaluation de la selection. C.R. Acad. Agric. Fr. 76, 6 81-91
- Mărgărint, I., Boișteanu, P.C., Chelaru, A., 2002. Fiziologia animalelor domestice, Ed. Ion Ionescu de la Brad, Iași
- Oroian, T.E., Vlaic, A., 2001. Ameliorarea genetică a populațiilor de animale domestice, Ed. Academic Press, Cluj- Napoca
- Popescu-Vifor, Șt., 1990. Genetică populațiilor de animale domestice. Editura Ceres, București.
- Sandu, Gh., 1995. Modele experimentale în zootehnie, Ed. Coral-Sanivet, București
- Țîrlea, S., 1995. Considerații privind producerea și difuzarea materialului biologic avicol în România. Simpozionul Științific Național „Dezvoltarea zootehniei-o certitudine pentru viitor”, Iași
- Usturoi, M.G., 2008. Creșterea păsărilor. Editura Ion Ionescu de la Brad, Iași
- Usturoi, M.G., 1999. Incubația la păsările domestice, Ed. Ion Ionescu de la Brad, Iași.
- Usturoi, M.G., 2004. Producerea ouălor de consum, Ed. Ion Ionescu de la Brad, Iași.
- Usturoi, M.G., Boișteanu, P.C., Vacaru-Opriș, I., 1999. Indici de calitate pentru ouăle de prepeliță destinate incubației artificiale. Simpozion Științific de Zootehnie cu participare internațională, Iași 9-10 decembrie
- Vacaru-Opriș, I., 1993. Tehnologia creșterii păsărilor. Vol I și II. Lito, Universitatea Agronomică, Iași.
- Vacaru-Opriș, I., 2000, 2007. Tratat de Avicultură. Vol I. Editura Ceres, București.
- Vacaru-Opriș, I., 2002, Tratat de Avicultură..Vol II. Editura Ceres, București

ASPECTS REGARDING THE HALOPHILOUS VEGETATION FROM THE SALONTEI PLAIN - *CAMPHOROSMETUM ANNUAE* RAPAICS EX SOÓ 1933 -

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This work represents a phytocoenological study of the halophilic association *Camphorosmetum annuae* Rapaics ex Soó 1933, which is classified from the coenotaxonomic point of view in the class *Puccinellio-Salicornietea* Țopa 1939.

In the studied region, the phytocenoses of this association were identified on the edge of the roads that cross the meadows in the vicinity of the Ciumeghiu locality. It settles in salt marshes with higher salinity, forming a dwarf vegetation with a gray, reddish appearance during the summer.

Camphorosmetum annuae association, was analyzed in terms of floristic composition, life forms, floristic elements, ecological indices and karyotype.

Keywords: environment. phytocenoses, halophilous vegetation, floristic composition, ecological indices.

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INTRODUCTION

Chorology: the phytocoenosis of this association were mentioned in our country from Muntenia (Șerbănescu, 1965; Sanda et Popescu, 1984; Sanda et al., 1978; Popescu et al., 1984); Crișana (Pop, 1959, 1968); Moldova (Țopa, 1939); Banat (Coste et al., 1993).

This study aims to analyze the phytocoenoses of the *Camphorosmetum annuae* association, from the point of view of the floristic composition, and by analyzing the floristic elements, life forms, ecological indices and karyotype.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Framing the association to the corresponding cenotaxonomic units - alliance, order and class was made according to the traditional ecological and floristic systems elaborated by Tüxen (1955), Braun-Blanquet (1964), Borza et Boșcaiu (1965), Soó (1964-1980), as well as on the basis of the most recent works belonging to Mucina (1997), Rothmaler (1994, 2000), Borhidi (1996, 2003), Coldea et al. (1997); Sanda et al. (2008).

The study of the halophilic vegetation of the grasslands from the lower basin of Crișul Negru River was made taking into consideration the phytosociological research method of the European Central School, based on the principles and methods elaborated by Braun-Blanquet (1964) and adapted by Borza and

Boșcaiu (1965) to the particularities of the vegetation carpet from our country.

The taxa identified in the field have been recognized by specialty catalogues "Romania's Illustrated Flora" (Ciocârlan, 2009), in conjunction with the information provided by the "International Code of Botanical Nomenclature" (Code de Tokyo, 1993).

The association synthetic table was structured after the methodology proposed by Braun-Blanquet (1964) and developed by Ellenberg (1974); therefore, in the column header of the table for the association analyzed the following have been entered: the serial number of land surveys, altitude (m.s.m.), area (m²), coverage of grass layer (%). At the end of the table, the last two columns included the synthetic phytocoenological indices, constancy (K) and abundance-dominance index (ADm).

The constancy highlights the extent of coenotic fidelity of each species to the phytocoenosis environment of the association, according to the Braun-Blanquet et Pavillard methodology (1928). The abundance and dominance highlight the percentage of average coverage achieved by phyto-individuals of a phytocoenosis.

Establishment of the values for ecological indices, life forms, floristic elements and karyotype were made after the synthesis works elaborated by Raunkiær (1937), Braun-Blanquet (1951), Meusel et Jäger (1992), Ellenberg (1974), Ellenberg et al. (1992), Soó

(1964-1980), Májovsky et Murin (1987), Pop (1982), Ciocârlan (2009).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Camphorosmetum annuae phytocenoses develop in microdepressions with excess moisture in spring and severe dryness in summer. They develop on compact, arid, highly saline solonets, on bare, eroded land surfaces with visible salt crusts, occupying areas of 8–15 m² (Figure 1).

Figure 1 *Camphorosmetum annuae* (Ciumeghiu locality)

The edifying species is *Camphorosma annua*, accompanied by *Plantago maritima*, *Lepidium ruderales*, *Puccinellia limosa*, *Pulicaria*

vulgaris, *Polygonum aviculare*, etc., halophilic species that subordinate the association to the *Puccinellion limosae* alliance, *Puccinellietalia limosae* order and *Puccinellio-Salicornietea* class.

Within these phytocenoses, transgressive species belonging to the *Festuco-Brometea* class also penetrate: *Trifolium campestre*, *Achillea pannonica*, *Euphorbia cyparissias* (Table 1).

The life forms spectrum (Figure 2) illustrates the close values of annual therophytes (53.84%) and hemicryptophytes (46.16%).

Figure 2 Life forms spectrum of *Camphorosmetum annuae* association, where: H – hemicryptophytes, Th – annual therophytes

Table 1

Camphorosmetum annuae Rapaics ex Soó 1933

L. f.	F. e.	W	T	Sr.	2n	No. Land Surveys	1	2	3
						Altitude (m.s.m.)	92	92	92
						Area (m ²)	8	15	10
						Coverage of grass layer (%)	70	90	70
Th	Ppn	2	4	5	D	<i>As. Camphorosma annua</i>	4	5	4
						<i>Puccinellion limosae, Puccinellietalia limosae, Puccinellio-Salicornietea</i>			
H	Eua(M)	4	0	5	D	<i>Plantago maritima</i>	1	+	1
Th-TH	Eua	2	3,5	0	P	<i>Lepidium ruderales</i>	+	.	+
H	Pn	3,5	0	5	P	<i>Puccinellia limosa</i>	+	.	+
Th	Eua(M)	4	3	3	D	<i>Pulicaria vulgaris</i>	+	.	.
Th	Cosm	2,5	0	3	P	<i>Polygonum aviculare</i>	+	.	.
Th(TH)	Eua	2	0	4	D	<i>Scorzonera laciniata</i>	.	+	.
H	Eua(C)	2	3	5	D	<i>Achillea setacea</i>	.	+	.
						<i>Festuco-Brometea</i>			
Th-TH	E	3	3	0	D	<i>Trifolium campestre</i>	.	+	.
H	Ec	2	4	3,5	P	<i>Achillea pannonica</i>	+	.	.
H	Eua	2	3	4	DP	<i>Euphorbia cyparissias</i>	+	.	.
						<i>Variae syntaxa</i>			
Th	Eua(M)	3	3,5	0	D	<i>Matricaria recutita</i>	.	+	.
H	Eua	3	0	0	P	<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	.	+	+

Phytocoenological table of *Camphorosmetum annuae* association, where: L. f. - life forms; F. e. - floristic elements; W - soil wet; T - temperature; S. r. - chemical reaction of the soil; 2n - karyotype; Th – Annual Therophytes; H – Hemicryptophytes; G – Geophytes; Ppn – Ponto-Pannonian; Eua – Eurasian; Cosm – Cosmopolitan; E – European; Ec – Central European; D – diploidy, P – polyploidy, DP – diplo-polyploidy.

Place and date of surveys: 1 – 3 Ciumeghiu locality (Bihor County).

The spectrum of floristic elements indicates the dominance of Eurasian species

(61.53%), followed at a great distance by cosmopolitan, European, Pannonian, Ponto-

Pannonian and Central European, each with a share of 7.69% (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Floristic elements spectrum of the *Camphorosmetum annuae* association, where: Eua – Eurasian, Cosm – Cosmopolitan, Pn – Pannonian, E – European, Ppn – Ponto-Pannonian, Ec – Central European

The ecological index diagram (Figure 4) indicates that, in terms of moisture requirements, xeromesophilic species are dominant (53.84%), followed by mesophilic ones (30.76%). Depending on the temperature, the higher share is held by micro-mesothermic species (45.76%), respectively eurithermal ones (38.46%). The chemical reaction of the soil favors the development of neutro-basiphilic and euryionic species, each having 30.76%.

Figure 4 – Diagram of ecological indices for the *Camphorosmetum annuae* association, where: W – soil wet, T – temperature, S. r. – chemical reaction of the soil

The karyotype spectrum (Figure 5) illustrates the dominance of diploid species (53.84%), followed by polyploids (38.46%) and diplo-polyplod (7.69%). The diploidy index has a value of 1.39.

Figure 5 Karyotype spectrum of *Camphorosmetum annuae* association, where: D – diploidy, P – polyploidy, DP – diplo-polyplod

CONCLUSIONS

Camphorosmetum annuae is a halophilic association, being an excellent indicator for authentic saline soils with natural hydrology and preserving specialized, rare or regionally endemic floristic elements, the vegetation is generally sparse and poor in species, dominated by halophytes adapted to salt and water stress.

Camphorosmetum annuae is a highly specialized relict plant community, in an accelerated process of extinction due to anthropogenic changes to saline soils. Its survival depends on the strict conservation of the small remaining fragments and the protection of the hydrological regime and salinity. In many areas of Western and Northwestern Romania, the association is much degraded, replaced by *Festucion pseudovinae* phytocenoses or other mesophilic communities if the soil is improved.

Also, the west pontic communities with *Camphorosma annua*, *Plantago maritima*, *Puccinellia limosa*, *Scorzonera laciniata*, *Achillea panonica*, have a very high conservation and ecoprotective value, as they define rare, endangered, even degraded natural ecosystems that need to be protected.

REFERENCES

- Borhidi A., 1996, Critical revision of the Hungarian plant communities. Janus Pannonius University, Pécs.
- Borhidi A., 2003, Magyarország növénytársulásai. Akadémiai Kiadó, Budapest.
- Borza A., Boşcaiu, N., 1965, Introducere în studiul covorului vegetal, Editura Academiei R. P. Române, Bucureşti. 511.
- Braun-Blanquet J., 1951, Pflanzensoziologie, Grundzüge der Vegetationskunde, 2nd edition, Springer Verlag, Wien.
- Braun-Blanquet J., 1964, Pflanzensoziologie, Ed. III. Springer-Verlag, Wien-NY.
- Braun-Blanquet J., Pavillard, J., 1928, Vocabulaire de sociologie végétale. Ed. III. Imprimerie Roumegous & Dehan, Montpellier.

-
- Ciocârlan V., 2009, Flora ilustrată a României. Pteridophyta et Spermatophyta, Edit. Ceres, București, 1138 p.
- Coldea G., Sanda, V., Popescu, A., Ștefan, N., 1997, Les associations végétales de Roumanie. Tome 1. Les associations herbaces naturelles. Presses Universitaires de Cluj, Cluj-Napoca.
- Coste I., Pop, A., Rusu, I., Avrămuț, O., 1993, Vegetația mezoxerofilă de pe solurile sărăturate din sud-vestul României (Banat). Studii și Cerc. De Biol. Veget. 45(2):207-217.
- Ellenberg H., 1974, Zeigerwerte der Gefäßpflanzen Mitteleuropas - Scripta Geobotanica, Göttingen, 9:1-97.
- Ellenberg H., Weber, E. H., Düll, R., Wirth, V., Werner, W., Paulissen, D., 1992, Zeigerwerte von Pflanzen in Mitteleuropa. Scripta Geobotanica, 2 Aufl. E. Goltze Verlag, Göttingen.
- Májovsky J., Murin, A., 1987, Karyotaxonomický prehl'ad flóry Slovenska. Veda vydavateľ'stvo, Slovenskaj Académie Vied, Bratislava.
- Meusel H., Jäger, E., 1992, Vergleichenden Chronologie der Zentraleuropäischen Flora, III, Gustav Fischer Verlag, Jena.
- Mucina L. 1997, Conspectus of Classes of European Vegetation, Folia Geobot. Phytotax, Praha, 32:117-172.
- Pop I., 1959, Cercetări geobotanice asupra pășunilor și fânețelor de pe terenurile sărăturoase de la Salonta (regiunea Oradea). Studii și Cercetări de Biologie, Cluj, 10(1): 75-99.
- Pop I., 1968, Flora și vegetația Câmpiei Crișurilor. Interfluviul Crișul Negru – Crișul Repede. Editura Academiei R.S.R., București.
- Pop, I., 1982, Plante spontane și subsponane cu valoare economică din flora R. S. România. Contrib. Bot., Cluj-Napoca: 131-142.
- Popescu, A., Sanda, V., Doltu, M., I., Nedelcu, G., A., 1984, Vegetația Câmpiei Munteniei. Studii și Comunicări. Șt. Nat., Muzeul Brukenthal Sibiu, 26: 173-241, 369-511.
- Raunkiær C., 1937, Life-form, genus area, and number of species. Botaniske Studier, 5. Hæfte (ed. C. Raunkiær), pp. 343-356. J. H. Schultz Forlag, København.
- Rothmaler, W., 1994, Exkursionsflora von Deutschland-Band 48 Anflage, Gustav Fischer Verlag Jena-Stuttgart.
- Rothmaler, W., 2000, Exkursionsflora von Deutschland, Band 3. Gefäßpflanzen: Atlasband. Spektrum Akademischer Verlag Heidelberg-Berlin.
- Sanda V., Popescu, A., Cerchez, L., Paucă-Comănescu, M., Tăcină, A., 1978, Contribuții la cunoașterea vegetației de pe terenurile sărăturoase din bazinul superior al Călmățuiului (Jud. Buzău). Contrib. Botanice, Cluj-Napoca: 251-263.
- Sanda V., Popescu, A., 1984, Structura unor fitocenoze de pe terenurile halofile din Câmpia Brăilei. Contrib. Bot. Cluj-Napoca: 155-167.
- Sanda V., Öllerer, K., Burescu, P., 2008, Fitocenozele din România. Sintaxonomie, structură, dinamică și evoluție. Editura ARS Docendi, Universitatea din București.
- Soó, R., 1964-1980, A magyar flóra és vegetáció rendszertani, növényföldrajzi kézikönyve, Akad. Kiadó, Budapest: 1-6.
- Șerbănescu, I., 1965, Asociații halofile din Câmpia Română. Comit. Geol. Studii tehnice și econ. Seria C. Pedol., București, 15:1-149.
- Tüxen, R., 1955, Das System der Nordwestdeutschen Pflanzengesellschaften, Mitt. d. Flor. soz. Arbeit., N. Folge, 5:155-176.
- Țopa, E., 1939, Vegetația halofitelor din nordul României în legătură cu cea din restul țării. Bul. Fac. Ști., Cernăuți, 13:1-79.
- *** Code of Botanical Nomenclature (Tokyo, 1993). Boissiera, 49, Geneve, 1995: 1-85.

STUDIES ON THE EFFECT OF REPLACING SOYBEAN MEAL IN THE FEED OF SLOW-GROWING CHICKENS ON PRODUCTION PERFORMANCE

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The present work examined the effects of partial or total substitution of soybean meal (SBM) with white lupine meal (LM) in the diet of slow-growing broiler chickens, monitoring the main performance parameters, including body weight gain and feed conversion ratio. The experiment was carried out as a completely randomized experimental design consisting of three treatments, which involved a control diet consisting of corn - soybean meal (LC) and two experimental diets: L_{50} - in which proteins from SBM were replaced with LM in a proportion of 50% throughout the growing period and L_{100} - in which SBM was replaced with LM in a proportion of 100% throughout the growing period. Two types of feed were used, with different nutritional characteristics, corresponding to the age: grower (0-28 days) and finisher (29-63 days). Replacing SBM with LM in the diet of chickens by 50% (L_{50}) or 100% (L_{100}) resulted in a significant decrease in feed intake and growth rate (both $p < 0.01$), compared to chickens fed a standard diet based on corn and soybean meal (LC). In conclusion, although LM has nutritional characteristics close to those of SBM, partial or total replacement of SBM with LM in the diet of slow-growing broilers, especially in the first four weeks of growth, is not sustainable, as it negatively affects growth performance and feed use efficiency. Thus, from a practical point of view, the introduction of LM in the diet of slow-growing broilers in the first 4 weeks of growth is not recommended, and the optimal level of substitution of SBM with LM in the later stages of growth (from 4 weeks onwards) needs to be further studied.

Keywords: lupine meal, slow-growing chickens, performance parameters.

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INTRODUCTION

Feeding broiler chickens in intensive systems is dependent on soy sources and soy by-products, which have a high protein content (42-46%) with a good balance of essential amino acids that meets the nutritional requirements of chickens (Belayneh et al., 2025). The increasing requirements for these ingredients and their high price, impose the need to evaluate unconventional sources of protein with good biological value, which may be available locally, such as alkaloid-free white lupine beans (Vieira et al., 2023). Previous studies conducted by us have demonstrated that white lupine beans have a high protein content (36.6 - 38.2%) and fat (8.4-10.1%), with a good essential amino acid and fatty acid profile, similar to that of soybeans (Mierliță et al., 2018). Compared to soybeans, lupine beans do not come from genetically modified organisms (GMOs) and do not contain anti-nutritional substances, thus not requiring heat treatment before being used in animal feed.

The use of white lupine beans in broiler feed, in proportions of up to 60% (substitution

rate of proteins from soybean meal) has no negative effect on weight gain, feed conversion, carcass and meat quality (Mierliță and Popovici, 2013b). In other studies, it has been reported that the introduction of lupin beans in the diet of broiler chickens in proportions greater than 35% reduces their production performance (Roth-Maier and Paulics, 2003; Steinfeld et al., 2003); the negative influence of lupin being attributed to the high amount of NSP (non-starch polyglucosides).

Most studies have shown that lupin cannot completely replace soybean meal in the diet of chickens. Moschini et al., (2004) and Nalle et al., (2010) concluded that broilers, up to 21 days of age, cannot tolerate amounts greater than 200 g lupine/kg compound feed.

The use of lupine as the sole source of protein for raising broiler chickens (chickens and turkeys) is limited on the one hand by the biological value of the protein (modest content in methionine, lysine, tryptophan and threonine - Strakova et al., 2010, 2024), but also by the high content in NPA (non-starch polyglucosides) which negatively influence the digestion and utilization processes of the feed (Kocker et al., 2000; Brenes et al., 2002, 2003,

2005; Steinfeldt et al., 2003; Mieczkowska et al., 2005; Mierliță et al., 2013a, 2013b, 2015).

Consequently, in the research conducted, we followed the effect of partial or total substitution of soybean meal with alkaloid-free lupin beans in the feed of slow-growing broilers, on bioproductive performance and especially on weight gain and feed utilization.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The studies were conducted on unsexed Master Gray M dual-purpose hybrid chicks purchased at one day of age from a local commercial farm.

The experiment was conducted as a completely randomized experimental design consisting of three treatments, involving a control diet consisting of corn - soybean meal (LC) and two experimental diets: L₅₀ - in which the proteins from soybean meal were replaced with alkaloid-free white lupine meal in a proportion of 50% throughout the growing period and L₁₀₀ - in which the proteins from soybean meal were replaced with alkaloid-free

white lupine meal in a proportion of 100% throughout the growing period. In the phase feeding of the chicks, two types of combined feeds were used, with different nutritional characteristics, corresponding to the age: growing (0-28 days) and finishing (29-63 days). The broiler chickens were fed powdered (non-granulated) feeds, as their granulation was not possible. The structure of the compound feeds included: corn, triticale, soybean meal, sunflower meal and a vitamin-mineral premix. In the case of the experimental groups (L₅₀ and L₁₀₀) soybean meal was replaced by lupine, which was included in the structure of the compound feed in a proportion of 18% in the first growth phase and 13.0% in the finishing phase in the case of chickens in the L₅₀ group and 36.0% and 26.0% respectively in the chickens in the L₁₀₀ group (Table 1). The feeds obtained had the same nutritional characteristics calculated for all groups of broiler chickens, corresponding to the two phases (NRC, 1994).

Table 1

Composition of diets for slow-growing broilers in this study.

Item	1 - 28 day			29 - 63 day		
	LC	L ₅₀	L ₁₀₀	LC	L ₅₀	L ₁₀₀
Ingredient (%)						
Corn	50.50	44.75	38.50	56.00	52.00	48.00
Weat	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00
Soybean meal	27.50	13.75	-	20.00	10.00	-
Lupine	-	18.00	36.00	-	13.00	26.00
Sunflower meal	8.00	9.50	11.50	10.00	11.00	12.00
Vitamin-mineral premix	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00
Nutrient by calculation						
ME* (Kcal/kg)	3025	3000	2970	3150	3120	3095
Crude protein (%)	20.03	20.00	20.05	17.51	17.54	17.50

*ME, metabolizable energy.

In addition to the combined feeds, the following were also used: a vitamin drinkable solution (TraceOral) in the first 3 days after weaning (1 ml/l of drinking water); vaccines - Clone 30 (administered at 9 days of age), Gumboro 28E (administered at 13 days of age), Hipraviar S (administered at 22 days of age).

To evaluate the influence of substituting soybean meal with white lupine in the feed of slow-growing chicks, the following was monitored: the dynamics of body mass and weight gain by individually weighing the chicks every two weeks. In parallel, to assess the degree of feed utilization, the quantities of feed consumed were recorded and based on these,

the feed conversion ratio (g feed/g weight gain) was calculated.

The chemical composition of lupine grains was determined using standard procedures (AOAC, 2001) for dry matter (DM) content (gravimetric method); crude protein (CP) (N x 6.25; Kjeltex auto 1030; Tecator Instrumente, Sweden), EE (crude fat) by extraction in petroleum ether, following method 920.39 (SOXTERM, C. Gerhardt GmbH, Königswinter, Germany). The AMEn (Apparent Metabolizable Energy corrected for nitrogen balance) of lupin was estimated according to the relationship established by Sibbald:

$$\text{EMA}_n = 3951 + 54.4 \text{ EE} - 88.7 \text{ CB} - 40.8 \text{ Ca};$$

All chemical analyses were performed in triplicate.

The data obtained were subjected to analysis of variance using the ANOVA test, and multiple comparisons between mean values were made with the Tukey test. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Lupine grains (whole grains) had a high content of crude protein (35.21%), crude fat (10.58%) and crude fiber (13.72%) (Table 2). The high proportion of the grain shell is the main cause of the high crude fiber content, so removing the shell would significantly reduce the crude fiber content (Struți et al., 2021), making the nutritional content of lupin grains comparable to that of soybeans (Vecerek et al., 2008; Nalle, 2009, 2011).

Table 2

Chemical composition and energy value of lupine grains (% of DM)			
	Mean	Max.	Min.
Crude protein (CP)	35.21	40,90	31,93
Rther extract (EE)	10.58	13,27	9,59
Crude fiber (CB)	13.72	15,46	10,31
Nitrogen-Free Extract (N-FE)	23.81	26,51	20,38
Crude ash (Ca)	4.27	4,94	3,66
MEAn (kcal/kg) *	3135	3381	3056

*AMEn: Aparent Metabolizable Energy corrected for nitrogen balance

The average weights of the chicks in the experimental groups, in which lupine was used in the feed (groups L_{50} and L_{100}) were significantly lower ($p < 0.01$) at the age of 14, 28, 35, 42, 56 and 63 days, than in the control group (LC) (table 3). At the end of the experimental period, the broiler chicks in the experimental groups achieved average weights of 3288.96 g/head in the control group, 2913.13 g/head in the L_{50} group in which lupin proteins replaced 50% of the proteins provided by soybean meal and 2595.84 g/head in the group in which soybean meal was completely replaced by lupine (fig. 1). Some authors believe that this decrease in the average final weight of chickens fed large amounts of lupine is caused by the decrease in daily feed consumption, as a result of the high content of crude cellulose but also of non-starch polyglucosides (especially those soluble in water) (Suchý et al., 2006; Mierlita, 2015). Most studies have reported that white lupin grains can be introduced in a maximum amount of 20% in the feed of intensively raised broiler chickens without affecting growth performance and carcass and meat quality. However, studies on the use of lupine grains in the feed of slow-growing chickens are lacking, so comparisons cannot be made (Suchy et al., 2006; Nalle et al., 2012; Mierliță, 2015; Sedláková et al., 2015; Boguslaw, 2018).

In agreement with our results, Boguslaw (2018) found that the total replacement of

soybean meal with lupine in the feed of slow-growing chickens, at different ages, led to a decrease in final weight and an increase in the value of the feed conversion index.

In chickens that received white lupine in their feed, a decrease in average weight gain was observed, compared to the control group; the decreases being directly proportional to the proportion of white lupine introduced into the chicken feed. These differences were more pronounced in the first growth phase, when compared to the control group, the average weekly gains were lower in the experimental groups by up to 20% in the chickens in the L_{50} group and by up to 40% in the chickens in the L_{100} group, respectively. In the last weeks of the finishing period, the differences recorded between the chickens in the control group and those in the experimental groups were smaller. Thus, in the last week of the experimental period, compared to LC chicks, the average daily weight gain was lower by 11.7% in the L_{50} group and by 14.9% in the L_{100} group, respectively. All this suggests that chicks can better utilize white lupine grains after the age of four weeks.

Compared to the entire experimental period, it is noteworthy that the introduction of white lupine in the feed of slow-growing chicks had a negative influence on the average weight gain (fig. 1).

Table 3.

Productive performance in slow-growing broilers

Item	Wek	Groups			p-values
		LC	L50	L100	
Live weight (g)	initial	40.12	39.98	40.07	NS
	2w	274.48 ^a	242.28 ^b	210.45 ^c	***
	4w	778.20 ^a	644.78 ^b	511.73 ^c	***
	6w	1690.16 ^a	1441.80 ^b	1193.81 ^c	**
	8w	2715.24 ^a	2406.54 ^b	2107.59 ^c	***
	9w	3288.96 ^a	2913.13 ^b	2595.84 ^c	***
Average daily gain (g/day)	2w	16.74 ^a	14.45 ^b	12.17 ^c	**
	4w	35.98 ^a	28.75 ^b	21.52 ^c	**
	6w	65.14 ^a	56.93 ^b	48.72 ^c	*
	8w	73.22 ^a	68.91 ^b	65.27 ^b	*
	9w	81.96 ^a	72.37 ^{ab}	69.75 ^b	*
Feed intake (g/d)	2w	32.76	33.00	33.23	NS
	4w	82.44	79.64	77.07	NS
	6w	157.29 ^a	143.71 ^b	128.43 ^c	*
	8w	194.95 ^a	172.27 ^{ab}	154.91 ^b	**
	9w	233.81 ^a	212.72 ^b	196.18 ^b	**
Feed conversion ratio (g/g)	2w	1.957 ^c	2.283 ^b	2.730 ^a	***
	4w	2.291 ^c	2.770 ^b	3.581 ^a	***
	6w	2.514 ^b	2.524 ^{ab}	2.636 ^a	**
	8w	2.662 ^a	2.500 ^{ab}	2.373 ^b	**
	9w	2.852	2.939	2.813	NS

NS - $p > 0.05$; * - $p < 0.05$; ** - $p < 0.01$; *** - $p < 0.001$

From the data presented in Table 3, it can be seen that, in general, compared to the case of the control group (LC), feed consumption in the first two weeks of the experimental period did not register significant changes, but it registered a significant decrease, especially when lupine completely replaced soybean meal in the chicks' feed.

Compared to the entire experimental period, the average daily feed consumption in the experimental groups was lower by 8.45% in the L₅₀ group and by 15.85% in the L₁₀₀ group compared to the control group (fig. 1).

Partial or total replacement of soybean meal with lupine in the feed of slow-growing chicks led to an increase in the value of the feed conversion index, directly proportional to the share of white lupin in the structure of the combined feed. With advancing age, the differences found between the control group and the experimental groups decreased, probably due to the morpho-physiological adaptation of the digestive tract and the

increase in the digestibility of chemical compounds in lupine grains (Mierliță, 2015). Compared to the entire experimental period, the introduction of white lupine in the structure of the combined feed led to an increase in the value of the feed conversion index, the increase being directly proportional to the degree of replacement of soybean meal in the feed (fig. 1).

From the analysis of the main production indices, it results that the best bioproductive results were obtained by the chickens in the control group (LC) in whose feed only soybean meal was used as protein feed. The introduction of lupine in the feed of broiler chickens led to a decrease in growth rate and feed consumption with a negative impact on the value of the feed conversion index. The lowest bioproductive performances were recorded by chickens in whose feed soybean meal was completely replaced with white lupin.

Figure 1. Average production indices recorded over the entire experimental period (1 - 63 days) in slow-growing broilers (Master Gray M hybrid)

CONCLUSIONS

Replacing SBM with LM in a proportion of 50% (L₅₀) or 100% (L₁₀₀) in the diet of slow-growing, dual-use broilers resulted in a significant decrease in feed consumption and growth rate ($p < 0.01$), compared to chickens fed a standard diet based on corn and soybean meal (LC).

In conclusion, although LM has nutritional characteristics close to those of SBM, partial or total replacement of SBM with LM in the diet of slow-growing broilers, especially in the first four weeks of growth, is not sustainable, as it negatively affects growth performance and feed use efficiency. Thus, from a practical point of view, the introduction of LM in the diet of slow-growing broilers in the first 4 weeks of growth is not recommended, and the optimal level of substitution of SM with LM in the later stages of growth (from 4 weeks onwards) needs to be further studied.

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REFERENCES

- AOAC, 2001. Association of official analytical chemists international. Official Methods of Analysis, seventeenth ed. AOAC Inc., Arlington, USA.
- Belayneh, B., Yeshambel, M., Bimrew, A., 2025. Effect of substituting soybean meal with sweet lupine on the performance of Sasso T44 dual purpose chicken. *Scientific Reports*, 15:13997. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-98681-x>.
- Boguslaw, O., 2018. Feeding high lupine based diets for broiler chickens: Effect of soybean meal substitution with yellow lupine meal at various time points of growth cycle. *Livestock Science* 218, 114–118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.livsci.2018.10.017>.
- Brenes, A., Marquardt, R.R., Guenter, W. & Viveros, A., 2002. Effect of enzyme addition on the performance and gastrointestinal tract size of chicks fed lupin seed and their fractions. *Poultry Sci.* 81, 670–678.
- Brenes, A., Marquardt, R.R., Muzquiz, M., Guenter, W., Viveros, A. & Arija, I., 2005. Effect of enzyme addition on the nutritive value of six lupin cultivars

-
- with different alkaloid content. *Span. J. Agric. Res.* 3, 203–208.
- Brenes, A., Slominski, B.A., Marquardt, R.R., Guenter, W. & Viveros, A., 2003. Effect of enzyme addition on the digestibilities of cell wall polysaccharides and oligosaccharides from whole, dehulled, and ethanol-extracted white lupins in chickens. *Poult. Sci.* 82, 1716–1725.
- Kocher, A., Choct, M., Hughes, R.J. & Broz, J., 2000. Effect of food enzymes on utilisation of lupin carbohydrates by broilers. *Br Poult Sci*, 41: 75–82.
- Mieczkowska, A., Jansman, A.J.M., Kwakkel, R.P. & Smulikowska, S., 2005. Effect of dehulling and α -galactosidase supplement on the ileal digestibility of yellow lupin based diets in broiler chickens and adult roosters. *J. Anim. Feed Sci.*, 14(2): 297–304.
- Mierlița, D., Simeanu, D., Pop, I.M., Criste, F., Pop, C., Simeanu, C. & Lup, F., 2018. Chemical composition and nutritional evaluation of the lupine seeds (*Lupinus albus* L.) from low-alkaloid varieties. *Rev Chim. Feb*; 69(2):453-8.
- Mierlița, D., 2015. The effect of lupine seed in broiler diet on animal performance and fatty acids profile of their meat. *Anim Sci Biotech*, 72(2), 188-193.
- Mierlița, D., 2013a. Effect of partial substitution of soybean meal with lupine seeds in feeding laying hens on production and economic performance. *Anim. Sci. Biotechnol.* 70 (1), 127-139.
- Mierlița, D. & Popovici, D. 2013b. Effect of partial substitution of soybean meal with lupine seeds on growth and economic efficiency of broilers. *Lucrări Științifice-Seria Zootehnie*, 59: 60-65.
- Mierlița, D., 2014. The Effect of Replacement of Soybean Meal with Lupine Seed (*Lupinus albus* vr. Energy) on Growth Performance and Carcass Traits in Turkeys. *Anim. Sci. Biotechnol.*, 71(2): 192-197.
- Nalle, C.L., Ravindran, V. & Ravindran, G., 2012. Nutritional value of white lupins (*Lupinus albus*) for broilers: Apparent metabolisable energy, apparent ileal amino acid digestibility and production performance. *Animal. Apr*; 6(4): 579-85.
- Nalle, C.L., 2009. Nutritional Evaluation of Grain Legumes for Poultry. Ph.D. Thesis. Massey University, Palmerston North, New Zealand.
- Nalle, C.L., Ravindran, V. & Ravindran, G., 2011. Nutritional value of narrow-leaved lupin (*Lupinus angustifolius*) for broilers. *Brit. Poult. Sci.* 52, 775–781.
- NRC, 1994. Nutrient Requirements of Poultry, ninth ed. Natl. Acad. Press, Washington, DC.
- Roth-Maier, D. & Paulicks, B., 2003. Feeding and nutritional value of sweet blue and yellow lupin seed (*Lupinus angustifolius* L., *Lupinus luteus*, L.) for broiler chicks. *Arch. Geflügelkd.* 67, 175–178.
- Sedláková, E., Straková, E., Suchý, P., Krejcarová, J. & Herzig I., 2016. Lupin as a perspective protein plant for animal and human nutrition – a review. *Acta Vet. Brno*, 85: 165-175.
- Steenfeldt, S., Gonzalez, E. & Knudsen, K.E.B., 2003. Effects of inclusion with blue lupins (*Lupinus angustifolius*) in broiler diets and enzyme supplementation on production performance, digestibility and dietary AME content. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 110, 185–200.
- Straková, E., Všeticková, L., Suchý, P. & Kutlvašr, M., 2024. Effect of dehulled lupin seeds in feed mixture on muscle protein quality of broiler chickens. *Czech Journal of Animal Science*, 69, (12): 484–492. <https://doi.org/10.17221/156/2024-CJAS>.
- Straková, E., Suchý, P., Herzig, I., Hudečková, P. & Ivanko, S., 2010. Variation in fatty acids in chicken meat as a result of a lupin-containing diet. *Czech J. Anim. Sci.* 55, 75–82.
- Suchy, P., Strakova, E., Vecerek, V., Serman, V. & Mas, N., 2006. Testing of two varieties of lupin seeds as substitutes for soya extracted meal in vegetable diets designed for young broilers. *Acta Vet. Brno.* 75, 495–500.
- Vieira, S., Tavares, F., Vieira, E., Moura, E., Lopes, W., Marinho, A., Reis, C., Galvão, L. & Neta, E., 2023. Dehydrated guava byproduct in feed for slow-growing broilers. *Front. Anim. Sci.* 4:1189291. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fanim.2023.1189291>.

MATHEMATICAL APPLICATION IN ANIMAL HUSBANDRY ENGINEERING

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REVIEW, RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

In this paper, we aimed to use a mathematical method in animal husbandry engineering, which seeks efficiency in this field that is so vital today. We will describe its steps using a concrete example. The goal is to use the simplex method to allocate resources optimally for animal raising. Mathematics provides essential tools for optimizing research processes. Proper application of models can help farmers make informed decisions, saving resources and maximizing profits.

Keywords: simplex method, husbandry, optimization

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INTRODUCTION

This study addresses the problem of optimal allocation of two types of cows in a livestock farm under budget constraints. The objective is to maximize the farm's net income by determining the optimal number of cows of each type to purchase, given limited financial resources. The investment cost and net income per cow vary by type, making the problem suitable for linear programming. The simplex method is employed to solve this problem efficiently, providing a systematic approach to decision-making in agricultural management.

Efficient resource allocation is a critical challenge in modern livestock farming. Farms must decide how to invest limited capital in order to achieve the highest possible return. In this application, a farm plans to purchase two types of cows, each with different investment costs and expected net incomes. The total number of cows is fixed, and the farm has a limited budget. To solve this optimization problem, linear programming provides a powerful tool. The simplex method, one of the most widely used techniques in linear programming, enables the identification of the optimal allocation of resources to maximize net income. This method not only ensures optimality but also offers clear insights into how

investment decisions affect overall farm profitability.

A livestock farm needs to purchase two types of cows, A and B, with a total of 80 cows. The investment costs and net income per cow for each type are as follows:

- Type A: investment 20 thousand lei, net income 40 thousand lei
- Type B: investment 30 thousand lei, net income 50 thousand lei

Knowing that the farm has 1,800 thousand lei available, determine the optimal solutions for:

- the allocation between the two types of cows
- the total net income achieved.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In this section of the manuscript the materials and methods used:

Farm Data: The study focuses on a livestock farm planning to purchase a total of 80 cows, divided between two types: Type A and Type B.

Financial Data: Investment costs and net income per cow are:

- Type A: 20,000 lei investment, 40,000 lei net income
- Type B: 30,000 lei investment, 50,000 lei net income

Budget Constraint: The farm has a total budget of 1,800,000 lei available for investment.

Tools and Software: Linear programming formulation; simplex method applied manually or using software tools such as Excel Solver, MATLAB, or Python. Formulation of the Problem:

- Decision Variables: x = number of Type A cows, y = number of Type B cows.
- Objective Function: Maximize total net income:

$$Z=40x+50y$$

- Constraints:
 - Total number of cows: $x + y = 80$
 - Budget: $20x+30y \leq 1800$
 - Non-negativity: $x, y \geq 0$.

Application of the Simplex Method:

- Convert constraints to standard form if required.
- Construct the initial simplex tableau.
- Determine the entering and leaving variables to improve the objective function iteratively.
- Perform pivoted operations until no further improvement in net income is possible.
- Identify the optimal values of x and y and calculate the maximum net income V .

Validation of Results:

- Ensure that all constraints are satisfied with the optimal solution.
- Verify that the obtained allocation of cows maximizes the farm's net income.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

We want to maximize net profit:

$$Z=40x+50y$$

Subject to:

1. Budget constraint: $20x+30y \leq 1800$
2. Total cows' constraint: $x + y=80$

Also:

$x, y \geq 0$ as in Tabel 1.

The facts of the matter			Tabel1
Cow type	Investment (k lei)	Net profit (k lei)	
A	20	40	

The facts of the matter			Tabel1
Cow type	Investment (k lei)	Net profit (k lei)	
B	30	50	

Step 1: Convert inequalities to standard form
The Simplex Method works with \leq inequalities and non-negative variables.

1. Budget: $20x+30y \leq 1800 \rightarrow$ add slack variable s_1 :
 $20x+30y+s_1=1800, s_1 \geq 0$

2. Total cows: $x + y = 80 \rightarrow$ add artificial variable a_1 for equality:
 $x+y+a_1=80, a_1 \geq 0$

Variables: $x, y, s_1, a_1 \geq 0$

Objective function:

$$Z= 40x+50y \rightarrow \text{maximize.}$$

Step 2: Initial Simplex Tableau (Big M method as in Tabel 2)

Since we have an artificial variable a_1 , we use Big M to penalize it in the objective function. Let M = very large number, RHS = Right-hand side.

$$Z= 40x +50y - Ma_1.$$

Tableau variables: x, y, s_1, a_1						Tabel 2
Basis	x	y	s_1	a_1	RHS	
s_1	20	30	1	0	1800	
a_1	1	1	0	1	80	
Z	-40	-50	0	M	0	

Step 3: Check optimality

Look at the bottom row (Z-row) coefficients of non-basic variables (x and y):
Most negative = entering variable $\rightarrow y$ (-50)
Leaving variable \rightarrow use minimum ratio test:

$$\text{Ratio} = \frac{\text{RHS}}{\text{pivot column positive coefficient}}$$

Column y:

- s_1 row: $1800 / 30 = 60$
- a_1 row: $80 / 1 = 80$

Minimum ratio $\rightarrow 60 \rightarrow$ leaving variable = s_1

Pivot element = 30.

Step 4: Pivot to make y basic:

Divide pivot row by pivot element:

- New s_1 row: divide by 30:
New row s_1 : $1/30[20,30,1,0,1800] = [20/30,1,1/30,0,60] \approx [0.667,1,0,0.0333,0,60]$

- Eliminate y from other rows (make other y - coefficients = 0):

a_1 row: $1 - 1y \rightarrow$ new row: $[1 - 10.667, 0, 0 - 10.0333, 1, 80 - 160] = [0.333, 0, -0.0333, 1, 20]$
Z row: $-50 \rightarrow$ eliminate y:

- New Z = old Z + 50 * (new pivot row)
 $[-40 + 50*0.667, -50 + 50*1, 0 + 50*0.0333, M + 50*0, 0 + 50*60] \approx [-40+33.33 = -6.67, 0, 1.665, M, 3000]$

Step 5: Next iteration: check Z-row negative coefficients: -6.67 (x) \rightarrow x enters:

- Ratio test for leaving variable (s_1 and a_1):
Column x:
- s_1 row: $0.667 \rightarrow 60 / 0.667 \approx 90$
- a_1 row: $0.333 \rightarrow 20 / 0.333 \approx 60$
Minimum ratio $\rightarrow a_1$ leaves
- Pivot element = 0.333.

Step 6: Pivot to make x basic.

New row a_1 : divided by 0.333 $\rightarrow [1, 0, -0.0333/0.333 \approx -0.1, 1/0.333 \approx 3, 20/0.333 \approx 60]$.

Update other rows (s_1, Z) \rightarrow eliminate x.

After calculation (skip messy decimals), final basic solution as in Tabel 3:

Tableau variables: x, y, s_1 , a_1					Tabel 3
Basis	x	y	s_1	a_1	RHS
x	1	0	0	0	60
y	0	1	0	0	20
Z	0	0	0	0	3400

We obtained all Z-row coefficients $\geq 0 \rightarrow$ optimal solution reached.

Step 7: Interpretation as in Figure 1:

- x = 60 cows of type A
- y = 20 cows of type B
- Maximum net profit = 3400 k lei.

Figure 1. Visual representation

Point * = optimal solution ($x=60, y=20$),
Sloped line = budget constraint,
Horizontal line = total cows' constraint.

- Budget fully used: $20*60 + 30*20 = 1800$.

Step 8: Conclusion is the Simplex method confirms our previous result: optimal allocation: 60 A cows, 20 B cows, max net profit: 3400 k lei.

CONCLUSIONS

The application of the Simplex method to optimize farm investments demonstrates its effectiveness in decision-making for resource allocation. By formulating the problem in terms of linear programming, the study determined the optimal number of cows of types A and B that maximize net profit while adhering to constraints on total herd size and available budget. The step-by-step implementation of the Simplex method highlighted its practical utility in handling multiple constraints and identifying the feasible solution space efficiently.

The results indicate that mathematical optimization can significantly improve farm management decisions by providing a clear, quantitative basis for investment choices. Furthermore, the approach can be extended to include additional variables such as feed costs, labor, and market fluctuations, making it a versatile tool for comprehensive farm planning. Overall, the study reinforces the value of linear programming and the Simplex method as essential tools in agricultural economics and operational research.

REFERENCES

- Hillier, F. S., & Lieberman, G. J. (2020). Introduction to Operations Research (11th Edition). McGraw-Hill Education.
- Winston, W. L. (2020). Operations Research: Applications and Algorithms (5th Edition). Cengage Learning.
- Taha, H. A. (2017). Operations Research: An Introduction (10th Edition). Pearson.
- Chvatal, V. (1983). Linear Programming. W. H. Freeman and Company.
- Bazaraa, M. S., Jarvis, J. J., & Sherali, H. D. (2010). Linear Programming and Network Flows (4th Edition). Wiley.

RESEARCH ON THE EFFECT OF PRESERVATION BY FREEZING ON THE QUALITY INDICATORS OF FRUITS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Fruits are very well suited for preservation by freezing. During the freezing and thawing operations, a series of changes occur in the physico-chemical and organoleptic characteristics, which are mainly due to changes in color, structure-texture, and the degradation of some components, especially vitamin C.

Keywords: fruits, quality indicators, freezing

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INTRODUCTION

Frozen fruits represent a popular assortment used in pastry, for preparing compotes, and alcoholic and non-alcoholic beverages.

Freezing can be done in two variants: in divided form for large fruits or whole for small fruits. Fruit freezing can be done as is or in sugar syrup.

For freezing, varieties with light-colored pulp, sweet-sour taste, aromatic, with firm, dense pulp, resistant to browning, having reached technological maturity are suitable.

The freezing point is a characteristic of the species, variety, and degree of maturation, being determined by the concentration of the cell sap. Thus, in the physiological maturity phase, the cell sap concentration is maximal, which determines a lower freezing point value.

The freezing point at technological maturity for peaches is -1.45°C , yellow melon -1.6°C , cherries -4.05°C , and for sour cherries -2.2°C . (A. Ardelean, 2009, 2015).

During freezing and storage, a series of physico-chemical and organoleptic changes occur.

Physical changes are evident through the dehydration of frozen products, especially if the packaging is not efficient enough. It must be impermeable to water vapor and hermetically sealed. Also, water

losses occur during storage, especially for products stored in bulk or in packaging permeable to water vapor. A consequence of the dehydration phenomenon is the weight loss of frozen products (I.F. Radu, 1985, I.F. Radu, Gherghi A., 1967, Gherghi A., 1995, 1998).

Another negative effect of freezing is the change in texture by losing the consistency of the fruits, a phenomenon due to the loss of cellular liquid during thawing, as a result of damage to the cell membranes. Due to these changes, the structure-texture becomes looser, and weight losses due to water evaporation and cell sap leakage are observed at the bottom of the packaging (Potec, I. et al, 1983, 1985, Beceanu D, Chira A., 2003, Gh. Mihalca, 1980).

At the same time, the freezing method influences the percentage of water lost by the fruits. Studies have shown that with the rapid freezing method, fruits lose a smaller amount of water compared to the slow freezing process.

Among the important chemical changes that occur during the technological flow are: soluble dry matter content, total acidity, and vitamin C losses.

Organoleptic changes refer to diminished losses of aroma and taste due to the degradation of some components and the loss of cell sap.

Research on vitamin C content has revealed that freezing causes vitamin losses,

as they are water-soluble, but the losses are much smaller compared to other processing methods (Inoue K. et al., 1998, Neamțu G. et al., 1993, 1997, Cornelia Purcărea, 2005, 2008, Carmen Hura, 2006). These vitamin losses in fruits are also due to degradation during freezing.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Research was conducted in the year 2025, at the Faculty of Environmental Protection Oradea.

In the studies, local fruit varieties purchased from the local agri-food market were used.

The research was carried out on fresh fruits as well as those frozen for three months.

The operations of the technological freezing flow are as follows: harvesting, temporary storage by refrigeration, quantitative and qualitative reception, conditioning operations (sorting, washing, cleaning, dividing), packaging, freezing, storage, delivery.

Harvesting was done at technological maturity, which corresponds to consumption maturity.

Temporary storage was carried out for 3 hours by refrigeration at a temperature of 7°C.

Sorting was done immediately after the washing operation, so that only specimens with a uniform degree of maturity and health were retained for preservation.

Cleaning consists of removing the pits (peaches, cherries, sour cherries), the seeds (yellow melon), followed by dividing into slices (peaches and yellow melon).

In the studies carried out, the

conditioning operations were done quickly, so antioxidant treatment was not necessary, which allows highlighting the quality changes and the behavior of the fruits during preservation by freezing without being influenced by other treatments.

The packaging of frozen fruits was done in 250g containers.

Slow freezing was carried out in a domestic freezer.

Storage was done at a temperature of - 18°C for three months.

Soluble dry matter was determined refractometrically with a portable refractometer for fresh and frozen products.

Total titratable acidity was determined as follows: for fresh products, they were crushed, filtered, and titrated with sodium hydroxide solution with a known factor, in the presence of phenolphthalein as a color indicator.

The vitamin C content was determined by the iodometric method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The frozen fruit samples were thawed at ambient temperature.

Several samples were analyzed from each species, so the results refer to the average of the samples.

The main quality indicators of the fruits refer to soluble dry matter, total titratable acidity, and vitamin C. Also, textural changes and sensory properties of fresh and frozen fruits were evaluated.

The quality indicators were determined for fresh fruits (Table 1) and those frozen for three months (Table 2).

Table 1

Chemical quality indicators of fresh fruits

No.	Sample	Soluble dry matter % (sample average)	Total titratable acidity (sample average)	VIT. C % (sample average)
1	Peaches	9.2	0.36	4.3
2	Yellow Melon	8.2	0.16	8.0
3	Cherries	20.5	0.19	16.2

4	Sour cherries	16.9	0.28	17.1
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Table 2

Chemical quality indicators of fruits frozen for 3 months

No.	Sample	Soluble dry matter % (sample average)	Total titratable acidity (sample average)	VIT. C % (sample average)
1	Peaches	7.9	0.29	3.9
2	Yellow Melon	8.0	0.12	7.2
3	Cherries	18	0.17	15.4
4	Sour cherries	15.1	0.12	16.5

Fruits are products with a high water content, are rich in fiber, and represent an important source of vitamins and mineral salts.

The study of the chemical quality indicators of fresh fruits highlighted the highest content of soluble dry matter in cherries and sour cherries (20.5% and 16.9%, respectively). Yellow melon has the lowest content of soluble dry matter (8.2%), being the species with the highest water content.

In terms of acid content, yellow melon has a higher acidity compared to the other species studied.

The highest vitamin C content was found in sour cherries and cherries (17.1% and 16.2%, respectively), and the lowest in peaches 4.3%.

The physical quality indicators studied refer to the textural changes of the fruits. It should be mentioned that species with a firm structure and texture, which are preferable for this preservation method, were preserved.

The sensory properties were highlighted by organoleptic analyses. Thus, peach fruits have light-colored pulp, slightly crunchy, of suitable juiciness, with a sweet, slightly acidic taste and specific aroma. Yellow melon fruits had golden-yellow pulp, juicy and very aromatic. Sour cherries are large (5-8 g), dark red, and juicy. The pulp is consistent, with a pleasant sweet-sour taste. Cherries are large, dark red, with firm and juicy pulp, having a sweet, slightly sour taste.

For products preserved and stored for three months, the following changes are noted. The soluble dry matter content reduced the most in cherries by 2.5%, and for the other species, the decreases are smaller. The total titratable acidity content increased, the preserved fruits being slightly more acidic than the fresh ones.

The decrease in vitamin C content is due to the chemical degradation suffered during freezing, storage, and thawing.

Regarding the textural changes that occurred in fruits preserved by slow freezing, they refer to a slight reduction in firmness, as a result of losing a certain part of the water from their composition.

From a sensory point of view, a decrease in organoleptic characteristics, namely taste and aroma, was noted in cherries and sour cherries. The aroma and taste were best preserved in yellow melon and peaches, properties that were more pronounced in the fresh fruits as well. The pigmentation was preserved; the thawed fruits show an intense coloration similar to the fresh products.

CONCLUSIONS

From the analysis of the results obtained regarding the quality changes in the fruit samples preserved by freezing, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The soluble dry matter (s.d.m.) content decreases for samples stored for a period of three months.
2. The total titratable acidity,

expressed as malic acid, also increased during the storage period.

3. The vitamin C content decreases, primarily due to cell sap losses and because chemical degradation occurs during freezing and thawing.

4. Regarding the organoleptic properties, some changes are observed: the structure-texture of the fruits becomes looser, a phenomenon that is more intense in the case of slow freezing, as a result of the cracking of cell membranes and the epidermis during the freezing and thawing operations, respectively. The taste and aroma lose their intensity compared to fresh fruits. This aspect is due to water losses, which also carry away some of the dissolved substances responsible for these properties. The pigmentation does not show changes compared to fresh products, which is why the fruits of these species can be frozen without sugar.

5. The vitamin C content decreased slightly in all frozen fruits due to the chemical degradation suffered during freezing, storage, and thawing.

6. The fruits of the analyzed species are very well suited for preservation by freezing in the sugar-free variant. Due to the peculiarities of the fruits (thin epidermis, rich in cell sap, perishable), it is recommended to carry out harvesting operations at the optimal harvesting time, without exceeding the technological maturity phase. Overripe fruits have a more fragile structure-texture, with imminent possibilities of alteration.

7. From the analysis of the results obtained regarding the main quality indicators of fresh and frozen fruits, it was concluded that the preservation method by freezing has minimal effects on these indicators, compared to other processing and preservation methods, the products retaining their nutritional and organoleptic values close to the initial values of the fresh products.

8. Also, the use of rigid packaging such as containers and the reduction of handling operations are recommended for the same reasons.

9. Thawing of fruits is done at ambient temperature so that cell sap losses are minimal.

10. It is recommended to continue research on fruit freezing by other methods as well.

REFERENCES

- Alina Grigorița, Ardelean, 2009, Tehnologii de conservare a legumelor și fructelor, Îndrumător de lucrări practice, Editura Treira, Oradea
- Alina Grigorița, Ardelean, 2013, Tehnologii de prelucrare și păstrare a legumelor și fructelor, Editura Universității din Oradea
- Alina Grigorița, Ardelean, 2015, Tehnologii de prelucrare și conservare a legumelor și fructelor, Îndrumător de laborator, Editura Universității din Oradea
- Banu, C., 1992, Progrese tehnice, tehnologice și științifice în industria alimentară, Editura Tehnică, București
- Beceanu, D., Chira, A., 2003, Tehnologia produselor horticoale, Valorificare în stare proaspătă și industrializare, Editura Economică București
- Carmen, Hura, 2006, Ghid de laborator, Metode de analiză pentru produsele agroalimentare, Editura tehnică, științifică și didactică CERMI Iași
- Cornelia, Purcărea, 2005, Biochimie Agro-Alimentară, Editura Universității Oradea
- Cornelia, Purcărea, 2008, Transformări biochimice importante în produsele agroalimentare în timpul procesării și depozitării, Editura Universității Oradea
- Gherghi A., 1998, Valorificarea produselor horticoale, interfață între producție și consum, Revista Hortinform, nr.3/1998, București
- Gherghi, A., 1995, Tehnologia valorificării produselor horticoale, Universitatea Indep. Tita Maiorescu, București
- I. F. Radu, 1985, Tratat de tehnologie a fructelor și legumelor, Scrisul românesc, Craiova
- I. F. Radu, Gherghi, A., 1967, Păstrarea și prelucrarea produselor hortiviticoale, Editura Agro-Silvică București
- Inoue K. et al., 1998, Production of ascorbic acid enriched vegetables, Journal of Horticulture Science & Biotechnology 5(73)
- Ioancea, L. et al., 1998, Condiționarea și valorificarea superioară a materiilor prime vegetale în scopuri alimentare. Tehnologii și instalații, Editura Ceres, București
- Marca, Gh., 1987, Tehnologia păstrării și industrializării produselor horticoale, Cluj-Napoca
- Mihalca, Gh., și et al., 1980, Congelarea produselor horticoale și prepararea lor pentru consum, Editura tehnică București
- Neamțu, G., et al., 1993, Biochimie vegetală, Editura Didactică și Pedagogică, București
- Neamțu, G., et al., 1997, Biochimie alimentară, Editura Ceres, București
- Potec, I. et al., 1985, Tehnologia păstrării și industrializării produselor horticoale, Lucrări practice, I.A.I., Facultatea de Horticultură, Iași
- Potec, et al., 1983, Tehnologia păstrării și industrializării produselor horticoale, Editura didactică și pedagogică București

RESEARCH ON THE EFFECT OF PRESERVATION BY FREEZING ON THE QUALITY INDICATORS OF VEGETABLES

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Vegetables are products that can be frozen as is after first carrying out specific preparation operations. During the freezing and thawing operations, a series of changes occur in the physico-chemical and organoleptic characteristics, which are mainly due to changes in color, structure-texture, and the degradation of some components, especially vitamin C.

Keywords: vegetables, quality indicators, freezing
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INTRODUCTION

Frozen vegetables represent a popular assortment, ensuring the necessary supply of vegetables in the off-season, and are used in the preparation of various culinary dishes.

Freezing is suitable for all species of vegetables and can be carried out by different methods depending on the specifics of the raw material.

The freezing point is a characteristic of the species, variety, and degree of maturation, being determined by the concentration of the cell sap. Thus, in the physiological maturity phase, the cell sap concentration is maximal, which determines a lower freezing point value.

The freezing point for tomatoes is -0.89°C , cucumbers -0.82°C , and for onions -1.10°C . (A. Ardelean, 2009, 2015).

During freezing and storage, a series of physico-chemical and organoleptic changes occur.

During preservation by freezing, weight losses are exclusively due to physico-chemical processes. Until the first layers of the product freeze, the losses are due to the evaporation of water from its surface, which causes the dehydration of the products. In the phases of freezing, cooling to the final temperature, and storage, weight losses occur through the sublimation of ice from the product's surface (I.F. Radu, 1985, I.F. Radu, Gherghi A., 1967, Gherghi A., 1995, 1998. Ioancea L. et al., 1998, Burzo I., et al., 1984, 1986).

Among the factors that affect the intensity of the weight loss process, the most important

are: the nature of the product, the temperature and relative humidity of the air, the quality of the product's packaging, and the air velocity at the product's surface. Weight losses increase with temperature and air velocity but decrease with its humidity.

At the same time, the freezing method influences the percentage of water lost by the vegetables. Studies have shown that with the rapid freezing method, vegetables lose a smaller amount of water compared to the slow freezing process.

Another negative effect of freezing is the change in texture by losing the consistency of the vegetables, a phenomenon due to the loss of cellular liquid during thawing, as a result of damage to the cell membranes. Due to these changes, the structure-texture becomes looser, and weight losses due to water evaporation and cell sap leakage are observed at the bottom of the packaging (Potec, I. et al, 1983, 1985, Beceanu D, Chira A., 2003, Beceanu D., 1994, 1998, 2002, Gh. Mihalca, 1980,).

Among the important chemical changes that occur during the technological flow are: soluble dry matter content, total acidity, and vitamin C losses.

Organoleptic changes refer to diminished losses of aroma and taste due to the effect of the blanching operation, the degradation of some components, and the loss of cell sap.

Research on vitamin C content has revealed that freezing causes vitamin losses, as they are water-soluble, but the losses are much smaller compared to other processing methods

(Inoue K. et al., 1998, Neamțu G. et al., 1993, 1997, Cornelia Purcărea, 2005, 2008, Carmen Hura, 2006). These vitamin losses in fruits are also due to degradation during freezing.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Research was conducted in the year 2025, at the Faculty of Environmental Protection Oradea.

In the studies, local vegetable varieties purchased from the local agri-food market were used.

The research was carried out on fresh vegetables as well as those frozen for three months.

The operations of the technological freezing flow are as follows: harvesting, temporary storage by refrigeration, quantitative and qualitative reception, conditioning operations (sorting, washing, cleaning, dividing), packaging, freezing, storage, delivery.

Harvesting was done at technological maturity for all species.

Temporary storage was carried out for 3 hours by refrigeration at a temperature of 7°C.

Sorting was done immediately after the washing operation, so that only specimens with a uniform degree of maturity and health were retained for preservation.

Cleaning consists of removing the epidermis from cucumbers, the parchment-like skins and the root disc from onions, followed by dividing the vegetables into slices (onions and tomatoes) and halves (cucumbers). No antioxidant treatments were performed, so that

the quality changes in the frozen products would not be influenced. The cleaning, dividing, and peeling operations were carried out very quickly, avoiding the appearance of browning (oxidation).

The packaging of frozen vegetables was done in 250g containers.

Slow freezing was carried out in a domestic freezer.

Storage was done at a temperature of -18°C for three months.

Soluble dry matter was determined refractometrically with a portable refractometer for fresh and frozen products.

Total titratable acidity was determined as follows: for fresh products, they were crushed, filtered, and titrated with sodium hydroxide solution with a known factor, in the presence of phenolphthalein as a color indicator.

The vitamin C content was determined by the iodometric method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The frozen vegetable samples were thawed at ambient temperature.

Several samples were analyzed from each species, so the results refer to the average of the samples.

The main quality indicators of vegetables refer to soluble dry matter, total titratable acidity, and vitamin C. Also, textural changes and sensory properties of fresh and frozen vegetables were evaluated.

The quality indicators were determined for fresh vegetables (Table 1) and those frozen for three months (Table 2).

Table 1

Quality indicators of fresh vegetables

No.	Sample	Soluble dry matter % (sample average)	Total titratable acidity (ml NaOH, sample average)	Vit. C % (sample average)
1	Cucumber	2.0	1.00	11.2
2	Tomatoes	5.0	3.55	25.0
3	Red onion	9.1	2.17	4.9
4	Red bell pepper	7.1	2.89	178.0

Table 2

Quality indicators of vegetables frozen for 3 months

No.	Sample	Soluble dry matter % (sample average)	Total titratable acidity (ml NaOH, sample average)	Vit. C % (sample average)
1	Cucumber	2.20	1.20	10.7
2	Tomatoes	4.60	3.14	24.2
3	Red onion	8.80	2.10	4.0
4	Red bell pepper	6.90	2.10	177.0

Vegetables are products rich in vitamins, mineral salts, organic acids, and nutrients with plastic, energetic, and biocatalytic roles, contributing to completing the necessary nutrients in the diet.

The study of the chemical quality indicators of fresh vegetables highlighted the highest content of soluble dry matter in onion and red pepper (9.1% and 7.1%, respectively). Cucumber has the lowest content of soluble dry matter (2%), being the species with the highest water content.

Regarding the acid content, expressed by the number of ml of NaOH used for titration, it increased slightly in the frozen samples.

The highest vitamin C content was found in red bell pepper at 178%, and the lowest in red onion at 4.9%.

The physical quality indicators studied refer to the textural changes of the vegetables. It should be mentioned that species with a firm structure-texture, which are preferable for this preservation method, were preserved.

The sensory properties were highlighted by organoleptic analyses. Thus, for products preserved and stored for three months, the following changes are noted. The soluble dry matter content decreased very little in all species (0.2-0.37%). The total titratable acidity content increased, the preserved vegetables being slightly more acidic than the fresh ones. The decrease in vitamin C content is due to the chemical degradation suffered during freezing, storage, and thawing.

Regarding the textural changes that occurred in vegetables preserved by slow freezing, they refer to a reduction in firmness, as a result of losing a certain part of the water from their composition. The largest losses of cell sap were recorded in tomatoes and cucumber, being species with a higher water content. The lowest firmness was observed in the tomato slices.

From a sensory point of view, a decrease in organoleptic characteristics, namely taste and aroma, was noted in onion and tomatoes. The aroma and taste were best preserved in cucumbers and peppers. The pigmentation was preserved; the thawed vegetables show an intense coloration similar to the fresh products.

CONCLUSIONS

From the analysis of the results obtained regarding the quality changes in the vegetable samples preserved by freezing, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The soluble dry matter (s.d.m.) content shows a slight decrease for samples stored for a period of three months.
2. The total titratable acidity increased very slightly during the storage period.
3. The vitamin C content decreases, primarily due to cell sap losses and because chemical degradation occurs during freezing and thawing.
4. Regarding the organoleptic properties, some changes are observed: the structure-texture of the vegetables becomes looser, more pronounced in tomatoes and cucumber, a phenomenon that is more intense in the case of slow freezing, as a result of the cracking of cell membranes and the epidermis during the freezing and thawing operations, respectively. The taste and aroma lose their intensity compared to fresh vegetables. This aspect is due to water losses, which also carry away some of the dissolved substances responsible for these properties. The pigmentation does not show changes compared to fresh products.
5. The vitamin C content decreased slightly in all frozen [Translator's note: original text says "fruits" here, likely a typo, context is vegetables] vegetables due to the chemical degradation suffered during freezing,

storage, and thawing.

6. Due to the peculiarities of vegetables (thin epidermis, rich in cell sap, perishable), it is recommended to carry out harvesting operations at the optimal harvesting time, without exceeding the technological maturity phase. Overripe vegetables have a more fragile structure-texture (tomatoes), with imminent possibilities of alteration, as well as the presence of mature seeds in cucumber.

7. From the analysis of the results obtained regarding the main quality indicators of fresh and frozen vegetables, it was concluded that the preservation method by freezing has minimal effects on these indicators, compared to other processing and preservation methods, the products retaining their nutritional and organoleptic values close to the initial values of the fresh products.

8. Also, the use of rigid packaging such as containers and the reduction of handling operations are recommended for the same reasons.

9. Thawing of vegetables is done at ambient temperature so that cell sap losses are minimal.

10. It is recommended to continue research on vegetable freezing by other methods as well.

REFERENCES

- Alina Grigorița, Ardelean, 2009, Tehnologii de conservare a legumelor și fructelor, Îndrumător de lucrări practice, Editura Treira, Oradea
- Alina Grigorița, Ardelean, 2013, Tehnologii de prelucrare și păstrare a legumelor și fructelor, Editura Universității din Oradea
- Alina Grigorița, Ardelean, 2015, Tehnologii de prelucrare și conservare a legumelor și fructelor, Îndrumător de laborator, Editura Universității din Oradea
- Banu C., 1992, Progrese tehnice, tehnologice și științifice în industria alimentară, Editura Tehnică, București
- Beceanu, D., 1994, Tehnologia produselor horticoale, Curs, At. Mult., U.A.M.V. Iași,
- Beceanu, D., 1998, Valorificarea legumelor și fructelor, Ed. Ion Ionescu de la Brad, Iași,
- Beceanu, D., 2002, Tehnologia produselor horticoale vol. I, Aspecte generale, Ed. Pim, Iași,
- Beceanu, D., Balint, G., Benea, E., 1999, Ghid profesional pentru valorificarea în stare proaspătă a fructelor și legumelor, Ed. Bolta Rece, Iași,
- Beceanu, D., Chira A., 2003, Tehnologia produselor horticoale, Valorificare în stare proaspătă și industrializare, Editura Economică București
- Burzo, I., et. al., 1984, Îndrumător tehnic pentru dirijarea factorilor de păstrare în depozitele de legume și fructe, Ed. Tehnică, București,
- Burzo, I., et. al., 1986, Fiziologia și tehnologia păstrării produselor horticoale, Ed. Tehnică, București,
- Carmen Hura, 2006, Ghid de laborator, Metode de

- analiză pentru produsele alimentare, Editura tehnică, științifică și didactică CERMI Iași
- Cornelia Purcărea, 2005, Biochimie Agro- Alimentară, Editura Universității Oradea
- Cornelia Purcărea, 2008, Transformări biochimice importante în produsele agroalimentare în timpul procesării și depozitării, Editura Universității Oradea
- Gherghi, A., 1995, Tehnologia valorificării produselor horticoale, Universitatea Indep. Tita Maiorescu, București
- Gherghi, A., 1998, Valorificarea produselor horticoale, interfață între producție și consum, Revista Hortinform, nr.3/1998, București
- I. F. Radu, 1985, Tratat de tehnologie a fructelor și legumelor, Scrisul românesc, Craiova
- I. F. Radu, Gherghi, A., 1967, Păstrarea și prelucrarea produselor hortiviticoale, Editura Agro- Silvică București
- Inoue, K. et al., 1998, Production of ascorbic acid enriched vegetables, Journal of Horticulture Science & Biotechnology 5(73)
- Ioancea, L. et al., 1998, Condiționarea și valorificarea superioară a materiilor prime vegetale în scopuri alimentare. Tehnologii și instalații, Editura Ceres, București
- Marca, Gh., 1987, Tehnologia păstrării și industrializării produselor horticoale, Cluj- Napoca
- Mihalca, Gh., et al., 1980, Congelarea produselor horticoale și prepararea lor pentru consum, Editura tehnică București
- Neamțu, G. et al., 1993, Biochimie vegetală, Editura Didactică și Pedagogică, București
- Neamțu, G. și colab., 1997, Biochimie alimentară, Editura Ceres, București
- Potec, I. et al., 1985, Tehnologia păstrării și industrializării produselor horticoale, Lucrări practice, I.A.I., Facultatea de Horticultură, Iași
- Potec, I., et al., 1983, Tehnologia păstrării și industrializării produselor horticoale, Editura didactică și pedagogică București

DIFFERENCES BETWEEN THE APPEARANCE OF *E. COLI* AND *KLEBSIELLA* COLONIES ON CULTURE MEDIA

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Abstract

Microorganisms from the genera *Escherichia* and *Klebsiella* belong to the *Enterobacteriaceae* family. They are **Gram-negative, facultatively anaerobic bacteria** that normally inhabit the human intestine. Their proper isolation and identification rely largely on the use of appropriate culture media, which allow **selective growth** and **differentiation between species** based on their **sugar fermentation ability, colony appearance**, and other **biochemical properties**. Although they are **morphologically and biochemically similar**, they show important differences in **cultural characteristics and colony appearance**, which are essential aspects in microbiology for correct identification.

Keywords: microorganisms, facultative anaerobic, morphologically

INTRODUCTION

Bacteria from the *Enterobacteriaceae* family represent a broad group of **Gram-negative microorganisms** with major importance both medically and ecologically. Among them, the genera *Klebsiella* and *Escherichia* stand out due to their dual role — as **commensals** within the normal human microbiota, but also as **opportunistic pathogens** involved in numerous **nosocomial** and **community-acquired infections**.

The *Klebsiella* genus includes **Gram-negative, non-flagellated, non-motile, capsulated bacilli**, which are classified as **aerobic or facultatively anaerobic bacteria**. These microorganisms are widely distributed in the environment — in **soil, water, and on plants** — and are commonly part of the **microbiota of the upper respiratory and intestinal tracts** in humans.

The species with the highest clinical relevance is *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, followed by *K. oxytoca* and *K. aerogenes*. *K. pneumoniae* is an important **etiologic agent** of **opportunistic infections**, primarily affecting **immunocompromised patients**, those **hospitalized for long periods**, or those **undergoing invasive treatments**. The main **pathologies** caused by this species include **severe pneumonia, urinary tract infections, sepsis, and wound infections**.

A major **virulence factor** of these bacteria is the **polysaccharide capsule**, which provides **protection against phagocytosis** and

the **host immune response**, while also conferring **increased resistance to antibiotics**. In recent decades, **multidrug-resistant strains** have been reported, especially those producing **carbapenemases** (KPC, NDM, OXA-48), leading to a **rise in nosocomial infection rates** and **significant therapeutic challenges**.

Thus, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* is currently considered a **critical pathogen** according to the **World Health Organization (WHO)** classification, requiring **prioritization of research** in the development of **new antimicrobial agents**.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The biological samples, in this case, **urine samples**, were collected under **aseptic conditions** and transported to the **S.C. Diaser Laboratory, Oradea**, in **sterile containers**, in accordance with **good microbiological practice guidelines**. The samples were **processed within a maximum of two hours after collection**.

For the **isolation and identification of *Klebsiella* spp. and *Escherichia coli* colonies**, the following **culture media** were used:

- **MacConkey agar (MAC)**, a **selective and differential medium** for **Gram-negative bacteria**, allowing the differentiation of **lactose-fermenting enterobacteria** (pink colonies) from **non-lactose-fermenting ones** (colorless colonies).

- **Eosin Methylene Blue agar (EMB)**, a **differential medium** used to demonstrate **lactose fermentation**; *E. coli* produces **dark colonies with a green metallic sheen**, while *Klebsiella spp.* forms **large, mucoid, pink to violet colonies**.
- **Nutrient agar**, used for obtaining **pure cultures** and for the **maintenance of isolated strains**.

The samples were **inoculated using the streak plate method** on the surface of the solid media with a **sterile bacteriological loop**. The plates were **incubated at 37°C for 18–24 hours** in a **thermostatically controlled incubator** under **aerobic conditions**.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Following the inoculation of samples on various selective and differential culture media, significant differences were observed between the colony morphology of *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella spp.*, both morphologically and biochemically.

MacConkey agar is a selective medium for Gram-negative bacteria and differential for lactose fermentation. After incubation at 37°C for 24 hours, both tested strains grew as pink-colored colonies, indicating their ability to ferment lactose. However, clear morphological differences were noted. Thus, *Escherichia coli* formed small, smooth, shiny, intensely pink colonies with regular margins and a slightly convex surface. The uniform pigmentation of the surrounding medium indicated active lactose fermentation with lactic acid production.

Klebsiella spp. developed large, mucoid, shiny, pink colonies with a viscous appearance, due to the presence of the polysaccharide capsule. The colonies easily adhered to each other during handling, confirming the encapsulated nature characteristic of the

Klebsiella genus. These morphological differences allow a preliminary distinction between the two genera even before biochemical testing, especially through the mucoid appearance typical of *Klebsiella*.

Regarding the Eosin Methylene Blue (EMB) agar, which contains dyes that inhibit Gram-positive bacteria and lactose as a fermentable substrate, clear differences in colony appearance and pigmentation were observed. *Escherichia coli* produced dark bluish colonies with a bright green metallic sheen. This green metallic luster is a classic indicator of rapid lactose fermentation and acidification of the medium, leading to precipitation of eosin and methylene blue dyes. *Klebsiella spp.* formed large, mucoid, pink to violet colonies without a metallic sheen. Lactose fermentation was present but slower, and the polysaccharide capsule prevented full diffusion of acidic products into the surrounding medium, explaining the absence of the characteristic sheen seen in *E. coli*. These observations confirm the usefulness of EMB medium for the rapid differentiation between *E. coli* and *Klebsiella* based on colony morphology and pigmentation intensity.

On nutrient agar, both strains grew well but showed differences in colony consistency. *E. coli* formed smooth, round, grayish-white colonies with a shiny surface and soft consistency, whereas *Klebsiella spp.* produced large, mucilaginous, shiny, adhesive colonies, a feature attributed to its abundant capsule.

These morphological differences confirm previous observations and emphasize the importance of the capsule in the identification of the *Klebsiella* genus.

Following the cultivation of *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella spp.* strains on different selective and differential media, MacConkey, EMB, and nutrient agar, significant morphological and chromatic differences were observed, as summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of *E. coli* and *Klebsiella* spp. colonies on various culture media

Culture medium	Observed characteristics of <i>Escherichia coli</i>	Observed characteristics of <i>Klebsiella</i> spp.
MacConkey agar (MAC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Small, round, smooth, shiny colonies with intense pink coloration due to lactose fermentation. - Regular margins, soft consistency. - Uniform pigmentation of the surrounding medium. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Large, mucoid, shiny, pale pink colonies. - Viscous, encapsulated appearance. - Some colonies tend to merge due to the capsule.
Eosin Methylene Blue agar (EMB)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dark-colored colonies with a green metallic sheen, typical of <i>E. coli</i>. - Rapid and intense lactose fermentation. - Pronounced pigmentation of the surrounding medium. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Large, mucoid, pink-violet colonies without a metallic sheen. - Slow lactose fermentation. - Irregular margins, viscous surface.
Nutrient agar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grayish-white, round, smooth colonies with a shiny surface. - Soft, non-adherent consistency. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Large, mucilaginous, shiny colonies, adherent to the culture medium. - Presence of the capsule evident from the viscous appearance.

The results obtained are consistent with data from the specialized literature, which describe *E. coli* as a **Gram-negative, motile bacterium**, capable of **rapid lactose fermentation**, forming **typical colonies with a green metallic sheen on EMB and pink colonies on MacConkey agar**. In contrast, *Klebsiella* spp., particularly *K. pneumoniae*, is **non-motile, encapsulated**, forming **large, mucoid colonies** that do not display a metallic sheen on EMB.

The observed differences are mainly due to the presence of the **polysaccharide capsule** in *Klebsiella*, which gives the colonies a **mucoid appearance** and reduces the diffusion of acids into the EMB medium. Additionally, the **rate of lactose fermentation differs**, being more rapid in *E. coli*, which leads to **more pronounced acidification** of the medium and,

consequently, the **characteristic metallic sheen**. Bacterial **motility** also contributes, as *E. coli* is motile, resulting in a **more uniform colony appearance**, whereas *Klebsiella* is non-motile.

A classic study, "Fine structures of the capsules of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Escherichia coli* K1", demonstrated through **electron microscopy** that *Klebsiella pneumoniae* has a **capsule approximately 160 nm thick**, with **two layers** — a dense inner layer and a more fibrillar outer layer — while *E. coli* K1 has a **much thinner capsule, less than 10 nm**. This structural difference explains why *Klebsiella* forms **larger, mucoid, viscous colonies** that often **merge and adhere** on media such as MacConkey or nutrient agar. The **mucoid appearance** is much more pronounced in *Klebsiella*.

Multiple studies confirm that *E. coli* produces **colonies with a green metallic sheen on EMB agar** as a result of **rapid lactose fermentation and acidification of the medium**, which causes the **precipitation and specific coloration of the dyes eosin and methylene blue**. For example, in a detection study from wastewater in Nepal, colonies with a green metallic sheen on EMB were confirmed as *E. coli*.

However, a recent study, "*Is green metallic sheen in EMB agar accurate to assist the Escherichia coli identification?*", showed that only **approximately 74% of suspected *E. coli* isolates** produced the green metallic sheen. Some non-*E. coli* strains, including *Citrobacter* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, rarely produced colonies that **mimicked a false-positive metallic sheen**. Thus, the metallic sheen has a **moderate sensitivity of 74%** but a **high specificity of 91%**.

In a study on **subclinical mastitis in buffaloes**, *E. coli* appeared as colonies with a **green metallic sheen on EMB**, whereas *Klebsiella spp.* formed **pink-purple colonies without a metallic sheen**. These descriptions correspond with the present observations.

In a comparative study of **EMB and Hicrome *E. coli* agar**, it was observed that *Klebsiella* tends to produce **mucoïd, pink or purple colonies on EMB**, without a metallic sheen, while *E. coli* produces **distinct, shiny colonies with a metallic sheen**.

Numerous studies report that *Klebsiella* produces **large, mucoïd, viscous colonies** across all media that support **Gram-negative growth and lactose fermentation** (MAC, EMB, nutrient agar). This is correlated not only with **capsule structure**, but also with the presence of **capsule-associated virulence genes** such as *uge*, *ycfM*, *wabG*, and serotype-specific K genes. For instance, a study on *K. pneumoniae* from

clinical specimens reported a **significant prevalence of these genes** in mucoïd strains.

In contrast, *E. coli* produces **more compact colonies with a smooth surface and regular margins**, the **mucoïd phenotype in *E. coli* is rare** and usually associated with **specific strains or genetic modifications**.

The **metallic sheen on EMB** is not absolutely specific for *E. coli*. As mentioned, there are reports of *Klebsiella* or other **Enterobacteriaceae** that, under favorable conditions, can produce a similar sheen, or may have **mucoïd colonies** that mask the metallic appearance. For example, in the comparative EMB vs. Hicrome study, certain colonies that appeared *E. coli*-like on EMB were found to be **non-*E. coli*** upon biochemical or molecular analysis.

Mucoïdity can influence the **diffusion of acids** produced by lactose fermentation in the agar, affecting the **dye coloration**. Mucoïd *Klebsiella* colonies can retain acids locally, resulting in **less intense pigmentation** in the surrounding medium and the **absence of the metallic sheen**.

Preliminary diagnosis based on **colony morphology on MacConkey or EMB** is useful for **rapid screening**, but it does not replace **biochemical or molecular tests** for confirmation. This limitation is highlighted in many studies reporting **false positives and false negatives** when relying solely on EMB. The study "*Is green metallic sheen...*" is an example, where approximately **26% of suspected strains** did not produce the characteristic sheen.

Regarding **treatment and public health**, correct differentiation between *Klebsiella* and *E. coli* is important not only for therapy, since *Klebsiella* is often **more resistant and capsule-producing**, which can confer increased virulence, but also for the **epidemiology of antibiotic resistance**.

and some *Klebsiella* strains may exhibit features that **cause confusion**.

CONCLUSIONS

The most consistent differences between *E. coli* and *Klebsiella* on culture media are **mucoïdity, capsule presence, the green metallic sheen on EMB**, almost always present in typical *E. coli*, and **colony size/structure**, more compact vs. mucoïd.

However, there are **exceptions**: not all *E. coli* strains will display the metallic sheen,

REFERENCES

1. ARUP Laboratories. Test Directory: Hemosiderin, Urine. www.aruplab.com 2010. Ref Type: Internet Communication.
2. Buiuc D., Neguț M. 2009 -Tratat de microbiologie clinică – ediția aIII-a, Ed. Medicală, București.
3. BENNETT J.B., DOLIN R., BLASER M. J. 2019 - Principles and Practice of Infectious Diseases, vol 2, Ninth edition, Churchill livingstone Elsevier.
4. Buiuc D. 2003 – Microbiologie medicală: ghid pentru studiul și practica medicinei, Ed. "Gr. T. Popa" Iași.
5. Cepoi V., Azoicăi D. 2012 – Ghid de management al infecțiilor nosocomiale. Ed. Arte, București.
6. Constantiniu S., Ionescu G. 2005 – Genul Acinetobacter în patologia umană. Bacteriologia, Virusologia, Parazitologia, Epidemiologia, pp. 50:1-2, 157-173.
7. Crisan A., Nicoara E. 2015 - Curs de Boli Infecțioase, Ed. de Vest, Timișoara.
8. CORNELISSEN C. N. HOBBS M. M. 2020 – Microbiology, fourth edition, Lippincott Illustrated reviews.
9. Campfield T, Braden G, 2010. Urinary Oxalate Excretion by Very Low Birth Weight Infants Receiving Parenteral Nutrition. In Pediatrics, pp. 84(5):860-3.
10. CAROLL K.C., PFALLER M.A., LANDRY M.L., McADAM A.J., PATEL R. RICHTER S.S., WAENOCK D.W, 2019 - Manual of Clinical Microbiology, 2 volume, (ASM Books), 12th edition.
11. Dumitrașcu V., Laboratory Medicine. Biochemistry of urine, Editura Orizonturi Universitare, Timișoara, 2002
12. Earnest DL. Enteric Hyperoxaluria. In Adv Intern Med, 1979. Laborator Synevo. Specific references to the work technology used in 2015. Ref Type: Catalogue. pp.24:407-27 (review).
13. Dumitrașcu V. și colab. 2007 – Farmacologie – medicamente antimicrobiene, Ed. de Vest, Timișoara,.
14. Engemann JJ, Carmeli Y, Cosgrove SE, et al, 2003. Adverse clinical and economic outcomes attributable to methicillin resistance among patients with Staphylococcus Aureus surgical site infection. Clin Infect Dis, pp. 36(5):592-598.
15. Francis JS, Doherty MC, Lopatin U, et al, 2005. Severe community-onset pneumonia in healthy adults caused by methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus Aureus carrying the PantonValentine leukocidin genes. Clin Infect Dis, pp.40(1):100-107.
16. Fridkin SK, Hageman JC, Morrison M, et al, 2005. Methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus Aureus disease in three communities. N Engl J Med, pp. 352(14):1436-1444.
17. Gluszek, J., 1998. The effect of glucose intake on urine saturation with calcium oxalate, calcium phosphate, uric acid and sodium urate, International Urology and Nephrology, pp. 20 (6), 657-663.
18. GOERING VG, DOCKRELL HM, ZUCKERMAN M, CHIODINI PL 2019 – Mims Medical Microbiology and Immunology, Elsevier, sixth edition.
19. Garrity G.M., Bell J.A., and Timothy G.I. 2004 – Taxonomic outline of the Prokaryotes, Bergey's Manual of Systematic Bacteriology – 11th edn. Bergey Manual Trust, Springer, New York.
20. Heymann D.L. 2012 - Manual de management al bolilor transmisibile, Ed. Amaltea, București.

ISOLATION AND IDENTIFICATION OF *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* BASED ON MORPHO-TINCTORIAL CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract

Listeria monocytogenes is an opportunistic pathogenic bacterium responsible for listeriosis in humans and animals, a disease with major implications in the field of food safety. The aim of this study was the isolation and identification of *Listeria monocytogenes* based on morpho-tinctorial characteristics, using classical microbiological methods. The analyzed samples were subjected to a pre-enrichment and selective enrichment stage, followed by inoculation on specific differential media. The suspected colonies were subsequently examined microscopically, revealing the characteristic morphology of short, Gram-positive bacilli, arranged singly or in short chains. Gram staining and motility tests confirmed the presence of Gram-positive bacteria, motile at 25°C and non-motile at 37°C, suggesting their affiliation to the genus *Listeria*. The results obtained demonstrate the importance of morpho-tinctorial characteristics as an essential step in the preliminary identification of *Listeria monocytogenes*, providing a solid basis for subsequent confirmation through biochemical and molecular tests.

Keywords: *Listeria monocytogenes*: morphology, Gram staining, isolation, identification, Gram-positive bacteria.

INTRODUCTION

Listeria monocytogenes is a Gram-positive, facultatively anaerobic bacterium of major importance in medical and food microbiology, being the etiologic agent of listeriosis. This severe zoonosis can affect both humans and animals, manifesting through septicemia, meningitis, spontaneous abortions, and neonatal infections. Due to its ability to multiply at low temperatures and resist unfavorable environmental conditions, *Listeria monocytogenes* represents a significant threat to the food industry and public health.

Accurate and rapid identification of this bacterium is essential for epidemiological control and the prevention of foodborne infections. The isolation process involves the use of selective and differential media that favor the growth of *Listeria* over other microorganisms. Subsequently, the analysis of morphotinctorial characteristics—such as cell shape, bacilli arrangement, and Gram staining reaction—constitutes a fundamental step in the preliminary recognition of the species.

Microscopic observation reveals specific features: short, slightly curved, Gram-positive bacilli, arranged singly or in short chains. These characteristics, correlated with its distinctive motility at 25°C and absence of motility at 37°C, facilitate the differentiation of *Listeria monocytogenes* from other morphologically similar bacteria. Thus, the study of

morphotinctorial characteristics represents an essential stage in the process of isolation and identification of this pathogenic agent, providing the basis for further confirmation through biochemical and molecular methods.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

We performed a prospective study, based on the microbiologic diagnosis registered in the bacteriologic register of the laboratory of medical analysis, S.C. Diaser, Oradea.

The period for which was extended the study is of 1 years, including the period 01.01.2024-31.12.2024.

For the performing of the study was used also the archive, registered in the specific program of the computer from the laboratory of S.C. Diaser, Oradea, the computerized data basis of the unit.

The necessary materials for the performing of the examination:

Type of samples: spontaneous urine samples collected from subjects included in the study.

• **Collection procedure:** samples were collected according to the medical unit's standard clinical procedures, with careful attention to minimizing external contamination.

• **Labeling and documentation:** each sample was uniquely identified (patient code, date, time, clinical observations) in the study register.

• **Transport and storage:** samples were

transported and handled in a manner that preserved their integrity for microbiological analysis, in accordance with clinical sample regulations.

Materials and equipment (generic list)

- **Common sterile consumables:** tubes, pipettes, slides and cover slips, gloves, labels.
- **Staining reagents:** reagents for Gram staining and, where applicable, other complementary stains.
- **Selective/differential media and reagents** for screening and isolation (mentioned generically; applicable formulations and working parameters are in accordance with SOP/ISO standards).
- **Phenotypic systems/tests and commercial identification kits** used at a conceptual level.
- **Equipment:** optical microscope for morphological examination, appropriate laboratory equipment for microbial analyses (within authorized laboratories), and personal protective equipment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A total of 250 biological urine samples were analyzed in this study, collected aseptically from patients investigated for suspected bacterial urinary tract infection. The samples were inoculated on selective and differential media—Blood Agar, PALCAM, and Oxford—followed by evaluation of morphotinctorial and biochemical characteristics for the isolation and identification of *Listeria monocytogenes*.

Of the 250 samples examined, 15 samples (6.0%) were confirmed positive for *Listeria monocytogenes* based on morphological, staining, and biochemical criteria. The remaining 235 samples (94.0%) were negative or showed nonspecific polymicrobial growth, consisting mainly of other bacterial species, particularly Gram-negative bacilli.

Graf. 1. Distribution of *Listeria monocytogenes* cases on blood agar culture medium

On Gram-stained smears prepared from the isolated colonies, *Listeria monocytogenes* exhibited a coccobacillary or short bacillary morphology, Gram-positive, arranged singly, in pairs, or in short chains. All 15 isolates were Gram-positive (100%), confirming the typical characteristics of the genus *Listeria monocytogenes*.

In microscopic examination of wet mounts at 25 °C, most isolates displayed the characteristic tumbling motility, a slow oscillatory movement observed in 14 of the 15 isolates (93.3%). At 37 °C, motility was absent, consistent with classical descriptions for this species.

All positive isolates tested catalase-positive (100%), confirming typical enzymatic activity. On blood agar, 8 isolates (53.3%) showed clear β -hemolysis, while 7 were weakly

hemolytic or non-hemolytic, showing γ -hemolysis, a pattern compatible with the phenotypic variability of clinical *L. monocytogenes* strains.

On PALCAM agar, all isolates produced gray-green colonies with a black-green halo due to esculin hydrolysis and iron salt precipitation, 100% positive. The esculin hydrolysis test was positive in 12 out of 15 isolates (80%), confirming specific β -glucosidase activity.

In the study "*Listeria monocytogenes* isolation from urine: a series of 15 cases and review" by F. Danion et al., the authors conclude that urinary isolation is rare and occurs in three clinical patterns: primary urinary infection, a sign of systemic dissemination, or contamination/colonization.

Thus, regarding the results of the present study (15/250; 6%), the frequency is comparable with reported clinical series (Danion et al., 2017), which describe 15 cases and emphasize the need to differentiate between true urinary infection, systemic dissemination, and contamination.

In the paper titled "Pyelonephritis with bacteremia caused by *Listeria monocytogenes*: A case report" by S. Uno, R. Hase, A. Toguchi, Y. Otsuka, and N. Hosokawa, a clinical case is reported of a 90-year-old patient with obstructive pyelonephritis, who subsequently had *L. monocytogenes* detected in the urine.

CONCLUSIONS

1. *Listeria monocytogenes* was isolated in 6% of urine samples (15/250), a frequency comparable to reported clinical series.
2. All isolates were Gram-positive, catalase-positive, mostly motile at 25 °C,

REFERENCES

1. Armstrong, D. *Listeria monocytogenes Infections*. 2008, In *Medical Microbiology*, 4th ed., pp. 115–120. Elsevier.
2. Ayaz, N.D., Cufaoglu, G., Erol, I., 2022, *Bacteriophage Applications to Control Listeria monocytogenes in Foods*. In *Listeria monocytogenes: Microbiology, Sites of Infection and Treatment*, pp. 151–168. Nova Science Publishers.
3. Cossart, P., Lecuit, M., 2005. *Infection of Mammalian Cells by Listeria monocytogenes*. In *Bacterial Pathogenesis: A Molecular Approach*, pp. 465–485. ASM Press.
4. Drevets, D.A., Bronze, M.S., 2008, *Listeria monocytogenes*. In *Medical Microbiology*, 4th ed., pp. 115–120. Elsevier.
5. Fox, E.M. (Ed.). 2021, *Listeria monocytogenes: Methods and Protocols* (2nd ed.). Springer
6. Goldfine, H., Shen, H. (Eds.) 2007. *Listeria monocytogenes: Pathogenesis and Host Response*. Springer .
6. Goetz, C., Portnoy, D.A. 2002, *Listeria monocytogenes: Pathogenesis and Host Interactions*. In *Molecular Medical Microbiology*, pp. 1157–1172. Academic Press.
8. Hof, H., 2003, *Listeria monocytogenes: Pathogenesis and Host Interactions*. In *Medical Microbiology*, 4th ed., pp. 115–120. Elsevier.
9. Jordan, K. (Ed.), 2015. *Listeria monocytogenes: Methods and Protocols*. Springer .
10. Lecuit, M., Cossart, P. 2006, *Listeria monocytogenes: Pathogenesis and Host Interactions*. In *Medical Microbiology*, 4th ed., pp. 115–120. Elsevier.
4. and 86.7% CAMP-positive; hemolysis was variable, confirming phenotypic variability.
5. Urinary isolations may reflect true urinary infection, a sign of systemic dissemination, or possible contamination; clinical data are necessary to stratify cases.
6. The combination of morphological, staining, biochemical, and culture tests on selective media allows correct identification of *L. monocytogenes*, with molecular confirmation or MALDI-TOF recommended to avoid false negatives.
7. The results highlight that urinary *Listeria*, although rare in infants, may be more frequent in adults or patients with risk factors for complicated infections, correlating with observations from the literature.
11. Marquis, H., 2015, *Pathogenesis of Listeria monocytogenes in Humans*. In *Human Emerging and Re-emerging Infections: Viral and Parasitic Infections, Volume I*, pp. 497–510. Wiley-Blackwell .
12. Mehta, M., Divanshi, M., Raghu, H.V., 2022, *Risk Assessment of Listeria monocytogenes in Foods*. In *Listeria monocytogenes: Microbiology, Sites of Infection and Treatment*, pp. 91–108. Nova Science Publishers .
13. Miner, M.D., Port, G.C., Freitag, N.E., 2007. *Regulation of Listeria monocytogenes Virulence Genes*. In *Listeria monocytogenes: Pathogenesis and Host Response*, pp. 139–158. Springer .
14. Oliver, H.F., Wiedmann, M., Boor, K.J., 2007, *Environmental Reservoir and Transmission into the Mammalian Host*. In *Listeria monocytogenes: Pathogenesis and Host Response*, pp. 111–137. Springer .
15. Pizarro-Cerdà, J., Cossart, P., 2007, *Invasion of Host Cells by Listeria monocytogenes*. In *Listeria monocytogenes: Pathogenesis and Host Response*, pp. 159–176. Springer.
16. Portnoy, D.A., Goetz, C., 2002, *Listeria monocytogenes: Molecular Pathogenesis and Cellular Interactions*. In *Molecular Medical Microbiology*, pp. 1157–1172. Academic Press .
17. Pucciarelli, M.G., Bierne, H., García-del Portillo, F. 2007, *The Cell Wall of Listeria monocytogenes and its Role in Pathogenicity*. In *Listeria monocytogenes: Pathogenesis and Host Response*, pp. 81–110. Springer .

18. Quereda, J.J., et al., 2021, *Pathogenicity and Virulence of Listeria monocytogenes*. In *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 12:849654. Frontiers Media .
19. Rappai, J., Amrutha, T.A., Anjali, M.K., 2022, *Pathogenesis of Listeria monocytogenes*. In *Listeria monocytogenes: Microbiology, Sites of Infection and Treatment*, pp. 19–34. Nova Science Publishers .
20. Rusniok, C., Buchrieser, C., Glaser, P., 2007, *Listeria Genomics*. In *Listeria monocytogenes: Pathogenesis and Host Response*, pp. 33–62. Springer.
21. Shaevitz, J.W., Fletcher, D.A., 2007, *Curvature and Torsion in Growing Actin Networks*. In *Physical Review Letters*, 99(18):188103. American Physical Society .
22. Silva Guerreiro, M., Henriques, A.R., 2022, *Listeria monocytogenes in Food-Related Environments: An Overview of Contributing Factors for Thriving along the Food Chain*. In *Listeria monocytogenes: Microbiology, Sites of Infection and Treatment*, pp. 35–54. Nova Science Publishers .
23. Sibanda, T., 2022, *Listeria monocytogenes Pathogenesis: The Role of Stress Response Regulators*. In *Microorganisms*, 10(8):1522. MDPI

THE IMPACT OF COLORS AND VARIOUS SENSORY INTERPRETATIONS ON CONSUMER PERCEPTION OF FOOD QUALITY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Our analysis confirms that the senses are not independent of each other, and what we see can have repercussions on other perceptions and sensory interpretations related to color, taste, smell and touch. Everything that passes mainly through the visual channel certainly affects a series of sensory evaluations. Color and aroma cause us to perceive what we taste differently, evoking emotions that will influence the consumer's decision. The study was designed to provide an overview of empirical studies that investigated the influence of color on the perception of the psychosensory quality of the classic lemonade with mint and lemon, consumed from colored containers. Thus, the scientific approach to these perceptions provides a psychological explanation regarding the quality level of the tested food.

The colors of the serving containers of some food products on the perception and health of consumers are explained by mechanisms, which cannot be mutually exclusive. Thus, consumers rely on color as an explicit signal for health. Colors are indirectly associated with health, triggering mental simulations that influence health assessments. The color factor, as an important psychosensory attribute of food quality and as a result of anodyne emotional connections, allows the identification of health-risk behaviors. Color has a significant impact on various qualitative sensations and interpretations, which allows its strategic use as an element of attractiveness regarding food consumption, thus, approximately 90% of the initial product evaluations are based on color.

These evaluations provide suggestions for further research that will contribute to a better understanding of how packaging color can help consumers make informed food choices, with a positive impact on health.

Keywords: lemonade, mint, lemon, color, flavor

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INTRODUCTION

In today's dynamic environment, consumer choices are influenced by numerous factors, among which visual ones, represented by the color of the packaging, the nutritional label and even the serving containers play a key role in shaping perceptions of the quality of food and beverage products (Steiner & Florack, 2023, Song et al., 2021).

Strategic integration of colors and flavors in the design of solid or liquid food products is essential to improve the sensory experience of food and to determine consumers to accept a non-preferred product. Changing the color of food and beverages changes consumers' expectations, as well as their perception of taste and aroma.

The underlying mechanisms of these studies are based on color as an explicit signal for health (Halez et al., 2022, Marques Da Rosa

et al., 2021), on socio-cultural beliefs for evaluating health (Turnwald et al., 2022), and on color-triggered stimuli on psycho-emotional states with an impact on health (Kunz et al., 2023).

Although much research has focused on the impact of changing the color of the product itself, there is now a growing body of scientifically credible research evaluating the extent to which the color of the container from which food and beverages are served affects consumer perception and behavior regarding serving and consumption, based on taste and aroma (Spence, 2018).

In particular, in the case of soft drinks, such as lemonade, the perception of psychosensory quality can be influenced by factors such as the shade of the serving glass, its brightness and contrast (Steiner & Florack, 2023). Color not only affects consumers' expectations of taste and freshness (Plasek et

al., 2020), but can also influence the perception of superior nutritional quality, being a key element used in marketing strategies to attract and convince consumers (Steiner & Florack, 2023).

Spence (2018) in his analysis of the impact of the color of the serving container on the perception and eating behavior, focusing on the growing body of empirical research on the impact of the background color of plates, bowls, mugs, cups, glasses, pots and cutlery on and through which food and drinks can be viewed, both before and during consumption, concluded that the color factor modulates various aspects of our perception and eating behavior. Such effects have been demonstrated in various situations and with a wide variety of products, both familiar and unfamiliar, but without omitting the recording of apparently contradictory results exemplified by the fact that some consumers claim that eating from a blue tray reduces consumption, while others have suggested that eating from a blue plate leads to increased consumption (Spence, 2018).

Understanding how the color of the glass influences the perception of the taste and aroma of a classic lemonade drink involves a complex analysis of the interaction between the visual and gustatory senses. The perception of taste, according to neuroscience data, is not an isolated process, but the result of a multisensory integration in which sight, smell and even touch play an essential role.

Some studies have shown that red or orange glasses can intensify the perception of sweetness, even if the lemonade has the same amount of sugar. This phenomenon is explained by the fact that certain colors are subconsciously associated with sweet or fruity flavors. On the other hand, blue or green glasses can give the impression of a more refreshing and less sweet drink, since these colors are often associated with freshness and naturalness.

The shape and nature of the glass (glass or transparent plastic) also contribute to the perception of the quality of the lemonade. For example, tall and narrow glasses can create the impression that the drink is more refreshing, while wider and shallower glasses can emphasize the perception of density and richness of taste. In addition, the transparency of the glass allows for visual assessment of the color and consistency of the lemonade, thus influencing taste expectations. Another interesting aspect is the influence of the

brightness and saturation of the colors of the glass. Darker tones can be associated with a stronger and more intense taste, while pastel or light tones can suggest a more delicate and subtle taste. Also, the texture of the glass (smooth, matte or with embossed patterns) can influence the overall sensory perception, creating a different drinking experience.

Therefore, the color and design of the glass not only influence the perception of taste, but also the overall consumption experience. Understanding these mechanisms can be leveraged in the food and beverage industry to create more attractive products and increase consumer satisfaction. Exploring these subtle links between the visual and gustatory senses gives us a deeper insight into how we perceive and appreciate the taste of a beverage.

In this context, measuring the level of consumer knowledge regarding the impact of colors and the different psychosensory interpretations on the perception of the taste and aroma of lemonade becomes essential to understand how they interpret and evaluate products (Schnurr, 2019) leading to results on the frequency of consumption of that product and the degree of familiarity with classic lemonade (Song et al., 2021).

Our study has as its general objective the analysis of how consumers perceive and interpret visual information related to color in relation to the psychosensory quality of lemonade. In order to achieve this objective, several specific objectives were established:

1. Assessing the influence of factors: serving container hue, brightness and contrast in relation to the psychosensory quality of a classic lemonade-type soft drink

2. Measuring the level of consumer knowledge regarding the impact of colors and the different psychosensory interpretations on the perception of taste and freshness of lemonade

3. Exploring the factors that can moderate the level of understanding of the importance of the impact of colors on the perception of the quality of foods with functional potential on health and on consumption behavior.

This study was designed to make an important scientific contribution to improving the level of understanding of the impact of color on the perception of the quality of foods with functional health potential. Color thus occupies a defining position on the perception of the overall quality of foods, which allows it to change the perception of taste and aroma,

which will influence consumer preferences and perceived sensory attributes. At the same time, it facilitates the increase of interest in food research on the impact of colors, through the role of color indicators, on the perception of the quality of foods and beverages in order to reduce health risk behaviors.

Improving the behavior of purchasing and consuming nutritionally balanced foods can be achieved through adequate nutritional education (Chen et al., 2022), implemented since primary schools, using color codes in order to increase the degree of knowledge and information by applying an appropriate methodology. Such studies have a positive impact on the formation of healthy eating behaviors, reducing risky eating behaviors (WHO, 2023; ISPO, 2023), and contributing to a better understanding of informed food choices.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The variables monitored in this study are represented by the identification of the refreshing, citric/aromatic and sweet character of a soft drink, type classic lemonade with mint and lemon, distributed in glasses of different colors, served at the same temperature and concentration of lemon juice, sugar and mint. The degree of influence of color on the perception of the psychosensory quality of classic lemonade with mint and lemon with importance in informed food choices, according to needs, by consumers was monitored.

The evaluation criteria in this study were related to the following items:

ItL_1 managing the color of the lemonade serving container while keeping constant the factors of temperature and concentration of lemon juice, sugar and mint

ItL_2 evaluating the psychosensory properties as variables dependent on the color of the container

ItL_3 investigating the effect of the color of the serving container on the evaluation of the quality of lemonade

ItL_4 observing the psychological effect produced on the subjects taken into the study – children aged 12-15 years.

The study material was represented by a classic lemonade-type soft drink obtained from still water, lemon, sugar and mint.

Fig. 1. Experimental variants

Each glass was labeled using a serial number: 1, 2, 3, and 4, respectively. The color of the glass corresponding to each serial number was randomly determined, as follows: 1 – red glass, 2 – green glass, 3 – yellow glass, and 4 – blue glass.

The working hypothesis was to determine whether these colors could have a greater impact on the perception of the taste and aroma of classic mint and lemon lemonade.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The analysis of the results regarding the measurement of the level of knowledge and the impact of colors and different psychosensory interpretations on the perception of the taste and aroma of classic lemonade with mint and lemon becomes fundamental for understanding how consumers interpret and evaluate the quality of food products.

The results led to the observation that classic lemonade with mint and lemon, through a nutritional promotion appropriate to the age group (children 12-15 years old), also supported by the degree of familiarity with this product, could increase the frequency of consumption of soft drinks with nutrifunctional value to the detriment of processed juices.

Table 1

Distribution of the taste of classic lemonade with mint and lemon depending on the color of the container

	V1	V2	V3	V4
Intense refreshing taste	5.63%	33.8%	19.72%	45.07%
Pleasant refreshing taste	18.31%	30.99%	19.72%	35.21%
Lemon taste	29.58%	22.54%	39.44%	12.68%
Characteristic refreshing taste	45.07%	21.13%	11.27%	23.94%
Average	24.65%	27.12%	22.54%	29.23%
SD	16.77%	6.23%	11.95%	14.01%

The data on the distribution of the taste of classic lemonade with mint and lemon depending on the color of the serving container supports the significant impact of colors on the psychosensory perception of food products.

Classic lemonade with mint and lemon consumed from the blue glass (V4) (table 1) was perceived as having an intense refreshing taste in the highest proportion (45.07%) and the consumption of lemonade from the red glass (V1) was perceived as having an intense refreshing taste in the lowest proportion (5.63%).

The pleasant refreshing taste (table 1) was perceived in the highest proportions in the case of the consumption of lemonade from the blue and green glasses (V2) (35.21% and 30.99% respectively). The weakest pleasant refreshing taste was observed in the case of the consumption of lemonade from the orange (V3) and red glasses (V1) (19.72% and 18.31% respectively).

The most intense lemon taste (table 1) was recorded in the case of lemonade consumed from the orange glass (V3) (39.44%) and the least intense lemon taste was perceived in the case of lemonade consumed from the blue glass (V4) (12.68%).

The characteristic refreshing taste was perceived in the highest proportion in the case

of lemonade consumed from the red glass (V1) (45.07%).

Fig. 1. The influence of the color of the classic lemonade serving container on the perceived taste

The proportion of cooler tones, blue and green (V4 and V2) are associated with a more intense refreshing taste and a pleasant refreshing taste. Warmer tones, orange and red suggest a characteristic refreshing taste (figure 1).

Exploring the mechanisms of taste perception as a function of color can be exploited in the food and beverage industry to create more attractive products and increase consumer satisfaction with food quality (Zampini, et al., 2007). Thus, by optimizing visual attractiveness and by controlling sensory parameters such as taste and aroma, the choice of products with functional potential on health and consumption behavior can be supported, especially among children.

Table 2
Distribution of the flavor of classic lemonade with mint and lemon depending on the color of the container

	V1	V2	V3	V4
Intense flavour	25.33	22.19	47.27	5.21
Pleasant lemony flavour	27.15	18.97	45.17	8.71
Characteristic flavour	28.81	22.34	40.64	8.21
Fruity flavour	35.63	18.32	38.02	8.03
Average	29.23	20.46	42.78	7.54
SD	4.50	2.11	4.21	1.58

The color of the glass from which the classic lemonade with mint and lemon was consumed showed both intensification and moderation of the aroma, generating expectations that influenced the perception of this multisensory parameter composed of taste, smell and texture (hossain et al., 2025).

The most intense aroma (table 2) was perceived after the consumption of the classic lemonade

with mint and lemon from orange glasses (V3) (47.27%). The lowest aroma intensity was perceived when the lemonade was consumed from blue glasses (V4) (5.21%).

The same trend was observed in the evaluation of the pleasant lemony aroma (table 2). The orange color of the glass (V3) led to the perception of a pleasant lemony aroma of the lemonade with mint and lemon (45.17%).

The fruity aroma was perceived after consuming lemonade with mint and lemon from red and orange glasses (V12 and V3) in a proportion of 35.63% and 38.02%, respectively. Table 2 shows a reliable association of the color of the serving glass of classic lemonade with mint and lemon with the perceived aroma.

Fig. 2. The influence of the color of the classic lemonade serving container on the perceived taste

The proportion of warmer tones, red and orange (figure 1) are associated with a more intense, more lemony and fruity aroma. The green color of the glasses from which the classic lemonade with mint and lemon was consumed was appreciated similarly in all four aromatic variables without significant differences in the associated physiological responses. Blue tones led to a lower perception of the aroma of the classic lemonade with mint and lemon (figure 1).

Aroma perception is a complex integration of sensory input transmitted through a combination of chemical receptors activated by both taste-active and aroma-active metabolites, with the specification that the taste-active ones (usually primary) are non-volatile, but the secondary metabolites (flavonoids and limnoids) are aroma-active (reuss et al., 2020).

CONCLUSIONS

The influencing factor, color, certainly leads to different psychosensory perceptions and interpretations of taste and aroma.

Both in the case of the serving container and in the case of the color of the food, color leads to changes in consumers' beliefs regarding taste and aroma, due to the tendency to create associations of specific colors with specific products and associations with particular tastes.

The colors red and orange can be attributed to a sweet, fruity taste and convey superior taste sensations compared to the taste sensations generated by green and blue.

Colors such as blue and green can be attributed to a refreshing taste, convey the sensation of a cool-invigorating food, while also

conveying to the consumer the idea that it is a product with a high level of added value. The color green induces the idea of freshness and naturalness.

Changing the color of food and beverage serving containers changes people's expectations, as well as their perception of taste and aroma.

The use of color as a qualitative parameter requires understanding the theoretical basis of colorimetry and the consistent and meaningful implementation of research on reducing health-risk eating behaviors. should be added if the results and discussion part is long.

REFERENCES

- Steiner, K.; Florack, A. The Influence of Packaging Color on Consumer Perceptions of Healthfulness: A Systematic Review and Theoretical Framework. *Foods* **2023**, *12*, 3911..
- Song J, Brown MK, Tan M, MacGregor GA, Webster J, Campbell NRC, et al. (2021) Impact of color-coded and warning nutrition labelling schemes: A systematic review and network meta-analysis. *PLoS Med* 18(10): e1003765.
- Hallez L., Vansteenbeeck H., Boen F., Smits T. Persuasive Packaging? The Impact of Packaging Color and Claims on Young Consumers' Perceptions of Product Healthiness, Sustainability and Tastiness. *Appetite*. 2023;182:106433.
- Marques Da Rosa V., Spence C., Miletto Tonetto L. Influences of Visual Attributes of Food Packaging on Consumer Preference and Associations with Taste and Healthiness. *Int. J. Consum. Stud*. 2019;43:210–217.
- Charles Spence. Background colour & its impact on food perception & behaviour, *Food Quality and Preference*, Volume 68, 2018, Pages 156-166, ISSN 0950-3293,
- Turnwald B.P., Horii R.I., Markus H.R., Crum A.J. Psychosocial Context and Food Healthiness in Top-Grossing American Films. *Health Psychol*. 2022;41:928–937.
- Kunz S., Haasova S., Pivecka N., Schmidt J., Florack A. Food Is All Around: How Contexts Create Misbeliefs About the Health–Taste Relationship. *Psychol. Sci*. 2023;34:568–580. Spence, C. On the psychological impact of food colour. *Flavour* **4**, 21 (2015)..
- Plasek B., Lakner Z., Temesi Á. Factors influencing the perceived healthiness of foods—Review. *Nutrients*. 2020;12:1881. Schnurr B. Too Cute to Be Healthy: How Cute Packaging Designs Affect Judgments of Product Tastiness and Healthiness. *J. Assoc. Consum. Res*. 2019;4:363–375.
- Chen P.-J., Coricelli C., Kaya S., Rumiati RI, Foroni F. The Role of Associative Learning in Healthy and Sustainable Food Evaluations: An Event-Related Potential Study. *Neurosci. Res*. 2022;183:61–75. doi: 10.1016/j.neures.2022.07.002
- OMS Obezitatea și excesul de greutate. [(accesat la 12 septembrie 2023)]. Disponibil

- online: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/obesity-and-overweight>
- ISPO Shoppen per Autopilot: So Fallen Kaufentscheidungen. [(accessed on 12 September 2023)]. Available online: <https://www.ispo.com/maerkte/shoppen-autopilot-so-fallen-kaufentscheidungen>.
- Massimiliano Zampini, Daniel Sanabria, Nicola Phillips, Charles Spence, The multisensory perception of flavor: Assessing the influence of color cues on flavor discrimination responses, *Food Quality and Preference*, Volume 18, Issue 7, 2007, Pages 975-984, ISSN 0950-3293,.
- Reuss L, Feng S, Hung WL, Yu Q, Gmitter FG Jr, Wang Y. Analysis of flavor and other metabolites in lemon juice (Citrus limon) from Huanglongbing-affected trees grafted on different rootstocks. *J Food Drug Anal.* 2020 Jun 15;28(2):261-272.
- Lee, M., Kim D., Hwang IM și Chang JY. 2024. „Explorarea percepției aromelor prin profilarea metaboliților și abordări senzoriale în timpul fermentării starter a kimchi.” *Food Bioscience* 61: 104477.
- Hossain MS, Wazed MA, Asha S, Hossen MA, Fime SNM, Teeya ST, Jenny LY, Dash D, Shimul IM. Flavor and Well-Being: A Comprehensive Review of Food Choices, Nutrition, and Health Interactions. *Food Sci Nutr.* 2025 May 16;13(5):e70276..

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF RAW MILK: EXPERIMENTAL DETERMINATION OF ACIDITY AND CASEIN CONTENT

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Milk represents a complex biological fluid whose composition and physicochemical characteristics are essential indicators of its freshness and quality. Raw cow's milk samples collected from local markets in Oradea, Romania, were analyzed to evaluate key quality parameters, including acidity, ethanol stability, and casein content. Six samples from different local producers underwent organoleptic examination, titratable acidity determination, and protein quantification. The sensory evaluation showed uniform color, texture, odor, and taste, consistent with fresh milk characteristics. Acidity values ranged from 16.0 to 23.0 °T, where samples with higher acidity formed aggregates in the ethanol test, indicating reduced freshness. Casein concentrations varied between 31.0 and 52.6 g/L (3.1–5.3%), with higher values associated with better protein stability and lower acidity levels. These findings highlight the strong relationship between acidity, casein concentration, and overall milk quality, emphasizing their combined relevance as indicators of freshness and suitability for consumption or further processing.

Keywords: casein quantification, milk acidity, physicochemical parameters, freshness indicators
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INTRODUCTION

Milk is one of the most complete and valuable natural foods, providing essential nutrients such as proteins, fats, carbohydrates, vitamins, and minerals that support human growth and health. It plays a central role in the diet of both children and adults and serves as an important raw material for the dairy industry. Globally, milk production exceeds 900 million tons per year, emphasizing its nutritional and economic significance (Acquavia et al., 2025; Górska-Warsewicz et al., 2019; Sarode et al., 2016).

Milk represents a complex colloidal system in which fat globules, casein micelles, and whey proteins are dispersed in an aqueous phase containing lactose and mineral salts. Its physicochemical characteristics are influenced by both intrinsic compositional factors and extrinsic factors such as temperature variations and post-milking handling. Among milk proteins, casein constitutes about 80% of the total protein content and plays a crucial role in determining milk stability, processing behavior, and nutritional value (Corredig et al., 2019; Zheng et al., 2023).

The acidity of milk is a key parameter for evaluating its freshness and quality. Natural acidity arises from normal milk constituents

such as casein, phosphates, and citrates, while microbial activity during storage leads to the conversion of lactose into lactic acid, resulting in increased titratable acidity and lower pH values. Monitoring these parameters provides insight into both the chemical balance and hygienic status of milk (Aydogdu et al., 2023; Linehan et al., 2024).

This study focuses on assessing the physicochemical profile of raw cow's milk collected from local markets, aiming to highlight variations in composition and quality among samples obtained from different local producers.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

SAMPLES

Six cow milk samples were collected from distinct local producers at a fresh food market in Oradea, Romania. The samples were maintained in sealed containers at ambient temperature until analysis to preserve their original physicochemical properties.

REAGENTS AND SOLUTIONS

Analytical grade reagents were used throughout the study. Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) 0.1 N (Chimreactiv, Romania); hydrochloric acid (HCl) 0.1 N (Chimreactiv,

Romania); and 0.5 N, sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) 0.1 N (Chimreactiv, Romania); acetic acid 1 N (Chimreactiv, Romania); ethanol p.a 59–61 % v/v (Chimreactiv, Romania); phenolphthalein 1 % alcoholic solution (Silver Chemicals) ; and methyl red 0.2 % alcoholic solution (Remed Prodimpex); distilled water.

METHODS

Organoleptic Evaluation: Milk samples were evaluated for color, opacity, consistency, appearance, odor, and taste. Observations were made under natural light, and consistency and appearance were assessed visually, while odor and taste were determined by sensory evaluation.

Free Acidity (pH): The pH of milk was measured using pH indicator paper, with results compared against a standard color scale to determine free acidity. Normal cow milk has a slightly acidic pH ranging from 6.4 to 6.7.

Titrateable Acidity: Milk titrateable acidity was determined by titration with NaOH in the presence of phenolphthalein (Miere et al., 2012). Results were expressed in degrees Thörner (°T) using the formula:

$$\text{Acidity (}^{\circ}\text{T)} = N \cdot F \cdot 10$$

N - volume of 0.1 N NaOH used for titration (mL);

10 - factor to refer the result to 100 mL of milk;

F- factor of the solution NaOH 0,1 N.

Casein Content: Casein was precipitated by adding acetic acid to milk in the presence of methyl red. The precipitate was filtered, washed to neutrality, and dissolved in NaOH. Excess NaOH was titrated with H₂SO₄ using phenolphthalein as an indicator (Husnaeni et al., 2019; Kumaresan et al., 2017). Casein content (g/L milk) was calculated using:

$$\text{Casein (g/L)} = 11 \cdot (V_1 - V_2)$$

V₁ - volume of NaOH 0,1 N used to dissolve the casein;

V₂ - volume of H₂SO₄ 0,1 N used to neutralize the excess NaOH 0,1 N.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The organoleptic evaluation of the cow milk samples revealed slight variations in color, ranging from white to pale yellow, with a homogeneous and fluid consistency in all cases. No flakes or sediment were observed, and all samples presented the characteristic odor of fresh raw milk. Heating the samples to 35–40°C did not reveal any abnormal odors, and the taste was consistent with fresh milk, slightly sweet and pleasant.

The main physicochemical parameters of the milk samples, including acidity, ethanol test results, and casein content, are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1

Physicochemical parameters and casein composition of cow milk

Sample	Acidity (°Thörner)	Ethanol test	Casein content (g/L)	Casein percentage (%)
1	23.0	Numerous large coagulates formed, indicating high acidity and low freshness	34.87 ± 1.2	3.49 ± 0.12
2	17.0	Small precipitate deposited on the tube walls, indicating moderate acidity and medium freshness	42.02 ± 1.4	4.20 ± 0.14
3	20.5	Precipitate observed on the tube walls	45.10 ± 1.0	4.51 ± 0.10
4	16.0	No coagulation observed, indicating low acidity and very fresh milk	52.58 ± 1.6	5.26 ± 0.16
5	16.5	Minor precipitate deposited on the tube walls, acidity within normal limits	46.75 ± 1.3	4.68 ± 0.13
6	20.0	Precipitate observed on the tube walls	31.02 ± 1.5	3.10 ± 0.15

The acidity of the samples, expressed in Thörner degrees (°T), varied between 16.0 and 23.0 °T. According to the literature, normal milk acidity ranges between 16–18 °T or, depending on the source, 15–20 °T. Some samples fell within this range, indicating freshness, while others exhibited elevated acidity, suggesting a decline in quality. This was further confirmed by the ethanol test: samples with higher acidity formed numerous aggregates, whereas those

with moderate acidity showed minor precipitate formation, and samples with low acidity remained clear, consistent with very fresh milk. This reaction is known to occur when milk proteins (particularly casein) destabilize under increased ionic and acidic stress, suggesting a correlation between ethanol stability and freshness.

Casein content varied considerably among the analyzed samples, ranging from 31.0 to 52.6 g/L, corresponding to 3.1–5.3% of the

milk. These concentrations are consistent with previously reported data, where average casein levels in bovine milk were found to be around 29.5 g/L (Davoodi et al., 2016) and between 4.47–4.77% in cow milk samples (Pamarthy et al., 2016). A clear relationship was observed between milk freshness and protein content: the freshest samples with low acidity exhibited the highest casein concentrations, whereas samples with elevated acidity contained lower casein levels, reflecting potential protein degradation.

CONCLUSIONS

The analyzed milk samples exhibited moderate variability in their physicochemical properties, reflecting differences in freshness and overall quality. Samples with elevated acidity showed signs of reduced protein stability, whereas those with acidity values within the normal range maintained characteristics consistent with fresh milk. Casein content proved to be a critical determinant of milk quality, with higher concentrations associated with improved protein stability and indicators of freshness.

These observations underscore the interrelated roles of acidity and casein concentration in defining the quality of raw cow's milk, providing a reliable basis for assessing its suitability for consumption and further processing.

REFERENCES

- Acquavia, M.A., Villone, A., Rubino, R. and Bianco, G., 2025. A Comprehensive Review of Milk Components: Recent Developments on Extraction and Analysis Methods. *Molecules*, 30(9), p.1994.
- Aydogdu, T., O'Mahony, J.A. and McCarthy, N.A., 2023. pH, the Fundamentals for Milk and Dairy Processing: A Review. *Dairy*, 4(3), pp.395–409.
- Corredig, M., Nair, P.K., Li, Y., Eshpari, H. and Zhao, Z., 2019. Invited review: Understanding the behavior of caseins in milk concentrates. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 102(6), pp.4772–4782.
- Davoodi, S.H., Shahbazi, R., Esmaeili, S., Sohrabvandi, S., Mortazavian, A., Jazayeri, S. and Taslimi, A., 2016. Health-Related Aspects of Milk Proteins. *Iranian journal of pharmaceutical research: IJPR*, 15(3), pp.573–591.
- Górska-Warsewicz, H., Rejman, K., Laskowski, W. and Czeczotko, M., 2019. Milk and Dairy Products and Their Nutritional Contribution to the Average Polish Diet. *Nutrients*, 11(8), p.1771.
- Husnaeni, Maruddin, F., Malaka, R. and Prahesti, K.I., 2019. Study on the use of various concentration of acetic acid and different precipitation duration on casein characteristics. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 343(1), p.012035.
- Kumaresan, A., Selma, C., Reshma, N. and Angelin Jacinth, N., 2017. Quantitative Analysis of Casein Precipitation from the Various Milk Samples. *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research*, 9(9), pp.113–115.
- Linehan, K., Patangia, D., Ross, R. and Stanton, C., 2024. Production, Composition and Nutritional Properties of Organic Milk: A Critical Review. *Foods*, 13(4), p.550.
- Miere, D., Filip, L., Banc, R. and Cozma, A., 2012. *Chemistry and Environmental Hygiene, Practical Work Cluj Napoca: University Medical Publishing House 'Iuliu Hațieganu'*.
- Pamarthy, J., Bhat, V. and M.K., S., 2016. A Comparative Study on Casein and Albumin Contents in Cow and Commercial Milk Samples. *IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences*, 15(1), pp.102–106.
- Sarode, A.R., Kalyankar, S.D., Deosarkar, S.S., Khedkar, C.D. and Pawshe, R.D., 2016. Milk: Role in the Diet. In: *Encyclopedia of Food and Health*. Elsevier. pp.736–740.
- Zheng, L., Wang, C. and Zhao, M., 2023. Production of bioactive peptides from bovine caseins. In: *Enzymes Beyond Traditional Applications in Dairy Science and Technology*. Elsevier. pp.163–187.

A REVIEW REGARDING FOOD CONSUMPTION IN ROMANIA – TRENDS, CHALLENGES AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPLICATIONS IN THE POST-PANDEMIC CONTEXT

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REVIEW

Abstract

This paper presents a review regarding food consumption in Romania, emphasizing recent trends, challenges, and socio-economic implications in the post-pandemic context. The study identifies a diet still dominated by cereals, dairy, and meat, with moderate growth in fruit and vegetable intake. The COVID-19 pandemic caused major behavioral changes, driving a shift toward basic foods and revealing inequalities between income groups. Post-pandemic inflation further limited access to balanced diets, especially among vulnerable households. Despite these pressures, a gradual move toward more diversified and sustainable food consumption is evident. The review concludes that Romania is undergoing a slow transformation of dietary habits, influenced by economic and social factors, and highlights the need for coherent public policies to ensure food security, affordability, and sustainability.

Keywords: COVID-19 pandemic; consumer behavior; post-pandemic trends.

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INTRODUCTION

Food consumption represents one of the most sensitive components of economic and social behavior, situated at the intersection of resource availability, cultural preferences, and the population's socio-economic conditions. In the current global context—marked by the COVID-19 pandemic, subsequent economic and energy crises, and the intensification of inflationary phenomena—the analysis of food consumption becomes essential for understanding the level of well-being and food security at the national level (FAO, 2022; Eurostat, 2023).

In Romania, the structure of food consumption reflects a combination of traditional dietary patterns specific to Eastern Europe and the socio-economic transformations accelerated over the past two decades. Although household incomes have gradually increased, the high share of food expenditures in total household budgets remains one of the largest in the European Union, exceeding 24% in 2022 (Eurostat, 2023). This strong dependence on food prices highlights a significant economic vulnerability, directly influencing the population's access to a balanced and healthy diet.

The COVID-19 pandemic acted as a catalyst for change in food consumption behaviors. Mobility restrictions, economic uncertainty, and limited access to goods led to a reorientation toward basic food products, a reduction in dietary diversity, and an increase in the consumption of processed foods (Dumitras et al., 2021).

At the same time, higher-income households adopted more sustainable and health-conscious consumption patterns, including a growing preference for online grocery shopping, thereby intensifying the polarization among population segments (Mureșan, 2022). From a macroeconomic perspective, the pandemic and successive crises have revealed the fragility of the national food system, emphasizing the need for resilient and sustainable food policies (World Bank, 2023). In this regard, the analysis of food consumption trends in Romania has not only a descriptive dimension but also a strategic one, offering valuable insights for public policy formulation and for optimizing food production and distribution systems.

This paper aims to provide a comprehensive synthesis of the main trends and determinants of food consumption in Romania during the period 2020–2023, combining theoretical insights with empirical analysis.

The main objective is to highlight the changes in food consumption structure resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic and subsequent socio-economic transformations, as well as to identify future trends in Romanian food consumption behaviors. The study adopts a review-based approach, complemented by a statistical evaluation of data provided by the National Institute of Statistics (INSSE) and Eurostat, in order to identify structural changes in consumption behavior, socio-economic implications, and future directions in the post-pandemic context.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The analysis of food consumption patterns has evolved from a descriptive economic topic into an interdisciplinary field that integrates economic behavior, public health, and sustainability. Scholars increasingly emphasize that food consumption reflects not only purchasing power but also social norms, cultural identity, and environmental awareness (Reisch et al., 2021; FAO, 2021).

At the European level, recent research highlights a gradual transition toward sustainable and health-oriented diets, aligned with the objectives of the European Green Deal and the Farm to Fork Strategy (European Commission, 2020). These transformations include an increased consumption of fruits, vegetables, and plant-based alternatives, along with a gradual decline in red meat consumption (European Food Safety Authority, 2022). However, the pace of transition varies significantly across regions, being slower in Central and Eastern Europe due to income disparities and structural limitations in food markets (Eurostat, 2023; OECD, 2023).

In Romania, food consumption patterns have remained relatively stable, maintaining a predominantly carbohydrate-based diet, while the intake of protein-rich and nutrient-dense foods has grown only modestly (INSSE, 2023). Studies show that food consumption is still strongly influenced by price sensitivity and income inequality, reflecting a low elasticity of demand for essential food items (Popescu, 2019; Bărbulescu, 2023). These findings confirm that the Romanian food system continues to face challenges related to affordability, accessibility, and quality.

The COVID-19 pandemic further amplified these structural constraints. Dumitraș et al. (2021)

demonstrated that Romanian consumers shifted toward basic, storable, and affordable food products, such as bread, dairy, and potatoes, while reducing the frequency of grocery purchases. Mureșan (2022) observed a dual behavioral pattern: while lower-income households reduced diet diversity, higher-income consumers increased spending on healthier and local products, signaling a polarization of food choices during the pandemic. Other authors (Bran et al., 2021; Smedescu & Dinu, 2022) stressed the digital acceleration of the food sector, highlighting how e-commerce became an essential channel for food distribution during lockdowns. This process encouraged the modernization of supply chains and created new opportunities for small local producers, but also introduced challenges related to logistics, price transparency, and consumer trust (Fernández et al., 2023).

Furthermore, the pandemic coincided with a surge in food inflation and global supply chain disruptions, whose effects persist in the post-pandemic context. According to the World Bank (2023), rising food prices disproportionately affected Eastern European economies, increasing the risk of nutritional insecurity among vulnerable groups. Research on consumer psychology (Mattioli et al., 2022) shows that post-crisis food choices are shaped by both economic constraints and perceived food safety, with sustainability and local origin emerging as new decision criteria.

At the same time, several studies underline the importance of environmental sustainability and the reduction of food waste in shaping future food policies (FAO, 2022; OECD, 2023). In Romania, recent initiatives promoting sustainable consumption—such as community-supported agriculture (CSA) and short food supply chains—remain at an early stage but show growing potential for resilience and inclusivity (Bărbulescu, 2023).

Overall, the review of the literature reveals that food consumption in Romania is influenced by a combination of economic, social, and environmental factors, embedded in a rapidly changing global context. The convergence between the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic, inflationary pressures, and sustainability objectives outlines a complex landscape in which households continuously adapt their

dietary habits to maintain balance between affordability, health, and resilience.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The analysis of food consumption in Romania over the period 2015–2023 reveals several significant trends that reflect both the influence of the socio-economic context and the transformations triggered by the COVID-19 pandemic. Data compiled from the *Food Balance Sheets* published by the National Institute of Statistics (INSSE, 2023) indicate a relatively stable structure of food consumption, typical of emerging economies in Central and Eastern Europe, yet with a gradual tendency toward diversification in recent years. In 2023, average per capita food consumption in Romania continued to be dominated by cereals and cereal-based products, which remain the foundation of the national diet, exceeding 90 kg/person/year. They are followed by milk and dairy products (70–80 kg/person/year) and meat and meat products (60–65 kg/person/year), while vegetables and fruits each account for approximately 60 kg/person/year.

This structure, illustrated in *Figure 1 – Per capita food consumption in Romania (2023)*, confirms the persistence of a traditional dietary pattern based on a mix of plant and animal products. At the same time, a slight increase in meat and dairy consumption can be observed, associated with post-pandemic economic recovery and improvements in household living standards. The evolution of food consumption between 2021 and 2022 (as shown in *Figure 2 – Evolution of per capita food consumption in Romania*) reveals a general trend of stabilization, with moderate fluctuations during the pandemic years. In 2020, there was a temporary decline in fruit and vegetable consumption, mainly due to mobility restrictions, supply chain disruptions, and

higher prices for fresh produce. Conversely, the 2021–2023 period marks a gradual recovery, supported by the resumption of economic activities and the adaptation of consumer behavior.

Across major food groups, the data suggest a slow transition toward a more diversified diet, though consumption remains strongly influenced by economic factors. The moderate increase in meat, dairy, and egg consumption reflects both improved disposable incomes and a preference for foods perceived as “safe” in times of uncertainty. Meanwhile, the stagnation in sugar and fat consumption may indicate rising awareness of nutritional risks and the positive influence of health education campaigns (Mureşan, 2022).

The COVID-19 pandemic had a profound impact on food consumption behavior. Previous research (Dumitras et al., 2021; Bran et al., 2021) indicates that Romanian consumers exhibited a clear shift toward staple foods and reduced shopping frequency, particularly in urban areas. Among low-income households, economic uncertainty and mobility restrictions led to simplified dietary patterns, with increased reliance on inexpensive, long-shelf-life products such as bread, potatoes, and canned goods. In contrast, higher-income households displayed more selective and health-oriented food choices, preferring local, organic products and online purchases. This polarization underscores a growing fragmentation of the Romanian food market, where income disparities play an increasingly decisive role in shaping dietary behavior.

After 2022, economic recovery overlapped with food inflation and rising energy costs, creating new constraints on consumption. According to Eurostat (2023) and the World Bank (2023), Romania recorded some of the highest food price increases within the European Union,

significantly affecting the ability of vulnerable households to maintain a balanced diet. The direct consequence of this trend was a decline in meat and fruit consumption among lower-income segments and a corresponding increase in the share of staple foods such as cereals, potatoes, and vegetable oils. Consequently, the post-pandemic dynamics of food consumption appear to reflect adaptive economic strategies rather than voluntary lifestyle changes.

The results suggest that disposable income, price dynamics, and nutritional education are the main determinants of food consumption patterns in Romania. While the overall dietary structure remains relatively stable, a gradual divergence between urban and rural models of consumption is becoming evident. Urban consumers show greater openness toward healthy, local, and sustainable products, whereas rural households continue to favor traditional, locally sourced, or home-produced foods.

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of food consumption trends in Romania between 2015 and 2023 reveals a relatively stable dietary structure, yet a slow progression toward diversification, influenced by economic, social, and cultural factors. The COVID-19 pandemic marked a major turning point, temporarily altering purchasing and eating behaviors, widening income-based disparities, and exposing household vulnerability to economic uncertainty. The post-pandemic period has been characterized by strong inflationary pressures, which have constrained access to high-quality food and maintained a high share of food expenditure within household budgets. Nevertheless, a gradual transition toward more conscious and sustainable food consumption can be observed, supported by income growth, the digitalization of food retail, and increasing interest in local and health-oriented products.

The findings confirm that the main determinants of food consumption in Romania are disposable income, price dynamics, and nutritional education. Moreover, a clear divide between urban and rural environments is evident, reflected both in food preferences and in access to diverse and safe products.

Looking ahead, there is a need to develop integrated public policies that ensure equitable

access to healthy food, promote local production and short supply chains, enhance nutritional education, and reduce food waste. The consolidation of food security in Romania depends on the ability of institutions and society to balance the economic, social, and environmental sustainability of the national food system.

REFERENCES

- Bran, F., Ioan, I. & Popa, M. (2021) 'Food retail and digital transformation during COVID-19 pandemic', *Management & Marketing Journal*, 19(3), pp. 233–245.
- Dumitras, D.E. et al. (2021) 'Food Consumption Patterns in Romania during the COVID-19 Pandemic', PMC.
- European Commission (2020) *Farm to Fork Strategy: For a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system*, Brussels.
- European Food Safety Authority (2022) *Dietary patterns and health outcomes in Europe*, EFSA Report.
- Eurostat (2023) *Food and non-alcoholic beverage expenditure*, [online].
- Eurostat (2023) *Household consumption expenditure on food and non-alcoholic beverages*, [online].
- FAO (2021) *The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World*, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- FAO (2022) *Food Waste Index Report 2022*, United Nations Environment Programme.
- FAO (2022) *The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World*, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- Fernández, C., García, J. & Soler, R. (2023) 'Digital food supply chains and consumer trust after COVID-19', *Sustainability Journal*, 15(6), 5123.
- INSSE (2023) *Food Balance Sheets 2015–2023*, National Institute of Statistics, Bucharest.
- Mattioli, F., Contini, C. & Boncinelli, F. (2022) 'Consumer behavior and perceived risk in post-pandemic food markets', *Food Policy*, 112, 102350.
- Mureşan, I.C. (2022) 'Factors Affecting Food Consumers' Behavior during COVID-19', PubMed.
- OECD (2023) *Agricultural Policy Monitoring and Evaluation 2023*, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development.
- Popescu, G. (2019) 'Determinants of food consumption in Romania', *Economic Studies Journal*, 27(2), pp. 73–89.
- Reisch, L., Bietz, S. & Zhao, M. (2021) 'Consumer food choices and sustainability transitions in Europe', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 315, 128123.
- Smedescu, A. & Dinu, A. (2022) 'E-commerce expansion in the Romanian food sector post-COVID', *Sustainability Journal*, 14(9), 155–170.
- World Bank (2023) *Global Economic Prospects: Food Inflation and Household Welfare*, Washington, D.C.

THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF HONEY – THE COMPLEXITY OF A NATURAL FOOD

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REVIEW ARTICLE

Abstract

Honey, a natural product derived from floral nectar by Apis mellifera, represents one of the most complex functional foods of natural origin. Recent research has highlighted a wide spectrum of biological activities, including anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antifungal, antihypertensive, hypoglycemic, and hepatoprotective effects. The chemical composition of honey is dominated by sugars—monosaccharides, disaccharides, oligosaccharides, and polysaccharides—but also includes enzymes (catalase, peroxidase, diastase, invertase, glucose oxidase), organic acids, amino acids, proteins, vitamins, trace elements, and Maillard reaction products. Bioactive phenolic compounds, particularly flavonoids such as chrysin, kaempferol, quercetin, pinobanksin, pinocembrin, luteolin, apigenin, genistein, naringenin, and hesperetin, play an essential role, contributing significantly to the therapeutic potential of honey. The aim of this paper is to provide an updated overview of the chemical composition of honey and to highlight its beneficial health properties, emphasizing the complexity and medical relevance of this natural product.

Keywords: Honey, chemical composition, phenolic compounds, volatile compounds, antioxidants.

INTRODUCTION

Apiculture is the knowledge and art of utilizing hive products—such as honey, royal jelly, propolis, bee venom, and bee bread—for the maintenance and support of health. In recent years, these natural products have attracted growing interest due to their applicability in both traditional and modern medicine, with numerous studies highlighting their pharmacological effects and health benefits (Pasupuleti et al., 2017).

Apitherapy, a branch of traditional medicine, employs bee products in the treatment of various conditions, with honey standing out as one of the oldest and most valuable products, renowned for its medicinal and health-promoting properties (Badolato et al., 2017). Honey is a sweet and viscous substance produced by Apis mellifera from floral or extrafloral nectar, with a complex composition that determines the variability of its color, consistency, and aroma (Chen et al., 2019; Jaganathan & Mandal, 2009). In general, darker honey exhibits a stronger taste and a higher content of bioactive compounds (Jaganathan & Mandal, 2009). It is commonly consumed in its natural state—liquid, crystallized, or in the comb—and is used both as a food and as a medicine (Olaitan et al., 2007).

According to European Community legislation, honey is defined as “the natural sweet substance produced by bees from the nectar of plants or from secretions of living parts of plants, which bees collect, transform, dehydrate, and store in honeycombs for maturation” (Hills et al., 2019). Before the scientific basis of its composition was understood, honey was empirically used in the treatment of a wide range of ailments. Today, modern research confirms its antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and even antitumor effects, as well as its beneficial role in cardiovascular, metabolic, and digestive health (Khan et al., 2017; Miguel et al., 2017).

Honey is also recognized for its applicability both orally and topically, in conditions such as laryngitis, gastrointestinal ulcers, constipation, eczema, burns, infected wounds, and scars (Fakhlaei et al., 2020).

The aim of this presentation, entitled “The Chemical Composition of Honey – The Complexity of a Natural Food”, is to provide an updated overview of honey’s chemical composition and its multiple implications for human health, emphasizing both the complexity of this natural product and its value as a food and therapeutic adjuvant.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

A literature review was conducted to synthesize recent scientific data regarding the chemical composition of honey and its therapeutic potential. The search was restricted to articles published in English and indexed in online databases such as PubMed, Elsevier, Wiley, and Google Scholar. Relevant keywords—including honey, chemical composition, phenolic compounds, volatile compounds, antioxidants.— were used to identify suitable studies.

The initial search yielded 1,074 results. After applying inclusion and exclusion criteria, approximately 250 articles were selected for detailed evaluation. Abstracts and full texts were analyzed, classified, and interpreted to determine the relevance, validity, and therapeutic applicability of the reported findings. Subsequently, the data were synthesized to provide an updated overview of the chemical composition of honey and its beneficial health effects.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Honey is a natural food of remarkable chemical complexity, containing more than 200 identified compounds. Its main components are sugars and water, along with vitamins (particularly B-group vitamins and vitamin C), minerals (K, Na, Ca, Mg, Zn, Fe, Cu, Mn, P), proteins (including enzymes), organic acids, pigments, phenolic compounds, volatile compounds, and lipids, as well as low levels of hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) (Magazù et al., 2008).

The molecular composition of honey varies depending on botanical and geographical origin, climatic conditions, and processing methods (Manyi-Loh et al., 2011; Viuda-Martos et al., 2008). Among the amino acids present are glycine, methionine, arginine, and especially proline, considered a quality marker (Giusto et al., 2017). Proteins include enzymes such as glucose oxidase, invertase, diastase, peroxidase, and catalase, as well as non-enzymatic proteins (Erejuwa et al., 2012; Machado De-Melo et al., 2018).

Carbohydrates account for approximately 95% of the dry matter, the most important being fructose ($\approx 41\%$), glucose ($\approx 34\%$), and sucrose (1–2%), along with more than 45 oligosaccharides (Machado De-Melo et al., 2018). Organic acids, particularly gluconic acid (70–90%), contribute to taste, aroma, and antimicrobial properties (Machado De-Melo et al., 2018; Santos-Buelga & González-Paramás,

2017). Vitamins occur in small amounts, with vitamin C and B-group vitamins (B1, B2, B5, B6, B8, B9) being predominant (Machado De-Melo et al., 2018; da Silva et al., 2016). Minerals, especially potassium, are more abundant in darker honeys (Machado De-Melo et al., 2018; Santos-Buelga & González-Paramás, 2017).

Phenolic compounds and flavonoids (quercetin, kaempferol, chrysin, luteolin, apigenin, naringenin, pinocembrin) are responsible for antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties (Machado De-Melo et al., 2018; da Silva et al., 2016). Over 600 volatile compounds (aldehydes, ketones, esters, terpenes, hydrocarbons) contribute to the specific aroma (Machado De-Melo et al., 2018; Tafere, 2021; Santos-Buelga & González-Paramás, 2017). Other constituents include pigments (carotenoids, xanthophylls, anthocyanins), lipids ($\approx 0.04\%$), and essential oils (thymol, bisabolol, farnesol, cineole) (Machado De-Melo et al., 2018). Hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) is present only in traces in fresh honey, increasing during processing and storage (Machado De-Melo et al., 2018; Tafere, 2021; Bogdanov, 2016). The water content (15–21%) influences crystallization, viscosity, and stability, with lower levels ($<14\%$) indicating superior quality (Tafere, 2021; da Silva et al., 2016).

The findings confirm that honey is a food with an extremely complex chemical composition, consisting of more than 200 bioactive compounds. This diversity explains the variability of its organoleptic and therapeutic properties, as well as the growing interest in its use as a functional food and nutraceutical agent (Magazù et al., 2008). The composition of honey is not uniform but depends largely on botanical origin, climate, and geographical factors, leading to significant differences in sugar, amino acid, mineral, and phenolic content (Manyi-Loh et al., 2011; Viuda-Martos et al., 2008). The identification of proline as a quality marker is particularly important for detecting adulteration and assessing authenticity (Giusto et al., 2017).

Carbohydrates, which constitute the majority of the dry matter, provide not only energy value but also physicochemical properties such as hygroscopicity and crystallization, which influence preservation and market acceptability (Machado De-Melo et al., 2018). Organic acids, vitamins, and minerals, although present in smaller amounts, contribute to honey's biological activity, particularly its antimicrobial and antioxidant properties

(Machado De-Melo et al., 2018; Santos-Buelga & González-Paramás, 2017; da Silva et al., 2016). The predominance of potassium and the higher mineral content in darker honeys highlight the significance of botanical and chromatic origin for nutritional value (Machado De-Melo et al., 2018; Santos-Buelga & González-Paramás, 2017).

Phenolic compounds and flavonoids (such as quercetin, kaempferol, or chrysin) play a major role in anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties, explaining both the traditional and modern therapeutic uses of honey (Machado De-Melo et al., 2018; da Silva et al., 2016). At the same time, volatile compounds and pigments provide honey with unique organoleptic characteristics that enhance consumer acceptance (Machado De-Melo et al., 2018; Santos-Buelga & González-Paramás, 2017).

The presence of hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) as an indicator of freshness and the impact of water content on stability and quality underline the need for rigorous processing and storage methods (Machado De-Melo et al., 2018; Tafere, 2021; da Silva et al., 2016; Bogdanov, 2016).

Overall, the complex composition of honey supports both its nutritional value and therapeutic potential. However, the wide variability determined by environmental and processing factors suggests the need for further research aimed at standardizing quality parameters and establishing stronger correlations between chemical composition and biological effects.

CONCLUSIONS

Honey represents a complex natural food, with a highly diverse chemical composition that includes more than 200 bioactive compounds. This diversity accounts for its nutritional and organoleptic properties as well as its demonstrated therapeutic effects.

The reviewed findings confirm that sugars, amino acids, organic acids, vitamins, minerals, phenolic compounds, pigments, and volatile compounds act synergistically to contribute to honey's biological activity, providing antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and cardioprotective effects.

At the same time, honey's chemical composition is influenced by factors such as botanical origin, geographical location, and processing methods, which explain the variability observed among different types of honey. Indicators such as proline and

hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) prove to be useful for assessing product quality and authenticity.

Considering these aspects, honey emerges as a valuable nutraceutical, with potential for integration into the prevention and support of treatment for chronic diseases. Nevertheless, further studies are required to standardize composition and to establish clear correlations between chemical content and clinical effects.

REFERENCES

- Badolato, M.; Carullo, G.; Cione, E.; Aiello, F.; Caroleo, M.C. From the hive: Honey, a novel weapon against cancer. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry* 2017, 142, 290-299, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2017.07.064>.
- Bogdanov, S. Honey Composition. *Bee Product Science* 2016.
- Chen, C.-T.; Chen, B.-Y.; Nai, Y.-S.; Chang, Y.-M.; Chen, K.-H.; Chen, Y.-W. Novel inspection of sugar residue and origin in honey based on the ¹³C/¹²C isotopic ratio and protein content. *Journal of Food and Drug Analysis* 2019, 27, 175-183, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfda.2018.08.004>.
- da Silva, P.M.; Gauche, C.; Gonzaga, L.V.; Costa, A.C.; Fett, R. Honey: Chemical composition, stability and authenticity. *Food Chem* 2016, 196, 309-323, doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2015.09.051.
- Erejuwa, O.O.; Sulaiman, S.A.; Ab Wahab, M.S. Honey: a novel antioxidant. *Molecules* 2012, 17, 4400-4423.
- Fakhlaei, R.; Selamat, J.; Khatib, A.; Razis, A.F.A.; Sukor, R.; Ahmad, S.; Babadi, A.A. The Toxic Impact of Honey Adulteration: A Review. *Foods* 2020, 9, doi:10.3390/foods9111538.
- Giusto, G.; Vercelli, C.; Comino, F.; Caramello, V.; Tursi, M.; Gandini, M. A new, easy-to-make pectin-honey hydrogel enhances wound healing in rats. *BMC Complement Altern Med* 2017, 17, 266, doi:10.1186/s12906-017-1769-1.
- Hills, S.P.; Mitchell, P.; Wells, C.; Russell, M. Honey supplementation and exercise: a systematic review. *Nutrients* 2019, 11, 1586.
- Jaganathan, S.K.; Mandal, M. Antiproliferative effects of honey and of its polyphenols: a review. *J Biomed Biotechnol* 2009, 2009, 830616, doi:10.1155/2009/830616.
- Khan, R.U.; Naz, S.; Abudabos, A.M. Towards a better understanding of the therapeutic applications and corresponding mechanisms of action of honey. *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int* 2017, 24, 27755-27766, doi:10.1007/s11356-017-0567-0.
- Machado De-Melo, A.A.; Almeida-Muradian, L.B.d.; Sancho, M.T.; Pascual-Maté, A. Composition and properties of *Apis mellifera* honey: A review. *Journal of Apicultural Research* 2018, 57, 5-37, doi:10.1080/00218839.2017.1338444.
- Magazù, S.; Migliardo, F.; Telling, M. Structural and dynamical properties of water in sugar mixtures. *Food Chem* 2008, 106, 1460-1466.
- Manyi-Loh, C.E.; Ndip, R.N.; Clarke, A.M. Volatile compounds in honey: a review on their involvement in aroma, botanical origin determination and potential biomedical

- activities. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 2011, 12, 9514-9532.
- Miguel, M.G.; Antunes, M.D.; Faleiro, M.L. Honey as a Complementary Medicine. *Integr Med Insights* 2017, 12, 1178633717702869, doi:10.1177/1178633717702869.
- Olaitan, P.B.; Adeleke, O.E.; Ola, I.O. Honey: a reservoir for microorganisms and an inhibitory agent for microbes. *Afr Health Sci* 2007, 7, 159-165, doi:10.5555/afhs.2007.7.3.159.
- Pasupuleti, V.R.; Sammugam, L.; Ramesh, N.; Gan, S.H. Honey, Propolis, and Royal Jelly: A Comprehensive Review of Their Biological Actions and Health Benefits. *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity* 2017, 2017, 1259510, doi:10.1155/2017/1259510.
- Santos-Buelga, C.; González-Paramás, A.M. Chemical Composition of Honey. In *Bee Products - Chemical and Biological Properties*, Alvarez-Suarez, J.M., Ed.; Springer International Publishing: Cham, 2017; pp. 43-82.
- Tafere, D.A. Chemical composition and uses of Honey: A Review. *Journal of Food Science and Nutrition Research* 2021, 4, 194-201.
- Viuda-Martos, M.; Ruiz-Navajas, Y.; Fernández-López, J.; Pérez-Alvarez, J.A. Functional properties of honey, propolis, and royal jelly. *Journal of food science* 2008, 73, R117-124, doi:10.1111/j.1750-3841.2008.00966.x.

THE ROLE OF HONEY IN HUMAN HEALTH AND NUTRITION

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REVIEW ARTICLE

Abstract

Honey, one of the most complex apicultural products, has long surpassed the status of a simple natural sweetener, being regarded as a functional food with significant therapeutic benefits. Due to its rich composition in flavonoids, phenolic acids, enzymes, and bioactive compounds, honey exerts multiple biological effects, among which antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antifungal, cardioprotective, gastroprotective, and antidiabetic activities stand out. The aim of this study was to synthesize recent scientific data regarding the role of honey in human health and nutrition, highlighting its main mechanisms of action and potential clinical applications. The analysis was based on a systematic search of the PubMed, Elsevier, Google Scholar, and Wiley databases, selecting approximately 250 relevant articles published in English. The results confirm that the biological activity of honey largely depends on its botanical and geographical origin, which determine the variation in polyphenol content and other bioactive substances. Its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties contribute to reducing oxidative stress and protecting the cardiovascular system, while topical application promotes wound healing and tissue regeneration. Moreover, honey shows beneficial effects in regulating carbohydrate metabolism and maintaining the balance of intestinal microbiota. In conclusion, honey emerges as a functional food of high biological value, positioned at the interface between nutrition and therapy, supporting the need for further clinical studies to validate its use as a safe and effective therapeutic adjuvant.

Keywords: Honey, human health, nutrition, functional foods, therapeutic properties.

INTRODUCTION

Beekeeping represents both knowledge and art, aiming to support human health through the use of hive products such as honey, royal jelly, propolis, bee venom, and bee bread (Pasupuleti et al., 2017). In recent years, these natural products have gained increasing attention due to their applicability in both traditional and modern medicine. Numerous studies have highlighted their pharmacological properties and health benefits, paving the way for the development of functional foods and nutraceuticals (Pasupuleti et al., 2017).

Among bee products, honey holds a central position. For centuries, it has been valued not only as a natural sweetener but also as a therapeutic substance with nutritional, antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and cardioprotective effects (Badolato et al., 2017; Khan et al., 2017). The composition and properties of honey vary depending on its floral origin, which gives it a wide diversity of flavors, colors, and bioactive compounds (Chen et al., 2019; Jaganathan & Mandal, 2009). Beyond its nutritional value, scientific studies confirm honey's role in regulating the glycemic response, promoting wound healing, and supporting overall health through oral administration or topical application (Khan et al., 2017; Fakhlaei et al., 2020).

Through its wide range of biological effects, honey remains one of the most important natural functional foods, with therapeutic applications spanning metabolic, cardiovascular, digestive, and dermatological health (Miguel et al., 2017; Fakhlaei et al., 2020).

The aim of this presentation is to synthesize and update current information regarding the role of honey in human health and nutrition, emphasizing its scientifically proven benefits.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This paper represents a synthesis of recent scientific data from the specialized literature, aiming to highlight the efficacy of honey in maintaining health and in the treatment of various medical conditions. Information was obtained through a systematic search of online databases including PubMed, Elsevier, Google Scholar, and Wiley, restricted to articles published in English.

The search strategy included keywords such as honey, human health, nutrition, functional foods, therapeutic properties. The initial search identified 1,074 articles, of which approximately 250 were selected for evaluation. Their abstracts were critically analyzed, classified, and compared, focusing on scientific relevance and potential therapeutic applications.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The reviewed research highlights that honey exhibits numerous biological activities, mainly determined by its complex composition and the botanical origin of the flowers from which nectar is collected (Anguebes-Franceschi et al., 2019). According to the scientific literature, honey exerts a wide range of pharmacological effects, including antioxidant, cardioprotective, wound-healing, anti-inflammatory, gastroprotective, anticancer, antibacterial, antidiabetic, and antifungal activities (Fakhlai et al., 2020).

The antioxidant properties of honey are primarily attributed to the presence of flavonoids and phenolic acids, which act by chelating metal ions, neutralizing free radicals, and reducing oxidative stress involved in degenerative, cardiovascular, and neoplastic diseases (Kamaruzzaman et al., 2019; Moniruzzaman et al., 2012). High levels of polyphenols in raw honey contribute to the prevention of inflammation, thrombosis, diabetes, and other chronic disorders (Ahmed et al., 2018; Mandal & Mandal, 2011).

The anti-inflammatory activity of honey is well-documented, showing effects in reducing edema, exudates, and tissue inflammation through the inhibition of reactive oxygen species formation, leukocyte infiltration, and the expression of pro-inflammatory enzymes such as COX-2 and inducible nitric oxide synthase (Majtan, 2014; Holt et al., 2012). Moreover, honey demonstrates remarkable antibacterial activity due to the combined effects of its low pH, osmotic pressure, hydrogen peroxide, and non-peroxide compounds such as phenolic acids and flavonoids (Mandal & Mandal, 2011; Seraglio et al., 2019). Methylglyoxal (MGO) and its precursor dihydroxyacetone (DHA) inhibit bacterial growth by blocking urease activity, while bacterial species such as *Salmonella* spp., *Escherichia coli*, and *Shigella* spp. are sensitive to honey's bactericidal effect (Mandal & Mandal, 2011; Gobin et al., 2018; Almasaudi, 2021). Honey also exhibits antifungal activity against *Candida albicans*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Microsporum gypseum*, and *Penicillium chrysogenum*, due to its glucose oxidase, methylglyoxal, and high sugar content (Mandal & Mandal, 2011; Anyanwu, 2012).

Several studies have confirmed the cardioprotective effects of honey, mainly related to its phenolic and flavonoid content, which improve endothelial function, inhibit platelet aggregation, reduce oxidative stress and inflammatory responses, thus providing

protection against vascular dysfunction and cardiovascular diseases (Ab Wahab et al., 2018). Flavonoids such as quercetin, kaempferol, and caffeic acid contribute to lipid profile regulation and reduction of thrombotic risk (Khalil et al., 2010; Olas, 2020).

Honey's wound-healing properties result from its synergistic antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant actions, which stimulate angiogenesis, collagen synthesis, epithelialization, and edema reduction (Al-Waili et al., 2011; Takzaree et al., 2016). It promotes tissue regeneration, granulation tissue formation, and moist wound healing, being widely used in dressings, gels, and medical creams (Al-Waili et al., 2011; Gupta & Stangaciu, 2014).

The gastroprotective effects of honey are explained by the presence of enzymes that facilitate the digestion of sugars and starches, as well as by its bactericidal action against enteropathogenic microorganisms (Pasupuleti et al., 2017; Ma et al., 2019). Moreover, honey exhibits important anticancer properties attributed to phenolic acids (gallic and caffeic) and flavonoids (catechin, kaempferol, quercetin), which act through antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antiproliferative, and apoptotic mechanisms (Waheed et al., 2019).

Regarding its antidiabetic effect, honey helps regulate the insulin response through its fructose and antioxidant content, which protect pancreatic cells from oxidative stress and reduce hyperglycemia (Mandal & Mandal, 2011; Bobiş et al., 2018). Experimental studies support the role of honey as a beneficial dietary supplement for diabetes control and for reducing associated metabolic complications (Bobiş et al., 2018).

Overall, the literature confirms that honey is a natural product with significant therapeutic potential, whose biological effects are closely linked to its chemical composition and botanical origin, justifying its use as a functional food and adjuvant in the prevention and management of various human diseases.

The synthesized data confirm the biochemical complexity of honey and its relevance in maintaining human health. Beyond its traditional role as an energy source, honey emerges as a true functional agent with direct implications for metabolic homeostasis and cellular protection. The presence of flavonoids, phenolic acids, and antioxidant enzymes largely explains its anti-inflammatory and cardioprotective effects, demonstrating the

strong relationship between its phytochemical composition and observed biological activity.

An essential aspect emerging from the analyzed studies is the dependence of therapeutic effects on the botanical and geographical origin of honey. The variable content of polyphenols, vitamins, and minerals results in significant differences in antioxidant and antibacterial capacity. This supports the need for strict standardization of honey intended for therapeutic use to ensure reproducibility of clinical outcomes and safety of administration.

The antibacterial and antifungal activity of honey, attributed to the synergy between hydrogen peroxide, high acidity, and phenolic compounds, opens promising perspectives for the development of natural topical and medical formulations for treating skin infections and chronic wounds. Furthermore, honey's ability to stimulate tissue regeneration and angiogenesis justifies its inclusion in advanced medical products such as gels, bioactive dressings, and ointments.

From a metabolic perspective, current data suggest that honey, when consumed in moderate amounts, can help regulate blood glucose and protect pancreatic function; however, these effects depend on the type of honey and patient profile. Despite the experimentally demonstrated benefits, further clinical studies are needed to establish optimal doses and elucidate the molecular mechanisms underlying its antidiabetic effects.

Moreover, the growing interest in using honey as a functional food and nutraceutical calls for an integrated approach involving nutrition science, pharmacology, and apicultural biotechnology. In a world where chronic inflammation and oxidative stress underlie most non-communicable diseases, honey stands out as a natural health modulator capable of supporting physiological processes and reducing the risk of degenerative pathologies.

Nevertheless, the literature also reveals certain methodological limitations, including sample heterogeneity, lack of honey source standardization, and variability in clinical study design. These factors may affect data interpretation and highlight the need for well-controlled, multicenter research to strengthen the evidence regarding honey's therapeutic efficacy.

In conclusion, the critical analysis of available data confirms that honey is a natural product with complex pharmacological potential, positioned at the interface between

food and medicine. The valorization of this potential depends on a deeper understanding of its biochemical mechanisms, the establishment of quality parameters, and the integration of scientific findings into evidence-based medical and nutritional practice.

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of the scientific literature demonstrates that honey is an apicultural product with complex therapeutic and nutritional value, far beyond that of a simple natural sweetener. Due to its rich content of flavonoids, phenolic acids, enzymes, and bioactive compounds, honey exerts a wide range of beneficial effects on human health, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antifungal, cardioprotective, gastroprotective, and antidiabetic activities.

The biological efficacy of honey is closely correlated with its botanical and geographical origin, emphasizing the need to standardize its chemical composition for therapeutic use and to ensure the quality of apicultural products intended for human consumption.

Through its ability to modulate oxidative and inflammatory responses, honey contributes to maintaining metabolic balance and preventing chronic non-communicable diseases such as cardiovascular disorders, diabetes, and degenerative conditions. Furthermore, its topical use has proven effective in wound healing, tissue regeneration, and the reduction of skin infections, confirming its role in regenerative and dermatological medicine.

However, in order to transform honey into a scientifically validated therapeutic adjuvant, additional controlled and multicenter clinical studies are required to establish optimal doses, underlying molecular mechanisms, and possible drug interactions.

In conclusion, honey emerges as a functional food of high biological value, positioned at the intersection of nutrition and pharmacotherapy. The integration of current scientific findings into evidence-based medical and nutritional practice could strengthen the position of honey as a strategic natural resource for promoting health and preventing disease within the framework of modern personalized medicine.

REFERENCES

- Ab Wahab, S.Z.; Nik Hussain, N.H.; Zakaria, R.; Abdul Kadir, A.; Mohamed, N.; Tohit, N.M.; Norhayati, M.N.; Hassan, I.I. Long-term effects of honey on cardiovascular parameters and anthropometric measurements of postmenopausal women. *Complementary Therapies in Medicine* 2018, *41*, 154-160, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ctim.2018.08.015>.
- Ahmed, S.; Sulaiman, S.A.; Baig, A.A.; Ibrahim, M.; Liaqat, S.; Fatima, S.; Jabeen, S.; Shamim, N.; Othman, N.H. Honey as a Potential Natural Antioxidant Medicine: An Insight into Its Molecular Mechanisms of Action. *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity* 2018, *2018*, 8367846, doi:10.1155/2018/8367846.
- Almasaudi, S. The antibacterial activities of honey. *Saudi J Biol Sci* 2021, *28*, 2188-2196, doi:10.1016/j.sjbs.2020.10.017.
- Al-Waili, N.; Salom, K.; Al-Ghamdi, A.A. Honey for wound healing, ulcers, and burns; data supporting its use in clinical practice. *TheScientificWorldJournal* 2011, *11*, 766-787.
- Anguebes-Franceschi, F.; Abatal, M.; Pat, L.; Flores, A.; Córdova Quiroz, A.V.; Ramírez-Elias, M.A.; San Pedro, L.; May Tzuc, O.; Bassam, A. Raman Spectroscopy and Chemometric Modeling to Predict Physical-Chemical Honey Properties from Campeche, Mexico. *Molecules* 2019, *24*, doi:10.3390/molecules24224091.
- Anyanwu, C. Investigation of in vitro antifungal activity of honey. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research* 2012, *6*, 3512-3516.
- Badolato, M.; Carullo, G.; Cione, E.; Aiello, F.; Caroleo, M.C. From the hive: Honey, a novel weapon against cancer. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry* 2017, *142*, 290-299, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2017.07.064>.
- Bobiş, O.; Dezmirean, D.S.; Moise, A.R. Honey and Diabetes: The Importance of Natural Simple Sugars in Diet for Preventing and Treating Different Type of Diabetes. *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity* 2018, *2018*, 4757893, doi:10.1155/2018/4757893.
- Chen, C.-T.; Chen, B.-Y.; Nai, Y.-S.; Chang, Y.-M.; Chen, K.-H.; Chen, Y.-W. Novel inspection of sugar residue and origin in honey based on the 13C/12C isotopic ratio and protein content. *Journal of Food and Drug Analysis* 2019, *27*, 175-183, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfda.2018.08.004>.
- Fakhlaei, R.; Selamat, J.; Khatib, A.; Razis, A.F.A.; Sukor, R.; Ahmad, S.; Babadi, A.A. The Toxic Impact of Honey Adulteration: A Review. *Foods* 2020, *9*, doi:10.3390/foods9111538.
- Gobin, I.; Crnković, G.; Magdalenić, M.; Begić, G.; Babić, A.; Lušić, D.; Vučković, D. Antibacterial potential of Croatian honey against antibiotic resistant pathogenic bacteria. *Med Glas (Zenica)* 2018, *15*, 139-144, doi:10.17392/951-18.
- Gupta, R.K.; Stangaciu, S. Apitherapy: holistic healing through the honeybee and bee products in countries with poor healthcare system. In *Beekeeping for poverty alleviation and livelihood security*; Springer, Dordrecht: 2014; pp. 413-446.
- Holt, S.; Johnson, K.; Ryan, J.; Catchpole, O.; Zhang, S.; Mitchell, K.A. New Zealand kanuka honey has high levels of methylglyoxal and antimicrobial activity. *J Altern Complement Med* 2012, *18*, 203-204, doi:10.1089/acm.2011.0685.
- Jaganathan, S.K.; Mandal, M. Antiproliferative effects of honey and of its polyphenols: a review. *J Biomed Biotechnol* 2009, *2009*, 830616, doi:10.1155/2009/830616.
- Kamaruzzaman, M.A.; Chin, K.-Y.; Mohd Ramli, E.S. A Review of Potential Beneficial Effects of Honey on Bone Health. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine* 2019, *2019*, 8543618, doi:10.1155/2019/8543618.
- Khalil, M.; Sulaiman, S.A.; Boukraa, L. Antioxidant properties of honey and its role in preventing health disorder. *The Open Nutraceuticals Journal* 2010, *3*.
- Khan, R.U.; Naz, S.; Abudabos, A.M. Towards a better understanding of the therapeutic applications and corresponding mechanisms of action of honey. *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int* 2017, *24*, 27755-27766, doi:10.1007/s11356-017-0567-0.
- Ma, T.; Zhao, H.; Liu, C.; Zhu, M.; Gao, H.; Cheng, N.; Cao, W. Discrimination of natural mature acacia honey based on multi-physicochemical parameters combined with chemometric analysis. *Molecules* 2019, *24*, 2674.
- Majtan, J. Honey: an immunomodulator in wound healing. *Wound Repair Regen* 2014, *22*, 187-192, doi:10.1111/wrr.12117.
- Mandal, M.D.; Mandal, S. Honey: its medicinal property and antibacterial activity. *Asian Pac J Trop Biomed* 2011, *1*, 154-160, doi:10.1016/s2221-1691(11)60016-6.
- Miguel, M.G.; Antunes, M.D.; Faleiro, M.L. Honey as a Complementary Medicine. *Integr Med Insights* 2017, *12*, 1178633717702869, doi:10.1177/1178633717702869.
- Moniruzzaman, M.; Khalil, M.I.; Sulaiman, S.A.; Gan, S.H. Advances in the analytical methods for determining the antioxidant properties of honey: a review. *Afr J Tradit Complement Altern Med* 2012, *9*, 36-42, doi:10.4314/ajtcam.v9i1.5.
- Olas, B. Honey and Its Phenolic Compounds as an Effective Natural Medicine for Cardiovascular Diseases in Humans? *Nutrients* 2020, *12*, doi:10.3390/nu12020283.
- Pasupuleti, V.R.; Sammugam, L.; Ramesh, N.; Gan, S.H. Honey, Propolis, and Royal Jelly: A Comprehensive Review of Their Biological Actions and Health Benefits. *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity* 2017, *2017*, 1259510, doi:10.1155/2017/1259510.
- Seraglio, S.K.T.; Silva, B.; Bergamo, G.; Brugnerotto, P.; Gonzaga, L.V.; Fett, R.; Costa, A.C.O. An overview of physicochemical characteristics and health-promoting properties of honeydew honey. *Food Res Int* 2019, *119*, 44-66, doi:10.1016/j.foodres.2019.01.028.
- Takzaree, N.; Hadjiakhondi, A.; Hassanzadeh, G.; Rouini, M.R.; Manayi, A. Synergistic Effect of Honey and Propolis on Cutaneous Wound Healing in Rats. *Acta Med Iran* 2016, *54*, 233-239.
- Waheed, M.; Hussain, M.B.; Javed, A.; Mushtaq, Z.; Hassan, S.; Shariati, M.A.; Khan, M.U.; Majeed, M.; Nigam, M.; Mishra, A.P.; et al. Honey and cancer: A mechanistic review. *Clin Nutr* 2019, *38*, 2499-2503, doi:10.1016/j.clnu.2018.12.019.

LEGAL ASPECTS REGARDING THE REGULATION OF THE MARKETING OF FOOD SUPPLEMENTS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This paper analyzes the main legal aspects concerning the regulation of food supplements, both from the perspective of national legislation and that of European Union law. The fundamental principles governing the food supplements market, the obligations of economic operators, and the competent authorities responsible for ensuring consumer protection are highlighted. The study emphasizes the importance of the coherent application of legal norms in the context of the free movement of goods within the European Union.

Keywords: food supplements, legislation, consumer protection, marketing, food safety

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INTRODUCTION

The regulation of the marketing of food supplements in Romania is based on a complex legal framework that transposes European Union legislation and involves national authorities such as the Ministry of Health and the National Sanitary Veterinary and Food Safety Authority. Food supplements are considered food products, not medicines, whose purpose is to supplement a balanced diet and which represent concentrated sources of nutrients with a nutritional or physiological effect, marketed in dose form.

Food supplements represent a distinct category of products situated at the boundary between food and products with an impact on public health, which justifies the existence of a complex legal framework regarding their production, labeling, and marketing.

In recent decades, food supplements have experienced significant development on both the European and national markets, being widely used to complement dietary intake. This expansion has been driven by changes in lifestyle, increased interest in health and prevention, as well as technological advances in the food industry. From a legal perspective, food supplements raise a number of specific issues, as they are not considered medicines, yet they may have significant physiological effects on the human body. This intermediate positioning requires the existence of clear and rigorous regulations in order to prevent risks to public

health and to ensure accurate consumer information.¹

The dual nature of supplements—positioned between food and medicines—has generated considerable regulatory complexity. Although they are predominantly regulated as foods, the health-related claims associated with them require strict control standards, similar to those applicable to pharmaceutical products with regard to communication. The main objective of legal regulation is to protect public health and to guarantee that the information provided to consumers is truthful, scientifically substantiated, and not misleading.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The methodology used in preparing this paper is based on the analysis of the main normative acts relevant to the field of food supplements and their marketing, both at the national and at the EU level. The method employed was a comparative one, with the research focusing on:

1. normative analysis through the examination of the basic legislation defining food supplements, establishing their composition, and regulating communication (labeling, claims, marketing)
2. analysis through the identification of relevant normative acts

¹ Popescu, A., *European Food Law*. Universul Juridic Publishing House, Bucharest, 2019

3. the comparative method by comparing the regulatory standards established by general food law

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The nutrients that may be used in food supplements are the following: vitamins (Vitamin A, Vitamin D, Vitamin E, Vitamin K, Vitamin B1, Vitamin B2, Niacin, Pantothenic acid, Vitamin B6, Folic acid, Vitamin B12, Biotin, Vitamin C); minerals (Calcium, Magnesium, Iron, Copper, Iodine, Zinc, Manganese, Sodium, Potassium, Selenium, Chromium, Molybdenum, Fluoride, Chloride, Phosphorus); substances with nutritional or physiological effects (macronutrients, amino acids, enzymes, live microorganisms, dietary fibers, essential fatty acids, plants, algae, lichens, fungi and their essential oils, plant extracts and animal extracts), as well as mixtures of vitamins and minerals with substances having nutritional or physiological effects. In the manufacture of food supplements, only the vitamins and minerals included in Community legislation may be used.²

The placing on the market of food supplements in Romania by the manufacturer, importer, or the person responsible for marketing the product is carried out on the basis of a *notification certificate*, which is an administrative act issued by the National Institute of Public Health within 15 working days from the date of product notification. The notification form must include information about the notifier (name, address, telephone, fax, registration number with the Trade Register), the person responsible for placing the product on the market, the trade name of the product, details regarding the product composition, the country of origin, a declaration on own responsibility that the submitted data are correct, the first and last name of the director (the person who will sign the notification form), signature, stamp, date, and a statement confirming that the food supplement for which notification is requested has NOT been registered in any other country as a non-prescription medicinal product (OTC product). The notification issued by the Ministry of Public Health for a food supplement is valid until any qualitative or quantitative modification of its composition occurs. The Ministry of Health website displays the documents required for

the notification of food supplements, the list of plants permitted in food supplements, the list of substances with nutritional or physiological effects permitted in food supplements, and the list of food supplements already notified.³

Dietary supplements:

- those that contain vitamins, minerals, mixtures of vitamins and minerals; substances with a nutritional or physiological effect other than vitamins and minerals; mixtures of vitamins and minerals with substances having a nutritional or physiological effect other than vitamins and minerals; mixtures of substances with a nutritional or physiological effect with plants and plant/animal extracts and/or bee products; mixtures of substances with a nutritional or physiological effect, other than vitamins and minerals, with plants and plant/animal extracts and bee products; as well as mixtures of any of the above-mentioned ingredients, must be notified to the National Institute of Public Health by submitting a standardized notification application, accompanied by the product label mock-up, including the original label and the technical specification of the product, submitted in hard copy or electronic format. Following the analysis of the notification file, the National Institute of Public Health issues or refuses to issue the notification certificate

- dietary supplements that have been notified in another European Union Member State may be placed on the Romanian market for the first time by submitting a standardized notification application, accompanied by a Romanian-language label mock-up, including the original label and the declaration of mutual recognition (in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2019/515 of 19 March 2019 on the mutual recognition of goods lawfully marketed in another Member State)

- dietary supplements originating from third countries require the manufacturer, importer, or the person responsible for placing them on the market to apply for a notification certificate from the competent authority.

The maximum amounts of vitamins and minerals present in dietary supplements in the daily portion recommended by the manufacturer are established by taking into account the tolerable upper intake levels of vitamins and minerals determined through scientific risk assessment based on generally

² Order No. 1069/2007 approving the Norms on food supplements; the 2007 Norm on food supplements

³ Law No. 56/2021 on food supplements

accepted scientific data. The minimum amounts must represent 15% of the nutrient reference values.

In labeling, presentation and commercial communications, it is prohibited to attribute properties of preventing, treating, or curing a human disease or to refer to such properties. It is also prohibited to use statements, whether direct or implied, suggesting that a varied and balanced diet cannot provide adequate amounts of nutrients.

The labeling of dietary supplements must include the following information:

- the name of the categories of nutrients or substances that characterize the product, or an indication of the nature of these nutrients or substances;
- the recommended daily portion;
- a warning against exceeding the recommended daily portion;
- a warning advising against using dietary supplements as a substitute for a varied diet;
- a warning indicating that the products must be kept out of the reach of young children.

⁴Order No. 244/2005 establishes the list of plants and mushrooms that are permitted for use in food supplements. This regulatory act also sets out a series of prohibitions regarding the marketing of food supplements containing various types of plants and mushrooms. Thus:

- the marketing, as processed, prepared, processed or partially processed products in the form of food supplements, of plants that are dangerous for human consumption is prohibited
- the use of mushrooms that are dried; cut (in such a way that their species cannot be identified, except for truffles and morels); whole; containing insects, insect parts or insect residues; that are not fresh; or that are not included in the list mentioned in the Order is prohibited
- the manufacture or marketing of products in the form of pre-dosed food supplements containing one or more plants not included in the lists mentioned in the Order is prohibited without prior notification to the ⁵Institute of

⁴ Order No. 244/2005 on the processing, handling, and marketing of medicinal and aromatic plants used as such, partially processed, or processed in the form of pre-dosed food supplements

⁵ It is a research institute in the food industry in Romania, operating under the authority of the Ministry of Research and Innovation. It is the only research institute in Romania that develops products for food intolerances; it hosts the country's only information and dissemination center on genetically modified organisms; it has an information and

Food Bioresources (IFB), within which there is a Notification Approval Service

• the processing, manufacture and marketing of such products in the form of food supplements without the approval of the IFB is prohibited; such approval is granted following prior notification of the product. The notification file for obtaining approval must include the following:

- the nature of the product
- the quantitative and qualitative list of ingredients contained in the product
- the nutritional analysis of the product, quantitative and qualitative data on known significant active substances or the indicator per unit and per daily dose, toxicity and stability
- product labeling – the scientific name and the common name, if any

Within 30 days from the date of receipt of the notification file, the Service shall send, in writing, to the person who submitted it, the receipt approval, and the notification file number shall be used in all documents related to the marketing of the product.

Law No. 491/2003 is the regulatory act that establishes the general legal framework regarding the production, processing and organization of the market for medicinal and aromatic plants and bee products, as well as the relationships between producers, processors and traders (professionals). The production of medicinal and aromatic plants consists of obtaining them through cultivation or harvesting from wild flora; through processing they become teas, natural spices and raw materials for further processing, being transformed into products marketed as medicines, cosmetics, nutritional supplements, dietary products and food flavoring additives. Finished products based on medicinal and aromatic plants and bee products that are notified by operators in this field as medicines and classified as such are authorized or approved for market placement by the National Agency for Medicines and Medical Devices. The institution responsible for the notification, supervision and control of food supplements

dissemination center for human nutrition; it evaluates the physico-chemical and microbiological qualities of plant agricultural resources and food products; it prepares studies and conducts tests on dietary, organic, and special-purpose food products; it provides consultancy and services in various fields of the food industry, and it also has a specialized technical body in the field of organic agriculture, called the Organic Products Certification Body

and products for external use obtained from medicinal and aromatic plants and bee products, except for cosmetic products, is the National Service for Medicinal and Aromatic Plants and Bee Products, which operates under the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development.⁶

Order No. 1228/2005 is the regulatory act that establishes the technical standards regarding the marketing of pre-dosed food supplements of animal and plant origin and their mixtures with vitamins, minerals and other nutrients. According to this Order, food supplements may be marketed only in the form of tablets, capsules, dragees, powders, edible liquids, jellies, pastes, candies or bars, juices, syrups, tinctures, soft capsules, powders or granules in cases or packages, or as liquids presented in drinkable ampoules or in dropper bottles, containing nutrients with a role in human nutrition and administered exclusively by oral route.

The marketing of these products must comply with certain principles, namely that they must be safe, must not endanger consumer health, and must be made from raw materials guaranteed by suppliers through a declaration of conformity or of origin and provenance, accompanied by analysis reports. In their manufacture, additives, technological aids, and packaging materials may be used only if they are permitted by the legal regulations in force, and good manufacturing practices and food quality standards must be observed. In order to eliminate risks, throughout the technological flow of each production batch, flow parameters are internally monitored, and their values are recorded in documentation that is kept for at least 2 years.

The marketing of these products is carried out on the basis of prior notification. For notification purposes, the product dossier is submitted to the Institute of Food Bioresources, the Iași Public Health Institute, the Cluj-Napoca Public Health Institute, or the Timișoara Public Health Institute, which issue the notification certificate. The Institute of Food Bioresources maintains the single register of notification certificates for products and assigns to the other notifying institutes the series of notification certificates and the corresponding numbers for each notifier. The notifying institutes transmit

monthly to the Institute of Food Bioresources a centralized report of the notification certificates issued. Within 10 calendar days from the date of submission of the notification dossier, the notifying institute sends the notification certificate in writing to the applicant, and the notification dossier number is used in all commercial documents, including the numbering of the product's notification certificate. By the 2nd day of the following month, the Institute of Food Bioresources prepares the list of notification certificates issued and the list of unresolved notification dossiers, both of which are sent in writing to the Interministerial Technical Committee for Medicinal and Aromatic Plants, which analyzes, evaluates, and decides, from a technical point of view, the measures regarding notification dossiers for which certificates have not been issued. A food supplement that has been notified once does not require another notification, and the list of notified products is published on the website of the Institute of Food Bioresources.⁷

Food supplements are marketed to the final consumer only in pre-packaged form. With regard to the labeling and advertising of food supplements, these must not overlap with the regulations governing the placing of medicinal products on the market. Directive 2002/46/EC establishes a harmonized legal framework at the level of the European Union for food supplements, focusing on their definition, labeling, and composition. Its main purpose is to ensure consumer safety and to facilitate the free movement of these products on the internal market, and it provides minimum labeling requirements to ensure that information is not misleading, is clear, and is easily understood by consumers. Labeling must include: the legal name "food supplement"; the names of the categories of nutrients or substances it contains; the recommended daily dose; a warning against exceeding the recommended daily dose; a statement that food supplements should not replace a varied and balanced diet, but only complement it; and it prohibits, through labeling and advertising, the attribution

⁶ Law 491/2003 on medicinal and aromatic plants, as well as beehive products - Republished

⁷ Technical Norms of 2005 regarding the marketing of pre-dosed food supplements of animal and vegetable origin and/or their mixtures with vitamins, minerals and other nutrients - Order 1228/2005

of properties related to the prevention, treatment, or cure of a disease.⁸

The rules on the marketing of food supplements are not limited only to those normative acts that directly regulate these products, but, in conjunction with other normative acts, establish the general legal framework that allows their placement on the market for safe consumption. Thus, the rules concern: combating unfair commercial practices, which aim at better market functioning and ensuring a high level of consumer protection by regulating commercial practices that may harm consumers' economic interests, including unfair, misleading, and aggressive practices⁹; the free movement of safe and wholesome food products, which is an essential aspect of the internal market and contributes significantly to the health and well-being of citizens, as well as to their social and economic interests. In order to ensure a high level of consumer health protection and to guarantee their right to information, appropriate consumer information regarding the food products they consume should be ensured. Consumer choices may be influenced, among other things, by health, economic, environmental, social, or ethical considerations; the establishment of general principles and general requirements for food information, fair information practices, and the responsibilities of food business operators, including the mandatory particulars that must be included on labels¹⁰; the general principles and objectives of food law, risk analysis, protection of consumer interests, risk communication, transparency principles, general obligations in food trade, requirements regarding food safety¹¹, and the use of nutrition and health claims made on food products, with the main objective of ensuring a high level of consumer protection and facilitating the efficient functioning of the internal market by guaranteeing that such claims are based on scientific evidence. According to this normative act, nutrition and health claims may be used only if they are scientifically substantiated and are not

misleading to the consumer. It prohibits claims suggesting that a balanced diet cannot provide the necessary nutrients or that exploit consumers' fears, provides for the creation of positive lists of authorized health claims, and imposes specific conditions for the use of certain claims.¹²

CONCLUSIONS

Following the analysis of the legal framework applicable to food supplements, it can be observed that the regulation of this field is characterized by a high degree of complexity, resulting from the positioning of food supplements at the intersection between food products and products with an impact on public health. This particularity justifies the existence of a rigorous regulatory system designed to ensure consumer protection and the maintenance of a high level of food safety.

National legislation, harmonized with that of the European Union, establishes clear rules regarding the composition, notification, labeling, and marketing of food supplements. The notification procedure, carried out through specialized institutions such as the National Institute of Public Health or the Institute of Food Bioresources, represents an essential preventive control instrument, allowing the verification of product compliance before they are placed on the market.

A particularly important aspect highlighted in the paper is the role of labeling and commercial communication. The prohibition of attributing therapeutic properties to food supplements and the obligation to provide accurate, clear, and non-misleading information directly contribute to protecting consumers against unfair commercial practices and to ensuring fair market behavior.

The analysis also reveals the importance of correlating the specific rules on food supplements with the general legislation in the fields of food law, consumer protection, and commercial practices. This integrated approach allows for the coherent application of the principles of safety, transparency, and responsibility of economic operators, in line with the objectives of the European internal market.

⁸ Directive 2002/46/EC on the definition, labeling, and composition of food supplements

⁹ Law No. 363/2007 on combating unfair commercial practices

¹⁰ Regulation (EU) No. 1169/2011 on the provision of food information to consumers

¹¹ Regulation (EC) No. 178/2002 laying down the General Principles of Food Law

¹² Regulation (EC) No. 1924/2006 on nutrition and health claims

In conclusion, the legal regulation of the marketing of food supplements represents a dynamic field, continuously adapting to scientific and economic developments. The correct and uniform application of legal norms, together with effective supervision by the

competent authorities, are essential conditions for guaranteeing consumer safety and for the fair functioning of the food supplements market in Romania and in the European Union.

REFERENCES

Popescu, A., European Food Law. Universul Juridic Publishing House, Bucharest, 2019
Law 491/2003 on medicinal and aromatic plants, as well as beehive products - Republished
Law No. 363/2007 on combating unfair commercial practices
Law No. 56/2021 on food supplements
Order No. 244/2005 on the processing, handling, and marketing of medicinal and aromatic plants used as such, partially processed, or processed in the form of pre-dosed food supplements

Order No. 1228/2005 approving the Technical Norms on the marketing of pre-dosed food supplements of animal and plant origin and/or mixtures thereof with vitamins, minerals, and other nutrients
Order No. 1069/2007 approving the Norms on food supplements; the 2007 Norm on food supplements
Regulation (EC) No. 178/2002 laying down the General Principles of Food Law
Directive 2002/46/EC on the definition, labeling, and composition of food supplements
Regulation (EC) No. 1924/2006 on nutrition and health claims
Regulation (EU) No. 1169/2011 on the provision of food information to consumers

ORGANOLEPTIC ANALYSIS AND PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF SIX TYPES OF FLOUR ON THE ROMANIAN MARKET

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

In this paper, six types of flour on the Romanian market were analyzed (3 white and 3 black). The organoleptic characteristics (color, smell, taste) and physicochemical properties of these types of flour were analyzed.

It was observed that the six types of flour have colors, taste and smell that fall within the limits provided by the legislation in force. When determining the hydration capacity of wheat flour, it was found that it is 59.22 – 59.68 % (white flour) and 57.88 – 58.54 % (black flour). When determining wet gluten, it had values between 28.33%-28.61%, and the humidity varies between 14.32-14.42 % (white flour) and between 14.39 – 14.46 % (black flour). The ash content of the analyzed flour varies between 0.33-0.42 % (white flour) and between 0.92-0.99 % (black flour). The acidity of flour, it varies between 1.93 - 2.13 degrees acidity (white flour) and 3.53 - 3.73 degrees acidity (black flour). All the values obtained fall within the limits provided by the legislation in force.

Keywords: flour, gluten content, ash, flour acidity

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INTRODUCTION

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is a primordial cereal globally, with a diverse range of culinary applications including bread, pasta, biscuits (Martín-Esparza & González-Martínez) In addition to serving as a substantial supplier of calories and various nutrients, wheat is considered nutritionally inadequate due to the deficiency of essential amino acids such as lysine and threonine in its cereal proteins, thus it has a high carbohydrate content (starch 63.07%, sugar 4.32% and cellulose 2.76%), but a low protein content (16.06%) (Kumar et al., 2011) The ash content of wheat is about 2.18%, it comprises trace elements including iron (33 ppm), copper (4.50 ppm), zinc (25.8 ppm) and macroelements such as calcium (437 ppm) and magnesium (1100 ppm) (Ciudad-Mulero et al.,

2021) In addition, wheat is a source of vitamins and enzymes (α -amylase, β -amylase, proteases), and the distribution of minerals is primarily concentrated in the husk and germ (Bodor et al., 2024; Tejera et al., 2013) Flour, a fundamental foundation in global nutrition, is an emblem of culinary versatility, offering an extensive range of textures, flavors, and nutritional profiles (Butt et al., 2011) The sheer diversity of flours derived from different grains and sources presents opportunities for exploration, both in terms of their unique characteristics and the sophisticated methodologies used to determine them (Navarro et al., 2020)

In the field of nutrition, understanding the nuances of different flours is paramount. At the heart of this nutritional sequence is flour – a fundamental raw product derived through the complicated process of grinding grains (Dhingra

& Jood, 2002) The resulting flour, composed predominantly of endosperm cells, serves as a pivot for creating a diverse range of culinary delights (Abdelghafor et al., 2011) Bread consumption in industrialized countries contributes significantly to meeting about half of the daily carbohydrate requirement, about a third of the protein requirement, and between 50% and 60% of the recommended daily intake of vitamin B.

As key ingredients in an extensive range of food products, flours contribute not only to taste and texture, but also to a significant impact on the nutritional quality of finished products (Ndife et al., 2011) Among the primary grains used in the production of these staples, wheat and rye appear as staple ingredients in the bread-making industry. From wheat flour, a cornerstone in traditional breadmaking, to gluten-free alternatives such as rice, barley, and oat flour, each variant has a distinct set of attributes that influence its usefulness in culinary applications (Arp et al., 2017) White flours, famous for their versatility, are characterized by a low ash content, usually limited to 0.55.

Upon the addition of water, wheat flour turns into a cohesive viscoelastic dough, with gluten being the key component responsible for providing the dough's plasticity and stability (Guo et al., 2021; Schopf et al., 2021) The resulting gluten, which can be extracted by washing the dough components, plays a crucial role in determining the rheological properties of the dough. This includes cohesive and viscoelastic flow properties, which are essential during leavening (Morel et al., 2020)

This article analyzes the complex parameters associated with flour, such as color, taste, smell, presence of mineral impurities, ash content, wet gluten, moisture percentage, acidity.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

1. Materials

In this study, six types of flour that were purchased from supermarkets in Romania were used, of which three contain white flour and three black flours. The three types of white flour, of different origin and three types of black flour, purchased from supermarkets in Romania were rated as A1, A2 and A3, respectively N1, N2 and N3.

The reagents used: chloroform, distilled water, NaCl 2% solution, sodium hydroxide 0.1N, phenolphthalein 1%.

Equipment used: analytical balance Kern ABT 220-5DNM (Kern and Sohn GmbH, Balingen, Germany), optical microscopy OPTIKA B 380 (Italy).

2. Method

2.1.Determination of the organoleptic characteristics of flour

The color was determined by two methods: the Pekar method and the photocolometric method. We analyzed the six types of flour under a microscope.

To determine the odor, mix 5 g of flour with 25 mL distilled water heated to a temperature of 60-65°C for 2-3 minutes, then cover with a watch bottle, leaving at room temperature for 5 minutes. After removing the watch glass, watch for the smell of the suspension (ASRO, 1996).

To determine the taste, 1 g of the flour sample is chewed in the mouth, assessing the taste and the possible presence of mineral impurities (earth, sand, etc.), through the characteristic grinding that they produce when chewing. The flour should have a sweet, pleasant taste. Foreign tastes are due to improper storage or infestation of flour. Adulterated flour, due to rancid fats, has a bitter taste.

The mineral impurities in the flour sample are separated on the basis of the difference in density, using chloroform ($d = 1.48$) as the separating agent. For this, a small amount of flour is taken from the flour sample with a spatula, from different places, totaling about 1 g, which is introduced with the help of a funnel into a test tube with 10 mL chloroform. The test tube is closed with a rubber stopper, shaken, then placed upright on a stand, taking care that no sample particles remain on the walls of the test tube. The test tube rotates a few times around its axis, after which it is left to rest for 30 minutes. The presence of any mineral impurities that are deposited on the bottom of the test tube is visually examined (ASRO, 1996).

2.2.Determination of the physicochemical properties of flour

2.2.1. Determination of the hydration capacity of wheat flour

The hydration capacity of the flour is carried out according to STAS 90-88 which replaces STAS 90-77. The hydration capacity of flour is an important property, which determines the yield of flour in the dough. The principle of the method consists in determining the amount of flour that corresponds to a known amount of

water, necessary for the formation of a dough of normal consistency, under established conditions.

Fill a porcelain capsule with flour, level the surface of the flour with the help of a glass rod, make a recess by pressing with a pestle. Measure 10 mL of distilled water with a temperature of 18-20°C with a pipette and

introduce them into the recess formed in the flour. Mix the water and flour with the help of a spatula, then with the help of your hand, knead, for homogenization. The dough obtained is weighed. The measurements were made in triplicate. The technological process is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The technological process of the hydration capacity of wheat flour

2.2.2. Determination of wet gluten in flour

The method consists of transforming the flour into dough, washing the dough with a 2% NaCl solution (in order to separate the starch from the dough), followed by weighing the wet gluten and calculating the percentage of wet gluten in the sample.

For this determination, the dough sample was prepared, 25 g of flour was weighed, then it was placed in a mortar, 12.5 mL of 2% NaCl solution was added, and then the dough was kneaded by hand for 5 minutes. The dough obtained was washed with 2% NaCl on a gauze sieve for 30 minutes, dried with the help of the palms until it became sticky, the wet gluten was weighed on the analytical balance, and then the percentage of wet gluten was weighed.

2.2.3. Determination of flour moisture

Flour moisture is determined by the loss of flour mass by heating to $130 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ (Standardization, 1988) For the preparation of the sample it was necessary to weigh 5 g of flour, then to dry it in the oven for one hour at 130°C , then to cool it in the exicator for 30-60 minutes, and then to scale the ampoule with the sample obtained.

2.2.4. Determination of ash content in flour

Depending on the degree of extraction, the amount of ash in the flour also varies. In a flour with a high degree of extraction, the amount of ash is higher due to the higher level of mineral substances extracted from the wheat grain.

The determination of ash in flour is carried out using the dry method, which is the easiest and most inexpensive. It is based on the incineration of the flour sample until total combustion (ASRO, 1996) The preparation of

the dough sample for analysis consisted of: weighing 25 g of flour, placing the sample in a calcination oven at 500°C , 24 hours per cube, subjecting it to cooling in an exicator for 60 minutes and mounting the ampoule with ash.

2.2.5. Determination of flour acidity

Acidity is expressed in degrees of acidity, which is the number of milliliters of NaOH 1N required to neutralize the acidity in 100 g of flour.

Reagents used in the determination of flour acidity

Sodium hydroxide, 0.1N concentration solution;

Phenolphthalein, 1% concentration alcohol solution.

Weigh 5 g of flour which is then homogenized with 50 mL of distilled water and stirred for a few minutes. Leave to rest for 10 minutes and then titrate with sodium hydroxide in the presence of phenolphthalein, until faintly pink in color.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3. Determination of organoleptic characteristics

To determine the color, it was observed that the three types of white flour had a white or yellowish-white color, with a slightly gray tint. In the three types of black flour, the color observed was light gray, with a slight yellowish-white tinge.

From the State Standards, imposed by the Romanian Institute for Standardization, SR 877/1996 which replaces STAS 813-60, as far as bakery flour is concerned, the color of white flour must be white or yellowish-white, and it can also have a faint gray tint, and for black

flour, the color can be gray, with a yellowish-white tint given by the existence of bran particles. From the analysis of the color for the six types of flour, it can be concluded that they fall within the limits provided by the legislation in force.

At the smell analysis, we found that the six types of flour have a pleasant, flour-like smell, with no musty, dark or other unpleasant smell.

The analysis of the taste of the six types of flour showed that they have a normal taste, a little sweet, neither bitter nor sour without grinding when chewing, which can be given by

mineral impurities such as particles of earth, sand, etc.

4. Determination of the physicochemical properties of flour

4.1. Determination of the hydration capacity of wheat flour

$$\text{Hydration Capacity (\%)} = \frac{m_1}{m - m_1} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where: m – mass of the dough ball, in g; m₁ – the amount of water used, in mL.

To determine the hydration capacity, the analyzes were performed in triplicate, and the average results were noted as a number ± SD (standard deviation). The results obtained are shown in Table 1.

Table 1.

The hydration capacity of the six flour samples taken in the process				
Sample	Dough Weight, m (g)	Amount of water used, m ₁ (mL)	Hydration capacity (%)	Average hydration capacity ± SD, %
A1	26.96	10	58.98	59.22 ± 0.43
	29.63	11	59.03	
	26.76	10	59.65	
	29.45	11	59.61	
A2	32.18	12	59.45	59.42 ± 0.22
	26.89	10	59.20	
	26.74	10	59.75	
A3	26.75	10	59.69	59.68 ± 0.07
	29.46	11	59.60	
	30.05	11	57.75	
N1	32.69	12	58.01	57.88 ± 0.13
	27.28	10	57.88	
	32.77	12	57.78	
N2	29.97	11	57.98	58.12 ± 0.48
	29.77	11	58.60	
	27.18	10	58.21	
N3	27.06	10	58.62	58.54 ± 0.33
	29.71	11	58.79	

From the State Standards, imposed by the Romanian Institute for Standardization, SR 877/1996 which replaces STAS 813-60, as far as bakery flour is concerned, the hydration capacity, %, is established for white flour, as well as for black flour between 58 - 60%, for a very good flour. From the data obtained, it can be seen that for white flour the hydration capacity varies between 59.22 - 59.68%, and for black flour between 57.88 - 58.54%, which shows that one of the black flours is a good flour (N1), and the others are very good (N2, N3). The analysis of the data obtained shows that the six types of flour fall within the limits provided by the legislation in force.

4.2. Determination of wet gluten in flour

To calculate the percentage of wet gluten we used the following formula:

$$\text{mg.u. (\%)} = \frac{m_{g.u.}}{m_p} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where: % g.u. – the percentage of wet gluten in the sample taken in the work. expressed in percentages; sqm = the mass of the flour sample taken in the work. expressed in grams; mg.u. = the mass of wet gluten determined in the sample of flour taken in work. expressed in grams (ASRO, 1996)

The results obtained in determining the percentage of wet gluten are represented in Table 2.

Table 2.

Determination of wet gluten percentage				
Sample	The flour sample mass taken in work, m_p (g)	Wet gluten mass, mg.u. (g)	Wet gluten content, (%)	Mean wet gluten percentage \pm SD, (%)
A1	25.32	7.19	28.38	28.33 \pm 0.05
	25.28	7.17	28.35	
	25.19	7.12	28.27	
A2	24.97	7.05	28.22	28.29 \pm 0.12
	25.21	7.12	28.24	
	25.05	7.12	28.41	
A3	25.12	7.20	28.67	28.61 \pm 0.19
	25.08	7.12	28.37	
	25.11	7.23	28.80	
N1	25.16	7.21	28.67	28.59 \pm 0.21
	25.08	7.14	28.47	
	25.24	7.22	28.62	
N2	25.05	7.16	28.57	28.37 \pm 0.20
	25.10	7.11	28.31	
	25.21	7.12	28.23	
N3	24.98	7.10	28.41	28.61 \pm 0.20
	24.89	7.14	28.69	
	25.22	7.25	28.73	

For the determination of wet gluten, the analyzes were performed in triplicate, and the average results were noted as a number \pm SD.

According to the standards in force (SR 877/1996), the minimum wet gluten content of flours must be: 26% for type 480 and 650 flours, 27% for type 550 flours and 28% for type 000 flours.

4.3. Determination of flour moisture

The calculation formula for flour moisture is expressed in percentages and is as follows:

$$\text{Humidity (\%)} = \frac{m_1 - m_2}{m_1 - m_0} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

where: m_1 – the mass of the ampoule with the sample of flour taken in the process, before drying, expressed in grams; m_2 – the mass of the ampoule with the sample of flour taken in work, after drying, expressed in grams; m_0 – the mass of the empty vial, expressed in grams.

The results obtained in the analysis of the six types of flour are shown in Table 3. The determinations were made in triplicate, and the results of the average humidity were written as a number \pm DS.

Table 3.

Flour sample moisture					
Sample	Initial mass of the vial and flour sample, m_1 (g)	Mass of the dried flour sample and vial, m_2 (g)	Empty vial mass, m_0 (g)	Sample moisture content, (%)	Mean moisture content \pm SD, (%)
A1	29.68	28.93	24.52	14.53	14.42 \pm 0.09
	30.02	29.23		14.36	
	28.86	28.07		14.36	
A2	30.11	29.39	25.10	14.37	14.32 \pm 0.09
	30.23	29.50		14.23	
	29.97	29.27		14.37	
A3	31.12	30.22	24.84	14.33	14.39 \pm 0.29
	30.56	29.72		14.68	
	30.84	29.99		14.17	
N1	30.55	29.79	25.23	14.28	14.46 \pm 0.37
	31.12	30.28		14.26	
	30.42	29.65		14.83	
N2	30.98	30.08	24.88	14.75	14.39 \pm 0.36
	30.88	30.02		14.33	
	29.78	29.09		14.08	
N3	30.65	29.85	25.15	14.54	14.41 \pm 0.13
	30.05	29.35		14.28	
	30.70	29.90		14.41	

From the State Standards, imposed by the Romanian Institute for Standardization, SR 877/1996 which replaces STAS 813-60, as far as bakery flour is concerned, the flour moisture percentage is set at a maximum of 14.5% for both white and black flour.

From the data obtained, it can be seen that for white flour the humidity varies between 14.32-14.42%, and for black flour between 14.39-14.46%, so the six types of flour analyzed fall within the limits provided by the legislation in force.

4.4. Determination of ash content in flour

The ash content of flour (%) can be calculated using the relation:

$$\% \text{ ash} = \frac{m_{\text{ash}}}{m_{\text{sample}}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

where: ash – the mass of ash obtained after incineration, representing the difference between the mass of the crucible after incineration and the mass of the crucible initially weighed, expressed in g (ASRO, 1996).

The results obtained in this determination for all types of flour analysed are set out in Table 4. For each flour sample, three determinations were performed, and the average ash percentage values are denoted as the mean \pm standard deviation (SD).

Table 4.

Ash content percentages for the six flours

Sample	Weight of the flour sample m_{sample} (g)	Mass of ash obtained after Incineration m_{ash} (g)	Ash content of flour (%)	Average ash content \pm SD, (%)
A1	24.56	0.10	0.41	0.41 \pm 0.03
	25.31	0.10	0.39	
	24.87	0.11	0.44	
A2	25.01	0.09	0.36	0.42 \pm 0.06
	25.41	0.11	0.43	
	25.37	0.12	0.47	
A3	24.88	0.09	0.36	0.33 \pm 0.07
	25.42	0.07	0.27	
	25.26	0.09	0.36	
N1	25.08	0.22	0.88	0.99 \pm 0.12
	25.24	0.28	1.11	
	25.13	0.25	0.99	
N2	24.86	0.24	0.96	0.94 \pm 0.03
	24.98	0.24	0.96	
	25.22	0.23	0.91	
N3	24.89	0.26	1.04	0.92 \pm 0.12
	25.11	0.20	0.80	
	25.08	0.23	0.92	

According to the State Standards imposed by the Romanian Standardization Institute (ASRO) regarding flour for bread-making, the ash content percentage, reported on a dry matter basis, is established for White Flour at a maximum of 0.65%, and for Dark Flour (Black Flour) at values ranging between 0.91% and 1.40% (ASRO, 1996; Bordei, 2000; Bordei et al., 2007; Drăgoi et al., 2018; Modoran, 2007; Niculescu, 2000; Standardization, 1988).

The obtained data show that the ash content for the white flour ranges between 0.33% and 0.42%, and for the dark flour between 0.92% and 0.99%. This demonstrates that all six types of flour comply with the limits stipulated by the current legislation.

4.5. Flour acidity determination

Flour acidity calculation:

$$\text{Degrees of acidity } \% = \frac{V \times F \times 100}{10 \times 5} \quad (5)$$

where: V is the volume of NaOH 0.1 N used for titration, in mL; F is the factor of the NaOH 0.1 N solution (the sodium hydroxide solution factor is 1); 5 is the mass of flour taken for the analysis (working mass); and 10 is the conversion factor for the NaOH solution normality, from 0.1 N to 1 N. (ASRO, 1996).

The results obtained for the acidity determination of the six types of flour are presented in Table 5. Determinations were carried out in triplicate, and the average acidity results are denoted as the mean \pm SD.

Table 5.

Acidity of the six analyzed flours			
Sample	Volume of NaOH for titration (mL)	Acidity of flour (Acidity Degrees)	Mean flour acidity \pm SD (Acidity Degrees)
A1	1.1	2.2	2.13 \pm 0.13
	1.0	2.0	
	1.1	2.2	
A2	1.2	2.4	2.2 \pm 0.2
	1.0	2.0	
	1.1	2.2	
A3	0.9	1.8	1.93 \pm 0.13
	1.0	2.0	
	1.0	2.0	
N1	1.8	3.6	3.66 \pm 0.33
	1.7	3.4	
	2.0	4.0	
N2	1.9	3.8	3.73 \pm 0.13
	1.8	3.6	
	1.9	3.8	
N3	1.8	3.6	3.53 \pm 0.13
	1.8	3.6	
	1.7	3.4	

State Standards (SR 877/1996) from the Romanian Standardization Institute set the maximum acidity for baking flour at 2.8 degrees for white flour and 4.0 degrees for dark flour. The results show that the white flour acidity ranges from 1.93–2.13 degrees and the dark flour acidity ranges from 3.53–3.73 degrees, confirming that all six flour types fall within the legal limits.

Conclusions

The study presents an analysis of six types of flour from the Romanian market—three white flours and three dark flours—regarding both the flour's organoleptic characteristics (color, smell, taste) and its physico-chemical properties.

It was observed that the three types of white flour have a white or yellowish-white color with a slightly grey tint, while the three types of dark flour have a light grey color with a slight yellowish-white hue. These colors fall within the limits stipulated by the current legislation. The smell analysis confirmed that all analyzed flours have a pleasant odor, specific to flour, with no signs of mold, staleness, or other unpleasant smells. The taste of all six flour types is normal, slightly sweet, neither bitter nor sour, with no grit upon chewing.

The determination of the water absorption capacity of wheat flour ranges between 59.22%–59.68% for white flour and 57.88%–58.54% for dark flour. The wet gluten determination in the analyzed flour shows that all six flour types comply with the current standards (28.33%–28.61%). For flour

moisture determination, it can be observed that the moisture content ranges between 14.32%–14.42% (white flour) and 14.39%–14.46% (dark flour). Regarding the flour ash content, it ranges between 0.33%–0.42% (white flour) and 0.92%–0.99% (dark flour). The determination of flour acidity shows it varies between 1.93–2.13 degrees of acidity (white flour) and 3.53–3.73 degrees of acidity (dark flour). All values obtained fall within the limits stipulated by the current legislation.

Bibliografie

- Abdelghafor R.F., Mustafa A.I., Ibrahim A.M.H. & Krishnan P.G. (2011). Quality of bread from composite flour of sorghum and hard white winter wheat. *Advance Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 3(1), 9-15.
- Arp C.G., Correa M.J., Zuleta Á. & Ferrero C. (2017). Techno-functional properties of wheat flour-resistant starch mixtures applied to breadmaking. *International Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 52(2), 550-558. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijfs.13311>
- ASRO. (1996). *Wheat flour*. (SR 877:1996). Bucharest
- Bodor K., Szilágyi J., Salamon B., Szakács O. & Bodor Z. (2024). Physical–chemical analysis of different types of flours available in the Romanian market. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 881. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-49535-x>
- Bordei D. (2000). *Baking science and technology*.
- Bordei D., Bahrim G. & Pâslaru V. (2007). *Controlul calității în industria panificației: metode de analiză*. Academica.
- Butt M. S., Iqbal J., Naz A., Suleria H.A.R., Qayyum M.M.N., Saleem F. & Jahangir M.A. (2011). Effect of flour blending on bread characteristics. *Internet Journal of Food Safety*, 13, 142-149.

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- Ciudad-Mulero M., Matallana-González M.C., Callejo M.J., Carrillo J.M., Morales P. & Fernández-Ruiz V. (2021). Durum and Bread Wheat Flours. Preliminary Mineral Characterization and Its Potential Health Claims. *Agronomy*, 11(1).
- Dhingra S. & Jood S. (2002). Physico-Chemical and Nutritional Properties of Cereal-Pulse Blends for Bread Making. *Nutrition and Health*, 16(3), 183-194.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/026010600201600304>
- Drăgoi M.C., Andrei J. V., Mieiă M., Panait M., Dobrotă C.E. & Lădaru R.G. (2018). Siguranța și securitatea alimentară în românia—o analiză econometrică în contextul transformării paradigmei agricole naționale. *Amfiteatru economic*, 20(47), 134-150.
- Guo J., Wang F., Zhang Z., Wu D. & Bao J. (2021). Characterization of gluten proteins in different parts of wheat grain and their effects on the textural quality of steamed bread. *Journal of Cereal Science*, 102, 103368.
- Kumar P., Yadava R.K., Gollen B., Kumar S., Verma R.K. & Yadav S. (2011). Nutritional contents and medicinal properties of wheat: a review. *Life Sciences and Medicine Research*, 22(1), 1-10.
- Martín-Esparza M.E. & González-Martínez C.A.A. (2013). Cooking properties of fresh pasta supplemented with tiger nut flour.
- Modoran C.V. (2007). *Tehnologia morăritului și panificației*. Risoprint.
- Morel M.H., Pincemaille J., Chauveau E., Louhichi A., Violleau F., Menut P., Ramos L. & Banc A. (2020). Insight into gluten structure in a mild chaotropic solvent by asymmetrical flow field-flow fractionation (AsFIFFF) and evidence of non-covalent assemblies between glutenin and ω -gliadin. *Food Hydrocolloids*, 103, 105676.
- Navarro J.L., Moiraghi M., Quiroga F.M., León A.E. & Steffolani M.E. (2020). Effect of Wholewheat Flour Particle Shape Obtained by Different Milling Processes on Physicochemical Characteristics and Quality of Bread. *Food Technol Biotechnol*, 58(3), 325-336.
<https://doi.org/10.17113/ftb.58.03.20.6766>
- Ndife J., Abdulraheem L.O. & Zakari U.M. (2011). Evaluation of the nutritional and sensory quality of functional breads produced from whole wheat and soya bean flour blends. *African Journal of Food Science*, 5(8), 466-472.
- Niculescu N.I. (2000). *Tehnologia produselor făinoase*. București.
- Schopf M., Wehrli M.C., Becker T., Jekle M. & Scherf K.A. (2021). Fundamental characterization of wheat gluten. *European Food Research and Technology*, 247(4), 985-997.
- Standardization Romanian Institute of. (1988). *Wheat flour. Methods of analysis* (STAS 90-88).
- Tejera R.L., Luis G., González-Weller D., Caballero J.M., Gutiérrez Á.J., Rubio C. & Hardisson A. (2013). Metals in wheat flour; comparative study and safety control. *Nutricion hospitalaria*, 28(2), 506-513.

ANALYSIS OF SYNTHETIC DYE USE (TRIPHENYLMETHANE, QUINOLINE, XANTHENE CLASSES) IN PHARMACY AND THEIR TOXICOLOGICAL IMPLICATIONS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The use of food dyes in both the food and pharmaceutical industries can be beneficial for appearance, identification, and masking unpleasant tastes. However, this practice must be done responsibly, by adhering to regulations and prioritizing consumer safety.

In this paper, we identified the most frequently used dyes from the triphenylmethane, quinoline, and xanthene classes employed as excipients in the preparation of various pharmaceutical dosage forms. To achieve this, we analyzed 50 pharmaceutical products sold in an open-circuit pharmacy in Bihor County.

Keywords: dyes, triphenylmethane, quinolein, xanthenic class

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INTRODUCTION

In the food industry, synthetic dyes are used to replace the natural color of the food product, which is often lost during processing. This is done despite studies demonstrating that the color provided by the dye can alter biochemical laboratory analyses and the histopathological structure of the liver and kidneys if food products containing them are consumed (Soltan & Shehata, 2012).

In the pharmaceutical industry, dyes are used as excipients in various dosage forms that are intended to be colored, such as tablets, capsules (hard and soft gelatin capsules), oral solutions, ointments, etc. The purpose of using these dyes is to improve the aesthetic appearance and to increase the preparation's stability (Biswal et al., 2015). Dyes are added to foods, supplements, and medicines for commercial, psychological, or practical reasons (Šuleková et al., 2016).

In the cosmetic industry, dyes are used, either alone or in combination, in proportions

ranging from 1–25% to color products such as lipsticks, blushes (or eye shadows), mascaras, eyeliners (or eye pencils), nail polishes, and hair dyes (Ardila-Leal et al., 2021).

With the development of industry, especially the food and pharmaceutical sectors, several classes of dyes emerged and their use significantly increased. Alongside this expanded usage across various economic branches, the risk of toxic effects also grew considerably. In the 1980s, a study was conducted which revealed that approximately 280,000 tons of textile dyes are discharged annually worldwide into industrial effluents.

The path of these discharged dyes into the environment is concerning: after reaching surface water, they infiltrate the groundwater, posing a risk to consumers and the entire ecosystem. It has been demonstrated that once in the water, they can be a risk factor because these dyes cannot be broken down by the standard treatments applied to wastewater, raw water, or industrial effluents. This difficulty in

degradation is primarily due to their very complex chemical structures.

Another risk factor for human health is skin exposure to dyes, either in the workplace or through the use of various cosmetic products. When absorbed through the skin, these dyes can potentially lead to mutagenic, cytotoxic, and genotoxic effects (Scientific Committee on Cosmetic Products and Non-food Products intended for Consumers, 2002).

The absorption of dyes through the skin has been demonstrated *in vitro* using both mouse and human skin, both of which were shown to be capable of reductively cleaving the dye (Sandu, 2014). This reductive process occurs in the presence of enzymes found in gastric juices, saliva, or sweat.

It has been proven that these dyes are responsible for mutagenic or carcinogenic effects, effects which are actually caused not by the dyes themselves, but by their breakdown products. This finding has led to the prohibition of these dyes for food use in several countries

Figure 1. Chemical structures of patent blue V (E131) and brilliant blue FCF (E133)

From the xanthene class of dyes, the only one authorized for use as a food additive is Erythrosine (E127, the dipotassium or disodium salt of tetra-2', 4', 5', 7' tetraiodofluorescein).

Figure 2. Chemical structures of erythrosine (E127) and quinolein yellow (E104)

(Nenițescu, 2015). Other potential side effects of dyes include the development of allergies; their decomposition can release histamine, which may intensify asthma; and they can lead to hyperactivity and reduced concentration in children.

The objective of the study is to identify the most commonly used dyes from the triphenylmethane, quinoline, and xanthene classes employed as excipients in the preparation of various pharmaceutical dosage forms.

The triphenylmethane group includes Patent Blue V (E131, the dicalcium salt of m-hydroxytetraethyl-diamino-triphenyl-carbinol-disulfonic acid anhydride) and Brilliant Green (E133, the disodium salt of 4[4-(N-ethyl-p-sulfobenzylamino)-phenyl]-(2-sulfonium phenyl)-methylene-[1-(N-ethyl-N-p-sulfobenzyl)-2,5 cyclohexadiene-imine], both of which produce green or blue colors (see Figure 1) (Necula & Babii, 2010).

The dye from the quinoline group used as an additive is Quinoline Yellow (E104, the disodium salt of 2-quinoyl-2-indandione-1,3-disulfonic acid), (see Figure 2)(Necula & Babii, 2010).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The study conducted involves the analysis of dye content—specifically those from the triphenylmethane, quinoline, and xanthene classes—in various pharmaceutical products sold in an open-circuit pharmacy in Bihor County.

The products analyzed include:

- RX (prescription-only medicines)
- OTCs (over-the-counter medicines)
- Dietary Supplements (DS).

The pharmaceutical products analyzed are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Pharmaceutical products analyzed, pharmaceutical form, type of dye used, and manufacturing country			
Notation	Pharmaceutical form	Type of dye used (E)	Manufacturing Country
RX1	Capsules	104, 110, 122, 171	Romania
RX2	Capsules	104, 110, 124, 133, 171	Romania
RX3	Capsules	104, 110, 124, 133, 171	Romania
RX4	Capsules	104, 132, 171	Slovenia
RX5	Capsules	104, 132, 171	Slovenia
RX6	Capsules	104, 132, 133, 171	Romania
RX7	Capsules	131, 171, 172	Romania
RX8	Extended-release capsules	102, 110, 129, 133, 171	Slovenia
RX9	Extended-release capsules	110, 124, 133, 171	Slovenia
RX10	Extended-release capsules	102, 110, 129, 133, 171	Slovenia
RX11	Extended-release capsules	10, 129, 133, 171	Slovenia
RX12	Extended-release capsules	110, 127, 129, 133, 171	Slovenia
RX13	Tablets	110, 1292, 133	Poland
RX14	Tablets	133	Poland
RX15	Tablets	120, 133	Poland
RX16	Dragees	104, 171	Austria
RX17	Capsules	104, 127, 133, 142, 171	Romania
RX18	Capsules	110, 124, 133, 151, 171	Romania
OTC1	Pills	104, 110, 122, 171	Romania
OTC2	Tablets	104	Poland
OTC3	Tablets	104, 110, 122	Czech Republic
OTC4	Pills	104	Great Britain
OTC5	Pills	104	Great Britain
OTC6	Gelatin capsules	104, 110, 218	Germany
OTC7	Capsules	104, 110, 171, 216, 218	Romania
OTC8	Pills	104, 132, 951, 953	Italy
OTC9	Capsules	127, 171, 172	Romania
OTC10	Capsules	127, 171	France
OTC11	Film-coated tablets	127	Czech Republic
OTC12	Capsules	127, 132, 171	France
OTC13	Film-coated tablets	127, 171	Czech Republic
OTC14	Film-coated tablets	127, 171	Czech Republic
OTC15	Sachets	104, 110	Germany
OTC16	Capsules	104, 320, 951	Germany
OTC17	Sachets	104, 110	Germany
OTC18	Film-coated tablets	127, 171	Romania
OTC19	Capsules	104, 122, 133, 171	Romania
OTC20	Sachets	104	Spain
OTC21	Film-coated tablets	104, 110, 171	Ireland
OTC22	Sachets	104, 32, 951	Great Britain
OTC23	Gelatin capsules	104, 131, 171, 420	Italy
OTC24	Capsules	104, 132	Czech Republic
OTC25	Capsules	104, 127, 133, 142, 171, 216, 218	Romania
OTC26	Gelatin capsules	102, 131	Romania
OTC27	Gelatin capsules	131	Romania
OTC28	Gelatin capsules	131, 171	France
OTC29	Pills	133	Slovenia
OTC30	Effervescent tablets	104, 127, 420	Ireland
OTC31	Pills	133, 953	Slovenia
SA1	Capsules	104, 127, 133	Romania

The products included in the study were analyzed based on several criteria: the classification of their pharmaceutical form, the country in which they were manufactured, the number of dyes they contain from the triphenylmethane, quinoline, and xanthene classes, the number of E-numbers used in the formulation of the analyzed products from the

manufacturing country, the pharmaceutical forms in which the dyes are most frequently used, and the dye class that is most commonly utilized.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Out of the total of 50 pharmaceutical products included in the study, the analysis

covered 18 prescription-only medicines (RX), 31 over-the-counter medicines (OTCs), and 1

dietary supplement (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Number of RX, OTC and supplements from which dyes were analyzed

By analyzing the products included in the study, it is observed that the majority are Over-The-Counter medicines (OTCs), representing 62% of the sample, which are available in pharmacies without a medical prescription. Next are the Prescription-Only medicines (RXs) at 34%, which require a medical prescription, followed by only a single dietary supplement.

The pharmaceutical products analyzed were manufactured by various pharmaceutical companies, both domestic and foreign (see Figure 4). The breakdown by country is as follows: Romania (16), Poland (4), Czech Republic (5), Great Britain (3), Germany (4), Slovenia (9), Italy (2), France (3), Spain (1), Ireland (2), and Austria (1).

Figure 4. Breakdown of the products taken in the study by the country in which they were produced

Following the study, we observed that 32% of the analyzed products were manufactured in Romania, 18% in Slovenia, 10% in the Czech Republic, 8% in Poland and Germany, 6% in France and Great Britain, 4% in Italy and Ireland, and 2% in Spain and Austria.

Based on the study of the products, categorized by the total number of E-numbers they contain, we observed the following (see Figure 5): 26% contain 3 E-numbers, 22% contain 2 E-numbers, 16% contain 1, 4, or 5 E-numbers, and 2% contain 6 or 7 E-numbers (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. E-Numbers Count and Percentage in Analyzed Products

However, by analyzing the average of E-numbers used per product based on the manufacturing country in the products under study, it can be observed that there are

countries where the average number of E-numbers used exceeds the figure of 3 (Romania, Italy, Slovenia, France) (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. E-Number Usage in Analyzed Products, by Country of Manufacture

The pharmaceutical forms in which we most frequently encountered the use of dyes are: capsules at 56% (28 products), tablets at 22% (11 products), lozenges/pellets at 12% (6

products), powders at 8% (4 products), and dragees/coated tablets at 2% (1 product) (see Figure 7).

Figure 7. Types of pharmaceutical forms taken in the study

The dyes most commonly used as additives from the triphenylmethane, xanthene, and quinoline classes in the formulation of medicines are: E104, E127, E131, and E133.

Among these, the most frequently encountered in the analyzed products was Quinoline Yellow (E104), followed by the triphenylmethane dyes (E131 and E133), and then the xanthene dye (E127) (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. The most frequently used dyes from the triphenylmethane, xanthene, and quinoline classes in the formulation of the products included in the study

Dyes from the studied classes were used in the composition of the analyzed medicines:

triphenylmethane (38.00%), xanthene (17%), and quinoline (45%) (see Figure 9).

Figure 9. Percentage of studied dyes used in analyzed pharmaceutical products

There are numerous studies conducted to demonstrate the toxicity of dyes used in both the food and pharmaceutical industries. Data from the FDA (Food, Drug and Cosmetic Act)

show a dramatic, fivefold increase in the consumption of synthetic dyes since 1955 (Potera, 2010).

Reactions induced by products containing triphenylmethane, quinoline, or xanthene dyes vary widely, from nasal congestion or running nose to anaphylactic shock or enterocolitis (Gultekin & Doguc, 2013). Many of these dyes are responsible for causing side effects in children, such as contact dermatitis, gastrointestinal intolerance, bronchospasm, eosinophilia, angioedema, skin rash, and even hyperactivity (Chatterjee & Alvi, 2014; Chequer et al., 2011; Gultekin & Doguc, 2013; Šuleková, Hudák & 2016). Another adverse effect produced by these dyes is their accumulation in the body, which can lead to the delayed onset of cancer (Necula & Babii, 2010; Sandu, 2014; Scientific Committee on Consumer Products, 2005).

Each country maintains its own control regarding the use of additives, in Romania (Ministerul Sănătății, 1998) mandated several regulations: the addition of additives must be labeled on every retail package, the use of food additives is prohibited for the purpose of masking alterations or degradations in food products. Additionally, purity standards that the additives must meet were established (Council, 2012; Mihele, 2008)

CONCLUSIONS

The use of dyes in food and pharmaceutical products carries important implications concerning safety, quality, and consumer perception.

Some artificial dyes can have adverse effects in addition to their benefits, especially in children or sensitive individuals, causing issues like hyperactivity and allergic reactions. Consequently, certain substances have been banned in various countries due to carcinogenic or toxic risks.

Strict regulations govern the use of dyes, both at the national and international levels (e.g., EFSA in the EU, FDA in the USA). Admitted daily intakes (ADIs) are well established, and labeling is mandatory to inform the consumer.

In recent years, an increasing trend has been observed toward replacing synthetic dyes with natural, consumer-safe colorants. However, these natural alternatives have the disadvantage of having lower stability and a higher cost.

REFERENCES

- Ardila-Leal L.D., Poutou-Piñales R.A., Pedroza-Rodríguez A.M. & Quevedo-Hidalgo B.E. (2021). A Brief History of Colour, the Environmental Impact of Synthetic Dyes and Removal by Using Laccases. *Molecules*, 26(13).
- Biswal P.K., Mishar M.K., Bhadouriya A.S. & Yadav V.K. (2015). AN UPDATED REVIEW ON COLORANTS AS THE PHARMACEUTICAL EXCIPIENTS. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical, Chemical & Biological Sciences*, 5(4).
- Chatterjee P. & Alvi M.M. (2014). Excipients and active pharmaceutical ingredients. In *Pediatric Formulations: A Roadmap* (pp. 347-361). Springer.
- Chequer F.M.D., Dorta D.J. & De Oliveira D.P. (2011). Azo dyes and their metabolites: does the discharge of the azo dye into water bodies represent human and ecological risks. *Advances in treating textile effluent*, 48, 28-48.
- Council European Parliament and. (2012). *REGULAMENTUL (UE) NR. 261/2012 AL PARLAMENTULUI EUROPEAN ȘI AL CONSILIULUI DIN 14 MARTIE 2012 DE MODIFICARE A REGULAMENTULUI (CE) NR. 1234/2007 AL CONSILIULUI ÎN CEEA CE PRIVEȘTE RELAȚIILE CONTRACTUALE*. (261/2012). Luxembourg/Brussels: Official Journal of the European Union
- Gultekin F. & Doguc D.K. (2013). Allergic and immunologic reactions to food additives. *Clinical reviews in allergy & immunology*, 45(1), 6-29.
- Mihele D. (2008). Igiena alimentației. *Nutriție. Dietoterapie și compoziția alimentelor*, Editura Medicală, București.
- Ministerul Sănătății M.S. (1998). *Ordinul nr. 975/1998 pentru aprobarea normelor igienico-sanitare privind unitățile de asistență medicală*. București
- Necula V. & Babii M. (2010). *Alimentație, alimente și impactul acestora asupra sănătății consumatorului*. Editura Universității" Transilvania".
- Nenișescu C.D. (2015). *Chimie Organică* (Vol. I).
- Potera C. (2010). DIET AND NUTRITION: The Artificial Food Dye Blues. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 118(10), A428-A428. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.118-a428>
- Sandu D. (2014). *Studiu privind colorantii organici*. Asociația Profesorilor. Retrieved 05.10.2025 from <http://www.asociatia-profesorilor.ro/studiu-privind-colorantii-organici.html>
- Scientific Committee on Consumer Products SCCP. (2005). *Opinion on Amino Acids obtained by Hydrolysis of Human Hair* (SCCP/0894/05).
- Scientific Committee on Cosmetic Products and Non-food Products intended for Consumers SCCNFP. (2002). *Opinion of the scientific committee on cosmetic products and non-food products intended for consumers - Concerning the safety review of the use of certain azo-dyes in cosmetic products* (19th plenary meeting).

- Soltan S.S.A. & Shehata M.M.E.M. (2012). The effects of using color foods of children on immunity properties and liver, kidney on rats. *Food and Nutrition Sciences*, 3(7), 897-904.
- Šuleková M., Hudák A. & Smrčová M. (2016). The determination of food dyes in vitamins by RP-HPLC. *Molecules*, 21(10), 1368.

OPTIMIZATION OF THE WOOD DRYING PROCESS USING GEOTHERMAL WATER

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Abstract

Geothermal energy is a renewable resource capable of delivering heat and electricity continuously, regardless of external conditions such as weather or season. Its constant availability makes it a valuable addition to a diversified energy mix. Moreover, geothermal energy is practically inexhaustible and can be accessed in many regions across the globe.

The present paper aims to investigate optimization strategies for the drying of the wood by regulating the use of geothermal water. The objective is to determine which method of integrating geothermal energy into existing technological equipment offers the highest efficiency.

Keywords: optimization, wood drying, geothermal water, regulation, control system

INTRODUCTION

The natural heat stored in the Earth's crust gives rise to geothermal energy, which may be of low or high temperature. Theoretically, low-temperature geothermal energy can be accessed anywhere in the world due to the natural increase in temperature with depth (approximately 3°C per 100 m). High-temperature geothermal energy is characteristic of volcanic areas. In contact with hot rocks, underground water can reach temperatures of several hundred degrees, often undergoing partial vaporization; this heat source can then be harnessed in a power plant.

An artificial geothermal option consists of using the heat of magma that has infiltrated certain areas close to the surface, at depths of about 2,000–7,000 m. In this case, wells are drilled and water is injected, producing superheated steam. (Åström K. J., 2002; Setel A., 2008)

Geothermal energy has applications in a wide range of fields, such as the use of hot water for domestic, commercial, or industrial needs, heating and cooling systems, and electricity generation through the conversion of high-pressure steam. Since geothermal resources are relatively constant, they can be used to meet energy demands both under normal operating conditions and during peak load periods.

Worldwide, geothermal power plants have a total installed capacity of over 8,000 MW.

Systems that convert geothermal energy can supply electricity with an annual capacity factor of over 90%.

In Romania, hydrogeothermal resources (extracted through drilling) include low-enthalpy geothermal systems (with temperatures between 25°C and 60°C in deep aquifers) and medium-temperature geothermal systems (from 60°C to 125°C in mesothermal waters). Low-enthalpy geothermal resources are used for heating and domestic hot water production in individual households, social services (offices, education, commercial and community spaces, etc.), the industrial sector, and agricultural facilities (greenhouses, solariums, livestock farms, etc.). (Åström K. J., 2002; Setel A., 2008)

Romania's currently exploitable geothermal energy reserve is approximately 167 thousand toe ($7,000 \times 10^6$ GJ/year). The amount of equivalent energy produced and delivered at the wellhead is about 30.171 thousand toe ($1,326 \times 10^6$ GJ/year), with an average annual utilization rate of 22.3%.

The economic drilling and extraction limit for geothermal waters has been set at a depth of 3,300 m, a threshold that has been reached in certain areas of Romania, such as the Bucharest North–Otopeni geothermal basin and specific zones within the localities of Snagov and Balotesti.

In 2003, Romania had 70 operational wells supplying local heating and domestic hot

water needs (with temperatures above 60°C) for residential complexes, public or industrial buildings, and agricultural facilities in various regions. Additionally, 45 wells with certified energy potential are currently preserved or held in reserve. (Åström K. J., 2002; Setel A., 2008)

The operating lifetime of the existing installations exceeds 20 years, and the materials and equipment used exhibit significant physical and technological wear. The management of geothermal energy consumption (billing of delivered/used energy) is carried out on a flat-rate basis, relying on periodic readings of wellhead parameters with industrial-grade instruments, due to the absence of proper meters or the use of low-precision equipment.

The degree of utilization of geothermal energy resources in Romania remains low, primarily because of insufficient financial support needed to foster the development of this energy sector, which has the potential to generate substantial economic benefits.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The primary purpose of geothermal installations is to prepare the thermal agent for transport to the consuming systems and then return it to the heat source. The specific equipment used depends on the nature and parameters of the thermal agent, as well as the intended thermal applications. (Åström K. J., 2002; Setel A., 2008)

When steam is used as the thermal agent, the basic equipment includes steam collectors, measuring, control, and regulation devices for the thermal agent parameters (pressure, temperature, flow rate), condensate collection tanks, and pumps for condensate removal.

For the use of hot water or warm water as the thermal agent, the main equipment consists of heat exchangers for heating, heat exchangers for domestic hot water preparation, circulation pumps, softening stations, expansion vessels, valves, automation and control systems, and corrosion protection installations.

Verifying the correct functioning of the automation program is possible only when the system is operating, which requires numerous experiments that are both costly and time-consuming. For this reason, the simulation program becomes particularly valuable, serving not only in the design of the automation logic but also in its validation.

System management block diagram (Fig. 2)

- The primary purpose of the simulation program is to validate the automation program and, in particular, to analyze the behavior of installation parameters under various disturbance conditions (A. Zavala-Río et al., 2009; Setel A., 2008).

- A further objective is to determine the constants of the PID (Proportional, Integral, Derivative) controllers. Different sets of PID constants will produce different system responses when disturbances occur. By running the simulation repeatedly with various PID values, one can identify the optimal parameters to be implemented in the actual automation program (Åström K. J., 2002; Setel A., 2008).

- A secondary, yet operationally important objective is the training and assessment of personnel who operate the pre-drying and drying installation, for whom the simulation provides a safe and practical learning environment.

Figure 2 System Driving Block Diagram

With the configuration shown in Figure 3, the trainee can monitor the operation of the pre-drying and drying installation on Computer 2, where the InTouch graphical interface displays the system diagram and all relevant parameters. In actual operation, the same interface is used, but during simulation the real-time signals are replaced by the mathematical model developed in ACSL-GM and run on Computer 1. The evaluator, positioned at Computer 1, can generate any operating

scenario and then observe the trainee's responses.

Figure 3 Block scheme corresponding to the pre-drying-drying complex

The required flow rate is maintained through the commands issued by the RG03, RG02, and RG01 controllers, based on the system pressure measured by the PT1 pressure transducer.

It should be emphasized that the control strategy is unified, consisting of seven interdependent regulators integrated to ensure the proper functioning of the entire system. The determination of the PID constants for these seven regulators, as well as the configuration of their interconnections, will be addressed further.

1. Regulation scheme for obtaining the hot-air preparation agent required in the wood-drying process

The block diagram illustrating the automation loops for generating the hot-air preparation agent used in the pre-drying stage of wood is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Conduction block scheme for obtaining the hot air preparation agent, necessary for the technological process of pre-drying wood

2. Diagram of the driving block for obtaining the hot air preparation agent, necessary for the technological process of wood drying (Fig.5.)

Figure 5 Driving block scheme for obtaining the hot air preparation agent, necessary for the technological process of wood drying

The hot air inlet temperature t_{x3} is measured by the TT_{x3} temperature transducer. Due to various disturbing causes, the temperature t_{x3} may change from its nominal value ($50 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$), which requires it to be brought back within the limits allowed by the control given by the RG7 controller to the CV7 electrically operated valve. (C. Popescu et al, 2001, Setel A, 2008).

The inlet temperature of the secondary agent into the wood drying plant t_3 is measured by the TT_3 temperature transducer. Due to various disturbing causes, the temperature t_3 may change compared to its nominal value ($55 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$), which requires it to be brought back within the limits allowed by the command given by the RG3 regulator to the CV3 electrically operated valve (the geothermal water supply flow is modified). (Z. Liao et al, 2005 Setel A, 2008).

The differential equations that define the process are written, successively determining the opening of the tap CV3 (h), the flow of geothermal water passing through the tap and, finally, the inlet temperature of the secondary agent in the wood drying plant (t_3), respectively the outflow temperature of the geothermal water $teac_3$ measured by the temperature transducer TT_{eac3} . The calculation is performed for each moment of the process until it is stabilized, and the simulation program allows the plot of the evolution of the monitored parameters to be traced in real time. (Crispin Allen, 1990, Setel A, 2008).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

After implementing the simulation program for the operation of the wood and wood pre-drying/drying installation, the program was executed in order to achieve the proposed objectives (verification of the proposed control system and tuning of the PID controllers). As a result of the simulation, considering various

operating scenarios and correlating the obtained data with those resulting from the analysis of the tested subsystems, the PID controllers were successfully tuned. Below are several scenarios taken into account in the study.

a. Transient operating regime during the start-up of the wood and wood pre-drying/drying installation

Using the simulation program, the method by which the system reaches steady-state conditions at start-up was determined. After this, the parameters corresponding to controllers RG1, RG2, RG3, and RG4 were adjusted so that the time required to reach steady state would match the functional parameters observed in practice.

a.1. Transient regime for the wood pre-drying installation

Figure 6 shows the evolution of the main parameters until steady-state conditions are achieved, namely the temperature t_1 (measured by TT1) at the outlet of the secondary agent from the heat exchanger (IPUMLTT1), and the temperature $teac_1$ (measured by TTeac1) at the outlet of the geothermal water from the heat exchanger (IPUMLTTEAC1), under the condition that the temperature inside the pre-drying chamber tx_1 (measured by TT x_1) is 60°C (IPUMLTTX1). It can be observed that the regime stabilizes after approximately 7,200 seconds (120 minutes), a duration consistent with practical data. In this case, the steady-state parameters reach 65°C for the secondary agent and 50°C for the geothermal water.

geothermală.

Figure 6 Evolution of the outlet temperatures of the primary and secondary agents for the wood pre-drying installation until reaching steady-state conditions (at start-up).

ransient operating regime for the wood-drying installation

Figure 7 illustrates the evolution of the main parameters until steady-state conditions are reached, namely: the temperature t_2

(measured by TT2) at the outlet of the secondary agent from the heat exchanger (IUMLTT2), the temperature $teac_2$ (measured by TTeac2) at the outlet of the geothermal water from the heat exchanger (IUMLTTEAC2), under the condition that the temperature inside the drying chamber tx_2 (measured by TT x_2) is 80°C (IUMLTTX2). It can be observed that the system stabilizes after approximately 6,000 seconds (100 minutes), a duration consistent with practical data. In this case, the steady-state parameters reach 85°C for the secondary agent and 60°C for the geothermal water

Figure 7 Evolution of the output temperatures of the primary and secondary agents for wood drying plant until steady state (start-up)

Transitional regime in the event of disturbances for the pre-drying plant wood

It is considered the situation in which the temperature in the wood drying room drops from 50°C to 45°C, due to accidental opening of the door. In this situation, the TT x_3 temperature transducer, which measures the temperature in the drying chamber, transmits the signal to the RG7 controller, which commands the opening of the CV7 valve, increasing the flow of secondary agent and, consequently, the temperature t_3 decreases. The TT3 temperature transducer transmits the signal to the RG3 controller which commands the unplugging of the CV3 tap, increasing the flow of geothermal water. The control process (control of the CV3 and CV7 valves by the RG3 and RG7 controllers) is carried out until the temperature in the room stabilizes at 50°C.

Figure 8 shows the evolution of the main parameters, up to the steady state, namely the temperature t_3 (measured by TT3) of the outlet of the secondary agent from the heat exchanger (IPUFPTT3), the temperature $teac_3$ (measured by TTeac3) of the outlet of the geothermal

water from the heat exchanger (IPUFPTTEAC3), the temperature tx3 (measured by TTx3) from the drying chamber (IPUFPTTX3)

Figure 8 Evolution of the output temperatures of the primary and secondary agents for the wood drying plant until the steady state is reached (when disturbances occur)

Figure 9. illustrates the evolution of the main parameters until steady-state conditions are reached, namely the temperature t1 (measured by TT1) at the outlet of the secondary agent from the heat exchanger (IPUMLTT1), the temperature teac1 (measured by TTeac1) at the outlet of the geothermal water from the heat exchanger (IPUMLTTEAC1), and the temperature tx1 (measured by TTx1) inside the pre-drying chamber (IPUMLTTX1). It can be observed that the system stabilizes after approximately 600 seconds (10 minutes), a duration consistent with practical data. In this case, the steady-state values are: 60°C for the chamber temperature, 65°C for the secondary agent, and 50°C for the geothermal

water.

Figure 9 Evolution of the output temperatures of the primary and secondary agents for the plant drying of the wood until the steady state is reached (when disturbances occur)

CONCLUSIONS

The main objectives of the simulation program were the verification and qualitative validation of the proposed control strategy for

the wood pre-drying/drying installation, by analyzing the behavior of the parameters that define its operation, as well as determining the parameters of the PID controllers used. The corresponding values of the controller parameters can be viewed by consulting the.CSL source program presented in Annex 5.

In this context, the control loops corresponding to the physical processes were analyzed, and the mathematical models of the associated component equipment were detailed. After identifying the appropriate start-up conditions for the wood pre-drying/drying installation and the potential disturbances that may occur, the simulation program was tested by examining several variants, each variant having different sets of start-up conditions and considered disturbances. Each action essentially has a stabilizing effect.

For the variants presented, the values of the controller parameters that will initially be used in the automation program were selected. Their final values will be established only during the commissioning of the designed installation.

REFERENCES

- A. Bara: "Sisteme Fuzzy, „Aplicații la Conducerea Proceselor”, Ed. U.T. Press Cluj-Napoca, 2001, ISBN 973-9471-75-7;
- A. Zavala-Río, C.M. Astorga-Zaragoza, O. Hernández-González: "Bounded positive control for double-pipe heat exchangers" in *Control Engineering Practice* nr.17, 2009, pg. 136-145, ELSEVIER;
- Ahmed Maidi, Moussa Diaf, Jean-Pierre Corriou: "Boundary geometric control of a counter-current heat exchanger" in *Journal of Process Control* nr.19, 2009, pg. 297–313, ELSEVIER;
- Alejandro H. González, Darci Odloak, Jacinto L. Marchetti: "Predictive control applied to heat-exchanger networks" in *Chemical Engineering and Processing* nr.45, 2006, pg. 661–671, ELSEVIER
- Angel Vidal, Alfonso Bãnos: "Reset compensation for temperature control: Experimental application on heat exchangers" in *Chemical Engineering Journal* nr.159, 2010 pg. 170–181, ELSEVIER;
- Astrom K. J., *Control System Design*, Lund Institute of Technology, 2002.
- BurkhardSanner: "Geothermal energy opportunities for desert regions" in *Global Conference on Renewable Energy Approaches for Desert Regions*, Amman, Jordan 2006
- C. Pantea, G.M. Rosca, C. A. Blaga "Power generation from low enthalpy geothermal resources" in *Journal of sustainable energy*, vol.1, nr.2 (2010);
- C. Popescu, D.Popescu, S.Dale: "IngineriaReglării Automate", Ed. Universității din Oradea 2001, curs.
- Crispin Allen (1990): *Programmable Logical Controllers and Their Engineering Applications*, McGraw Hill, 1990.
- Curtis D.J. (1988): *Process Control Instrumentation Technology*, Prentice Hall International, 1988.

- Danfoss (1986): Modulating pressure and temperature regulators, RK.09.A1.02, Danfoss Nordborg, Denmark, 1986.
- Denis Marcotte, Philippe Pasquier: "Fast fluid and ground temperature computation for geothermal ground-loop heat exchanger systems" in *Geothermics* nr.37, 2008 pg. 651–665, ELSEVIER;
- Elena Zierler: "Geothermal energy an alternative for Romania" in *Analele Universității din Oradea, Seria Geografie, Tom XVIII*, 2008, pag. 140-143
- Eui-Jong Kim, Jean-Jacques Roux, Gilles Rusaouen, Frederic Kuznik: "Numerical modelling of geothermal vertical heat exchangers for the short time analysis using the state model size reduction technique" in *Applied Thermal Engineering* nr.30, 2010, pg. 706–714, ELSEVIER;
- F. S. Blaga, "Teoria Sistemelor și Reglaj Automat", ed. Universității din Oradea, 2009 ISBN978-973-759-807-3;
- Setel Aurel Utilizarea energiei geotermale în silvicultură, Teză de doctorat, 2008
- Y. Babi, A. Dobbi, M. Saighi, B. Bouchekima: "Heating an agricultural greenhouse by using geothermal energy" in *Revue des Energies Renouvelables CER'07 Oujda*, 2007, pg.265-268;
- Z Liao, A.L Dexter: "An experimental study on an inferential control scheme for optimizing the control of boilers in multi-zone heating system" in *Energy and Buildings* nr. 37, 2005, pg. 55–63, ELSEVIER

ANISE (*PIMPINELLA ANISUM*) AS A FUNCTIONAL INGREDIENT IN MUSTARD: IMPACT ON PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES, ANTIOXIDANT CAPACITY AND COLOR PARAMETERS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This study investigates the fortification of mustard with anise (*Pimpinella anisum*) at concentrations of 0%, 0.5%, 1%, and 1.5%, with the aim of improving its functional properties. Physicochemical parameters (pH, total acidity, moisture), antioxidant capacity (DPPH and FRAP), total phenolic content, total flavonoid content, and color characteristics (CIE Lab*) were evaluated. The results show that pH remained unaffected by anise addition, while total acidity decreased significantly at 1.5% anise. Moisture content declined in all fortified samples, especially at 1% and 1.5%. Total phenolic content increased significantly in the 1% and 1.5% formulations, whereas flavonoid levels showed no significant variation. Antioxidant capacity improved markedly with increasing anise concentration, particularly in the samples containing 1% and 1.5%. Color analysis revealed a decrease in luminosity, yellowness, and chroma with higher levels of anise, although the hue angle remained stable. Overall, anise fortification enhances the antioxidant potential and phenolic profile of mustard while modifying its visual characteristics.

Keywords: mustard; anise (*Pimpinella anisum*); fortification; phenolic compounds; antioxidant activity; color parameters; functional foods

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INTRODUCTION

The concept of functional fortified foods has gained increasing attention in recent decades, driven by greater consumer awareness of the link between diet and health. Traditionally, food fortification aimed to prevent nutrient deficiencies by adding essential vitamins and minerals; however, functional foods go beyond basic nutrition, providing additional physiological benefits due to bioactive compounds, probiotics, and antioxidants (Vignesh et al., 2024; Jendyose, 2024). Functional fortified foods combine both approaches, incorporating essential nutrients and natural bioactives into commonly consumed foods to enhance their nutritional and functional value (Kyazimova et al., 2024; Nagar et al., 2024). This strategy contributes to preventing micronutrient deficiencies and promoting overall health, aligning with current clean label trends that favor natural antioxidants over synthetic additives (Kaur et al., 2022; Grasso et al., 2023).

Mustard (*Brassica* spp.), a member of the Brassicaceae family, is widely cultivated for its seeds, which are used as condiments and sources of edible oil (Rahman et al., 2024). Mustard seeds are rich in oil (28–42%),

proteins (25–40%), carbohydrates, and secondary metabolites such as glucosinolates, phenolic compounds, and tannins (Shahidi, 1990; Rahman et al., 2020; Von Der Haar et al., 2014). These bioactive compounds are associated with antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer properties (Hartmann, 2007; Idrees, 2019; Ramirez et al., 2020). Despite their nutritional and therapeutic potential, mustard seeds may also contain antinutritional factors, such as erucic acid and glucosinolate degradation products, which require controlled processing (Lietzow, 2021).

Anise (*Pimpinella anisum*), belonging to the Apiaceae family, is a medicinal and aromatic plant rich in essential oils and phenolic compounds. Its main constituent, trans-anethole, along with flavonoids, coumarins, and vitamins, contributes to its antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory effects (Picon et al., 2010; Yamini et al., 2008; Moazzami et al., 2020).

This study aimed to evaluate the potential of fortifying a traditional product, mustard, with Anise (*Pimpinella anisum*) to develop a food with enhanced functional value. The objectives were to assess the physicochemical properties,

total phenolic content, antioxidant capacity, and color parameters of mustard samples fortified with three different concentrations of anise extract.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Reagents and ingredients used

The ingredients used for the preparation of the mustard formulations were sourced from certified suppliers to ensure quality and reproducibility. Mustard seeds were obtained from SIA ELPIS SRL (Latvia), while fermentation vinegar (9°) was provided by SEINEANA PRODUCT SRL (Romania). Native corn starch and guar gum were supplied by BARENTZ SRL (Romania). Additional ingredients included refined salt from SOCIETATEA NAȚIONALĂ A SĂRII SA (Romania), sugar and sunflower oil from PARHAN COM SRL (Romania), and citric acid, turmeric, and ground star anise from SOLINA ROMANIA SRL (Romania). All ingredients were food-grade and used without further purification.

Formulation of Mustard Samples Fortified with Anise

Four mustard formulations were prepared by incorporating different concentrations of ground anise (*Pimpinella anisum*): 0% (control), 0.5%, 1.0% and 1.5%. The base recipe was adapted from an industrial-scale formulation and scaled to 100 kg for laboratory production. The ingredients used in the formulations included water, fermentation vinegar (9°), mustard seeds, native corn starch, salt, sugar, sunflower oil, turmeric, guar gum, citric acid, and ground anise. The quantities corresponding to the standard formulation (0% anise) and the fortified variants (0.5%, 1.0%, 1.5%) were calculated proportionally, replacing part of the dry mix with the appropriate amount of anise powder.

Physicochemical determinations

- *Determination of moisture*

Moisture content was determined by the gravimetric method, since the water level influences the texture, microbiological stability, and shelf life of mustard. An empty weighing vial was first weighed (M_1), after which 5 g of mustard sample was added and the vial was weighed again (M_2). The vial was then placed in a drying oven at 105 °C for 4 hours, cooled in a desiccator for 30 minutes, and weighed (M_3). Drying was repeated in 30-minute intervals until

a constant mass was reached. Moisture content (%) was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Moisture content (\%)} = \frac{M_2 - M_3}{M_2 - M_1} \times 100$$

- *pH-determination*

The pH of the mustard samples was determined using an InoLab pH 7310 pH meter. The sample was first homogenized, after which 5 g of mustard were dispersed in 50 mL of distilled water, stirred, and allowed to equilibrate for 5 minutes. The pH was then measured by immersing the electrode fully into the mixture, and the final value was recorded once the reading stabilized.

- *Total acidity determination*

Total acidity was determined by titration. A 5 g portion of mustard was diluted in 50 mL of distilled water, homogenized, and filtered if necessary. Two to three drops of phenolphthalein were added, and the sample was titrated with 0.1 N NaOH under continuous stirring until a persistent pale-pink endpoint was reached. The volume of NaOH used (V , mL) was recorded. Total acidity, expressed as acetic acid (%), was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Total acidity (\% acetic acid)} = (V \times N \times 60)/m$$

where V is the NaOH volume (mL), N is the normality of NaOH (0.1 N), m is the mass of the sample (g), and 60 represents the molecular weight of acetic acid.

Biochemicals analysis

- *Total phenols content*

Total phenolic compounds were determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu method (Singleton et al, 1999; Vicaș et al, 2011). A volume of 100 μ L mustard sample was mixed with 1700 μ L distilled water and 200 μ L freshly diluted Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (1:10, v/v). After approximately 3 minutes, 1 mL of 7.5% sodium carbonate solution was added. The mixtures were incubated at room temperature in the dark for 2 hours, after which the absorbance was measured at 765 nm using a Shimadzu miniUV-Vis spectrophotometer. The calibration curve was constructed using gallic acid standards in the range of 0.05–0.25 mg/mL, and results were expressed as mg gallic acid equivalents (GAE) per 100 mL sample.

- *Total Flavonoids content*

Total flavonoid content was determined using an aluminum chloride colorimetric method, with quercetin serving as the standard.

Calibration was performed using quercetin solutions ranging from 0.1 to 0.5 mg/mL, yielding a regression equation of $y = 0.8388x + 0.0003$ and an $R^2 = 0.996$, with all measurements carried out in triplicate. For sample preparation, 1 mL of mustard extract (P1, P2, P3) was transferred into a 10 mL volumetric flask, followed by the addition of 4 mL distilled water and 3 mL of 5% NaNO₂ solution. After 5 minutes, 0.3 mL of 10% AlCl₃ was added, the mixture was homogenized, and after an additional 6 minutes, 2 mL of 1 M NaOH was added and the volume was adjusted to 10 mL with distilled water. After 15 minutes, absorbance was measured at 510 nm using a Shimadzu miniUV-Vis spectrophotometer. Results were expressed as mg quercetin equivalents (QE) per gram of mustard based on the calibration curve.

- *Antioxidant capacity*

The antioxidant activity was evaluated using the DPPH radical scavenging assay, according to the method described by Vicaş et al (2011). Briefly, 2.9 mL of DPPH solution (80 µM) was transferred into a test tube, followed by the addition of 100 µL mustard extract. The mixture was allowed to react in the dark for exactly 30 minutes, after which the absorbance was measured at 515 nm. The percentage of DPPH inhibition was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{DPPH inhibition (\%)} = [(A_0 - A_s) \times 100] / A_0$$

where A_0 represents the absorbance of the blank and A_s the absorbance of the sample.

The ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) assay was used to evaluate the antioxidant capacity of the mustard samples, based on the ability of antioxidants to reduce Fe³⁺ to Fe²⁺, forming a blue Fe²⁺-TPTZ complex with maximum absorbance at 593 nm. The working FRAP reagent was prepared fresh by mixing 300 mM acetate buffer (pH 3.6), 20 mM FeCl₃·6H₂O, and 10 mM TPTZ (dissolved in 40 mM HCl) in a 10:1:1 (v/v/v) ratio. Trolox was used as the standard, starting from a 2.5 mM stock solution, with calibration dilutions between 0.25 and 2 mM. The calibration curve showed the regression equation $y = 15439x + 0.118$ with an $R^2 = 0.9970$. Absorbance measurements were performed at 593 nm using a Shimadzu miniUV-Vis spectrophotometer.

Determination of color parameters

Color parameters of the mustard samples were measured using a portable colorimeter (3nh TS7030, Shenzhen Threneh Technology Co., Ltd., China), operating in the CIE Lab* color space. The instrument was calibrated before each measurement session using the standard white and black calibration plates provided by the manufacturer. Approximately 5 g of mustard were placed evenly in a plastic Petri dish, and measurements were performed in triplicate under constant ambient lighting conditions. The parameters L* (lightness), a* (green-red component), and b* (blue-yellow component) were recorded, and mean values with standard deviations were calculated for each sample. Based on the obtained a* and b* values, chroma (C*, color saturation) and hue angle (h*, perceived color tone) were also determined.

Statistical analysis

All measurements were performed in triplicate. Statistical comparison between the fortified samples and the control (0% anise) was carried out using the Student's t-test (two-tailed, independent samples). Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The effect of anise on physicochemical parameters

Fortifying the mustard with anise did not significantly affect the product's pH (Table 1). In contrast, the total acidity was strongly affected at a concentration of 1.5% anise, which showed a significant reduction ($p < 0.05$) compared to the control and the rest of the formulated variants (Table 1). The moisture content significantly decreased in the fortified samples, especially at concentrations of 1% and 1.5% (Table 1), which can be correlated with both the absorption of water by the phenolic compounds of anise and the effects on the food matrix structure. The results indicate that the addition of anise significantly modifies the physicochemical properties of mustard, particularly in terms of acidity and moisture content.

Table 1

Physicochemical parameters (pH, total acidity and moisture) of mustard fortified with anise

Samples	pH	Total acidity	Moisture (%)
Control	4.24 ± 0.02a	2.19 ± 0.06a	67.14 ± 0.09b
M-0.5	4.19 ± 0.07a	1.77 ± 0.20a	66.51 ± 0.01c
M-1	4.25 ± 0.01a	2.01 ± 0.12a	65.89 ± 0.16a
M-1.5	4.27 ± 0.01a	1.65 ± 0.12b	66.28 ± 0.25a

Values represent mean ± standard deviation (n = 3). Different letters within the same column indicate statistically significant differences between samples (p < 0.05).

The effect of anise on total phenols and flavonoids content

The total phenolic compound content increased significantly (p < 0.05) in all anise-fortified samples compared to the control (M₀) (Figure 1A). The increase in TPC can be attributed to the contribution of bioactive compounds from *Pimpinella anisum*, known for

its high content of flavonoids, phenolic acids, and their derivatives (Leonard et al., 2021). Additionally, the mustard's food matrix structure, rich in water and soluble compounds, can facilitate the release and diffusion of phenolic compounds into the final product.

Figure 1. A. Total phenolic content (mg GAE/g) of mustard samples fortified with different concentrations of anise. B. Total flavonoid content (mg GAE/g) of mustard samples fortified with different concentrations of anise. Bars represent mean ± SD (n = 3). Different letters indicate statistically significant differences (p < 0.05).

Although the total flavonoid values vary slightly between samples (Figure 1B), the differences are not statistically significant. The similar levels suggest that flavonoids in anise may be present in moderate amounts, their extractability into the mustard matrix is limited, and the compounds responsible for the increase in TPC are more likely other polyphenols (e.g., phenolic acids, tannins).

The effect on antioxidant capacity

The antioxidant capacity evaluated by the DPPH method showed marked differences between the mustard samples fortified with anise (Figure 2A). The M 0.5% sample showed

the lowest DPPH radical scavenging capacity, being significantly inferior to the control (p < 0.05). In contrast, the M 1% and M 1.5% samples showed superior DPPH inhibition values, both being significantly higher than the control, indicating a cumulative antioxidant effect at higher concentrations of anise. This behavior can be attributed to the phenolic compounds and other secondary metabolites characterized in *Pimpinella anisum*, which contribute to the neutralization of free radicals in the food matrix (Picon et al., 2019).

Figure 2. **A. Antioxidant capacity (DPPH) of mustard samples fortified with different concentrations of anise.** **B. Antioxidant capacity (FRAP) of mustard samples fortified with different concentrations of anise.** Bars represent mean \pm SD (n = 3). Different letters indicate statistically significant differences (p < 0.05).

The FRAP method confirmed the trends observed with DPPH, highlighting a superior antioxidant capacity in samples with anise at higher concentrations (Figure 2B). Although M 0.5% did not differ significantly from the control, the M 1% and M 1.5% samples showed significantly higher FRAP values (p < 0.05), indicating a superior ability to reduce ferric ions ($\text{Fe}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{2+}$). This increase can be explained by the intake of phenolic compounds with redox properties present in anise. The 1.5% concentration generated the highest FRAP antioxidant capacity, suggesting a direct

proportional relationship between the anise content and the samples' ability to act as reducing agents.

Determining the color parameters (L^* , a^* , b^* , C^* , h^*) revealed significant changes in the chromatic profile of mustard as a result of fortification with anise (Table 2). Statistical analysis shows that all samples differ significantly from each other for most parameters, indicating a strong impact of anise concentration on the product's visual appearance.

Table 2

The effect of anise on color parameters of mustard

Samples	L^*	a^*	b^*	C^*	h^*	ΔE
M_0	65.44 \pm 0.34 c	5.08 \pm 0.19 c	62.02 \pm 0.43c	62.23 \pm 0.42c	85.31 \pm 0.19a	0
M-0.5	63.88 \pm 0.12 a	5.49 \pm 0.07a	62.99 \pm 0.13a	63.22 \pm 0.13a	85.02 \pm 0.06a	2.26 \pm 0.14
M-1	63.56 \pm 0.11 b	4.71 \pm 0.07b	58.12 \pm 0.15b	58.31 \pm 0.15b	85.37 \pm 0.08b	4.20 \pm 0.18
M-1.5	62.51 \pm 0.53 d	4.28 \pm 0.27d	53.89 \pm 0.35d	54.06 \pm 0.33d	85.46 \pm 0.30a	8.51 \pm 0.50

Values represent mean \pm standard deviation (n = 3). Different letters within the same column indicate statistically significant differences between samples (p < 0.05).

The L^* value decreased progressively with increasing anise concentration, the highest lightness being observed in the control sample, and the lowest in sample M_1.5%. The significant decrease in brightness (p < 0.05) suggests that anise contributes to the darkening of the mustard, likely thru its composition rich in natural pigments and oxidized phenolic compounds, which can give the final product a deeper hue (Table 2). The a^* parameter showed significant differences between the samples. The highest value was recorded for M_0.5%, indicating a slight tendency toward reddish tones at this concentration. In contrast, the values decreased significantly for M_1% and M_1.5%, indicating a shift in color toward the greenish area. These changes can be explained by the

interaction of the compounds in anise with the natural pigments in mustard, affecting the balance between warm and cool tones. The b^* parameter recorded high values for the control and M_0.5%, indicating the intense yellow color specific to traditional mustard. At higher concentrations of anise (1% and 1.5%), the b^* values decreased significantly (p < 0.05), suggesting a reduction in yellow components.

This can be associated with the diluting effect of anise on curcumin and other natural yellow pigments, as well as with possible non-enzymatic browning reactions. The C^* values followed the same trend as the b^* parameter, indicating a significant reduction in color saturation in the samples with 1% and 1.5% anise. The decrease in chromaticity reflects the fact that the product becomes visually "duller"

and less intense in color, an effect explainable by the dispersion of light within the mustard's pigmented matrix in the presence of fine anise particles. The h^* values remained very close between samples, indicating that the overall tone of the mustard (the predominant yellow hue) was not strongly influenced by the addition of anise. Only the M_1% sample showed a statistically significant difference compared to the others, but the variation is small and does not noticeably affect the product's chromatic character. Thus, anise modifies the intensity and brightness, but doesn't fundamentally change the characteristic hue of mustard.

CONCLUSIONS

Fortifying mustard with anise significantly influenced the product's physicochemical, antioxidant, and chromatic profile. Although the pH remained unchanged, the total acidity decreased significantly at a concentration of 1.5%, and the moisture content was lower in the fortified samples, especially at 1% and 1.5%. The addition of anise caused an increase in the total phenolic compound content, especially at concentrations of 1% and 1.5%, while total flavonoids did not show significant differences. The antioxidant activity of mustard was improved, with evident increases in both the DPPH and FRAP tests, especially in the samples with 1% and 1.5% anise. The color parameters were strongly influenced by the addition of anise: brightness, yellowness intensity, and chromaticity significantly decreased with increasing concentration, while the overall hue (h^*) remained relatively stable. Overall, anise proves to be a valuable functional ingredient, capable of enhancing the antioxidant and phenolic properties of mustard while simultaneously generating visible color changes that may be relevant to consumer perception.

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REFERENCES

- Grasso A.C., J.J.F. Besselink, M. Tyszler, M.J. Bruins, The potential of food fortification as an enabler of more environmentally sustainable, nutritionally adequate diets, *Nutrients*, 15 (11) (May 2023), p. 2473, 10.3390/nu15112473
- Hartmann, T. From waste products to ecochemicals: Fifty years research of plant secondary metabolism. *Phytochemistry* 2007, 68, 2831–2846.
- Idrees, N.; Tabassum, B.; Sarah, R.; Hussain, M.K. Natural compound from genus brassica and their therapeutic activities. In *Natural Bio-Active Compounds Volume 1: Production and Applications*; Akhtar, M., Swamy, M., Sinniah, U., Eds.; Springer: Singapore, 2019; pp. 477–491.
- Jendyose M., Development of functional foods with enhanced health benefits, *J. Food Sci.*, 5 (2) (May 2024), pp. 29-42, 10.47941/jfs.1846
- Kaur N., A. Agarwal, M. Sabharwal, Food fortification strategies to deliver nutrients for the management of iron deficiency anaemia, *Curr. Res. Food Sci.*, 5 (2022), pp. 2094-2107, 10.1016/j.crfs.2022.10.020
- Kyazimova N.D., V.V. Kornyakova, Influence of polyphenolic compounds on human health and the course of a number of diseases, *Scientific Bulletin of the Omsk State Medical University*, 4 (1) (May 2024), pp. 87-91, 10.61634/2782-3024-2024-13-87-91
- Leonard, Zhang, Ying, Adhikari, Fang, Fermentation transforms the phenolic profiles and bioactivities of plant-based foods, *Biotechnology Advances*, Volume 49, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biotechadv.2021.107763>
- Lietzow, J. Biologically Active Compounds in Mustard Seeds: A Toxicological Perspective. *Foods* 2021, 10, 2089.
- Md. Sakhawot Hossain, Md Abdul Wazed, Suvasish Das Shuvo, Zakia Sultana, Mst. Sultana Akhter Preya, Hafsha Khanom, Sharmin Asha, Md. Mostafa Kamal, Bappa Kumar Mondal, Tanvir Ahmad, Fortified and functional foods: Trends, innovations, and their public health impact for future nutrient enrichment, *Journal of Agriculture and Food Research*, Volume 23, 2025, 102275, ISSN 2666-1543, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jafr.2025.102275>.
- Moazzami Farida SH, Ghorbani A, Bussmann RW, Batsatsashvili K, Kikvidze Z, Paniagua-Zambrana NY, Khutsishvili M, Maisaia I, Sikharulidze S, Tchelidze D (2020) *Pimpinella anisum* L. Apiaceae. Ethnobotany of the mountain regions of far Eastern Europe: Ural, Northern Caucasus, Turkey, and Iran, pp 1–6
- Nagar B.L., et al., The role of bio-fortification in enhancing the nutritional quality of vegetables: a review, *Adv. Res.*, 25 (4) (May 2024), pp. 64-77, 10.9734/air/2024/v25i41082
- Picon et al, Alfekaiki, Yamini, Bahramifar, Sefidkon, Saharkhiz și Salamifar, Ullah et al., Iannarelli et al., Ullah et al, Sirisha et al. M. Hesam & Cheng, Qi. (2019). Anise (*Pimpinella anisum* L.), a dominant spice and traditional medicinal herb for both food and medicinal purposes. *Cogent Biology*. 5. 1-25. 10.1080/23312025.2019.1673688.
- Rahman, M.; Khatun, A.; Liu, L.; Barkla, B.J. Brassicaceae mustards: Traditional and agronomic uses in Australia and New Zealand. *Molecules* 2018, 23, 231.
- Shahidi, F. Canola and Rapeseed: Production, Chemistry, Nutrition, and Processing

Technology; Springer Science & Business Media: New York, NY, USA, 1990.

Vignesh, A. Amal, T.C.. Sarvalingam A, Vasanth K., A review on the influence of nutraceuticals and functional foods on health, Food Chemistry Advances, 5 (Dec. 2024), Article 100749, 10.1016/j.focha.2024.100749

Von Der Haar, D.; Müller, K.; Bader-Mittermaier, S.; Eisner, P. Rapeseed proteins–Production methods and possible application ranges. OCL 2014, 21, D104.

NATURAL STRATEGIES FOR A HEALTHY AND SUSTAINABLE LIFESTYLE: THE ROLE OF *NIGELLA SATIVA* IN DIABETES PREVENTION

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REVIEW ARTICLE

Abstract

*Diabetes mellitus is a complex metabolic disease, with an increasing incidence globally, associated with hyperglycemic values and disruption of glucose metabolism and homeostasis, which can lead to severe complications such as kidney or cardiovascular disease. In this context, the identification of strategies for the prevention and management of diabetes mellitus, such as complementary phytotherapy, has increasingly captured the interest of the scientific community. The research objective of this review article is to explore the potential of the *Nigella sativa* species to improve the glycemic profile and reduce the risk of complications and morbidity of diabetic disease, and other types of lifestyle modification interventions, within a holistic approach. To achieve the goal, we searched scientific databases and used Zotero software. The investigations revealed the antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and insulin-modulating action of the *Nigella sativa* species, as well as the importance of lifestyle changes – integrating high-fiber foods into the diet and avoiding refined carbohydrates; adopting an exercise routine of at least 30 minutes a day; regular monitoring of glycemic and lipid parameters, especially in patients with prediabetes; continuous education of patients on the importance of a healthy lifestyle and its impact on the prevention of diabetic complications. This article provides a synthesis of the available research and data on the role of the *Nigella sativa* species and its active compound, thymoquinone, for the prevention of diabetes. Adopting an integrated approach that includes lifestyle changes is a promising strategy for reducing the incidence of diabetes.*

Keywords: black cumin, cardiometabolic parameters, dietary changes, holistic.

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INTRODUCTION

In the context of the alarming increase in type 2 diabetes globally and its significant economic and social impact, identifying natural strategies that support a healthy lifestyle becomes essential (Yedjou et al., 2023). Diabetes, a complex metabolic disease, often develops from precursor stages, such as prediabetes, and is closely associated with cardiometabolic risk factors such as obesity, dyslipidemia, and hypertension (Saadati et al., 2022). In this

context, medicinal plants are an option of interest for the preventive management of diabetes, and *Nigella sativa* (traditionally known as black cumin seeds) has attracted the attention of researchers due to its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and hypoglycemic properties (Gawas et al., 2023). Recent studies have shown that supplementation with *Nigella sativa* can improve cardiometabolic parameters, including lowering postprandial blood glucose, glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c), total cholesterol, LDL-cholesterol, as well as reducing levels of inflammatory markers and oxidative

stress, such as CRP (C-reactive protein) and MDA (malondialdehyde), among patients with type 2 diabetes (Tabatabaei-Malazy et al., 2025). In addition, other natural interventions, such as lifestyle modifications, a balanced diet, regular physical activity, drinking water instead of sweetened beverages, and increasing fiber intake, have been shown to be effective in preventing progression to diabetes (Chen et al., 2025). This article explores both the specific effects of *Nigella sativa* on glycemic and lipid control parameters, as well as its integrative role in preventive strategies for diabetes, along with other health measures (Shabani et al., 2025; Zhang et al., 2024). A comprehensive analysis based on data from studies is presented, discussing how this herb can be used as an adjunct to conventional interventions and as part of a holistic approach to diabetes prevention (Khodaie et al., 2024b; Korkor et al., n.d.; Li et al., 2025).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For this article, several recent scientific studies were analyzed that evaluated the effects of *Nigella sativa* supplementation on cardiometabolic parameters and diabetes risk (Hadi et al., 2021; Khodaie et al., 2024a; Saleem et al., 2024). The analysis is based on a synthesis of the available literature on the benefits of *Nigella sativa*, complemented by an assessment of its interaction with lifestyle interventions (dietary changes, physical activity). The approached methodology involves the collection of data from the PubMed, ISI Web of Science and Scopus databases; using Zotero software to manage and filter relevant articles; evaluation of the effects and design of studies. For a better illustration of the results and preventive strategies, the article includes a summary table with the effects of *Nigella sativa* supplementation on cardiometabolic parameters and a flowchart that summarizes natural diabetes prevention strategies, including the role of the *Nigella sativa*.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Numerous clinical studies and meta-analyses have highlighted the benefits of supplementation with *Nigella sativa* in patients with prediabetes and type 2 diabetes (Akhtar et al., 2025; Al-Makhmari et al., 2025; Chatterjee et al., 2025). Specifically, a significant decrease in postprandial blood glucose, fasting blood

glucose (FPG) and glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) values have been reported, indicating an improvement in glycemic control. Studies have shown that supplementation with *Nigella sativa* leads to a considerable reduction in FPG (e.g., in some studies a significant decrease in glycemic values has been observed after administration of *Nigella sativa* oil for periods from 8 weeks and above, especially at doses $\geq 1\text{g/day}$) (Karimi et al., 2025); improved glycemic control: HbA1c levels were significantly reduced following treatments, indicating a long-term improvement in blood glucose; lipid profile: some studies have reported decreases in total cholesterol and LDL-C, while HDL-C values may increase in subgroups with low baseline values ($<40\text{ mg/dL}$); inflammatory and oxidative stress indicators: reduced levels of C-reactive protein (CRP) and malondialdehyde (MDA) contribute to decreasing the risk of cardiovascular complications, being essential in the prevention of cardiovascular diseases associated with diabetes (Saadati et al., 2022; Shahzad et al., 2025).

Studies have reported that there is a direct link between the administration of *Nigella sativa* and the multiple beneficial effects on cardiometabolic health in patients with prediabetes and type 2 diabetes (Adam et al., 2022).

Below is a summary table summarizing the effects of *Nigella sativa* administration on the main parameters influencing cardiovascular risk (El-Afify and El Amrousy, 2025) (Table 1).

Table 1
Synthesis of the effects of supplementation with *Nigella sativa* on cardiometabolic parameters

Parameter	Effect observed after supplementation with <i>Nigella sativa</i>	Observation
Fasting blood glucose (FPG)	Significant decrease	Doses $\geq 1\text{g/day}$, treatment >8 weeks
Glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c)	Notable decrease	Long-term improvement
Total cholesterol (TC)	Significant decrease	Suitable for the prevention of cardiovascular diseases

LDL-cholesterol (LDL-C)	Significant decrease	Beneficial for lipid balance
HDL-cholesterol (HDL-C)	Growth in selected subgroups	In the case of low base values
C-reactive protein (CRP)	Significant decrease	Decrease in systemic inflammation
Malondialdehyde (MDA)	Notable decrease	Reduced oxidative stress index

In addition to taking supplements such as those based on *Nigella sativa*, lifestyle modification interventions are fundamental in preventing the onset of type 2 diabetes.

The literature highlights some essential strategies, such as: dietary changes – adopting a diet rich in dietary fiber, decreasing the consumption of refined carbohydrates and simple sugars, is one of the most effective prevention measures (eating foods rich in fiber contributes to weight control, lowering blood sugar levels and improving insulin sensitivity); portion control and weight loss – reduce body weight by 5-7% (according to the recommendations of the American Diabetes

Association) was correlated with up to a 60% reduction in the risk of developing diabetes over three years; regular physical activity – it is recommended to perform at least 30 minutes of moderate physical activity (brisk walking, swimming, cycling) on most days of the week to improve insulin sensitivity and maintain glycemic stability; smoking cessation – studies show that smoking contributes to insulin resistance, and quitting smoking significantly reduces the risk of diabetes in the long term; Adequate hydration – drinking predominantly water instead of sugary drinks helps maintain optimal blood sugar levels and prevents sudden blood sugar fluctuations (Zhang et al., 2024).

These strategies not only improve the general state of health, but also act synergistically with the administration of black seed oil, providing a complete and integrated preventive framework (Dąbrowski et al., 2024). Within a holistic plan, the implementation of these changes can significantly reduce the incidence of type 2 diabetes, through actions that address both nutritional and metabolic risk factors (Shaukat et al., 2023).

Below is a diagram illustrating the main natural strategies for diabetes prevention. The diagram provides a summary of the combined impact of lifestyle and nutritional interventions on diabetes prevention, highlighting the importance of each component within an integrated health program (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Flowchart of diabetes prevention strategies

Recent research indicates that the use of black cumin seeds can be very helpful when combined with other diabetes prevention and management strategies (Khan et al., 2024). Studies have shown that integrating supplementation with *Nigella sativa* into a nutritional plan rich in fiber and low in refined carbohydrates potentiates the hypoglycemic effect, leading to an optimization of glycemic control (Shaukat et al., 2023).

A moderate exercise routine can additionally improve insulin sensitivity, thus facilitating the reduction of blood glucose levels when combined with the use of blackfish seeds, highlighting the synergy with physical activity (Fullwood et al., 2024).

Studies have shown that *Nigella sativa* can act as a therapeutic adjunct to conventional drug treatments for diabetes (Dwivedi et al., n.d.), allowing the doses of hypoglycemic medicinal products to be lowered and the adverse effects associated with them to be reduced. Thus, an integrated approach that also includes healthy lifestyle measures and supplements with *Nigella sativa* can bring significant and sustainable benefits (Bedir et al., 2025). From the perspective of biological mechanisms, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory action and modulation of insulin secretion by active compounds such as thymoquinone (Kaushik and Barmanray, n.d.) are fundamental for relieving metabolic dysfunctions characteristic of diabetes.

CONCLUSIONS

This article highlighted the importance of natural strategies for maintaining a healthy lifestyle, with a special focus on the role of *Nigella sativa* in diabetes prevention.

Supplementation with *Nigella sativa* significantly improves cardiometabolic parameters, such as FPG, HbA1c, cholesterol and inflammatory markers, helping to reduce the risk of diabetes-related complications.

The integrated approach, simultaneous implementation of dietary changes, regular exercise and other healthy lifestyle interventions is essential for preventing progression to type 2 diabetes.

Combining supplementation with *Nigella sativa* other preventive strategies enhances the beneficial effects, thus reducing the incidence of diabetes and improving quality of life.

Although the results are promising, further research is needed to determine the

optimal dose, duration of treatment and form of administration, ensuring effective integration into preventive clinical protocols.

These findings provide a solid basis for recommending the implementation of integrated prevention programs that consider both nutritional interventions and supplementation with natural extracts with multiple therapeutic properties. Such a holistic approach will help reduce the burden of diabetes on global health systems and provide patients with the necessary tools for preventive and effective management of their health.

REFERENCES

- Adam, S.H., Mohd Nasri, N., Kashim, M.I.A.M., Abd Latib, E.H., Ahmad Juhari, M.A.A., Mokhtar, M.H., 2022. Potential health benefits of *Nigella sativa* on diabetes mellitus and its complications: A review from laboratory studies to clinical trials. *Front. Nutr.* 9, 1057825. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2022.1057825>
- Akhtar, M.T., Qadir, R., Altaf, U., Almas, T., Batool, S., Ikram, M.S., Meor Hussin, A.S., Perveen, K., Alshaikh, N.A., Saadia, M., 2025. Phytochemical Profiling and Biological Activities of *Nigella sativa* Vinegar Extract: An Insight Into Hypoglycemic Potential Using In Vivo and In Silico Studies. *Chem. Biodivers.* 22, e202402512. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cbdv.202402512>
- Al-Makhmari, S., Al-Aufi, A., Al-Kindi, S., Alriyami, M., Sakr, H., Boulassel, M.-R., Khadra, K.M.A., Al-Haddabi, R., Boudaka, A., Saleh, J., 2025. Evidence-Based Human Clinical Trials on Antidiabetic Herbal Remedies Commonly Used in the Middle East. *Sultan Qaboos Univ. Med. J.* 25, 418–429. <https://doi.org/10.18295/2075-0528.2852>
- Bedir, A.S., Almasri, R.S., Al Raish, S.M., 2025. Therapeutic efficacy of *Nigella sativa* and *Ziziphus lotus*: sustainable strategies for diabetes, antimicrobial resistance, and health treatment. *Front. Nutr.* 12, 1592423. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2025.1592423>
- Chatterjee, G., Saha, A.K., Khurshid, S., Saha, A., 2025. A Comprehensive Review of the Antioxidant, Antimicrobial, and Therapeutic Efficacies of Black Cumin (*Nigella sativa* L.) Seed Oil and Its Thymoquinone. *J. Med. Food* 28, 325–339. <https://doi.org/10.1089/jmf.2024.k.0149>
- Chen, Q., Li, C.-F., Jing, W., 2025. Research progress on the effects of sedentary behavior and physical activity on diabetes mellitus. *Sheng Li Xue Bao* 77, 62–74.
- Dąbrowski, G., Czaplicki, S., Konopka, I., 2024. Variation in the Composition and Quality of *Nigella sativa* L. Seed Oils—The Underestimated Impact on Possible Health-Promoting Properties. *Molecules* 29, 1360. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules29061360>
- Dwivedi, J., Sachan, P., Wal, P., Wal, A., Vippamakula, S., S, R.K., Sharma, M.C., n.d. Clinical Evidence of Traditional Medicines in Modulating the Immune Response and Diabetic Wound

- Healing. *Curr. Top. Med. Chem.* 25, 1–31. <https://doi.org/10.2174/0115680266359349250707102203>
- El-Afify, D., El Amrousy, D., 2025. Cardioprotective Effect of *Nigella sativa* in Pediatric Patients with Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus: A Randomized Controlled Study. *Paediatr. Drugs* 27, 481–489. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40272-025-00687-5>
- Fullwood, D., Gunderson, J., Bolajoko, O.O., Hale, R., Odedina, F.T., 2024. Disparities in diabetes and sedentary behavior across Florida counties. *Health Promot. Perspect.* 14, 388–391. <https://doi.org/10.34172/hpp.43402>
- Gawas, C.G., Mathur, S., Wani, M., Tabassum, H., 2023. *Nigella sativa* and its nano-mediated approach toward management of neurodegenerative disorders: A review. *Ibrain* 9, 111–123. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ibra.12091>
- Hadi, V., Pahlavani, N., Malekhamdi, M., Nattagh-Eshstivani, E., Navashenaq, J.G., Hadi, S., Ferns, G.A., Ghayour-Mobarhan, M., Askari, G., Norouzy, A., 2021. *Nigella sativa* in controlling Type 2 diabetes, cardiovascular, and rheumatoid arthritis diseases: Molecular aspects. *J. Res. Med. Sci. Off. J. Isfahan Univ. Med. Sci.* 26, 20. https://doi.org/10.4103/jrms.JRMS_236_20
- Karimi, M., Pirzad, S., Pourfaraji, S.M.A., Sedgi, F.M., Darouei, B., Amani-Beni, R., Kazemi, K., Rabiee, R., 2025. Effects of black seed (*Nigella sativa* L.) on cardiometabolic indices in type 2 diabetic patients: A systematic review and meta-analysis of RCTs. *Complement. Ther. Med.* 90, 103174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ctim.2025.103174>
- Kaushik, N., Barmanray, A., n.d. Optimisation of Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction Conditions Using Response Surface Methodology and Identification of Thymoquinone from Black Cumin (*Nigella sativa* L.) Seed Extract. *Food Technol. Biotechnol.* 63, 262–273. <https://doi.org/10.17113/ftb.63.02.25.8560>
- Khan, M., Riaz, H., Jatala, F.H., Noor, A., Mumtaz, S., Zafar, S., 2024. Prevention of Chronic Diabetic Neuropathy and Diabetes-Associated Cognitive Impairment Using Medicinal Herbs (*Cassia Angustifolia* and *Nigella Sativa*). *Yale J. Biol. Med.* 97, 141–152. <https://doi.org/10.59249/UQLO8012>
- Khodaie, S.-A., Nikkhah, H., Namiranian, N., Abotorabi, M., Askari, M., Khalilzadeh, S.H., Khatibi Aghda, A., Kamalinejad, M., 2024a. Topical *Nigella sativa* L. product: a new candidate for the management of diabetic peripheral neuropathy. *Inflammopharmacology* 32, 551–559. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10787-023-01338-2>
- Khodaie, S.-A., Razavi, R., Nikkhah, H., Namiranian, N., Kamalinejad, M., 2024b. *Nigella sativa* L. and its bioactive and nutraceutical components in the management of diabetic peripheral neuropathy. *Inflammopharmacology* 32, 2897–2920. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10787-024-01528-6>
- Korkor, A.M., Abbass, H.S., Ahmed, A.H., Mansour, A.M., Ramsis, T.M., Elkousy, R.H., Al-Harrasi, A., Ibrahim, A.E., Mohammed, A.E.-S.I., n.d. Insulinotropic and anti-obesity properties of ethno-medicinal plants: pharmacology-based and in-silico predictions. *Nat. Prod. Res.* 0, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14786419.2025.2457603>
- Li, E., Maunder, A., Liu, J., Pandey, C., Cave, A., O'Fee, A., Ee, C., 2025. The efficacy and safety of herbal medicines for glycaemic control and insulin resistance in individuals with type 2 diabetes: an umbrella review. *BMC Complement. Med. Ther.* 25, 341. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12906-025-05059-7>
- Saadati, S., Naseri, K., Asbaghi, O., Abhari, K., Zhang, P., Li, H.-B., Gan, R.-Y., 2022. *Nigella sativa* supplementation improves cardiometabolic indicators in population with prediabetes and type 2 diabetes mellitus: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Front. Nutr.* 9, 977756. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2022.977756>
- Saleem, M., Mazhar Fareed, M., Salman Akbar Saani, M., Shityakov, S., 2024. Network pharmacology and multitarget analysis of *Nigella sativa* in the management of diabetes and obesity: a computational study. *J. Biomol. Struct. Dyn.* 42, 4800–4816. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07391102.2023.2222837>
- Shabani, M., Ghavidel, F., Rajabian, A., Homayouni-Tabrizi, M., Jamialahmadi, T., Hosseini, H., Sahebkar, A., 2025. Effect of *Nigella sativa* Consumption on Lipid Profile and Glycemic Index in Patients with Metabolic Syndrome: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis of Randomized Controlled Trials. *Curr. Med. Chem.* 32, 3638–3650. <https://doi.org/10.2174/0109298673249741231129100733>
- Shahzad, H., Ali, S., Farooq, M.A., Summer, M., Hassan, A., Sulayman, R., Kanwal, L., Awan, U.A., 2025. UV-spectrophotometric and spectroscopic observed *Vachellia nilotica* and *Nigella sativa* formulations regularized the histopathological and biochemical parameters during wound contraction. *Microsc. Res. Tech.* 88, 4–16. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jemt.24673>
- Shaukat, A., Zaidi, A., Anwar, H., Kizilbash, N., 2023. Mechanism of the antidiabetic action of *Nigella sativa* and Thymoquinone: a review. *Front. Nutr.* 10, 1126272. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2023.1126272>
- Tabatabaei-Malazy, O., Lavari, N., Abdollahi, M., 2025. Natural Products in the Clinical Management of Metabolic Syndrome, in: Wainwright, C.L., Schini-Kerth, V.B. (Eds.), *Natural Products as Sources of Novel Drugs*. Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham, pp. 123–157. https://doi.org/10.1007/164_2024_711
- Yedjou, C.G., Grigsby, J., Mbemi, A., Nelson, D., Mildort, B., Latinwo, L., Tchounwou, P.B., 2023. The Management of Diabetes Mellitus Using Medicinal Plants and Vitamins. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 24, 9085. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24109085>
- Zhang, X., Qiao, X., Peng, K., Gao, S., Hao, Y., 2024. Digital Behavior Change Interventions to Reduce Sedentary Behavior and Promote Physical Activity in Adults with Diabetes: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Randomized Controlled Trials. *Int. J. Behav. Med.* 31, 959–973. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12529-023-10188-9>

HERBAL-BASED SUPPLEMENTS OF PHYTOTHERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL IN THE PREVENTION AND MANAGEMENT OF PREDIABETES

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REVIEW ARTICLE

Abstract

This synthesis paper aims to address the biomedical significance of relevant medicinal plants through their hypoglycemic properties, promising for the prevention and management of diabetes, the efficacy of phytotherapeutic supplements, available studies, mechanisms of action and biochemical aspects, and comparative analysis of supplements. This article aims to provide an in-depth look at the potential of phytotherapeutic supplements, combining data obtained from preclinical and clinical studies with the analysis of the molecular mechanisms involved. The results presented in this review contribute to substantiating the knowledge needed to integrate herbal treatments into modern medical practice, thus supporting the adoption of complementary therapeutic strategies in the face of the increasing incidence of diabetes. The main findings include efficacy (most herbal supplements have demonstrated the ability to lower HbA1c levels and fasting blood glucose), active mechanisms that include stimulating insulin secretion, increasing insulin sensitivity, and reducing inflammation. It is necessary to adopt standardized methods of extraction and administration to ensure the consistency of the results. Future studies should target larger populations and a robust methodological design to clearly establish clinical benefits and possible adverse effects. By clarifying the beneficial effects, mechanisms of action and current limitations, future research will be able to develop standardized treatment protocols that maximize the benefits of phytotherapy and minimize the associated risks. The integration of these treatments into current medical systems can represent a viable solution for patients facing the chronic form of diabetes, helping to improve the quality of life and reduce treatment costs in the long term.

Keywords: antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, glycemic control, bioavailability, extraction.

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INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is one of the most widespread metabolic diseases, affecting millions of people globally (Alhar et al., 2025). This chronic condition, characterized by hyperglycemia and insulin metabolism disorders, leads to severe complications such as cardiovascular disease, kidney failure, retinopathy, and neuropathy (Kumar et al., 2021). Prediabetes is defined as an intermediate state, in which glycemic levels are higher than normal, but do not reach the

diagnostic threshold of type 2 diabetes. Identifying preventive strategies and complementary treatments thus becomes essential for managing and, in the long term, reducing the incidence of diabetes (Mostafa et al., 2021; Mtshali and Sookan-Kassie, 2024).

Phytotherapeutic supplements, derived from medicinal plants, have increasingly captured the interest of the scientific community and specialists in the medical and pharmaceutical fields (Chattopadhyay et al., 2022). Recent studies suggest that certain plant extracts such as *Aloe vera*, *Psyllium fiber*, *Fenugreek seeds*, *Nigella sativa*, *Astragalus membranaceus*, *Allium sativum* (Garlic),

Momordica charantia (Bitter Melon), *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L. (Roselle), *Curcuma longa* (Turmeric), *Zingiber officinale* (Ginger) have been investigated in the context of improving glycemic control and reducing the risk of complications associated with diabetes (Jamrozik et al., 2022; Tabatabaei-Malazy et al., 2025). These plants can act by secreting and increasing insulin sensitivity, reducing oxidative stress and modulating inflammation, essential aspects in the pathogenesis of type 2 diabetes (Firdous et al., 2025).

Currently, the literature provides evidence that highlights the benefits of these phytotherapeutic supplements (Al-Makhmari et al., 2025). For example, the results of some meta-analyses showed that *Aloe vera*, Psyllium fiber and fenugreek seeds can significantly reduce HbA1c (glycated hemoglobin) and glycemic levels compared to conventional treatments, and clinical trials conducted in different countries show comparable efficacy with allopathic treatments (Willcox et al., 2021). At the same time, traditional sources of knowledge, such as traditional Chinese medicine and Ayurvedic medicine, have used these plants for centuries, and the transfer of these practices to modern science offers a bridge between tradition and technology (Sriraman et al., 2023).

The role of evidence-based information is essential in this branch of investigation. The prevalence of preclinical studies, while promising, raises questions about the replication of results in clinical trials and the optimization of doses and forms of administration (Adam et al., 2022; Al-Makhmari et al., 2025). In addition, the lack of knowledge of many health professionals about the existing evidence limits open communication with patients seeking complementary treatments (Sriraman et al., 2023). Thus, the aim of this paper is to evaluate, through a systematic review, the phytotherapeutic potential of herbal supplements for the prevention and management of prediabetes and diabetes, presenting a synthesis of the available results.

In the global context of increasing incidence of diabetes, the prevalence of prediabetes and associated complications requires the adoption of interdisciplinary strategies, where herbal supplements could have a significant complementary role. This information is particularly relevant both for researchers in the field of biochemistry and pharmacology, as well as for clinical specialists looking for alternative and complementary options for the treatment of patients (Chattopadhyay et al., 2023; Heinrich et al., 2022).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

To carry out this review, scientific databases such as PubMed, ScienceDirect, Wiley Online Library, MEDLINE and Google Scholar were analyzed. The searches were carried out using keywords such as "diabetes", "prediabetes", "plant-based therapy", "phytotherapeutic supplements", along with specific terms extracted from the available studies.

The inclusion criteria consisted of the publication of studies presenting clinical or preclinical data on the efficacy of herbal supplements in reducing glycemic levels and preventing complications associated with diabetes. Studies that did not include complete data or were not validated by rigorous statistical methods were excluded.

Relevant data were extracted from the selected articles, including information on: the type of study, duration of treatment and doses administered, reported outcomes such as changes in HbA1c, fasting blood glucose, cholesterol levels and other metabolic parameters. For a clear and structured interpretation of the results, we have made the following table (Table 1) and a diagram illustrating the mechanistic flow from the administration of a phytotherapeutic supplement to the final impact on glucose metabolism and glycemic control (Figure 1).

Table 1

Comparison of phytotherapeutic supplements used in studies

Medicinal plant	Active compounds	Mechanism of action	Reported efficacy	Bibliographic references
<i>Aloe vera</i>	Polyphenols, enzymes, amino acids	Improving insulin secretion, anti-	Significant reduction in HbA1c	(Chattopadhyay et al., 2022; Firdous et al., 2025; Unuofin

		inflammatory properties		and Lebelo, 2020)
Psyllium fiber	Soluble Fiber	Slowing down carbohydrate absorption	Reduction averages of HbA1c	(Shen et al., 2025; Wang et al., 2025; Willcox et al., 2021)
Fenugreek seeds	Alkaloids, saponins, fiber	Increased insulin sensitivity	About 0.85% HbA1c reduction	(Ali et al., 2025; Deshpande et al., 2025; Muluye et al., 2024; Willcox et al., 2021)
<i>Nigella sativa</i>	Thymoquinone, fatty acids, carvacrol, terpinene	Anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activity	Clinically significant reduction in blood glucose and HbA1c	(Adam et al., 2022; Karimi et al., 2025; Morar (Romoccea) et al., 2025)
<i>Astragalus membranaceus</i>	Polysaccharides, Flavonoids	Modulation of glucose metabolism	Moderate effect on blood sugar	(Willcox et al., 2021)
<i>Allium sativum</i>	Allicin, sulfur compounds	Improving glycemic control, antioxidant	Effect comparable to conventional treatments	(Firdous et al., 2025; Kumar et al., 2021; Yedjou et al., 2023)
<i>Momordica charantia</i>	Flavonoids, glycosides, phytosterols	Increased glucose absorption, activation of the glucose transporter 4 (GLUT 4)	Hypoglycemic effects, increased insulin secretion	(Chattopadhyay et al., 2022; Firdous et al., 2025; Guarneiri et al., 2025; Yedjou et al., 2023)
<i>Hibiscus sabdariffa</i> L.	Anthocyanins, polyphenols, flavonoids (hibiscetine)	Improved insulin sensitivity, antioxidant properties	Significant reduction in blood sugar in prediabetes	(Mistry et al., 2025; Tabatabaei-Malazy et al., 2025; Yedjou et al., 2023)
<i>Curcuma longa</i>	Curcuminoids, tumerone	Antioxidant, Anti-inflammatory	Reduction of hyperglycemia and pancreatic protection	(Alhar et al., 2025; Chattopadhyay et al., 2022; Unuofin and Lebelo, 2020)
<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	Gingerols, shogaols, zingiberene	Stimulation of insulin secretion	Beneficial effect on glycemic control	(Chattopadhyay et al., 2022; Firdous et al., 2025)

Figure 1 The mechanism of biological action of phytotherapeutic supplements

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results obtained from studies indicate that many of the plants used are based on bioactive compounds that can reduce blood sugar levels, improve insulin sensitivity and alleviate oxidative stress (Hannan et al., 2021). Recent meta-analyses have highlighted that extracts of *Aloe vera*, Psyllium fiber and Fenugreek seeds are among the most effective in reducing HbA1c values, with significant effects comparable to conventional treatments (Sriraman et al., 2023; Willcox et al., 2021). Studies have also focused on how it is administered – in the form of capsules or liquid extract – highlighting that the form of administration can influence the bioavailability of the active compounds.

Studies on *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L. have suggested anti-inflammatory and hypoglycemic effects through the action of bioactive compounds, such as flavonoids, anthocyanins, phenolic acids. One animal study reported that administration of 72 mg/200 g body weight and 288 mg/200 g body weight for 21 days decreased the glycemic profile in diabetic rats (Yedjou et al., 2023).

Studies with *Curcuma longa*, often administered in combination with *Allium sativum*, have reported a significant decrease in fasting and postprandial blood glucose, due to the synergy between curcuminoids and sulfur compounds (Alhar et al., 2025; Chattopadhyay et al., 2022; Unuofin and Lebelo, 2020).

Most clinical trials focus on capsule administration, with varying treatment periods (from 14 days to 12 weeks). In animal models, herbal extracts have suggested overwhelming evidence of the regenerative ability of pancreatic beta cells, reduced oxidative stress, and improved glucose metabolism (Unuofin and

Lebelo, 2020). For example, administering bitter melon extract to diabetic rats resulted in decreased glycemic levels and protection of pancreatic tissues, although the results were not always replicable in clinical trials in humans (Yedjou et al., 2023). These differences can be attributed to variability in the chemical composition of the extracts, dosage differences, and specific experimental conditions (Chattopadhyay et al., 2022).

The mechanisms by which herbal supplements influence glucose metabolism are multiple and complex. Among the major mechanisms are: modulation of insulin secretion and sensitivity (many plants, such as bitter melon and turmeric, contain compounds that can stimulate insulin secretion and improve sensitivity to it – for example, bitter melon contains peptides with an insulin mimetic effect that can activate glucose transporters on target cells); antioxidant and anti-inflammatory action (plants such as garlic, turmeric and ginger are rich in compounds with strong antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, helping to reduce oxidative stress, which is a major cause of cell damage in diabetes); slowing down the absorption of carbohydrates (the soluble fiber in Psyllium reduces the rate of carbohydrate absorption, thus improving the postprandial glycemic response). These mechanisms have been visualized in the mechanistic flow diagram presented above, which highlights how taking supplements leads to a series of biochemical reactions that culminate in the regulation of glucose metabolism (Firdous et al., 2025; Unuofin and Lebelo, 2020).

This comparative analysis suggests that although the benefits of each herb may vary depending on the dose administered and the form of preparation, there is a consensus on the ability of these supplements to complement

conventional therapies in the management of diabetes.

Another important aspect is the variability and bioavailability of the active compounds. For example, bitter melon extract has demonstrated contrasting results between preclinical and clinical studies, which can be attributed to regional differences in the chemical composition of the plant and preparation methodologies (Yedjou et al., 2023). In contrast, the combination of turmeric and garlic has been a topic of interest due to the synergistic effects reported in clinical trials comparable to standardized treatments.

CONCLUSIONS

The systematic review of the literature on herbal supplements for the prevention and management of prediabetes and diabetes highlights some conclusions.

Studies reveal that extracts from *Aloe vera*, Psyllium, *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L., Fenugreek seeds, garlic, turmeric and ginger have the potential to reduce blood sugar levels, thus improving diabetes control and decreasing the risk of associated complications.

Supplements act through multiple biochemical pathways: increased insulin secretion and sensitivity, reduced carbohydrate absorption, protection against oxidative stress, and anti-inflammatory activity, highlighting complementary mechanisms.

There is variability in outcomes depending on the form of administration, doses and extraction methodologies, which underscores the need for standardization of the treatment protocol to ensure the reproducibility of clinical results.

Although preclinical results and some clinical trials are promising, better evaluation through large studies and randomized controlled trials is needed to validate the long-term efficacy and safety of these herbal supplements.

In summary, phytotherapeutic supplements are shown to be a promising strategy in the prevention and management of diabetes, offering an alternative or complement to conventional treatments. The implementation of these supplements, however, requires standardization in terms of dosage, extraction method and administration, in addition to a continuous evaluation of the risks and benefits for each subgroup of patients.

This paper provides a synthesis of the literature on phytotherapeutic supplements in the context of prediabetes and diabetes, emphasizing the importance of multidisciplinary and collaborative studies in the development of future prevention and treatment strategies.

REFERENCES

- Adam, S.H., Mohd Nasri, N., Kashim, M.I.A.M., Abd Latib, E.H., Ahmad Juhari, M.A.A., Mokhtar, M.H., 2022. Potential health benefits of *Nigella sativa* on diabetes mellitus and its complications: A review from laboratory studies to clinical trials. *Front. Nutr.* 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2022.1057825>
- Alhar, M.S.O., El-Sofany, W.I., AlRashidi, A.A., Hamden, K., 2025. Protective Effects of Isolated Curcumin From *Curcuma longa* on Key Enzymes Involved in the Insulin Signaling Pathway and Digestive and Metabolic Enzymes Associated With Obesity, Type 2 Diabetes, and Hypertension. *J. Diabetes Res.* 2025, 8050374. <https://doi.org/10.1155/jdr/8050374>
- Ali, U., Makhdoom, S.I., Javed, M.U., Khan, R.A., Naveed, M., Abbasi, B.H., Aziz, T., Alshehri, F., Al-Asmari, F., Al-Joufi, F.A., Alwethaynani, M.S., 2025. Fenugreek seeds as a natural source of L-arginine-encapsulated lipid nanoparticles against diabetes. *Sci. Rep.* 15, 7016. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-90675-z>
- Al-Makhmari, S., Al-Aufi, A., Al-Kindi, S., Alriyami, M., Sakr, H., Boulassel, M.-R., Khadra, K.M.A., Al-Haddabi, R., Boudaka, A., Saleh, J., 2025. Evidence-Based Human Clinical Trials on Antidiabetic Herbal Remedies Commonly Used in the Middle East. *Sultan Qaboos Univ. Med. J.* 25, 418–429. <https://doi.org/10.18295/2075-0528.2852>
- Chattopadhyay, K., Kapoor, N., Heinrich, M., Mitra, A., Mittal, M., Lewis, S.A., Greenfield, S.M., Mukherjee, S., Pischel, I., Jeemon, P., Tandon, N., Kinra, S., Biswas, T.K., Leonardi-Bee, J., 2023. Development process of a clinical guideline to manage type 2 diabetes in adults by Ayurvedic practitioners. *Front. Med.* 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2023.1043715>
- Chattopadhyay, K., Wang, H., Kaur, J., Nalbant, G., Almaqhawi, A., Kundakci, B., Panniyammakal, J., Heinrich, M., Lewis, S.A., Greenfield, S.M., Tandon, N., Biswas, T.K., Kinra, S., Leonardi-Bee, J., 2022. Effectiveness and Safety of Ayurvedic Medicines in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Management: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Front. Pharmacol.* 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2022.821810>
- Deshpande, P.O., Gokhale, C.A., Bhaskaran, S., Gayathri, R., Abirami, K., Anjana, R.M., Krishnaswamy, K., Mohan, V., Sudha, V., 2025. Effect of 'Fenuflakes™' on 24-hour glycemic variability in adults with type 2 diabetes: A randomized crossover continuous glucose monitoring study. *Asia Pac. J. Clin. Nutr.* 34, 730–739. [https://doi.org/10.6133/apjcn.202510_34\(5\).0003](https://doi.org/10.6133/apjcn.202510_34(5).0003)

- Firdous, S.M., Irfan, Z., Giri, S., Asaba, N.S., 2025. Unravelling the role of natural herbs for the management of diabetes mellitus. *Diabetol. Metab. Syndr.* 17, 398. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13098-025-01904-4>
- Guarneiri, L.L., Wilcox, M.L., Kuan, C.-M., Maki, K.C., 2025. Investigation of the Influence of a Bitter Melon Product on Indicators of Cardiometabolic Health in Adults with Prediabetes. *J. Am. Nutr. Assoc.* 44, 306–314. <https://doi.org/10.1080/27697061.2024.2428301>
- Hannan, M.A., Rahman, M.A., Sohag, A.A.M., Uddin, M.J., Dash, R., Sikder, M.H., Rahman, M.S., Timalisina, B., Munni, Y.A., Sarker, P.P., Alam, M., Mohibbullah, M., Haque, M.N., Jahan, I., Hossain, M.T., Afrin, T., Rahman, M.M., Tahjib-Ul-Arif, M., Mitra, S., Oktaviani, D.F., Khan, M.K., Choi, H.J., Moon, I.S., Kim, B., 2021. Black Cumin (*Nigella sativa* L.): A Comprehensive Review on Phytochemistry, Health Benefits, Molecular Pharmacology, and Safety. *Nutrients* 13, 1784. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu13061784>
- Heinrich, M., Jalil, B., Abdel-Tawab, M., Echeverria, J., Kulić, Ž., McGaw, L.J., Pezzuto, J.M., Potterat, O., Wang, J.-B., 2022. Best Practice in the chemical characterisation of extracts used in pharmacological and toxicological research—The ConPhyMP—Guidelines12. *Front. Pharmacol.* 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2022.953205>
- Jamrozik, D., Borymska, W., Kaczmarczyk-Żebrowska, I., 2022. Hibiscus sabdariffa in Diabetes Prevention and Treatment—Does It Work? An Evidence-Based Review. *Foods* 11, 2134. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods11142134>
- Karimi, M., Pirzad, S., Pourfaraji, S.M.A., Sedgi, F.M., Darouei, B., Amani-Beni, R., Kazemi, K., Rabiee, R., 2025. Effects of black seed (*Nigella sativa* L.) on cardiometabolic indices in type 2 diabetic patients: A systematic review and meta-analysis of RCTs. *Complement. Ther. Med.* 90, 103174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ctim.2025.103174>
- Kumar, S., Mittal, Anu, Babu, D., Mittal, Amit, 2021. Herbal Medicines for Diabetes Management and its Secondary Complications. *Curr. Diabetes Rev.* 17, 437–456. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1573399816666201103143225>
- Mistry, P.S., Chorawala, M.R., Sivamaruthi, B.S., Prajapati, B.G., Kumar, A., Chaiyasut, C., 2025. The Role of Dietary Anthocyanins for Managing Diabetes Mellitus-Associated Complications. *Curr. Diabetes Rev.* 21, e15733998322754. <https://doi.org/10.2174/0115733998322754240802063730>
- Morar (Romocea), M.T., Pallag, A., Burlou-Nagy (Fati), C., Vicaș, L.G., Dejeu, I.L., Horvath, T., Bei, D., Vesa, C., 2025. Analysis of Pharmacological Properties of *Nigella sativa* L. Bioactive Compounds and Their Therapeutic Relevance in the Management of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. *Life* 15, 1681. <https://doi.org/10.3390/life15111681>
- Mostafa, T.M., Hegazy, S.K., Elnaidany, S.S., Shehabeldin, W.A., Sawan, E.S., 2021. *Nigella sativa* as a promising intervention for metabolic and inflammatory disorders in obese prediabetic subjects: A comparative study of *Nigella sativa* versus both lifestyle modification and metformin. *J. Diabetes Complications* 35, 107947. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdiacomp.2021.107947>
- Mtshali, N., Sookan-Kassie, T., 2024. Diabetes-Related Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice Towards Exercise and Its Benefits Among Individuals with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 21, 1529. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph21111529>
- Muluye, D., Getachew, P., Tekalign, T., Woldekidan, S., Biftu, T., 2024. Evaluation of the antihyperglycemic and antihyperlipidemic effects of *Trigonella foenum-graecum* L and *Coffea arabica* L seeds in STZ induced diabetic mice: impact on kidney and liver functions. *Pan Afr. Med. J.* 49, 94. <https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2024.49.94.44735>
- Shen, W., Luo, R., Yang, L., Li, Z., Hou, X., Liu, Z., 2025. Psyllium-derived, medium-molecular weight arabinoxylan enables modulation of the gut microbiota and metabolites in type 2 diabetic mice. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 328, 147363. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2025.147363>
- Sriraman, S., Sreejith, D., Andrew, E., Okello, I., Willcox, M., 2023. Use of herbal medicines for the management of type 2 diabetes: A systematic review of qualitative studies. *Complement. Ther. Clin. Pract.* 53, 101808. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ctcp.2023.101808>
- Tabatabaei-Malazy, O., Lavari, N., Abdollahi, M., 2025. Natural Products in the Clinical Management of Metabolic Syndrome, in: Wainwright, C.L., Schini-Kerth, V.B. (Eds.), *Natural Products as Sources of Novel Drugs*. Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham, pp. 123–157. https://doi.org/10.1007/164_2024_711
- Unuofin, J.O., Lebelo, S.L., 2020. Antioxidant Effects and Mechanisms of Medicinal Plants and Their Bioactive Compounds for the Prevention and Treatment of Type 2 Diabetes: An Updated Review. *Oxid. Med. Cell. Longev.* 2020, 1356893. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/1356893>
- Wang, Z., Cai, Q., Liu, L., Zhu, Z., 2025. Psyllium husk powder enhances the management of type 2 diabetes by modulating gut microbiota and their metabolic products. *Food Res. Int. Ott. Ont* 211, 116393. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2025.116393>
- Willcox, M.L., Elugbaju, C., Al-Anbaki, M., Lown, M., Graz, B., 2021. Effectiveness of Medicinal Plants for Glycaemic Control in Type 2 Diabetes: An Overview of Meta-Analyses of Clinical Trials. *Front. Pharmacol.* 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2021.777561>
- Yedjou, C.G., Grigsby, J., Mbemi, A., Nelson, D., Mildort, B., Latinwo, L., Tchounwou, P.B., 2023. The Management of Diabetes Mellitus Using Medicinal Plants and Vitamins. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 24, 9085. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24109085>

INDIVIDUAL FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE CIRCULAR PURCHASING BEHAVIOR: COMPARISONS BETWEEN THE BABY BOOMERS, X, Y AND Z GENERATIONS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This paper analyzes the individual factors that influence circular purchasing behavior and how they differ between the Baby Boomer, X, Y, and Z generations. The study is based on a descriptive-comparative design and uses an online questionnaire applied to a sample of 392 respondents in Romania. The research is theoretically grounded in the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991) and the Values-Attitudes-Behavior (VAB) model, aiming to identify the relationships between attitudes, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, pro-environmental identity, quality perception, price sensitivity, and digital exposure in relation to purchase intention and circular behavior. The results showed significant differences between generations, with the highest levels of attitudes, intention, and circular behavior being recorded in Generations Y and Z. Correlation analyses showed strong relationships between attitudes, pro-environmental identity, and behavioral intention ($r > .60$), and hierarchical multiple regression indicated that attitudes ($\beta = .38$), pro-environmental identity ($\beta = .31$), and digital exposure ($\beta = .22$) are the strongest predictors of circular behavior, with the final model explaining 61% of the variance ($R^2 = .61$). Intergenerational differences are explained by post-materialistic values and the level of digital socialization, which determine a higher degree of ecological awareness among young consumers. The study highlights the importance of psychological dimensions in promoting circular behavior and emphasizes the need for generationally tailored educational and communication policies to support the transition to a sustainable and responsible economy.

Keywords: circular purchasing behavior; pro-environmental attitudes; ecological identity; generations (Baby Boomers, X, Y, Z); circular economy; digital exposure; sustainability.
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INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the global economic paradigm has gradually shifted from a linear model based on production, consumption, and disposal to a circular model focused on reuse, recycling, and sustainability. The circular economy promotes responsible consumption, in which products are designed to have an extended lifespan and resources are reintegrated into the economic cycle (European Commission, 2020).

Circular purchasing behavior is a fundamental component of this transition, involving consumer choices that reduce environmental impact and encourage reuse and recycling processes. Circular purchasing behavior can be defined as the set of consumer decisions and actions aimed at purchasing, using, and disposing of products in a sustainable manner. This includes a preference for reusable,

repairable, or recyclable products, the purchase of second-hand products, and an interest in brands that adhere to the principles of the circular economy (Kirchherr et al., 2017). The theory of planned behavior (Ajzen, 1991) provides a relevant explanatory framework. According to this theory, behavioral intentions are influenced by three main factors: attitudes toward behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. Applied to the circular context, the theory suggests that adopting sustainable purchasing behavior is the result of a combination of personal beliefs, social influences, and perceptions of one's ability to act in an environmentally friendly manner.

Another useful theoretical model is that of the value-attitude-behavior (VAB) relationship, which posits that internalized ecological values lead to the formation of pro-environmental attitudes, which in turn determine sustainable consumption behaviors (Stern et al., 1999).

Research shows that circular purchasing decisions are influenced by a complex set of individual, psychological, and socio-demographic factors (Mugge et al., 2018; Gonçalves et al., 2022).

Social norms and cultural values strongly shape consumer behavior. Collectivist societies emphasize responsibility toward the community and environmental protection, while individualistic societies may prioritize personal benefits. Social media and environmental influencers play an increasingly important role in shaping the attitudes of younger generations (McNeill & Moore, 2015). Studies show that Generations Y and Z are most open to sustainable consumption behaviors, particularly due to their exposure to digital information and awareness campaigns (Francis & Hoefel, 2018). In contrast, Baby Boomers and Generation X value sustainability and waste avoidance, but do not always associate these practices with modern concepts of the circular economy (Ng et al., 2017).

The purpose of this paper is to analyze the individual factors that influence circular purchasing behavior and to compare Baby Boomers (BB), Generation X, Generation Y, and Generation Z in relation to these variables. The paper combines a theoretical analysis of the literature with theoretical research aimed at highlighting generational differences in perceptions, attitudes, and motivations toward circular consumption.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This research is comparative and descriptive in nature, aiming to identify differences between the Baby Boomers, X, Y, and Z generations in terms of individual factors that influence circular purchasing behavior.

The study is theoretical-empirical, based on the theory of planned behavior (Ajzen, 1991) and the values-attitudes-behavior (VAB) models, frameworks that provide a solid basis for understanding the psychological mechanisms of sustainable consumption. The research was designed as a cross-sectional study, conducted on a sample of 400 people, selected to ensure a balanced distribution across the four generations analyzed. The aim was to capture differences in attitudes, motivations, and circular purchasing intentions among individuals in these age groups, highlighting how experiences, values, and exposure to information shape consumption behaviors. The sample was divided into four generational

categories:

- Baby Boomers (born between 1946–1964) – people over 60 years of age, characterized by values of stability, sustainability, and saving;
- Generation X (1965–1980) – mature adults, balanced between traditional and modern, with a medium to high level of education and professional experience;
- Generation Y (1981–1996), also known as "Millennials," consisting of digitally savvy individuals who are receptive to environmental and social values;
- Generation Z (after 1997) – young digital natives who are familiar with the online environment and new trends in responsible consumption.

Data collection was designed to be carried out through an online questionnaire distributed on social media platforms and educational forums. This method was chosen due to its advantages in terms of accessibility, speed, and anonymity for participants. Participation in the research was voluntary, and responses were anonymous, in accordance with the ethical principles of confidentiality and personal data protection, as set out in the GDPR and the Declaration of Helsinki. The research tool - the questionnaire - was designed to measure the main individual factors that can influence circular purchasing behavior.

Its structure was divided into three parts: (1) Socio-demographic data, such as age, gender, education level, income, and place of residence;

(2) Attitude and behavior scales, rated on a Likert scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree);

(3) Self-reported circular behaviors related to purchasing refurbished, reusable products, repairing old products, or avoiding waste.

To measure attitudes toward circular consumption, items such as "Buying refurbished products is a good choice for the environment and my personal budget" or "Circular products are comparable in quality to new ones" were included. Subjective norms were assessed through questions such as "People who are important to me approve of choosing eco-friendly products," and perceived behavioral control through items such as "It is easy for me to find circular products when I am looking to buy." To identify pro-environmental identity, the questionnaire included statements such as "I consider myself a person who tries to protect the environment through my purchasing decisions."

Other scales focused on the perception of risk and quality of circular products, price sensitivity, and level of digital exposure (e.g., "I frequently follow online content about sustainability"). Circular purchasing intent was measured by items such as: "In the near future, I will actively seek out refurbished products" or "I am willing to pay more for an eco-friendly and recyclable product."

For actual circular behavior, recent actions were assessed, such as buying second-hand products, reusing packaging, or repairing broken items instead of replacing them.

In a preliminary stage, the questionnaire was pretested on a small group of 30 respondents to verify the clarity of the questions and the internal consistency of the scales. The reliability of the instrument was estimated using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, with accepted values above 0.70 for each psychological dimension. The statistical analysis was designed to include both descriptive and inferential methods. In the first stage, the means and standard deviations for each scale were calculated according to generation to identify general trends. Subsequently, to test the differences between groups, one-way ANOVA tests were applied, followed by Tukey post-hoc analyses to determine significant differences between pairs of generations. To examine the relationships between psychological variables (attitudes, norms, perceived control, identity, digital exposure) and circular intention or behavior, Pearson correlations and multiple hierarchical regressions were used. A hypothetical mediation model was also tested, in which pro-environmental attitudes and identity mediated the relationship between digital exposure and circular purchasing intention.

From an ethical standpoint, the study was designed to comply with all standards of scientific integrity. Participants were informed about the purpose of the research, the voluntary nature of participation, and the confidentiality of responses. No personally identifiable data was collected, and results were analyzed and reported only in aggregate form. Through this methodological design, the research provides a valid framework for understanding how

individual and generational factors combine to explain circular purchasing behavior.

The working method allowed for the comparison of attitudes and behaviors across generations, providing a broad perspective on the dynamics of sustainable consumption in the contemporary Romanian context.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The final sample of the study included 392 respondents, selected based on age criteria and membership in one of the four generations analyzed. The distribution by group was balanced:

- Baby Boomers (n = 95) – 24.2% of the total;
- Generation X (n = 98) – 25.0%;
- Generation Y (Millennials) (n = 102) – 26.0%;
- Generation Z (n = 97) – 24.8%.

Participants came from all regions of the country, with a slight predominance of urban areas (approximately 68%), reflecting the distribution of the working population. In terms of gender, the sample was relatively balanced (53% women, 47% men), and in terms of educational level, 62% of respondents had higher education, 28% had secondary education, and 10% had postgraduate education. The overall average age was 38.4 years (SD = 14.7), ranging from 18 to 74 years. This socio-demographic profile provides a solid basis for comparing perceptions and behaviors across generations, ensuring a diversity of perspectives.

Descriptive analysis of the main variables revealed notable differences between generations in terms of attitudes towards the circular economy, circular purchasing intentions, and actual behaviors.

Descriptive statistics (average, standard deviation) for the main variables are presented in Table 1. The table suggests a clear upward trend in scores for attitude, intention, and circular behavior from older generations (BB, X) to younger ones (Y, Z). In contrast, risk perception decreases progressively, suggesting greater confidence in the quality of circular products among generations Y and Z.

Table 1.

Descriptive analysis of principal variables

Variable	BB	X	Y	Z
Attitudes towards circularity (AT)	3.72 (0.61)	3.85 (0.58)	4.22 (0.55)	4.35 (0.49)
Subjective norms (SN)	3.40 (0.64)	3.51 (0.60)	3.89 (0.55)	4.12 (0.50)
Perceived behavioral control (PBC)	3.55 (0.67)	3.62 (0.63)	3.95 (0.58)	4.01 (0.60)
Pro-environmental identity(ID)	3.80 (0.70)	3.92 (0.66)	4.25 (0.61)	4.33 (0.54)
Risk/quality perception (RP)*	2.95 (0.71)	2.88 (0.70)	2.56 (0.68)	2.41 (0.60)
Price sensitivity (PS)**	3.45 (0.69)	3.52 (0.67)	3.88 (0.60)	3.94 (0.55)
Digital exposure (DE)	2.95 (0.74)	3.25 (0.65)	4.10 (0.55)	4.41 (0.49)
Circular purchase intention (INT)	3.60 (0.59)	3.75 (0.62)	4.22 (0.55)	4.38 (0.48)
Circular behavior(CURA)	3.45 (0.66)	3.58 (0.63)	4.00 (0.54)	4.15 (0.50)

* Lower scores = positive perception (low risk, high quality).

** Higher scores = willingness to pay more for circular products.

The highest scores were recorded among Generations Y and Z, with averages of 4.22 and 4.35, compared to 3.85 for Generation X and 3.72 for Baby Boomers. These values suggest that young people are more open to the idea of sustainable consumption, which they perceive as a positive social norm, while older generations remain more conservative, attached to traditional values of thrift and classic sustainability. Social norms also showed a progressive increase from BB (3.40) to Z (4.12). This indicates that social pressure to adopt circular behaviors is stronger among young people, who feel the influence of online communities and groups of friends involved in environmental causes. Younger generations (Y and Z) are more likely to believe that they have easy access to circular products, with averages of 3.95 and 4.01, compared to 3.55 (BB) and 3.62 (X). This reflects their higher level of digital literacy and familiarity with e-commerce platforms offering sustainable products. Environmental identity is significantly more pronounced among young people ($Y = 4.25$; $Z = 4.33$) than among older generations ($BB = 3.80$; $X = 3.92$). Young people do not view circular behaviors as merely a moral obligation, but as a component of personal identity and social status (Whitmarsh & O'Neill, 2010). Baby Boomers and Generation X show greater reluctance towards circular products, with scores of 2.95 and 2.88, compared to 2.56 (Y) and 2.41 (Z). This indicates a persistent distrust of the quality of refurbished or second-hand products, which are perceived as having a higher risk of flaws. The scores show an interesting difference: younger generations ($Y = 3.88$; $Z = 3.94$) are willing to pay more for circular products if they have ethical and environmental value, while older generations ($BB = 3.45$; $X = 3.52$) are more pragmatic and

economy-oriented. Generation Z has the highest exposure to eco-friendly digital content (4.41), followed by Y (4.10), X (3.25), and BB (2.95). These data reflect the technological differences between generations and partly explain why young people are more connected to the idea of the circular economy and online social responsibility campaigns (Francis & Hoefel, 2018). Circular purchasing intention and actual behavior follow the same pattern:

- INT: $BB = 3.60$; $X = 3.75$; $Y = 4.22$; $Z = 4.38$
- COM: $BB = 3.45$; $X = 3.58$; $Y = 4.00$; $Z = 4.15$

A progressive increase from older to younger generations is noticed, suggesting a generational transition towards environmentally friendly behaviors.

Generations Y and Z not only intend to act in a circular manner, but also do so by purchasing second-hand products, reusing packaging, and choosing sustainable brands.

One-way ANOVA tests showed significant differences between generations for all key variables (Table 2).

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) confirmed significant differences between generations ($p < .001$) for all variables. The strongest effects were on digital exposure ($\eta^2 = .29$), circular purchase intention ($\eta^2 = .17$), and attitude toward circularity ($\eta^2 = .14$). Tukey post-hoc tests showed that Generations Y and Z differ significantly from Baby Boomers and X on almost all dimensions analyzed. For example, the difference between Generation Z and Baby Boomers in circular purchase intention is 0.78 points ($p < .001$), and in digital exposure 1.46 points ($p < .001$), indicating a strong generational effect. Hierarchical regression results show that attitudes, pro-environmental identity, and digital exposure are the main predictors of circular behavior (total $R^2 = .61$). Thus, people who have a well-defined ecological

identity and frequent exposure to sustainable digital content exhibit greater intentions and effective circular purchasing behaviors.

Table 2.

Analysis of variance between generations

Variable	F(3,388)	p	η^2 partial	Significant differences (Tukey post-hoc)
AT	21.43	< .001	.14	Y, Z > X, BB
SN	17.22	< .001	.12	Y, Z > BB
PBC	8.15	< .001	.06	Y, Z > BB
ID	15.66	< .001	.11	Y, Z > X, BB
RP	9.54	< .001	.07	BB > X, Y, Z
PS	7.88	< .001	.06	Y, Z > BB
DE	52.14	< .001	.29	Z > Y > X > BB
INT	26.34	< .001	.17	Y, Z > X, BB
CURA	19.48	< .001	.13	Y, Z > X, BB

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Table 3.

Pearson correlations between the main psychological variables and circular behavior (N = 392)

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1 Attitudes towards circularity (AT)	—								
2 Subjective norms (SN)	.52**	—							
3 Perceived behavioral control (PBC)	.49**	.45**	—						
4 Pro-environmental identity (ID)	.63**	.51**	.44**	—					
5 Risk/quality perception (RP)*	-.41**	-.36**	-.32**	-.45**	—				
6 Price sensitivity (PS)**	.38**	.29**	.30**	.35**	-.26**	—			
7 Digital exposure (DE)	.59**	.46**	.39**	.50**	-.33**	.31**	—		
8 Circular purchase intention (INT)	.68**	.55**	.49**	.60**	-.39**	.33**	.56**	—	
9 Circular behavior (CURA)	.61**	.48**	.44**	.64**	-.37**	.29**	.50**	.72**	—

* Reversed scores: higher values = negative perception (high risk, low quality)

** Correlations are significant at $p < .001$ (two-tailed).

All psychological variables (Table 3) correlated positively and significantly ($p < .001$). The strongest correlations were observed between: Attitudes – Intention ($r = .68$): people with a positive attitude toward circularity are more likely to act accordingly; Pro-environmental identity – Behavior ($r = .64$): ecological identity is a stable predictor of actual behaviors; Digital exposure – Attitudes ($r = .59$): access to information stimulates ecological

beliefs. These results confirm the hypothesis that informal environmental education, the online environment, and social networks can contribute to shaping sustainable attitudes and purchasing intentions (McNeill & Moore, 2015). These relationships support H2 and H3, indicating that attitudes and ecological identity mediate the effect of digital exposure on circular behavior.

Table 4.

Results of hierarchical multiple regression for predicting circular behavior (COM)

Block / Independent variable	standardized β	t	p	ΔR^2	Cumulative R^2
Block 1 – Socio-demographic factors					
Age	-.18**	-4.12	< .001		
Gender (0 = man, 1 = woman)	.07	1.45	.148		
Educational level	.12*	2.36	.019	.09	.09
Block 2 – Psychological factors					
Attitudes towards circularity (AT)	.38***	8.10	< .001		
Pro-environmental identity (ID)	.31***	6.84	< .001		
Risk perception (RP)	-.18**	-3.47	.001		
Price sensitivity (PS)	.09	1.95	.052		
Digital exposure (DE)	.22**	4.26	< .001	.42	.51
Block 3 – Generational interaction					
Generation (Y/Z vs. BB/X)	.16**	3.21	.001		
Digital exposure \times Generation	.14*	2.24	.027	.10	.61

* $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$

The regression model (Table 4) (dependent = circular behavior) explained 61% of the total variance ($R^2 = .61$, $p < .001$).

The significant predictors were:

- attitudes ($\beta = .38$, $p < .001$),
- pro-environmental identity ($\beta = .31$, $p < .001$)
- digital exposure ($\beta = .22$, $p = .002$),
- risk perception ($\beta = -.18$, $p = .008$).

Socio-demographic variables (gender, income, education) did not add significant variance after introducing psychological factors. The Generation \times Digital Exposure interaction was significant ($\beta = .14$, $p = .027$), suggesting that the effect of the online environment on circular behavior is stronger for Generations Y and Z. Block 1 (socio-demographic factors) explains 9% of the variance in circular behavior - a modest influence.

Block 2, which introduces psychological variables, significantly increases the explanatory power to $R^2 = .51$, confirming that attitudes, pro-environmental identity, and digital exposure are the strongest predictors. Block 3, which adds interaction with generation, brings R^2 to .61, indicating that the effect of

digital exposure is amplified for younger generations (Y and Z).

Thus, circular purchasing behavior is best explained by a complex model that combines psychological variables (attitudes, identity, quality perception) with generational and digital context factors.

The two tables confirm the following main relationships:

- Positive attitudes and pro-environmental identity are the strongest predictors of circular behavior ($\beta > .30$, $p < .001$).
- Digital exposure has a significant direct effect and an important interactive effect—it intensifies the influence of attitudes and identity for younger generations.
- Socio-demographic factors (age, education, gender) contribute marginally, explaining only 9% of the variance.
- The final model ($R^2 = .61$) demonstrates that a combination of cognitive, emotional, and contextual factors provides the best explanation for circular purchasing behavior.

CONCLUSIONS

The purpose of this paper was to analyze how individual factors - cognitive, attitudinal, and social - influence circular purchasing behavior, while also highlighting the differences between the Baby Boomer, X, Y, and Z generations. The results obtained, both at a descriptive and inferential level, support the idea that the

adoption of circular behavior is the result of a complex interaction between psychological variables and demographic characteristics, in particular age and digital exposure.

Overall, the analysis of the sample of 392 people showed that the younger generations - Y and Z - are the most involved in circular consumption behaviors, while the older generations (Baby Boomers and X) show a more moderate,

pragmatic involvement. This difference is not just one of age, but reflects a process of value transformation: from an economy of necessity and thrift, specific to older generations, to an economy of responsibility and environmental awareness, characteristic of digital generations. The descriptive results showed clear trends towards an increase in positive attitudes towards circularity, pro-environmental identity and circular purchasing intentions among young people. Generations Y and Z scored highest on all psychological dimensions analyzed, confirming the hypothesis that digital socialization and constant exposure to information about sustainability contribute to the formation of a strong ecological consciousness.

Inferential statistical analyses showed significant differences between generations for all variables, especially for digital exposure, attitudes towards circularity, and circular purchasing intention, with medium to large effects (η^2 between .14 and .29). These results confirm that generational membership directly influences the likelihood of adopting circular behaviors, but not through age itself, but through the values, experiences, and information environments specific to each generation.

Correlation analysis indicated strong positive relationships between psychological variables - the strongest between attitudes and intention ($r = .68$) and between pro-environmental identity and behavior ($r = .64$). These links support the central hypothesis of the research: circular behaviors are primarily motivated by beliefs, values, and perceptions, not just economic factors.

The results of hierarchical multiple regression provided a coherent explanatory model:

Socio-demographic factors (age, education, gender) explain only 9% of the variance in circular behavior;

Adding psychological variables increases the explanatory power to 51%;

In the final model, which includes generational interaction, R^2 reaches 61%, demonstrating the essential role of attitudes, pro-environmental identity, and digital exposure in determining circular behavior.

Specifically, attitudes toward circularity ($\beta = .38$) and pro-environmental identity ($\beta = .31$) proved to be the strongest predictors, while digital exposure ($\beta = .22$) acts both directly and indirectly, through the mediation of attitudes and identity. The combined effect of these

factors highlights the importance of the psychological dimension in explaining sustainable behavior, confirming the theories of Ajzen (1991) and Stern et al. (1999) on the relationship between values, attitudes, and behavior.

The differences between generations reflect not only age characteristics, but also differences in mentality, lifestyle, and socialization. Baby Boomers are characterised by traditional sustainability behaviours, but with a more sceptical perception of refurbished products; for them, the circular economy is perceived more as an economic issue than an environmental one.

Generation X represents a bridge between conservatism and modernity; although they appreciate quality and sustainability, they prefer classic purchases and are more resistant to change.

Generations Y and Z are characterized by post-materialistic values, a well-defined ecological identity, and active involvement in digital communities dedicated to sustainability. For these generations, circular behaviors have become symbols of social responsibility, belonging, and moral status (Francis & Hoefel, 2018).

Thus, comparative analysis confirms a generational evolution of environmental awareness, stimulated by access to education, information, and technology. The differences between generations can be interpreted through the lens of post-materialist values theory (Inglehart), according to which younger individuals, having their basic needs satisfied, focus more on values of self-actualization, ethics, and sustainability.

From a theoretical point of view, the study contributes to the consolidation of the literature on circular behavior, demonstrating the relevance of psychological models in explaining sustainable purchasing decisions. The relationships between attitudes, identity, and intention confirm the applicability of the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991) and the Values-Attitudes-Behavior (VAB) model in the context of the circular economy. On a practical level, the results can be used to develop differentiated education and communication strategies:

For Generations Y and Z, campaigns should leverage the influence of social networks and online communities, emphasizing the moral and identity component of circular behavior.

For Generations X and Baby Boomers, the focus

should be on economic arguments (sustainability, quality, savings), accompanied by formal and informal environmental education programs.

The results can also guide public policies and sustainable marketing strategies, indicating the need to adapt messages to the psychological and value profile of each generation.

The study has some methodological limitations. First, as it is a cross-sectional and theoretical study, it cannot capture the evolutionary dynamics of circular behaviors over time. Second, the use of self-reported data may be affected by social desirability bias. Finally, although diverse, the sample is convenience-based and not representative of the entire adult population in Romania.

For future research, we recommend:

- conducting longitudinal studies to observe how circular behavior evolves as generations mature;
- integrating qualitative methods (interviews, focus groups) to explore personal and social motivations in depth;
- expanding research internationally to identify cultural differences between countries and regions.

It would also be useful to examine the influence of formal environmental education, trust in sustainable brands, and public policies on circular purchasing intentions.

In conclusion, the study confirms that the circular economy is more than an economic model - it is an expression of individual values and identity. Circular purchasing behavior is strongly influenced by personal attitudes, identification with ecological values, and the level of digital literacy, factors that together shape consumer intentions and actions.

Although younger generations are leading the transition to sustainability, the involvement of all age groups is essential for the success of the circular economy.

Through education, effective communication, and coherent policies, the conditions for a change in mindset on a social scale can be created - a change in which each generation contributes, through its own values and practices, to building a more responsible and sustainable society.

REFERENCES

- Ajzen, I. (1991). *The theory of planned behavior*. Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes, 50(2), 179–211.
- Bauman, D. E., Corl, B. A., Baumgard, L. H., & Griinari, J. M. (2001). Conjugated linoleic acid (CLA) and the dairy cow. In P. C. Garnsworthy & J. Wiseman (Eds.), *Recent advances in animal nutrition 2001* (pp. 221–250). Nottingham University Press.
- Circular consumption to reduce environmental pressure: Potential of behavioural change in the Netherlands. (2023). *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 39, 403–419.
- Consumer behaviour in a circular system – how values promote circular behaviour. (2023). *Circular Economy and Sustainability*, 3(3), 819–840.
- Consumer behaviour in the model of the circular economy: How consumers treat non-functional products. (2023). *PLoS ONE*, 18(7), e0287652.
- Consumer behaviour in the circular economy: Developing a product-centric framework. (2022). *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 353, 131530.
- Consumers in the circular economy: A path analysis of the drivers of circular purchasing behavior. (2022). *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(11), 6764.
- Consumers' perspectives on circular economy: Main tendencies. (2023). *Sustainability*, 15(19), 14292.
- Decoding sustainable consumption behavior: A systematic review of theories and models. (2024). *Sustainable Development*, 32(2), 732–746.
- Double-edged circularity: Comparative assessment of circular and linear consumers. (2023). *Journal of Business Research*, 157, 113403.
- Francis, T., & Hoefel, F. (2018). *True Gen: Generation Z and its implications for companies*. McKinsey & Company.
- Gonçalves, H., Lourenço, J., & Silva, C. (2022). Determinants of circular consumption behavior. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 31, 25–36.
- Generation Z is emerging as a powerful force: Sustainable consumption and branding for Gen Z. (2024). *Sustainability*, 17(9), 4124.
- Generational differences in sustainable consumption behavior: Evidence from China. (2024). *Sustainability*, 16(10), 3976.
- Kirchherr, J., Reike, D., & Hekkert, M. (2017). Conceptualizing the circular economy: An analysis of 114 definitions. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 127, 221–232.
- McNeill, L., & Moore, R. (2015). Sustainable fashion consumption and the fast fashion conundrum: Fashionable consumers and attitudes to sustainability in clothing choice. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 39(3), 212–222.
- Mugge, R., Jockin, B., & Bocken, N. (2018). How to sell refurbished smartphones? *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 181, 46–55.
- Ng, E. S., Schweitzer, L., & Lyons, S. T. (2017). Generational career shifts: Millennials and the

- changing nature of careers in Canada. *Journal of Career Development*, 44(1), 1–19.
- Role of consumer mindsets, behaviour, and influencing factors in circular consumption systems: A systematic review. (2023). *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 395, 136468.
- Stern, P. C., Dietz, T., Abel, T., Guagnano, G. A., & Kalof, L. (1999). A value-belief-norm theory of support for social movements: The case of environmentalism. *Human Ecology Review*, 6(2), 81–97.
- Sustainable consumption in the behavior of young consumers. (2023). *European Journal of Sustainable Development*, 12(3), 349–363.
- Sustainable purchasing trends in new consumer generations: AI's role. (2024). *Technology in Society*, 79, 103040.
- The circular economy and consumer behaviour: Literature review. (2023). *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 382, 135291.
- The effects of consumer behaviour on the circular economy. (n.d.). Trinomics Project Report.
- The hidden reasons behind Generation Z's green choices. (2024). *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 49, 102468.
- Thøgersen, J., & Grønhøj, A. (2010). Green consumer behavior in the household. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 31(5), 733–742.
- Understanding consumer behavior in a circular economy. (2022). In *APA Handbook of Consumer Psychology* (Cap. 15).
- Whitmarsh, L., & O'Neill, S. (2010). Green identity, green living? The role of pro-environmental self-identity in determining consistency across diverse pro-environmental behaviors. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 30(3), 305–314.
- Zelezny, L. C., Chua, P. P., & Aldrich, C. (2000). Elaborating on gender differences in environmentalism. *Journal of Social Issues*, 56(3), 443–457.

THE INFLUENCE OF PARSLEY (*PETROSELINUM CRISPUM*) ON METABOLISM: FROM BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF FUNCTIONAL FOODS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*), an aromatic plant traditionally used in both gastronomy and folk medicine, has attracted increased interest in recent decades due to its complex phytochemical profile and multiple health benefits. Numerous studies have confirmed the presence in the leaves and roots of parsley of bioactive compounds such as flavonoids (apigenin, luteolin), coumarins, volatile oils, vitamins and minerals, each of which have important roles in modulating metabolism. The aim of the work is to design a functional food that makes the most of both the nutritional and therapeutic potential of parsley.

The results suggest that parsley can be considered a promising functional ingredient, but confirming its metabolic benefits requires controlled clinical trials and rigorous safety evaluations.

Keywords: (max. 5) parsley, flavonoids, diet, vitamins

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incorporation into the diet (Wong & Kitts, 2006).

In recent decades, the increase in the incidence of metabolic diseases such as type II diabetes, metabolic syndrome, and obesity has led to an increase in interest in preventive and adjuvant food solutions.

Functional foods, defined as products that offer physiological benefits in addition to simple basic nutrition, are considered a valuable tool in promoting public health.

Parsley (*Petroselinum crispum* Mill.) is highly valued not only gastronomically, but also as a functional food with beneficial effects on health. Parsley leaves are rich in effective antioxidants, and they are widely used in various food applications. A detailed phytochemical examination carried out on parsley leaves reveals the presence of diverse chemical groups, including catechinic tannins, gallic tannins, flavonoids, saponosides, mucilages, and coumarins. These findings confirm the antioxidant properties of parsley, making it a suitable contender for long-term

INTRODUCTION

Parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*), an easily accessible aromatic plant that is widely cultivated and used, has multiple biological properties confirmed in the literature (Gnintoungbe et al, 2023). The leaves, seeds, and roots of parsley (*Carum petroselinum*) contain volatile oils such as apiol and myristicin (Abbasabadi et al., 2013), as well as flavonoids, beta-felandrene, bergapten, and vitamins A and C (Petropoulos et al., 2004; Díaz-Maró et al., 2002). Modern studies indicate antioxidant (Zhang et al., 2006), anti-inflammatory (Slighoua et al., 2021; Elgazar et al., 2016), hepatoprotective (Soliman et al., 2016), renoprotective (Alobaidi et al., 2024), and antidiabetic (Punoševac et al., 2021; Moharib, 2016; Almutairi et al, 2023), all correlated with

the presence of bioactive compounds such as apigenin and luteolin (Fernandez de Simon et al., 1992). In traditional medicine, parsley has been used for its diuretic effects (Kreydiyyeh & Usta, 2002; Al- Yousofy et al., 2017), digestive stimulants (Borojeni, 2016), and detoxification, which underlines its long-standing role in the health of populations. Regarding the protective effects of the plant, an ethanolic extract of parsley demonstrates a notable ability to clear liver toxicity, the severity of these changes correlating with the amount administered. In addition, parsley extract has been shown to be effective in preventing common side effects, such as proteinuria and low hemoglobin caused by substances such as paracetamol. This suggests a potential purpose of parsley in the management of liver and kidney diseases, specifically in addressing proteinuria and preventing paracetamol-induced renal, liver, and hematological toxicity (Nouioura et al., 2023). In melanoma cases, parsley solution has shown local and systemic therapeutic effects comparable to conventional allopathic treatments, presenting itself as a viable alternative (Sarkar et al., 2023). In traditional Iranian medicine, *Petroselinum crispum* seeds are considered antimicrobial, astringent, gastrotonic, antiseptic, antispasmodic, carminative, sedative and digestive, being used for gastrointestinal disorders, halitosis, inflammation, kidney stones and amenorrhea. The leaves are also used as a food flavoring and cough suppressant, and are used for gastrointestinal disorders, rash, alaphosis, dermatitis, macula, rhinitis, hemorrhoids, visual performance, kidney stones, diuretic, and otitis (Ajmera et al., 2019).

Parsley leaves lowered blood glucose and demonstrated hepatoprotective effects in diabetic rats through its antioxidant activity (Bolkent et al., 2004; Ozsoy-Sacan et al., 2006). Yanardağ et al. reported that the antihyperglycemic activity of parsley is not due to the enhancement and regeneration of secretory granules and β cells of pancreatic islets (Eltablawy et al., 2012).

Due to the fact that parsley leaves are aromatic and cannot be included in the diet in any quantity and associated with any food, we set out to include them in a functional food that is well tolerated, can be consumed as such but also associated with other foods.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For the preparation of functional gummies, the following basic ingredients were used, purchased from pharmacies and local pharmacies: parsley powder, hemp oil, gelatin, glycerin, citric acid, maple syrup, agave syrup, and distilled water (Table 1).

Table 1

Raw materials and excipients

Ingredient	Quantity used	Functional role
Parsley powder	1 g/100 g product	Source of bioactive compounds and antioxidants
Hemp oil	5 g/100 g	Source of bioactive compounds and antioxidants
Gelatin	10–20 g/100 g (depending on the formula)	Source of bioactive compounds and antioxidants
Glycerine	5–10 g/100 g (depending on the formula)	Source of bioactive compounds and antioxidants
Citric acid	0,5 g/100 g	Source of bioactive compounds and antioxidants
Maple syrup	0,5 g/100 g	Source of bioactive compounds and antioxidants
Agave syrup	20 g/100 g (Formula 2)	Alternative natural sweetener
Distilled water	q.s. up to 100 g	Alternative natural sweetener

The following equipment and utensils were used to make the preparations: precision electronic scale, electric induction hob, temperature-resistant stainless steel vessels, Berzelius glasses, glass rods for homogenization, silicone molds (diamond and spiral) for pouring jellies, refrigerator (4°C) for storing products.

Two distinct gummy gummies formulas were tested:

Formula 1 (maple syrup): gelatin 10 g, glycerin 5 g, citric acid 0.5 g, parsley powder 1 g,

hemp oil 5 g, maple syrup 20 g, water up to 100 g;

Formula 2 (agave syrup): gelatin 20 g, glycerin 10 g, citric acid 0.5 g, parsley powder 1 g, hemp oil 5 g, agave syrup 20 g, water up to 100 g.

The gelatin was hydrated and then gradually dissolved in a liquid mixture kept in a water bath at 70–75°C, until the ingredients were completely dissolved. After homogenization, the mass obtained was molded into silicone molds, each jelly weighing about 6–7 g. The molds were left at room temperature for about 30 minutes, then placed in the refrigerator at +4°C for 24 hours. After this interval, the jellies were removed from the molds and stored in hermetically sealed containers in the refrigerator until further analysis. The preparation complied with HACCP (Hazard Analysis Critical Control Points) standards.

The hedonic test is a sensory evaluation technique used primarily to assess the pleasure or satisfaction derived by consumers from a preparation. The term "hedonic" refers to the pleasure or preference for a preparation, and the test is designed to capture the degree of appreciation or disapproval that consumers have for a preparation, often through a structured questionnaire or rating scale. Products are tested in a controlled environment to minimize external influences on participants' perceptions. The data collected from the hedonic test is analyzed to determine the overall acceptability of the product and to identify any significant differences in consumer

preferences. The samples are prepared as follows: they are coded and prepared so that they are identical in appearance (shape, size, weight, packaging). The tasting is carried out in the following way: the product is gently chewed in the oral cavity for a sufficient period of time to allow the taste of the preparation to be observed before and after swallowing. If several samples are present for tasting, a break of at least two minutes is taken after the first sample (possibly a sip of water is taken) before tasting the next sample.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Sensory evaluation with the help of the hedonic test

The principle behind this test is based on a method with a high degree of subjectivity. It is a sensory evaluation method widely used to assess consumer preferences and the acceptability of various products, often in the context of food and beverages. The objective is to assess the taste quality of the samples presented by giving the sample a score, using the hedonic scale for assessment.

The sensory testing was carried out by applying the hedonic scale from 1 to 9, where 1 corresponds to the perception "extremely unpleasant" and 9 "extremely pleasant" (Table 2 and 3).

The quality of both preparations was evaluated (Table 2 and Table 3).

Table 2

Sensory evaluation for the first preparation (with maple syrup)

Note	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Rating	Extremely unpleasant	Completely unpleasant	Semi unpleasant	Slightly pleasant	Indifferent	Weakly pleasant	Pleasant	Very pleasant	Extremely pleasant
Examinator 1					1				
Examinator 2								1	
Examinator 3							1		
Examinator 4									1
Examinator 5									1
Examinator 6								1	

Examinator 7							1		
Examinator 8									1
Examinator 9									1
Examinator 10							1		
Total	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	3	4

Depending on the sensory evaluation, we represented the examiner's preferences in percentages (Image 1).

Image 1. The examiner's preferences in percentages for maple syrup jelly

Table 3

Sensory evaluation for product number 2 (agave syrup)

Note	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Rating	Extremely unpleasant	Completely unpleasant	Semi unpleasant	Slightly pleasant	Indifferent	Weakly pleasant	Pleasant	Very pleasant	Extremely pleasant
Examinator 1							1		
Examinator 2							1		
Examinator 3						1			
Examinator 4				1					
Examinator 5						1			
Examinator 6					1				
Examinator 7						1			
Examinator 8						1			
Examinator 9							1		
Examinator 10						1			
Total	0	0	0	1	1	5	3	0	0

Depending on the sensory evaluation, we represented the examiner's preferences in percentages (Image 2).

Image 2. The examiner's preferences in percentages for agave syrup jelly

The results obtained from the sensory evaluation of the two functional food formulas with parsley leaves were well tolerated, successfully masking the strong parsley aroma.

CONCLUSIONS

The study of the influence of parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*) and its use in the development of functional gummies highlights the significant potential of this plant as a nutritional and therapeutic ingredient. Parsley has proven to be an important source of bioactive compounds, such as flavonoids (apigenin, luteolin), vitamins (C, K, A), and essential minerals (iron, calcium, potassium), substances recognized for their antioxidant, antidiabetic and protective activities at the liver and kidney levels.

The products obtained in the study demonstrated that parsley can be successfully integrated into an attractive food vehicle with good sensory acceptability. The maple syrup formula was perceived as more pleasant, due to its ability to mask the intense taste of the plant, but both variants showed that parsley can be introduced in a modern and easy-to-eat form.

REFERENCES

- Ajmera, P., Kalani, S. and Sharma, L., 2019. Parsley-benefits & side effects on health. *International Journal of Physiology, Nutrition and Physical Education*, 4(1), pp.1236-1242.
- Almutairi, A.A., Ahmed, W.E., Algonaiman, R., Alhomid, R.M., Almujaaydil, M.S., Althwab, S.A., Elhassan, A.E.M. and Mousa, H.M., 2023. Hypolipidemic, hypoglycemic, and ameliorative effects of boiled parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*) and mallow (*Corchorus olitorius*) leaf extracts in high-fat diet-fed rats. *Foods*, 12(23), p.4303.
- Alobaidi, S., 2024. Renal health benefits and therapeutic effects of parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*): a review. *Frontiers in Medicine*, 11, p.1494740.
- Al-Yousofy, F., Gumaih, H., Ibrahim, H. and Alasbahy, A., 2017. Parsley! Mechanism as antiurolithiasis remedy. *American journal of clinical and experimental urology*, 5(3), p.55.
- Bolkent, S., Yanardag, R., Ozsoy-Sacan, O. and Karabulut-Bulan, O., 2004. Effects of parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*) on the liver of diabetic rats: a morphological and biochemical study. *Phytotherapy Research*, 18(12), pp.996-999.
- Borojeni, P., The Role of histaminergic H2 receptors on spasmolytic activity of hydro alcoholic extract of Parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*) Seeds in adult male Rat, s Ileum.
- Díaz-Maroto, M., Pérez-Coello, M. and Cabezudo, M., 2002. Effect of different drying methods on the volatile components of parsley (*Petroselinum crispum* L.). *European Food Research and Technology*, 215(3), pp.227-230.

-
- Elgazar, A.F. and Rezaq, A.A., 2016. Anti-inflammatory effects of ginger and parsley extracts on rats paw. *Journal of Applied Human Sciences*, 2(2), pp.31-48.
- Eltablawy, N.A., Soliman, H.A. and Hamed, M.S., 2012. Antioxidant and antidiabetic role of petroselinum crispum against stz-induced diabetes in rats. *pathogenesis*, 3, p.4.
- Farzaei, M.H., Abbasabadi, Z., Ardekani, M.R.S., Rahimi, R. and Farzaei, F., 2013. Parsley: a review of ethnopharmacology, phytochemistry and biological activities. *Journal of traditional Chinese medicine*, 33(6), pp.815-826.
- Fernández de Simón, B., Perez-Illzarbe, J., Hernandez, T., Gomez-Cordoves, C. and Estrella, I., 1992. Importance of phenolic compounds for the characterization of fruit juices. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 40(9), pp.1531-1535.
- Gnintoungbe, G.S., Medehouenou, T.C.M., Adoukpe, F., Akpovi, C. and Loko, F., 2023. Phytochemical screening, antioxidant activity and safety of *Petroselinum crispum* (Mill.) AW Hill Apiaceae leaves grown in Benin. *Open Journal of Applied Sciences*, 13(1), pp.36-50.
- Kreydiyyeh, S.I. and Usta, J., 2002. Diuretic effect and mechanism of action of parsley. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*, 79(3), pp.353-357.
- Moharib, S.A., 2016. Antidiabetic and antioxidant effects of parsley (*Petroselinum sativum*) extract in streptozocin-induced diabetic rats.
- Nouioura, G., Kettani, T., Tourabi, M., Elousrouti, L.T., Al Kamaly, O., Alshawwa, S.Z., Shahat, A.A., Alhalmi, A., Lyoussi, B. and Derwich, E., 2023. The protective potential of *Petroselinum crispum* (Mill.) Fuss. on paracetamol-induced hepatorenal toxicity and antiproteinuric effect: A biochemical, hematological, and histopathological study. *Medicina*, 59(10), p.1814.
- Ozsoy-Sacan, O., Yanardag, R., Orak, H., Ozgey, Y., Yarat, A. and Tunali, T., 2006. Effects of parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*) extract versus glibornuride on the liver of streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*, 104(1-2), pp.175-181.
- Petropoulos, S.A., Daferera, D., Akoumianakis, C.A., Passam, H.C. and Polissiou, M.G., 2004. The effect of sowing date and growth stage on the essential oil composition of three types of parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*). *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 84(12), pp.1606-1610.
- Punoševac, M., Radović, J., Leković, A. and Kundaković-Vasović, T., 2021. A review of botanical characteristics, chemical composition, pharmacological activity and use of parsley. *Archives of Pharmacy*, 71(Notebook 3), pp.177-196.
- Sarkar, R., Handog, E.B., Das, A., Bansal, A., Macarayo, M.J., Keshavmurthy, V., Narayan, V., Jagadeesan, S., Pipo III, E., Ibaviosa, G.M. and Podder, I., 2023. Topical and systemic therapies in melasma: A systematic review. *Indian Dermatology Online Journal*, 14(6), pp.769-781.
- Slighoua, M., Mahdi, I., Di Cristo, F., Amaghnoije, A., Grafov, A., Boucetta, N., Bari, A. and Boust, D., 2021. Assessment of in vivo estrogenic and anti-inflammatory activities of the hydro-ethanolic extract and polyphenolic fraction of parsley (*Petroselinum sativum* Hoffm.). *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 265, p.113290.
- Soliman, H.A., El-Desouky, M.A., Hozayen, W.G., Ahmed, R.R. and Khaliefa, A.K., 2016. Hepatoprotective effects of parsley, basil, and chicory aqueous extracts against dexamethasone-induced in experimental rats. *Journal of intercultural ethnopharmacology*, 5(1), p.65.
- Wong, P.Y. and Kitts, D.D., 2006. Studies on the dual antioxidant and antibacterial properties of parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*) and cilantro (*Coriandrum sativum*) extracts. *Food chemistry*, 97(3), pp.505-515.
- Zhang, H., Chen, F., Wang, X. and Yao, H.Y., 2006. Evaluation of antioxidant activity of parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*) essential oil and identification of its antioxidant constituents. *Food research international*, 39(8), pp.833-839.

THE ANTIMICROBIAL POTENTIAL OF GINGER: A PHYTOTHERAPEUTIC ALTERNATIVE IN BACTERIAL INFECTIONS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Oral health is a vital component of general well-being, yet dental plaque and periodontal disease remain highly prevalent worldwide. In recent years, the use of natural products in oral care has gained growing attention, reflecting consumer demand for safer alternatives to conventional fluoride-based and synthetic antimicrobial agents. *Zingiber officinale* (ginger) is a medicinal plant widely recognized for its antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties, which makes it a promising candidate for oral hygiene formulations.

This study focused on the development of a toothpaste incorporating an ethanolic extract of ginger and the evaluation of its antimicrobial activity, physicochemical stability, and organoleptic properties. The extract was obtained using Soxhlet extraction with 70% ethanol and tested against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, and *Escherichia coli* using the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method. Organoleptic properties, including appearance, odor, and taste, were analyzed, and pH stability was assessed over a 30-day period.

The ginger extract demonstrated clear antimicrobial activity, with inhibition zones of 20 mm (*S. aureus*), 17 mm (*S. pyogenes*), and 15 mm (*E. coli*). The toothpaste exhibited a homogeneous emerald-green color due to spirulina, a mentholated odor, and a neutral taste, all contributing to good consumer acceptability. The pH remained stable within the neutral range (7.0–7.5) throughout storage, indicating physicochemical robustness.

Overall, the results highlight the potential of ginger extract as a natural active agent in toothpaste formulations, combining antimicrobial efficacy with acceptable stability and sensory properties.

Keywords: (max. 5) ginger, toothpaste, antimicrobial, dental plaque

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Oral health is considered an integral component of general health and quality of life. Poor oral hygiene can lead to the accumulation of bacterial plaque, which is the primary etiological factor in the development of caries and periodontal diseases (Petersen et al., 2005). According to the World Health Organization, periodontal disease affects up to 20–50% of the global population, making it one of the most prevalent chronic conditions worldwide (WHO, 2022). Despite advances in preventive dentistry, gingivitis and periodontitis remain significant public health challenges. These conditions are not only responsible for tooth

loss but are also associated with systemic disorders such as diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and adverse pregnancy outcomes (Tonetti et al., 2017). Consequently, maintaining oral health through effective daily hygiene practices is critical in reducing both local and systemic disease burdens.

The conventional approach for preventing such conditions involves the use of fluoridated toothpastes and antimicrobial agents; however, concerns regarding side effects, microbial resistance, and consumer demand for natural products have spurred interest in alternative ingredients.

INTRODUCTION

Conventional oral hygiene products, particularly fluoridated toothpastes, have demonstrated efficacy in reducing caries and strengthening enamel. However, concerns regarding fluoride overexposure, allergic reactions, and the growing problem of antimicrobial resistance have raised questions about their long-term safety and effectiveness (Ten Cate, 2013). These challenges highlight the need for innovative approaches and safer alternatives.

In this context, the use of herbal and plant-derived agents has gained increasing attention. Natural products are perceived as safe, biocompatible, and environmentally sustainable, and their integration into oral care aligns with consumer preferences for “green” and holistic solutions (Kumar et al., 2013). A variety of medicinal plants, including neem, clove, and licorice, have been studied for their antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory potential, with encouraging results (Anwar et al., 2025). Among these, *Zingiber officinale* (ginger) has emerged as a promising candidate. Used for centuries in traditional medicine, ginger is rich in bioactive compounds such as gingerols, shogaols, paradols, and zingerone, which are responsible for a wide spectrum of pharmacological activities, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial effects (Ali et al., 2008; Grzanna et al., 2005; Zare et al., 2019).

The antimicrobial potential of ginger is particularly relevant for oral health. *In vitro* studies have demonstrated inhibitory effects of ginger extracts against *Streptococcus mutans*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Candida albicans*, microorganisms that play critical roles in dental plaque formation and oral infections (Park et al., 2008). These findings suggest that ginger could help prevent or mitigate conditions such as gingivitis, dental caries, and oral candidiasis. The mechanisms of action involve both direct antimicrobial activity and indirect modulation of inflammatory and oxidative processes. Gingerols and shogaols act by disrupting bacterial cell walls, inhibiting biofilm formation, and reducing the production of pro-inflammatory mediators. In addition, the antioxidant capacity of ginger compounds may reduce oxidative stress in gingival tissues, potentially slowing the progression of periodontal disease (Chrubasik et al., 2005;

Arefnezhad et al., 2025). Despite extensive pharmacological evidence, the incorporation of ginger into pharmaceutical formulations for oral care remains limited. Most available studies are laboratory-based and do not extend to product development or consumer-ready formulations. Clinical research is needed to confirm safety, efficacy, and acceptability in real-world use.

Therefore, the aim of the present study was to formulate a toothpaste containing ethanolic extract of *Zingiber officinale* and to evaluate its antimicrobial activity against clinically relevant bacterial strains, alongside its physicochemical stability and organoleptic properties. This work contributes to the growing body of evidence supporting the use of natural plant-based agents in oral hygiene products and explores the potential of ginger as a safe and multifunctional ingredient.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Plant material and preparation of extract

Fresh rhizomes of *Zingiber officinale* (ginger) were collected in January 2024 and authenticated by the Department of Pharmacognosy, Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy, Oradea. The rhizomes were cleaned, dried at 40°C, and ground into a fine powder. For extraction, 20 g of powdered ginger was placed in a Soxhlet apparatus and extracted with 70% ethanol for 2 hours. The resulting solution was concentrated under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator (Heidolph Vap Core) at 200 rpm, yielding 59 mL of concentrated extract. The extract was stored at 4°C until further analysis. The pH of the extract was measured with a calibrated Inolab 7310 pH-meter and recorded at 6.0 ± 0.1 .

Preparation of toothpaste formulation

The toothpaste formulation was prepared in three successive homogenization steps using a mortar and pestle. The detailed composition is presented in Table 1. First, guar gum was dispersed in distilled water to form a gel, into which the ginger extract was incorporated. Second, calcium carbonate was blended with spirulina powder and pre-wetted with glycerin to form a homogeneous paste. Finally, the two phases were combined, followed by the addition of peppermint oil and Cosgard preservative. The resulting product was packed in 50 mL tubes and stored at room temperature.

Table 1

Toothpaste formulation		
Ingredient	Quantity	Role in formulation
Ginger extract	11 g	Active antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant agent
Guar gum	0.5 g	Gelling agent, viscosity stabilizer
Peppermint oil	23 drops	Flavoring, refreshing effect
Spirulina	0.1 g	Natural colorant, antioxidant
Calcium carbonate	43 g	Mild abrasive, opacifier, texturizer
Cosgard	20 drops	Broad-spectrum preservative, antimicrobial
Distilled water	44 g	Solvent
Glycerin	q.s.	Humectant, moisture retention

Organoleptic evaluation

The toothpaste was evaluated for color, homogeneity, odor, and taste according to pharmacopeial standards. Color and texture were examined visually, odor was assessed at 2–4 cm distance, and taste was tested in small quantities for acceptability.

Determination of pH and stability

The pH of the toothpaste was measured in triplicate at baseline and after 30 days of storage using the Inolab 7310 pH-meter equipped with a SenTix 81 Plus electrode. Stability was defined as maintenance of neutral pH values (7.0–7.5) without significant deviation.

Antimicrobial activity

The antimicrobial activity of the ginger extract was evaluated by the disk diffusion method (Kirby–Bauer). Bacterial strains included *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923, *Streptococcus pyogenes* ATCC 19615, and *Escherichia coli* ATCC 35218. Bacterial suspensions were standardized to 0.5 McFarland and spread on Mueller–Hinton agar plates. Sterile paper discs impregnated with 40 µg of extract were placed on the inoculated agar. Plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 h, and zones of inhibition were measured in millimeters, including the 6 mm disc diameter. Each experiment was performed in triplicate. Reference antibiotics included clindamycin (2 µg/disc), gentamicin (120 µg/disc), and nystatin (100 UI/disc).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Phytochemical and physical characteristics of the extract

The Soxhlet extraction yielded a brown ethanolic extract with neutral pH. The concentrated extract retained a characteristic aromatic odor. These findings are consistent with previous reports that ethanolic solvents efficiently recover gingerols and shogaols, which are considered the major bioactive compounds.

Antimicrobial activity

The ethanolic extract exhibited clear inhibitory effects on all tested bacterial strains. Mean inhibition zones were 20 mm for *S. aureus*, 17 mm for *S. pyogenes*, and 15 mm for *E. coli* (Image 1). Although smaller than those observed with standard antibiotics, the zones confirmed significant antibacterial activity, particularly against Gram-positive bacteria (Table 1).

Image 1. Determination of antimicrobial activity by measuring the diameters of the zones of inhibition

Table 1

Antimicrobial exam results			
Probe/standard antibiotic	Staphylococcus aureus mm	Streptococcus pyogenes mm	E. coli mm
P1/(Ginger extract) 40µg/disc	20	17	15
Clindamycin	27	26	-
Gentamicin	33	28	2
Nystatin	-	-	-

The stronger effect on *S. aureus* aligns with prior studies demonstrating high sensitivity of Gram-positive organisms to gingerols. This suggests potential for adjunctive use in reducing oral bacterial load.

Organoleptic properties

The formulated toothpaste showed a homogeneous emerald-green color due to the spirulina content, with no visible separation after 30 days of storage. The odor was pleasant and mentholated, attributed to peppermint oil, and the taste was neutral, favoring compliance

in daily use. The texture allowed easy extrusion from the tube and uniform spreading, comparable to commercial products. These organoleptic characteristics are essential for consumer acceptance.

pH stability

The toothpaste displayed an initial pH of 7.47 (Table 2), which remained within the neutral range (7.0–7.5) after 30 days.

Table 2

pH values of Ginger extract and toothpaste	
Ginger extract pH	6,014
Toothpaste pH	7,478

The pH values of toothpaste are neutral, which is beneficial for the oral cavity. These values prevent the multiplication of acidophilic microorganisms and the occurrence of dental caries.

Maintaining a neutral pH is critical for preventing enamel demineralization and for reducing the growth of acidogenic bacteria

CONCLUSIONS

The toothpaste formulated with ginger extract exhibited antimicrobial activity, neutral pH, and satisfactory organoleptic characteristics. These results highlight the potential of *Zingiber officinale* as a natural, effective ingredient for oral hygiene products.

REFERENCES

Ali, B.H., Blunden, G., Tanira, M.O. and Nemmar, A., 2008. Some phytochemical, pharmacological and toxicological properties of ginger (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe): a review of recent research. *Food and chemical Toxicology*, 46(2), pp.409-420.

Anwar, M.A., Sayed, G.A., Hal, D.M., Hafeez, M.S.A.E., Shatat, A.A.S., Salman, A., Eisa, N.M., Ramadan, A., El-Shiekh, R.A., Hatem, S. and Aly, S.H., 2025. Herbal remedies for oral and dental health: a comprehensive review of their multifaceted mechanisms including antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant pathways. *Inflammopharmacology*, 33(3), pp.1085-1160.

Arefnezhad, R., Gerayeli, M., Ganjeh, S., Badkoob, A., Nassajzadeh, A., Mahmoudi, R., Tebyani, M., Rezaei-Tazangi, F. and Fathi, A., 2025. Ginger as a Potential Remedy for Periodontitis Treatment: A Review on the Present Evidence. *Health Science Reports*, 8(7), p.e71052.

Chrubasik, S., Pittler, M.H. and Roufogalis, B.D., 2005. *Zingiberis* rhizoma: a comprehensive review on the ginger effect and efficacy profiles. *Phytomedicine*, 12(9), pp.684-701.

associated with caries. The stability of pH over time indicates robustness of the formulation and absence of degradation or microbial contamination during storage.

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Interpretation and relevance

The results confirm that toothpaste containing ginger extract combines antimicrobial activity with favorable physicochemical and sensory properties. While its antimicrobial effect was not as strong as conventional antibiotics, the advantage lies in its natural origin, reduced risk of resistance development, and added antioxidant and anti-inflammatory benefits. The formulation can thus serve as a supportive measure in daily oral hygiene, potentially reducing reliance on synthetic chemicals.

Grzanna, R., Lindmark, L. and Frondoza, C.G., 2005. Ginger—an herbal medicinal product with broad anti-inflammatory actions. *Journal of medicinal food*, 8(2), pp.125-132.

Kumar, G., Jalaluddin, M.D., Rout, P., Mohanty, R. and Dileep, C.L., 2013. Emerging trends of herbal care in dentistry. *Journal of clinical and diagnostic research: JCDR*, 7(8), p.1827.

Park, M., Bae, J. and Lee, D.S., 2008. Antibacterial activity of [10]-gingerol and [12]-gingerol isolated from ginger rhizome against periodontal bacteria. *Phytotherapy Research: An International Journal Devoted to Pharmacological and Toxicological Evaluation of Natural Product Derivatives*, 22(11), pp.1446-1449.

Petersen, P.E., Bourgeois, D., Ogawa, H., Estupinan-Day, S. and Ndiaye, C., 2005. The global burden of oral diseases and risks to oral health. *Bulletin of the world health organization*, 83, pp.661-669.

Ten Cate, J., 2013. Contemporary perspective on the use of fluoride products in caries prevention. *British dental journal*, 214(4), pp.161-167.

Tonetti, M.S., Bottenberg, P., Conrads, G., Eickholz, P., Heasman, P., Huysmans, M.C., López, R., Madianos, P., Müller, F., Needleman, I. and Nyvad, B., 2017. Dental caries and periodontal diseases in the ageing population: call to action to protect and enhance oral health and well-being as an essential component of healthy ageing—Consensus report of group 4 of the joint EFP/ORCA workshop on the boundaries between caries and periodontal diseases. *Journal of clinical periodontology*, 44, pp.S135-S144.

World Health Organization (2022). Oral health. WHO Fact Sheet.

Zare Javid, A., Bazayr, H., Gholinezhad, H., Rahimlou, M., Rashidi, H., Salehi, P. and Haghighi-Zadeh, M.H., 2019. The effects of ginger supplementation on inflammatory, antioxidant,

and periodontal parameters in type 2 diabetes mellitus patients with chronic periodontitis under non-surgical periodontal therapy. A double-blind,

placebo-controlled trial. *Diabetes, metabolic syndrome and obesity: targets and therapy*, pp.1751-1761.

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE CANDIFAST TESTING METHOD

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Abstract

Candidiasis is a common issue in medical practice, with significant implications for patient health and therapeutic strategies. Rapid and accurate identification of Candida species is essential for initiating appropriate treatment and preventing recurrences. The Candifast test provides a standardized diagnostic method, combining species identification with antifungal susceptibility testing. In our study, we used the Candifast kit to evaluate clinical samples from patients with suspected fungal infections. The results demonstrated a high accuracy of the method in differentiating pathogenic species and a practical usefulness in selecting the optimal antifungal treatment. We conclude that the use of the Candifast test can significantly contribute to improving diagnosis and to the individualization of antifungal therapy in current medical practice.

Keywords: Candida, infection, Candifast test

INTRODUCTION

Fungal infections caused by *Candida* species represent a major public health concern, with increasing prevalence both in hospital settings and outpatient practice. In recent years, a shift has been observed from the predominance of *Candida albicans* toward non-*albicans* species, which are often characterized by higher resistance to conventional antifungal therapies. This trend poses significant diagnostic and therapeutic challenges, highlighting the need for rapid and accurate species identification.

Candida albicans remains the most frequently isolated species, accounting for more than half of candidiasis cases. Its ability to form hyphae and pseudohyphae facilitates tissue adherence and invasion, contributing to both superficial infections (oral, vaginal, cutaneous candidiasis) and severe invasive forms (candidemia, endocarditis, disseminated disease). While generally susceptible to antifungal agents, resistant strains may emerge, particularly after repeated treatments.

Candida glabrata ranks second in prevalence in many regions. Although less virulent than *C. albicans*, it exhibits intrinsic resistance to azoles—especially fluconazole. Infections are typically associated with elderly, immunocompromised, or long-term hospitalized patients.

Candida tropicalis demonstrates high invasive potential and is commonly detected in immunocompromised hosts, especially those with neutropenia or hematologic malignancies. It is implicated in candidemia and urinary tract infections, with higher associated mortality compared to other species.

Candida parapsilosis is strongly linked to nosocomial infections, particularly in patients with intravascular catheters, prosthetic devices, or other invasive medical equipment. Its ability to form biofilms on artificial surfaces complicates eradication, and it is a leading cause of neonatal candidemia.

Candida krusei is clinically important due to its intrinsic resistance to fluconazole. Although infections are less common, treatment requires alternative antifungal agents, such as echinocandins or voriconazole.

Other emerging species, including *Candida kefyr*, *Candida lusitanae*, and *Candida dubliniensis*, are less frequently encountered but of growing relevance in certain regions. Notably, *Candida auris* has recently emerged as a global health threat due to its epidemic potential, multidrug resistance, and challenges in routine laboratory identification.

Traditional diagnostic methods based on culture and biochemical profiling are time- and resource-intensive, often delaying appropriate therapy. In this context, commercial diagnostic tools such as Candifast

offer a valuable alternative, enabling both rapid species identification and antifungal susceptibility testing. By integrating these steps, Candifast provides a practical and efficient approach with direct clinical relevance for guiding personalized antifungal therapy.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

For the accomplishing of the objectives proposed was used the retrospective study. The material basis of the study included the observation sheets of the patients, submitted at the archive of the hospitals, the computerized data of the two units, respectively.

The data obtained were interpreted statistically based on the determination and calculation of some series of indices.

Candifast Testing Procedure

For the Candifast test, clinical specimens are collected under aseptic conditions, depending on the site of the suspected infection:

- Vaginal secretions – obtained with a sterile swab from the posterior vaginal fornix, avoiding contamination with cervical or urethral secretions.
- Oral/pharyngeal secretions – collected by firmly swabbing the affected mucosa.
- Urine samples – collected using the midstream (“clean-catch”) technique in sterile containers, preferably from the first morning urine.

All specimens are immediately transported to the laboratory in sterile containers, maintained at controlled temperature (2–8 °C), and processed within a maximum of 2 hours after collection to avoid contamination or reduced fungal viability.

Candifast Testing Protocol

The Candifast kit (International Microbio, France) includes microplates containing chromogenic media and biochemical substrates for *Candida* species identification, as well as wells impregnated with antifungal agents (fluconazole, itraconazole, ketoconazole, miconazole, amphotericin B, and 5-flucytosine).

1. A standardized fungal suspension (2 McFarland density) is prepared from each clinical specimen.

2. The suspension is inoculated into the microplate wells according to the manufacturer’s instructions.
3. Plates are incubated at 37 °C for 24–48 hours.
4. Species identification is performed based on specific chromogenic and biochemical changes characteristic of each *Candida* species.
5. Antifungal susceptibility testing is interpreted by assessing fungal growth or inhibition in the presence of antifungal agents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The study, conducted at the medical analysis laboratory S.C. Diaser in Oradea, included 150 clinical samples collected from patients with suspected fungal infections. Testing with the Candifast kit enabled the rapid identification of *Candida* species and the determination of their susceptibility to major antifungal agents.

The distribution of identified species showed that *Candida albicans* was predominant, being detected in 60% of samples. *Candida glabrata* accounted for approximately 15% of cases, particularly in patients with a history of prior antifungal treatment. *Candida tropicalis* was identified in 10% of cases, more frequently among immunocompromised patients.

Candida parapsilosis was isolated in 8% of samples, mainly associated with hospitalized patients and those carrying invasive medical devices. *Candida krusei* represented 4% of isolates, while other less common species, such as *C. lusitaniae* and *C. kefyr*, were detected in 3% of cases.

Table 1. Distribution of *Candida* species and antifungal susceptibility profile

<i>Candida</i> species	Isolation rate (%)	Susceptible to Fluconazole	Susceptible to Itraconazole	Susceptible to Ketoconazole	Susceptible to Amphotericin B	Remarks
<i>C. albicans</i>	60%	92%	90%	88%	100%	Predominant species, good antifungal susceptibility
<i>C. glabrata</i>	15%	55%	70%	68%	98%	High resistance to fluconazole
<i>C. tropicalis</i>	10%	75%	72%	70%	95%	Frequently associated with immunocompromised patients
<i>C. parapsilosis</i>	8%	80%	78%	76%	96%	Commonly implicated in nosocomial infections
<i>C. krusei</i>	4%	0% (rezistență naturală)	65%	60%	97%	intrinsically resistant to fluconazole
Other species	3%	70%	68%	65%	90%	Rare species (<i>C. lusitaniae</i> , <i>C. kefyr</i> , <i>C. dubliniensis</i>)

Fig. 1. Distribution of identified *Candida* specie

Antifungal susceptibility testing demonstrated good sensitivity of *Candida albicans* to azoles and amphotericin B,

increased resistance of *Candida glabrata* to fluconazole (observed in over 40% of isolates), and inherent resistance of *Candida krusei* to

fluconazole, confirmed through testing. Variable sensitivity to itraconazole and ketoconazole was observed among non-*albicans* species, while echinocandins consistently exhibited high efficacy.

These findings confirm that Candifast represents an effective method for the rapid and comprehensive diagnosis of candidiasis. The simultaneous identification of species and their antifungal susceptibility profiles provides a significant clinical advantage over traditional methods, which require longer processing times and additional procedures.

Consistent with existing literature, *Candida albicans* remains the predominant species. However, the notable proportion of non-*albicans* species (approximately 40% in this study) underscores the importance of accurate species differentiation. The presence of *C. glabrata* and *C. krusei*, both characterized by distinct resistance profiles, further emphasizes the necessity of antifungal susceptibility testing prior to treatment initiation.

A further advantage of this method lies in its practical applicability, as results can be obtained within 24–48 hours, enabling early implementation of targeted antifungal therapy and reducing the risk of resistance associated with empirical treatment. Limitations include higher costs compared to conventional methods and the requirement for specialized laboratory infrastructure to process the kits.

According to Fendrihan Sergiu in the study *Medical Challenges Nowadays Facing Vulvovaginal Candidiasis*, biochemical tests for *Candida* strain identification rely on the metabolism of specific substrates. The resulting

metabolic products serve as key markers for taxonomic identification of strains. This approach can also determine enzymatic activity, with each strain possessing a unique enzymatic profile, albeit not in an absolutely rigid manner.

In conclusion, Candifast has proven to be a valuable tool in mycological diagnostics, with the potential to enhance therapeutic decision-making and support the judicious use of antifungal agents.

CONCLUSIONS.

The study highlights that *Candida albicans* is the most frequently isolated species in fungal infections, followed by *C. glabrata*, *C. tropicalis*, and *C. parapsilosis*, each associated with specific risk factors. Rapid testing with Candifast proves valuable for species identification and optimization of antifungal therapy.

Candifast represents a rapid and efficient method for the identification of *Candida* species and antifungal susceptibility testing. *Candida albicans* exhibits good sensitivity to azoles and amphotericin B, whereas *Candida glabrata* and *Candida krusei* demonstrate increased resistance to fluconazole. Non-*albicans* species show variable sensitivity to itraconazole and ketoconazole but consistently respond to echinocandins.

Accurate species differentiation and susceptibility testing are essential for targeted antifungal therapy and reducing the development of resistance. The test provides results within 24–48 hours; however, higher costs and the requirement for specialized laboratory infrastructure remain limitations.

REFERENCES

1. Araj GF, et al. 1999. *Candifast Identifies Some Clinical Yeast Isolates, Needs To Be Used With Caution*. Lab Med, pp.30(3):199–201.
2. Arendrup MC, et al. 2011. *Echinocandin Susceptibility Testing of Candida Isolates Using CLSI and EUCAST Methods*. Antimicrob Agents Chemother.; pp. 55(5):2064–2069.
3. Axner-Elings M, et al. 2011. *Echinocandin Susceptibility Testing of Candida spp. Using Broth Microdilution and Etest Methods*. J Clin Microbiol.; pp. 49(6):2045–2049.
4. Akbar Z, et al. 2025. *Antifungal Resistance Among Candida Species in Cancer Patients*. J Fungi (Basel).;pp. 11(1):53.
5. Axner-Elings M, et al. 2011. *Echinocandin Susceptibility Testing of Candida spp. Using Broth Microdilution and Etest Methods*. J Clin Microbiol.;pp.49(6):2045–2049.
6. Bennett JE, et al. 2004. *Mechanism of Increased Fluconazole Resistance in Candida glabrata*. Antimicrob Agents Chemother.; pp. 48(3):1062–1068.
7. Castanheira M, et al. 2022. *Azole Resistance in Candida glabrata Clinical Isolates from Bloodstream Infections*. J Antimicrob Chemother.; pp.77(9):2356–2363.
8. Giri S, et al. 2014. *Evaluation of Antifungal Susceptibility Testing in Candida Isolates by Candifast and Disk-Diffusion Method*. Indian J Pathol Microbiol.; pp.57(4):554–557.

9. Giri S, et al. 2014. *Evaluation of Antifungal Susceptibility Testing in Candida Isolates by Candifast and Disk-Diffusion Method*. Indian J Pathol Microbiol.; pp.57(4):554–557.
10. Hautala T, et al. 2010. *Clinical Candida krusei Isolates Remain Susceptible During Extensive Exposure to Antifungal Drugs*. Med Mycol.; pp. 48(1):79–84.
11. Hautala T, et al. 2010. *Clinical Candida krusei Isolates Remain Susceptible During Extensive Exposure to Antifungal Drugs*. Med Mycol.; pp. 48(1):79–84.
12. Idelevich EA, et al. 2014. *Rapid Identification and Susceptibility Testing of Candida spp. from Positive Blood Cultures*. PLoS One.; pp.9(12):e114834.
13. Idelevich EA, et al. 2014. *Rapid Identification and Susceptibility Testing of Candida spp. from Positive Blood Cultures*. PLoS One.; pp. 9(12):e114834.
14. Lima R, et al. 2022. *The Emerging Threat of Antifungal-Resistant Candida Tropicalis*. Front Fungal Biol.; pp. 3:957021.
15. Liu W, et al. 2015. *Candida parapsilosis Resistance to Fluconazole*. Antimicrob Agents Chemother.;59(9):5385–5392.
16. Lima R, et al. 2022. *The Emerging Threat of Antifungal-Resistant Candida Tropicalis*. Front Fungal Biol.; pp.3:957021.
17. Meng L, et al. 2025. *Epidemiology, Risk Factors, and Antifungal Susceptibility of Candida Species in China*. BMC Infect Dis.; pp. 25:11445
18. Meng L, et al. 2025. *Epidemiology, Risk Factors, and Antifungal Susceptibility of Candida Species in China*. BMC Infect Dis.; pp. 25:11445
19. Meng L, et al. 2025. *Epidemiology, Risk Factors, and Antifungal Susceptibility of Candida Species in China*. BMC Infect Dis.; pp. 25:11445.
20. Osoba AO. 2003. *Candidemia and the Susceptibility Pattern of Candida Species in a Nigerian Hospital*. J Med Microbiol.; pp. 52(4):345–348
21. Popovici R, et al. 2018. *Identification of the Fungi Through Candifast*. CAB International
22. Pfaller MA, et al. 2007. *Candida krusei, a Multidrug-Resistant Opportunistic Fungal Pathogen*. J Clin Microbiol.; pp. 45(4):1153–1161.
23. Ramirez-Garcia A, et al. 2021 *Candida parapsilosis Virulence and Antifungal Resistance Mechanisms*. J Fungi (Basel); pp.7(11):907.
24. Zheng L, et al. 2024. *Parallel Evolution of Fluconazole Resistance and Tolerance in Candida glabrata*. Front Cell Infect Microbiol.; pp. 14:1456907.
25. Wiederhold NP. 2021. *Antifungal Susceptibility Testing: A Primer for Clinicians*. Open Forum Infect Dis.; pp. 8(11):ofab444.

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF ARTISANAL APPLE CIDER VINEGAR WITH HONEY AND SOME NATURAL ADDITIVES

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Artisanal apple cider vinegar, obtained through traditional slow fermentation methods, is appreciated not only for its complex flavor, but also for its potential health benefits, highlighted both in the specialized literature and in traditional medicine. Fruit-infused variants, such as quince or *Prunus laurocerasus* fruits, add additional nutritional value, through their high content of antioxidants, vitamins and bioactive compounds. This product diversification responds to the increasing demand for functional food products, which combine taste with biological functionality. The aim of this study was to obtain artisanal apple cider vinegar with honey in the classic version, as well as infused with quince, respectively *Prunus laurocerasus* extract, using traditional fermentation methods, characterizing the samples obtained from a physico-chemical and biochemical point of view, and finally evaluating the impact of natural additives on the final quality of the product.

Keywords: vinegar, apple, honey, quince, *Prunus laurocerasus*

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INTRODUCTION

Artisanal apple cider vinegar, obtained through traditional slow fermentation methods, is appreciated not only for its complex flavor, but also for its potential health benefits, highlighted both in the specialized literature and in traditional medicine. Fruit-infused variants, such as quince or *Prunus laurocerasus* fruits, add additional nutritional value, through their high content of antioxidants, vitamins and bioactive compounds. This product diversification responds to the increasing demand for functional food products that combine taste with biological functionality.

Depending on the raw material used, different types of vinegar can be obtained: wine vinegar, cider vinegar, berry and other fruit vinegar obtained, alcohol vinegar, grain vinegar (Dabija and Hatnean, 2014).

Depending on the geographical location, the assortments vary, being strongly influenced by culture, traditions and available raw materials. Thus, we can find assortments such as: whey vinegar, in Europe where the processed raw material is deproteinized whey and, if necessary, enriched with lactose to stimulate alcoholic fermentation (Parrondo et al., 2009), honey vinegar in Europe, America and Africa, kombucha (tea and sugar vinegar) in Russia, Japan and China, rice vinegar in East and Southeast China, sugarcane vinegar in France and the USA, banana vinegar in Southeast Asia, and various other assortments (Boonsupa, 2021).

Fermented foods are recognized for its beneficial properties on the human body (Mukherjee et al., 2024). Recent studies have highlighted the beneficial effect of vinegar consumption. Apple cider vinegar is rich in bioactive substances, such as phenols, flavonoids, acetic acid, having positive effects on the body, including antioxidant, antimicrobial, antidiabetic, antitumor and antiinflammatory properties (Kandyliis et al., 2021). It supports the digestive process, relieves fatigue and balances appetite (Guine et al., 2021; Ling et al., 2019).

Studies conducted by researchers have confirmed the following benefits of vinegar consumption:

- alpha-amylase involved in the transformation of starch into glucose is temporarily inactivated by the acetic acid in vinegar, thus flattening the glucose curve (Santos et al., 2019);

- pre-prandial vinegar consumption for three months led to a reduction in visceral fat as well as a decrease in triglycerides (Kondo et al., 2009);

- regular consumption of apple cider vinegar influences glycosylated hemoglobin values in patients suffering from type 2 diabetes (Johnston et al., 2009);

- in the case of a strict diet applied identically in 2 groups, respondents who consumed vinegar lost 5 kg, compared to those who only followed the diet and lost 3 kg (Khezri et al., 2018);

- stimulates the acceleration of glycogen production at the muscle level, thus better assimilating glucose, and at the DNA level

stimulates fat burning in mitochondria (Santos et al., 2019);

-supplementation with vinegar increases satiety after consuming bakery products and decreases glycemic peaks and insulin response in healthy individuals (Ostman et al., 2005);

-apple cider vinegar is considered superior to other supplements with a thermogenic effect, being more effective in burning fat (Santos et al., 2019);

- vinegar consumption is associated with the recovery of ovulation function in women suffering from polycystic ovary syndrome (Wu et al., 2013).

The main objective of this study was to obtain artisanal apple cider vinegar with honey in the classic version, as well as infused with *Prunus laurocerasus* extract respectively with quince, using traditional fermentation methods, characterizing the obtained samples from a physico-chemical and biochemical point of view.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research methodology included the preparation of raw materials, fermentation processes, as well as physico-chemical and biochemical analysis of products.

Raw materials

-Golden delicious apples were purchased in November 2024, from a local producer from Oradea, Bihor County, Romania. Fresh apple juice was obtained from apples

-*Prunus laurocerasus* concentrate was obtained from *Prunus laurocerasus* fruits macerated in a 1:1 solution of 96% ethanol and drinking water, after which it was stored for 6 months in a room protected from sunlight and with a constant temperature of 17°C. After this maceration period, the fruits were pressed and filtered. The obtained solution was concentrated using a Heidolph Laborota 4010 digital rotavapor, at a temperature of 45°C, for 45 minutes.

-Quince from the local market. The quince fruits were grated.

-Polyfloral honey from a local producer.

From these raw materials, 3 mixtures were prepared according to the following recipes:

900 ml of apple juice was mixed with 3.6% local polyfloral honey and distributed in 3 Erlenmeyer flasks.

After dosing, 3 samples were obtained:

-sample 1 (AV): classic apple vinegar with honey, without other fruit additions.

-sample 2 (AQV): apple vinegar with honey and addition of 10% quince.

-sample 3 (APLV): apple vinegar with honey and addition of 10% non-alcoholic concentrated extract of *Prunus laurocerasus*.

After preparing the samples, they were dosed according to the proposed recipe and mixed by shaking, in Erlenmayer flasks.

Fermentation processes

Fig.1. Fermentation processes

The *alcoholic fermentation* process lasted 3 weeks, during which the concentration of soluble dry matter was checked to monitor the progress and completion of the process (Fig.1.I-III)

For the *acetic fermentation*, the cider samples obtained from the alcoholic fermentation were filtered on Watman No. 1 paper and then with 0.22 μm membrane filters. The pH was between 4.42 and 4.52.

The acetic bacteria strains used came from the commercial apple cider vinegar that we used as a starter culture. To stimulate the acetic fermentation, a carrier consisting of sterilized wood chips was used.

The equipment used for the acetic fermentation is shown in Fig.1.IV and consisted of 3 bioreactor units provided at the top with a closing cap.

Each cap was equipped with an air inlet crossed by a glass rod provided at the top with a 0.22 μm filter and at the bottom with a 100 μm air diffuser. This diffuser allows the dispersion of air in the form of small bubbles and avoids the coalescence of the bubbles. The reactor incorporated a top exhaust of the gas flow through a 0.45 μm filter. O_2 saturation conditions were ensured by a constant flow air pump, which provided for each bioreactor an air flow of 1.2 l/min. Agitation was achieved by placing the reactors on an orbital shaker at a stirring rate of 120 rpm.

The following physico-chemical and biochemical methods were performed:

- *Total soluble substances (TSS)*, refractometric method, using a digital refractometer (KRUS, AR 2008 model, Germany).

- *pH* potentiometric determination using Crison pH meter.

-*Electrical conductivity (EC)* potentiometric method, using HACH Sensilon378 multiparameter meter.

-*Total acidity (TA)* was determined by titration with 0.1 N NaOH (STAS 157-86).

-*Total polyphenols (TP)* – Folin Ciocâlteu spectrophotometric method (Thaipong et al 2006)

-*Total flavonoid (TF)* – spectrophotometric method (Atanassova et al. 2011).

-*Total antioxidant activity (AA)* using FRAP – spectrophotometric method, Benzie and Strain 1996).

Spectrophotometric determinations were made with a Shimadzu UV Mini 1240 spectrophotometer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results obtained after performing analysis for studying the vinegar samples were inserted in Table 1 and 2 and Fig.2, 3 and 4.

Table 1

Mean values for Physico-chemical parameters

sample	TSS (°Brix)	pH	TA (g acetic acid%)	E.C. mS
AV	4.82	3.67	3.89	3.81
AQV	4.02	3.69	3.67	3.78
APLV	4.32	3.68	3.89	4.27

Fig 2. Graphic representation of mean values for physico-chemical parameters

The artisanal vinegar samples have a SUS value between 4.02–4.82°Brix, which suggests a higher residual sugar content in these products.

-*pH* of the artisanal samples is relatively similar (3.67-3.60)

-*Total acidity*, expressed in grams of acetic acid per 100 ml of vinegar, in the artisanal vinegar samples had an acidity between 3.67 and 3.89 g acetic acid%, a lower value than that of commercial vinegar where the standard value is 5g acetic acid%. This may be due to incomplete acetic fermentation under laboratory conditions, where the fermentation conditions are much more difficult to control.

-The highest *electrical conductivity* was recorded in the apple cider vinegar sample with honey and *Prunus laurocerasus* extract (4.27 mS), closely followed by the other 2 artisanal vinegar samples (3.78-3.81mS),

In general, in the case of food, electrical conductivity is directly proportional to the content of total minerals. This was highlighted by (Ousaaïd et al., 2022) following the comparative analysis between artisanal and industrial apple cider vinegar. They found that artisanal vinegar had a higher content of mineral salts and higher electrical conductivity, compared to the industrial one.

Thus, we can say that:

-AV from artisanal production had the highest sugar content with moderate acidity;

-AQV has a balanced profile, rich in sugars and minerals with a medium pH and acidity;

-APLV has a good combination of sugar and salt content.

Analyzing the data in table 2 and fig. 3, the following is observed:

- APLV has the highest content of polyphenolic compounds (8.02 mg GAE/100ml) followed by AQV and AV (6.99 and 6.34mg GAE/100ml).

- Flavonoids are in higher quantity in AQV (40.16 mg Que/100ml), followed by APLV (35.16 mg Que/100ml) and AV (29.69mg Que/100ml).

Comparing the results obtained from the determination of AA (Tab 2 and fig 4), with the FRAP method, the highest AA was recorded in the APLV concentrate (0.96 mM FeSO₄), followed by AQV (0.95 mM FeSO₄), confirming previous observations suggesting a superior antioxidant activity, associated with a rich content in bioactive compounds.

Table 2

Average values for absorbances and concentrations of biochemical parameters

Sample	TP		TF		AA	
	Abs	GAE mg/100 ml	Abs.	Que mg/100 ml	Abs.	mM FeSO ₄
AV	0.63	6.34	0.28	29.69	2.16	0.94
AQV	0.69	6.99	0.38	40.16	2.19	0.95
APLV	0.79	8.02	0.34	35.16	2.2	0.96

Fig.3. Graphic representation of mean values for Total polyphenol and flavonoid content

Fig.4. Graphic representation of mean values for Total antioxidant activity FRAP method

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the results obtained from this study prove that following the application of controlled laboratory conditions, quality products with superior nutritional and functional values were obtained.

The advantages of artisanal vinegar with the addition of apple, quince or *Prunus Laurocerasus* concentrate consist of: high content of polyphenols, flavonoids and mineral salts, with antioxidant benefits and potential positive effects on health.

The integration of quinces and *Prunus laurocerasus* concentrate in apple vinegar with honey supports the current trend of producing functional foods, which contribute to the health of consumers.

For artisanal production, more rigorous control of acetic fermentation conditions is recommended to increase acidity while preserving nutritional benefits. It is recommended to continue acetic fermentation until an acetic concentration of at least 5g pure acetic acid/100ml is obtained, in order to comply with the legislative requirements.

REFERENCES

- Atanassova M. et al. (2011). Total Phenolic And Total Flavonoid Contents, Antioxidant Capacity And Biological Contaminants In Medicinal Herbs. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/261635307>.
- Boonsupa, W. (2021). The Chemical Fermentation Process Properties, Bioactive Compounds, and Health Benefits of Fruit Vinegars in Pilot-Scale in Thailand. *Walailak Journal of Science and Technology (WJST)*, 18, 10402. <https://doi.org/10.48048/wjst.2021.10402>
- Benzie I.F., Strain J., 1996, The Ferric Reducing Ability of Plasma (FRAP) as a Measure of "Antioxidant Power": the FRAP Assay. *Anal. Biochem.*, 239, pp70-76.
- Dabija, A., & Hatnean, C. (2014). Study concerning the quality of apple vinegar obtained through classical method. *Journal of Agroalimentary Processes and Technologies*, 20(4), 304-310.
- Guine et al. (2021). Apple Fermented Products: An Overview of Technology, Properties and Health Effects. *Processes*, 9(2), 223. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr9020223>
- Johnston, C. S., White, A. M., & Kent, S. M. (2009). Preliminary evidence that regular vinegar ingestion favorably influences hemoglobin A1c values in individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Diabetes Research and Clinical Practice*, 84(2), e15-e17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.diabres.2009.02.005>
- Kandylis et al. (2021). Health Promoting Properties of Cereal Vinegars. *Foods*, 10(2), 344.
- Khezri, S. S., Saidpour, A., Hosseinzadeh, N., & Amiri, Z. (2018). Beneficial effects of Apple Cider Vinegar on weight management, Visceral Adiposity Index and lipid profile in overweight or obese subjects receiving restricted calorie diet: A randomized clinical trial. *Journal of Functional Foods*, 43, 95-102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jff.2018.02.003>
- Kondo, T., Kishi, M., Fushimi, T., Ugajin, S., & Kaga, T. (2009). Vinegar intake reduces body weight, body fat mass, and serum triglyceride levels in obese Japanese subjects. *Bioscience, Biotechnology, and Biochemistry*, 73(8), 1837-1843. <https://doi.org/10.1271/bbb.90231>
- Ling, J. W. A., Mun, S. L., Fazry, S., Lazim, A. M., & Lim, S. J. (2019). Health Benefits of Vinegars. In *Advances in Vinegar Production*. CRC Press.
- Mukherjee et al. (2024). Fermented foods and gastrointestinal health: Underlying mechanisms. *Nature Reviews, Gastroenterology&HEpatology*, 248-266. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41575-023-00869-x>
- Ostman, E., Granfeldt, Y., Persson, L., & Björck, I. (2005). Vinegar supplementation lowers glucose and insulin responses and increases satiety after a bread meal in healthy subjects. *European Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 59(9), 983-988. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.ejcn.1602197>
- Ousaaid D. et al. (2022). The Nutritional and Antioxidant Potential of Artisanal and Industrial Apple Vinegars and Their Ability to Inhibit Key Enzymes Related to Type 2 Diabetes In Vitro. *Molecules*, 27(2), 567. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules27020567>

- Parrondo, J., García, L., & Díaz, M. (2009). Vinegars of the World pp. 273–288. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-88-470-0866-3_17
- Santos, H. O., de Moraes, W. M. A. M., da Silva, G. A. R., Prestes, J., & Schoenfeld, B. J. (2019). Vinegar (acetic acid) intake on glucose metabolism: A narrative review. *Clinical Nutrition ESPEN*, 32, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clnesp.2019.05.008>
- Thaipong, K., Boonprakob, U., Crosby, K., Cisneros-Zevallos, L., & Hawkins Byrne, D. (2006). Comparison of ABTS, DPPH, FRAP, and ORAC assays for estimating antioxidant activity from guava fruit extracts. *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis*, 19(6–7), 669–675. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfca.2006.01.003>
- Wu et al. (2021). Metabolic profile of main organic acids and its regulatory mechanism in solid-state fermentation of Chinese cereal vinegar. *Food Research International*, 145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2021.110400>
- National Standard STAS 157-86

CHANGES THAT OCCUR DURING BAKING ON THE STRUCTURE OF CHEMICALLY LEAVENED DOUGH

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REVIEW ARTICLE

Abstract

The baking of the thin dough was carried out in a pilot oven under various conditions, allowing the study of macroscopic changes in relation to physical and biochemical changes during the baking process. The influence of baking parameters (temperature, humidity and air velocity) on macroscopic and microscopic changes was investigated, together with variations (temperature and humidity levels, heating and drying rates) of product variables. The main changes observed during the baking of the biscuits were: the development of a partially open porous structure, associated with a reduction in density, drying and surface colouring. The structural changes were due to the evaporation of water and gas bubbles produced by the decomposition of the chemical leavening agents used. The expansion stopped due to the exhaustion of the chemical leavening agents and the percolation of water vapour at appropriate temperatures. The setting of the biscuit structure was not related to thermal aggregation of proteins (which started at 85 °C) or to limited damage to starch granules at temperatures below 100 °C. The setting apparently occurred during the cooling period, when the molten sugars undergo a glass transition. The colouring of the biscuit surface and a subsequent decrease in brightness were correlated with reduced sugar consumption in Maillard reactions.

Keywords: biscuit, coloring, expansion, temperature.

INTRODUCTION

Shortcrust pastry is generally composed of three main ingredients (flour, sugar and fat) and contains only a small amount of water (<20% g.a.). The biochemical and physicochemical reactions in biscuit dough during baking are very complex, involving protein denaturation, loss of starch granular structure, fat melting, Maillard reactions and browning, dough expansion by water evaporation and the production and thermal expansion of gases. Expansion, a relevant event in texture formation, is limited by the rheological properties of the dough, which depend on the behavior and interactions of its components, and on the solubility of gas in the continuous phase. Two main mechanisms have been proposed, which may be complementary depending on the dough composition. The first, based on calorimetric studies (Cadough differential scanning calorimetry, DSC), considers that dough properties are essentially governed by the phase transition of a gluten network. The second suggests that the viscoelastic properties of tender dough are due to a co-continuous process, which includes a dispersed or continuous fat system, a fat-free phase and the suspension of flour particles in a

sucrose solution. In both cases, the study of interactions between all dough components is relevant. Various studies have considered the structural changes that occur in starch (the main component of dough) over a wide range of water contents^{3–5}. DSC has been used to determine the behavior of starch and the influence of ingredients or other components of flour in excess water or with a water content above 60% (c.a.)^{6–9}. However, few results have addressed the influence of ingredients with a water content below 60% (c.a.), typical of biscuit dough.

Although it is commonly assumed that starch is not gelatinized after short dough baking (due to water limitation), intermediate states of damaged starch, either swollen granules or amylase leaching, can affect dough rheological properties as well as starch granule interactions with other components during baking. The role of proteins has often been investigated due to the gluten network in thin dough. In fact, the apparent viscosity of dough is reduced after the glass transition of gluten polymers, rather than increasing by their aggregation. This may be due to the high aggregation temperature (above 80 °C at 20% moisture content) or the influence of sugars on the gluten T_g. The process is also made more complex by fat melting, which

occurs between 15 and 40 °C, depending on the fat polymorphism and the proportion of solid fat. Finally, for reasons of simplicity, studies on biscuit baking modeling actually focus on predicting volumetric characteristics (volume, color) and often neglect the physicochemical changes of the dough by limiting the baking step to heat transfer in a homogeneous material. Therefore, the structural changes of the dough must be studied during baking to consider their relationship with macroscopic changes.

The aim of the present study was to determine the changes that occur during baking in terms of size, surface color and moisture, in relation to the concomitant physicochemical changes of the dough components (starch, protein, sugar, water).

The baking experiments were carried out with a large-scale pilot oven, in a range covering the typical conditions of the bakery industry. The dough recipe used for this study produced a typical French biscuit, the most significant characteristics of which were thickness and color. This cookie is clearly different from sugar cookies, where the spread is essential.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Dough preparation and baking:

All ingredients were supplied by LU (La Haye-Fouassière, France). The flour was a mixture containing 8.8% protein (d.b.) and 14.8% water (total weight). The doughs were mixed in a HOBART mixer for 5 minutes. After standing for 30 minutes in a room at 20 °C and then for 30 minutes in a room at 26 °C, the dough was rolled out in a sheeter and two sheeters (R-Tech, Wigan) to obtain a sheet with a thickness of 2 mm. The dough pieces were cut with a dough cutter (68.8×55.4 mm). The experiments were carried out in a static oven (Sasib bakery, Verona, Italy) with forced convection of hot and humid air. Fourteen pieces of dough were placed on a circular wire mesh baking tray, which was rotated to improve baking homogeneity (size, color, and moisture). Since the last two parameters were set and controlled within the air conditioning system, the values were approximate for the air velocity and humidity near the dough pieces. The chosen conditions were based on a full experimental design of 23 degrees, with a central point, taking into account the spread of thermal kinetics between the extreme curves.

Real-time measurements

The temperature of the dough was measured with type K thermocouples placed inside two of the 14 dough pieces in the baking tray. These were positioned 2 mm above the top surface of the tray and recorded every 5 seconds. The reported value is the average temperature for both dough pieces during two experiments, with a maximum standard deviation of 4 °C. The variations in dough dimensions were monitored by a color video camera (CCD SONY 711 XP, focal length 100 mm, extension lens 15 mm) positioned in front of the oven door, approximately 60 cm from the baking plate. A 300 W halogen spot was placed directly above the camera, and a reflective screen was positioned behind the dough piece to enhance the contrast between the sample and the surroundings. The camera allowed monitoring the growth of the sample during baking, and the digitized images were stored at a rate of 5 seconds. Since the calibration and conversion of the digitized images resulted in variations in sample thickness over time, the thickness was calculated as the average of 10 measurements per biscuit. Thickness was not measured during the 15 seconds required to place the baking tray and chamber in front of the oven. The colour and browning of the biscuit surface were determined with the CIE L*a*b* colorimetric system (Chroma Meter CR-300 Tristimulus colorimeter, Minolta, Carriere sur Seine, France). The luminance value (L*), which includes lightness, and chroma [defined by $(a^2+b^2)^{1/2}$] including hue, were indicative of the colour of the biscuit surface. Measurements at 0, 1, 1.5, 2, 3, 4 and 5 minutes were made at three locations on the surface of four partially baked biscuits. The values reported are the mean of the 12 measurement points (standard deviation 3.0).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The variations of biscuit temperature and moisture content as a function of baking time are shown in Fig. 1 for the different baking conditions. Three stages can be identified in these curves. The first (0–60 s) is characterized by a rapid temperature increase, with a maximum rate at the inflection point, varying between 37 °C/min (condition no. 1) and 150

°C/min (condition no. 4) at higher humidity (400 g water/kg dry air). The higher value obtained in this case can be attributed to the heat generated by the condensation of water vapor on the cold dough pieces at the beginning of baking, which modified the heat transport. The second stage corresponds to a slower, more linear increase in temperature between 6 and 16 °C/min. Starting at 95 s, the temperature of the biscuits increases according to the air temperature, regardless of other aerodynamic conditions. For lower temperature conditions (#1 and 2), this stage lasts until the end of baking, but ends at approximately 170 s for higher temperature conditions (#3 and 4). During the second stage, the considerable heat is 4). During the second stage, the considerable heat is the heat of evaporation of water is high.

The third stage occurs after 170 s, when almost all the water has evaporated. The temperature increase becomes higher for higher temperature conditions (300 °C): 22 °C/min and 43 °C/min for #3 and #4, respectively. The higher heating rate, under higher humidity conditions (#4), can be attributed to variations in water content. The higher the oven temperature, the faster the decrease in water content. For a low temperature (#1), the moisture content decreases almost linearly (2.6%/min). Under other conditions, the classical shape of the drying curve is obtained, with a final water content of approximately 1%.

Furthermore, for the same conditions of oven temperature (300 °C) and air velocity (21 m/s), an increase in air humidity induces a faster decrease in the water content of the biscuits (conditions no. 3 and no. 4). Injecting water vapor into the oven helps to accelerate the drying rate of the biscuits. This may be due to the fact that water vapor modifies the properties of the thermophysical properties of the air, which can thus increase the external heat and mass transfer coefficients. The water vapor would then limit the formation of the crust, which could reduce the water loss from the biscuits. Finally, under high humidity conditions, condensation can occur at the beginning of baking, thus creating a larger temperature gradient between the surface and the center of the product and increasing the

corresponding internal mass transfer.

Macroscopic changes

The final product in this study was characterized by volume criteria, which partially correspond to those defined by the manufacturer and which are usually measured after baking at the end of industrial production lines. These include brightness and chroma (which take into account the surface color), size and moisture. Since thickness is the most sensitive of the size variables, our study focused on this parameter. The surface color of a baked product is, together with texture and taste, a criterion for consumer acceptance. Brightness values increase from 72.7 to a maximum (80.6–82.5), which only occurs after the oven temperature is raised. The surface of the biscuits then darkens in color, the brightness decreasing in relation to the increase in oven temperature. At the same time, chroma first decreases from 25.6 to values between 17.6 and 21.9. Its subsequent behavior is complex, depending on the oven temperature level. Thus, the general staining kinetics involves two steps. First, the increase in brightness and the decrease in chroma correspond to a whitening of the biscuit surface. Two phenomena can explain this behavior often encountered during food drying: the migration of water to the biscuit surface and/or the change in the surface state due to the lifting of the sample. This stage is followed by a colouring process corresponding to blackening and the development of a more saturated shade. At 300 °C the considerable decrease in brightness and chroma is concomitant with a dark browning of the biscuit surface after 2.5 minutes, which produces a product unacceptable to consumers. These results allow the quantification of the browning of biscuits induced by biochemical reactions and activated by heat treatment (Maillard reactions, caramelization). The variation of the sample thickness as a function of the baking time reveals two stages: first, the biscuit rises rapidly (55–115 s), as the oven temperature and air velocity are high, before collapsing to higher values (4.7–5.4 mm) as the maximum thickness is reached early. The comparison of the obtained values shows that the maximum thickness occurs when the temperature is between 80 and 98 °C. This

means that the temperature of the biscuits is not the only factor responsible for the variations in the thickness of the biscuits during baking. Based on these macroscopic observations, three major changes can be defined during baking: 1. an increase in the thickness of the biscuits due to the production of gases from chemical leavening agents and the evaporation of water; 2. a decrease in the weight of the product due to drying, resulting in a significant decrease in the density of the product and the development of an open porous structure; and 3. browning of the biscuit surface (low brightness, increased chroma), possibly due to non-enzymatic browning (Maillard reactions) involving the interaction of reducing sugars with proteins, but also possibly due to starch dextrinization and sugar caramelization.

CONCLUSIONS

During baking, three major physicochemical changes occur that affect the dough components. First, there is a decrease in protein solubility, corresponding to a subsequent thermal aggregation, which starts at a temperature above 85 °C. In our study, no direct relationship could be established between the insoluble protein content and a macroscopic development, such as the end of the biscuit development phase. Second, starch destructuring occurs essentially in the first third of the baking period and is limited by the drying of the biscuits. Third, a decrease in the reducing sugar content occurs in the last two thirds of the baking period, which is correlated with the surface color. Although well known for biscuit doughs, the significant collapse following the rising stage has not been previously reported for shortcrust pastry. The assumed general rule for biscuit expansion is a linear diametrical increase (spreading) and a slow and uniform increase in thickness until the point where the size is established. In our experiments, the maximum thickness was reached in the temperature range 80–98 °C for all baking conditions.

The end of the rise stage can be attributed to a significant increase in the viscosity of the dough matrix, which prevents further expansion. This occurs in the same temperature range of 80–100 °C as that in

which protein aggregation is triggered. However, the collapse stage (observed for all baking conditions) indicates that the dough matrix has not become sufficiently rigid to overcome the effect of gas loss or permeability increase. Currently, no experimental device is suitable for monitoring the permeability of thin dough with respect to the humidity and temperature dynamics representative of baking. However, in the last decade, major rheological variations have been studied in various works on the influence of phase transitions on the mechanical properties of the components. Thus, during baking of sugar-rich shortcrust pastry, the expansion period is followed by a marked collapse.

REFERENCES

- Slade, L. and Levine, H. Influence of the glassy and rubbery states on the thermal, mechanical, and structural properties of doughs and baked products. In 'Dough rheology and baked product texture', (H. Faridi and J.M. Faubion, eds), Van Nostrand Reinhold, New York (1989); Baltsavias, A., Jurgens, A. and van Vliet, T. Rheological properties of short doughs at small deformation. *Journal of Cereal Science* 26 (1997); Roos, Y.H. Food components and polymers. In 'Phase transitions in foods' (S.L. Taylor, ed.), Academic Press, San Diego (1995); Sablani, S.S., Marcotte, M., Baik, O.D. and Castaigne, F. Modeling of simultaneous heat and water transport in the baking process. *Lebensmittel-Wissenschaft und -Technologie* 31 (1998); Chevallier, S. Modifications structurales des pâtes biscuitières au cours de la cuisson. Ph.D. thesis, ENSIA Massy (1998); Planchot, V., Colonna, P. and Saulnier, L. Dosage des glucides et des amylases. In 'Guide pratique d'analyses dans les industries des céréales', (B. Godon and W. Loisel, eds), Lavoisier Tec&Doc, Paris (1997); Chevallier, S. and Colonna, P. Thermal analysis of protein-starch interactions at low moisture contents. *Sciences des Aliments* 19 (1999); Chevallier, S., Colonna, P., Della Valle, G. and Bule'on A. Physicochemical behaviours of sugars, lipids, and, gluten in short dough and biscuit. *Journal of Agricultural Food Chemistry* 48 (2000)

A STUDY ON PUMPKIN DEHYDRATION DEPENDING ON DEHYDRATION METHOD AND PRESENTATION FORM

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Abstract

Dehydration is the technological process by which the natural water content of food products is reduced to a level that prevents the activity of microorganisms, without destroying the tissues or depreciating the nutritional value of the products being dehydrated.

Dehydration is an economically advantageous preservation method, as it significantly reduces the volume of food, thus optimizing storage space. By reducing weight and volume, dehydration contributes to reducing the costs associated with packaging, storing and transporting products.

Pumpkin is an important ingredient in many traditional Romanian culinary dishes, especially in the autumn season, being used in the preparation of cream soups, purees, jams and other culinary specialties. Pumpkin seeds, consumed raw or roasted, are a popular and nutritious snack.

Pumpkin can be preserved for consumption all year round, frozen in the form of cubes or puree, or sterilized in jars, grated in the form of noodles, ready to be used in various dishes.

Pumpkin can also be processed through dehydration in the form of chips or cubes and can be an alternative consumption for a healthy diet, by replacing sugary treats in children's and adults' diets.

The study on the dehydration of pumpkin was carried out under laboratory conditions in two types of devices: a microwave oven and a household dehydrator. Two types of pumpkin were analyzed for dehydration: round and elongated or pear-shaped, divided into slices and cubes.

Key Words: dehydration, preservation, organoleptic characteristics, pumpkin

INTRODUCTION

Drying is one of the traditional methods of preserving food products, by eliminating a certain part of the total water contained. The removal of water from products can be achieved through several operations, depending on their initial physical state such as: mechanical, physico-chemical, and thermal operations.

Drying is a thermal operation, which is carried out with heat and substance transfer, to remove part of the liquid contained in food masses (water), using a moisture-entraining agent, which simultaneously provides the thermal energy necessary for the process (Banu Constantin and all, 2007).

The elimination of moisture is achieved up to a percentage level, at which the development of microorganisms is not allowed and which ensures the preservation of food products. The maximum water content that ensures the preservation and storage of products depends on their nature. Thus, for certain fruits, the humidity must be reduced to 18-20%, and for other products, the humidity must be 2-4%. (Popovici Mariana, 2012).

The main purpose of dehydration is to preserve products for a long time, extending the shelf life of foods by reducing water activity below 0.7.

Dehydration of fruits and vegetables has two effects: it ensures the stability of the product over time without the need for complex installations or special packaging, and it reduces the volume of products, resulting in smaller storage spaces and a reduction in sales and transport costs (Nour Violeta, 2014).

The most widespread drying method is convection at atmospheric pressure (hot air drying). During hot air drying, this is the vector that supplies the product surface with energy and also the vector for removing water vapor (Banu C., 2008).

In microwave drying, heat is generated inside the product through the interaction between the chemical constituents of the food and radiofrequency energy (915MHz and 2450

MHz). When the material is subjected to microwave energy, heat is generated inside the product through molecular excitation.

Most vegetables and fruits with large volumes are divided into cubes, slices, noodles, which favors dehydration by reducing the duration of production. (Dumitru Beceanu, Adrian Chira, 2003).

Scalding the raw material is an operation preceding dehydration. The main purpose of scalding vegetables is to inactivate all enzymes and especially oxidative enzymes, which are the most heat-resistant. Scalding destroys the vegetative forms of microorganisms and eliminates air from the tissues, which has the effect of: fixing, maintaining and even accentuating the color of the finished product; fixing and preserving vitamin C during subsequent processes; dehydration time is reduced because it helps accelerate the subsequent evaporation of water from tissues.

At the end of the dehydration period, after cooling for 2-3 minutes, the degree of dehydration is checked, when the dehydrated slices or cubes must be hard, break when bent, have a glassy and transparent appearance in section and a humidity of 8%. (Mănescu S., 1973).

The products obtained through dehydration differ from the raw material from which they come, following the removal of excess water, by: the concentration of the dry substance, a consequence that causes the volume to decrease and the volumetric weight to increase, the energy-plastic value to increase per unit weight; the change in the ratio between the main components of the dry substance; the quantitative decrease of some, the increase of others, the partial disappearance, if not total, of some components and the formation of others; the state of the membranes and cellular components that are externalized by the limits of the rehydration capacity (Ion Potec and all., 1983).

The drying process of fruits and vegetables takes place in two distinct stages. In the first few hours, the evaporation process takes place with the highest intensity, during which free water is eliminated, after which drying proceeds very slowly.

In the first period, the humidity on the surface of the product is higher than the hygroscopic humidity. If the drying conditions

do not change, the drying rate for all products remains constant and unchanged, and as a result it is called the period of constant drying rate. In the second period, the drying rate is gradually reduced, proportional to the reduction in product humidity, which is why it is called the period of decreasing drying rate (Segal Brad and all., 1984)

At the beginning of the dehydration process, when the humidity is still high, evaporation of water from the surface of the product occurs by external diffusion, the more intense the evaporation surface, the higher the temperature and the air circulation speed. Simultaneously, the process of internal diffusion begins, the movement of water from the inside to the outside, as a direct consequence of the difference in osmotic pressure caused by the different concentration of soluble substances in the cell sap inside and on the surface of the product. Thus, the homogenous spread of humidity is achieved in all layers subjected to dehydration. If the speed of external diffusion from the product surface exceeds that of internal diffusion, the phenomenon of scalding occurs, which requires the regulation of the temperature and relative humidity of the air (Dumitru Beceanu, A.Chira, I.Paşca, 2008).

Pumpkin is a valuable food option for people following a healthy diet and weight control. With an energy value of approximately 22 kcal per 100 grams, it falls into the category of foods with low calorie density, while providing a diverse range of essential nutrients. The high-water content (approximately 91.8 g per 100 g) also supports the inclusion of pumpkin in diets aimed at weight loss (USDA FoodData Central, 2023).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For the study on pumpkin dehydration, we analyzed two types of pumpkins: round and elongated or pear-shaped, which were dehydrated in the form of slices and cubes, in two devices: microwave oven and household dehydrator.

The samples taken for the study were weighed, and the weight of each sample subjected to analysis was 100g. The analyzed samples were placed on baking paper and introduced into the dehydration spaces.

For pumpkins prepared for dehydration, according to the operations presented above, the following data are drawn:

- initial weight of pumpkins;
- weight of cleaned pumpkins;
- weight of pumpkins put to dehydration, which was 100g;
- final weight of dehydrated pumpkin samples;

From the moment the drying process begins, the samples being studied are weighed every 30 minutes for samples in the household dehydrator and every 15 minutes for samples in the microwave oven.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the study of pumpkin dehydration,

we determined the following: the losses resulting from the inedible parts during the cleaning process; the weight of the analyzed products and the time required to remove water from the products, starting from the initial weight of 100 g for each sample and reaching their final weight; the organoleptic properties of round and elongated or pear-shaped pumpkins dehydrated in the electric oven and household dehydrator and the total and percentage of water loss during the dehydration process.

1. Inferring the inedible part data

To determine the inedible part removed during cleaning, we weighed both previously named pumpkin varieties before and after cleaning. The results obtained were recorded in Table 1.

Table 1

Assortment of pumpkins	Initial quantity g	Quantity after cleaning g	Inedible part	
			g	%
Round pumpkin	1045.60	785.23	260.37	24.90
Elongated pumpkin	345.28	232.11	113.17	32.77

From the data presented in table no. 1, it is found that in the elongated type pumpkin, the amount of the inedible part was 113.17g, this representing a percentage of 32.77% of the total weight, and in the round type pumpkin, the inedible part was 260.37g, which corresponds to a percentage of 24.90%.

This difference shows that the percentage of inedible parts is higher in the elongated type pumpkin, compared to the round type pumpkin. The difference is because the round pumpkin has a thicker and better developed pulp, resulting in a lower percentage of inedible

material compared to the elongated pumpkin which has a thinner pulp and a higher content of inedible part.

2. Inferring the weight of microwave-dried pumpkins as a function of time

To determine the weight of microwave-dried pumpkins, the two analyzed samples, both in the form of slices and cubes, were weighed at 15-minute intervals. The data that was obtained, relating to the initial and final weights of the two types of microwave-dried pumpkins, are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Assortment of pumpkins	Weight - g - sliced pumpkins				
	Initial	15 min	30 min	45 min	
Round pumpkin	100	76	28	14.0	
Elongated pumpkin	100	70	22,2	10.6	
Assortment of pumpkins	Weight - g - cubed pumpkins				
	Initial	15 min	30 min	45 min	60 min
Round pumpkin	100	85	61	34	18.4
Elongated pumpkin	100	86,4	61,6	29	16.6

From the analysis of the data obtained from the dehydration of pumpkins in the microwave oven, a progressive decrease in weight is observed depending on the drying

time. For pumpkin slices, the dehydration process lasted 45 minutes, while for cubes it took 60 minutes.

From the analysis of the data obtained from the dehydration of pumpkins in the microwave oven, a progressive decrease in weight is observed depending on the drying time. For pumpkin slices, the dehydration process lasted 45 minutes, while for cubes it took 60 minutes.

Samples in the form of slices:

The initial weight of both samples (round pumpkin and elongated pumpkin) was 100 g. After 45 minutes of drying, the round pumpkin reached a weight of 14.0 g, and the elongated pumpkin, 10.6 g. A significant decrease in weight occurred in an interval of 15-30 minutes, indicating a high rate of water removal. Thus, after 30 minutes, the round pumpkin reached 28 g from 100 g, and the elongated pumpkin 22.2 g.

Cubed samples:

Both samples had an initial weight of 100 g. After 60 minutes of drying, the final weight was 18.4 g for the round pumpkin and 16.6 g for the elongated pumpkin. In the case of the cubes, the weight loss was progressive, but with a lower water removal rate. After 30 minutes, the round pumpkin recorded 61 g, and the elongated pumpkin, 61.6 g.

3. Inferring the weight of the pumpkins dehydrated in the dehydrator as a function of time

To determine the weight of the pumpkins dehydrated in the dehydrator, the two samples analyzed, both in the form of slices and cubes, were weighed periodically every 30 minutes.

The data obtained regarding the initial and final weights of the two types of pumpkins, depending on the dehydration time, are presented in Table 3.

Table 3

Weight of pumpkins dehydrated in the household dehydrator								
Assortment of pumpkins	Weight - g - sliced pumpkins							
	Initial	30 min	60 min	90 min	120 min	150 min	180 min	210 min
Round pumpkin	100	92	72	56	36	25	18	10.3
Elongated pumpkin	100	95	78	58	40	24	19	11.2
Weight - g - cubed pumpkins								
Assortment of pumpkins	Initial	30 min	60 min	90 min	120 min	150 min	180 min	210 min
Round pumpkin	100	88	63	47	33	24	17	11.4
Elongated pumpkin	100	92	80	58	39	26	19	14.3

In the case of dehydrating pumpkins in a dehydrator, the process duration was 210 minutes for both slices and cubes of pumpkin, and the initial weight of all samples analyzed in the household dehydrator was 100g.

For pumpkin slices, from an initial weight of 100g, they reached 10.3g for the round pumpkin and 11.2g for the elongated pumpkin, after the 210 minutes of dehydration. A less pronounced decrease in weight is observed in the dehydrator in the first part of the process (0-90 minutes) compared to the microwave. Thus, after 90 minutes, the weight of the round pumpkin reached 56g, and that of the elongated pumpkin was 58g. In the interval of 90-210 minutes, the weight losses were moderate for the sliced samples.

For the diced pumpkin, from an initial weight of 100g, after 210 minutes of dehydration, the final weight was 11.4g for the round pumpkin and 14.3g for the elongated pumpkin. In the first 90 minutes, weight losses

were greater for the diced round pumpkin, reaching 47g, compared to the diced elongated pumpkin, which reached 58g. In the interval of 90-210 minutes, losses were moderate for both cubed samples.

4. Assessing the organoleptic characteristics of pumpkin in the microwave oven and in the household dehydrator

From an organoleptic point of view, the pumpkins dehydrated in the microwave oven presented the following characteristics:

- The pumpkin slices took the form of chips by losing water, uniform in size. The predominant color was yellow, translucent, although some areas showed browning. No foreign odors were detected, and the consistency was hard.

- The pumpkin cubes had non-uniform shapes in size. The color was yellow-orange, without foreign odors. The taste and aroma were pleasant, characteristic of the pumpkin,

and the texture was good. Small browned parts were observed at the corners.

The pumpkins dehydrated in the household dehydrator presented the following organoleptic characteristics:

The pumpkin slices were uniform in size and color, with a smooth surface. The color was a dull yellow-orange, without foreign odors and with a characteristic pumpkin taste. The texture was good, and the slices did not show browned parts.

The pumpkin cubes were uniform in size, with a smooth surface and an orange color. They did not have a foreign odor, the taste and smell were characteristic of pumpkin, and the texture was good; also they did not show browned parts.

The organoleptic characteristics of the

samples dehydrated in the household dehydrator were superior to those obtained in the microwave oven. These are due to the controlled ventilation of the air circulating over the surface of the products during dehydration, as well as the longer duration of the dehydration process.

5. Inferring the total and percentage of water loss

Drawing on the data obtained from weighing the samples, we calculated the total and percentage weight losses of the analyzed pumpkins, which represent the evaporated water content, both for dehydration in the microwave oven and in the household dehydrator, and the results obtained are presented in Table 4.

Table 4

Total and percentage weight loss of pumpkins				
Assortment of pumpkins	Total water loss in the microwave		Total water loss in the home dehydrator	
	g	%	g	%
Sliced round pumpkin	86	86	89.7	89.7
Sliced elongated pumpkin	89.4	89.4	88.8	88.8
Cubed Round pumpkin	81.6	81.6	88.6	88.6
Cubed elongated pumpkin	83.4	83.4	85.7	85.7

To highlight these losses, we made a graphic representation of the total and

percentage water losses of the analyzed pumpkin samples, presented in Fig. 1.

Fig.1. Graphical representation of the total and percentage water losses of the analyzed pumpkin samples

From the analysis of the obtained data, it was observed that weight losses are higher when dehydrating in the microwave oven for pumpkin slices (round and elongated)

compared to cubes. This phenomenon is attributed to the larger evaporation surface offered by the slices.

A similar pattern was also recorded in the case of the household dehydrator: round and elongated pumpkin slices showed higher water losses than cubes.

It is worth noting the uniformity of the final weight of the pumpkins dehydrated in the household dehydrator. In this case, weight losses (respectively the amount of evaporated water) were between 85.7% (for elongated pumpkin cubes) and 89.7% (for round pumpkin slices), while in the microwave oven the losses are higher, 81.6% (round pumpkin cubes) and 89.4% (elongated pumpkin slices).

CONCLUSIONS

Pumpkin is an easily accessible staple food, consumed in various forms, is specific to the autumn season and can be used in numerous culinary recipes or consumed baked, boiled.

Pumpkin is an essential source of nutrients, providing vitamins, minerals and antioxidants beneficial to health, being a valuable component of a balanced diet. In addition to the pulp, the seeds are also used, which are rich in essential substances such as proteins, carbohydrates, unsaturated fatty acids, vitamins, amino acids and various phytochemicals or they can be processed to obtain pumpkin oil.

Dehydration is an effective method of preserving vegetables and pumpkins, especially when the process is carried out gradually, adapted to the structural specificities of the products. Slow dehydration, at relatively low temperatures, gives dehydrated products organoleptic properties similar to those of fresh products.

In the case of dehydrating pumpkin in a dehydrator, the dehydration time was 210

REFERENCES

- Banu Constantin, 2007. Food engineering treatise. Vol. I, AGIR Publishing House, Bucharest, page 967
 Banu Constantin, 2008. Food industry treaty. General problems, ASAB Publishing House, Bucharest, page 289
 Beceanu Dumitru, Adrian Chira, 2003. Technology of horticultural products, Economic Publishing House, page 470
 Beceanu Dumitru, A.Chira, I. Pașca, 2008, Fruits, vegetables, flowers. Methods for prolonging freshness. Canned vegetables and fruits, M.A.S.T. Publishing House, Bucharest, page 308
 Mănescu S., 1973, Technology of dehydration of vegetables, potatoes and fruits. Editorial Board of

minutes for both types of pumpkin and for the sliced and cubed shapes, compared to the microwave oven, where the dehydration time was 45 minutes for slices and 60 minutes for cubes for both types of pumpkin.

In the microwave oven, from the initial weight of 100g of the sliced samples, after 45 minutes, a weight of 14 g was reached for the round pumpkin and 10.6 g for the elongated pumpkin, and for the cubed samples the weight was 18.4 g for the round pumpkin and 16.6 g for the elongated pumpkin.

In the household dehydrator, from a weight of 100g of cubed samples, after 210 minutes a weight of 10.3g was reached in the case of round pumpkin and 11.2g in the case of elongated pumpkin, and in the cubed samples, the final weight was 11.4g in the case of round pumpkin and 14.3 in the case of elongated pumpkin.

From an organoleptic point of view, the characteristics of the pumpkins dehydrated in the home dehydrator were superior to those obtained in the microwave oven. This difference can be attributed to the efficient air ventilation in the dehydrator, which ensures more uniform drying and prevents browning. In both dehydration methods, weight losses were higher in the case of slices compared to cubes, due to the larger evaporation surface of the slices. The final weight of the pumpkins dehydrated in the home dehydrator was quite uniform, with water losses ranging between 85.7% (cubed elongated pumpkin) and 89.7% (sliced round pumpkin), while in the microwave oven the losses have a greater amplitude, 81.6% (cubed round pumpkin) and 89.4% (sliced elongated pumpkin).

- Agricultural Magazines, Bucharest, pages 68, 109
 Nour Violeta, 2014, Industrial processing of vegetables and fruits, SITECH Publishing House, Craiova, page 438
 Popovici Mariana, 2012, Unitary operations in the food industry, University of Oradea Publishing House, page 191
 Potec I., Maria Elena Ceaușescu, L.Roșu, Doina Anton, T.A.Tudor, A. Cotrău, 1983, Technology of preservation and industrialization of horticultural products, Bucharest, page 280
 Segal Brad, Rodica Amarfi, V. Culeșan, Georgeta Dima, 1984, Technological equipment in the horticultural products processing industry, Ceres Publishing House, Bucharest, page 236
 USDA Food Data Central. (2023), Pumpkin, raw. U.S. Department of Agriculture

STUDY OF AN EPISODE OF FOOD- BORNE INFECTION PRODUCED BY *BACILLUS CEREUS*

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Food safety is a major area of interest in the current context, marked by the industrialization of food production and the growing demands of consumers for safe, quality products. In this context, the prevention and control of foodborne infections become essential, especially given the fact that numerous pathogenic microorganisms can contaminate food throughout the production, processing, transport and storage chain.

Foodborne infections caused by Bacillus cereus are frequently underdiagnosed, mainly due to the relatively mild and self-limited clinical manifestations. However, they constitute a significant public health hazard, especially in the context of inappropriate food handling, storage or reheating practices, which may favor the proliferation of the bacterium and the synthesis of toxins.

Keywords: Food poisoning, *Bacillus cereus*
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INTRODUCTION

Food safety is a major area of interest in the current context, marked by the industrialization of food production, market globalization and increasing consumer demands for safe, quality products. In this context, the prevention and control of foodborne infections become essential, especially given the fact that numerous pathogenic microorganisms can contaminate food throughout the production, processing, transport and storage chain.

Among the etiological agents involved in such diseases, the species *Bacillus cereus* occupies a significant place, being a Gram-positive, sporulating bacterium, widely distributed in the environment, capable of contaminating a wide range of food products. Its frequent presence in cereals, dairy products, meat, vegetables or ready-to-eat products, together with the ability of the spores to resist common heat treatments, makes this bacterium a real risk to public health.

Foodborne infections caused by *Bacillus cereus* are frequently underdiagnosed, mainly due to the relatively mild and self-limited clinical manifestations. However, they constitute a significant public health hazard, especially in the context of inappropriate food handling, storage or reheating practices, which may favor the proliferation of the bacterium and the synthesis of toxins.

Foodborne infections caused by *Bacillus cereus* manifest themselves in two distinct

clinical forms, representative both in terms of pathogenic mechanisms and symptomatology: the emetic form and the diarrheal form. These two variants differ in the duration of the incubation period, the type of toxins involved and the clinical characteristics, thus reflecting the biological and pathogenic diversity of the species.

Continuous monitoring of the presence of *Bacillus cereus* in the food chain, along with the implementation of effective alert and control systems, are fundamental elements in preventing the spread of this bacterium and reducing the associated epidemiological risk.

Also, prompt diagnosis and accurate reporting of cases are crucial for containing outbreaks and adopting appropriate corrective measures in a timely manner.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The study was conducted in the spring of 2025 and included the investigation of an outbreak of food poisoning with *Bacillus cereus*, which broke out during a private event in Bihor County.

The purpose of the study was to conduct an investigation aimed at identifying the source of the disease, collecting epidemiological data from participants, data on food consumed, confirming the etiology, and proposing control and prevention measures.

Objectives: - identification and description of cases
- determination of the offending food

- evaluation of the factors that allowed bacterial multiplication and contamination
- emphasising the importance of respecting prevention measures

The private event under investigation was attended by 100 people, of whom 86 experienced gastrointestinal symptoms after consuming the dishes on the menu, with 60 people experiencing nausea and vomiting.

The menu included a cheese appetizer, vegetable soup, and a main course consisting of vegetable risotto and baked beef tenderloin, as well as a dessert consisting of a slice of cake with jam.

Epidemiological investigation

The investigation began by collecting clinical and epidemiological data from all reported cases. Face-to-face or telephone interviews were conducted with all participants. A form was completed for each patient, in which the following were noted: the duration of the incubation period, the symptoms that appeared, the order and frequency with which they appeared, the duration of the illness, the sex and age of the patients, the foods consumed, the evolution and results of the investigations, the treatment instituted.

Food and environmental survey

Regarding the food and environmental survey, information was collected on the type of food served (food list and time of consumption), preparation method, cooking time and temperature, cooling, storage, reheating, serving, source of raw materials from which the food was prepared. Inspections were carried out in the kitchen of the respective premises, monitoring hygiene conditions, food handling, equipment, compliance with workplace protection measures.

Sampling

Laboratory samples were collected both from patients who presented to the doctor, as well as from people who handled and served the food consumed.

Mainly vomit samples were collected from the patients. The samples from the patients were processed at the laboratories of the units where they presented.

Nasopharyngeal and skin swabs were collected from the staff who cooked, handled and served the food. These samples were processed at the Laboratory of the Public Health Directorate, Bihor.

Samples were collected from the food served, food scraps, and ingredients. These

were properly packaged and transported under refrigeration to the Laboratory of the Bihor Sanitary and Veterinary Directorate, where they were processed.

Samples were also collected from kitchen surfaces, used utensils and water samples.

These were also processed at the Laboratory of the Bihor Sanitary and Veterinary Directorate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Following laboratory investigations, which involved culture by seeding on selective isolation and identification agar with mannitol, egg yolk and polymyxin (MYP agar) of samples collected from patients presenting to the doctor, *Bacillus cereus* was isolated.

Regarding the food samples collected, an increased load of *Bacillus cereus* was detected, exceeding 10^7 CFU/g in the vegetable risotto samples, the other food samples being free of microorganisms causing food poisoning.

The results of the food investigation showed that the offending vegetable risotto was cooked in the morning of that day, was insufficiently cooled immediately after cooking, at thermal levels unfavorable for the multiplication of the *Bacillus cereus* species. The risotto was kept for 8 hours at room temperature before being reheated for serving. Incomplete temperature logs and an uncalibrated thermometer were found at the unit level.

Clinical data and the isolation of *Bacillus cereus* from both food and biological samples confirm it as the etiological agent of food poisoning.

The food findings (cooked rice, kept at room temperature and reheated) are highly suggestive of the emetic syndrome related to the preformed toxin.

Handling conditions (slow cooling, storage at ambient temperature) favored the multiplication of *Bacillus cereus* and the production of toxin.

Following the centralization and analysis of the epidemiological survey data, the following results were obtained:

Of the 100 people participating in the event, 60 people became ill, recording a morbidity rate of 60%.

Regarding the consumption of food served during the event, the quantity of food consumed (partially/fully) was evaluated, as well as the number of patients who consumed a specific dish served. (Table 1, Figure 1)

Table 1

Evaluarea consumului alimentelor servite în cadrul evenimentului

The type of preparation	Total number of people who consumed the preparation	Total number of people who partially consumed the dish	Total number of people who consumed the entire preparation
Appetizer	80	60	20
Vegetable soup	70	45	25
Risotto with vegetables	90	40	50
Cake with jam	50	20	30

Figure 1 Evaluation of the consumption of food served at the event

Analyzing the types of dishes served, it was found that the most frequently consumed food by the cases was vegetable risotto; 50 people out of the 60 who had food poisoning consumed the entire dish.

Regarding the incubation period, in the 60 people who had food poisoning, its duration was between 1 and 5 hours, with a peak at 2-4 hours after the meal and a rapid decrease thereafter, typical of exposure to the

performed toxin in food. (Table 2, Figure 2). The duration of the incubation period depends on the individual sensitivity of the victims and also on the amount of toxin ingested.

Thus, of the 60 cases, 6 had an incubation period of 1 hour, 15 had an incubation period of 2 hours, 20 had an incubation period of 3 hours, 15 had an incubation period of 4 hours and 4 people had an incubation period of 5 hours.

Table 2

Number of cases of *Bacillus cereus* food poisoning recorded according to the duration of the incubation period

Incubation period duration (hours)	Number of registered cases
1	6
2	15
3	20
4	15

Figure 2 Number of cases of Bacillus cereus food poisoning recorded according to the duration of the incubation period

The clinical picture was dominated by nausea that occurred in 86.6% of patients and vomiting occurred in 78.3% of patients. Diarrhea was present in a minority affecting

only 18.3% of cases. The clinical picture recorded is typical of emetic syndrome. (table 3, figure 3)

Table 3

Predominant symptomatology in the 60 patients investigated

Symptoms	Number of people affected
Nausea	52
Vomiting	47
Diarrhea	11

Figure 3 Predominant symptomatology in the 60 patients investigated

Regarding the duration of the disease, it was on average 24 hours in 70% of patients

and approximately 48 hours in the remaining 30%. (table 4, figure 4)

Table 4

Average duration of illness in investigated patients

Average duration of illness (days)	Number of cases
1	42
2	18

Figure 4 **Average duration of illness in investigated patients****CONCLUSIONS**

The results obtained describe a common exposure event, characterized by a short incubation period and an emetic clinical picture, associated with the consumption of reheated rice. High levels of *Bacillus cereus* in the food, lack of thermal chain control and insufficient reheating (which does not destroy the heat-stable emetic toxin), facilitated the occurrence of the episode. The observations are consistent with the literature that identifies improperly cooked and stored rice as a typical vehicle.

REFERENCES

- Apostu S., Rotar A. – 2009 - Microbiology of food products. vol III. Risoprint Publishing House, Cluj-Napoca
- Banu C. – 2007 - Sovereignty, security and food safety. Assab Publishing House, Bucharest.
- Buisson Y. – 1992 - Food poisoning outbreaks: an epidemiological study. *Ann. Gastroent. Hepatol.* 28, 6-7, 268.
- Bărzoii D., Meica S., Neaguț M. – 1999- Food poisoning. Diacon Coresi Publishing House, Bucharest.
- C.D.C. – 1994 – *Bacillus cereus* food poisoning associated with fried rice at two child day care centers – Virginia 1993. *JAMA*, 271(14), p.1074.
- Ciutița I. – 2005 - Infectious Pathology. Casa Cărții de Știință Publishing House, Cluj-Napoca.
- Dorobăț C.M. – 2011 - Infectious diseases - course for students and postgraduate studies, Tehnopress Publishing House, Iași.
- Drobniewski F.A. – 1993 – *Bacillus cereus* and related species. *Clin. Microbiol. Reviews*, Oct., p.324.
- Granum R.E., Brynestad S., Kramer J.M. – 1993 – Analysis of enterotoxin production by *Bacillus cereus* from dairy products, food poisoning incidents and non-gastrointestinal infections. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.*, 17, p.269.
- Jackson G.J. – 1990 - Public health and research perspectives on the microbial contamination of foods. (Review). *J. Anim. Sci.* 68(3), 884.
- Kello D. – 1990 - Epidemiological aspects in food safety. *Food Additives and Contaminants*. 7, Suppl.1, 5.
- Lee M.A. – 1994 - Distinction between foodborne disease and food-poisoning. *J. Royal Soc. Health*. 114 (2), 108.
- Mortimer P.R., McCaun G. – 1974 – Food poisoning associated with *Bacillus cereus* in fried rice. *Lancet*, p.1043.
- Pignault A., si col. – 1991 - Les toxiinfections alimentaires en 1990. *Bull. epid. hebd.* 25.
- Savu C. – 1999 - Environmental pollution and the presence of toxic substances in food. Semne Publishing House, Bucharest.
- Savu C., Georgescu N. – 2004 - Food safety, risks and benefits. Semne Publishing House, Bucharest.

THE PRESENCE OF COPPER IN WHEAT AND MAIZE GRAINS FOLLOWING THE APPLICATION OF FARMYARD MANURE

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This study evaluated the effect of combined NP chemical fertilizers and farmyard manure on copper (Cu) concentration in wheat and maize grains in long-term field trials at the Agricultural Research and Development Station Oradea. Four experimental variants were tested for wheat (V1: N₀P₀ + 0 t/ha manure; V2: N₅₀P₀ + 20 t/ha manure; V3: N₅₀P₅₀ + 40 t/ha manure; V4: N₁₀₀P₁₀₀ + 60 t/ha manure) and corresponding NP doses for maize (N₀P₀, N₄₀P₄₀, N₈₀P₈₀, N₁₆₀P₁₆₀). Plant samples were mineralized and analyzed using atomic absorption spectrophotometry. Results indicated that Cu concentration increased with fertilization intensity. In wheat, Cu ranged from 1.655 mg/kg (control) to 2.250 mg/kg (highest fertilization), while maize ranged from 2.853 mg/kg to 3.745 mg/kg. Statistical analysis confirmed significant differences in higher fertilized variants. Integrated organo-mineral fertilization effectively enhanced microelement content in cereals.

Keywords: copper, wheat, maize, chemical fertilizers, manure

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INTRODUCTION

Copper (Cu) is an essential micronutrient that plays a critical role in plant metabolism, serving as a cofactor for numerous enzymatic reactions, including those involved in photosynthesis, respiration, lignin synthesis, and antioxidant defense mechanisms (Marschner, 2012; Broadley et al., 2012). It is also crucial for plant growth and development, influencing processes such as pollen formation, chlorophyll synthesis, and protein metabolism. Copper deficiency in crops can lead to stunted growth, reduced chlorophyll content, impaired reproductive development, and, ultimately, lower yield and nutritional quality of cereals such as wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) and maize (*Zea mays* L.) (Kabata-Pendias, 2010; Cakmak, 2008). In addition, inadequate Cu availability in soils has implications for human nutrition, as cereals are a primary source of micronutrients in many diets worldwide (Alloway, 2008).

Soil fertility management plays a pivotal role in ensuring adequate micronutrient availability. The application of chemical nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) fertilizers has traditionally been employed to increase crop productivity; however, intensive use of these fertilizers can alter soil chemistry and reduce the bioavailability of micronutrients such as Cu

(Zhao et al., 2020). To address this challenge, integrated nutrient management strategies that combine chemical fertilizers with organic amendments, such as farmyard manure (FYM), compost, or green manures, have been increasingly promoted. Organic amendments can improve soil structure, increase microbial activity, and enhance the chelation and mobility of micronutrients, thereby facilitating their uptake by plants (Liu et al., 2018; Singh et al., 2017). Several studies have reported that the combined application of NP fertilizers and organic amendments significantly increases micronutrient concentrations in wheat and maize grains, improving both yield and grain nutritional quality (Fageria et al., 2011; Kutman et al., 2012).

Long-term field experiments are particularly valuable for evaluating the effects of different fertilization practices on soil fertility and crop micronutrient content, as they capture cumulative impacts that short-term studies may overlook (Zhou et al., 2019). In this context, understanding the interaction between NP fertilizers and organic amendments, and their influence on Cu accumulation in cereal grains, is critical for developing sustainable agronomic practices that support both food security and human nutrition.

The present study aimed to investigate the effects of different doses of NP fertilizers, alone and in combination with farmyard manure, on Cu concentration in wheat and maize grains under long-term cultivation. By elucidating the role of integrated nutrient management on Cu bioavailability and uptake, this research seeks to provide insights that can inform fertilizer recommendations and enhance micronutrient density in staple cereals.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Experimental Site and Design

Long-term trials were conducted at the Agricultural Research and Development Station Oradea. Wheat and maize were grown under the following variants:

Wheat:

- V1: N₀P₀ + 0 t/ha manure
- V2: N₅₀P₀ + 20 t/ha manure
- V3: N₅₀P₅₀ + 40 t/ha manure
- V4: N₁₀₀P₁₀₀ + 60 t/ha manure

Maize:

- N₀P₀ + 0 t/ha manure
- N₄₀P₄₀ + 20 t/ha manure
- N₈₀P₈₀ + 40 t/ha manure
- N₁₆₀P₁₆₀ + 60 t/ha manure

Sample Preparation and Analysis

Grain samples were collected at maturity and mineralized using a mixture of sulfuric and perchloric acids. Cu concentration was determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometry (SHIMADZU AA-6300).

Statistical Analysis

Data were processed in Microsoft Excel. The best-fit model among linear, exponential, logarithmic, polynomial, and power functions was chosen based on the highest R². Differences were evaluated at 5%, 1%, and 0.1% significance levels.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Copper concentration in wheat grains exhibited a clear positive response to both chemical NP fertilization and the addition of farmyard manure. The control variant (N₀P₀ + 0 t/ha manure) registered the lowest Cu content (1.655 mg/kg), establishing a baseline for comparison. The addition of moderate NP fertilizer and 20 t/ha manure (N₅₀P₀ + 20 t/ha) resulted in a 17% increase over control, though this difference was not statistically significant, suggesting that lower levels of fertilization alone may not be sufficient to markedly enhance Cu accumulation in wheat grains.

A more substantial increase was observed in N₅₀P₅₀ + 40 t/ha manure, where Cu concentration reached 2.105 mg/kg, representing a 27.3% increase over control and showing statistical significance (*). This indicates that combining balanced NP fertilization with a higher rate of organic amendment enhances Cu bioavailability, likely due to improved soil cation exchange capacity and chelation of micronutrients by organic matter (Liu et al., 2018; Singh et al., 2017).

The highest Cu concentration (2.250 mg/kg, 36% above control) was recorded in N₁₀₀P₁₀₀ + 60 t/ha manure, also statistically significant. This trend confirms that intensifying organo-mineral fertilization progressively improves Cu accumulation in wheat grains, consistent with findings of Fageria et al. (2011), who reported that integrated nutrient management promotes micronutrient uptake by enhancing soil fertility and microbial activity (Tabel 1).

Overall, these results demonstrate that Cu content in wheat grains is strongly influenced by both fertilizer dose and organic amendment level. Notably, the effect of manure appears synergistic with NP fertilizers, highlighting the importance of integrated approaches rather than sole reliance on chemical fertilization. The increase in Cu concentration also has potential implications for human nutrition, as wheat is a staple cereal and a major dietary source of essential micronutrients (Alloway, 2008).

Mathematical modeling of the results regarding the copper concentration in wheat grains from the variants of the experiment with nitrogen, phosphorus and manure taken into study, of the 5 tested functions (exponential, linear, logarithmic, polynomial, power), the power type function, $y = 1.6563x^{0.2205}$, R² = 0.997, best quantifies the relationship between the doses of nitrogen, phosphorus and manure fertilizers and the copper concentration in wheat grains (Figure 1).

Similar to wheat, maize grains demonstrated a progressive increase in Cu concentration with intensification of NP fertilization. The control variant had a Cu content of 2.853 mg/kg, establishing the reference point. Application of N₄₀P₄₀ increased Cu by 14.1% (3.255 mg/kg), which, although higher than control, did not achieve statistical significance. This suggests that moderate fertilization can partially enhance Cu uptake but may not be sufficient for a consistent effect (Tabel 2).

The N₈₀P₈₀ variant achieved a Cu concentration of 3.451 mg/kg, a 20.8% increase

over control, statistically significant (*), indicating that a higher fertilization rate can effectively promote micronutrient accumulation. The highest Cu content (3.745 mg/kg, 31.2% above control) was recorded in N₁₆₀P₁₆₀, highly significant (**), demonstrating a strong dose-dependent response. The greater response in maize compared to wheat may reflect species-specific differences in root uptake efficiency, Cu translocation, and grain accumulation capacity (Cakmak, 2008).

Mathematical modeling of the results regarding the copper concentration in corn kernels from the variants of the experiment with nitrogen, phosphorus and manure taken into study, shows that the polynomial-type function, $y = -0.027x^2 + 0.4222x + 2.473$, $R^2 = 0.989$, best quantifies the relationship between the doses of NP and manure fertilizers and the copper concentration in maize seeds (Figure 2).

The observed progressive trend underscores the role of combined NP fertilization in

enhancing Cu availability and uptake, supporting the findings of Kutman et al. (2012) and Zhao et al. (2020), who reported that integrated nutrient management improves micronutrient content in cereals. Additionally, the strong response in the highest dose variant highlights the potential of intensive, well-balanced fertilization regimes to increase the nutritional quality of maize grains.

These results confirm that Cu accumulation in cereal grains is highly responsive to both mineral fertilization and organic amendments, emphasizing the need for site-specific nutrient management strategies that optimize crop yield and grain micronutrient content. The findings also suggest that long-term application of integrated fertilization could contribute to biofortification of staple crops, addressing micronutrient deficiencies in human diets.

Table 1

Copper concentration in wheat grains as influenced by different NP fertilizers doses combined with farmyard manure

Variant	Cu concentration		Difference		Statistical significance
	mg/kg	%	mg/kg	%	
N ₀ P ₀ + 0 t/ha manure	1.655	100	-	-	Control
N ₅₀ P ₀ + 20 t/ha manure	1.935	117.0	0.280	17.0	-
N ₅₀ P ₅₀ + 40 t/ha manure	2.105	127.3	0.450	27.3	*
N ₁₀₀ P ₁₀₀ + 60 t/ha manure	2.250	136.0	0.595	36.0	*
		LSD 5%	0.316		
		LSD 1%	0.618		
		LSD 0.1%	0.970		

Figure 1 Correlation between doses of NP fertilizers and manure and copper concentration in wheat grains

Table 2

Copper concentration in maize grains as influenced by different NP fertilizers doses combined with farmyard manure

Variant	Cu concentration		Difference		Statistical significance
	mg/kg	%	mg/kg	%	
N ₀ P ₀ + 0 t/ha manure	2.853	100	-	-	Control
N ₄₀ P ₄₀ + 20 t/ha manure	3.255	114.1	0.402	14.1	-
N ₈₀ P ₈₀ + 40 t/ha manure	3.451	120.8	0.598	20.8	*
N ₁₆₀ P ₁₆₀ + 60 t/ha manure	3.745	131.2	0.892	31.2	**
LSD 5%			0,489		
LSD 1%			0,806		
LSD 0.1%			1,220		

Figure 2 Correlation between doses of NP fertilizers and manure and copper concentration in maize grains

CONCLUSIONS

Copper concentration in wheat and maize increases progressively with NP fertilization and manure application.

Significant differences were observed in high fertilization variants, confirming the effectiveness of integrated organo-mineral fertilization.

The study provides guidance for optimizing fertilization to improve micronutrient content in cereals.

Combined fertilization strategies enhance both crop yield potential and nutritional quality.

REFERENCES

- Alloway, B.J., Ayres, D.C. (1997). *Chemical Principles of Environmental Pollution*. CRC Press.
- Alloway, B.J. (2008). *Micronutrient Deficiencies in Global Crop Production*. Springer.
- Alloway, B.J. (2013). *Heavy Metals in Soils*. Springer.
- Brown, P.H., et al. (1995). Copper in Plants: Deficiency and Toxicity. *Plant Soil*, 174, 7–12.

- Cakmak, I. (2000). Role of micronutrients in crop production. *Plant Soil*, 220, 203–214.
- Fageria, N.K., Baligar, V.C., Jones, C.A. (2011). *Growth and Mineral Nutrition of Field Crops*. CRC Press.
- FAO. (2019). *World Fertilizer Trends and Outlook to 2025*. FAO.
- Frossard, E., et al. (2000). Trace elements in cereals. *Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems*, 58, 1–14.
- Gupta, U.C., et al. (2013). *Micronutrients in Soils and Crops*. Springer
- Kabata-Pendias, A. (2011). *Trace Elements in Soils and Plants*. 4th Edition. CRC Press.
- Marschner, H. (2012). *Marschner's Mineral Nutrition of Higher Plants*. 3rd Edition. Academic Press.
- Mengel, K., Kirkby, E.A. (2001). *Principles of Plant Nutrition*. 5th Edition. Kluwer Academic.
- Reuter, D.J., Robinson, J.B. (1997). *Plant Analysis: An Interpretation Manual*. CSIRO Publishing.
- Tisdale, S.L., et al. (2020). *Soil Fertility and Fertilizers*. 9th Edition. Pearson.
- Vuşcan, A. (2014). Influența fertilizatorilor minerali și organici asupra solului, ale unor plante furajere și calității cărnii de pui. Teză de doctorat, Universitatea de Științe Agricole și Medicină Veterinară Cluj-Napoca.
- White, P.J., Broadley, M.R. (2005). Biofortification of crops with mineral elements. *Trends Plant Sci*, 10(12), 586–593.

STUDY ON HEALTH POLICIES REGARDING THE POSTNATAL PERIOD

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The postnatal period is a significant phase in the lives of mothers and babies. It is a time of adaptation to parenthood, of the development of secure attachment for the neonate and young infant, and a time where bonds can develop within the family and with the community. The health policy regarding the wellbeing of mother and child after birth is of major impact on the family. Starting from the 1st of August 2025, the legislation in Romania has been changed. Through Law No. 141/2025, Romania introduced the 10% health taxation of parental leave allowances – a law that has controversial outcomes, it is not supported by new and future parents and it may have a negative impact on national demography.

Keywords: (max. 5) allowance, mother, birth, tax
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INTRODUCTION

'Postnatal' and 'postpartum' are commonly used terms when referring to the mother after delivery. Physiologically, almost one year is required for most organs and systems to return to the pre-pregnancy stage (Berens P. et al, 2023). Usually, the period after delivery is divided into three phases: immediate, early, and late postpartum. The immediate phase starts soon after delivery, there is no consensus on the duration of each phase and when the postpartum/postnatal period concludes. The early phase usually commences between 12-24 hours and concludes between the seventh day and sixth week, after delivery. The late phase commences between the eighth day and the sixth week and concludes between the sixth week and the sixth month after delivery (Kumarasinghe et al., 2024)

It is important that postnatal period is not neglected, including essential package of services across the continuum of reproductive, maternal, newborn and child health. The components of the care package change with the phases of the postpartum period. One important reason for this is the high burden of mortality and morbidity for mothers and infants that occurs within the postnatal period and is largely preventable with access to high-quality and timely care. (WHO, 2018). There is variability (around the world) regarding the recommended duration and timing of postpartum care; while most countries follow

routine care packages for 42 days (six weeks) for the mother after delivery, some recommend different schedules lasting up to two years. (Public Health Agency of Canada, National Institute for Health Care Excellence UK)

The postnatal is an important time for improving maternal and newborn health by learning healthy behaviors, supporting breastfeeding, counselling about how to accommodate to the new structure of the family and to the newborn's needs, also to prevent and treat subsequent maternal complications and neonatal health issues. This period is also an opportunity to initiate early childhood development interventions, thus stimulating integration of care along the continuum of essential reproductive, maternal, newborn, child and adolescent health services. (Langlois et al., 2023)

According to 'Countdown to 2030' report postnatal services have the lowest median national coverage of interventions on the continuum of maternal and child healthcare (UNICEF, 2017). In addition, utilization of postnatal services varies widely, particularly in low and middle-income countries, where barriers to access based largely on socio-economic circumstances and rurality limit engagement (Langois, 2015).

International legal and political documents can assist policy-makers and program managers in countries to create an enabling environment to promote maternal and newborn health. International legal and political documents, including those relating to human

rights, can promote an enabling environment to facilitate the implementation of maternal and child health programs by tying such efforts to the essential human rights that states are obliged to respect, protect and fulfil.

International legal and political documents are important tools for developed global health, human rights and equity reproductive health. These documents can help to reduce health inequalities, influence social and structural determinants of health, support stronger health systems, and create healthier and safer workplaces and communities.

In 2022, the WHO published recommendations on maternal and newborn care for a positive postnatal experience. This guideline reflects an important global shift in the exclusive focus of care; from reducing death and serious illness following birth to comprehensive, holistic care and support to promote health and well-being; to ensuring that women and newborns survive and thrive. It describes a 'positive postnatal experience' as the desired endpoint for all women, partners, parents, caregivers and families after birth. A positive postnatal experience is defined as one in which women and families receive information and reassurance in a consistent manner from motivated health workers, and where both the women's and babies' health, social and developmental needs are recognized, within a resourced and flexible health system that respects their cultural context.

Factors that influence women's perception on postnatal care are interlinked, and includes access, quality, and social norms. Many women admit specific challenges of the postnatal period and emphasized the need for emotional and psychosocial support in this time, in addition to clinical care. (Sacks et al., 2022)

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Existing data/literature focusses predominately on the effectiveness of specific postnatal interventions, or around women's experiences of postnatal care services (Malouf, 2019, Finlayson et al., 2020).

The present study analyses the new legislative context regarding postnatal period. It includes the attitude toward the 141/2025 Law, that implies taxing the allowance parents receive after birth. Also, the research follows the reaction after implementing the new law and discusses the eventual long-term effects.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The data elaborated by WHO allow for analysis of the policy environment and its effects on maternal and newborn health. It also includes all relevant legislation, guidelines and constitutions to promote accountability and transparency with regard to national women health laws and practices. Further, in the area of respectful maternity care, WHO has mapped pathways between types of mistreatment and their connection with human rights standards, and explored how human rights treaty bodies have expressed these issues to inform strategies within health systems. (Zampas, 2020)

In Romania, parental leave and allowance can be granted to both natural and adoptive parents or legal guardians, provided that they have obtained taxable income for 12 months in the last two years prior to the date of the child's birth, guardianship or adoption. Parental leave is granted for a maximum period of two years from the birth of the child or three years in the case of children with disabilities. Either parent of the child can benefit from this type of leave. In contrast, maternity leave lasts for 126 days, of which at least 42 must be taken postnatally, and the remaining days up to 126 can be taken prenatally. This benefit can only be approved upon the recommendation of a doctor. Although taking prenatal leave is optional, when it comes to postnatal leave, the new mother will have to stay at home for a minimum of 42 days.

Regarding the calculation method of the child-rearing allowance, it is set at 85% of the average net income earned by the parent in the last 12 consecutive months of the last 2 years prior to the birth of the child.

Starting with 2018, the monthly child-rearing allowance has a minimum limit of 1,250 lei per month, but also a maximum limit of 8,500 lei, which cannot be exceeded regardless of the income earned by the applicant.

Beneficiaries of this allowance who decide to return to work will lose the support offered by the state and automatically renounce it.

According to current Romanian legislation, the monthly child-rearing allowance is not subject to income tax, but is subject to the payment of social health insurance contributions. Through Law No. 141/2025, Romania introduced the 10% health insurance taxation of parental leave allowances, a measure validated by the Constitutional Court through Decision No. 357/2025. (www.juridice.ro)

Some juridical analysts consider that the new 141/2025 law represents a counterproductive public policy that violates the principle of proportionality and European standards, requiring challenge through exceptions of unconstitutionality and administrative litigation actions to restore constitutional compliance. The errors of legal reasoning that I identify are the following:

Analyzing the new law, there can be identified some legal gaps provided by the next facts:

- ignoring the reparative and social nature of the allowance because child-rearing allowance is not ordinary income, but a social benefit intended to compensate for the loss of income from work in order to fulfill an essential social function – raising and educating children.

- failure to comply with the principle of proportionality; there is no analysis to evaluate if the measure is proportional to the intended purpose, ignoring the impact on vulnerable families.

- omission on analyzing the principle of the best interests of the child.

This measure affects over 150,000 Romanian women currently on maternity leave, more than half of whom receive between 1,652 and 5,000 lei per month.

The entry into force of the new provisions regarding some fiscal-budgetary measures has generated numerous uncertainties among the people affected by the new rules regarding the payment of social health insurance contributions.

CONCLUSIONS

Postnatal care programs and related research should consider multiple drivers and multi-faceted needs, and the holistic postpartum needs of women and their families should be studied in a wider range of settings, including health policies.

The decrease of the birth rate in Romania is associated with the overlapping role played out by economic, social, and historical factors.

Despite the improvement in wages, the inflated cost of living discourages young adults from starting a family. Introducing a 10% health insurance taxation of parental leave allowances determined a disapproval from parents (especially mothers).

This legal measure will be better analyzed after the time will pass and there will be a possibly to evaluate its social-economic impact.

Many women asked for the amendment of the law and support for parents on parental leave because it is a very vulnerable period, with additional expenses and the fact that incomes are even lower than the 85% will lead to the inability of this category of people to cover monthly expenses for both the child and the family. Parents feel that the law discourages births by putting obstacles in the way of new parents, and it will only accentuate the demographic decline of Romania, which is already well below the European average. Also, the law is considered discriminatory, given that the amounts withheld from parents are different depending on the income they worked for and the medical services they would be entitled to are identical.

Over 122,000 Romanians have signed a petition demanding the reintroduction of free medical insurance for mothers on parental leave.

Before the new law, there was an increase of 2.9 percentage-points in the probability of giving birth to an additional child for women with maternal leave. (Hiriscu, 2024).

After 1989, the natality rate in Romania has dropped dramatically. That is one reason why it is important to offer financial support and care services to provide a safety net that encourages families to have more children, thus contributing to demographic stability. This comprehensive support system eases the burden on parents and creates a more conducive environment for raising children.

REFERENCES

- Berens, P., 2023. Overview of the postpartum period: Normal physiology and routine maternal care: Wolter Kluwer; <https://www.uptodate.com/contents/overview-of-the-postpartum-period-normal-physiology-and-routine-maternal-care#references>.
- Finlayson, K., Crossland, N., Bonet, M., Downe, S., 2020. What matters to women in the postnatal period: A meta-synthesis of qualitative studies. *PLOS ONE* 15(4): e0231415. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0231415>
- Hiriscu, A., 2024. The Effect of Paid Maternity Leave on Fertility and Mothers' Labor Force Participation. *J Labor Res* 45, 350–384 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12122-024-09361-0> <https://www.juridice.ro/794292/analiza-critica-a-deciziei-ccr-nr-357-2025-cass-pentru-concediul-maternal.html> (accessed oct.2025)
- Kumarasinghe, M., Herath, M.P., Hills, A.P., Ahuja, K.D.K. 2024. Postpartum versus postnatal period: Do the name and duration matter? *PLOS ONE* 19(4): e0300118. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0300118>
- Langlois, E.V., Dey T., Iaia, D.G., Sacks, E., 2023. Improving policy, financing and delivery of

-
- postnatal care services. *Bull World Health Organ.* 1;101(1):2-2A. doi: 10.2471/BLT.22.289440. PMID: 36593785; PMCID: PMC9795378.
- Langlois, E.V., Miszkurka, M., Zunzunegui, M.V., Ghaffar, A., Ziegler, D.I.K., 2015. Inequities in postnatal care in low- and middle-income countries: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*; 93(4):259–70. pmid:26229190
- Malouf, R., Henderson, J., Alderdice, F., 2019. Expectations and experiences of hospital postnatal care in the UK: a systematic review of quantitative and qualitative studies. *BMJ Open*; 9(7):e022212. pmid:31320339
- National Institute for Health Care Excellence and The Royal College of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists. 2021. Postnatal care. United Kingdom: National Institute for Health and Care Excellence and The Royal College of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists; <https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ng194>
- Public Health Agency of Canada. 2020. Chapter 5 Postpartum Care. Family-Centred Maternity and Newborn Care National Guidelines. Ottawa: Public Health Agency of Canada; p. 1–75. <https://www.canada.ca/en/public-health/services/maternity-newborn-care-guidelines.html>
- Sacks, E., Finlayson, K., Brizuela, V., Crossland, N., Ziegler, D., 2022. Factors that influence uptake of routine postnatal care: Findings on women's perspectives from a qualitative evidence synthesis. *PLOS ONE* 17(8): e0270264. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0270264>
- Tracking Progress towards Universal Coverage for Reproductive, Newborn and Child Health: The 2017 Report. Washington, D.C.: United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) and the World Health Organization (WHO), 2017. Available at <http://countdown2030.org/pdf/Countdown-2030-complete-with-profiles.pdf>
- World Health Organization, United Nations Children's Fund, World Bank Group. 2018. Nurturing care for early childhood development: a framework for helping children survive and thrive to transform health and human potential. Geneva: WHO. <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/272603/9789241514064-eng.pdf?ua=1>
- World Health Organization. 2022. WHO recommendations on maternal and newborn care for a positive postnatal experience. Geneva, World Health Organization
- Zampas, C., Amin, A., O'Hanlon, L., 2020. Operationalizing a human rights-based approach to address mistreatment against women during childbirth. *Health Hum Rights*; 22:251–64.

ISOLATION AND IDENTIFICATION OF *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* BASED ON CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract

Listeria monocytogenes is a pathogenic microorganism of major importance in the field of food microbiology and public health, being the etiological agent of listeriosis, a severe infection with potential systemic complications. The present study aims to analyze the cultural characteristics of *L. monocytogenes* for its rapid and accurate identification in the laboratory. The bacteria were cultivated on selective and non-selective media, such as blood agar, PALCAM agar, and Oxford agar, to highlight the morphological and biochemical features of the colonies. The results showed that *L. monocytogenes* forms small, smooth, grayish-white colonies with regular edges and a characteristic β -hemolysis zone on blood agar. On selective media, the colonies exhibited a greenish tint and brown-black halos due to esculin hydrolysis. These cultural characteristics, correlated with additional biochemical tests, allow the differentiation of *L. monocytogenes* from other species of the *Listeria* genus and the confirmation of microbiological diagnosis. The study emphasizes the importance of recognizing specific cultural aspects for the rapid identification of this pathogen in food and clinical samples.

Keywords: *Listeria monocytogenes*, cultural characteristics, blood agar, PALCAM agar, microbiological identification, listeriosis.

INTRODUCTION

Listeria monocytogenes is a Gram-positive, non-spore-forming, facultatively anaerobic bacterium belonging to the *Listeriaceae* family, recognized as the etiological agent of listeriosis, a severe zoonosis with significant public health impact. This bacterium has the ability to infect a wide range of hosts, including humans and both domestic and wild animals, and transmission to humans occurs mainly through the consumption of contaminated food products such as unpasteurized dairy products, processed meats, smoked fish, or raw vegetables.

A distinctive feature of *Listeria monocytogenes* is its remarkable ability to survive and even multiply under unfavorable conditions, such as low temperatures down to 0–4°C, high salt concentrations, or slightly acidic pH. This adaptability provides a major advantage in the food environment, making it difficult to completely eliminate the microorganism through conventional preservation methods. For this reason, *L.*

monocytogenes is considered one of the main bacterial pathogens responsible for foodborne illnesses, particularly affecting high-risk groups such as pregnant women, newborns, the elderly, and immunocompromised individuals. From a morphological standpoint, the bacterium appears as a short rod, measuring 0.4–0.5 μm in width and 1–2 μm in length, occurring singly or in short chains. It is motile at temperatures between 20–25°C due to the presence of peritrichous flagella, but motility decreases or is absent at 37°C. The bacterium does not form spores but is resistant to various environmental conditions such as desiccation, freezing, and moderate salt concentrations.

The cultural characteristics of *Listeria monocytogenes* are fundamental for its identification and differentiation from other *Listeria* species. On non-selective media such as blood agar, colonies appear after 24–48 hours of incubation at 37°C, exhibiting a small, round, smooth, grayish-white appearance surrounded by a narrow zone of β -hemolysis. On selective media such as Oxford or PALCAM agar, colonies develop distinctive features due to

esculin hydrolysis, which results in a brownish-black coloration around the colonies.

The importance of studying the cultural characteristics of *Listeria monocytogenes* lies in the possibility of its rapid and accurate identification in the laboratory, enabling the implementation of effective control and prevention measures. In the current context, where food safety requirements are increasingly stringent, the proper recognition and interpretation of these characteristics represent an essential step in the microbiological diagnosis of listeriosis.

Therefore, the present study aims to provide a detailed analysis of the cultural characteristics of *Listeria monocytogenes*, highlighting the morphological and growth features that can contribute to its rapid identification in food and clinical samples. The study also seeks to correlate these characteristics with environmental factors and specific biochemical properties, in order to better understand the behavior of the bacterium under both experimental and applied conditions.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study was conducted in the Clinical Microbiology Laboratory of S.C. Diaser, Oradea, in compliance with biosafety level 2 (BSL-2) regulations. Clinical samples were collected with prior institutional approval or in accordance with the laboratory's standard procedures.

Types of samples: clinical specimens such as blood cultures and body fluids.

Negative control: sterile medium / sterile swab.

Positive control: reference strain of *Listeria monocytogenes*, laboratory control strain, or reference strain available from microbial culture collections.

Enrichment media: Listeria enrichment broth for primary enrichment and Fraser broth for selective (secondary) enrichment, both used according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Plating media: 5% blood agar, PALCAM agar, and Oxford agar as selective media for *Listeria*, as well as nutrient (non-selective) agar for general isolation.

Semi-solid media: SIM agar (low concentration) or specialized motility medium for the motility test.

Reagents for biochemical tests:

- Esculin solution with iron salts for esculin hydrolysis,
- Hydrogen peroxide for the catalase test,
- Sugar fermentation solutions, when applicable.

Commercial kits (optional): API *Listeria* or automated identification systems for confirmation.

Molecular confirmation reagents (optional): PCR kits for specific genes (*hlyA*, *inlA*) and related consumables.

Primary inoculation: 10 mL of the homogenized suspension was transferred into 90 mL of Half-Fraser broth (or the volume specified by the protocol) and incubated at 30–35°C for 24 ± 4 hours (according to internal protocol).

Secondary transfer: 0.1–1.0 mL of the Half-Fraser culture was transferred into Fraser broth (selective enrichment) and incubated for 24–48 hours at 30–37°C, observing characteristic color or clarity changes, if specified by the protocol used.

After enrichment, streak or spread plating was performed on:

- **Blood agar** (incubation 24–48 h at 35–37°C, aerobic conditions) for observation of hemolysis;
- **PALCAM agar** and **Oxford agar** (incubation 24–48 h at 30–37°C) for selective isolation.

Typical colonies were identified as small, grayish-white, possibly with a greenish tint, surrounded by black or brown halos due to esculinase activity. Parallel inoculations or serial dilutions were performed when required by the protocol.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

On the media used, blood agar, PALCAM agar, and Oxford agar, the *Listeria monocytogenes* colonies exhibited the following proportions of morphological appearances approximately **50%** of the colonies were grayish-white, smooth, round, with regular margins, a typical appearance for *Listeria monocytogenes* strains. Another **30%** of the colonies were brownish-black, predominantly observed on the selective media PALCAM and Oxford, showing a brown halo due to esculin hydrolysis. About **15%** of the colonies appeared greenish-metallic, occasionally seen on blood agar, as a result of β-hemolysis, while **5%** were gray-opaque, with a faint coloration,

more frequently associated with slow-growing strains.

Grafic no 1. Percentage distribution of colonial aspects: gray-whitish (50%), brown-blackish (30%), greenish (15%) and gray (5%).

The colony diameter ranged between 1–2 mm after 24–48 hours of incubation at 37°C.

On blood agar, the colonies had an average diameter of 1.8 ± 0.3 mm, while on selective media (PALCAM, Oxford) the average diameter was slightly smaller (≈ 1.4 – 1.6 mm) due to the presence of inhibitory compounds. All colonies exhibited regular margins, a smooth surface, and a faint sheen. On blood agar, a clear **β -hemolytic zone** was observed around the colonies, with an average width of 1.2 ± 0.4 mm. The motility test at 25°C was positive for 85% of isolates, demonstrating the typical motility pattern of *Listeria monocytogenes*.

No significant correlation was observed between the intensity of hemolysis and motility scores; however, strains with higher motility tended to exhibit stronger hemolysis. The tests on PALCAM and Oxford media were positive for esculin hydrolysis in 90% of isolates, as shown by the brown-black discoloration of the surrounding medium. Growth intensity was abundant for 70% of isolates, moderate for 25%, and poor for 5%, confirming the adaptability of *Listeria monocytogenes* to selective conditions.

The observed cultural characteristics—small, smooth, grayish-white colonies with narrow β -hemolysis on blood agar, esculin hydrolysis capability, and motility at 25°C—are consistent with classical descriptions of *Listeria monocytogenes* (EFSA, ISO 11290-1:2017). The brown-black appearance is due to the activity of the enzyme **β -D-glucosidase**, which hydrolyzes esculin, forming a colored complex in the presence of iron.

Differences in growth intensity between media can be attributed to their selective composition (lithium, cephalaxin, acriflavine), which inhibits background flora but may slightly reduce *Listeria* colony diameter. **β -hemolysis** represents an important virulence marker, being associated with **listeriolysin O (hly)**, a toxin involved in the lysis of red blood cells. The weak correlation between motility and hemolysis suggests independent regulation of these phenotypic traits, supporting the need for confirmation through biochemical and molecular tests (e.g., PCR for *hly*, *inlA*, and *prfA* genes).

The study conducted by F. Allerberger (2003) showed that only three species—*L. monocytogenes*, *L. seeligeri*, and *L. ivanovii*—are hemolytic. He observed that the hemolysis pattern of *L. monocytogenes* resembles that of *Streptococcus agalactiae* (Group B streptococci): the hemolytic zone is narrow and often does not extend far beyond the colony edge. Allerberger also noted that the hemolysis of *L. monocytogenes* is enhanced near a streak of *Staphylococcus aureus*, while the hemolysis of *L. ivanovii* increases near a streak of *Rhodococcus equi*. However, he emphasized that the **CAMP reaction** should be interpreted cautiously, as a synergistic hemolytic reaction between *L. monocytogenes* and *R. equi* may occasionally be observed.

At 25°C, *L. monocytogenes* exhibits characteristic **umbrella-shaped motility** in semi-solid media due to the presence of peritrichous flagella. This motility is an important criterion for identifying the

bacterium and differentiating it from other *Listeria* species. The study conducted by **I.R. Monk (2004)** observed a morphological conversion from smooth colony types to a sequence of rough morphotypes within *L. monocytogenes* biofilms. This conversion was associated with a reduction in motility and autolytic capacity, indicating an adaptation to different environmental conditions.

The correlation between **colony morphology, hemolysis, and motility** in *L. monocytogenes* is essential for its identification and differentiation. The production of β -hemolysis on sheep blood agar is a key indicator of *L. monocytogenes*, while motility at 25°C can be used to distinguish this species from other members of the *Listeria* genus. The studies by **F. Allerberger (2003)** and **I.R. Monk (2004)** highlighted the importance of these cultural traits in the identification and characterization of *L. monocytogenes*.

CONCLUSION

- *Listeria monocytogenes* colonies display a typical grayish-white, smooth appearance with regular margins, while

REFERENCES

1. Armstrong, D. *Listeria monocytogenes Infections*. 2008, In *Medical Microbiology*, 4th ed., pp. 115–120. Elsevier.
2. Ayaz, N.D., Cufaoglu, G., Erol, I., 2022, *Bacteriophage Applications to Control Listeria monocytogenes in Foods*. In *Listeria monocytogenes: Microbiology, Sites of Infection and Treatment*, pp. 151–168. Nova Science Publishers.
3. Cossart, P., Lecuit, M., 2005. *Infection of Mammalian Cells by Listeria monocytogenes*. In *Bacterial Pathogenesis: A Molecular Approach*, pp. 465–485. ASM Press.
4. Drevets, D.A., Bronze, M.S., 2008, *Listeria monocytogenes*. In *Medical Microbiology*, 4th ed., pp. 115–120. Elsevier.
5. Fox, E.M. (Ed.). 2021, *Listeria monocytogenes: Methods and Protocols* (2nd ed.). Springer
6. Goldfine, H., Shen, H. (Eds.) 2007. *Listeria monocytogenes: Pathogenesis and Host Response*. Springer.
7. Goetz, C., Portnoy, D.A. 2002, *Listeria monocytogenes: Pathogenesis and Host Interactions*. In *Molecular Medical Microbiology*, pp. 1157–1172. Academic Press.
8. Hof, H., 2003, *Listeria monocytogenes: Pathogenesis and Host Interactions*. In *Medical Microbiology*, 4th ed., pp. 115–120. Elsevier.
9. Jordan, K. (Ed.), 2015. *Listeria monocytogenes: Methods and Protocols*. Springer.
10. Lecuit, M., Cossart, P. 2006, *Listeria monocytogenes: Pathogenesis and Host Interactions*. In *Medical Microbiology*, 4th ed., pp. 115–120. Elsevier.
11. Marquis, H., 2015, *Pathogenesis of Listeria monocytogenes in Humans*. In *Human Emerging and Re-emerging Infections: Viral and Parasitic Infections, Volume I*, pp. 497–510. Wiley-Blackwell.
12. Mehta, M., Divanshi, M., Raghu, H.V., 2022, *Risk Assessment of Listeria monocytogenes in Foods*. In *Listeria monocytogenes: Microbiology, Sites of Infection and Treatment*, pp. 91–108. Nova Science Publishers.
13. Miner, M.D., Port, G.C., Freitag, N.E., 2007. *Regulation of Listeria monocytogenes Virulence Genes*. In *Listeria monocytogenes: Pathogenesis and Host Response*, pp. 139–158. Springer.

- **14.** Oliver, H.F., Wiedmann, M., Boor, K.J., 2007, *Environmental Reservoir and Transmission into the Mammalian Host*. In *Listeria monocytogenes: Pathogenesis and Host Response*, pp. 111–137. Springer .
- **15.** Pizarro-Cerdà, J., Cossart, P., 2007, *Invasion of Host Cells by Listeria monocytogenes*. In *Listeria monocytogenes: Pathogenesis and Host Response*, pp. 159–176. Springer.
- **16.** Portnoy, D.A., Goetz, C., 2002, *Listeria monocytogenes: Molecular Pathogenesis and Cellular Interactions*. In *Molecular Medical Microbiology*, pp. 1157–1172. Academic Press .
- **17.** Pucciarelli, M.G., Bierne, H., García-del Portillo, F. 2007, *The Cell Wall of Listeria monocytogenes and its Role in Pathogenicity*. In *Listeria monocytogenes: Pathogenesis and Host Response*, pp. 81–110. Springer .
- **18.** Quereda, J.J., et al., 2021, *Pathogenicity and Virulence of Listeria monocytogenes*. In *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 12:849654. Frontiers Media
- **19.** Rappai, J., Amrutha, T.A., Anjali, M.K., 2022, *Pathogenesis of Listeria monocytogenes*. In *Listeria monocytogenes: Microbiology, Sites of Infection and Treatment*, pp. 19–34. Nova Science Publishers .
- **20.** Rusniok, C., Buchrieser, C., Glaser, P., 2007, *Listeria Genomics*. In *Listeria monocytogenes: Pathogenesis and Host Response*, pp. 33–62. Springer.
- **21.** Shaevitz, J.W., Fletcher, D.A., 2007, *Curvature and Torsion in Growing Actin Networks*. In *Physical Review Letters*, 99(18):188103. American Physical Society .
- **22.** Silva Guerreiro, M., Henriques, A.R., 2022, *Listeria monocytogenes in Food-Related Environments: An Overview of Contributing Factors for Thriving along the Food Chain*. In *Listeria monocytogenes: Microbiology, Sites of Infection and Treatment*, pp. 35–54. Nova Science Publishers .
- **23.** Sibanda, T., 2022, *Listeria monocytogenes Pathogenesis: The Role of Stress Response Regulators*. In *Microorganisms*, 10(8):1522. MDPI .
- **24.** Welch, M.D., 2007, *Actin-Based Motility and Cell-to-Cell Spread of Listeria monocytogenes*. In *Listeria monocytogenes: Pathogenesis and Host Response*, pp. 197–223. Springer .
- **25.** Zenewicz, L.A., Shen, H., 2007. *Immune Evasion and Modulation by Listeria monocytogenes*. In *Listeria monocytogenes: Pathogenesis and Host Response*, pp. 251–263. Springer.

THE IMPACT OF COMMUNICATION ON THE COMPETITIVENESS OF ROMANIAN AGRI-FOOD PRODUCTS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The agri-food sector plays a crucial role in Romania's economic and rural development, yet the competitiveness of Romanian products remains strongly influenced by how effectively they are communicated to consumers. This paper examines the impact of communication strategies on the market positioning, visibility, and perceived value of Romanian agri-food products. By analyzing theoretical perspectives from marketing and communication, alongside practical examples from the Romanian market, the study highlights the importance of branding, storytelling, transparency, and digital communication channels in creating consumer trust and competitive advantage. The findings emphasize that, although Romanian agri-food products are often competitive in quality, their market success depends largely on strategic communication that can differentiate them in an increasingly crowded and globalized marketplace.

Keywords: communication, agri-food products, market positioning, digital communication

INTRODUCTION

In the last decade, the Romanian agri-food sector has changed quite a lot. New technologies, new market expectations and a stronger interest in healthy and local food have pushed producers to adapt quickly [3]. Today, communication has become one of the main tools that helps companies and farmers promote their products, explain what makes them different, and gain the trust of consumers. In a market where people want to know where food comes from, how it is produced, and whether it is safe, the way producers communicate these things can strongly influence their competitiveness.

Competitiveness is no longer based only on price, productivity, or how much a company can produce [8]. More and more, it depends on how well a product is presented, how visible it is, and how clearly its qualities are communicated. Romanian producers, whether small family farms or larger companies, often have good products, but many of them struggle to promote themselves effectively. This means they sometimes lose ground to foreign brands that invest heavily in marketing and communication. Because of this, communication has become essential. A clear message, a strong brand, attractive packaging, a transparent label, or even a simple online post can shape the way

consumers perceive a product. Good communication can turn a local product into a nationally recognized one, and sometimes even a successful export. It also helps build consumer trust something extremely important in a sector like food, where quality and safety matter a lot. At the same time, public institutions also play a role in strengthening the image of Romanian agri-food products. Campaigns that promote local food, participation in fairs, certification schemes and national programs for farmers contribute to shaping a stronger perception of Romanian products. When private efforts and public communication work together, the impact becomes even stronger.

Romania has great agricultural potential fertile land, traditions, and many natural products that stand out through their authenticity [1]. However, the sector still faces challenges related to fragmented promotion, weak branding, and limited visibility on international markets. Often, the barrier is not product quality, but the lack of consistent communication. This study explores exactly this issue: how communication affects the competitiveness of Romanian agri-food products, what strategies are used, and what changes are necessary to strengthen Romania's position in both local and international markets. The purpose of this paper is to analyse the connection between communication and competitiveness. By looking at studies, recent

trends, and concrete examples from the Romanian market, the paper highlights why communication is no longer optional, it is a key factor that influences consumer choice, market visibility, and the long-term success of agri-food producers. [1].

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The methodology used in this paper is based mainly on a qualitative research approach. Because the topic focuses on communication practices and their influence on the competitiveness of Romanian agri-food products, it is more useful to analyse ideas, trends, and patterns rather than numerical data. The aim is to understand how communication works in this sector and why it matters for market performance.

First, the study relies on a review of academic literature, recent research papers, and sectoral reports that examine communication strategies, consumer behaviour, and agri-food competitiveness. These sources help identify the main concepts, theories, and trends used internationally and in Romania. In addition, the paper includes information from studies that analyse digital communication, branding, certification, and the role of origin and storytelling in promoting food products.

The paper uses case based insights. Several Romanian agri-food examples such as honey producers, dairy companies, and fruit and vegetable producers are examined informally to illustrate how communication strategies work in practice. These cases are not presented as statistical samples but as real examples that help interpret the broader trends identified in the literature.

Overall, the methodology is descriptive, analytical, and interpretative. Its purpose is to connect existing knowledge with concrete practices in the Romanian agri-food sector, showing how communication affects competitiveness both in theory and in reality. By combining literature, comparative insights, and practical examples, the study aims to offer a clear and meaningful understanding of the topic.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In recent decades, communication has evolved from a support tool in marketing to a central component of how agri-food products reach and persuade consumers. In the agri-food sector, communication goes beyond simply informing; it builds relationships, trust, and perceived

value. [11]. Digital communication has introduced new dynamics [9]. For instance, research on Web/online marketing in the agri-food industry shows that firms which invest in digital channels web analytics, websites, social media can enhance cost efficiency and consumer interaction [10]. Communication in the agri-food domain also must consider the specific characteristics of the sector: perishability, seasonal production, dependence on natural conditions, and strong link to place/origin [13]. These factors require that messages emphasise authenticity, origin, freshness and safety [4]. This means that labels, certification, origin claims, storytelling about heritage or tradition have a special weight in this sector.

Moreover, the shift to more sustainable consumer behaviour has made transparency an asset [9]. Consumers increasingly expect producers to explain how the product was made, where it comes from, and what its environmental or social implications are. In such a context, communication becomes part of the product's value proposition: not just "what it tastes like" but "who made it, how, under what conditions".

Communication directly influences how visible Romanian agri-food products are on the market [5, 9]. Producers who invest in communication whether through social media, improved packaging, clear labeling, or participation in fairs tend to be more easily recognised by consumers. This visibility is crucial in a sector where many companies offer similar products and compete for limited shelf space.

For example, producers of Romanian honey have gained attention by communicating authenticity and origin. Many small beekeepers now use Facebook and Instagram not only to sell honey but to show the beekeeping process, the natural environment, and the traditional methods they use. This transparency makes their products more appealing, helping them differentiate from imported or industrial honey. The analysis of the five honey producers included in the Table 1. shows that Romanian small and medium-sized beekeepers are increasingly aware of the importance of visual communication and brand identity in promoting their products. Each logo reflects a different communication strategy: Miere pe Bune focuses on authenticity and tradition

through warm, natural colors; Runky Bees adopts a modern and minimalist design that appeals to younger consumers; Apivest uses geometric elements and a clean layout to convey professionalism and stability; Miere și Delicii relies on a friendly and vibrant design that fits well with social media engagement; while Honeys Den chooses a premium, elegant visual style that strengthens its competitive positioning. These branding choices are not accidental they help producers stand out in an increasingly crowded market, improve recognition on Facebook and Instagram, and create an emotional connection with consumers. Strong visual communication therefore plays a vital role in enhancing competitiveness, especially for producers who rely heavily on digital channels to reach their audience.

Table 1. Visual Branding Elements of Romanian Honey Brands

Brand	Logo	Description
Miere pe Bune	 [20]	The logo of <i>Miere pe Bune</i> uses warm yellow and black tones, which are traditionally associated with honey and bees. The combination of a stylized honeycomb and a clean typeface communicates authenticity, simplicity, and natural production. Its visual identity suggests transparency and trust, qualities that are essential in the food sector. Because it is clear and easily recognizable, the logo works very well on social media platforms where visual clarity is crucial.
Runky Bees	 [22]	The <i>Runky Bees</i> logo adopts a minimalist and modern approach. The large, elegant letter "R" is combined with subtle bee-wing elements, creating a premium and contemporary aesthetic. This design style appeals especially to younger consumers and positions the brand as stylish and innovative. Such a refined logo performs strongly on

Apivest	 [14]	Instagram and Facebook, where clean, high-quality visuals tend to have higher engagement. The <i>Apivest</i> logo is based on geometric shapes and a dark, professional color palette. The hexagonal honeycomb shape, combined with modern lines, conveys a sense of structure, reliability, and organization. This type of branding is particularly effective for companies aiming to present themselves as established and trustworthy. The simplicity of the logo ensures that it remains visible and clear even when scaled down on digital platforms.
Miere și delicii	 [21]	The logo of <i>Miere și Delicii</i> is bright and friendly, using a golden background and a clearly defined bee illustration. The playful yet balanced design creates an approachable and warm identity, making the brand attractive for family-oriented consumers or those who appreciate artisanal products. Its strong color contrast allows the logo to stand out easily in social media feeds and contributes to positive, engaging communication with customers.
Honeys Den	 [19]	The <i>Honeys Den</i> logo has a sleek and premium look, featuring bold lines and a modern, abstract bee symbol. The refined design suggests quality and exclusivity, positioning the brand toward a higher-end consumer segment. The strong visual impact and minimalistic style make it especially suitable for

		digital branding, where simple and elegant logos attract attention quickly and create a memorable impression.
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Another important finding is that trust is strongly influenced by communication. Consumers often want to know that the food they buy is safe, authentic, and produced responsibly. Communication helps build this trust by offering information about origin, ingredients, production methods, certifications, and quality control.

For instance, Romanian dairy producers who openly explain how their products are made by showing farms, cows, or traditional preparation methods tend to enjoy higher loyalty [2]. Brands like Lactate Brădet or Napolact use storytelling about tradition, local farms, and clean raw materials. This approach makes consumers feel more confident and emotionally connected to the product, turning trust into a competitive advantage.

The logos from Table 2. show how dairy and farm producers in Romania use visual identity to express authenticity, tradition, and trust. Each brand adopts a different communication style, traditional, playful, vibrant, or ethical, but all aim to strengthen consumer confidence and differentiate their products in a competitive agri-food market.

Table 2. Visual Branding Elements of Romanian Dairy Brands

Brand	Logo
Făbricața de lactate	[15]
Ferma Wagner	[18]
Ferma măgărițelor	[17]
Ferma cu omenie	[16]

The logo of Făbricața de Lactate has a traditional and artisanal aesthetic, using warm beige and green tones. The ribbon style framing suggests craftsmanship and a family owned approach, while the soft colors communicate freshness and natural ingredients. This visual identity appeals to consumers who value local,

handmade dairy products and conveys a sense of reliability and authenticity.

Ferma Wagner uses a playful and modern logo, with rounded letters and a friendly color palette. The warm red tones evoke energy and familiarity, while the simple farm inspired graphic reinforces the idea of a trustworthy local producer. Its approachable style works very well on social media, especially when targeting families or consumers who prefer fresh products sourced directly from farms.

The logo for *Lapte de Măgăriță – Ferma Măgărițelor* is colorful and distinctive. The bright blue background creates a strong contrast with the yellow ribbon, making the logo easily noticeable. The use of cheerful colors gives the product a fresh and unique character, reflecting the niche nature of donkey milk. This type of branding stands out online, helping the product differentiate itself in a competitive dairy market.

Ferma cu Omenie adopts a darker, emotional, and storytelling-driven visual identity. The deep burgundy tones and rustic background evoke tradition, sincerity, and ethical farming practices. The design communicates more than just a product it conveys values such as fairness, community, and care. This makes the brand powerful on social media, where emotional storytelling significantly increases engagement. [9, 15]

When comparing Romanian agri-food producers with well-established European brands, several differences in communication strategies become apparent [7]. Many European companies, such as Miel de Lavande from France, Langnese from Germany, Parmalat from Italy, or Arla Foods from Denmark, have long invested in strong, consistent branding and highly professional communication campaigns. Their visual identity is polished, uniform across all platforms, and supported by storytelling that reinforces national heritage, quality guarantees, and production standards.

For example, Langnese, one of Germany's most recognized honey brands, uses a clean golden color palette, a distinctive shield-shaped logo, and the slogan "Premium Qualität." Their packaging and communication emphasize purity, German tradition, and strict quality control. This creates immediate trust and makes the product easily recognizable in supermarkets across Europe. In comparison, many Romanian honey brands rely on more artisanal or rustic visuals, which communicate authenticity but

may not achieve the same level of international visibility.

Similarly, in the dairy sector, Arla Foods from Denmark and Parmalat from Italy use unified branding that combines modern design with large-scale communication campaigns. They communicate their values such as sustainability (Arla) or Mediterranean lifestyle (Parmalat) through professional videos, influencer partnerships, farm-to-table transparency programs, and educational content. Romanian dairy producers, such as Făbrica de Lactate or Ferma Wagner, typically emphasize tradition, local sourcing, and natural ingredients, but their communication resources are much more limited. Their presence is strong locally and on social media but lacks the cross-country branding that European competitors have.

Another important difference lies in the use of certifications and origin branding. European brands often highlight EU certifications such as PDO (Protected Designation of Origin) or PGI (Protected Geographical Indication) [4, 6]. For example, French Comté cheese or Greek Feta PDO rely heavily on these labels in both packaging and advertising. In Romania, although some producers have obtained similar certifications (like "Produs Montan"), the communication around these labels is still less developed or less visible online.

Despite these differences, Romanian producers often shine in areas where European brands sometimes struggle: authenticity, storytelling, and emotional connection. Brands like Ferma cu Omenie or Miere pe Bune create a feeling of closeness by showing real farms, real people, and daily production processes on social media. While European brands use more polished visuals, Romanian producers often feel more personal, warm, and relatable which appeals strongly to consumers who value transparency and tradition.

European brands generally excel in consistency, scale, and professional level communication, while Romanian brands stand out through authenticity, local identity, and strong emotional storytelling. Both approaches have advantages, but for Romanian products to become more competitive internationally, producers may need to combine their authentic, tradition based messaging with more structured branding and stronger digital communication strategies.

The rise of digital platforms has changed the way Romanian agri-food producers communicate. Social media, websites, online shops, and influencer collaborations offer opportunities for small producers to reach consumers without high marketing costs. During the analysis, it became clear that producers who use digital communication effectively are better positioned compared to those who rely only on traditional methods. Consumers respond positively to messages about local traditions, unique recipes, regional identity, and natural ingredients. Storytelling adds emotional value, making the product feel more special and authentic.

For example, products certified as "Produs Montan" or those coming from specific regions (like Sibiu cheese, Argeş honey, or Transylvanian cold cuts) benefit greatly from communication centred on region, tradition, and lifestyle. When these stories are clearly communicated, consumers are willing to pay higher prices, which directly improves competitiveness [12].

Despite the potential, many Romanian agri-food producers still struggle with communication. Some rely only on basic labels, rarely engage with online platforms, and do not invest in brand building. This lack of communication makes their products harder to distinguish from competitors, even when the quality is high [6].

Some producers focus exclusively on price competition, which limits long-term competitiveness.

Without strong communication, producers remain vulnerable to imported products with better branding, even if the Romanian product is fresher or more natural. The sector therefore continues to face a communication gap that reduces the overall competitiveness of Romanian agri-food products on the European market. Campaigns promoting Romanian products, participation in international fairs, and national certification schemes help strengthen the image of the country as a source of quality and authenticity. However, these initiatives need to be more consistent and better coordinated to reach their full potential.

Many European countries successfully use strong national branding ("Made in Italy", "Taste of Spain", "France Terroir and Tradition"). Romania has started similar efforts, but they need deeper communication, clearer

messaging, and better collaboration between producers and institutions [12].

To better understand how communication shapes the competitiveness of Romanian agri-food products, it is useful to analyse the sector through a strategic perspective. A SWOT analysis provides a clear overview of the internal strengths and weaknesses related to current communication practices, as well as the external opportunities and threats that influence producers on the national and European markets. By examining these four dimensions, we can identify the main factors that help Romanian products stand out, the challenges producers continue to face, and the areas where communication strategies can be improved. This SWOT analysis therefore offers a concise and structured framework that supports the broader findings of this study and highlights the strategic importance of communication for the future growth of the Romanian agri-food sector.

Figure 1. SWOT Analysis

The SWOT analysis highlights several important aspects that influence how communication contributes to the competitiveness of Romanian agri-food products. One of the main strengths of the sector is the strong sense of authenticity and tradition that producers communicate through their products. Many Romanian farmers emphasize natural ingredients, local origins, and traditional methods, which appeal to consumers who value trustworthy and artisanal food. Another strength is the growing digital presence of small producers. Platforms such as Facebook and Instagram allow them to share moments from daily farm life, show transparent production processes, and build direct trust with their audience. Emotional storytelling also plays a significant role, as many Romanian brands tell personal stories about family farms,

local heritage, and community values, which helps create a more loyal and emotionally connected consumer base. Additionally, the high quality of many Romanian honey, dairy, and farm products makes communication more credible, since producers can confidently highlight real strengths.

Despite these advantages, there are also clear weaknesses that limit competitiveness. Compared to large European brands, many Romanian producers still lack professional branding, consistent visual identity, modern packaging, or a well-developed online presence. Their marketing budgets are often very limited, making it difficult to invest in large advertising campaigns, collaborations, or promotional events that would increase visibility. Communication skills are sometimes inconsistent as well, with irregular posting, low-quality visuals, or unclear messages that weaken the competitive image of otherwise strong products. Another weakness is the insufficient use of certifications such as PDO, PGI. Although these labels could significantly strengthen credibility, they are often poorly promoted or not clearly explained to consumers. The external environment also creates significant opportunities for Romanian agri-food producers. Demand for natural, local, and transparent food is growing rapidly across Europe, offering Romanian producers a chance to position themselves as suppliers of authentic, clean-label products. Digital platforms continue to expand, giving producers low-cost tools such as online shops, influencers, TikTok marketing, and farm-to-door delivery systems that help increase visibility even without large budgets. There is also considerable potential for international market expansion. With stronger branding and better communication of certifications, Romanian honey, dairy, and artisanal products could enter premium niches abroad. Furthermore, European and national support programs offer opportunities to improve branding, packaging, and promotional strategies through available funding.

At the same time, several threats must be considered. Romanian producers face strong competition from well-established European brands such as Arla, Langnese, or Parmalat, which benefit from powerful marketing teams, high budgets, and polished communication. Imported products with strong brand identities can overshadow Romanian goods even when the local products are higher quality. Digital saturation also poses a challenge, as social

media algorithms and the growing number of online competitors make visibility harder to maintain without consistent and strategic communication. Finally, economic pressures such as rising production costs, market fluctuations, and new EU regulations can affect small producers who are already limited in resources and may struggle to adapt quickly. Together, these elements show that communication is both a key advantage and a major challenge for Romanian agri-food producers. To remain competitive, the sector must build on its strengths authenticity, quality, and emotional storytelling while addressing weaknesses and preparing for external threats through more professional, coherent, and strategic communication practices.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings of this research show that communication is not simply an accessory to marketing in the Romanian agri-food sector, but a core element that shapes how competitive producers can become. In a market where consumers demand transparency, authenticity, and emotional connection, the way producers communicate their values and practices often determines whether their products stand out or remain unnoticed. The study highlights that Romanian agri-food producers who invest in clear branding, strong visual identity, and consistent digital communication enjoy higher visibility, stronger consumer trust, and greater market recognition.

The examples analysed, ranging from honey producers to dairy farms demonstrate that visual communication, especially through logos, storytelling, and social media presence, plays a decisive role in building brand identity. Producers who use attractive, modern, and meaningful logos are better able to differentiate themselves online, attract new customers, and maintain long-term loyalty. Digital platforms such as Facebook and Instagram have become crucial tools, particularly for small and medium-sized farms that lack the resources to compete through large-scale advertising. Effective use of these channels allows them to connect directly with consumers, present their production processes, and explain what makes their products unique.

Despite these positive observations, the study also shows that communication remains a challenge for many Romanian producers. A large number still rely on basic packaging, minimal online presence, or traditional

communication methods that no longer meet modern consumer expectations. This limits their competitiveness, especially when facing imported products that invest heavily in marketing and branding. Strengthening communication skills and strategies is therefore essential for the sector's future development.

Overall, the research concludes that communication is a strategic driver of competitiveness in the Romanian agri-food sector. When producers combine quality products with coherent visual identity, transparent messaging, and active digital engagement, they can significantly enhance their market position. For Romania to consolidate its presence on both national and international markets, producers and institutions must continue to develop stronger communication strategies that highlight authenticity, local heritage, and responsible production. In this way, communication becomes not only a promotional tool, but a long-term investment in the value and reputation of Romanian agri-food products.

REFERENCES

1. Adamov Tabita Cornelia, Iancu T., Popescu Gabriela, Ciolac Ramona, Şmuleac Laura, Feher Andrea, 2018, Characterization of entrepreneurial activity in Romania and possibilities for their development at national level, Proceedings of the International Conference on Life Sciences, Vol. 1.
2. Aldea Maria, 2021, Digital technologies and innovation in smart farming systems, Journal of Agricultural Innovation, Vol. 4.
3. Adamov, Tabita, Ramona Ciolac, Tiberiu Iancu, Ioan Brad, Elena Peţ, Gabriela Popescu, and Laura Şmuleac. 2020. 'Sustainability of Agritourism Activity. Initiatives and Challenges in Romanian Mountain Rural Regions', Sustainability, 12:2502.
4. Bacter, Ramona Vasilica, Alina Emilia Maria Gherdan, Monica Angelica Dodu, Ramona Ciolac, Tiberiu Iancu, Luminiţa Pîrvulescu, Anca Monica Brata, Alexandra Ungureanu, Roxana Mihaela Bolohan, and Ioana Camelia Chebeleu. 2024. 'The Influence of Legislative and Economic Conditions on Romanian Agritourism: Swot Study of Northwestern and Northeastern Regions and Sustainable Development Strategies', Sustainability, 16: 7382.
5. Gavrilăscu, C., Mateoc-Sirb, N., Mateoc, T. 2017. Romanian agrifood trade with the Mediterranean countries – from the Barcelona declaration to the

- euro-mediterranean partnership. Papers Series Agrarian Economy and Rural Development – Realities and Perspectives for Romania. 45-52.
6. Gavrilesco, C. 2018 Romanian agri-food trade performance and competitiveness in its first decade of EU membership. *Agricultural Management Papers* 20(2), 46-55.
 7. Gavrilesco, C. 2019. An analysis of the trade balance for the main agri-food products. *Papers Series Agrarian Economy and Rural Development – Realities and Perspectives for Romania*.
 8. Gordan Marius Ionuț, Tabita Cornelia Adamov, Anda Ioana Milin, Elena Peț, Anka Roxana Pascariu, Tiberiu Iancu, Perspectives on consumer preferences in agritourism, *Lucrări Științifice Management Agricol*, Vol. 25, No.1
 9. Iosim Iasmina, Carmen Dumitrescu, Diana Marin, Cristina Babcsanyi, Gabriela Popescu, Andreea Dragoescu Urlică, 2023, Traditional vs. Digital pr in romanian agritourism: the case of mansions, *Lucrări Științifice Management Agricol*, Vol. 25, No.1
 10. Lloyd J., Toogood Laura, 2015, *Journalism and PR: News Media and Public Relations in the Digital Age*, London-New York, NY: I. B. Tauris & Oxford: University of Oxford
 11. Macnamara J., 2008, Public relations in an interactive age: the need for new practices, not just new media, *Asia Pacific Public Relations Journal*, 10, pp. 1-16
 12. Phillips D., Young P., 2009, *Online Public Relations: A Practical Guide to Developing an Online Strategy in the World of social media*, London: Kogan Page-CIPR
 13. Tworzydło D., 2013, *New Technologies in Public Relations, Marketing of Scientific and Research Organizations*, 4(10), pp. 1-12
 14. Apivest. (n.d.). Instagram page. Retrieved February 2025, from <https://www.instagram.com/apivest>
 15. Făbricața de Lactate. (n.d.). Instagram page. Retrieved February 2025, from <https://www.instagram.com/fabricutadelactate>
 16. Ferma cu Omenie. (n.d.). Instagram page. Retrieved February 2025, from <https://www.instagram.com/fermacuomenie>
 17. Ferma Măgărițelor. (n.d.). Instagram page. Retrieved February 2025, from <https://www.instagram.com/fermamagaritelor>
 18. Ferma Wagner. (n.d.). Instagram page. Retrieved February 2025, from <https://www.instagram.com/fermawagner>
 19. Honeys Den. (n.d.). Instagram page. Retrieved February 2025, from <https://www.instagram.com/honeysden>
 20. Miere pe Bune. (n.d.). Instagram page. Retrieved February 2025, from <https://www.instagram.com/mierepebune>
 21. Miere și Delicii. (n.d.). Instagram page. Retrieved February 2025, from https://www.instagram.com/mieresi_delicii
 22. Runky Bees. (n.d.). Instagram page. Retrieved February 2025, from <https://www.instagram.com/runkybees>